

Square-Root Type Selfie Numbers

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Abstract

Numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations are considered as *selfie numbers*. Some times they are called as *wild narcissistic numbers*. There are many ways of representing *selfie numbers*. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basic operations along with *factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, s-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers, quadratic numbers, cubic numbers*, etc. This paper brings selfie numbers with *square-root* up to seven digits.

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1 Introduction

Let's analyse historical aspects of some numbers:

- (i) Consider the following classical number famous as **printer's error** (Dudeney, 1917, pp. 379 [5]):

$$2592 := 2^5 \times 9^2 \tag{1}$$

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Actually it is not a **printer's error**, it represents number in its own digits. The first number similar property is $25 = 5^2$, but is in **reverse order**.

(ii) Let consider another examples (Madachy, 1966, pp.167-175 [11]):

$$\begin{aligned} 34425 &:= 3^4 \times 425 \\ 312325 &:= 31^2 \times 325 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Above two are represented their own digits. Moreover, if we multiply by both sides by 10, they continued with property of same digits both sides. These kinds of numbers are famous as **number patterns**. Still there is another number with different property, i.e.,

$$27594 := 73 \times 9 \times 42 = 7 \times 3942 \quad (3)$$

In this case, the two expressions on right side of (4) are with same digits, but the total value is with different digits. This type of study is not under work.

(iii) Madachy, 1966, pp.167-275 [11] also gave an interesting property with factorials know by **sum of factorials**:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &:= 1! \\ 2 &:= 2! \\ 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! \\ 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Above numbers also have the property of same digits on both sides, but with factorial and addition.

In all the three situations, we observe that we are dealing with numbers those have same digits on both sides, where one side is number another with same digits with certain operations. Based on above idea of numbers, the author studies numbers calling **selfie numbers**, i.e., numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. Some studies in this direction can seen in the works of Friedman [6, 7] and Rose [2, 3, 4].

Below are some examples of **selfie numbers** extending the idea of equation (2) using the operations of addition and subtraction with **factorial**:

$$\begin{aligned} 145 &= 1! + 4! + 5! & 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! \\ 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! \\ 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! \\363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \\317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! \\352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! \\357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! \\357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9!\end{aligned}$$

There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **binomial coefficients**, **s-gonal values**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. Below is item-wise details of author's work on **selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order**, and in **reverse order of digits**:

1. Selfie numbers with **Basic Operations**; [14, 15, 16, 34];
2. Selfie numbers with **Factorial**: [30, 31];
3. Selfie numbers with **Square-root**: [14, 15] - and this work;
4. Selfie numbers with **Factorial and Square-root**: [14, 15, 16];
5. Selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**: [26, ?, 28];
6. Selfie numbers with **Triangular numbers**: [21, ?, ?];
7. Selfie numbers with **Binomial coefficients**: [24, ?];
8. Selfie numbers with **S-gonal numbers**: [17];
9. Selfie numbers with **Centered Polygonal**: [17];
10. Selfie numbers with **Concatenation-Type**: [32];
11. Selfie numbers with **Quadratic numbers**: [29];
12. Selfie numbers with **Cubic numbers**: [33];

2 Digit's Order Selfie Numbers

This section bring **selfie numbers** in digit's order by use of basic operations along with square-root. This we have done up to seven digits.

2.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

This subsection brings symmetric representations of **selfie numbers**. These are blocks of either 10 or 100.

$$46660 := 4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 0$$

$$46661 := 4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 1$$

$$46662 := 4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 2$$

$$46663 := 4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 3$$

$$46664 := 4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 4$$

$$46665 := 4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 5$$

$$46666 := 4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 6$$

$$46667 := 4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 7$$

$$46668 := 4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 8$$

$$46669 := 4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 9$$

$$117660 := 11 + 7\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 0$$

$$117661 := 11 + 7\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 1$$

$$117662 := 11 + 7\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 2$$

$$117663 := 11 + 7\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 3$$

$$117664 := 11 + 7\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 4$$

$$117665 := 11 + 7\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 5$$

$$117666 := 11 + 7\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 6$$

$$117667 := 11 + 7\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 7$$

$$117668 := 11 + 7\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 8$$

$$117669 := 11 + 7\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 9$$

$$194490 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 + 9 + 0$$

$$194491 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 + 9 + 1$$

$$194492 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 + 9 + 2$$

$$194493 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 + 9 + 3$$

$$194494 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 + 9 + 4$$

$$194495 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 + 9 + 5$$

$$194496 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 + 9 + 6$$

$$194497 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 + 9 + 7$$

$$194498 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 + 9 + 8$$

$$194499 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 + 9 + 9$$

$$438980 := 4 + 38^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 + 0$$

$$438981 := 4 + 38^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 + 1$$

$$438982 := 4 + 38^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 + 2$$

$$438983 := 4 + 38^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 + 3$$

$$438984 := 4 + 38^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 + 4$$

$$438985 := 4 + 38^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 + 5$$

$$438986 := 4 + 38^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 + 6$$

$$438987 := 4 + 38^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 + 7$$

$$438988 := 4 + 38^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 + 8$$

$$438989 := 4 + 38^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 + 9$$

$$466540 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6^6) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 0$$

$$466541 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6^6) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 1$$

$$466542 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6^6) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 2$$

$$466543 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6^6) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3$$

$$466544 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6^6) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 4$$

$$466545 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6^6) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 5$$

$$466546 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6^6) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 6$$

$$466547 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6^6) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 7$$

$$466548 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6^6) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 8$$

$$466549 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6^6) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 9$$

$$466550 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 - 5) + 0$$

$$466551 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 - 5) + 1$$

$$466552 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 - 5) + 2$$

$$466553 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 - 5) + 3$$

$$466554 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 - 5) + 4$$

$$466555 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 - 5) + 5$$

$$466556 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 - 5) + 6$$

$$466557 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 - 5) + 7$$

$$466558 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 - 5) + 8$$

$$466559 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 - 5) + 9$$

$$995340 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 4 + 0$$

$$995341 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 4 + 1$$

$$995342 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 4 + 2$$

$$995343 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 4 + 3$$

$$995344 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 4 + 4$$

$$995345 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 4 + 5$$

$$995346 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 4 + 6$$

$$995347 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 4 + 7$$

$$995348 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 4 + 8$$

$$995349 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 4 + 9$$

$$1048560 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 6 + 0$$

$$1048561 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 6 + 1$$

$$1048562 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 6 + 2$$

$$1048563 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 6 + 3$$

$$1048564 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 6 + 4$$

$$1048565 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 6 + 5$$

$$1048566 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 6 + 6$$

$$1048567 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 6 + 7$$

$$1048568 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 6 + 8$$

$$1048569 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 6 + 9$$

$$1048570 := 1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - 7 + 0$$

$$1048571 := 1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - 7 + 1$$

$$1048572 := 1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - 7 + 2$$

$$1048573 := 1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - 7 + 3$$

$$1048574 := 1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - 7 + 4$$

$$1048575 := 1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - 7 + 5$$

$$1048576 := 1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - 7 + 6$$

$$1048577 := 1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - 7 + 7$$

$$1048578 := 1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - 7 + 8$$

$$1048579 := 1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - 7 + 9$$

$$1119740 := \left(-1 + \left((1+1) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^7 \right) \times 4 + 0$$

$$1119741 := \left(-1 + \left((1+1) \times \sqrt{9}\right)^7\right) \times 4 + 1$$

$$1119742 := \left(-1 + \left((1+1) \times \sqrt{9}\right)^7\right) \times 4 + 2$$

$$1119743 := \left(-1 + \left((1+1) \times \sqrt{9}\right)^7\right) \times 4 + 3$$

$$1119744 := \left(-1 + \left((1+1) \times \sqrt{9}\right)^7\right) \times 4 + 4$$

$$1119745 := \left(-1 + \left((1+1) \times \sqrt{9}\right)^7\right) \times 4 + 5$$

$$1119746 := \left(-1 + \left((1+1) \times \sqrt{9}\right)^7\right) \times 4 + 6$$

$$1119747 := \left(-1 + \left((1+1) \times \sqrt{9}\right)^7\right) \times 4 + 7$$

$$1119748 := \left(-1 + \left((1+1) \times \sqrt{9}\right)^7\right) \times 4 + 8$$

$$1119749 := \left(-1 + \left((1+1) \times \sqrt{9}\right)^7\right) \times 4 + 9$$

$$1176480 := (-1 + 1 \times 7^6) \times (\sqrt{4} + 8) + 0$$

$$1176481 := (-1 + 1 \times 7^6) \times (\sqrt{4} + 8) + 1$$

$$1176482 := (-1 + 1 \times 7^6) \times (\sqrt{4} + 8) + 2$$

$$1176483 := (-1 + 1 \times 7^6) \times (\sqrt{4} + 8) + 3$$

$$1176484 := (-1 + 1 \times 7^6) \times (\sqrt{4} + 8) + 4$$

$$1176485 := (-1 + 1 \times 7^6) \times (\sqrt{4} + 8) + 5$$

$$1176486 := (-1 + 1 \times 7^6) \times (\sqrt{4} + 8) + 6$$

$$1176487 := (-1 + 1 \times 7^6) \times (\sqrt{4} + 8) + 7$$

$$1176488 := (-1 + 1 \times 7^6) \times (\sqrt{4} + 8) + 8$$

$$1176489 := (-1 + 1 \times 7^6) \times (\sqrt{4} + 8) + 9$$

$$1180980 := 1 \times 180 \times \sqrt{9^8} + 0$$

$$1180981 := 1 \times 180 \times \sqrt{9^8} + 1$$

$$1180982 := 1 \times 180 \times \sqrt{9^8} + 2$$

$$1180983 := 1 \times 180 \times \sqrt{9^8} + 3$$

$$1180984 := 1 \times 180 \times \sqrt{9^8} + 4$$

$$1180985 := 1 \times 180 \times \sqrt{9^8} + 5$$

$$1180986 := 1 \times 180 \times \sqrt{9^8} + 6$$

$$1180987 := 1 \times 180 \times \sqrt{9^8} + 7$$

$$1180988 := 1 \times 180 \times \sqrt{9^8} + 8$$

$$1180989 := 1 \times 180 \times \sqrt{9^8} + 9$$

$$1675860 := (-1 + 6^7 - \sqrt{5^8}) \times 6 + 0$$

$$1675861 := (-1 + 6^7 - \sqrt{5^8}) \times 6 + 1$$

$$1675862 := (-1 + 6^7 - \sqrt{5^8}) \times 6 + 2$$

$$1675863 := (-1 + 6^7 - \sqrt{5^8}) \times 6 + 3$$

$$1675864 := (-1 + 6^7 - \sqrt{5^8}) \times 6 + 4$$

$$1675865 := (-1 + 6^7 - \sqrt{5^8}) \times 6 + 5$$

$$1675866 := (-1 + 6^7 - \sqrt{5^8}) \times 6 + 6$$

$$1675867 := (-1 + 6^7 - \sqrt{5^8}) \times 6 + 7$$

$$1675868 := (-1 + 6^7 - \sqrt{5^8}) \times 6 + 8$$

$$1675869 := (-1 + 6^7 - \sqrt{5^8}) \times 6 + 9$$

$$1682190 := (1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 - 19 + 0$$

$$1682191 := (1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 - 19 + 1$$

$$1682192 := (1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 - 19 + 2$$

$$1682193 := (1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 - 19 + 3$$

$$1682194 := (1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 - 19 + 4$$

$$1682195 := (1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 - 19 + 5$$

$$1682196 := (1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 - 19 + 6$$

$$1682197 := (1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 - 19 + 7$$

$$1682198 := (1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 - 19 + 8$$

$$1682199 := (1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 - 19 + 9$$

$$1688680 := (-1 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times (8 + \sqrt{6^8}) + 0$$

$$1688681 := (-1 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times (8 + \sqrt{6^8}) + 1$$

$$1688682 := (-1 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times (8 + \sqrt{6^8}) + 2$$

$$1688683 := (-1 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times (8 + \sqrt{6^8}) + 3$$

$$1688684 := (-1 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times (8 + \sqrt{6^8}) + 4$$

$$1688685 := (-1 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times (8 + \sqrt{6^8}) + 5$$

$$1688686 := (-1 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times (8 + \sqrt{6^8}) + 6$$

$$1688687 := (-1 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times (8 + \sqrt{6^8}) + 7$$

$$1688688 := (-1 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times (8 + \sqrt{6^8}) + 8$$

$$1688689 := (-1 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times (8 + \sqrt{6^8}) + 9$$

$$1749600 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 00$$

$$1749601 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 01$$

$$1749602 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 02$$

$$1749603 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 03$$

$$1749604 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 04$$

$$1749605 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 05$$

$$1749606 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 06$$

$$1749607 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 07$$

$$1749608 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 08$$

$$1749609 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 09$$

$$1749610 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 10$$

$$1749611 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 11$$

$$1749612 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 12$$

$$1749613 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 13$$

$$1749614 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 14$$

$$1749615 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 15$$

$$1749616 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 16$$

$$1749617 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 17$$

$$1749618 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 18$$

$$1749619 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 19$$

$$1749620 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 20$$

$$1749621 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 21$$

$$1749622 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 22$$

$$1749623 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 23$$

$$1749624 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 24$$

$$1749625 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 25$$

$$1749626 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 26$$

$$1749627 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 27$$

$$1749628 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 28$$

$$1749629 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 29$$

$$1749630 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 30$$

$$1749631 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 31$$

$$1749632 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 32$$

$$1749633 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 33$$

$$1749634 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 34$$

$$1749635 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 35$$

$$1749636 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 36$$

$$1749637 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 37$$

$$1749638 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 38$$

$$1749639 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 39$$

$$1749640 := (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 40$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1749641 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 41 \\ 1749642 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 42 \\ 1749643 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 43 \\ 1749644 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 44 \\ 1749645 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 45 \\ 1749646 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 46 \\ 1749647 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 47 \\ 1749648 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 48 \\ 1749649 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 49 \\ 1749650 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 50 \\ 1749651 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 51 \\ 1749652 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 52 \\ 1749653 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 53 \\ 1749654 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 54 \\ 1749655 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 55 \\ 1749656 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 56 \\ 1749657 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 57 \\ 1749658 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 58 \\ 1749659 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 59 \\ 1749660 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 60 \\ 1749661 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 61 \\ 1749662 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 62 \\ 1749663 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 63 \\ 1749664 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 64 \\ 1749665 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 65 \\ 1749666 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 66 \\ 1749667 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 67 \\ 1749668 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 68 \\ 1749669 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 69 \\ 1749670 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 70 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1749671 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 71 \\ 1749672 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 72 \\ 1749673 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 73 \\ 1749674 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 74 \\ 1749675 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 75 \\ 1749676 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 76 \\ 1749677 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 77 \\ 1749678 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 78 \\ 1749679 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 79 \\ 1749680 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 80 \\ 1749681 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 81 \\ 1749682 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 82 \\ 1749683 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 83 \\ 1749684 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 84 \\ 1749685 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 85 \\ 1749686 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 86 \\ 1749687 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 87 \\ 1749688 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 88 \\ 1749689 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 89 \\ 1749690 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 90 \\ 1749691 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 91 \\ 1749692 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 92 \\ 1749693 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 93 \\ 1749694 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 94 \\ 1749695 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 95 \\ 1749696 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 96 \\ 1749697 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 97 \\ 1749698 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 98 \\ 1749699 &:= (-1 + 7^4) \times \sqrt{9^6} + 99 \end{aligned}$$

$$1834990 := (1 - 8) \times (3 - 4^9) + \sqrt{9} + 0$$

$$1834991 := (1 - 8) \times (3 - 4^9) + \sqrt{9} + 1$$

$$1834992 := (1 - 8) \times (3 - 4^9) + \sqrt{9} + 2$$

$$1834993 := (1 - 8) \times (3 - 4^9) + \sqrt{9} + 3$$

$$1834994 := (1 - 8) \times (3 - 4^9) + \sqrt{9} + 4$$

$$1834995 := (1 - 8) \times (3 - 4^9) + \sqrt{9} + 5$$

$$1834996 := (1 - 8) \times (3 - 4^9) + \sqrt{9} + 6$$

$$1834997 := (1 - 8) \times (3 - 4^9) + \sqrt{9} + 7$$

$$1834998 := (1 - 8) \times (3 - 4^9) + \sqrt{9} + 8$$

$$1834999 := (1 - 8) \times (3 - 4^9) + \sqrt{9} + 9$$

$$1889570 := 18^{8-\sqrt{9}} - 5 + 7 + 0$$

$$1889571 := 18^{8-\sqrt{9}} - 5 + 7 + 1$$

$$1889572 := 18^{8-\sqrt{9}} - 5 + 7 + 2$$

$$1889573 := 18^{8-\sqrt{9}} - 5 + 7 + 3$$

$$1889574 := 18^{8-\sqrt{9}} - 5 + 7 + 4$$

$$1889575 := 18^{8-\sqrt{9}} - 5 + 7 + 5$$

$$1889576 := 18^{8-\sqrt{9}} - 5 + 7 + 6$$

$$1889577 := 18^{8-\sqrt{9}} - 5 + 7 + 7$$

$$1889578 := 18^{8-\sqrt{9}} - 5 + 7 + 8$$

$$1889579 := 18^{8-\sqrt{9}} - 5 + 7 + 9$$

$$1966080 := (1 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times 60 \times 8 + 0$$

$$1966081 := (1 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times 60 \times 8 + 1$$

$$1966082 := (1 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times 60 \times 8 + 2$$

$$1966083 := (1 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times 60 \times 8 + 3$$

$$1966084 := (1 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times 60 \times 8 + 4$$

$$1966085 := (1 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times 60 \times 8 + 5$$

$$1966086 := (1 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times 60 \times 8 + 6$$

$$1966087 := (1 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times 60 \times 8 + 7$$

$$1966088 := (1 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times 60 \times 8 + 8$$

$$1966089 := (1 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times 60 \times 8 + 9$$

$$2343750 := 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \times 5 + 0$$

$$2343751 := 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \times 5 + 1$$

$$2343752 := 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \times 5 + 2$$

$$2343753 := 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \times 5 + 3$$

$$2343754 := 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \times 5 + 4$$

$$2343755 := 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \times 5 + 5$$

$$2343756 := 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \times 5 + 6$$

$$2343757 := 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \times 5 + 7$$

$$2343758 := 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \times 5 + 8$$

$$2343759 := 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \times 5 + 9$$

$$2863290 := 2 + ((8 + 63) \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} + 0$$

$$2863291 := 2 + ((8 + 63) \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} + 1$$

$$2863292 := 2 + ((8 + 63) \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} + 2$$

$$2863293 := 2 + ((8 + 63) \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} + 3$$

$$2863294 := 2 + ((8 + 63) \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} + 4$$

$$2863295 := 2 + ((8 + 63) \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} + 5$$

$$2863296 := 2 + ((8 + 63) \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} + 6$$

$$2863297 := 2 + ((8 + 63) \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} + 7$$

$$2863298 := 2 + ((8 + 63) \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} + 8$$

$$2863299 := 2 + ((8 + 63) \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} + 9$$

$$2965950 := 2 \times (\sqrt{9} \times 65)^{\sqrt{9}} / 5 + 0$$

$$2965951 := 2 \times (\sqrt{9} \times 65)^{\sqrt{9}} / 5 + 1$$

$$2965952 := 2 \times (\sqrt{9} \times 65)^{\sqrt{9}} / 5 + 2$$

$$2965953 := 2 \times (\sqrt{9} \times 65)^{\sqrt{9}} / 5 + 3$$

$$2965954 := 2 \times (\sqrt{9} \times 65)^{\sqrt{9}} / 5 + 4$$

$$2965955 := 2 \times (\sqrt{9} \times 65)^{\sqrt{9}} / 5 + 5$$

$$2965956 := 2 \times (\sqrt{9} \times 65)^{\sqrt{9}} / 5 + 6$$

$$2965957 := 2 \times (\sqrt{9} \times 65)^{\sqrt{9}} / 5 + 7$$

$$2965958 := 2 \times (\sqrt{9} \times 65)^{\sqrt{9}} / 5 + 8$$

$$2965959 := 2 \times (\sqrt{9} \times 65)^{\sqrt{9}} / 5 + 9$$

$$3604480 := (-3 + 60 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 0$$

$$3604481 := (-3 + 60 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 1$$

$$3604482 := (-3 + 60 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 2$$

$$3604483 := (-3 + 60 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 3$$

$$3604484 := (-3 + 60 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 4$$

$$3604485 := (-3 + 60 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 5$$

$$3604486 := (-3 + 60 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 6$$

$$3604487 := (-3 + 60 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 7$$

$$3604488 := (-3 + 60 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 8$$

$$3604489 := (-3 + 60 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 9$$

$$3893450 := ((3 + 89)^3 + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 0$$

$$3893451 := ((3 + 89)^3 + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 1$$

$$3893452 := ((3 + 89)^3 + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 2$$

$$3893453 := ((3 + 89)^3 + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 3$$

$$3893454 := ((3 + 89)^3 + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 4$$

$$3893455 := ((3 + 89)^3 + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 5$$

$$3893456 := ((3 + 89)^3 + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 6$$

$$3893457 := ((3 + 89)^3 + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 7$$

$$3893458 := ((3 + 89)^3 + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 8$$

$$3893459 := ((3 + 89)^3 + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 9$$

$$4194560 := \sqrt{4^{-1+9}} + 4^{5+6} + 0$$

$$4194561 := \sqrt{4^{-1+9}} + 4^{5+6} + 1$$

$$4194562 := \sqrt{4^{-1+9}} + 4^{5+6} + 2$$

$$4194563 := \sqrt{4^{-1+9}} + 4^{5+6} + 3$$

$$4194564 := \sqrt{4^{-1+9}} + 4^{5+6} + 4$$

$$4194565 := \sqrt{4^{-1+9}} + 4^{5+6} + 5$$

$$4194566 := \sqrt{4^{-1+9}} + 4^{5+6} + 6$$

$$4194567 := \sqrt{4^{-1+9}} + 4^{5+6} + 7$$

$$4194568 := \sqrt{4^{-1+9}} + 4^{5+6} + 8$$

$$4194569 := \sqrt{4^{-1+9}} + 4^{5+6} + 9$$

$$4410940 := (4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}} - 4 + 0$$

$$4410941 := (4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}} - 4 + 1$$

$$4410942 := (4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}} - 4 + 2$$

$$4410943 := (4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}} - 4 + 3$$

$$4410944 := (4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}} - 4 + 4$$

$$4410945 := (4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}} - 4 + 5$$

$$4410946 := (4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}} - 4 + 6$$

$$4410947 := (4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}} - 4 + 7$$

$$4410948 := (4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}} - 4 + 8$$

$$4410949 := (4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}} - 4 + 9$$

$$5242890 := 5 \times \left(2 + 4 \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^9} \right) + 0$$

$$5242891 := 5 \times \left(2 + 4 \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^9} \right) + 1$$

$$5242892 := 5 \times \left(2 + 4 \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^9} \right) + 2$$

$$5242893 := 5 \times \left(2 + 4 \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^9} \right) + 3$$

$$5242894 := 5 \times \left(2 + 4 \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^9} \right) + 4$$

$$5242895 := 5 \times \left(2 + 4 \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^9} \right) + 5$$

$$5242896 := 5 \times \left(2 + 4 \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^9} \right) + 6$$

$$5242897 := 5 \times \left(2 + 4 \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^9} \right) + 7$$

$$5242898 := 5 \times \left(2 + 4 \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^9} \right) + 8$$

$$5242899 := 5 \times \left(2 + 4 \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^9} \right) + 9$$

$$5359380 := (5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 + 8 + 0$$

$$5359381 := (5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 + 8 + 1$$

$$5359382 := (5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 + 8 + 2$$

$$5359383 := (5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 + 8 + 3$$

$$5359384 := (5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 + 8 + 4$$

$$5359385 := (5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 + 8 + 5$$

$$5359386 := (5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 + 8 + 6$$

$$5359387 := (5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 + 8 + 7$$

$$5359388 := (5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 + 8 + 8$$

$$5359389 := (5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 + 8 + 9$$

$$5555790 := (5 \times 5 + 5) \times 57^{\sqrt{9}} + 0$$

$$5555791 := (5 \times 5 + 5) \times 57^{\sqrt{9}} + 1$$

$$5555792 := (5 \times 5 + 5) \times 57^{\sqrt{9}} + 2$$

$$5555793 := (5 \times 5 + 5) \times 57^{\sqrt{9}} + 3$$

$$5555794 := (5 \times 5 + 5) \times 57^{\sqrt{9}} + 4$$

$$5555795 := (5 \times 5 + 5) \times 57^{\sqrt{9}} + 5$$

$$5555796 := (5 \times 5 + 5) \times 57^{\sqrt{9}} + 6$$

$$5555797 := (5 \times 5 + 5) \times 57^{\sqrt{9}} + 7$$

$$5555798 := (5 \times 5 + 5) \times 57^{\sqrt{9}} + 8$$

$$5555799 := (5 \times 5 + 5) \times 57^{\sqrt{9}} + 9$$

$$5764780 := -57 + \sqrt{6^4} + 7^8 + 0$$

$$5764781 := -57 + \sqrt{6^4} + 7^8 + 1$$

$$5764782 := -57 + \sqrt{6^4} + 7^8 + 2$$

$$5764783 := -57 + \sqrt{6^4} + 7^8 + 3$$

$$5764784 := -57 + \sqrt{6^4} + 7^8 + 4$$

$$5764785 := -57 + \sqrt{6^4} + 7^8 + 5$$

$$5764786 := -57 + \sqrt{6^4} + 7^8 + 6$$

$$5764787 := -57 + \sqrt{6^4} + 7^8 + 7$$

$$5764788 := -57 + \sqrt{6^4} + 7^8 + 8$$

$$5764789 := -57 + \sqrt{6^4} + 7^8 + 9$$

$$5764830 := 5 + 7^{\sqrt{64}} + 8 \times 3 + 0$$

$$5764831 := 5 + 7^{\sqrt{64}} + 8 \times 3 + 1$$

$$5764832 := 5 + 7^{\sqrt{64}} + 8 \times 3 + 2$$

$$5764833 := 5 + 7^{\sqrt{64}} + 8 \times 3 + 3$$

$$5764834 := 5 + 7^{\sqrt{64}} + 8 \times 3 + 4$$

$$5764835 := 5 + 7^{\sqrt{64}} + 8 \times 3 + 5$$

$$5764836 := 5 + 7^{\sqrt{64}} + 8 \times 3 + 6$$

$$5764837 := 5 + 7^{\sqrt{64}} + 8 \times 3 + 7$$

$$5764838 := 5 + 7^{\sqrt{64}} + 8 \times 3 + 8$$

$$5764839 := 5 + 7^{\sqrt{64}} + 8 \times 3 + 9$$

$$5774410 := (-5 + 7 + 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} + 1 + 0$$

$$5774411 := (-5 + 7 + 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} + 1 + 1$$

$$5774412 := (-5 + 7 + 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} + 1 + 2$$

$$5774413 := (-5 + 7 + 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} + 1 + 3$$

$$5774414 := (-5 + 7 + 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} + 1 + 4$$

$$5774415 := (-5 + 7 + 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} + 1 + 5$$

$$5774416 := (-5 + 7 + 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} + 1 + 6$$

$$5774417 := (-5 + 7 + 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} + 1 + 7$$

$$5774418 := (-5 + 7 + 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} + 1 + 8$$

$$5774419 := (-5 + 7 + 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} + 1 + 9$$

$$5784020 := -5 + (\sqrt{78} + 4)^{02} + 0$$

$$5784021 := -5 + (\sqrt{78} + 4)^{02} + 1$$

$$5784022 := -5 + (\sqrt{78} + 4)^{02} + 2$$

$$5784023 := -5 + (\sqrt{78} + 4)^{02} + 3$$

$$5784024 := -5 + (\sqrt{78} + 4)^{02} + 4$$

$$5784025 := -5 + (\sqrt{78} + 4)^{02} + 5$$

$$5784026 := -5 + (\sqrt{78} + 4)^{02} + 6$$

$$5784027 := -5 + (\sqrt{78} + 4)^{02} + 7$$

$$5784028 := -5 + (\sqrt{78} + 4)^{02} + 8$$

$$5784029 := -5 + (\sqrt{78} + 4)^{02} + 9$$

$$5788840 := (5 + \sqrt{78})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} + 4 + 0$$

$$5788841 := (5 + \sqrt{78})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} + 4 + 1$$

$$5788842 := (5 + \sqrt{78})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} + 4 + 2$$

$$5788843 := (5 + \sqrt{78})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} + 4 + 3$$

$$5788844 := (5 + \sqrt{78})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} + 4 + 4$$

$$5788845 := (5 + \sqrt{78})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} + 4 + 5$$

$$5788846 := (5 + \sqrt{78})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} + 4 + 6$$

$$5788847 := (5 + \sqrt{78})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} + 4 + 7$$

$$5788848 := (5 + \sqrt{78})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} + 4 + 8$$

$$5788849 := (5 + \sqrt{78})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} + 4 + 9$$

$$5859150 := (5^8 - 5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 15 + 0$$

$$5859151 := (5^8 - 5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 15 + 1$$

$$5859152 := (5^8 - 5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 15 + 2$$

$$5859153 := (5^8 - 5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 15 + 3$$

$$5859154 := (5^8 - 5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 15 + 4$$

$$5859155 := (5^8 - 5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 15 + 5$$

$$5859156 := (5^8 - 5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 15 + 6$$

$$5859157 := (5^8 - 5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 15 + 7$$

$$5859158 := (5^8 - 5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 15 + 8$$

$$5859159 := (5^8 - 5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 15 + 9$$

$$5859300 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 00$$

$$5859301 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 01$$

$$5859302 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 02$$

$$5859303 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 03$$

$$5859304 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 04$$

$$5859305 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 05$$

$$5859306 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 06$$

$$5859307 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 07$$

$$5859308 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 08$$

$$5859309 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 09$$

$$5859310 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 10$$

$$5859311 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 11$$

$$5859312 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 12$$

$$5859313 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 13$$

$$5859314 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 14$$

$$5859315 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 15$$

$$5859316 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 16$$

$$5859317 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 17$$

$$5859318 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 18$$

$$5859319 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 19$$

$$5859320 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 20$$

$$5859321 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 21$$

$$5859322 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 22$$

$$5859323 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 23$$

$$5859324 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 24$$

$$5859325 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 25$$

$$5859326 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 26$$

$$5859327 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 27$$

$$5859328 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 28$$

$$5859329 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 29$$

$$5859330 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 30$$

$$5859331 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 31$$

$$5859332 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 32$$

$$5859333 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 33$$

$$5859334 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 34$$

$$5859335 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 35$$

$$5859336 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 36$$

$$5859337 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 37$$

$$5859338 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 38$$

$$5859339 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 39$$

$$5859340 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 40$$

$$5859341 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 41$$

$$5859342 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 42$$

$$5859343 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 43$$

$$5859344 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 44$$

$$5859345 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 45$$

$$5859346 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 46$$

$$5859347 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 47$$

$$5859348 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 48$$

$$5859349 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 49$$

$$5859350 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 50$$

$$5859351 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 51$$

$$5859352 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 52$$

$$5859353 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 53$$

$$5859354 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 54$$

$$5859355 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 55$$

$$5859356 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 56$$

$$5859357 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 57$$

$$5859358 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 58$$

$$5859359 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 59$$

$$5859360 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 60$$

$$5859361 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 61$$

$$5859362 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 62$$

$$5859363 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 63$$

$$5859364 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 64$$

$$5859365 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 65$$

$$5859366 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 66$$

$$5859367 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 67$$

$$5859368 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 68$$

$$5859369 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 69$$

$$5859370 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 70$$

$$5859371 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 71$$

$$5859372 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 72$$

$$5859373 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 73$$

$$5859374 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 74$$

$$5859375 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 75$$

$$5859376 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 76$$

$$5859377 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 77$$

$$5859378 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 78$$

$$5859379 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 79$$

$$5859380 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 80$$

$$5859381 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 81$$

$$5859382 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 82$$

$$5859383 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 83$$

$$5859384 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 84$$

$$5859385 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 85$$

$$5859386 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 86$$

$$5859387 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 87$$

$$5859388 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 88$$

$$5859389 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 89$$

$$5859390 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 90$$

$$5859391 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 91$$

$$5859392 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 92$$

$$5859393 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 93$$

$$5859394 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 94$$

$$5859395 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 95$$

$$5859396 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 96$$

$$5859397 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 97$$

$$5859398 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 98$$

$$5859399 := \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5^9}\right) \times 3 + 99$$

$$5859450 := (5^8 + 5) / \sqrt{9} \times 45 + 0$$

$$5859451 := (5^8 + 5) / \sqrt{9} \times 45 + 1$$

$$5859452 := (5^8 + 5) / \sqrt{9} \times 45 + 2$$

$$5859453 := (5^8 + 5) / \sqrt{9} \times 45 + 3$$

$$5859454 := (5^8 + 5) / \sqrt{9} \times 45 + 4$$

$$5859455 := (5^8 + 5) / \sqrt{9} \times 45 + 5$$

$$5859456 := (5^8 + 5) / \sqrt{9} \times 45 + 6$$

$$5859457 := (5^8 + 5) / \sqrt{9} \times 45 + 7$$

$$5859458 := (5^8 + 5) / \sqrt{9} \times 45 + 8$$

$$5859459 := (5^8 + 5) / \sqrt{9} \times 45 + 9$$

$$6298560 := \left(6^{2\sqrt{9}} / 8\right) \times 5 \times 6 + 0$$

$$6298561 := \left(6^{2^{\sqrt{9}}}/8\right) \times 5 \times 6 + 1$$

$$6298562 := \left(6^{2^{\sqrt{9}}}/8\right) \times 5 \times 6 + 2$$

$$6298563 := \left(6^{2^{\sqrt{9}}}/8\right) \times 5 \times 6 + 3$$

$$6298564 := \left(6^{2^{\sqrt{9}}}/8\right) \times 5 \times 6 + 4$$

$$6298565 := \left(6^{2^{\sqrt{9}}}/8\right) \times 5 \times 6 + 5$$

$$6298566 := \left(6^{2^{\sqrt{9}}}/8\right) \times 5 \times 6 + 6$$

$$6298567 := \left(6^{2^{\sqrt{9}}}/8\right) \times 5 \times 6 + 7$$

$$6298568 := \left(6^{2^{\sqrt{9}}}/8\right) \times 5 \times 6 + 8$$

$$6298569 := \left(6^{2^{\sqrt{9}}}/8\right) \times 5 \times 6 + 9$$

$$6495390 := 6 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times 5 \times 3^9 + 0$$

$$6495391 := 6 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times 5 \times 3^9 + 1$$

$$6495392 := 6 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times 5 \times 3^9 + 2$$

$$6495393 := 6 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times 5 \times 3^9 + 3$$

$$6495394 := 6 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times 5 \times 3^9 + 4$$

$$6495395 := 6 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times 5 \times 3^9 + 5$$

$$6495396 := 6 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times 5 \times 3^9 + 6$$

$$6495397 := 6 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times 5 \times 3^9 + 7$$

$$6495398 := 6 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times 5 \times 3^9 + 8$$

$$6495399 := 6 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times 5 \times 3^9 + 9$$

$$7398400 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 00$$

$$7398401 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 01$$

$$7398402 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 02$$

$$7398403 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 03$$

$$7398404 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 04$$

$$7398405 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 05$$

$$7398406 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 06$$

$$7398407 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 07$$

$$7398408 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 08$$

$$7398409 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 09$$

$$7398410 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 10$$

$$7398411 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 11$$

$$7398412 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 12$$

$$7398413 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 13$$

$$7398414 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 14$$

$$7398415 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 15$$

$$7398416 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 16$$

$$7398417 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 17$$

$$7398418 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 18$$

$$7398419 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 19$$

$$7398420 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 20$$

$$7398421 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 21$$

$$7398422 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 22$$

$$7398423 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 23$$

$$7398424 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 24$$

$$7398425 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 25$$

$$7398426 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 26$$

$$7398427 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 27$$

$$7398428 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 28$$

$$7398429 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 29$$

$$7398430 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 30$$

$$7398431 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 31$$

$$7398432 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 32$$

$$7398433 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 33$$

$$7398434 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 34$$

$$7398435 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 35$$

$$7398436 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 36$$

$$7398437 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 37$$

$$7398438 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 38$$

$$7398439 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 39$$

$$7398440 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 40$$

$$7398441 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 41$$

$$7398442 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 42$$

$$7398443 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 43$$

$$7398444 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 44$$

$$7398445 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 45$$

$$7398446 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 46$$

$$7398447 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 47$$

$$7398448 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 48$$

$$7398449 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 49$$

$$7398450 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 50$$

$$7398451 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 51$$

$$7398452 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 52$$

$$7398453 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 53$$

$$7398454 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 54$$

$$7398455 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 55$$

$$7398456 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 56$$

$$7398457 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 57$$

$$7398458 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 58$$

$$7398459 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 59$$

$$7398460 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 60$$

$$7398461 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 61$$

$$7398462 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 62$$

$$7398463 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 63$$

$$7398464 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 64$$

$$7398465 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 65$$

$$7398466 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 66$$

$$7398467 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 67$$

$$7398468 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 68$$

$$7398469 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 69$$

$$7398470 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 70$$

$$7398471 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 71$$

$$7398472 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 72$$

$$7398473 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 73$$

$$7398474 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 74$$

$$7398475 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 75$$

$$7398476 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 76$$

$$7398477 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 77$$

$$7398478 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 78$$

$$7398479 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 79$$

$$7398480 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 80$$

$$7398481 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 81$$

$$7398482 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 82$$

$$7398483 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 83$$

$$7398484 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 84$$

$$7398485 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 85$$

$$7398486 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 86$$

$$7398487 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 87$$

$$7398488 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 88$$

$$7398489 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 89$$

$$7398490 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 90$$

$$7398491 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 91$$

$$7398492 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 92$$

$$7398493 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 93$$

$$7398494 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 94$$

$$7398495 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 95$$

$$7398496 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 96$$

$$7398497 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 97$$

$$7398498 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 98$$

$$7398499 := \left((7^3 - \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 99$$

$$7864530 := (7 + 8^6) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times 3 + 0$$

$$7864531 := (7 + 8^6) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times 3 + 1$$

$$7864532 := (7 + 8^6) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times 3 + 2$$

$$7864533 := (7 + 8^6) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times 3 + 3$$

$$7864534 := (7 + 8^6) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times 3 + 4$$

$$7864535 := (7 + 8^6) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times 3 + 5$$

$$7864536 := (7 + 8^6) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times 3 + 6$$

$$7864537 := (7 + 8^6) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times 3 + 7$$

$$7864538 := (7 + 8^6) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times 3 + 8$$

$$7864539 := (7 + 8^6) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times 3 + 9$$

$$7890490 := (7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9})^{04} + 9 + 0$$

$$7890491 := (7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9})^{04} + 9 + 1$$

$$7890492 := (7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9})^{04} + 9 + 2$$

$$7890493 := (7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9})^{04} + 9 + 3$$

$$7890494 := (7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9})^{04} + 9 + 4$$

$$7890495 := (7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9})^{04} + 9 + 5$$

$$7890496 := (7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9})^{04} + 9 + 6$$

$$7890497 := (7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9})^{04} + 9 + 7$$

$$7890498 := (7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9})^{04} + 9 + 8$$

$$7890499 := (7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9})^{04} + 9 + 9$$

$$7971650 := (7 + \sqrt{9^{7 \times 1 + 6}}) \times 5 + 0$$

$$7971651 := (7 + \sqrt{9^{7 \times 1 + 6}}) \times 5 + 1$$

$$7971652 := (7 + \sqrt{9^{7 \times 1 + 6}}) \times 5 + 2$$

$$7971653 := (7 + \sqrt{9^{7 \times 1 + 6}}) \times 5 + 3$$

$$7971654 := (7 + \sqrt{9^{7 \times 1 + 6}}) \times 5 + 4$$

$$7971655 := (7 + \sqrt{9^{7 \times 1 + 6}}) \times 5 + 5$$

$$7971656 := (7 + \sqrt{9^{7 \times 1 + 6}}) \times 5 + 6$$

$$7971657 := (7 + \sqrt{9^{7 \times 1 + 6}}) \times 5 + 7$$

$$7971658 := (7 + \sqrt{9^{7 \times 1 + 6}}) \times 5 + 8$$

$$7971659 := (7 + \sqrt{9^{7 \times 1 + 6}}) \times 5 + 9$$

$$8597750 := 85^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7 \times (7 - 5) + 0$$

$$8597751 := 85^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7 \times (7 - 5) + 1$$

$$8597752 := 85^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7 \times (7 - 5) + 2$$

$$8597753 := 85^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7 \times (7 - 5) + 3$$

$$8597754 := 85^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7 \times (7 - 5) + 4$$

$$8597755 := 85^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7 \times (7 - 5) + 5$$

$$8597756 := 85^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7 \times (7 - 5) + 6$$

$$8597757 := 85^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7 \times (7 - 5) + 7$$

$$8597758 := 85^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7 \times (7 - 5) + 8$$

$$8597759 := 85^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7 \times (7 - 5) + 9$$

$$9764870 := \sqrt{9} + 7^6 \times (-4 + 87) + 0$$

$$9764871 := \sqrt{9} + 7^6 \times (-4 + 87) + 1$$

$$9764872 := \sqrt{9} + 7^6 \times (-4 + 87) + 2$$

$$9764873 := \sqrt{9} + 7^6 \times (-4 + 87) + 3$$

$$9764874 := \sqrt{9} + 7^6 \times (-4 + 87) + 4$$

$$9764875 := \sqrt{9} + 7^6 \times (-4 + 87) + 5$$

$$9764876 := \sqrt{9} + 7^6 \times (-4 + 87) + 6$$

$$9764877 := \sqrt{9} + 7^6 \times (-4 + 87) + 7$$

$$9764878 := \sqrt{9} + 7^6 \times (-4 + 87) + 8$$

$$9764879 := \sqrt{9} + 7^6 \times (-4 + 87) + 9$$

$$9765540 := -9 - 76 + 5^{5 \times \sqrt{4}} + 0$$

$$9765541 := -9 - 76 + 5^{5 \times \sqrt{4}} + 1$$

$$9765542 := -9 - 76 + 5^{5 \times \sqrt{4}} + 2$$

$$9765543 := -9 - 76 + 5^{5 \times \sqrt{4}} + 3$$

$$9765544 := -9 - 76 + 5^{5 \times \sqrt{4}} + 4$$

$$9765545 := -9 - 76 + 5^{5 \times \sqrt{4}} + 5$$

$$9765546 := -9 - 76 + 5^{5 \times \sqrt{4}} + 6$$

$$9765547 := -9 - 76 + 5^{5 \times \sqrt{4}} + 7$$

$$9765548 := -9 - 76 + 5^{5 \times \sqrt{4}} + 8$$

$$9765549 := -9 - 76 + 5^{5 \times \sqrt{4}} + 9$$

$$9765640 := \sqrt{9} \times 7 - 6 + 5^{6+4} + 0$$

$$9765641 := \sqrt{9} \times 7 - 6 + 5^{6+4} + 1$$

$$9765642 := \sqrt{9} \times 7 - 6 + 5^{6+4} + 2$$

$$9765643 := \sqrt{9} \times 7 - 6 + 5^{6+4} + 3$$

$$9765644 := \sqrt{9} \times 7 - 6 + 5^{6+4} + 4$$

$$9765645 := \sqrt{9} \times 7 - 6 + 5^{6+4} + 5$$

$$9765646 := \sqrt{9} \times 7 - 6 + 5^{6+4} + 6$$

$$9765647 := \sqrt{9} \times 7 - 6 + 5^{6+4} + 7$$

$$9765648 := \sqrt{9} \times 7 - 6 + 5^{6+4} + 8$$

$$9765649 := \sqrt{9} \times 7 - 6 + 5^{6+4} + 9$$

$$9834490 := \sqrt{9} + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 - 9 + 0$$

$$9834491 := \sqrt{9} + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 - 9 + 1$$

$$9834492 := \sqrt{9} + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 - 9 + 2$$

$$9834493 := \sqrt{9} + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 - 9 + 3$$

$$9834494 := \sqrt{9} + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 - 9 + 4$$

$$9834495 := \sqrt{9} + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 - 9 + 5$$

$$9834496 := \sqrt{9} + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 - 9 + 6$$

$$9834497 := \sqrt{9} + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 - 9 + 7$$

$$9834498 := \sqrt{9} + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 - 9 + 8$$

$$9834499 := \sqrt{9} + (8 \times (3 + 4))^4 - 9 + 9$$

$$9953280 := (9 + \sqrt{9})^5 \times (32 + 8) + 0$$

$$9953281 := (9 + \sqrt{9})^5 \times (32 + 8) + 1$$

$$9953282 := (9 + \sqrt{9})^5 \times (32 + 8) + 2$$

$$9953283 := (9 + \sqrt{9})^5 \times (32 + 8) + 3$$

$$9953284 := (9 + \sqrt{9})^5 \times (32 + 8) + 4$$

$$9953285 := (9 + \sqrt{9})^5 \times (32 + 8) + 5$$

$$9953286 := (9 + \sqrt{9})^5 \times (32 + 8) + 6$$

$$9953287 := (9 + \sqrt{9})^5 \times (32 + 8) + 7$$

$$9953288 := (9 + \sqrt{9})^5 \times (32 + 8) + 8$$

$$9953289 := (9 + \sqrt{9})^5 \times (32 + 8) + 9$$

$$9953400 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 40 + 0$$

$$9953401 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 40 + 1$$

$$9953402 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 40 + 2$$

$$9953403 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 40 + 3$$

$$9953404 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 40 + 4$$

$$9953405 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 40 + 5$$

$$9953406 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 40 + 6$$

$$9953407 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 40 + 7$$

$$9953408 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 40 + 8$$

$$9953409 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 3 \right) \times 40 + 9$$

2.2 General Representations - Up to 6 Digits

Below are **selfie numbers** in a general way up to 6 digits.

$$\begin{aligned}
 729 &:= (7 + 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1764 &:= \sqrt{(1 \times 7 \times 6)^4} \\
 2378 &:= -23 + \sqrt{7^8} \\
 2744 &:= \sqrt{(2 \times 7)^{\sqrt{4}+4}} \\
 2746 &:= 2 + \sqrt{(7 \times \sqrt{4})^6} \\
 3645 &:= \sqrt{3^{6 \times \sqrt{4}}} \times 5 \\
 4372 &:= \sqrt{4} \times 3^7 - 2 \\
 4374 &:= 4 \times 3^7 / \sqrt{4} \\
 4913 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times 9 - 1)^3 \\
 5184 &:= \sqrt{(5 + 1)^8} \times 4 \\
 6495 &:= (6^4 - \sqrt{9}) \times 5 \\
 6859 &:= (6 + 8 + 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 8192 &:= \sqrt{(8 \times 1)^9} / 2 \\
 11495 &:= \sqrt{11^4} \times 95 \\
 12288 &:= \sqrt{(1 + 2)^2 \times 8^8} \\
 13823 &:= -1 + \sqrt{(3 \times 8)^{2 \times 3}} \\
 13824 &:= \sqrt{(1 \times 3 \times 8)^{2+4}} \\
 15544 &:= ((1 + 5)^5 - 4) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 15546 &:= (1 + 5)^5 \times \sqrt{4} - 6 \\
 15549 &:= (1 + 5)^5 \times \sqrt{4} - \sqrt{9} \\
 15564 &:= ((1 + 5)^5 + 6) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 15627 &:= -1 + 5^6 + \sqrt{2 + 7} \\
 15628 &:= -1 + 5^6 + \sqrt{2 \times 8} \\
 15629 &:= \sqrt{(1 + 5^6)^2} + \sqrt{9} \\
 15634 &:= 1 \times 5^6 + \sqrt{3^4} \\
 15674 &:= 1 \times 5^6 + \sqrt{7^4} \\
 16791 &:= -16 + \sqrt{7^{9+1}} \\
 16807 &:= \sqrt{(1 + 6)^8} \times 07 \\
 16849 &:= (1 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times (4 + 9) \\
 17459 &:= 17 \times (4^5 + \sqrt{9}) \\
 17496 &:= (-1 + 7) \times 4 \times \sqrt{9^6} \\
 19454 &:= 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4} \\
 19459 &:= 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9} \\
 19682 &:= -1 + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{6 \times (8-2)}}}} \\
 19684 &:= 1 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{6+8+4}}} \\
 19699 &:= 1 + 9 + 6 + \sqrt{9^9} \\
 24389 &:= (24 - 3 + 8)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 26244 &:= \sqrt{(2 \times (6/2)^4)^4} \\
 26995 &:= (2 \times (6 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 \\
 26998 &:= -2 + (6 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 \\
 27648 &:= 2^7 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^{4+8}}} \\
 28671 &:= \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^6} \times 7 - 1 \\
 28672 &:= \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^6} \times 7^2 \\
 28674 &:= \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^6} \times 7 + \sqrt{4} \\
 29281 &:= 2 \times \sqrt{(9 + 2)^8} - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$29284 := 2 + \sqrt{(9+2)^8} \times 4$$

$$29435 := \sqrt{29^4} \times 35$$

$$29584 := (-2 + \sqrt{9} \times 58)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$31684 := \sqrt{(31 \times 6 - 8)^4}$$

$$32684 := \sqrt{32^6} - 84$$

$$32774 := (3 + 2^{7+7}) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$32805 := \sqrt{3^{2 \times 8}} \times 05$$

$$34295 := (3 + 4^2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 5$$

$$34445 := (3^4 + \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5$$

$$34992 := 3 \times (4 \times \sqrt{9} \times 9)^2$$

$$35945 := 35 \times (\sqrt{9} + 4^5)$$

$$36450 := \sqrt{3^{6 \times \sqrt{4}}} \times 50$$

$$36864 := 36 \times \sqrt{8^6 \times 4}$$

$$36882 := (3 + 6) \times (\sqrt{8^8} + 2)$$

$$37485 := \sqrt{(3 \times 7)^4} \times 85$$

$$38475 := \sqrt{3^8} \times 475$$

$$39364 := 3^9 / 3 \times 6 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$39374 := (3^9 - 3 + 7) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$39384 := 3 \times (\sqrt{9} + 3^8) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$39494 := (3^9 + 4^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$42873 := -\sqrt{4} + (28 + 7)^3$$

$$42879 := 4 + (28 + 7)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$43264 := 4^3 \times \sqrt{26^4}$$

$$44944 := \sqrt{((4 + 49) \times 4)^4}$$

$$45357 := -\sqrt{4^{5 \times 3}} + 5^7$$

$$45945 := (4^5 - \sqrt{9}) \times 45$$

$$46627 := -\sqrt{4} + 6^6 - 27$$

$$46629 := \sqrt{4} + 6^6 - 29$$

$$46636 := -\sqrt{4} + 6^6 - 3 \times 6$$

$$46637 := \sqrt{4} + 6^6 - 3 \times 7$$

$$46642 := \sqrt{4} + 6^6 - 4^2$$

$$46645 := -4 + 6^6 - \sqrt{4} - 5$$

$$46646 := -4 + \sqrt{6^{6 \times \sqrt{4}}} - 6$$

$$46647 := \sqrt{4} + 6^6 - 4 - 7$$

$$46649 := 4 + 6^6 - \sqrt{4} - 9$$

$$46654 := \sqrt{4} + 6 \times 6^5 - 4$$

$$46658 := \sqrt{4} + (6 \times 6)^{-5+8}$$

$$46672 := \sqrt{4} + 6^6 + 7 \times 2$$

$$46674 := 4 + 6^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$46679 := \sqrt{4} + 6^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$46694 := \sqrt{4} + 6^6 + 9 \times 4$$

$$48729 := 4^8 - 7^{2+\sqrt{9}}$$

$$49147 := -\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{9} \times (-1 + 4^7)$$

$$49575 := \sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9} \times 5}} + 7^5$$

$$49928 := (-\sqrt{4} + 9 \times 9)^2 \times 8$$

$$51840 := \sqrt{(5+1)^8} \times 40$$

$$52822 := \sqrt{(5+2)^8} \times 22$$

$$54675 := \sqrt{(5+4)^6} \times 75$$

$$56644 := (\sqrt{5^6 - 6 \times \sqrt{4}})^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$58991 := -58 + \sqrt{9^{9+1}}$$

$$59054 := 5 + \sqrt{9^{05 \times \sqrt{4}}}$$

$$59319 := (5 + \sqrt{9} + 31)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$64006 := 6 + \sqrt{40^{06}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64950 &:= (6^4 - \sqrt{9}) \times 50 \\
 68644 &:= (6 + \sqrt{8^6/4})^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 69978 &:= -6 + \sqrt{(9+9)^7 \times 8} \\
 69984 &:= (6 \times \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \times (8+4) \\
 72688 &:= 7 \times (2 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 8 \\
 73984 &:= \sqrt{((7+3 \times 9) \times 8)^4} \\
 74431 &:= \sqrt{7^{4+4}} \times 31 \\
 75168 &:= (7+51) \times \sqrt{6^8} \\
 81920 &:= 8^{1+\sqrt{9}} \times 20 \\
 82944 &:= 8^2 \times \sqrt{(9 \times 4)^4} \\
 84672 &:= \sqrt{(8+4)^6 \times 7^2} \\
 85176 &:= -8 + \sqrt{(51-7)^6} \\
 85734 &:= (-8 + (5 \times 7)^3) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 98286 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (\sqrt{8^{2+8}} - 6) \\
 98297 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2+\sqrt{9}} - 7 \\
 98304 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8^{3+\sqrt{04}} \\
 98328 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8^{3+2} + 8) \\
 98385 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} + 3 \times 8^5 \\
 98598 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8^5 + 98) \\
 102487 &:= \sqrt{(10 + 2/\sqrt{4})^8} \times 7 \\
 104964 &:= -10 - \sqrt{4} + (\sqrt{9} \times 6)^4 \\
 104976 &:= (10 - \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{9^7} \times 6 \\
 106929 &:= (106 + \sqrt{9})^2 \times 9 \\
 114677 &:= -11 + (-\sqrt{4} + 6)^7 \times 7 \\
 114687 &:= -1 \times 1 + \sqrt{4^{6+8}} \times 7 \\
 114688 &:= (11 \times \sqrt{4} + 6) \times \sqrt{8^8} \\
 114950 &:= \sqrt{11^4} \times 950 \\
 116424 &:= 11 \times 6 \times \sqrt{42^4} \\
 116645 &:= (1 + 1 + 6^6) / \sqrt{4} \times 5 \\
 116964 &:= ((11 \times 6 - 9) \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 117572 &:= (-11 + 7^5) \times \sqrt{7^2} \\
 117574 &:= (-11 + 7^5) \times 7 + \sqrt{4} \\
 117640 &:= -11 + 7^6 + \sqrt{4} + 0 \\
 117645 &:= -1 + 1 \times 7^6 - \sqrt{4+5} \\
 117646 &:= 1 + 1 \times 7^6 + \sqrt{4} - 6 \\
 117649 &:= (1^{17} + 6)^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \\
 117654 &:= 1 + 1 + 7^6 + \sqrt{5+4} \\
 117659 &:= 1 + 1 + 7^6 + 5 + \sqrt{9} \\
 117674 &:= 11 + 7^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{4} \\
 117676 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{(1+1+7)^6} + 7^6} \\
 117726 &:= 11 \times 7 + \sqrt{7^{2 \times 6}} \\
 117764 &:= 117 + 7^6 - \sqrt{4} \\
 117766 &:= 117 + 7^{\sqrt{6 \times 6}} \\
 117769 &:= 117 + 7^6 + \sqrt{9} \\
 117996 &:= -1 \times 17 + \sqrt{9^9} \times 6 \\
 118098 &:= 1 \times 18 \times \sqrt{09^8} \\
 124413 &:= (12^4 \times \sqrt{4} - 1) \times 3 \\
 124416 &:= 12^4 \times (4 + \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}) \\
 124419 &:= (12^4 \times \sqrt{4} + 1) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 124428 &:= (12^4 + \sqrt{4}) \times (-2 + 8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$124852 := \sqrt{(1+2+4)^8} \times 52$$

$$124856 := -\sqrt{12^4} + 8 \times 5^6$$

$$124995 := (1^2 + 49)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5$$

$$124999 := -1 + (-2 + 49 + \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$129375 := (12^{\sqrt{9}} - 3) \times 75$$

$$131071 := \sqrt{(1+3)^{10+7}} - 1$$

$$131074 := \sqrt{(1+3)^{10+7}} + \sqrt{4}$$

$$132519 := -132 + 51^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$136462 := (\sqrt{13^6} + 4) \times 62$$

$$136857 := \sqrt{(1^3 + 6)^8} \times 57$$

$$137979 := (1 + (3^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 7) \times 9$$

$$138915 := (13 + 8)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 15$$

$$139953 := (((1+3) \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5) \times 3$$

$$139962 := 1 \times 3 \times ((9 - \sqrt{9})^6 - 2)$$

$$139964 := 1 \times 3 \times (9 - \sqrt{9})^6 - 4$$

$$139968 := (1+3) \times 9 \times \sqrt{9 \times 6^8}$$

$$139969 := 1 + \sqrt{(3 \times 9 + 9)^6} \times 9$$

$$139972 := 1 + 3 + (9 - \sqrt{9})^7 / 2$$

$$139996 := 1 + 3 \times (9 + (9 - \sqrt{9})^6)$$

$$143749 := 1 + 4 \times (37 - 4)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$147438 := (1 \times 4^7 - \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}$$

$$147439 := 1 + (4^7 - \sqrt{4}) \times 3 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$147454 := 1 \times 4^7 \times (4 + 5) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$147456 := 1 \times 4^7 \times (\sqrt{4+5} + 6)$$

$$147459 := 1 \times 4^7 \times (4 + 5) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$147465 := (1 + 4^7) \times (-\sqrt{4} + 6 + 5)$$

$$147474 := (1 \times \sqrt{4} + 7) \times (4^7 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$147492 := (1 \times 4^7 + 4) \times \sqrt{9^2}$$

$$147493 := 1 + (4^7 + 4) \times \sqrt{9} \times 3$$

$$147494 := (1 \times 4^7 + 4) \times 9 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$148862 := \sqrt{\sqrt{(1+48)^8} \times 62}$$

$$148945 := ((-1 + 4 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$148955 := (-1 + 4 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{5 \times 5}$$

$$149769 := (-1 + 4 \times 97)^{6/\sqrt{9}}$$

$$149797 := (1 \times 4^{\sqrt{9}+7} + \sqrt{9}) / 7$$

$$151875 := 15^{\sqrt{18+7}} / 5$$

$$157459 := (-1 \times 5 + \sqrt{7^4} + 5)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$157464 := (1 + 57 - 4)^{6/\sqrt{4}}$$

$$157469 := 1 \times 5 + ((7 + \sqrt{4}) \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$157479 := 15 + (7 + 47)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$158499 := (1 + \sqrt{(5 \times 8)^4}) \times 99$$

$$159744 := (-1 + 5^{\sqrt{9}+7}) \times 4^4$$

$$160867 := \sqrt{(1+6)^{08}} \times 67$$

$$161999 := -1 + 6 \times ((1+9) \times \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$163296 := (1+6) \times 32 \times \sqrt{9^6}$$

$$163297 := (-1 + 6^{3+2}) \times \sqrt{9} \times 7$$

$$163825 := (1-6) \times (3 - \sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}})$$

$$163840 := \sqrt{\sqrt{(1+63)^8} \times 40}$$

$$163885 := (-1 + 6) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8} + 8^5} \right)$$

$$164592 := 1 \times 6^4 \times (5^{\sqrt{9}} + 2)$$

$$165884 := \sqrt{(1 + 6 + 5)^8} \times 8 - 4$$

$$165887 := -1 + \sqrt{6 \times ((-5 + 8) \times 8)^7}$$

$$165888 := \sqrt{(1 + 6 + 5)^8} \times 8 \times 8$$

$$165889 := 1 + 6^5 \times 8 \times 8 / \sqrt{9}$$

$$166464 := \left((\sqrt{16} + 64) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$166698 := \left(\sqrt{(1 + 6)^6} \times 6 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}$$

$$167961 := (-1 + 6^7) \times \sqrt{9} / (6 - 1)$$

$$168070 := \sqrt{(1 + 6)^8} \times 070$$

$$169744 := ((1 \times 6 + 97) \times 4)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$172872 := 1 \times 7^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \times 72$$

$$175446 := \sqrt{(175 - 4)^4} \times 6$$

$$175609 := -1 \times 7 + 56^{\sqrt{09}}$$

$$175623 := 1 \times 7 + \sqrt{56^{2 \times 3}}$$

$$175633 := 17 + 56^{\sqrt{3 \times 3}}$$

$$176129 := 1 + (\sqrt{7^6} + 1) \times 2^9$$

$$176469 := (-1 + 7^6) / 4 \times 6 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$176474 := (1 - 7^6 \times (4 - 7)) / \sqrt{4}$$

$$176499 := \left((-1 + 7^6) / \sqrt{4} + 9 \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$176868 := \sqrt{17 \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \times \sqrt{6^8}}$$

$$177147 := \sqrt{(17 - 7 - 1)^{4+7}}$$

$$177674 := 1 \times 7 \times \sqrt{7^6} \times 74$$

$$179469 := (17 \times \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{4}} \times 69$$

$$181447 := (-1 + 81 \times \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \times 7$$

$$186599 := (-1 + 8 \times (6^5 \times \sqrt{9} - \sqrt{9}))$$

$$186616 := -1 \times 8 + 6^6 \times \sqrt{16}$$

$$186628 := (1^8 + 6^6) \times \sqrt{2 \times 8}$$

$$186649 := (-1 + 8 + 6^6) \times 4 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$186687 := (1 + 8) \times \left(\sqrt{(6 + 6)^8} + 7 \right)$$

$$188415 := -1 + \sqrt{8^8} \times (41 + 5)$$

$$188461 := (1 + \sqrt{8^8}) \times 46 - 1$$

$$188462 := (1 + \sqrt{8^8}) \times \sqrt{46^2}$$

$$188464 := (1 + \sqrt{8^8}) \times 46 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$188646 := (-1 + \sqrt{8^8} + 6) \times 46$$

$$194463 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 - 6 \times 3$$

$$194472 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 - 7 - 2$$

$$194474 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 - \sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}}$$

$$194479 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^4 + 7 - 9$$

$$194481 := (19 + \sqrt{4})^{-4+8 \times 1}$$

$$194634 := (-19 + 46^3) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$194662 := -1 - 9 + \sqrt{46^6} \times 2$$

$$194664 := 1 - 9 + \sqrt{46^6} \times 4$$

$$194666 := (-1 + \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{46^6} - 6$$

$$194669 := (-1 + \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{46^6} - \sqrt{9}$$

$$194672 := (-1 + \sqrt{9}) \times 46^{\sqrt{7+2}}$$

$$194692 := (1 + 9 + 46^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 2$$

$$195113 := 1 + (\sqrt{9} + 5 \times 11)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 195776 &:= -1 + \sqrt{9} + 5^7 + 7^6 \\
 196608 &:= (1 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times 6 \times 08 \\
 196882 &:= \sqrt{(1^9 + 6)^8} \times 82 \\
 199955 &:= (1 + 9) \times \sqrt{9^9} + 5^5 \\
 209949 &:= 2 \times (09 + 9)^4 - \sqrt{9} \\
 215994 &:= -2 + (1 + 59)^{\sqrt{9}} - 4 \\
 215995 &:= (2 - 1 + 59)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 \\
 215996 &:= 2 + (1 + 59)^{\sqrt{9}} - 6 \\
 215998 &:= -2 + (1 + 59)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \\
 215999 &:= 2 + (1 + 59)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9} \\
 218568 &:= (21 \times 8) \times (5 + \sqrt{6^8}) \\
 218756 &:= 2 \times (\sqrt{1 + 8} + 7 \times 5^6) \\
 225792 &:= 2 \times (-2 - 5 + 7^{\sqrt{9}})^2 \\
 226979 &:= -2 + (-2 + (6 + \sqrt{9}) \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 226981 &:= (2 \times 26 + 9)^{\sqrt{8+1}} \\
 226983 &:= \sqrt{2+2} + (69 - 8)^3 \\
 228484 &:= (-2 + (2 + 8) \times 48)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 228488 &:= \sqrt{(2/2 + 8 + 4)^8} \times 8 \\
 229374 &:= 2^{2 \times 9 - 3} \times 7 - \sqrt{4} \\
 229379 &:= 2^{2 \times 9 - 3} \times 7 + \sqrt{9} \\
 229397 &:= (2^{2 \times 9 - 3} + \sqrt{9}) \times 7 \\
 232324 &:= (2 \times (3^{2+3} - 2))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 232897 &:= \sqrt{(2 + 3 + 2)^8} \times 97 \\
 233295 &:= ((2 \times 3)^{3 \times 2} + \sqrt{9}) \times 5 \\
 234357 &:= -2 \times \sqrt{3^4} + 3 \times 5^7 \\
 234365 &:= (-2 + 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)^6) \times 5 \\
 234373 &:= -2 + (-3 + \sqrt{4^3})^7 \times 3 \\
 234579 &:= (2 \times 34 + 5^7) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 234757 &:= -2 + 3 \times (\sqrt{4^7} + 5^7) \\
 235224 &:= 2 \times 3^5 \times \sqrt{22^4} \\
 235292 &:= 2 \times (-3 + ((5 + 2)^{\sqrt{9}})^2) \\
 235294 &:= 2 \times ((-3 + 52)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{4}) \\
 235298 &:= 2 \times (-3 + 52)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \\
 235784 &:= 2 \times (3^5 + 7^{8-\sqrt{4}}) \\
 236198 &:= 2 + 36 \times 1 \times \sqrt{9^8} \\
 236204 &:= (2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{(3 + 6)^2 0}}) \times 4 \\
 236268 &:= (2 + 3^{6+2}) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} \\
 236665 &:= -\sqrt{23^6} + (6 + 6)^5 \\
 238144 &:= (2 \times 3 \times 81 + \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 238328 &:= \sqrt{(23 + 8)^{3 \times 2}} \times 8 \\
 238464 &:= \sqrt{(2 \times 3)^8} \times 46 \times 4 \\
 238519 &:= (-2 + 3 \times (-8 + 51)^{\sqrt{9}}) \\
 239432 &:= 2 \times (3 + (9 - \sqrt{4})^3)^2 \\
 242064 &:= ((2 + 4 \times 20) \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 248831 &:= (\sqrt{2^4} + 8)^{8-3} - 1 \\
 248834 &:= 2 - (4 - 8 - 8)^{3+\sqrt{4}} \\
 249856 &:= 2^4 \times \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} + 5^6} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 253265 &:= \sqrt{(2^5 + 3 + 2)^6} \times 5 \\
 255894 &:= -2 \times 5^5 + 8^{\sqrt{9 \times 4}} \\
 258064 &:= (-2 + (5 + 80) \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 261949 &:= -(2^6 + 1) \times \sqrt{9} + 4^9 \\
 262154 &:= 2^{6 \times (2+1)} + 5 \times \sqrt{4} \\
 262159 &:= 2^{6 \times (2+1)} + 5 \times \sqrt{9} \\
 262186 &:= \sqrt{-2 + 6} \times 21 + 8^6 \\
 263169 &:= \left((2 + 6)^3 + 1 \right)^{6/\sqrt{9}} \\
 263869 &:= (2 \times 6)^3 + 8^6 - \sqrt{9} \\
 268322 &:= -2 + (6 + 8^3)^{\sqrt{2+2}} \\
 268326 &:= 2 + (6 + 8^3)^{\sqrt{-2+6}} \\
 268329 &:= 2 + (6 + 8^3)^2 + \sqrt{9} \\
 268877 &:= \left(2 + \sqrt{(6 + 8)^8} - 7 \right) \times 7 \\
 269568 &:= 26 \times (\sqrt{9} + 5) \times \sqrt{6^8} \\
 272484 &:= \left(2^{7+2} + \sqrt{4} + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 272976 &:= (-2 + 7)^{2\sqrt{9}} - 7^6 \\
 274639 &:= 2 \times 7 + \left(\sqrt{4} + 63 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 274653 &:= 2 \times 7 \times \sqrt{4} + 65^3 \\
 278868 &:= \left(-2 + 7 + \sqrt{8^8} \right) \times 68 \\
 278949 &:= -2 + 7^{8-\sqrt{9}} + 4^9 \\
 279675 &:= -\sqrt{2^{7+9}} + 6^7 - 5 \\
 279814 &:= -27 + \left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 1 \right)^4 \\
 279844 &:= \sqrt{2+7} + (-9 + 8 \times 4)^4 \\
 279927 &:= -2 - 7 + \sqrt{((9 + 9) \times 2)^7} \\
 279928 &:= 2^7 \times \sqrt{9^{9-2}} - 8 \\
 279933 &:= 2^7 \times \sqrt{9} \times 9^3 - 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 279939 &:= 2^7 \times \sqrt{9} \times 9^3 + \sqrt{9} \\
 279945 &:= 2 + 7 + \left(9 - \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{4+5}} \\
 279947 &:= 2 \times 7 - \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{(9 \times 4)^7} \\
 279966 &:= \left(-2 + 7 + \left(9 - \sqrt{9} \right)^6 \right) \times 6 \\
 279997 &:= -2 + 7 \times 9 + \left(9 - \sqrt{9} \right)^7 \\
 286497 &:= (2^8 + 6) / \sqrt{4} \times \sqrt{9^7} \\
 287492 &:= -2 + (-8 + 74)^{\sqrt{9}} - 2 \\
 287493 &:= ((2 + 8) \times 7 - 4)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 \\
 287494 &:= ((2 + 8) \times 7 - 4)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{4} \\
 287498 &:= 2 + (-8 + 74) \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \\
 287499 &:= ((2 + 8) \times 7 - 4)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{9} \\
 289444 &:= \sqrt{(2^8 + 9 + 4)^4} \times 4 \\
 292820 &:= (2 + 9)^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \times 20 \\
 292864 &:= 2^9 \times 286 \times \sqrt{4} \\
 293764 &:= (2 + 9 \times (3 + 7) \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 294350 &:= \sqrt{29^4} \times 350 \\
 294698 &:= 2 + \left(-\sqrt{9} + 4^6 \right) \times 9 \times 8 \\
 294784 &:= 2 \times \left(9 \times 4^7 - \sqrt{8^4} \right) \\
 294847 &:= -2 + 9 \times \left(4^8 / \sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \\
 294849 &:= \left(2 - 9 + 4^8 / \sqrt{4} \right) \times 9 \\
 294856 &:= -2 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{4}} \times (8^5 - 6) \\
 294865 &:= -2 + 9 \times \left(\sqrt{(4 \times 8)^6} - 5 \right) \\
 294874 &:= -2 + 9 \times \left(\sqrt{4^{8+7}} - 4 \right) \\
 294892 &:= -2 + 9 \times \left((4 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}} - 2 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$294910 := -2 + 9 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{4} \sqrt{9 \times 10}}$$

$$294914 := 2 + 9 \times 4^{9-1} / \sqrt{4}$$

$$294939 := \left(2^{\sqrt{9} \times (-4+9)} + 3\right) \times 9$$

$$294955 := \left(-29 \times \sqrt{4} + 9^5\right) \times 5$$

$$295198 := -2 + 9 \times 5 \times \left(-1 + \sqrt{9^8}\right)$$

$$295225 := \left(-2 + 9^5 - 2\right) \times \sqrt{25}$$

$$295265 := \left(-2 + \sqrt{9^{5 \times 2}} + 6\right) \times 5$$

$$295295 := \left(2 + \sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(5 \times 2 + 9^5\right)$$

$$296344 := \left(\left((-2 + 9) \times 6\right)^3 - \sqrt{4}\right) \times 4$$

$$296349 := \left(\left((-2 + 9) \times 6\right)^3 \times 4 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$297434 := 2 + \sqrt{9^7} \times (4 \times 34)$$

$$299617 := -2 + \sqrt{9^9} + (6 \times 1)^7$$

$$299975 := 2 + \sqrt{9} \times \left(-9 + \left(\sqrt{9} + 7\right)^5\right)$$

$$311364 := (31 \times 1 \times 3 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$311469 := 3 \times (1 \times 1 + 46)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$314432 := \left((3 + 14) \times 4\right)^{\sqrt{3^2}}$$

$$314434 := \left((3 + 14) \times 4\right)^3 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$314463 := 31 + \left(4 + \sqrt{4^6}\right)^3$$

$$314931 := 3 \times \left(1 + \left(\sqrt{4} \times 9\right)^{3+1}\right)$$

$$314946 := 3 \times 1 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 9\right)^4 + 6\right)$$

$$319488 := \left(-3 + \sqrt{(1 \times 9)^4}\right) \times \sqrt{8^8}$$

$$326627 := \left(3 + \sqrt{(2 + 6^6)^2}\right) \times 7$$

$$327680 := \sqrt{(3^2 + 7)^6} \times 80$$

$$327695 := 3 + 2^{7+6+\sqrt{9}} \times 5$$

$$328050 := \sqrt{3^{2 \times 8}} \times 050$$

$$328509 := (3 \times (28 - 5))^{\sqrt{09}}$$

$$331779 := 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}}$$

$$331869 := 3 \times \left(31 + (8 \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}}\right)$$

$$334365 := -\sqrt{3 \times 3} + 43 \times 6^5$$

$$334368 := (3 + 3) \times 43 \times \sqrt{6^8}$$

$$334611 := 3^{\sqrt{3^4}} \times (6 + 11)$$

$$338724 := (3 + 3 + 8 \times 72)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$342950 := (3 + 4^2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 50$$

$$342995 := (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5$$

$$344450 := \left(3^4 + \sqrt{4}\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 50$$

$$344605 := \sqrt{(-3 + 44)^6} \times 05$$

$$345744 := \left((3 + 4 + 5) \times \sqrt{7^4}\right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$348145 := \left(\sqrt{(3 + 4)^8} \times 145\right)$$

$$349920 := 3 \times \left(\sqrt{4} \times 9\right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 20$$

$$349965 := (3 + \sqrt{4}) \times (9 + 9 \times 6^5)$$

$$352962 := 3 \times \left(5 + (-2 + 9)^{\sqrt{6^2}}\right)$$

$$352964 := 3 \times \left(5 + (-2 + 9)^6 + \sqrt{4}\right)$$

$$354186 := \left(\sqrt{3^{5 \times 4}} - 18\right) \times 6$$

$$354246 := \left(\sqrt{3^{5 \times 4}} - 2 \times 4\right) \times 6$$

$$354273 := \left(\sqrt{3^{5 \times 4}} \times 2 - 7\right) \times 3$$

$$354276 := \left(\sqrt{3^{5 \times 4}} - \sqrt{2 + 7}\right) \times 6$$

$$354282 := \left(\sqrt{3^{5 \times 4}} - 2\right) \times (8 - 2)$$

$$354287 := \sqrt{3^{5 \times 4}} \times (-2 + 8) - 7$$

$$354329 := 35 + \sqrt{4} \times 3^{2+9}$$

$$354347 := \left(\sqrt{(3 \times 5)^{\sqrt{4^3}} - 4} \right) \times 7$$

$$354354 := \left((3 \times 5)^4 - 3 \right) \times \left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$354375 := (3 \times 5)^4 \times \left(\sqrt{-3+7} + 5 \right)$$

$$354486 := \left(\sqrt{3^{5 \times 4}} + 4 \times 8 \right) \times 6$$

$$354487 := \left((3 \times 5)^4 + \sqrt{4} \times 8 \right) \times 7$$

$$354726 := \left(\sqrt{3^{5 \times 4}} + 72 \right) \times 6$$

$$356445 := \sqrt{(3^5 + 6 \times 4)^4} \times 5$$

$$364500 := \sqrt{3^{6 \times \sqrt{4}}} \times 500$$

$$365471 := \sqrt{36^5} \times 47 - 1$$

$$365472 := \sqrt{36^5 \times 47^2}$$

$$365474 := \sqrt{36^5} \times 47 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$366052 := \sqrt{3^6} + 605^2$$

$$366795 := \left(-3^6 + (6 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 5$$

$$368640 := 3 \times 6 \times \sqrt{8^6} \times 40$$

$$373269 := 3 \times \left(7 + \sqrt{3 \times (2 \times 6)^9} \right)$$

$$374452 := \left(3 \times 7^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 52$$

$$374544 := \left((37 \times 4 + 5) \times 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$374845 := \left(37^4 + \sqrt{8^4} \right) / 5$$

$$374850 := \sqrt{(3 \times 7)^4} \times 850$$

$$384066 := \left(3 + 8 + \sqrt{40^6} \right) \times 6$$

$$384750 := \sqrt{3^8} \times 4750$$

$$388999 := \left(\sqrt{3^8} - 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9 - 9$$

$$389344 := (3 + 89)^3 \times \sqrt{4}/4$$

$$389893 := -3 + \left(8 - \sqrt{9} \right)^8 - 9^3$$

$$389899 := 3 + \left(8 - \sqrt{9} \right)^8 - 9^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$390584 := -39 + 05^8 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$393198 := (-3 + 9) \times \left(-3 + \left(1 + \sqrt{9} \right)^8 \right)$$

$$393217 := 3/\sqrt{9} + 3 \times 2^{17}$$

$$393264 := (3 + 9) \times \left(\sqrt{32^6} + 4 \right)$$

$$393645 := \left(-3 + \sqrt{(9 \times 3)^6 \times 4} \right) \times 5$$

$$394384 := \left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{\left(\sqrt{4} + 3 \right)^8} \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$411772 := \sqrt{4} - 1 - (1 - 7^7) / 2$$

$$411774 := \sqrt{4} \times (1 + (1 + 7^7) / 4)$$

$$411845 := (41 \times (-1 + 8))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5$$

$$413357 := \left(\sqrt{4} + (1 \times 3 \times 3)^5 \right) \times 7$$

$$413499 := \left(41^3 \times \sqrt{4} - 9 \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$413526 := \sqrt{41^{3+5-2}} \times 6$$

$$413556 := \left(41^3 + \sqrt{5 \times 5} \right) \times 6$$

$$417595 := \left(-\sqrt{4} + 17^{-5+9} \right) \times 5$$

$$419888 := \left(-\sqrt{4} \times 1 + \sqrt{9^8} \times 8 \right) \times 8$$

$$419944 := 4 \times \left(1 + 9 + \left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right)^4 \right)$$

$$425958 := \left(-\sqrt{4} + 2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} \right) \times (5 + 8)$$

$$435456 := \sqrt{\left(\sqrt{4} \times 3 \right)^{5 \times \sqrt{4}}} \times 56$$

$$437512 := 4 \times \left(3 + 7 \times \sqrt{5^{12}} \right)$$

$$437512 := -4 \times \left(-3 - 7 \times \sqrt{5^{12}} \right)$$

$$438928 := \left(-4 + 38^{\sqrt{9}} - 2 \right) \times 8$$

$$438938 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times 38 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 38$$

$$438944 := \sqrt{4} \times (38^{\sqrt{9}} - 4) \times 4$$

$$438948 := 4 + (38^{\sqrt{9}} - 4) \times 8$$

$$438964 := (\sqrt{4} \times 38)^{\sqrt{9}} - 6 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$438965 := (\sqrt{4} \times 38)^{\sqrt{9}} - 6 - 5$$

$$438968 := (\sqrt{4} \times 38)^{9-6} - 8$$

$$438976 := (\sqrt{4} \times 38)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (7 - 6)$$

$$438977 := (\sqrt{4} \times 38)^{\sqrt{9}} + 7/7$$

$$438994 := (\sqrt{4} \times 38)^{\sqrt{9}} + 9 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$438997 := (\sqrt{4} \times 38)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{9} \times 7$$

$$438997 := (\sqrt{4} \times 38)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{9} \times 7$$

$$438998 := -\sqrt{4} + (38^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{9}) \times 8$$

$$442368 := 4 \times \sqrt{(4 \times 2 \times 3)^6} \times 8$$

$$446148 := (4 + \sqrt{4^6}) \times (-1 + 4)^8$$

$$451584 := (-4 + 51 + \sqrt{5^8})^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$453789 := (\sqrt{4} + 5) \times 3 \times \sqrt{7^8} \times 9$$

$$455147 := (-4 + \sqrt{(5 \times 51)^4}) \times 7$$

$$455589 := (-4 + \sqrt{(5 + 5 + 5)^8}) \times 9$$

$$455593 := -\sqrt{4^5} + 5 \times (5 \times 9)^3$$

$$455596 := -4 + 5 \times (-5 + \sqrt{(5 \times 9)^6})$$

$$455645 := \left(\sqrt{((4 + 5) \times 5)^6} + 4 \right) \times 5$$

$$456529 := -4 + ((5 + 6) \times (5 + 2))^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$456973 := (4 \times 5 + 6)^{\sqrt{9+7}} - 3$$

$$456974 := (4 \times 5 + 6)^{\sqrt{9+7}} - \sqrt{4}$$

$$456979 := (4 \times 5 + 6)^{\sqrt{9+7}} + \sqrt{9}$$

$$458748 := -\sqrt{4^5}/8 + 7 \times 4^8$$

$$458752 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8+7}}} \times (5 + 2)}$$

$$459450 := (4^5 - \sqrt{9}) \times 450$$

$$466375 := (\sqrt{4} \times 6^6 + 37) \times 5$$

$$466495 := (\sqrt{4} \times 6^6 + 4 + 9) \times 5$$

$$466515 := (\sqrt{4} \times (6^6 - 5) + 1) \times 5$$

$$466530 := (\sqrt{4} \times 6^6 \times 5 - 30)$$

$$466533 := (\sqrt{4} \times 6^6 \times 5 - 3^3)$$

$$466534 := ((-\sqrt{4} + 6^6) \times 5 - 3) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$466538 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 - 3 - 8)$$

$$466550 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 - 5 + 0)$$

$$466572 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 + 7) - 2$$

$$466574 := 4 \times (6^6 \times 5 + 7) / \sqrt{4}$$

$$466575 := (\sqrt{4} \times (6^6 + 5) - 7) \times 5$$

$$466584 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 + 8 + 4)$$

$$466585 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times 6^6 + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}} \right) \times 5$$

$$466594 := ((4 + 6^6) \times 5 - \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$466595 := (\sqrt{4} \times (6^6 + 5) - \sqrt{9}) \times 5$$

$$466596 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 \times 5 + \sqrt{9} \times 6)$$

$$466615 := (\sqrt{4} \times (6^6 + 6) - 1) \times 5$$

$$466635 := (\sqrt{4} \times (6^6 + 6) + 3) \times 5$$

$$466944 := 4^6 \times 6 \times (\sqrt{9} + 4 \times 4)$$

$$469264 := 4^6 \times \sqrt{9} + 26^4$$

$$469732 := 4 \times (-6^{\sqrt{9}} + 7^{3 \times 2})$$

$$470604 := (\sqrt{4} + 7^{06}) \times 04$$

$$470628 := 4 \times (7^{\sqrt{06^2}} + 8)$$

$$472385 := -\sqrt{4} + 72 \times 3^8 - 5$$

$$472386 := (\sqrt{4} + 7)^{2+3} \times 8 - 6$$

$$472387 := \sqrt{4} + 72 \times 3^8 - 7$$

$$472389 := (\sqrt{4} + 7)^{2+3} \times 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$472394 := \sqrt{4} + 72 \times (3 \times \sqrt{9})^4$$

$$473344 := \sqrt{4} \times (7^3 - 3 + 4)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$474546 := (4 + 74)^{\sqrt{5+4}} - 6$$

$$474549 := (4 + 74)^{\sqrt{5+4}} - \sqrt{9}$$

$$474568 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(7 + \sqrt{4^5})^6} \right) \times 8$$

$$483149 := \left(-(4) - \left(- \left((8 + 3)^{1+4} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$483159 := \left(\sqrt{4} + ((8 + 3) \times 1)^5 \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$486655 := \left(\sqrt{(-\sqrt{4} + 8 \times 6)^6} - 5 \right) \times 5$$

$$486695 := \left(\sqrt{(-\sqrt{4} + 8 \times 6)^6} + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5$$

$$491775 := (-4 + \sqrt{9^{1+7}}) \times 75$$

$$492375 := (4 + \sqrt{9^{2^3}}) \times 75$$

$$492802 := -\sqrt{4} + (9 \times (-2 + 80))^2$$

$$493039 := (49 + 30)^{\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}}}$$

$$493832 := \sqrt{4} + 9 \times (38^3 - 2)$$

$$493834 := 4 + 9 \times (38^3 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$493838 := -\sqrt{4} + 9 \times 38^3 - 8$$

$$493839 := (-4 + \sqrt{9} + 38^3) \times 9$$

$$493844 := (-4 + 9 \times \sqrt{38^{\sqrt{4+4}}})$$

$$493846 := \left(-\sqrt{4} + 9 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{38^{4 \times 6}}}} \right)$$

$$493861 := 4 + (9 \times (\sqrt{38^6} + 1))$$

$$493862 := -4 + 9 \times (\sqrt{38^6} + 2)$$

$$493864 := -\sqrt{4} + 9 \times (\sqrt{38^6} + \sqrt{4})$$

$$493895 := \sqrt{4} + 9 \times (38^{\sqrt{9}} + 5)$$

$$495616 := (4^{\sqrt{9}} \times (5 + 6))^{\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}}$$

$$497442 := 4^9 + 7^{\sqrt{4+4}} \times 2$$

$$497666 := \sqrt{4} + ((9 - 7) \times 6)^6 / 6$$

$$499280 := \left((-\sqrt{4} + 9 \times 9)^2 \right) \times 80$$

$$499755 := \left(-49 + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^5 \right) \times 5$$

$$511949 := -51 + (-1 + \sqrt{9^4})^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$518400 := \sqrt{(5 + 1)^8} \times 400$$

$$524184 := (-52 + 4^{1+8}) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$524236 := -52 + \sqrt{4} \times 2^{3 \times 6}$$

$$524263 := -5^2 + \sqrt{4} \times (2^{6 \times 3})$$

$$524274 := (-5 - 2 + 4^{2+7}) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$524278 := -5 \times 2 + \sqrt{4^{27-8}}$$

$$524284 := -5 + (2 + 4^{2+8}) / \sqrt{4}$$

$$524286 := -\sqrt{5 - 2 / \sqrt{4}} + 2 \times 8^6$$

$$524289 := 5 - 2 \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^9} \right)$$

$$524291 := 5 - 2 + \sqrt{4^{2 \times 9 + 1}}$$

$$524294 := \left(5 - 2 + \sqrt{4^{2 \times 9}} \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$524297 := -5 + 2 \times \left(\sqrt{4^{2 \times 9}} + 7 \right)$$

$$524299 := 5 + 2 \times \left(\sqrt{4^{2 \times 9}} + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$524328 := \left(5 + \sqrt{2^{4^3/2}} \right) \times 8$$

$$524392 := \left(52 + 4^{3 \times \sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2$$

$$524488 := \left(5^2 + \sqrt{(4 \times 4)^8} \right) \times 8$$

$$524979 := 5 + 2 \times \left(4^9 + 7^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$528220 := \sqrt{(5 + 2)^8} \times 220$$

$$529984 := ((5 \times 2 + 9 \times 9) \times 8)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$531389 := -53 + 1 + \sqrt{3^{8 \times \sqrt{9}}}$$

$$531434 := -5 + (3 \times 1)^{4 \times 3} - \sqrt{4}$$

$$531439 := -5 + (3 \times 1)^{4 \times 3} + \sqrt{9}$$

$$531444 := 5 + (31 - 4)^4 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$531449 := 5 + (31 - 4)^4 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$531969 := 531 + 9^6 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$537824 := (5 + 3) \times \sqrt{7^{8+2}} \times 4$$

$$546750 := \sqrt{(5 + 4)^6} \times 750$$

$$546847 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{4 \times (6+8)}}} - 4} \right) \times 7$$

$$548937 := \left(-5 + \sqrt{4^8} \right) \times (9/3)^7$$

$$559867 := -5 + \sqrt{5 - 9 + 8} \times 6^7$$

$$559872 := \left(\sqrt{5 \times 5 + 9 - 8} \right)^7 \times 2$$

$$562428 := (5^6 - 2) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(4 + 2)^8}}$$

$$562464 := \left(5^6 - 2/\sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{6^4}$$

$$562495 := \sqrt{5^{6 \times 2}} \times 4 \times 9 - 5$$

$$563868 := (5^6 + 38) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}$$

$$566440 := \sqrt{(5^6 - 6)^{\sqrt{4}}} \times 40$$

$$566937 := \left(\sqrt{(5 \times 6)^6} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 3 \times 7$$

$$574644 := \left(5^7 + 4^{\sqrt{64}} \right) \times 4$$

$$574992 := \left(-5 + 74 - \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 2$$

$$575995 := (5 \times 7 + 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 - 5$$

$$584199 := \left(-\sqrt{5^8} + 4^{-1+9} \right) \times 9$$

$$585925 := (5^8 - 5) \times \sqrt{9}/2 - 5$$

$$585944 := \left((5^8 + 5) \times \sqrt{9} - \sqrt{4} \right) / \sqrt{4}$$

$$587615 := -\sqrt{5^8} + (7^6 - 1) \times 5$$

$$587635 := -\sqrt{5^8} + (7^6 + 3) \times 5$$

$$588245 := \left(5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}} \right)^{2+4} \times 5$$

$$589824 := (-5 + 8) \times \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 2)^4$$

$$589829 := 5 + \sqrt{8^9} \times 8 \times 2 \times 9$$

$$592697 := (5 \times 9 \times 2 - 6)^{\sqrt{9}} - 7$$

$$592699 := -5 + (9^2 - 6 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$592829 := 5^{\sqrt{9}} + (2 + 82)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$606528 := 6^{06} \times \left(\sqrt{5^2} + 8 \right)$$

$$614648 := ((6 + 1) \times 4)^{6-\sqrt{4}} - 8$$

$$627264 := (6 \times (2^7 - 2 + 6))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$629784 := 6^2 \times \left(\sqrt{9^7} \times 8 - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$629868 := 6 \times \left(2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} \times 6^8} \right)$$

$$629964 := 6 \times \left(2 \times 9 + (\sqrt{9} \times 6)^4 \right)$$

$$629984 := (6 - 2 + \sqrt{9^9}) \times 8 \times 4$$

$$638976 := \sqrt{6 \times 3 \times 8^9} \times (7 + 6)$$

$$649500 := (6^4 - \sqrt{9}) \times 500$$

$$649511 := -6 + (-\sqrt{4} + 9^5) \times 11$$

$$649539 := (-6 \times \sqrt{4} + 9 \times 5) \times 3^9$$

$$649545 := 6 + (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times (5 + 4)^5$$

$$649547 := \sqrt{64} + 9^5 \times (4 + 7)$$

$$649549 := 6 + 4 + 9^5 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9)$$

$$649583 := (6 - \sqrt{4} + 9^5) \times (8 + 3)$$

$$649589 := 6 + (4 + 9^5) \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$656274 := 6 \times (\sqrt{5^{6 \times 2}} \times 7 + 4)$$

$$656374 := 6 \times (5^6 + 3) \times 7 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$656379 := 6 \times (5^6 + 3) \times 7 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$656397 := (6 \times (5^6 + 3) + \sqrt{9}) \times 7$$

$$658464 := 6 \times \sqrt{5 \times 8 - \sqrt{4}^6} \times 4$$

$$658845 := (6 + 5)^{\sqrt{8+8}} \times 45$$

$$659344 := (6 \times 5 \times 9 \times 3 + \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$668174 := \sqrt{6 \times 6} + 8 \times 17^4$$

$$675684 := (6 + (7 + 5) \times 68)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$684288 := \sqrt{6^8} \times (4 + 2) \times 88$$

$$685464 := 6 \times (8 + 5)^4 \times (6 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$685984 := (((6 + 8) \times 5)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$685994 := (((6 + 8) \times 5)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$688128 := 6 \times \sqrt{8^8} \times 1 \times 28$$

$$690768 := (6 \times 90 - 7) \times \sqrt{6^8}$$

$$691482 := -6 + 9 \times \sqrt{14^8} \times 2$$

$$691484 := 6 \times \sqrt{9 \times 14^8} - 4$$

$$691488 := 6 \times \sqrt{9} \times 14^{\sqrt{8+8}}$$

$$699735 := (6^{9-\sqrt{9}} - 7) \times 3 \times 5$$

$$699840 := 6^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times 40$$

$$704899 := -\sqrt{\sqrt{70^4} + 89^{\sqrt{9}}}$$

$$704969 := (70 + 4 + 9 + 6)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$708295 := \sqrt{7^{08}} \times 295$$

$$715822 := 71^{-5+8} \times \sqrt{2+2}$$

$$715824 := 71^{-5+8} \times 2 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$726880 := 7 \times (2 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 80$$

$$728995 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(7+2)^8} + 9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5$$

$$729003 := \sqrt{7+2} + 90^{03}$$

$$729009 := 7 + 2 + 90^{\sqrt{09}}$$

$$729049 := 7^2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{90^4 \times \sqrt{9}}}$$

$$729072 := 72 + 90^{\sqrt{7+2}}$$

$$742592 := ((7 + 4 + 2)^5 + \sqrt{9}) \times 2$$

$$744310 := \sqrt{7^{4+4}} \times 310$$

$$744385 := (\sqrt{7^4} + 4)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}}} \times 5$$

$$746489 := -7 + \sqrt{4} \times (64 + 8)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$746496 := (7 + \sqrt{4}) \times (6 \times 4)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6$$

$$746503 := 7 + (\sqrt{4} \times 6)^5 \times 03$$

$$746523 := \left(7 + (\sqrt{4} \times 6)^5 + 2 \right) \times 3$$

$$751599 := (7 + (5 - 1)^5) \times 9^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$751689 := \sqrt{(7 + 5 - 1 + 6)^8} \times 9$$

$$753424 := (7 \times (5^3 - \sqrt{4}/2))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$756495 := (7^5 + 6 - \sqrt{4}) \times 9 \times 5$$

$$759368 := -7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{3-6+8}$$

$$759381 := 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1$$

$$759382 := 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{3+\sqrt{8/2}}$$

$$759384 := 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} + \sqrt{4}$$

$$765625 := \sqrt{7^6} \times 5^6 / (2 + 5)$$

$$765667 := 7 \times (6 + \sqrt{5^{6+6}} \times 7)$$

$$765674 := (7 - 6 + 5^6) \times \sqrt{7^4}$$

$$774198 := (77 + 41) \times \sqrt{9^8}$$

$$778034 := (-\sqrt{7 \times 7} + 80)^3 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$780325 := \sqrt{7^8} \times 0325$$

$$781258 := \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} + 1} + 2 \times 5^8$$

$$786329 := -7 + (8^6 - 32) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$786399 := (-7 + 8^6) \times 3 - 9 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$786417 := -7 - 8 + 6 \times \sqrt{4^{17}}$$

$$786419 := -7 + (8^6 - \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{1 \times 9}$$

$$786423 := (-7 + 8^6 + \sqrt{4^2}) \times 3$$

$$786427 := 7 + (8^6 - 4) \times \sqrt{2 + 7}$$

$$786429 := (7 + 8^6 - 4 \times 2) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$786431 := (-7 + 8^6 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3 \times 1$$

$$786432 := \sqrt{7 + 8 - 6} \times 4^{3^2}$$

$$786443 := -7 + (8^6 + 4 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3$$

$$786445 := 7 + (8^6 + \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{4 + 5}$$

$$786447 := (7 + 8^6 - \sqrt{4}) \times (-4 + 7)$$

$$786449 := -7 + (8^6 + 4 + 4) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$786463 := 7 + (8^6 + \sqrt{4} + 6) \times 3$$

$$786467 := (7 + 8^6 / \sqrt{4}) \times 6 - 7$$

$$786469 := 7 + (8^6 + 4 + 6) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$786483 := (7 + 8^6 + \sqrt{4} + 8) \times 3$$

$$786489 := (7 + 8^6 + 4 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$786493 := 7 + (8^6 + \sqrt{4} \times 9) \times 3$$

$$786499 := \sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} + (6 + 4^9) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$788544 := (7 + 885 - 4)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$788833 := \sqrt{7^8} + (8 \times 8)^3 \times 3$$

$$789647 := (7^{8-\sqrt{9}} - 6) \times 47$$

$$796488 := 7 \times (-\sqrt{9} + 6^4) \times 88$$

$$798848 := (79 \times \sqrt{8 + 8})^{\sqrt{4}} \times 8$$

$$819200 := 8^{1+\sqrt{9}} \times 200$$

$$823477 := -(8/2)^3 - \sqrt{4} + 7^7$$

$$823547 := \sqrt{8 + 2^3} + (5 + \sqrt{4})^7$$

$$823727 := 8 \times 23 + \sqrt{7^{2 \times 7}}$$

$$829440 := \sqrt{(8 \times 2 \times 9)^4} \times 40$$

$$839779 := -8 + ((-3 + 9)^7 - 7) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$839784 := 8 \times (-3 + (\sqrt{9} + 7 + 8)^4)$$

$$839793 := (-8 + (-3 + 9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3$$

$$839795 := -8 + (-3 + 9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5$$

$$839804 := (-8 + (-3 + 9)^8) / \sqrt{04}$$

$$839816 := 8 + (-3 + 9)^8 / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}$$

$$851964 := 8^5 \times \left(-1 + \sqrt{\sqrt{96}}\right) - 4$$

$$851969 := -8^5 + 1 + 96^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$851981 := (8 + 5) \times \left(\left(1 + \sqrt{9}\right)^8 + 1\right)$$

$$859775 := 85^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{7 \times 7} / 5$$

$$864557 := 8^6 \times \sqrt{4 + 5} + 5^7$$

$$875448 := 8 \times 7 \times \left(5^{\sqrt{4+4}} + 8\right)$$

$$879795 := \left((8 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} + 7^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times 5$$

$$884728 := (8 \times (8 + 4))^{\sqrt{7+2}} - 8$$

$$884734 := (8 \times 84/7)^3 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$884739 := (8 \times 84/7)^3 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$898779 := (8 - 9 + 8^7) / 7 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$907596 := \left(9 \times 07^5 + \sqrt{9}\right) \times 6$$

$$911493 := \sqrt{(9 \times 11)^4} \times 93$$

$$912673 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 1\right) \times 26 - 7\right)^3$$

$$917448 := \left(\sqrt{9} - 1\right) \times 7 \times (-4 + 4^8)$$

$$917484 := (-9 - 1 + 7 \times 4^8) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$917488 := \left(\sqrt{9} - 1\right) \times (7 \times 4^8 - 8)$$

$$917494 := -9 - 1 + 7 \times 4^9 / \sqrt{4}$$

$$923524 := \sqrt{9} + (2 \times 3 + 5^2)^4$$

$$933888 := (9 - 3) \times 38 \times \sqrt{8^8}$$

$$938492 := \sqrt{(93 + 8)^4} \times 92$$

$$941168 := \left(-\sqrt{9} + (-4 + 11)^6\right) \times 8$$

$$944559 := \left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4}\right)^4 - 5 \times 5\right) \times 9$$

$$944847 := 9 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} \times (8)\right)^4 + 7\right)$$

$$946176 := \sqrt{9} \times 4^6 \times (1 + 76)$$

$$948395 := \sqrt{\left(9 - \sqrt{4}\right)^8} \times 395$$

$$958464 := 9 \times (5 + 8) \times 4^6 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$968244 := \left(-\sqrt{9} + (6 \times 82)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times 4$$

$$970299 := (9 \times (7 \times 0 + 2 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$972405 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times 7\right)^{\sqrt{2^4}} \times 05$$

$$979766 := -\sqrt{9} - 7 + \sqrt{9} \times 7 \times 6^6$$

$$984375 := \left(\sqrt{9^8 \times 4} + 3\right) \times 75$$

$$989497 := \left(98 + \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 97$$

$$994842 := \sqrt{9 \times 9^4} \times (8^4 - 2)$$

$$995316 := \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9}\right)^5 - 3\right) \times \sqrt{16}$$

$$995319 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 9 \times 5\right)^3 - 1\right) \times 9$$

$$995324 := \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9}\right)^5 - 3 + 2\right) \times 4$$

$$995328 := \left(9 + \sqrt{9}\right)^5 \times 32/8$$

$$995364 := \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9}\right)^5 + 3 + 6\right) \times 4$$

$$995453 := \left(9 + \sqrt{9}\right)^5 \times 4 + 5^3$$

$$995544 := \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9}\right)^5 + 54\right) \times 4$$

$$999916 := -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9 + 1)^6$$

$$999919 := -9 \times 9 + (9 + 91)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$999973 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \left(\sqrt{9} + 97\right)^3$$

$$999976 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + \left(\sqrt{9} + 7\right)^6$$

$$999995 := (9/9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5$$

2.3 General Representations - 7 Digits

Below are **selfie numbers** with **square-root** having 7 digits. Due que high quantity of numbers there many brackets "(...)" . These simplified very easily.

$$1001489 := 1001^{\sqrt{4}} - 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1013917 := 101^3 - (\sqrt{9} + 1)^7$$

$$1023984 := \left((10 \times 2^3)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1023994 := \left((10 \times 2^3)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1024144 := (-10 - 2 + 4^{1+4})^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1028999 := -1 + (-02 + 8 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1033922 := (-10 + \sqrt{33+9})^2 \times 2$$

$$1039682 := \sqrt{1+03} \times (\sqrt{96} - 8)^2$$

$$1043199 := (10 + 43 \times 1) \times \sqrt{99}$$

$$1044474 := -10 + (-\sqrt{4} + 4^{-\sqrt{4}+7})^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1044484 := (-10 + 4^4 \times 4 + 8)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1044494 := 10 + (-\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4 \times 4^9})^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1044524 := 10 \times 4 + (4^5 - 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1046656 := \sqrt{\sqrt{10^{4 \times 6}}} + 6^5 \times 6$$

$$1048416 := (-10 + 4^8) \times 4 \times \sqrt{16}$$

$$1048447 := -1 + (04 \times 8)^4 - \sqrt{4^7}$$

$$1048448 := \left((-10 + 4^8) \times \sqrt{4} + 4 \right) \times 8$$

$$1048472 := -104 + (8 \times \sqrt{4})^{7-2}$$

$$1048484 := -\sqrt{10^4} + 8 + (4 \times 8)^4$$

$$1048494 := -1 + (04 \times 8)^4 - \sqrt{9^4}$$

$$1048524 := (-104 + 8^{5+2}) / \sqrt{4}$$

$$1048533 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 33$$

$$1048538 := (\sqrt{1 \times 04} \times 8)^5 - 38$$

$$1048539 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 3 \times 9$$

$$1048543 := 10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 43$$

$$1048544 := (10 - \sqrt{4}) \times (8^5 \times 4 - 4)$$

$$1048545 := 1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - \sqrt{4^5}$$

$$1048547 := -1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - 4 \times 7$$

$$1048552 := 1 + (\sqrt{04} \times 8)^5 - 5^2$$

$$1048556 := 10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 - 5 \times 6$$

$$1048584 := 10 - \sqrt{4} + (8 \times 5 - 8)^4$$

$$1048587 := 10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 + 8 - 7$$

$$1048588 := 10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}$$

$$1048589 := 10 + 4 \times (8^5 \times 8 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$1048593 := -10 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 + 9 \times 3$$

$$1048594 := (\sqrt{1 \times 04} \times 8)^5 + 9 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1048597 := (\sqrt{1 \times 04} \times 8)^5 + \sqrt{9} \times 7$$

$$1048616 := 10 \times 4 + 8^6 \times \sqrt{16}$$

$$1048648 := (10 \times \sqrt{4} + 8^6) \times 4 - 8$$

$$1048649 := 1 + 04 \times (8^6 + \sqrt{4} \times 9)$$

$$1049549 := 1 + 04 \times (\sqrt{9^5} + 4^9)$$

$$1049760 := (10 - \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{9^7} \times 60$$

$$1053696 := (10 \times 5 + \sqrt{36})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6$$

$$1062862 := \left(-10 + \sqrt{\sqrt{(6/2)^{8 \times 6}}} \right) \times 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1062892 &:= 10 + \sqrt{(6/2)^{8 \times \sqrt{9}}} \times 2 \\
 1062896 &:= -\sqrt{10-6} + 2 \times (8+9^6) \\
 1062964 &:= (10 + 6^2 + 9^6) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 1062999 &:= (1 + 06 \times (2 + \sqrt{9^9})) \times 9 \\
 1068445 &:= \sqrt{(1+06)^8} \times 445 \\
 1069290 &:= (106 + \sqrt{9})^2 \times 90 \\
 1071648 &:= ((-10 + 71) \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 8 \\
 1075584 &:= (-1 + 07^{\sqrt{5 \times 5}}) \times \sqrt{8^4} \\
 1075647 &:= -1 + (07 \times 56)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 7 \\
 1075648 &:= 1 \times 0 + 7^5 \times \sqrt{64} \times 8 \\
 1077444 &:= ((1 + 07 \times 74) \times \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 1077454 &:= 10 + (7 + 7 + 4^5)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 1079995 &:= (-1 + (07 \times 9 - \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 5 \\
 1085764 &:= (10^{8-5} + 7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 1092727 &:= (10 \times (9 + 2) - 7)^{\sqrt{2+7}} \\
 1093479 &:= ((10 \times 9)^3 / \sqrt{4} - 7) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 1093494 &:= ((10 \times 9)^3 - 4) \times \sqrt{9} / \sqrt{4} \\
 1093495 &:= (10 \times 9)^3 / \sqrt{4} \times \sqrt{9} - 5 \\
 1105869 &:= (-1 + 10 \times (-5 + (8 \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}})) \\
 1119764 &:= (-1 + ((1 + 1) \times \sqrt{9})^7 + 6) \times 4 \\
 1124864 &:= ((11 - 2 + 4) \times 8)^{6/\sqrt{4}} \\
 1124999 &:= -1 + (1^2 + 49)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \\
 1125099 &:= (-1 + 12 + 50^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 9 \\
 1127378 &:= (11^{-2+7} + 3) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{78}}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1141998 &:= 11^4 \times (-1 \times \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) \\
 1146957 &:= (11 + \sqrt{4^{6+9}} \times 5) \times 7 \\
 1146985 &:= (11 + 4 \times 6) \times (\sqrt{9} + 8^5) \\
 1147678 &:= (1 + 1 + 476) \times \sqrt{7^8} \\
 1149184 &:= (((1 + 14) \times 9 - 1) \times 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 1149500 &:= \sqrt{11^4} \times 9500 \\
 1149973 &:= -11 + 4 \times (\sqrt{9} + 9 \times 7)^3 \\
 1149984 &:= (11 \times \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \times (8 + 4) \\
 1154648 &:= 11 \times (\sqrt{(54 \times 6)^4} - 8) \\
 1157593 &:= -(1 + 1)^5 + (7 \times 5 \times \sqrt{9})^3 \\
 1157626 &:= 1 + (15 \times 7)^{\sqrt{6/2+6}} \\
 1157629 &:= 1 + (15 \times 7)^{6/2} + \sqrt{9} \\
 1158242 &:= (1 + (-1 + 5 \times 8)^2)^{\sqrt{4}} / 2 \\
 1161299 &:= 1 + 1 + (61 - 2) \times \sqrt{9^9} \\
 1162875 &:= (\sqrt{11^6} - 2) \times 875 \\
 1166345 &:= (-11 + 6^6 \times (3 + \sqrt{4})) \times 5 \\
 1166425 &:= (-1 + 1 \times 6^6 + \sqrt{4}) \times 25 \\
 1166445 &:= (-1 + \sqrt{(16 + 6)^4})^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 \\
 1166450 &:= (1 + 1 + 6^6) / \sqrt{4} \times 50 \\
 1166452 &:= 1 + 1 + (6^6 + \sqrt{4}) \times 5^2 \\
 1166455 &:= (1 + 1 \times 6^6 - \sqrt{4}) \times 5 \times 5 \\
 1166886 &:= (-1 + 16 + 6)^{\sqrt{8+8}} \times 6 \\
 1167399 &:= (116 + 73^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 1168129 &:= 1 + (\sqrt{(-1 + 6)^8} - 1)^2 \times \sqrt{9} \\
 1168562 &:= 1 + (1 + \sqrt{6^8} \times 5/6)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1168582 := (11 \times \sqrt{6^8} - 5) \times 82$$

$$1171858 := -1 \times 17 + \sqrt{1+8} \times 5^8$$

$$1171859 := -1 + ((-1 + 7 - 1)^8 - 5) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1171872 := (-1 + (-1 + 7 - 1)^8) \times \sqrt{7+2}$$

$$1171899 := (-1 + (-1 + 7 - 1)^8 + 9) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1172889 := (1 \times 17 + 2)^{\sqrt{8+8}} \times 9$$

$$1176425 := (-11 + 7^6 \times \sqrt{4} - 2) \times 5$$

$$1176445 := (1 - (1 - 7^6 + 4) \times \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$1176448 := -1 - 1 + (7^6 - 4) \times (\sqrt{4} + 8)$$

$$1176479 := -1 + (1 + 7^6 - \sqrt{4}) \times (7 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$1176514 := (11 + 7^6 \times 5 + 1) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1176545 := (1 + (1 \times 7^6 + 5) \times \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$1176584 := ((11 + 7^6) \times 5 - 8) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1176594 := ((11 + 7^6) \times 5 - \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1179484 := (1 + 17) \times (-9 + 4^8) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$1179486 := \sqrt{1+1+7} \times (-9 + 4^8) \times 6$$

$$1179489 := (1 + 17) \times (-9 + 4^8) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1179644 := (1 + 1)^7 \times 96^{\sqrt{4}} - 4$$

$$1179649 := 1 + (17 - 9)^6 / \sqrt{4} \times 9$$

$$1179960 := (-1 \times 17 + \sqrt{9^9}) \times 60$$

$$1180979 := -1 + 180 \times \sqrt{9^7} \times 9$$

$$1183248 := 11 \times 83 \times \sqrt{(2+4)^8}$$

$$1183744 := \left(-1 + \sqrt{(1+8 \times (-3+7))^4}\right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1185845 := \left(1 + \sqrt{18^5/8}\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5$$

$$1185921 := (11 \times (8 - 5))^{\sqrt{9+2-1}}$$

$$1188495 := 1 \times \sqrt{(-1+8)^8} \times 495$$

$$1192464 := ((-1 \times 1 + 92) \times \sqrt{4} \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1195741 := (-1 + (1 + \sqrt{9} + 5)^7) / 4 - 1$$

$$1195742 := (-1 + (1 + \sqrt{9} + 5)^7) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2)$$

$$1195744 := (-1 + (1 + \sqrt{9} + 5)^7) / 4 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$1195749 := (1 + (-1 + \sqrt{9^5+7}) / 4) \times 9$$

$$1229844 := (-1 + 22) \times (\sqrt{9} + 8)^4 \times 4$$

$$1236492 := 12 \times \left(\sqrt{(3 \times 6)^4} - \sqrt{9}\right)^2$$

$$1239945 := (-12 + 3^9 \times 9) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)$$

$$1239957 := (1 + 2) \times (-3 - (\sqrt{9} - 9^5) \times 7)$$

$$1239966 := (1^2 - 3^9) \times (\sqrt{9} - 66)$$

$$1243535 := (12^{\sqrt{4}+3} - 5^3) \times 5$$

$$1243775 := (12^{\sqrt{4}+3} - 77) \times 5$$

$$1244130 := (12^4 \times \sqrt{4} - 1) \times 30$$

$$1245448 := (124 \times (5 + 4))^{\sqrt{4}} - 8$$

$$1248520 := \sqrt{(1+2+4)^8} \times 520$$

$$1249857 := 1 - 2^4 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} - 5^7}\right)$$

$$1249924 := (124 \times \sqrt{9 \times 9} + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1252815 := (12 + 5)^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \times 15$$

$$1258884 := (1 \times 2 \times (\sqrt{5^8} - 8 \times 8))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1259469 := -(1 + 2)^5 + ((9 \times \sqrt{4}) \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1259646 := 12 \times (-5 + (\sqrt{9} \times 6)^4) - 6$$

$$1259648 := (-1 + (-2 + 5)^9) \times \sqrt{64} \times 8$$

$$1259649 := 12 \times \left(-5 + (\sqrt{9} \times 6)^4\right) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$1259669 := 1 \times 2 + (-5 + \sqrt{9} \times 6^6) \times 9$$

$$1261899 := (\sqrt{12^6} + \sqrt{1+8}) \times 9^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1265472 := 1 \times 26^{\sqrt{5+4}} \times 72$$

$$1265638 := 1 + 2 \times 6 + 5^6 \times \sqrt{3^8}$$

$$1272384 := ((1 \times 2 \times 72 - 3) \times 8)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1275749 := -1 + 2 \times 7 \times \left(5 \times (7 + \sqrt{4})\right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1277926 := (-1 + 2^{7+7} \times \sqrt{9}) \times 26$$

$$1279396 := 1 + (2 + 7 \times 9) \times 3^{\sqrt{9}+6}$$

$$1279399 := 1 + (2 + 7 \times 9) \times 3^9 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1279744 := 1 \times 2^7 \times (\sqrt{9} + 7)^4 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$1280024 := (12 + 800^2) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1281424 := \left(\sqrt{(1+2)^8} \times 14 - 2\right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1284419 := \left(1 + (2^8 + 4)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times 19$$

$$1285948 := (1+2)^8 \times \sqrt{(5+9)^4} - 8$$

$$1293750 := (12^{\sqrt{9}} - 3) \times 750$$

$$1295029 := (12 + 95 + 02)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1295044 := (1 + 2^9 + 5^{04})^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1295866 := (1 + 2^9 \times 5) \times (\sqrt{8^6} - 6)$$

$$1295999 := -1 + 2 \times \sqrt{9} \times \left(5 \times (9 + \sqrt{9})\right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1296874 := -1 + (2 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times (87 - 4)$$

$$1296875 := (1 \times 2 + \sqrt{9})^6 \times (8 + 75)$$

$$1299066 := -12 + \sqrt{9^9} \times 066$$

$$1299122 := (1 \times 2 + \sqrt{9^{9+1}}) \times 22$$

$$1299669 := ((1+2)^9 + 9) \times 66 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$1299786 := 1 - (2 + \sqrt{9}) \times (\sqrt{9^7} - 8^6)$$

$$1316929 := 1 + 3 \times (1 - 6 + 9^2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1318694 := (-1 + 3^{1+8}) \times (69 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$1326674 := -1 + 3 \times (-2 + 667)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1330995 := (1 \times 330 / \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} - 5$$

$$1330999 := -1 + (330 \times \sqrt{9} / 9)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1334139 := (1 + 33)^4 - 13^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1336336 := (1 + 33)^{-6/3+\sqrt{36}}$$

$$1340964 := \left(\left(1 + 3 \times 4^{\sqrt{09}}\right) \times 6\right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1342898 := 1 + 34^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} + \sqrt{9^8}$$

$$1343479 := \left(1 + \sqrt{3^{\sqrt{4^3}}}\right) \times 4^7 - 9$$

$$1343485 := -1 \times 3 + (43 - \sqrt{4}) \times 8^5$$

$$1343979 := (-1 + (-3 + 43)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 7 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1344555 := (-1 + 3^4) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)^5 - 5$$

$$1345769 := (13 + 4)^5 - (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1347921 := \left(\left(1^3 + \sqrt{4^7}\right) \times 9\right)^2 \times 1$$

$$1349673 := 13 \times (-\sqrt{4} + (9 \times 6 - 7)^3)$$

$$1349699 := 13 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9 \times 6 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1356578 := 13 + 565 \times \sqrt{7^8}$$

$$1358127 := (-1 - 3 + \sqrt{5^8}) \times (1 + 2)^7$$

$$1361916 := (1 + 3 + 61^{\sqrt{9}} + 1) \times 6$$

$$1361962 := (13 + 61^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 6 - 2$$

$$1361964 := (13 + 61^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^4}}$$

$$1362945 := 1 + (3 + 6 + 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 4^5$$

$$1363544 := (-1 + 3^6) \times (3 \times 5^4 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$1364620 := (\sqrt{13^6} + 4) \times 620$$

$$1364649 := 13 \times ((6 \times 4 - 6)^4 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$1364687 := -1 + (3 \times 6)^4 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} + 7} \right)$$

$$1364688 := 13 \times (6 \times 4 - 6)^{\sqrt{8+8}}$$

$$1365797 := 13 + (65 - 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7$$

$$1366874 := -1 + 3 \times (668 + 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1368488 := (-1 + 3 \times \sqrt{6^8} \times 4) \times 88$$

$$1368570 := \sqrt{(1^3 + 6)^8} \times 570$$

$$1369599 := (1 \times 3 + 69 + 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1371992 := (1 + 3) \times (7 \times (1 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} - 2$$

$$1371995 := (1 + 3) \times (7 \times (1 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} - 5$$

$$1375099 := (1 + 3 + 7) \times (50^{\sqrt{9}} + 9)$$

$$1376254 := (-1 + 3 \times 7 \times (6 + 2)^5) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1376259 := 1 \times 3 + 7 \times 6 \times 2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}}$$

$$1379709 := (1 + (3^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 70) \times 9$$

$$1379790 := (1 + (3^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 7) \times 90$$

$$1379998 := 1 + 3^7 \times (9^{\sqrt{9}} - 98)$$

$$1382978 := \sqrt{1+3} + (8^2 \times 9) \times \sqrt{7^8}$$

$$1384371 := 1 \times 3^8 \times (-\sqrt{4} + 3 \times 71)$$

$$1384444 := (13 \times \sqrt{8^4})^{\sqrt{4}} \times \sqrt{4} - 4$$

$$1384448 := (13 \times 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 4 \times 4 \times 8$$

$$1385099 := -1 + 38 \times 50 \times 9^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1387684 := (13 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 + 8)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1388645 := (-1 + (3 + 8) \times 8 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5$$

$$1389150 := (13 + 8)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 150$$

$$1394755 := \left(\sqrt{(1+3)^{9 \times \sqrt{4}} + 7^5} \right) \times 5$$

$$1397491 := -1 + 3^9 \times (74 - \sqrt{9}) - 1$$

$$1397492 := 1 + 3^9 \times (74 - \sqrt{9}) - 2$$

$$1397494 := 1 + 3 \times (-\sqrt{9} + 74) \times 9^4$$

$$1397564 := (1 + 3^9) \times (7 \times 5 + \sqrt{6^4})$$

$$1399530 := (((1 + 3) \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5) \times 30$$

$$1399615 := (-13 + (9 - \sqrt{9})^{6+1}) \times 5$$

$$1399655 := (((1 + 3) \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6 - 5) \times 5$$

$$1399656 := (-1 - 3 + (9 - \sqrt{9})^6 \times 5) \times 6$$

$$1399665 := (-1 \times 3 + (9 - \sqrt{9}) \times 6^6) \times 5$$

$$1399679 := -1 + (-3 + 9 + 9) \times 6^7 / \sqrt{9}$$

$$1399680 := (1 + 3) \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6 \times 80$$

$$1399695 := (((1 + 3) \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6 + \sqrt{9}) \times 5$$

$$1399745 := \left(13 + (9 - \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}}} \right) \times 5$$

$$1399785 := \left(13 + (9 - \sqrt{9})^7 + 8 \right) \times 5$$

$$1404928 := (14 \times 04)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^2}}} \times 8$$

$$1404929 := 1 + (40 + 4 \times 9 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1411766 := \sqrt{1 \times 4} \times (-11 + 7^6 \times 6)$$

$$1412884 := (-1 + 41^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} + 8) / \sqrt{4}$$

$$1414485 := \left(1 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{14}}} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 85$$

$$1417168 := (-1 + (4 - 1)^{7 + \sqrt{16}}) \times 8$$

$$1417176 := (-1 + 4)^{1+7} \times \sqrt{(-1 + 7)^6}$$

$$1417928 := (1 + 417 + \sqrt{9})^2 \times 8$$

$$1419843 := -14 + (1 \times 9 + 8)^{\sqrt{4}+3}$$

$$1419858 := 1 + (-\sqrt{4} + 19)^{8 \times 5/8}$$

$$1419859 := -1^4 + (1 \times 9 + 8)^5 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1419895 := \sqrt{1 \times 4} \times 19 + (8 + 9)^5$$

$$1419898 := 1 \times 41 + (9 + 8)^{-\sqrt{9}+8}$$

$$1428595 := \sqrt{(1 + 4 + 2)^8} \times 595$$

$$1429968 := (\sqrt{1 \times 4} + 29)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6 \times 8$$

$$1431644 := (143 - 1)^{6/\sqrt{4}} / \sqrt{4}$$

$$1437592 := \left(1 + (\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 / 5\right) \times 92$$

$$1439539 := -1 + (\sqrt{4^3} + 9)^5 + 3^9$$

$$1441747 := -1 - 4 + \sqrt{4^{17}} \times (4 + 7)$$

$$1441749 := 1 - 4 + \sqrt{4^{17}} \times (\sqrt{4} + 9)$$

$$1441789 := 1 - 4 + \sqrt{4^{17}} \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$1441794 := \sqrt{1 \times 4} + \sqrt{4^{17}} \times (9 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$1442985 := (1 + 44 \times (-2 + \sqrt{9^8})) \times 5$$

$$1446336 := \left(\sqrt{(1 + 4)^4} + 6\right) \times (3 + 3)^6$$

$$1449453 := (-1 + 4) \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + (9 + \sqrt{4})^5 \times 3\right)$$

$$1449549 := \left(14 + \left((\sqrt{4} + 9)^5 - 4\right)\right) \times 9$$

$$1449655 := \sqrt{14^4} + 9 \times (6 + 5)^5$$

$$1454961 := (-1 + \sqrt{4^5})^4 + 9^6 - 1$$

$$1454962 := (-1 + \sqrt{4^5})^4 + 9^{\sqrt{6^2}}$$

$$1454964 := (-1 + \sqrt{4^5})^4 + 9^6 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$1457999 := -1 + \sqrt{4} \times (5 \times (-7 + 9) \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1459759 := (-1 + \sqrt{4^5})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7^{5-\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1459995 := (1 + 45)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{9} - 9 \times 5$$

$$1468825 := \left(1 + (\sqrt{4} - 68 \times 8)^2\right) \times 5$$

$$1468944 := (1 - 4 + \sqrt{6^8} - \sqrt{9^4})^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1469468 := 14 \times \left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{9}\right)^4 - 6 - 8\right)$$

$$1469657 := (-1 + \sqrt{4^6}) \times \sqrt{9} \times 6^5 - 7$$

$$1469748 := 14 \times (6 + \sqrt{9^7} \times 48)$$

$$1470784 := (-1 + 470) \times \sqrt{(7 \times 8)^4}$$

$$1472328 := \left(\left(-1 + \sqrt{4} \times 72\right) \times 3\right)^2 \times 8$$

$$1474379 := -1 + (4^7 - \sqrt{4}) \times (3 + 7) \times 9$$

$$1474530 := (-1 + 4^7 \times \sqrt{4 + 5}) \times 30$$

$$1474547 := 1 + \sqrt{4} \times (-7 + 45 \times 4^7)$$

$$1474549 := -(1 - 4^7 \times 45) \times \sqrt{4} - 9$$

$$1474562 := (1 + 4^7 \times 45) \times \sqrt{6 - 2}$$

$$1474563 := (1 + \sqrt{4^{7 \times \sqrt{4}}} \times 5 \times 6) \times 3$$

$$1474565 := (1 + 4^7 \times \sqrt{4 + 5} \times 6) \times 5$$

$$1474569 := (1 + 4^7 \times \sqrt{4} \times 5) \times (6 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$1474574 := (1 \times 4^7 \times 45 + 7) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1474739 := -1 + (4^7 + \sqrt{4}) \times (7 + 3) \times 9$$

$$1475472 := \left(1 + (-\sqrt{4} + 7)^5\right) \times 472$$

$$1475496 := \left(-1 + \left((\sqrt{4} + 7) \times 5\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times \sqrt{9^6}$$

$$1475999 := -1^4 + 75 \times (\sqrt{9^9} - \sqrt{9})$$

$$1476384 := (\sqrt{1 \times 4} \times (7 + 6))^3 \times 84$$

$$1479117 := (-1 + 4) \times 79^{\sqrt{1+1+7}}$$

$$1479123 := (\sqrt{1 \times 4} + 79^{1+2}) \times 3$$

$$1479129 := (1 \times 4 + 79^{1+2}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1481537 := (14 \times 8 + \sqrt{-1 + 5})^3 - 7$$

$$1481543 := -1 + \left((\sqrt{4} - 8) \times (1 - 5 \times 4)\right)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1483524 &:= (1^4 - 8 + 35^2)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 1485159 &:= -1 + 4 \times (((8 + 5) \times 1)^5 - \sqrt{9}) \\
 1485164 &:= 1 \times 4 \times ((8 + 5)^{-1+6} - \sqrt{4}) \\
 1485166 &:= (1 + 4 + 8)^5 \times \sqrt{16} - 6 \\
 1485169 &:= (1 + 4 + 8)^5 \times \sqrt{16} - \sqrt{9} \\
 1485184 &:= ((1 + 4 + 8)^5 + \sqrt{1+8}) \times 4 \\
 1486849 &:= 1 + ((\sqrt{4} + 86) \times 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \times \sqrt{9} \\
 1488620 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{(1 + 48)^8} \times 620} \\
 1489450 &:= ((-1 + 4 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{4}) \times 50 \\
 1490446 &:= (1 + (\sqrt{4} \times 90)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 46 \\
 1490492 &:= ((1 + (\sqrt{4} \times (90^{\sqrt{4}}))) \times 92) \\
 1492956 &:= \left(\left(1 - \left((4 \times \sqrt{9})^{2+\sqrt{9}} \right) - 5 \right) \right) \times (-6) \\
 1492964 &:= ((-1) + (((4 \times 9) \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} - 6)) \times 4 \\
 1492986 &:= \left((-1) + \left((\sqrt{4 \times 9} \times 2)^{-\sqrt{9}+8} \right) \right) \times 6 \\
 1492988 &:= ((-1) + (((4 \times 9) \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}})) \times \sqrt{8+8} \\
 1492989 &:= (1 + (-4) \times ((\sqrt{9} - 2) - ((9 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}}))) \\
 1492991 &:= \left((1 \times 4) \times \left((9^2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 1 \right) \\
 1492994 &:= (\sqrt{1 \times 4} + (((9^2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 4)) \\
 1492995 &:= (-((1 - 4)) + ((\sqrt{9} \times 2) \times ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5))) \\
 1493248 &:= ((1 + (4 \times (9^3) \times 2))) \times \sqrt{4^8} \\
 1493497 &:= (((1 + (4 \times (9^3)))) \times \sqrt{4^9}) - 7 \\
 1494364 &:= (((14^{\sqrt{9}}) + ((4 \times 3)^6)) / \sqrt{4}) \\
 1494369 &:= ((1 + \sqrt{4^9}) \times ((4 \times (3^6)) - \sqrt{9}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1495480 &:= ((14^{\sqrt{9}}) \times ((5^4) - 80)) \\
 1495908 &:= \left((-((1 - 4))^9) \times (-5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{08}}}) \right) \\
 1495912 &:= ((1 + (\sqrt{49^5})) \times (91 - 2)) \\
 1498174 &:= ((-1) \times \sqrt{4}) + (((9 \times 8) \times 17)^{\sqrt{4}}) \\
 1498749 &:= -1 + \sqrt{(-4 + 9)^8} \times (7^4 - \sqrt{9}) \\
 1499964 &:= \left(\left(\left((1 + 49)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 1499995 &:= \left(\left((1 + 49)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (9 + \sqrt{9}) \right) - 5 \\
 1504278 &:= ((1 + (5^{04})) \times (2 + \sqrt{7^8})) \\
 1517824 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(1 + 5)^{1+7}} - (8^2) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 1518742 &:= (((15^{\sqrt{18+7}}) - 4) \times 2) \\
 1518749 &:= (-1) + (\sqrt{5 - 1} \times ((8 + 7)^{-4+9})) \\
 1518762 &:= (((15^{\sqrt{18+7}}) + 6) \times 2) \\
 1525488 &:= ((1 + \sqrt{5^2 \times 5}) \times 488) \\
 1526415 &:= (-1 + 5 \times 2^6)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 15 \\
 1529476 &:= \left((15 - 2) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{4}}}} + ((7^6)) \right) \right) \\
 1535979 &:= \left(\left((1 + (5 \times 3)) \times 5 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 7 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 1535995 &:= \left(\left((1 + (5 \times 3)) \times 5 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 5 \\
 1535999 &:= (-1) + \left(\left((5^3) - (5 \times 9) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 1539456 &:= ((1 + ((5 \times 3)^{\sqrt{9}})) \times 456) \\
 1539648 &:= (((1 + 5) + (3 \times 9)) \times (6^{-\sqrt{4}+8})) \\
 1542564 &:= \left(\left(\left((1 + 5)^4 \right) + 2 \right) - 56 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 1545692 &:= \left(\left(\left((1 \times 5) + \sqrt{4} \right)^5 \right) - 6 \right) \times 92 \\
 1546875 &:= (\sqrt{15^4} \times 6875)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1546974 &:= \left(1 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4 \times 6}}\right) \times 9 \times (7 + 4) \\
 1547666 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(\sqrt{(5 + 4)^{7+6}}\right) - (6^6)\right)\right) \\
 1548287 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(- (54) \times \left(\left(8^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}}\right) \times 7\right)\right)\right) \\
 1548397 &:= \left(1 - \left(- \left(\left(5^4\right) + 83\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9^7}\right) \\
 1548645 &:= \left(\sqrt{\left(1 \times 5 + \sqrt{4}\right)^8} \times 645\right) \\
 1548802 &:= \left(\sqrt{-1 + 5} + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(880^2\right)\right)\right) \\
 1548804 &:= \left(- \left((1 - 5)\right) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(880^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right)\right) \\
 1558974 &:= \left(\left(1 + \left(5^5\right)\right) - \left(- (8) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7\right)^4\right)\right)\right) \\
 1559584 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left((1 - 5) - 5\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \left(5^8\right)\right) \times (-4)\right) \\
 1560893 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (1) + \sqrt{5^6}\right) - 08\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3\right) \\
 1560894 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (1) + \sqrt{5^6}\right) - 08\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 1560896 &:= \left(\left(- (1) + \sqrt{5^6}\right) - 08\right)^{9-6} \\
 1560899 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (1) + \sqrt{5^6}\right) - 08\right)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 1562468 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 + \left(5^{6+2}\right)\right) \times 4\right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}\right) \\
 1562479 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 \times 5\right)^{6+2}\right) \times 4\right) + \left(- (7) \times \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 1562482 &:= \left(1 - \left(\left(\left(5^{6+2}\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) - 8\right)\right) \times (-2) \\
 1562489 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(1 \times 5\right)^{6+2}\right) \times 4\right) - 8\right) - \sqrt{9} \\
 1562516 &:= \left(- \left(\left(1 - \left(\left(5^{6+2}\right) + 5\right)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{16}\right) \\
 1562519 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(- \left(\left(\left(5^{6+2}\right) + 5\right)\right) \times \left(- (1) - \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \\
 1562548 &:= (-1 + 5) \times \left(6 \times 2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4 \times 8}}\right) \\
 1562644 &:= \left(- \left(\left(1 \times 5\right)^{6+2}\right) - \sqrt{6^4}\right) \times (-4) \\
 1562748 &:= \left(- \left((1 - 5)\right) \times \left(62 + \left(\left(7 - \sqrt{4}\right)^8\right)\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1567744 &:= \left(\left(1 + \left(\sqrt{5^6} \times \left(- (7 \times 7)\right)\right)\right) \times \left(- \left(4^4\right)\right)\right) \\
 1572159 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((72 + 1) - 5\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right)\right) \\
 1572544 &:= \left(- \left((1 - 5)\right) \times \left(7 + \left(\left(2 + \left(5^4\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right)\right) \\
 1572696 &:= \left(\left(\left((1 - 5) \times 7\right) + \left(\left(2^6\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times 6\right) \\
 1572834 &:= \left(\left(1 + 5\right) \times \left(- \left((7 - 2)\right) + \left(\left(8^3\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right)\right) \\
 1572846 &:= (1 + 5) \times \left(- \sqrt{7 + 2} + \sqrt{\sqrt{8^4 \times 6}}\right) \\
 1572869 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(\left((5 - 7) - \left(2 \times \left(8^6\right)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\
 1572882 &:= \left(\left(1 + 5\right) \times \left(\sqrt{7 + 2} + \left(\left(8^{8-2}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1572894 &:= \left(\left(1 + 5\right) \times \left(7 + \left(\left(\sqrt{\left(2 \times 8\right)^9} - \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1572898 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 + 5\right) \times \left(7 + \left(\sqrt{\left(2 \times 8\right)^9}\right)\right)\right) - 8\right) \\
 1572899 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(\left(5 + 7\right) \times \left(- \left(\left(2^{8+9}\right) - \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1572906 &:= \left(\left(1 + 5\right) \times \left(7 + \left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9} \times 06}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1574441 &:= \left(\left(- (15) + \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{4}\right)^4\right)\right) \times 41\right) \\
 1579294 &:= \left(\left(- \left((1 + 5)\right) + \left(7^{\sqrt{9} + 2}\right)\right) \times 94\right) \\
 1582528 &:= \left(\left(1 + \sqrt{5^8}\right) \times 2528\right) \\
 1582564 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{\left(1 + 5\right)^8} - \left(\left(2^5\right) + 6\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 1584990 &:= \left(\left(- (1) - \sqrt{\left(5 \times 8\right)^4}\right) \times (-990)\right) \\
 1585866 &:= (1 + 5)^8 - \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8 \times 6}}} \times 6 \\
 1586304 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\left(1 + 5\right)^{8 \times 6}}} \times (30 + 4)} \\
 1589247 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + (92)}}\right) \times \left(- \left(4^7\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1592644 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((1 - 5) \times 9\right) + 2\right) + \left(6^4\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1593472 &:= \left((-1) - \left((5 \times \sqrt{9})^3 \right) \right) \times (-472) \\
 1593596 &:= \left(\sqrt{-1+5} - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((3^5) - (9^6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1593949 &:= \left(1 - \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{9}}) - \left((3 \times 9)^4 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 1593998 &:= \left(-1 + \left(\left((5-9) + (3^9) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \right) \\
 1594196 &:= \left((1-5) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times (41 - (9^6)) \right) \right) \\
 1594296 &:= \left(-15 - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((2 - (9^6)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1594299 &:= \left(\left((1^5) + \left((9^{4+2}) - 9 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 1594308 &:= \left(-15 + \left(\sqrt{9\sqrt{4} + 3 + 08} \right) \right) \\
 1594309 &:= \left(1 - \left(\left(-5 + \left(\sqrt{9^{4 \times 3}} \right) \right) \times (0 - \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 1594311 &:= \left((1+5) - \left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left((3^{11}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1594312 &:= \left((1^5) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(4 - (3^{12}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1594314 &:= \left(-((1 \times 5)) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{4 \times 3 + 1}} \right) - 4 \right) \right) \\
 1594316 &:= \left(-\left((1^5) \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{4 \times 3 + 1}} \right) - 6 \right) \right) \\
 1594317 &:= \left((1^5) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{4 \times 3 + 1}} \right) - 7 \right) \right) \\
 1594318 &:= \left(-\left((15 - (9^{4+3})) \right) / \sqrt{1+8} \right) \\
 1594319 &:= \left((1 \times 5) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{4 \times 3 + 1}} \right) - 9 \right) \right) \\
 1594322 &:= \left((1^5) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{4+3^2}} \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 1594324 &:= \left((1^5) + \left(\sqrt{9^{4+3+2+4}} \right) \right) \\
 1594326 &:= \left(15 - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(4 - \left((3^2)^6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1594327 &:= \left(-((1-5)) - \left(\sqrt{9^4} \times \left(- (3^{2+7}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1594328 &:= \left((1 \times 5) - \left(-\left((9^4) \right) \times \sqrt{3^{2+8}} \right) \right) \\
 1594329 &:= \left(\sqrt{(1^5 \times 9)^{4 \times 3}} + 2 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 1594332 &:= \left((1+5) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^{4 \times 3}} \right) + 3 \right) / 2 \right) \right) \\
 1594333 &:= \left((1^5) - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^{4 \times 3}} \right) + 3 \right) \times (-3) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1594336 &:= \left((1^5) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left(4 + \left((3 \times 3)^6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1594338 &:= \left(15 - \left(\left(\sqrt{9\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \left(- (3^{3+8}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1594339 &:= \left(-((1-5)) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left(4 + (3^{3+9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1594341 &:= \left(\left(-((1+5)) - \left(\sqrt{9^{4 \times 3}} \right) \right) \times \left(- (4-1) \right) \right) \\
 1594343 &:= \left(-1 + \left(\left(5 + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{4 \times 3}} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \\
 1594347 &:= \left((1+5) - \left(-9 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + (3^{4+7}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1594353 &:= \left(15 - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^{4 \times 3}} \right) + 5 \right) \times (-3) \right) \right) \\
 1594356 &:= \left(15 - \left(-9 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((3^{5+6}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1594359 &:= \left(\left(-((1-5)) + \left(\sqrt{9^{-4+3 \times 5}} \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 1594367 &:= \left(\left((1 + (5 \times 9)) - \sqrt{4} \right) + \left((3^{6+7}) \right) \right) \\
 1594369 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(5 - \left(-\left((9^4) \right) \times \sqrt{3^6} \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 1594954 &:= \left((1+5) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{4+9}} \right) + \left((5^4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1595538 &:= \sqrt{(1^5 \times 9)^5} \times (5 + 3^8) \\
 1595979 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(-1+5)^9} + 5 \right) \times \left(9 \times (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \\
 1596475 &:= \left(\left((1^5) - 96 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - (7^5) \right) \right) \\
 1597243 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(-5 - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^7} + 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) / (-3) \right) \right) \\
 1597964 &:= \left(\left((1 \times 5) + \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times \sqrt{9^6} - 4 \right) \\
 1597968 &:= \left(\left((1 \times 5) + \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9}^{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}} \right) \right) \\
 1597969 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times \left(9^{-6+9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 1598697 &:= \left(\sqrt{-1+5} + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8 \times 6}}}} \right) \times \sqrt{9^7} \\
 1601613 &:= \left(\left(\left(-((1-60)) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{16}} \right) - 1 \right)^3 \right) \\
 1608670 &:= \sqrt{(1+6)^{08}} \times 670
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1613475 := \left((\sqrt{16} - 1) + \left(3 \times \left((\sqrt{4} \times 7)^5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1617984 := \left((((161 + 7) - 9) \times 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$1625039 := \left((1 + (6 \times 2)) \times \left((50^3) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$1628646 := \left(\left(\left(((1 + 6) + 2) + \sqrt{8^6} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$1629697 := \left(\left(((1 + 6)^{2+\sqrt{9}}) - 6 \right) \times 97 \right)$$

$$1632961 := \left(1 - \left(\left((6^{\sqrt{9}})^2 \right) \times (- (36 - 1)) \right) \right)$$

$$1632966 := \left((1 \times 6) + \left((32 + \sqrt{9}) \times (6^6) \right) \right)$$

$$1633284 := \left((1 \times 6^3 - 3) \times (-2 + 8) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$1633929 := \left(- \left(\left(1 - \left(\left((6 + 3)^3 + 9 \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$1638400 := \left(\left(16^{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}} \right) \times 400 \right)$$

$$1643031 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}} - ((4 \times 30)) \right) \right) \right)^3 - 1 \right)$$

$$1643032 := \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}} - ((4 \times 30)) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{3^2}} \right)$$

$$1643034 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}} - ((4 \times 30)) \right) \right) \right)^3 + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$1644685 := \sqrt{(1 + 6)^{4+4}} \times 685$$

$$1644785 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^4})^4 \right) - (7 \times (8^5)) \right)$$

$$1646764 := \left((1 + 6) \times \left(- (46) - \left(- \left((7^6) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1646847 := \left((- (1) + (6^{\sqrt{4+6}})) - (8^{-\sqrt{4+7}}) \right)$$

$$1646848 := \left(((1 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4+6}}) - ((8^4) \times 8) \right)$$

$$1646849 := \left(1 + \left((6^{\sqrt{4+6}}) - (8^{-4+9}) \right) \right)$$

$$1646885 := \left((1 + \sqrt{6^4}) + \left(((6^8) - (8^5)) \right) \right)$$

$$1647070 := \left(- (16) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((7^{07}) + 0 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1647071 := \left(- (16) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (7^{07}) \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1647073 := \left(- (16) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (7^{07}) \right) + 3 \right) \right)$$

$$1647074 := \left(- (16) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left((7^{07}) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$1647076 := \left(- (16) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (7^{07}) \right) + 6 \right) \right)$$

$$1647077 := \left(- (16) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (7^{07}) \right) + 7 \right) \right)$$

$$1647079 := \left(1 + \left(- \left((6 \times (4 - (7^{07}))) \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$1647081 := \left((1 - 6) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times (7^{08-1}) \right) \right)$$

$$1647086 := \left(((1 + 6) \times \sqrt{4}) \times (7^{0 \times 8 + 6}) \right)$$

$$1647092 := \left(\left(\left((- (1) + \sqrt{64})^7 \right) + \sqrt{09} \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$1647094 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}} \times \left(4 + (7^{09-\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right)$$

$$1647184 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(1 + 6)^4} + (7^{-1+8}) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$1647342 := \left(\sqrt{16^4} + \left((7^{3+4}) \times 2 \right) \right)$$

$$1647576 := \left(((1 + 6) \times \sqrt{4}) \times \left((7 \times 5) + (7^6) \right) \right)$$

$$1647749 := \left(- (1) - \left(- (6) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7) \times 7 + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1647776 := \left(\sqrt{16} + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((7^7) + \sqrt{7^6} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1647779 := \left((1 + 6) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((7^7) + (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1647799 := \left((- (16) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (7^7) \right) \right)) + (9^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$1649286 := \left(\left((1 + 64)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (2^8) \right) \times 6$$

$$1654877 := \left(- \left((1 - (6^5)) \right) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(8 + (7^7) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1656289 := \left(1 - \left(- \left((6^5) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{6^{-2+8}} - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1656396 := \left(\left(- (1) - \left(- \left((6 - 5) - (6^3) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) / (-6)$$

$$1658864 := \left(- (16) + \left(5 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{8+8} \times 6 \right)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1658880 := \left((((1 + 6) + 5)^{\sqrt{8+8}}) \times 80 \right)$$

$$1658884 := \left(\sqrt{16} + \left(\left(5 \times \left(((8 + 8) + 8)^4 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1658944 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(16 + \sqrt{58} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 1658945 &:= \left(1 \times 65 \right) + \left(\left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^4 \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 1659367 &:= \left(1 - \left(6 \times \left(\left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^3 \right) - \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1659932 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(6^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(\sqrt{9}^{3^2} \right) \right) \right) \\
 1659933 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 \times 6 \right)^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(\left(9 \times 3 \right)^3 \right) \right) \\
 1659934 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(6^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(\sqrt{9}^{\sqrt{3^4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 1659968 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 + 6 \right) \times 5 \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) - \left(6^8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1663489 &:= 1 + \left(-6 + 63 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times \left(8^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 1664065 &:= \left(1 - \left(\left(\sqrt{6^6} - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(0 - \left(6^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1664136 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(- (1) + \sqrt{6^6} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 1 \right) \times 36 \right) \\
 1666494 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(1 + 6 \right) \times 6 \right) \times 6 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(9^4 \right) \right) \\
 1666682 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(\left(\left(6/6 \right) - 6 \right) + \sqrt{6^8} \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 1668297 &:= \left(1 - \left(\left(\left(66 - (8/2) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-7) \right) \right) \\
 1668695 &:= \sqrt{\left(1^6 + 6 \right)^8} \times 695 \\
 1668968 &:= - \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(1 - 6 \right) \times 6 \right) + 8 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(6^8 \right) \right) \\
 1669264 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 - \left(\left(6 \times 6 \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \times \left(2 - 6 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 1674428 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(1^6 \right) - 7 \right) \right)^4 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) - 8 \right) \right) \\
 1676296 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (1) + \sqrt{6^7 \times 6} \right)^2 \right) - \sqrt{9^6} \right) \\
 1676694 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) - \sqrt{\left(6 \times 9 \right)^4} \right) \\
 1676866 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) - \sqrt{\left(8 + 6 \right)^6} \right) \\
 1676868 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{16} + \left(\left(\sqrt{7^6} \times 8 \right) - \left(6^8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1678368 &:= \left(- \left(\left(16 \times 78 \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{36^8} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1679136 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9^{1+3}} \right) \times (-6) \right) \\
 1679226 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-22) \right) \right) \times (-6) \right) \\
 1679268 &:= \left(- \left(\left(1 + 6 \right) \right) - \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(2 + \left(6^8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1679279 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times 2 \right) - \left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 1679346 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(1 \times 6 \right)^7 \right) - \left(9 \times \left(3 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 1679364 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{16} \times \left(- \left(7 \times 9 \right) \right) \right) + \left(36^4 \right) \right) \\
 1679376 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(1 \times 6 \right)^7 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) + 37 \right) \times (-6) \\
 1679449 &:= -167 + \sqrt{\left(9 \times 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4 \times \sqrt{9}}}} \\
 1679466 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right) + 6 \right) \right) \times (-6) \\
 1679467 &:= \left(1 - \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- (7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(4 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1679484 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{16^7}} - \left(\left(\sqrt{\left(9 \times 4 \right)^8} \right) - 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1679488 &:= -\sqrt{\sqrt{16^7}} + \sqrt{\left(9 \times 4 \right)^{\sqrt{8 \times 8}}} \\
 1679494 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(4^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 1679496 &:= \left(- \left(\left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9 \times 49} \right) \times (-6) \\
 1679498 &:= \left(- \left(\left(1 + \left(\left(6 + 7 \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{4 \times 9^8} \right) \right) \\
 1679512 &:= \left(\left(1 + \left(- \left(\left(6^7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 51 \right) \right) \times (-2) \\
 1679514 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(1 \times 6 \right)^7 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 51 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 1679523 &:= \left(\left(- (1) + \left(\left(- \left(\left(6^7 \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times 5 \right) \right) \times (-2) \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 1679529 &:= \left(- \left(\left(1 - \left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) - 9 \right) - 5 \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 1679534 &:= \left(\left(1 + \left(\left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) - 9 \right) - 5 \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 1679548 &:= \left(- \left(\left(1 + 67 \right) \right) + \left(\left(9 - \sqrt{5+4} \right)^8 \right) \right) \\
 1679558 &:= \left(1^6 - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{9+5}} - 58 \\
 1679561 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - 5 \right) \times 6 \right) - 1 \\
 1679561 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(6^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(7 - 61 \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1679564 := \left(\left(\left(\left(- \left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - 5 \right) \times 6 \right) + \sqrt{4}$$

$$1679567 := \left(\left(\left(\left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - 5 \right) \times 6 \right) - 7$$

$$1679574 := \left(- \left(\left(1 \times 6 \right) \times 7 \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(5 + 7 \right) \right)^4 \right) \right)$$

$$1679584 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(5 + 8 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1679588 := \left(\left(\sqrt{16} \times \left(-7 \right) \right) + \left(\left(\left(9 + 5 \right) - 8 \right)^8 \right) \right)$$

$$1679589 := \left(\left(- \left(1 \right) + \left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) \times \sqrt{9-5} \right) - 8 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$1679592 := \left(\left(\left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(\left(5 - 9 \right) - 2 \right) \right)$$

$$1679594 := \left(\left(\left(\left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(5 + 9 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$1679598 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(1 \times 6 \right)^7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(- \left(\left(5 + 9 \right) - 8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679599 := \left(1 + \left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(5 + \left(9/9 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679602 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right) - 02$$

$$1679604 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(- \left(6 + \left(0 \times 4 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679610 := \left(- \left(\left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9 \times \left(-6 + 10 \right)} \right)$$

$$1679614 := \left(\left(\left(\left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right) - 14 \right)$$

$$1679619 := \left(\left(\left(\left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right) - \left(1 \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$1679620 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right) - \left(20 \right)$$

$$1679625 := \left(\left(\left(\left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right) + \left(\left(2 - 5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679627 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(1 \times 6 \right)^7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{6^2} \right) - 7 \right)$$

$$1679629 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right) - \left(2 + 9 \right)$$

$$1679630 := \left(- \left(1 \right) + \left(\left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \right) - \left(3 + 0 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679631 := \left(\left(\left(\left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right) + \left(3 \times 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1679634 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(1 \times 6 \right)^7 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(6 - \left(3 \times 4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679636 := \left(- \left(1 \right) - \left(\left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right) - \sqrt{3+6} \right) \right)$$

$$1679639 := \left(- \left(1 \right) + \left(\left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \right) - \left(\left(3 - 9 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679640 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(- \left(6 + \left(4 \times 0 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679641 := \left(\left(\left(\left(- \left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) - 1$$

$$1679643 := \left(1 + \left(\left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \right) + \sqrt{4^3} \right) \right)$$

$$1679644 := \left(\left(\left(1 + 6 \right) \times \sqrt{7+9} \right) + \left(\left(6^{4+4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679645 := \left(\left(1 + \left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$1679647 := \left(\left(- \left(1 \right) + \left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times 7 \right) \right)$$

$$1679649 := \left(\left(\left(\left(1 \times 6 \right) \times 7 \right) - 9 \right) + \left(6^{\sqrt{4^9}} \right) \right)$$

$$1679653 := \left(\left(\sqrt{16} \times 7 \right) + \left(9 + \left(6^{5+3} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679654 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(1 \times 6 \right)^7 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right) + \left(\left(5 \times 4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679694 := \left(\left(\left(1 + \left(\left(6^7 \right) + 9 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) + \left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$1679695 := \left(\left(\left(1^6 \right) \times 79 \right) + \left(6^{\sqrt{9}+5} \right) \right)$$

$$1679696 := \left(- \left(\left(1 - \left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) + 9 \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{96}} \right)$$

$$1679697 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(1 \times 6 \right)^7 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right) + \left(\left(9 \times 7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679698 := \left(\left(1 + \left(6^{-7+9+6} \right) \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{98}} \right)$$

$$1679728 := \left(\left(16 \times 7 \right) + \left(\left(9 - \sqrt{7+2} \right)^8 \right) \right)$$

$$1679742 := \left(\left(\left(\left(1 \times 6 \right)^7 \right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-7 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(4 + 2 \right) \right)$$

$$1679743 := \left(1 - \left(\left(- \left(\left(6^7 \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} \times 3 \right) \right)$$

$$1679748 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-7 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - 8 \right) \right)$$

$$1679762 := \left(\left(\left(\left(1 - \left(6^7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 76 \right) \times \left(-2 \right) \right)$$

$$1679766 := \left(1 + 6^7 + \sqrt{\left(9 + 7 \right)} \times 6 \right) \times 6$$

$$1679768 := \left(- \left(1 - 6 \right) + \left(\left(\left(- \left(7 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-7 \right) \right) + \left(6^8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679772 := \left(\left(- \left(1 \right) + \left(\left(- \left(\left(6^7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 77 \right) \right) \times \left(-2 \right) \right)$$

$$1679796 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(1 \times 6 \right)^7 \right) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right)$$

$$1679856 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(1 + \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(8 + 5 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right)$$

$$1679861 := 1 + 6^8 + \sqrt{9+7} \times 61$$

$$1679868 := -\sqrt{16} + (-7 + 9)^8 + 6^8$$

$$1679946 := \left(\left((1 + (6^7)) + (9 \times \sqrt{9 \times 4}) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$1679968 := \left(\left((1^6 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} + (9 + (6^8)) \right) \right)$$

$$1679976 := \left(\left(- \left((1 \times 6)^7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) - (9 \times 7) \right) \times (-6)$$

$$1680344 := \left(- \left((1 - (6^8)) \right) + (03^{\sqrt{4+4}}) \right)$$

$$1680346 := 1 + 6^8 + \sqrt{\sqrt{03^{4 \times 6}}}$$

$$1680695 := \left(- \left((1 - (6^8)) \right) + \left((06^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$1680700 := \left(\sqrt{(1 + 6)^8} \times 0700 \right)$$

$$1680946 := -1 + 6^8 + \sqrt{(09 + \sqrt{4})^6}$$

$$1681346 := \left((1 + ((6^8) + 1)) + \sqrt{(3 \times 4)^6} \right)$$

$$1681664 := \left(((1 \times 6)^8) + \left((\sqrt{16^6}) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$1681665 := \left((1 + (6^8)) + \sqrt{\sqrt{16^{6+5}}} \right)$$

$$1681676 := \left((1 + ((6^8) + 1)) + (6 \times \sqrt{7^6}) \right)$$

$$1681797 := \left(\left(\left((1 \times 6)^8 + 1 \right) - 7 \right) + \sqrt{9^7} \right)$$

$$1682128 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) - \sqrt{(1 + 2)^8} \right)$$

$$1682146 := \left(\left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 + 1 \right) - \sqrt{4^6} \right) \right)$$

$$1682154 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) - (1 + 54) \right)$$

$$1682155 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + ((1 - 55)) \right)$$

$$1682167 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) - ((1 \times 6) \times 7) \right)$$

$$1682175 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + ((1 - (7 \times 5))) \right)$$

$$1682203 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) - (2 \times 03) \right)$$

$$1682204 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) - (20/4) \right)$$

$$1682205 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) - (20/5) \right)$$

$$1682207 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) - (2 + (0 \times 7)) \right)$$

$$1682227 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + (2 \times (2 + 7)) \right)$$

$$1682229 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + (2 + (2 \times 9)) \right)$$

$$1682231 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + (23 - 1) \right)$$

$$1682232 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + \sqrt{23^2} \right)$$

$$1682233 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + ((2^3) \times 3) \right)$$

$$1682234 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + \sqrt{(2 + 3)^4} \right)$$

$$1682236 := \left(\left((1 + (6^{8/2}))^2 \right) + \sqrt{3^6} \right)$$

$$1682241 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + (2^{4+1}) \right)$$

$$1682258 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{(2 + 5)^8}} \right)$$

$$1682292 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + ((2 + (9^2))) \right)$$

$$1682459 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + (\sqrt{4} \times (5^{\sqrt{9}})) \right)$$

$$1682686 := \left(\left((1 \times 6)^8 - 2 \right) - (-6 \times \sqrt{8^6}) \right)$$

$$1682689 := \left(- \left((1 - ((6^8) + 2)) \right) + (6 \times (8^{\sqrt{9}})) \right)$$

$$1682834 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + (8 - 3^4) \right)$$

$$1682934 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + (((9^3) - 4)) \right)$$

$$1682938 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^2 \right) + (9 \times \sqrt{3^8}) \right)$$

$$1683684 := \left(- \left((1 - (6^8)) \right) - \sqrt{3^6} \right) + (8^4)$$

$$1683712 := \left(((1 \times 6)^8) + \left(\sqrt{(-3 + 7)^{12}} \right) \right)$$

$$1684396 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + (3 \times \sqrt{9^6}) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1684735 &:= \left(- \left((1 - (6^8)) \right) + \left(\sqrt{4^{7+3}} \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 1684797 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(1 \times 6)^8} + \sqrt{4} \right)^{-7+9} \right) - 7 \right) \right) \\
 1684804 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(1 \times 6)^8} + \sqrt{4} \right)^{8/04} \right) \right) \\
 1684805 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(\sqrt{6^8} + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{80/5}} \right) \right) \\
 1684953 &:= \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{6^8})^{\sqrt{4}} + ((9+5)^3) \right) \right) \\
 1685159 &:= \left((((1+6) \times 85) \times 1) / 5 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1685449 &:= \left((1 + (6^8)) + \left((5+4) \times \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 1687402 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(\sqrt{6^8} + (7-4) \right)^{02} \right) \right) \\
 1687531 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{16} \times (8 + (75^3)) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 1687532 &:= \left(\sqrt{16} \times (8 + (75^{\sqrt{3^2}})) \right) \\
 1687534 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{16} \times (8 + (75^3)) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 1689986 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{16} \times (-8) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \times 86 \right) \\
 1692737 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 2 \right)^7 \right) + (3^7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1695456 &:= \left(\left((169 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 56 \right) \\
 1696464 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{16} + (9 + (6^4)) \right) \times (6^4) \right) \\
 1697684 &:= - \left(\left(\left(- ((1-6))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left((7 + \sqrt{6^8})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 1699298 &:= \left(\left(- (1) + \left(- ((6-9)^9) \right) \right) + \left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^8 \right) \right) \\
 1699299 &:= \left(\left((16 \times 9) \times 9 \right)^2 + \left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \\
 1699445 &:= \left(\left(\left(- ((1 - (6 \times 9))) \times (9 + \sqrt{4}) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 1707229 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(70 \times (7 + 22)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 1714995 &:= \left(\left(- (1) + \left((7 \times ((1^4) + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times 5 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1716715 &:= \left(\left((1 \times 7)^{\sqrt{16}} \right) \times 715 \right) \\
 1721344 &:= \left(\left(((1+7) \times 2) \times (1 + (3^4)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 1724968 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((1+7)^2 + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 6 \right) - 8 \right) \\
 1727950 &:= \left(\left(- \left((1+7) - (2^7) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 50 \right) \\
 1727964 &:= \left(\left(- \left((1+7) - (2^7) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{6^4} \right) \\
 1727979 &:= \left(\left(- \left((1+7) - (2^7) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} + \left(- (7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 1727983 &:= \left(- (17) + \left(\left(- ((2-7) \times \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right)^3 \right) \right) \\
 1727984 &:= \left(\left(- \left((1+7) - (2^7) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - (8 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 1727986 &:= \left(\left(- \left((1+7) - (2^7) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - (8+6) \right) \\
 1727989 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((1+7) - (2^7) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 1727991 &:= \left(\left(- \left((1+7) - (2^7) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - (9 \times 1) \right) \\
 1727993 &:= \left(- ((1 \times 7)) + \left((2 \times ((7 \times 9) - \sqrt{9}))^3 \right) \right) \\
 1727994 &:= \left(\left(- \left((1+7) - (2^7) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9 \times 4} \right) \\
 1727995 &:= \left(\left((1-7) + ((2 \times 7) \times 9) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 \right) \\
 1727999 &:= \left(\left(- \left((1+7) - (2^7) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - (9/9) \right) \\
 1728720 &:= \left(\left((1 \times 7)^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \right) \times 720 \right) \\
 1744496 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left((7^4) - 4 \right) - 4 \right) \times \sqrt{9^6} \right) \\
 1747684 &:= \left(\left(\left((17 + \sqrt{4}) + 7 \right) + \sqrt{6^8} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 1747692 &:= \left((1+7) + \left(\left(\sqrt{(4+7)^6} - 9 \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 1747928 &:= \left((17-4) \times \left((7^{\sqrt{9}+2}) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 1749438 &:= \left(\left(- \left((1 - (7^4)) \times 9 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{3^8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1749579 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(1 - \left(7^4 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9^5} - 7 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$1749595 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(1 - \left(7^4 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9^5 \times 9} - 5 \right)$$

$$1754460 := \left(\left(\left(175 - 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 60 \right)$$

$$1755899 := \left(- (1) + \left(\left((7 + 5) - \left(58^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times (-9) \right) \right)$$

$$1755999 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(1 - \left((7 \times 5) \times 5 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / \sqrt{9} - 9 \right)$$

$$1763584 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(17 - 6 \right)^3 + 5 \right) - 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$1764495 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(1 \times 7 \right)^6 - \left(4 \times 4 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$1764595 := \left(\left(1 - \left(\left(\left(\left(7^6 \right) - 4 \right) - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$1764615 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(1 \times 7 \right)^6 - \sqrt{4} \right) - 6 \right) \times 15 \right)$$

$$1764674 := \left(- (1) + \left(- \left(\left(\left(7^6 \right) - 4 \right) \right) \times \left(- \left((6 + 7) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1764720 := \left(- \left(\left(1 - \left(7^6 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left((7 - 20) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1764729 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(1 \times 7 \right)^6 \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right) - 2 \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1764731 := \left(\left(\left(1 - \left(- \left(\left(7^6 \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (-3) - 1 \right)$$

$$1764732 := \left(- (1) + \left(\left(- \left(\left(7^6 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \times 3 \right) \right) - 2 \right) \right)$$

$$1764733 := \left(1 + \left(\left(- \left(\left(7^6 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \times 3 \right) \right) - 3 \right) \right)$$

$$1764738 := \left(\left(1 + \left(- \left(\left(7^6 \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}} \right)$$

$$1764739 := \left(1 - \left(\left(- \left(\left(7^6 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \times (-3) \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$1764764 := \left(- (1) + \left(\left(7 + \sqrt{64} \right) \times \left(\left(7^6 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1764796 := \left(1 + \left(- \left(\left(\left(7^6 \right) + 4 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(- (7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1765093 := \left(- (17) \times \left(- (6) - \left(\left(50 - \sqrt{9} \right)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1765559 := \left(- (1) - \left(- \left(\left(\left(7^6 \right) + 55 \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$1765763 := \left(- (1) - \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(7^6 \right) \times 5 \right) \right) - \sqrt{7^6} \right) \times 3 \right) \right)$$

$$1766241 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\left(17 - 6 \right)^6 - 2} \right)^{\sqrt{4 \times 1}} \right)$$

$$1766455 := \left(\left(- (1) - \left(\sqrt{7^6} \times \left(6 + \left(4^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$1769094 := \left(- \left((1 - 7) \right) \times \left(\left(\left(6 \times 90 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$1769464 := \left(- \left((1 + 7) \right) - \left(\left(\left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(- \left(4^6 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$1769465 := \left(- \left((1 \times 7) \right) - \left(- \left(\left(6 \times 9 \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 6 \right)^5 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1769469 := \left(\left(\left(\left((1 + 7) \times 6 \right) \times 9 \right) \times \left(4^6 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$1769474 := \left(- \left(\left(\left(\left(1 - 7 \right) - 6 \right) \times 9 \right) \times \left(4^7 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4}$$

$$1769478 := \left(- \left((1 - 7) \right) - \left(- \left(\left(6 \times 9 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4^{7+8}} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1769499 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\left(1 + 7 \right)^6 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / (-4) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-9) \right)$$

$$1769648 := \left(176 + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} \times \left(4^8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1771496 := \left(- \left(\left((1 - 7) + 71 \right) \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 9 \right)^6 \right) \right)$$

$$1771544 := \left(- (17) + \left(\left((7 - 1) + 5 \right)^{\sqrt{4+4}} \right) \right)$$

$$1771939 := \left(1 + \left(\sqrt{7^{7+1}} \times \left(\left(9^3 \right) + 9 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1776740 := \left(\left(- \left((1 \times 7) \right) \times \sqrt{7^6} \right) \times (-740) \right)$$

$$1778743 := \left(1 + \left(\left(7 - \sqrt{7^8} \right) \times (-743) \right) \right)$$

$$1784694 := \left(- (17) \times \left(\left(- (8) + \sqrt{4} \right) - \left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1785174 := \left(- (1) + \left(7 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{8^{5+1}} - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1788745 := \left(\left((1 \times 7)^{\sqrt{8+8}} \right) \times 745 \right)$$

$$1789696 := \left(1 + \left(\left(\sqrt{7^8} + \left(9 \times 6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9^6} \right) \right)$$

$$1791699 := \left(\left(\left(1^7 \right) \times 91 \right) \times \left(6 + \left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1792921 := \left(\left((1 + 7) + \left(9 + 2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)^{2 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1794296 := \left(\left(179^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \left(2 + (9 \times 6) \right) \right)$$

$$1794690 := \left(\left(\left(17 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 690 \right)$$

$$1799344 := \left(1 - \left(- \left((7 \times 9) \right) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 3 \right) + 4 \right)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1806447 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{8^{06}} - 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 1814470 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (1) + \left(81 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 70 \right) \\
 1815849 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left((8 \times 15) + (8/4) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 1824494 &:= \left(- \left((1 - 8) \times 2 \right) \times \left(\left((4 \times 4) + \sqrt{9} \right)^4 \right) \right) \\
 1824768 &:= (1 + 8 + 2) \times \sqrt{4^7 \times 6^8} \\
 1827847 &:= \left(1 - 8^{2-7+8} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 7 \\
 1834945 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{1+8} \times (-3) \right) + \left(4^9 \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 5 \right) \right) \\
 1834952 &:= \left(- \left((1 - 8) \right) \times \left(- \left(\left(3 - \left(4^9 \right) \right) - \sqrt{5^2} \right) \right) \right) \\
 1834954 &:= \left(\left((1 - 8) \times \left(3 - \left(\left(4^9 \right) - 5 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 1834969 &:= \left(\left((1 - 8) \times \left(3 - \left(4^9 \right) \right) \right) + \left(- (6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 1834973 &:= \left(- \left((1 - 8) \right) \times \left(- \left(\left(3 - \left(4^9 \right) \right) - \sqrt{7-3} \right) \right) \right) \\
 1834986 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(- \left(\left((8 + 3) - 4 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(8^6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1842975 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(1 - \left(\left(8^4 \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times 75 \right) \\
 1843968 &:= \sqrt{(-1+8)^{\sqrt{4^3}}} \times 96 \times 8 \\
 1849372 &:= (-1+8) \times \left(\sqrt{4^9} + \sqrt{-3+7} \right)^2 \\
 1849427 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(8 + \left(\left(\sqrt{4^9} + \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 1849428 &:= \left(- \left((1 - 8) \right) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^9} + \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) + 8 \right) \right) \\
 1852195 &:= \left(\left(1 - \left((8 \times 5) \times \left(21^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \times (-5) \right) \\
 1856465 &:= \left(\left(\left((1 \times 8) + 5 \right)^{6-\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 65 \right) \\
 1858446 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 - \left(- (8) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 46 \right) \\
 1865729 &:= \left(\left(1 - \sqrt{8^6} \right) - \left(- (5) \times \left(72^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 1866155 &:= \left(\left(- (1) - \left(8 \times \left(- \left(\left(6^6 \right) + \sqrt{-1+5} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 1866185 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{1+8} - \left(\left(\left(6^6 \right) - 1 \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \times (-5) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1866204 &:= \left(- \left(\left(18 - \left(\left(6^6 \right) \times 20 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 1866229 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(\left(\left(8 \times \left(6^6 \right) \right) - 2 \right) \times \left(-2 - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 1866239 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(\left(8 \times \left(6^6 \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(\left(2^3 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1866275 &:= \left(\left(\left((1 \times 8) \times \left(6^{\sqrt{6^2}} \right) \right) + 7 \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 1866297 &:= \left(1 + \left(8 \times \left(\left(\left(6^6 \right) \times \left(2 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1866420 &:= \left(\left((1 + 8) + \left(\left(6^6 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 20 \right) \\
 1866435 &:= \left(\left(- (1) - \left(8 \times \left(\left(- \left(\left(6^6 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) - 3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 1866480 &:= \left(\left(1 - \left(\left(8 + \left(6^6 \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times (-80) \right) \\
 1866965 &:= \left(\left(1 - \left(8 \times \left(- \left(\left(6^6 \right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-6) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 1874154 &:= \left((1 - 8) + \left(\left(7 + \left(\sqrt{4} \times 15 \right) \right)^4 \right) \right) \\
 1874161 &:= \left(\left((1 + 8) + (7 \times 4) \right)^{\sqrt{16 \times 1}} \right) \\
 1874164 &:= \left(\sqrt{1+8} + \left(\left(7 + \left((4 + 1) \times 6 \right) \right)^4 \right) \right) \\
 1875168 &:= \left(\sqrt{1+8} \times \left(\left(7 + \left(5^{1+6} \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 1875169 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(8 \times \left(7 + \left(5^{1+6} \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 1878845 &:= \left(\sqrt{1+8} - 7 \times 88 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 \\
 1879642 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(- (87) + \sqrt{9^6 \times 4} \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 1879959 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(\left(87^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / (-9) \right) + \left(\left(5^9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1881792 &:= \left(\sqrt{1+8} \times \left(\left((81 + 7) \times 9 \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 1882384 &:= \left(\left(\left((1 + (8 \times (8 - 2)))^3 \right) \times 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 1882416 &:= \left((1 - 8)^{8-2} + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 16 \\
 1882448 &:= \left((1 - 8)^{8-2} + 4 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \times 8 \\
 1883925 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 - \left((8 + 83)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) / (-2) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 1887437 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left((1 + 8) \times \left(8^7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) / \left(- (3 + 7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1888326 &:= \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(1-8)^8} + 8^3} \right)^2 \times 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1889284 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - (284) \right) \\
 1889325 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - \sqrt{32 \times 5} \right) \\
 1889337 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - ((33 \times 7)) \right) \\
 1889367 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - ((3 \times 67)) \right) \\
 1889379 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - ((3 \times 7) \times 9) \right) \\
 1889439 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - (43 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 1889456 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - (\sqrt{4} \times 56) \right) \\
 1889474 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - (47 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 1889482 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - (4 + 82) \right) \\
 1889483 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - (\sqrt{4} + (83)) \right) \\
 1889485 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + (\sqrt{4} - (85)) \right) \\
 1889486 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + (4 - 86) \right) \\
 1889488 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + ((\sqrt{4} + 8) \times (-8)) \right) \\
 1889496 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - ((4 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 6) \right) \\
 1889497 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - ((4^{\sqrt{9}}) + 7) \right) \\
 1889498 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + (\sqrt{4} - (9 \times 8)) \right) \\
 1889509 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - (50 + 9) \right) \\
 1889526 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - ((5 + 2) \times 6) \right) \\
 1889536 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - (5 + \sqrt{36}) \right) \\
 1889554 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - ((5 + 5) + 4) \right) \\
 1889556 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8} \times 9} \right)^5 \right) - (5 + 6) \right) \right) \\
 1889557 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8} \times 9} \right)^5 \right) - (5 + 7) \right) \right) \\
 1889558 &:= \left(\left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - 5 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{58}}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1889562 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((1^8) + 8 \right) + 9 \right)^5 \right) - \sqrt{6^2} \right) \\
 1889563 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - \sqrt{56/3} \right) \\
 1889565 &:= \left((1 - \sqrt{8+8}) - (\sqrt{9^5} \times (- (6^5))) \right) \\
 1889566 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - \sqrt{5-6/6} \right) \\
 1889569 &:= \left(1 - \left(- \left((8+8) \times ((9^5) \times 6) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 1889581 &:= \left(\left((18^5) - \sqrt{9} \right) + ((8+8) \times 1) \right) \\
 1889581 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + ((5+8) \times 1) \right) \\
 1889583 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{58} \times 3}} \right) \right) \\
 1889586 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - (((5-8) \times 6)) \right) \\
 1889588 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + (5 \times \sqrt{8+8}) \right) \\
 1889596 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8} \times 9} \right)^5 \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} \right) \right) \\
 1889604 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + \sqrt{6^4} \right) \\
 1889617 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + ((6+1) \times 7) \right) \\
 1889625 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + (62 - 5) \right) \\
 1889626 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - (6 - (2^6)) \right) \\
 1889628 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + (6 \times (2+8)) \right) \\
 1889631 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + (63 \times 1) \right) \\
 1889632 &:= \left(((1 \times 8) \times 8) + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 6)^{3+2} \right) \right) \\
 1889635 &:= \left(\left(((1 \times 8) \times 8) + \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(((6 \times 3)^5) \right) \right) \\
 1889648 &:= \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + (((6+4) \times 8)) \right) \\
 1889649 &:= \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{1+8}^8} + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 6)^{-4+9} \right) \right) \\
 1889653 &:= \left((1 \times 88) + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 6)^5 \right) - 3 \right) \right) \\
 1889654 &:= \left((1 \times 88) + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 6)^5 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1889655 := \left(-((1-88)) + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 6)^{\sqrt{5 \times 5}} \right) \right)$$

$$1889659 := \left((1 \times 88) + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 6)^5 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$1889722 := \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + (7 \times 22) \right)$$

$$1889824 := \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + \left((8^2) \times 4 \right) \right)$$

$$1889892 := \left(-(18) \times \left(\left((-8) \times (\sqrt{9}^8) \right) - 9 \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$1889944 := \left((18^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + ((94 \times 4)) \right)$$

$$1889946 := \left(-(1) + \left((8+8) \times \left((\sqrt{9}^9) + 4 \right) \right) \right) \times 6$$

$$1890864 := \left((18^{-\sqrt{9}+08}) + (6^4) \right)$$

$$1897295 := \left(((1-89) \times 7)^2 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5$$

$$1897875 := \left(-(18) + \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times 875$$

$$1920984 := \left(1 - \left((\sqrt{9} + (20)) \times \left(-((9+8)^4) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1922347 := \left(\left(\left(\left(-1 - (\sqrt{9} \times (-22)) \right) \right)^3 \right) - 4 \right) \times 7$$

$$1924559 := \left(-(1) + \left(\left((9 \times 2)^4 \right) \times 55 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$1925616 := \left(\left(1 + \left((\sqrt{9} + 2)^5 \right) \right) \right) \times 616$$

$$1926544 := \left(\left(\left(\left(-1 + \sqrt{(9-2)^6} \right) + 5 \right) \times 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$1928648 := \left(\left(\left(-((19+2)) + \sqrt{8^6} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$1929784 := \left(\left(\left(\left((1 + (9^2))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 7 \right) - 8 \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$1929788 := \left(\left(\left(\left((1 + (9^2))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 7 \right) / \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}} \right) \right)$$

$$1934425 := \left(1 + \left(-\sqrt{9} + (3 + \sqrt{4})^4 \right)^2 \right) \times 5$$

$$1937664 := \left((((1+9) + (37 \times 6)) \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$1943995 := \left(\left(\left(\left((-1 - \sqrt{9}) + (4^3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 9 \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$1943999 := \left(-(1) + \left(\left((9-4) \times (3+9) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$1944791 := \left(1 + \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9+1) \right) \right)$$

$$1944810 := \left(\left((1 + \sqrt{9 \times 4})^4 \right) \times 810 \right)$$

$$1945349 := \left(-\left(\left((1+9) - 4 \right)^5 \right) + \left((3 + \sqrt{4})^9 \right) \right)$$

$$1946559 := 1 - 9^4 - 6 + \sqrt{(5 \times 5)^9}$$

$$1946563 := \left(-(1) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9 \times 4} + 6 \right) - \left((5^{6+3}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1946569 := \left(-\left((1 + (9^4) - 6) \right) + \left(\sqrt{5^6 \times 9} \right) \right)$$

$$1946920 := \left(-((1+9)) - (46^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times (-20)$$

$$1947959 := \left(\left((-1) - \sqrt{9^4} \right) \times (7 \times 9) + \left((5^9) \right) \right)$$

$$1948259 := \left(-(19) \times \sqrt{4^8} - (2 - (5^9)) \right)$$

$$1949029 := -\left(\left(\left(-((1-9))^4 \right) - \left((\sqrt{9} + 02)^9 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1949184 := \left((1 \times 94) \times \left((9 + \sqrt{1+8})^4 \right) \right)$$

$$1949747 := \left((19 - \sqrt{4}) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + (7 \times (4^7)) \right) \right)$$

$$1952274 := \left(\left((19 \times 52)^2 \right) - 7 \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1952288 := \left(\left((19 \times 52)^2 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}} \right)$$

$$1952294 := \left(\left((19 \times 52)^2 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$1952549 := -(19+5)^2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4 \times 9}}$$

$$1952759 := \left((1 - \sqrt{9}) - \left((52 \times 7) - (5^9) \right) \right)$$

$$1952779 := \left(\left((-1) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((5^{2+7}) \right) \right) - (7^{\sqrt{9}})$$

$$1952859 := \left(\left((-1) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-5) - \left((2^8) - (5^9) \right) \right)$$

$$1952899 := \left(-\left((1 + (9 \times (5^2))) \right) + \left((8 - \sqrt{9})^9 \right) \right)$$

$$1952929 := \left(-\left(\left((1 \times 9) + 5 \right)^2 \right) + \left((\sqrt{9} + 2)^9 \right) \right)$$

$$1953114 := \left(-\left((1 \times 9) - (5^{3^{1+1}}) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$1953121 := \left((-1) - \sqrt{9} + \left((5^{(3+1) \times 2+1}) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1953128 &:= (\sqrt{1 \times 9} + (5^{(3-1)/2+8})) \\
 1953142 &:= (19 + ((5^{\sqrt{(3 \times 1)^4}}) - 2)) \\
 1953145 &:= (((-1) - \sqrt{9}) - ((5^{(3-1) \times 4}))) \times (-5) \\
 1953169 &:= (-((1 - (9 \times 5))) + (\sqrt{(31 - 6)^9})) \\
 1953191 &:= (1 + (((\sqrt{9} + 1)^3) + (((5^9) + 1)))) \\
 1953253 &:= (\sqrt{1 \times 9} + ((5^{3^2}) + (5^3))) \\
 1953285 &:= (((((-1) + \sqrt{9})^5) + (((3 + 2)^8)))) \times 5 \\
 1953359 &:= (\sqrt{1 \times 9^5} - ((3 \times 3) - (5^9))) \\
 1953369 &:= ((1 + \sqrt{9^5}) + (-(((3/3) - 6)^9)) \\
 1953476 &:= (-((1 - 9)) + ((5^{\sqrt{3^4}}) + \sqrt{76})) \\
 1953499 &:= (((-1) - (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^3)))) + (-((4 - 9)^9)) \\
 1953549 &:= (-1 + 9) \times 53 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4 \times 9}} \\
 1953599 &:= (((1 \times 9) \times 53) + (5^9)) - \sqrt{9} \\
 1953859 &:= (((1 - \sqrt{9^5}) \times (-3)) + ((8 + (5^9)))) \\
 1954149 &:= (((1 + \sqrt{9})^5) + ((4 + (1^4))^9)) \\
 1955625 &:= ((((-1) - \sqrt{9}) - ((5^5))) \times (-625)) \\
 1956259 &:= ((1 - \sqrt{9}) + (((56^2) + (5^9)))) \\
 1958749 &:= (((-1) - (-9 \times \sqrt{5^8})) + ((7 - \sqrt{4})^9)) \\
 1958887 &:= (((((1 + 9) + 5) + 8)^{\sqrt{8+8}}) \times 7) \\
 1959231 &:= ((((-((1 - (9 \times 5)))^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 23) - 1) \\
 1959232 &:= ((((-((1 - (9 \times 5)))^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{23^2}) \\
 1959234 &:= ((((-((1 - (9 \times 5)))^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 23) + \sqrt{4}) \\
 1959566 &:= (-1) - (\sqrt{9} \times (-5 + ((9 + 5) \times (6^6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1959659 &:= ((((-1) + \sqrt{9^5}) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}) + ((5^9))) \\
 1959694 &:= (((-1) + \sqrt{9}) + (((5^9) + 6) + (9^4))) \\
 1962534 &:= (((1 + 96)^2) + (5^{\sqrt{3^4}})) \\
 1963443 &:= (((((-1) + \sqrt{9^6}) + ((3^4)))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 3) \\
 1966048 &:= (((((1 + \sqrt{9})^6) \times (-60)) + 4) \times (-8)) \\
 1966144 &:= (((-1) + ((\sqrt{9} \times 661)^{\sqrt{4}})) / \sqrt{4}) \\
 1968299 &:= (-1) - (-((96 + (8/2))) \times (\sqrt{9^9})) \\
 1968820 &:= (\sqrt{(1^9 + 6)^8} \times 820) \\
 1969445 &:= (-((1 - 96)) \times (((\sqrt{9} \times 4)^4) - 5)) \\
 1973727 &:= ((((-1) + ((\sqrt{9} + 73) \times 7))^2) \times 7) \\
 1979054 &:= (((-((1 - 9))^7) + (-((9^05)) \times \sqrt{4})) \\
 1985885 &:= (((-1) + ((\sqrt{9^8}) + (((5^8) - 8)))) \times 5) \\
 1985929 &:= (((-1) + ((\sqrt{9^8}) \times 5)) + ((\sqrt{9} + 2)^9)) \\
 1989768 &:= (((((-1) + \sqrt{9})^{8+9}) + ((7^6))) \times 8) \\
 1993744 &:= (-1 + 9 \times (9 + 37 \times 4))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 1994449 &:= (19 \times (((9 \times \sqrt{4})^4) + ((4 - 9)))) \\
 1994472 &:= ((19 \times ((9 \times \sqrt{4})^4)) - 72) \\
 1996499 &:= (-1) + ((9 + \sqrt{9}) \times ((6 + 49)^{\sqrt{9}})) \\
 1997648 &:= (((((1 - (9^{\sqrt{9}})) \times \sqrt{76}) - \sqrt{4}) \times (-8)) \\
 1997974 &:= (-1) + (((9 + 9) \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} - (7^4)) \\
 1999834 &:= (((1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - (83)) \times \sqrt{4}) \\
 1999856 &:= ((19 - \sqrt{9}) \times (-9 - (8 \times (5^6)))) \\
 1999964 &:= (((1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} + (\sqrt{9} \times (-6))) \times \sqrt{4})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1999976 &:= \left((- (1) + \sqrt{9}) \times \left((- (9) - \sqrt{9}) + \left((\sqrt{9} + 7)^6 \right) \right) \right) & 2097148 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + ((1 \times 4) - 8) \right) \\
 1999982 &:= \left(\left((1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9 \right) \times \sqrt{8/2} \right) & 2097149 &:= \left(\left((2 \times 0) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((7 + 1) \times (4^9) \right) \right) \\
 1999984 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((1^9) + 99 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) & 2097150 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{-1 + 5 + 0} \right) \\
 1999994 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((1^9) + 99 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) & 2097153 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + (1^5 3) \right) \\
 2048363 &:= \left(- (20) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(8 - 3)^6} \right)^3 \right) \right) & 2097155 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + (15/5) \right) \\
 2067844 &:= \left((((206 \times 7) - 8) + 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) & 2097156 &:= \left(\left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{-1 + 5} \right) + 6 \right) \\
 2074466 &:= \left(2 + \left(\left((07^4) \times 4 \right) \times \sqrt{6^6} \right) \right) & 2097157 &:= \left(\left(2 + \sqrt{09} \right) + \left(\left(7 + (1^5) \right)^7 \right) \right) \\
 2079364 &:= \left((20 + ((79 \times 3) \times 6))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) & 2097158 &:= \left(\left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{-1 + 5} \right) + 8 \right) \\
 2085139 &:= (-2 + 08 \times 5)^{1+3} + \sqrt{9} & 2097159 &:= \left(\left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - ((1 - 5)) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 2085479 &:= (-2 + 08 \times 5)^4 + 7^{\sqrt{9}} & 2097162 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - (((1 - 6) \times 2)) \right) \\
 2086398 &:= \left(((20 + 86) \times 3) \times (\sqrt{9^8}) \right) & 2097164 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + (16 - 4) \right) \\
 2089128 &:= \left(\left(- (20) - \left(\left((8^{\sqrt{9}}) - 1 \right)^2 \right) \right) \times (-8) \right) & 2097169 &:= \left(\left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - 1 \right) - \left(- (6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 2096421 &:= \left(\left(-2 - \sqrt{09^6} \right) + \left(\sqrt{4^{21}} \right) \right) & 2097192 &:= \left(20 + \sqrt{(9 + 7)^{1+9}} \right) \times 2 \\
 2097076 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - 076 \right) & 2097216 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + \left((2 \times 1)^6 \right) \right) \\
 2097088 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - (08 \times 8) \right) & 2097248 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + ((2 \times 48)) \right) \\
 2097119 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - (11 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) & 2097252 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + \left((2 \times 5)^2 \right) \right) \\
 2097126 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - (1 \times 26) \right) & 2097275 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + \left((2^7) - 5 \right) \right) \\
 2097128 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - ((1 + 2) \times 8) \right) & 2097368 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - \left(\sqrt{3^6} \times (-8) \right) \right) \\
 2097129 &:= \left(\left(- (20) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((7 + 1)^{-2+9} \right) \right) & 2097374 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + ((3 \times 74)) \right) \\
 2097139 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - ((1 + 3) + 9) \right) & 2097395 &:= \left(\left(2^{(0 \times 9 + 7) \times 3} \right) + \sqrt{9^5} \right) \\
 2097142 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - ((1 + 4) \times 2) \right) & 2097408 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{4^{08}} \right) \\
 2097145 &:= \left(\left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{1 \times 4} \right) - 5 \right) & 2097587 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + (5 \times 87) \right) \\
 2097147 &:= \left(\left(-2 - \sqrt{09} \right) + \left(\left((7 + (1^4))^7 \right) \right) \right) & 2097638 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + \left(6 \times \sqrt{3^8} \right) \right) \\
 & & 2097728 &:= \left(2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}} + (72 \times 8) \right) \\
 & & 2099875 &:= \left(\left(\left((2 + \sqrt{09})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(- (8 - (7^5)) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2101245 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((2^{10}) + 1 \right)^2 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - 5 \right) \\
 2107392 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left((2^{10}) \times (7^3) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-2) \right) \\
 2109449 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((2^{10}) + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - 9 \right) \\
 2109472 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((2^{10}) + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 7 \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 2117556 &:= \left(- (21) \times \left(\left(1 - (7^{\sqrt{5 \times 5}}) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 2117646 &:= \left((2 + 1) \times \left(\left((1 \times 7)^6 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 2117664 &:= \left(- \left(\left((2 + 1) \times (1 - (7^6)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^4}} \right) \\
 2117669 &:= \left(2 - \left(- \left((1 - ((1 - (7^6)) \times 6)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 2119924 &:= \left(\left(- ((2 + 1)) + \left((- (1) + (9^{\sqrt{9}}))^2 \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 2119928 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times (- (1) + ((1 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)^2 - 8 \right) \\
 2119944 &:= \left(\left(2 + \left((- (1) + ((1 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}}))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 2121849 &:= \left((2 + ((1 \times 21) + 8^4)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 2124786 &:= \left(\left((2^{12}) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (7 + \sqrt{8^6}) \right) \\
 2125746 &:= \left(2 \times \left(1 - \left(2 \times \left(5 - \left((7 + \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2125754 &:= \left(\left(2 \times (1 + 2)^{5+7} \right) - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 2125766 &:= \left(2 \times \left(1 - \left(- (2) \times \left(\sqrt{(5 + 76)^6} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2137444 &:= (2 \times (-13 + 744))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2145447 &:= \left(\left(\left((21 + \sqrt{4})^5 - \sqrt{4} \right) / (- (4 - 7)) \right) \right) \\
 2145449 &:= \left(\left(\left((21 + \sqrt{4})^5 + \sqrt{4 \times 4} \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 2145463 &:= \left(\left(\left((21 + \sqrt{4})^5 + 46 \right) / 3 \right) \right) \\
 2145469 &:= \left(\left(\left((21 + \sqrt{4})^5 + \sqrt{4^6} \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2146689 &:= \left(((2 - 1) + (((4 + 6) + 6) \times 8))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 2147599 &:= \left(\left((21^4) - 7 \right) + (5^{\sqrt{9 \times 9}}) \right) \\
 2148895 &:= \left(\sqrt{(2 + 1 + 4)^8 \times 895} \right) \\
 2151294 &:= \left(-2 - \left(((15 - 1)^{2 + \sqrt{9}}) \times (-4) \right) \right) \\
 2162754 &:= \left(\left((2^{16}) + 2 \right) \times (7 \times 5 - \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 2166784 &:= \left(\left(2 + \left(- (((1 - 6) \times 6) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 2186595 &:= \left(\sqrt{(2 + 1)^8 \times ((6 \times 5)^{\sqrt{9}}) - 5} \right) \\
 2196995 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \left((- (1) - \sqrt{9}) + 69 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 \right) \\
 2196998 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(\left((- (1) - \sqrt{9}) + 69 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 2207744 &:= \left(\sqrt{2^{20}} \times ((7 \times 7) \times 44) \right) \\
 2214799 &:= \left(\left((2^{21}) - \sqrt{4} \right) + (7^{9 - \sqrt{9}}) \right) \\
 2239459 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{2 + 2} + \left(3 - \left((\sqrt{9} \times 4)^5 \right) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 2239464 &:= \left(\left(- (2) \times \left((2 \times 3)^{9 - \sqrt{4}} \right) \right) + 6 \right) \times (-4) \\
 2239472 &:= \left((2 + (2 \times 3)) \times \left((\sqrt{9 \times 4^7}) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 2239474 &:= \left(2 - \left(- \left((2^3) \right) \times \left((\sqrt{9 \times 4^7}) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 2239478 &:= \left(- \left((2 + (2^3)) \right) - \left((\sqrt{9 \times 4^7}) \times (-8) \right) \right) \\
 2239479 &:= \left(\left((2 + (2 \times 3)) \times (\sqrt{9 \times 4^7}) \right) - 9 \right) \\
 2239483 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(\left((2 \times 3)^{9 - \sqrt{4}} \right) \times 8 \right) - 3 \right) \\
 2239484 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((2 - (2^3)) \right) \right)^{9 - \sqrt{4}} \right) \times 8 \right) - 4 \\
 2239486 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(\left((2 \times 3)^{\sqrt{9 \times 4}} \right) \times (8 \times 6) \right) \right) \\
 2239488 &:= \left(\left(- \left((2 - (2^3)) \right) \right)^{9 - \sqrt{4}} \times \sqrt{8 \times 8} \right) \\
 2239489 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(\left((2 \times 3)^{9 - \sqrt{4}} \right) \times 8 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 2239495 &:= \left(((2 + 2) + 3) + \left(9 \times \left((4 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2248093 &:= \left(2 + \left(\left(\left(2^4\right) \times 8\right) + \sqrt{09}\right)^3\right) \\
 2249566 &:= \left(-2 - \left(- (24) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(5^6\right)\right) \times (-6)\right)\right)\right) \\
 2249568 &:= \left((22 - 4) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(5^6\right)\right) \times (-8)\right)\right) \\
 2250396 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(22 + \left(50^3\right)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) \times (-6)\right) \\
 2252844 &:= \left(- (22) \times \left(- \left(\left(\left(5^2\right) \times \left(8^4\right)\right)\right) - \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 2254797 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times \left(2^{5+4}\right)\right) + 7\right) \times \sqrt{97}\right) \\
 2256004 &:= \left(2 + (25 \times 60)\right)^{\sqrt{04}} \\
 2268945 &:= \left(\sqrt{\left(2/2 + 6\right)^8} \times 945\right) \\
 2275923 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(2 + 2\right)\right) - \left(- (7) \times \left(5^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right)\right)^2\right) \times 3 \\
 2275936 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(\left(- \left(2 - 7\right)\right)^5 - \sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(3^6\right)\right) \\
 2278059 &:= \left(- \left(\left(22 - \left(7 + 8\right)^{05}\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 2279872 &:= \left(\left(- (2) + \left(2 + 7\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times \left(8 \times 7\right)^2\right) \\
 2281248 &:= \left(\left(\left(22 + \left(8^{1+2}\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times 8\right) \\
 2284895 &:= \left(2 - 28\right)^{-4+8} + \sqrt{9} \times 5 \\
 2284925 &:= \left(2 - 28\right)^4 + 9 \times \sqrt{25} \\
 2284955 &:= \left(2 - 28\right)^4 + \sqrt{9} \times 5 \times 5 \\
 2286144 &:= \left(\left(22 + 86\right) \times 14\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2293970 &:= \left(2^{2 \times 9 - 3} + \sqrt{9}\right) \times 70 \\
 2296348 &:= \left(-2 - \left(2 \times \left(\left(9^6\right) - \left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{4}\right)^8\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 2299884 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(22 \times \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times 8\right) - (84)\right) \\
 2299928 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(22 \times \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \sqrt{9}\right) - 2\right) \times 8\right) \\
 2299934 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (22) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - 9\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - 34\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2299944 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(22 \times \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \sqrt{9}\right) \times (4 + 4)\right) \\
 2299953 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (22) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - 9\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - (5 \times 3)\right) \\
 2299959 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(22 \times \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + 5\right)\right) - 9\right) \\
 2299961 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (22) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - 9\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - (6 + 1)\right) \\
 2299962 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (22) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - 9\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \sqrt{6^2}\right) \\
 2299964 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (22) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - 9\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \left(6 - \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 2299967 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (22) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - 9\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + \left(6 - 7\right)\right) \\
 2299968 &:= \left(22^{\sqrt{9}} \times (9 \times ((9 - 6) \times 8))\right) \\
 2299969 &:= \left(2/2 + \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - (9 \times (9 + 6))\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \\
 2299984 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (22) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - 9\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + \left(8 \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 2299986 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(22 \times \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + \sqrt{9}\right) \times 8\right) - 6 \\
 2299989 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(22 \times \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + \sqrt{9}\right) \times 8\right) - \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 2302911 &:= \left(- \left(2 - (30/2)\right)\right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^{11}}\right) \\
 2304324 &:= \left(23 \times \left(\left(04^3\right) + 2\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2313434 &:= \left(2 + \left(3 \times 13\right)^4\right) - \sqrt{3^4} \\
 2313437 &:= \left(- \left(2 - \left(3 \times 13\right)^4\right)\right) - \sqrt{-3 + 7} \\
 2313442 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \left(3 \times 13\right)^4\right) + \sqrt{4}\right) / 2 \\
 2313449 &:= \left(2 + \left(3 \times 13\right)^4\right) + \sqrt{4 \times 9} \\
 2316484 &:= \left(2 + \left(\left(31 \times 6\right) + 4\right) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2328674 &:= -2 + \left(3 - 2^8 \times 6 + 7\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2328774 &:= \left(2 \times 3\right) \times \left(\left(2 + 87\right) \times 7\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2328970 &:= \left(\sqrt{\left(2 + 3 + 2\right)^8} \times 970\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2332950 := \left(\left(- \left(\left((2 \times 3)^3 \right)^2 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-50)$$

$$2334784 := \left(2 \times \left(\left(\left((3^3) \times 4 \right) \times 7 \right) + 8 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$2343588 := \left(2 \times \left(- \left((3^4) \right) + \left(3 \times \left(5^{\sqrt{8 \times 8}} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2343650 := \left(\left(2 + \left(- (3) \times \left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (-50)$$

$$2343675 := \left(\left((2 + 3)^{\sqrt{4^3}} \times 6 \right) - 75 \right)$$

$$2343696 := \left(\left((2 + 3)^{\sqrt{4^3}} \times 6 \right) - (9 \times 6) \right)$$

$$2343735 := \left(\left(\left((2 \times 3) \times \left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \right) \right) - 3 \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$2343738 := \left(- \left((2 \times 3) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left((3 + \sqrt{7-3})^8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2343792 := \left(\left(\left((2 + 3)^{\sqrt{4^3}} + 7 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$2343795 := \left(\left(\left((2 \times 3) \times \left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \right) \right) + 9 \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$2343810 := \left((2 \times 3) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^8 \right) + 10 \right) \right)$$

$$2343846 := \left(\left((2 + 3)^{\sqrt{4^3}} + (8 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$2343850 := \left(2 \times \left(\left(3 \times \left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^8 \right) \right) + 50 \right) \right)$$

$$2343858 := \left((2 \times 3) \times \left(\sqrt{4 \times \sqrt{3^8}} + (5^8) \right) \right)$$

$$2345987 := \left(\left(\left(\left((2^3) + 4 \right)^5 + \sqrt{9} \right) + (8^7) \right) \right)$$

$$2346125 := \left(\left(\left(\left(2 \times \sqrt{(3+4)^6} - 1 \right)^2 \right) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$2347846 := 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} - 7)^8 + 4^6$$

$$2348358 := \left((2 \times 3) \times \left((\sqrt{4^8} \times 3) + (5^8) \right) \right)$$

$$2352629 := \left(- \left((2^3) \right) + \left(\left(5 + \left((2^6) \times 2 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$2352639 := \left(2 + \left((35 \times 2) + 63 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$2358999 := \left((2 - 35) + (8^{9-\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times 9$$

$$2359294 := \left(\left(\left((2^3)^5 \right) \times \left((9^2) - 9 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$2361958 := \left(- (2) + \left((\sqrt{36} - 1) \times \left((9^5) \times 8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2365444 := \left(\left((2 \times (3^6)) + ((5 \times 4) \times 4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$2369787 := \left(\left((23 \times 6) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{7^8} \times 7 \right)$$

$$2371844 := \left(2 + \left(\left(\left((3^7) - 1 \right) - 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} / \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$2374589 := \left(- \left((23 \times (7^4)) \right) \times \left(- ((5 \times 8)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$2375095 := \left(- ((2 - (3 \times 7))) \times \left((50^{\sqrt{9}}) + 5 \right) \right)$$

$$2377764 := (2 \times (3 - 777) + 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$2378979 := \left(\left(\left((2^3)^7 / 8 \right) + \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$2383280 := \left((23 + 8)^{\sqrt{3^2}} \times 80 \right)$$

$$2383928 := \left(\left(\left((2^3) + \left((8^3) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^2 - 8 \right) \right)$$

$$2384640 := \left(\sqrt{(2 \times 3)^8} \times (46 \times 40) \right)$$

$$2384928 := \left(\left(\left((23 \times 8) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^2 \times 8 \right)$$

$$2387929 := \left(23 \times \left(\sqrt{(8 \times 7 - 9)^2}^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$2388995 := \left(\sqrt{(2 - 3 + 8)^8} \times 995 \right)$$

$$2391473 := \left(\left(- (23) + (\sqrt{9}^{14}) \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right)$$

$$2391482 := \left(\left(- ((2 + 3)) + (\sqrt{9}^{14}) \right) / \sqrt{8/2} \right)$$

$$2391484 := \left(\left(- ((2 - 3)) - (\sqrt{9}^{14}) \right) / (- (8/4)) \right)$$

$$2391488 := \left(2 - \left(\left(- (3) - (\sqrt{9}^{14}) \right) / \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}} \right) \right)$$

$$2391492 := \left((2 \times 3) - \left(\left((\sqrt{9}^{14}) + \sqrt{9} \right) / (-2) \right) \right)$$

$$2391494 := \left((2 + 3) + \left(\left((\sqrt{9}^{14}) + 9 \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$2391496 := \left(\left(\left(- (23) - (\sqrt{9}^{14}) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / (-6) \right)$$

$$2414494 := \left((24 - 1) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((\sqrt{4} \times 9)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2426166 &:= \left(2 + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(26 \times \left(1 + \left(6^6\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 2427364 &:= \left(-2 + 4 \times \left(2^7 \times 3 + 6\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2439844 &:= \left(\left(2 + \left(4 \times 39\right) \times \left(8 + \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2452478 &:= \left(-2 - \left(\left(4^5\right) \times \left(2 + 4\right) - \sqrt{7^8}\right)\right) \\
 2454528 &:= \left(\sqrt{2^{4 \times 5}} \times \left(-4 + \sqrt{\left(5 + 2\right)^8}\right)\right) \\
 2455328 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(2 / \sqrt{4}\right) + 553\right)^2\right) \times 8\right) \\
 2457564 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times 4\right)^5\right) \times 75\right) - \sqrt{6^4} \\
 2457579 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times 4\right)^5\right) \times 75\right) + \left(-7\right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 2457584 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times 4\right)^5\right) \times 75\right) - \left(8 \times \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 2457589 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(2 \times 4\right)^5\right) \times 75\right) - 8\right) - \sqrt{9} \\
 2457594 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times 4\right)^5\right) \times 75\right) - \sqrt{9 \times 4} \\
 2457893 &:= \left(-2\right) + \left(\left(\left(4^5\right) \times \sqrt{7^8}\right) - \left(\left(9^3\right)\right)\right) \\
 2457974 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(2^{\sqrt{4}+5}\right) + 7\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \left(7^4\right)\right) \\
 2458644 &:= \left(\sqrt{2^4} \times \left(5 + \left(\left(-8\right) + \sqrt{6^4}\right)^4\right)\right) \\
 2459999 &:= \left(\left(-2\right) / \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(\left(5^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9}\right) - \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\
 2463744 &:= \left(2^{4+6}\right) \times \left(\left(3 + \left(7^4\right)\right) + \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 2464536 &:= \left(\left(-2\right) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(64 - 5\right)^3\right)\right)\right) \times 6 \\
 2464596 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(4 + \left(\left(64 - 5\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times 6\right)\right) \\
 2465195 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(2 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 6\right) \times 5\right)\right) - 1\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times 5\right) \\
 2465478 &:= \left(\left(2 + \left(-\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 6\right)\right)^5\right)\right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{7^8}\right)\right) \\
 2470619 &:= \left(2 - \left(\left(4 - \left(7^{06+1}\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\
 2470673 &:= \left(2 + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(7^{06}\right)\right) \times \left(7 \times 3\right)\right)\right) \\
 2470773 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(70\right)\right)\right) + \left(\left(\left(7^7\right) \times 3\right)\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2472662 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{2^4} + \left(\left(7^2\right)\right)\right) \times \left(\left(6^6\right) - 2\right)\right) \\
 2472664 &:= \left(2 + \left(\left(4 + \left(7^2\right)\right) \times \left(\left(6^6\right) - \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\
 2472766 &:= \left(-2\right) + \left(\left(4 + \left(\sqrt{7^2} \times 7\right)\right) \times \left(6^6\right)\right) \\
 2474739 &:= \left(-\left(\left(2 - \left(\left(4 + \left(7^4\right)\right) \times \left(7^3\right)\right)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 2475589 &:= \left(\left(2 + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7\right) + 5\right)^5\right)\right) - \left(8^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \\
 2476195 &:= \left(\left(\left(-2 - \left(\sqrt{4} \times 7\right)\right) \times \left(-6\right)\right) + \left(19^5\right)\right) \\
 2476773 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{2^{4 \times 7-6}} + \left(\left(7^7\right)\right)\right) \times 3\right) \\
 2476949 &:= \left(\sqrt{2^4} + \left(\left(7^6\right) + \left(9 \times \left(4^9\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 2478864 &:= \left(\left(2 + \sqrt{4 \times 7^8}\right) \times \left(\sqrt{8^6} + 4\right)\right) \\
 2479734 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(-7\right) \times \sqrt{9^7}\right) \times \left(-\left(3^4\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 2479932 &:= \left(\left(-2\right) + \sqrt{4^7}\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9}\right) - \left(3 - 2\right)\right) \\
 2479948 &:= \left(2 - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-7\right)\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{9+\sqrt{4}}}\right) - 8\right)\right)\right) \\
 2479956 &:= \left(24 - \left(-7\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(9^5\right)\right) \times \left(-6\right)\right)\right) \\
 2479974 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 + 4\right) \times 7\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{9}+7}}\right) - \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 2479979 &:= \left(\left(\left(-2\right) + \sqrt{4^7}\right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^9}\right) - 79\right) \\
 2479994 &:= \left(2 \times \left(-4 - \left(-7\right) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^9}\right) \times 9\right) - 4\right)\right)\right) \\
 2489454 &:= \left(\left(-2\right) + \sqrt{4^8}\right) \times \left(\left(94 + 5\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 2495382 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left(9 \times \left(5^3\right)\right) - 8\right)^2\right)\right)\right) \\
 2495595 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 + 4\right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(55^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right)\right) \times \left(-5\right)\right) \\
 2498688 &:= \left(\left(-\left(\left(249 - 8\right)\right) \times \sqrt{6^8}\right) \times \left(-8\right)\right) \\
 2499245 &:= \left(\left(\left(-24\right) + \left(\left(9^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + 2\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times 5 \\
 2499739 &:= \left(-2\right) + \left(\left(\left(4^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + \left(\left(9 \times 7\right)\right)\right) \times \left(3^9\right)\right) \\
 2506464 &:= \left(\left(2 - \sqrt{\left(50 - 6\right)^4}\right) \times \left(-\left(6^4\right)\right)\right) \\
 2519379 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{25} - \left(\left(\left(1 \times 9\right) - 3\right)^7\right)\right) \times \left(-9\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2519397 := (-(((2 \times 5) - 1)) \times (\sqrt{9} - (-((3 - 9))^7)))$$

$$2519436 := \left(2 \times \left(\left(\left(\left(5 + 1\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) / \sqrt{4}\right)^3 + 6\right)\right)$$

$$2519448 := \left(-((2 - 5)) \times \left(\left(-1\right) - \left(9 \times \sqrt{4}\right)^4\right) \times (-8)\right)$$

$$2519667 := \left(\left(2 \times 5\right) - 1\right) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{96}} + \left(6^7\right)\right)$$

$$2534464 := \left(\left(2 + \left(5 \times \left(\left(3^4\right) \times 4\right) - 6\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$2537649 := \left(\left(\left(\left(25 \times 3\right) \times 7\right) + 6\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 9\right)$$

$$2543936 := \left(2^5\right) \times \left(\left(43^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - (3 + 6)\right)$$

$$2544998 := \left(-2\right) + \left(-\left(5^4\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4^9} - \sqrt{9}\right) \times (-8)\right)\right)$$

$$2548982 := \left(2 + \left(5 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(89 \times 8\right)\right)^2\right)\right)\right)$$

$$2554664 := \left(\left(2 + 5\right)^5\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6 \times 6)\right) \times 4\right)$$

$$2559486 := -2 + (5 - 5 \times 9)^4 - \sqrt{86}$$

$$2559998 := -2 + (5 - 5 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9+9-8}}$$

$$2562498 := -2 + 5^6 \times \left(2 + \sqrt{4 \times \sqrt{98}}\right)$$

$$2562848 := \left(2 \times \left(5 - 6^2 \times 8\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 8$$

$$2564379 := \left(\left(\left(2 \times \left(5^6\right)\right) + \left(4 + 3\right)^7\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$2566355 := \left(\left(\sqrt{25} + \left(6 \times 6\right)^3\right)\right) \times 55$$

$$2574792 := \left(-2 - \left(57^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right) \times (-792)$$

$$2578119 := \left(\left(-2 - \left(\left(5\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{78}}}\right) \times (-11)\right)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$2578125 := \left(\left(\sqrt{25^7}\right) \times \left(8 \times 1\right) + 25\right)$$

$$2578147 := \left(\left(-2\right) + \left(-\left(5^7\right) \times \sqrt{8+1}\right)\right) \times (-4+7))$$

$$2578191 := \left(\left(2 + \left(5^7\right)\right) \times \left(\left(8 \times \left(1 + \sqrt{9}\right)\right) + 1\right)\right)$$

$$2578389 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{25^7}\right) + 8\right) \times \left(3 \times 8\right) + 9\right)$$

$$2581075 := \left(\sqrt{(2+5)^8} \times 1075\right)$$

$$2584586 := \left(\left(2 \times 5\right) - \left(-\left(8^4\right)\right) \times \left(\sqrt{58} + 6\right)\right)$$

$$2585664 := \left(\left(2 - \left(5 \times 8 + 5\right) \times 6\right) \times 6\right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$2586469 := \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{25^8}} + 6\right) \times \left(\left(4^6\right) + \sqrt{9}\right)\right)$$

$$2587641 := \left(\left(2 + 5\right) \times \left(\left(8 \times 76\right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 1\right)\right)$$

$$2587644 := \left(\left(2 + 5\right) \times \left(8 \times 76\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) - 4$$

$$2587648 := \left(\left(2 + 5\right) \times 8\right) \times \left(\left(76^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times 8\right)$$

$$2598156 := \left(\left(-\left(2 - 5\right)\right)^9\right) \times \left(\left(8 - 1\right) + \sqrt{56}\right)$$

$$2598166 := \left(2 \times \left(5 - \left(\left(\sqrt{98+1}\right) \times (-66)\right)\right)\right)$$

$$2598544 := \left(2 \times \left(5 + \left(9 \times \left(85 + 4\right)\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$2599135 := \left(\left(2 + 5\right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(9 + \left(13^5\right)\right)\right)\right)$$

$$2613645 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(2 + 6\right) + 1\right)^3 - 6\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5\right)$$

$$2621445 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(-2+6)^{21}}\right) + 4\right) / (-4)\right) \times (-5)\right)$$

$$2621475 := \left(\left(\left(-\left(\left(2^6\right)^{2+1}\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) - 7\right) \times (-5)$$

$$2627986 := \left(\left(2 \times \left(62 + 7\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - (86)$$

$$2627998 := \left(-2\right) + \left(\left(\left(62 + 7\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9\right) \times 8\right)$$

$$2629632 := \left(\left(\left(\left(2^6\right)^2\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(\left(6^3\right) - 2\right)\right)$$

$$2639629 := \left(-\left(26^3\right)\right) + \left(\left(9^6\right) \times \left(2 + \sqrt{9}\right)\right)$$

$$2642645 := \left(2 - \left(6 / \left(4 - 2\right)\right)^6\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5$$

$$2645998 := \left(-2\right) + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^4}} \times 5\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times 98\right)\right)$$

$$2654694 := \left(\left(\left(2^{6+5+4}\right) + 6\right) \times \sqrt{9^4}\right)$$

$$2654965 := \left(\left(\left(\left(2^6\right) \times \left(-5 - \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + \left(9^6\right)\right) \times 5\right)$$

$$2656876 := \left(-2 - \left(-6\right) \times \left(\left(-5 + \sqrt{6^8}\right) \times \sqrt{7^6}\right)\right)$$

$$2661984 := \left(\left(\left(-\left(2 \times \left(6 - 61\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right)$$

$$2661994 := \left(\left(\left(- \left((2 \times (6 - 61)) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$2665793 := \left(\left(\left((2 - 6) + (6^5) \right) \times (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$2665794 := \left(\left(\left((2 - 6) + (6^5) \right) \times (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$2665799 := \left(\left(\left((2 - 6) + (6^5) \right) \times (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$2667166 := \left(- (2) + \left(\left(- \left((6^6) \right) \times \sqrt{(7 \times 1)^6} \right) / (-6) \right) \right)$$

$$2681928 := \left(\left(\left(\left((2^6) \times (8 + 1) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)^2 \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$2683240 := \left(\sqrt{(-2 + 6)^8 + 3} \right)^2 \times 40$$

$$2685619 := \left(\left(\sqrt{2^{6+8} + (5 + 6)} \right)^{\sqrt{1 \times 9}} \right)$$

$$2685621 := \left(2 + \left(\left((6 + 8) + \sqrt{5^6} \right)^{2+1} \right) \right)$$

$$2706799 := \left((2 - 70) - \left((67^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-9) \right) \right)$$

$$2715845 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(2 + 7)^{1+5} + 8} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$2733754 := \left(2 \times \left(\sqrt{7 - 3} + \left((3^7) \times (5^4) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2733758 := \left(2 \times \left((7 - 3) + \left((3^7) \times \sqrt{5^8} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2734247 := \left(- \left((2^7) \right) - \left(\left((3 + \sqrt{4})^{2 \times 4} \right) \times (-7) \right) \right)$$

$$2734347 := \left((2 - 7)^{3 + \sqrt{4} + 3} - 4 \right) \times 7$$

$$2734348 := \left(- (27) - \left(- \left((3 + 4) \right) \times \left((3 + \sqrt{4})^8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2734373 := -2 + \left(7 \times \left(3 + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{(-3+7)^3}} \right)$$

$$2734384 := \left(2 - \left(- (7) \times \left(3 + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^8 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2734387 := \left(\left((2 + 7) + 3 \right) + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^8 \right) \times 7 \right) \right)$$

$$2734389 := \left(2 - \left(\left(- (7) \times \left(3 + \left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^8 \right) \right) \right) + 9 \right) \right)$$

$$2734394 := -2 + 7 \times \left(3 + \left(\sqrt{4} - 3 \times 9 \right)^4 \right)$$

$$2734398 := \left(2 + \left(- (7) \times \left(- (3) - \left((\sqrt{4^3} - \sqrt{9})^8 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2734575 := \left(\left(2 + \left(- (7) \times \left((3 \times \sqrt{4}) + (5^7) \right) \right) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$2734889 := \left(2 + \left(\left(7 \times \left((3 + \sqrt{4})^8 \right) \right) + (8^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$2735716 := \left(\left(2 + \left(7 \times \left((3^5) - 7 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}}$$

$$2739196 := \left(-2 - \left(\left((7 \times ((3 + 9) - 1))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-6) \right) \right)$$

$$2742498 := \left(\left((27^4) \times 2 \right) + \left(\sqrt{4 \times 9^8} \right) \right)$$

$$2743132 := \left(\left((2 \times 7) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times (313^2) \right)$$

$$2743134 := \left(2 - \left(- (7) \times \left((\sqrt{4} \times 313)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2743950 := \left(\left(\left((2^7) + (4 \times 3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 50 \right)$$

$$2743964 := \left(\left(\left((2^7) + (4 \times 3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{6^4} \right)$$

$$2743979 := \left(\left(\left((2^7) + (4 \times 3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(- (7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$2743984 := \left(\left(\left((2^7) + (4 \times 3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (8 \times \sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$2743986 := \left(\left(\left((2^7) + (4 \times 3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (8 + 6) \right)$$

$$2743989 := \left(\left(\left(\left((2^7) + (4 \times 3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 8 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$2743991 := \left(\left(\left((2^7) + (4 \times 3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (9 \times 1) \right)$$

$$2743994 := \left(\left(\left((2^7) + (4 \times 3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{9 \times 4} \right)$$

$$2743995 := \left(\left((2 \times 7) \times ((4 - 3) + 9) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 \right)$$

$$2743998 := \left(-2 - \left(\left((7 \times ((4 - 3) + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-8) \right) \right)$$

$$2743999 := \left(\left(\left((2^7) + (4 \times 3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (9/9) \right)$$

$$2748928 := \left((2 \times 7) \times \left(\left((4^8) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (2^8) \right) \right)$$

$$2748964 := \left(2^7 \times (4 - 8 - 9) + 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2752484 &:= \left((2 \times 7) \times \left((5 - 2) \times (4^8) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 2757824 &:= \left(\left((2 + (7^5) + 7) \right) \times 82 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 2758921 &:= \left(\left((2^7) \times (5 + 8) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)^{2 \times 1} \\
 2764794 &:= \left(\left((2 + (7^6)) \right) \times 47 \right) - 9 / \sqrt{4} \\
 2777895 &:= \left(\sqrt{2+7} \times \left(((7 \times 7) + 8)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 2782224 &:= \left(278 \times ((2 + 2) + 2) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2782985 &:= \left(-(27) + (8^{2+\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times 85 \\
 2784855 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{2+7^8} + 4} \right) \times \left((8^5) - 5 \right) \right) \\
 2787127 &:= \left(\sqrt{(2-7)^8 + 7 - 1} \right)^2 \times 7 \\
 2793899 &:= \left(\left((2 + (79^3)) \right) \times (8 + 9) \right) / \sqrt{9} \\
 2794176 &:= \left(((2 \times 7) \times 9)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 176 \\
 2794986 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(2+7)^9} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2795584 &:= \left(((2 \times (7 + 95)) + 5) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2798946 &:= \left(-2 - \left((7 \times 98) - \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times (-6) \\
 2799278 &:= \left(- (2) + \left((7 + \sqrt{9}) \times \left((\sqrt{9} \times 2)^7 \right) - 8 \right) \right) \\
 2799660 &:= \left((2 - 7) - \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^6 \right) \right) \times (-60) \\
 2799907 &:= \left(-2 - \left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (- (9 \times 907)) \right) \right) \\
 2815684 &:= \left(((2 \times 815) + (6 \times 8))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 2829124 &:= \left(\sqrt{2 \times 8} \times (29^{1^2 \times 4}) \right) \\
 2829132 &:= \left(\sqrt{2 \times 8} \times \left((29^{1+3}) + 2 \right) \right) \\
 2829164 &:= \left(- ((2 + 8)) - (29^{\sqrt{16}}) \right) \times (-4) \\
 2829492 &:= \left(\sqrt{2 \times 8} \times \left((29^4) + 92 \right) \right) \\
 2834349 &:= \left((2 \times 8) \times (3^{4+3+4}) \right) - \sqrt{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2834354 &:= \left((2 \times 8) \times (3^{-4+3 \times 5}) \right) + \sqrt{4} \\
 2834368 &:= \left((2 \times 8) - \left(- \left((3^{4+3}) \right) \times \sqrt{6^8} \right) \right) \\
 2834374 &:= \left(-2 - \left(8 \times \left(- (3) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (3^{7+4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2834384 &:= \left((2 \times 8) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^{4 \times (3+8)}} + \sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 2834546 &:= \left(2 - \left(8 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{3^{4 \times 5}}) + 4 \right) \times (-6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2834944 &:= \left(- (2) \times \left(\left((8^3)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - \left((9 \times 4)^4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2836944 &:= \left(\left(- ((2 - 8))^3 \right) \times \left(6 + (9^4) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 2839726 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left((8 + (3 \times \sqrt{9}))^{7-2} \right) + 6 \right) \right) \\
 2845969 &:= \left((2 \times 845) - \sqrt{9} \right)^{6/\sqrt{9}} \\
 2847474 &:= \left(\left(- (2) + \sqrt{8^4} \right) \times 7 \right) \times \left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^4 \right) \\
 2847995 &:= \left((28 \times (47^{\sqrt{9}})) - (9^5) \right) \\
 2849344 &:= \left((2 \times (849 - 3)) - 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2850990 &:= \left((2 + (8^5)) \times \left((0 - \sqrt{9}) + (90) \right) \right) \\
 2858247 &:= \left(\left((2 \times 8) + \sqrt{5^8} \right) - 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 7 \\
 2858919 &:= \left(- ((2 \times 8)) - \left(- (5) \times \left(- ((8 - 91))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 2858925 &:= \left(\left(\left((2 + \sqrt{(8-5)^8})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 2 \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 2858945 &:= \left(\left(\left((2 + \sqrt{(8-5)^8})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 2858965 &:= \left(\left(\left((2 + \sqrt{(8-5)^8})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 6 \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 2862858 &:= \left(2 - \left((8^{\sqrt{6^2}}) - \left((8 \times (5^8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2862864 &:= \left(\left((2 - 8) + \left((6^2) \times 8 \right) \right) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 2863279 &:= \left((2 \times (8 + 63))^{\sqrt{2+7}} - 9 \right) \\
 2863899 &:= \left(- \left(2 - \left((8^6) \times (3 + 8) \right) \right) \right) - (\sqrt{9})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2869759 := (-2) + (-((8 - ((6 + (9^7)) / 5))) \times \sqrt{9}))$$

$$2869795 := (2 + 8) + (((6 + (9^7)) \times \sqrt{9}) / 5)$$

$$2873994 := (2 \times (-8) + (73 \times ((\sqrt{9^9}) + \sqrt{4})))$$

$$2874955 := (2 \times ((-((8 - 74))^{v_9}) \times 5)) - 5$$

$$2881494 := (-((2 - 8)) \times (((81 - 4) \times 9)^{\sqrt{4}}))$$

$$2883204 := (2 - (88 - 3) \times 20)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$2883449 := (((2^{8+8}) - 3) \times 44) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$2883474 := ((-((2 + 8)) + ((8^3)^{\sqrt{4}})) \times (7 + 4))$$

$$2883494 := (-2 - ((8 - ((8^3)^{\sqrt{4}})) \times (9 + \sqrt{4})))$$

$$2883498 := (2 + ((\sqrt{8 \times 8} + 3) \times ((4^9) - 8)))$$

$$2883562 := (-((2 - ((8 \times 8)^3))) \times \sqrt{(5 + 6)^2})$$

$$2883564 := (-(((2 - ((8 \times 8)^3)) \times (5 + 6))) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$2883674 := (2 + ((8 + (8^{\sqrt{36}})) \times (7 + 4)))$$

$$2883694 := ((2 + 8) + (8^{\sqrt{36}})) \times (9 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$2885794 := ((((((2 \times 8) + 8) \times 5) - 7)^{v_9}) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$2892662 := (-((2 + 8)) + (((\sqrt{9} \times 2)^6) \times 62))$$

$$2892666 := (((28 + \sqrt{9}) \times (2 \times (6^6))) - 6)$$

$$2892669 := (((28 + \sqrt{9}) \times (2 \times (6^6))) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$2894440 := ((((((2^8) + 9) + 4)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 40)$$

$$2898918 := (2 \times (((8 + \sqrt{9})^{8-v_9}) \times (1 + 8)))$$

$$2898934 := (2 \times (8 + (9 \times ((8 + \sqrt{9})^{3+\sqrt{4}}))))$$

$$2898954 := ((-((2 - 8)) \times \sqrt{9}) \times (((8 + \sqrt{9})^5) + \sqrt{4}))$$

$$2898999 := (((2 \times ((8 + \sqrt{9})^{8-v_9})) + 9) \times 9)$$

$$2899622 := ((-((2^{8+9})) - \sqrt{9^6}) \times (-22))$$

$$2906496 := (((29 \times 06)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 96)$$

$$2910897 := (((2 + 9)^{\sqrt{1+08}}) \times \sqrt{9^7})$$

$$2910899 := (2 + (((91 + 08)^{v_9}) \times \sqrt{9}))$$

$$2915995 := ((\sqrt{2^{9+1}} \times (5 \times 9)^{v_9}) - 5)$$

$$2915998 := (-2) + ((\sqrt{9} + 1) \times (((5 \times 9)^{v_9}) \times 8))$$

$$2917264 := (2 \times 9 - 1726)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$2919645 := (((2 - 91) \times \sqrt{9^6}) \times (-45))$$

$$2926935 := (((((2 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 2)^6) - ((\sqrt{9} \times 3)^5))$$

$$2928200 := (((2 + 9)^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}}) \times 200)$$

$$2929688 := ((2 + (((\sqrt{9} + 2)^9) \times 6)) / \sqrt{8 + 8})$$

$$2933496 := (-(((2 \times 9)^3)) \times ((3 - \sqrt{4^9}) + 6))$$

$$2943500 := (\sqrt{29^4} \times 3500)$$

$$2947625 := (((2^9) / \sqrt{4}) + (7^6)) \times 25$$

$$2947961 := (((2^9)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (-7)) + (9^{6+1}))$$

$$2948490 := ((2 - 9) + ((4^8) / \sqrt{4})) \times 90$$

$$2948546 := (2 - (9 \times (-(((4^8) \times 5)) + \sqrt{4^6})))$$

$$2948895 := (((-2 - \sqrt{9}) + (\sqrt{4}^{8+8})) \times (9 \times 5))$$

$$2948949 := (((((2 + \sqrt{9}) \times ((4^8) - \sqrt{9})) - 4) \times 9)$$

$$2948965 := ((2 - (((\sqrt{9} - (4^8)) \times 9) + 6)) \times 5)$$

$$2948983 := (-2 - ((\sqrt{9} - (4^8)) \times (9 \times (8 - 3))))$$

$$2948987 := (2 - (((\sqrt{9} \times (4^8)) - 9) \times (-8 + 7)))$$

$$2948995 := ((2 - ((\sqrt{9} - (4^8)) \times \sqrt{9 \times 9})) \times 5)$$

$$2949120 := (((2^{9+4}) \times \sqrt{9}) \times 120)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2949280 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right)^4 \right) \times 9 \right) + 2 \right) \times 80 \right) \\
 2949390 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right)^{-4+9} \right) + 3 \right) \times 90 \right) \right) \\
 2949550 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (29) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(9^5 \right) \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 2952250 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(2 - \left(9^5 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{2+2} \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 2952425 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times \left(9^5 \right) \right) - \left(2/\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 25 \right) \\
 2952545 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times \left(\left(9^5 \right) + 2 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{5^4} \right) - 5 \right) \\
 2952548 &:= \left(-2 - \left(- \left(\left(\left(9^5 \right) + 2 \right) \times 5 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2952650 &:= \left(\left(- (2) + \left(\left(9^{\sqrt{5^2}} \right) + 6 \right) \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 2952950 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 + \left(9^5 \right) \right) + \left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 2956579 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(\sqrt{9^5} \times \left(\left((6 \times 5) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 2956599 &:= \left(\left(-2 - \left(\left((9 - 5) + 65 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times (-9) \right) \\
 2957294 &:= \left(2 \times \left(- (9) + \left(\left(\left((5 \times 7)^2 \right) - 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 2958402 &:= \left(2 + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (5 \times 8) \right) \times 40 \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 2959877 &:= \left(2 + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 5 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 877 \right) \right) \\
 2963440 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left((2 - 9) \times 6 \right)^3 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 40 \right) \right) \\
 2965284 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (2) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(6^{5-2} \right) \times 8 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 2966299 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((2 \times 9) - 6 \right)^6 \right) - 2 \right) - \left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \\
 2966467 &:= \left(-2 - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^6} - 6 \right) \times \left(- \left(4^6 \right) + 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2973696 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times \left(9 + \left(7^3 \right) \right) \right) \right)^{6/\sqrt{9}} \times 6 \right) \\
 2975632 &:= \left(- \left((2 - 9) \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{(7+5)^6} - 3 \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 2979246 &:= \left(\left(- (2) + \sqrt{9^7/9} \right) \times \left(2 + \left(4^6 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2983578 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((2 \times 9) \times 8 \right)^3 \right) - 5 \right) - \sqrt{7^8} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2983799 &:= \left(2 - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(8^{-3+7} \right) \right) \times \left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 2983936 &:= - \left(\left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}+8} \right) - \left((3+9)^{\sqrt{36}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 2984526 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(2^9 \right) \times 8 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left((5-2)^6 \right) \right) \\
 2984832 &:= \left(\left(2 - \left((9 \times 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times \left(- \left((8 \times 3)^2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2985469 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(2^9 \right) - \left((8-5) \times 4^6 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 2985496 &:= \left((2 - (98 \times 5)) + \left((4 \times \sqrt{9})^6 \right) \right) \\
 2985664 &:= \left(\left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 8 \right) \times \left(- \left((5 - (6^6)) \times 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2985859 &:= \left(\left(\left((2 \times 9) \times 8 \right)^{-5+8} \right) - \left(5^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 2985936 &:= -2 \times \sqrt{9} \times 8 + \left((5-9) \times 3 \right)^6 \\
 2985939 &:= \left(\left(- (2) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right)^{-5+9} \right) - 3 \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 2985946 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-8) \right) + 5 \right) \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 4 \right)^6 \right) \right) \\
 2985948 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(2 \times 9 \times 8)^5} \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (4+8) \right) \\
 2985964 &:= \left(- \left(\left((2 \times 9) - \left((8-5) + 9^6 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 2985968 &:= - \left(\left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(\left((8-5) + 9^6 \right) - 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2985969 &:= \left(\left(- (2) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left((8-5) + 9^6 \right) - 9 \right) \right) \\
 2985976 &:= -2^{\sqrt{9}} + (85 - 97)^6 \\
 2985981 &:= \left(-2 - \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right)^5 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / (-8) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 2985983 &:= \left(2 + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right)^5 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / 8 \right) - 3 \right) \\
 2985989 &:= \left(2 + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right)^5 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / 8 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 2985992 &:= \left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(\left((8-5) + 9 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)^2 \right) \\
 2985992 &:= \left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(\left((9-5) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)^2 \right) \\
 2985996 &:= \left(\sqrt{2 \times 9 \times 8} + \left(\left(- \left((5-9) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^6 \right) \right) \\
 2985999 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right)^{-5+9} \right) \right) \times 9 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 2986126 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 6) \right) + \left(12^6 \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2986146 := \left(\left(2 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) + \left(\left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{1 \times 4} \right)^6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2986165 := \left(\left(2 + \left(\sqrt{9^8} \right) \right) \times \left((6+1) \times 65 \right) \right)$$

$$2986359 := \left(\left(\sqrt{2 \times 9 \times 8^6} \right) - \left(- (3) \times \left(5^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2986492 := \left(\left(- (2) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 4 \right)^6 \right) \right) + \left(\left(8^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 2 \right) \right)$$

$$2986493 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{2 \times 9 \times 8^6} \right) + \sqrt{4^9} \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$2986494 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{2 \times 9 \times 8^6} \right) + \sqrt{4^9} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$2986499 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{2 \times 9 \times 8^6} \right) + \sqrt{4^9} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$2988765 := \left(\left(2 - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^8} \right) + 8 \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \times (-65) \right)$$

$$2989359 := \left(\left(\left((2 \times 9) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left((3 \times 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$2989441 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{144^{\sqrt{9}}} \right) - \left((8-9) \right) \right)^2 \right)$$

$$2989674 := \left(\left(2 + (9 \times 8) \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 67 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$2991816 := \left(2 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \times \left((1+81) - 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2991818 := \left(2 + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \times \left((18+1) \times 8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2992576 := \left(2 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) + \sqrt{25} \right) \times 76 \right) \right)$$

$$2992714 := \left(\left(2 + \left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(2 - \left((7+1)^4 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2994168 := \left(\left(\left(2 + \left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \left((4 \times 1)^6 \right) \right) - 8 \right)$$

$$2994173 := \left(\left(\left(2 + \left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \left(4^{-1+7} \right) \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$2994174 := \left(- (2) + \left(\left(\left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left((1+7)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2994176 := \left(\left(2 + \left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \left(4^{17 \times 6} \right) \right)$$

$$2994179 := \left(\left(\left(2 + \left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \left(4^{-1+7} \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$2996359 := \left(- (2) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(9 + \sqrt{9})^6} + 3 \right)^{5 - \sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2996363 := \left(2 + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(9 + \sqrt{9})^6} + 3 \right)^{6/3} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2997479 := \left(2 - \left(\left(9 - \left(\sqrt{9^7} \times 4 \right) \right) \times \left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2999763 := \left(\left(- \left((2 - (9 \times 9)) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right)^6 \right) \right) \times (-3) \right)$$

$$2999822 := \left(- (2) + \left(\left(\left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (8/2) \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2999847 := \left(\left(29^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 8 \right) + \sqrt{4^7} \right) \right)$$

$$2999976 := \left(\left(2 \times \left(- (9) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right)^6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2999979 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(- (2) + \sqrt{9} \right) + 99 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 7 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$2999995 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(- (2) + \sqrt{9} \right) + 99 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$3011499 := \left(\left(3^{011} \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}} \right) + 9 \right) \right)$$

$$3065445 := \left(\left(\left(\left(3^{06} \right) + 54 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$3079296 := \left(\left(3 - \left((0 - 7) \times 9 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(2 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^6 \right) \right)$$

$$3087099 := \left(\left((3 + 08) + \left(70^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$3111696 := \left((31 + 11)^{-6/\sqrt{9}+6} \right)$$

$$3121792 := \left(\left(- \left((31 - (21 \times 7)) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$3124984 := \left((3 + 1) \times 2 \times \left((4 - 9)^8 - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$3125248 := \left(\left(\sqrt{31^2} + \left(\left((5^2)^4 \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$3125288 := \left(\left(- \left((3 \times 12) \right) - \left(\sqrt{5^2} \right)^8 \right) \times (-8) \right)$$

$$3125824 := \left(\left((3 + 1) + \left((2 + (5 \times 8))^2 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$3134784 := \left(\left(\left(313^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 7 \right) \times (8 \times 4) \right)$$

$$3144984 := \left(\left(\left(31 \times \sqrt{4} \right) - \left(4^9 \right) \right) \times \left(- (8 + 4) \right) \right)$$

$$3144996 := \left(- \left(\left(3 \times \left(1 - \left(4 \times \left(4^9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9^6} \right)$$

$$3144999 := \left(\left(\left((3 \times 1) \times 4 \right) \times \left(4^9 \right) \right) - \left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$3145482 := \left(3 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{1 \times 4^{5 \times 4}} \right) - (82) \right) \right)$$

$$3145578 := \left(3 \times \left(- \left(\left(1 - \left(4^{5+5} \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{78}} \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3145726 &:= \left(-((3-1)) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{5+7 \times 2}} \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 3145734 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\sqrt{1 \times 4} + \left((5 \times 7) - 3^4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 3145743 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((3-1)^4 \right)^5 \right) + 7 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 3 \\
 3145759 &:= \left(31 + \left(\left((4+5) + 7 \right)^5 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 3146484 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(1 + (4^6) \right) \times \sqrt{4^8} - 4 \right) \right) \\
 3146488 &:= \left(\left(3 \times \left(1 + (4^6) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4^8} - 8 \right) \\
 3146496 &:= \left((3-1) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4^6} + (4^9) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 3176472 &:= \left(3 \times \left(1 - \left(- \left((7^6) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (7+2) \right) \right) \\
 3176493 &:= \left(- (3) - \left(\left(1 + (7^6) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (- (9 \times 3)) \right) \\
 3176494 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(1 + (7^6) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 9 \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 3176496 &:= \left(\left(- \left(3 \times \left(1 - (7^6) \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \\
 3176544 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(1 + (7^6) \right) \times (5+4) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 3176554 &:= \left(31 - \left(- \left((7^6) \right) \times (5 \times 5) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 3176736 &:= \left(- (3) - \left(- \left(1 + \left((7^6) + 7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{3^6} \right) \right) \\
 3177488 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{1+7} \right) + \left(7 - \sqrt{4} \right)^8 \right) \right) \times 8 \\
 3178695 &:= \left(- (317) + \left(86^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times 5 \\
 3188406 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{18 \times 8}} \right) - 40 \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 3188616 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{18 \times 8}} \right) - (6-1) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 3188623 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{18 \times 8}} \right) \times 6 \right) - (23) \right) \\
 3188634 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{18 \times 8}} \right) \times 6 \right) - (3 \times 4) \right) \\
 3188638 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{1+8+8}} \right) \times (6 \times 3) \right) - 8 \right) \\
 3188641 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{18 \times 8}} \right) \times 6 \right) - (4+1) \right) \\
 3188642 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{18 \times 8}} \right) \times 6 \right) - \sqrt{4^2} \right) \\
 3188643 &:= \left(\left(3 \times \left(\left((1^8) + 8 \right)^6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3188644 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{18 \times 8}} \right) \times 6 \right) - 4 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 3188645 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{18 \times 8}} \right) \times 6 \right) + ((4-5)) \right) \\
 3188648 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{18 \times 8}} \right) \times 6 \right) + \sqrt{-4+8} \right) \\
 3188649 &:= \left(\left(\left(3 \times \left(\left((1^8) + 8 \right)^6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 3188651 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{18 \times 8}} \right) \times 6 \right) + (5 \times 1) \right) \\
 3188664 &:= \left(\left(3 + \left(\left((1^8) + 8 \right)^6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^4}} \right) \\
 3188674 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{18 \times 8}} \right) \times 6 \right) + ((7 \times 4)) \right) \\
 3188682 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{18 \times 8}} \right) + 6 \right) \times (8-2) \right) \\
 3189969 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(1 - \left((8 + (\sqrt{9^9})) \times (-6) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 3194455 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{3^{1+9}} - \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 55 \right) \\
 3196844 &:= \left(\left(3 \times \left(1 + (9^6) \right) \right) + (8^4) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 3208329 &:= \left((3 + (20 \times 8)) \times \left(\sqrt{3^{2 \times 9}} \right) \right) \\
 3211264 &:= \left(\left(\left((3^{2+1}) + 1 \right) \times (2^6) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 3221199 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left((2 + 211)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / 9 \right) \right) \\
 3226926 &:= \left(\left(- (3) + \left((2 + (2 \times 6))^{\sqrt{9+2}} \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 3226944 &:= \left(\left(3 \times \left((2 + (2 \times 6))^{9-4} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 3241789 &:= \left(- (3) + \left(- \left((2 \times ((4 \times 1) - 78)) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 3255219 &:= \left(\left(32 + \left((5^5)^2 \right) \right) / \sqrt{1 \times 9} \right) \\
 3266270 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{3^2} + \left((6^6) + 2 \right) \right) \right) \times 70 \\
 3268832 &:= \left(- (32) + \left(\left(\sqrt{6^8} + (8^3) \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 3268864 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{\left((3-2) \times 6 \right)^8 + \sqrt{8^6}} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 3276726 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(3 + \sqrt{(2+7)^6} \right) + 7 \right)^2 \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 3276800 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(3^2+7)^6} \right) \times 800 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$3276950 := \left(\left(3 + \left(2^{7+6+\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times 50 \right)$$

$$3278163 := \left(- (3) + \left(\left(-2 - \left((7 \times 8)^{\sqrt{16}} \right) \right) / (-3) \right) \right)$$

$$3278169 := \left(3 - \left(\left(-2 - \left((7 \times 8)^{\sqrt{16}} \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$3278695 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(3^{2+7} \right) \right) - \left(86^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$3280500 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{3^{2^8}} \right) \times 0500 \right) \right)$$

$$3294167 := \left(3 - \left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(\left(4 \times \left((1+6)^7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3294184 := \left(\left(3 + \left(- \left((2-9)^{\sqrt{41+8}} \right) \right) \right) \times 4 \right)$$

$$3294225 := \left(\left(\left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{(2+9)^4} \right)^2 \right) \times 25 \right) \right)$$

$$3294297 := \left(\left((3+2)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(4 \times \left(- \left((2-9)^7 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3307949 := \left(\left((3 \times 30) + \left((7 \times 9) - 4 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$3319866 := \left(\left(\sqrt{3 \times 3^{-1+9}} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{8^6} - 6 \right) \right)$$

$$3322344 := \left(\left(\left(\left((3 \times 32) - 2 \right)^3 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 4 \right)$$

$$3327786 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{33^2} \times (-7) \right) \times \sqrt{7^8} \right) \times (-6) \right) \right)$$

$$3358784 := \left(\left(\left(\left(3^{3+5} \right) \times 8 \right) - 7 \right) \times \sqrt{8^4} \right)$$

$$3359194 := \left(\left(\left((3+3)^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) - (19) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3359216 := \left(\left(\left((3+3)^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \right) - (16) \right)$$

$$3359224 := \left(\left(\left((3+3)^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \right) - (2 \times 4) \right)$$

$$3359225 := \left(\left(\left((3+3)^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \right) - (2+5) \right)$$

$$3359227 := \left(\left(\left((3+3)^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \right) + (2-7) \right)$$

$$3359228 := \left(\left(\left((3+3)^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \right) - \sqrt{2 \times 8} \right)$$

$$3359229 := \left(\left(\left((3+3)^{(-5+9) \times 2} \right) \times 2 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$3359233 := \left(\left(\left((3+3)^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \right) + (3/3) \right)$$

$$3359234 := \left(\left(\left((3+3)^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left((2-3) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3359235 := \left(3 - \left((3-5) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 2 \right)^{3+5} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3359238 := \left((3+3) - \left(\left((5-\sqrt{9}) \times \left(- \left((2 \times 3)^8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3359248 := \left(\left(\left((3+3)^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \right) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times (-8) \right) \right)$$

$$3359252 := \left(\left(\left((3+3)^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) + (2 \times 5) \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$3359664 := \left(\left(\left((3+3)^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) + \sqrt{6^6} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3360684 := \left(- \left(\left((3 - (3^6)) - (06^8) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3364422 := \left(\left(\left(\left((3/3) + (6^4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 2 \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$3364424 := \left(3 + \left(-3 + 6^4 + 4 \right)^2 \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$3374529 := \left(3 \times \left(- \left((3 \times 7) \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 52 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3374589 := \left(- (3) - \left(- (3) \times \left(- \left((7 - (4 \times 5)) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3374950 := \left(3 + 3 \times \sqrt{7^4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 50$$

$$3374964 := \left(3 + 3 \times \sqrt{7^4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{6^4}$$

$$3374979 := \left(3 + 3 \times \sqrt{7^4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 7 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$3374984 := \left(3 + 3 \times \sqrt{7^4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$3374986 := \left(3 + 3 \times \sqrt{7^4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 - 6$$

$$3374989 := \left(3 + 3 \times \sqrt{7^4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$3374991 := \left(3 + 3 \times \sqrt{7^4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9 \times 1$$

$$3374994 := \left(3 + 3 \times \sqrt{7^4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9 \times 4}$$

$$3374995 := \left(\left((3 \times ((37+4)+9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$3374999 := \left(- \left((3/3) \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{7^4 \times 9} + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$3375003 := \left(3 + \left(\sqrt{(3 \times 7500)^3} \right) \right)$$

$$3375048 := \left((3+3) \times \left(\left(750^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 8 \right) \right)$$

$$3385202 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(3+3)^8} + 5 \right)^2 \right) \right) \times 02 \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3407866 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{4}) - (0 - 7) \right) \times (8^6) \right) - 6 \right) \\
 3407869 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{4}) - (0 - 7) \right) \times (8^6) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 3418804 &:= \left(3 + \left(\left(41 + \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}} \right)^{04} \right) \right) \\
 3425664 &:= \left(3 \times \left((4^{2 \times 5}) + \left((6^6) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 3429500 &:= \left(\left((3 + (4^2))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 500 \right) \\
 3429503 &:= \left(3 + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(2 \times (95^{03}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 3429534 &:= \left(\sqrt{34^2} + \left((95^3) \times 4 \right) \right) \\
 3429539 &:= \left(3 - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(2 \times \left((95^3) + 9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 3437368 &:= \left(\left(3 - \left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \right) \right) \times \left(- (36 + 8) \right) \right) \\
 3437441 &:= \left(\left((3 \times 437)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \sqrt{4} - 1 \right) \\
 3437442 &:= \left(\left((3 \times 437)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times (4 - 2) \right) \\
 3437444 &:= \left(\left((3 \times 437)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 3437452 &:= \left(\left((3 \times 437)^{\sqrt{4}} + 5 \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 3437469 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left((437^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 6 \right) + 9 \right) \right) \\
 3437496 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left((437^{\sqrt{4}}) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 3439875 &:= \left(\left(- \left((34^3) \right) - \left(\sqrt{9^8} \right) \right) \times (-75) \right) \\
 3444500 &:= \left(\left(\left((3^4) + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 500 \right) \\
 3444525 &:= \left(\left(3^{\sqrt{(4^4)/4}} \right) \times 525 \right) \\
 3448449 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left((3 + \sqrt{4})^4 \right) - 8 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 3448926 &:= \left(\left((3 + (4 \times (4 + 8)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 26 \right) \\
 3449943 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(\left((44 \times \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) - 3 \right) \right) \\
 3449944 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (3) \times \left((\sqrt{4} + (4^{\sqrt{9}}))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-4) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3449946 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 \times 44)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / \sqrt{4} - 6 \right) \\
 3449949 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 \times 44)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / \sqrt{4} - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 3449984 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (3) \times \left((\sqrt{4} + (4^{\sqrt{9}}))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) - 8 \right) \times (-4) \right) \\
 3455932 &:= \left(\left(34 - \left(\left(- (5) + (5^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)^3 \right) \right) \times (-2) \right) \\
 3455984 &:= \left(\left((3 \times (45 - 5))^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 3455994 &:= \left(\left((3 \times (45 - 5))^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 3455995 &:= \left(\left((3 \times (4^5)) \times \left((5^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 9 \right) \right) - 5 \right) \\
 3455999 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((3 \times 4)^5 \right) \right) \times (5^{\sqrt{9}}) + 9 \right) / (-9) \right) \\
 3457440 &:= ((3 - 45) \times 7)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 40 \\
 3457446 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^4 \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 3458895 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (3) \times \left((\sqrt{4} + 5)^8 \right) \right) - (8 \times 9) \right) / (-5) \right) \\
 3474726 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{4^7 \times 4}) - 7 \right)^2 \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 3481450 &:= \left(\sqrt{(3 + 4)^8} \times 1450 \right) \\
 3483648 &:= \left(\left((3 \times 4)^{8-3} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^4} + 8} \right) \right) \\
 3488994 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(3 + 4)^8} - 8 \right) \times \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 3493875 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 9)^3 \right) \times 875 \right) \right) \\
 3495879 &:= \left(\left((3^{\sqrt{49}}) - \left((5^8) - 7 \right) \right) \times (-9) \right) \\
 3496466 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 + (\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}}))^6 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - (6^6) \right) \\
 3496787 &:= \left(\left((3 + \sqrt{4}) \times \left(- (9 - (6^7)) \right) \right) + (8^7) \right) \\
 3498656 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} + 8 \right) \times \left(- (6 - (5^6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 3498975 &:= \left(-3 + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{(4 \times 9)^{8 \times \sqrt{9}}}}} \right) \times 75 \\
 3499125 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left((4 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 1 \right) \times 25 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3499200 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 9\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times 200\right)\right) \\
 3499275 &:= \left(\left(3 + \left(\left(4 \times 9\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - 2\right)\right) \times 75 \\
 3499575 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(3 \times 4\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}} + 5\right)\right) \times 75 \\
 3499725 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(\left(4 \times 9\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + 7\right)\right) \times 25 \\
 3511799 &:= \left(\left(35 + 117\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9\right) \\
 3515475 &:= \left(\left(-\left(3 \times \left(5^{1+5}\right)\right)\right) + \sqrt{4}\right) \times (-75) \\
 3515499 &:= \left(\left(\left(3 \times 5\right) - 1\right) - \left(5^{\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}}}\right)\right) \times (-9) \\
 3515599 &:= \left(-35 + \left(\left(-1\right) - \left(5^{5+\sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times (-9)\right) \\
 3515619 &:= 3 + \left(5^{\sqrt{-1+5+6}} - 1\right) \times 9 \\
 3515629 &:= \left(\sqrt{3 \times 5 + 1} + \left(\left(5^{6+2}\right) \times 9\right)\right) \\
 3515643 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(5 + 1\right) + \left(\left(5^{\sqrt{64}}\right) \times 3\right)\right)\right) \\
 3515649 &:= \left(3 \times 5 + \left(\left(-1\right) - \left(5^{\sqrt{64}}\right)\right) \times (-9)\right) \\
 3515715 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{5-1} + \left(5^7\right)\right) \times 15\right)\right) \\
 3515849 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^5\right) - 1\right) - \left(\left(-\left(5^8\right)\right) + \sqrt{4}\right) \times 9\right) \\
 3515869 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^5\right) + 1\right) - \left(\left(5^8\right) \times \left(-6 - \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \\
 3526884 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\sqrt{5^{2+6}} + 8/8\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 3529464 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(\left(5 \times 2\right) \times \left(\left(9 - \sqrt{4}\right)^6\right)\right) - \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 3529465 &:= \left(\left(\left(3 \times 5\right) \times 2\right) \times \left(\left(9 - \sqrt{4}\right)^6\right) - 5\right) \\
 3536379 &:= \left(\left(3 + 536\right) \times \left(3^7\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 3536405 &:= \left(\left(\left(-\left(3 - 5\right)\right) + \sqrt{3^6}\right)^4\right) \times 05 \\
 3536445 &:= \left(\left(3 + 5\right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{3^6} + \sqrt{4}\right)^4\right)\right) \times 5 \\
 3536448 &:= \left(3 - \left(-5\right) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{3^6} + \sqrt{4}\right)^4\right) + 8\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3538926 &:= \left(\left(3 - \left(\left(\left(5 - 3\right)^8\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right)^2\right)\right) \times (-6) \\
 3538942 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(3 + 5\right) \times 3\right) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{9}} / \sqrt{4} - 2\right) \\
 3538944 &:= \left(\sqrt{3^5} \times 3 \times \left(\left(8^{9-4}\right) \times 4\right)\right) \\
 3538947 &:= \left(3 - \left(\left(-\left(\left(5 - 3\right) - 8\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times \left(-\left(4^7\right)\right)\right) \\
 3541860 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(3^5\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) - 18\right)\right) \times 60 \\
 3541924 &:= \left(\left(\left(3 \times \left(5^4\right)\right) + \left(\left(1 \times 9\right) - 2\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 3542460 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(3^5\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) - 2 \times 4\right)\right) \times 60 \\
 3542730 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(3^5\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times 2\right) - 7\right) \times 30 \\
 3542760 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(3^5\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) - \sqrt{2+7}\right)\right) \times 60 \\
 3542955 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(\left(-5\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(-2 \times \left(9^5\right)\right)\right) + 5\right) \\
 3542975 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(3^5\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right)^2\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) + 7\right) \times 5 \\
 3542983 &:= \left(3 - \left(-\left(5 \times 4\right)\right) \times \left(2 + \left(\sqrt{9^{8+3}}\right)\right)\right) \\
 3544860 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(3^5\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) + \left(4 \times 8\right)\right)\right) \times 60 \\
 3544870 &:= \left(\left(\left(3 \times 5\right)^4\right) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-8\right)\right)\right) \times 70 \\
 3547260 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(3^5\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) + 72\right)\right) \times 60 \\
 3549428 &:= \left(\left(\left(3 \times \left(5^4\right)\right) + 9\right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 28\right) \\
 3549429 &:= \left(\left(-3\right) + \left(\left(5^4\right) + \sqrt{9}\right)^{4-2}\right) \times 9 \\
 3549446 &:= \left(3 \times 5^4 + 9\right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 4 - 6 \\
 3549447 &:= \left(3 \times 5^4 + 9\right)^{\sqrt{4}} - \sqrt{4} - 7 \\
 3549448 &:= \left(3 \times 5^4 + 9\right)^{4-\sqrt{4}} - 8 \\
 3549449 &:= \left(3 \times 5^4 + 9\right)^{\sqrt{4}} - \sqrt{49} \\
 3549451 &:= \left(3 \times 5^4 + 9\right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 5 \times 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3549455 &:= (3 \times 5^4 + 9)^{\sqrt{4}} - 5/5 \\
 3549456 &:= (3 \times 5^4 + 9)^{\sqrt{4}} \times (-5 + 6) \\
 3549461 &:= (3 \times 5^4 + 9)^{\sqrt{4}} + 6 - 1 \\
 3549462 &:= (3 \times 5^4 + 9)^{\sqrt{4}} + \sqrt{6^2} \\
 3549464 &:= (3 \times 5^4 + 9)^{\sqrt{4}} + \sqrt{64} \\
 3557448 &:= (3 \times (((55 \times 7)^{\sqrt{4}}) + \sqrt{4}) \times 8)) \\
 3564450 &:= (((3^5) + (6 \times 4))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 50 \\
 3564542 &:= (((3 + 56) \times \sqrt{4^5})^{\sqrt{4}}) - 2 \\
 3564544 &:= (((3 + 5) \times ((64 - 5) \times 4))^{\sqrt{4}}) \\
 3579664 &:= (((-3) + (5 \times ((7^{\sqrt{9}}) + (6 \times 6))))^{\sqrt{4}}) \\
 3583449 &:= ((((-3) + \sqrt{5^8}) + \sqrt{3^4})^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 9 \\
 3587228 &:= (((3 \times (\sqrt{5^8} + 7)) - 2)^2) - 8 \\
 3594816 &:= ((3 - 5) \times 948)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}} \\
 3601989 &:= (3 \times (60 + 1)) \times ((\sqrt{9^8}) \times \sqrt{9}) \\
 3601992 &:= (3 - ((60 + 1)) \times (9^{\sqrt{9+2}})) \\
 3616812 &:= (3 \times (((61 \times 6) \times \sqrt{8+1})^2)) \\
 3618727 &:= (((((3^6) - \sqrt{1+8}) - 7)^2) \times 7) \\
 3634582 &:= (((3 \times 6)^3) + \sqrt{4}) \times (\sqrt{5^8} - 2) \\
 3638887 &:= (((((3 + 6)^3) - 8)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}}) \times 7) \\
 3643542 &:= (-((3^6)) \times ((\sqrt{4^3} \times (-5^4))) + 2) \\
 3644964 &:= (-((3 \times 6)) \times (\sqrt{4} - ((4 \times (9 + 6^4))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3645000 &:= ((\sqrt{3^6}^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 5000) \\
 3646458 &:= ((3^6) \times (\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{64 \times 5^8})) \\
 3647034 &:= ((3 + 6) \times (((4 + 70)^3) + \sqrt{4})) \\
 3647119 &:= (\sqrt{3^6} + 4) \times 7^{(1+1) \times \sqrt{9}} \\
 3652264 &:= (-(((3 - 6) \times 52) + 2))^{6/\sqrt{4}} \\
 3652279 &:= (-(((3 - 6) \times 5)) + ((22 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}})) \\
 3654993 &:= ((3 - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^{\sqrt{9}})) \times (-93)) \\
 3655935 &:= (-((3^6)) \times (((5 + 5)^{\sqrt{9}}) + 3) \times (-5)) \\
 3657396 &:= (\sqrt{3^6} \times ((5^7) + ((3 \times \sqrt{9})^6))) \\
 3657399 &:= (3 - (-6) \times ((5^7) + (3^{9+\sqrt{9}}))) \\
 3667950 &:= (((3^6) - ((6 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}})) \times (-50)) \\
 3669974 &:= (-(((3 - (((6 \times 6) / 9)^9)) \times 7)) \times \sqrt{4}) \\
 3674924 &:= (((\sqrt{3^6} + 7)^4) \times (-9 + 2)) / (-4) \\
 3684753 &:= (3 + (6 \times (((8 + \sqrt{4}) + 75)^3))) \\
 3686400 &:= ((-((3 \times 6)) \times \sqrt{8^6}) \times (-400)) \\
 3687918 &:= (3 \times (-6) + (((8 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-1 - 8))) \\
 3687954 &:= (3 \times (6 - (((8 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-5 - \sqrt{4}))) \\
 3687957 &:= (3 \times ((-6) - (((8 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}}) - 5)) \times (-7)) \\
 3687978 &:= (3 \times (6 + (((8 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 7) + 8)) \\
 3696894 &:= ((3 \times 6) \times ((-((9 - 68))^{\sqrt{9}}) + 4)) \\
 3697488 &:= 3^6 \times (9 + \sqrt{(7 - \sqrt{4})^8}) \times 8 \\
 3698994 &:= (((-3) - (6 \times ((\sqrt{9^8}) - \sqrt{9}))) \times (-94)) \\
 3717696 &:= (3 + (-7) \times ((-1) + \sqrt{7^6}) - (9^6)) \\
 3719649 &:= (3 + (-7) \times (-((1 + (9^6)))) + (4^{\sqrt{9}}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$3719898 := \left(-((3 \times 7)) \times \left(1 - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{8+\sqrt{9}}} \right) - 8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3719919 := \left(-((3 \times 7)) \times \left(-1 - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) - 1 \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3719947 := \left(\left(- \left(\left((3 \times 7) - 1 \right) \right) + \left(9^{\sqrt{9 \times 4}} \right) \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$3719957 := \left(3 - \left(-7 \right) \times \left(-19 + \left(\sqrt{9^{5+7}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3720087 := \left(\left(3^{7+\sqrt{200/8}} \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$3721734 := \left(\left(\left(3 \times \left(\left((7^2) - 1 \right) - 7 \right) \right)^3 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3721925 := \left(\left(\left(3 + \left((7^2) + 1 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 25 \right)$$

$$3722494 := \left(\left(\left(3 + \left((7 \times 2)^2 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 94 \right)$$

$$3723872 := \left(-3 + \left(\left(\left((7^2) \times 3 \right) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{7+2}} \right) \right)$$

$$3723873 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{-3+7} - \left(\left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{3^8}) - 7 \right)^3 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3723879 := \left(- \left((3 - 7) \right) + \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{3^8}) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$3728249 := \left(\left(\left((3^7) - (2^8) \right)^2 \right) - \sqrt{4^9} \right)$$

$$3732480 := \left(\left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{7-3} \right)^{2+4} \right) \times 80 \right)$$

$$3735396 := \left(\left((3 \times 7) \times (3^5) \right) \times \left(3 + \sqrt{9^6} \right) \right)$$

$$3742848 := \left(3 \times \left(7 \times 4 - 2^8 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 8$$

$$3744226 := \left(\left((37^4) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - \left((2+2)^6 \right) \right)$$

$$3744520 := \left(\left((3 \times (7^4)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 520 \right)$$

$$3745822 := \left(\left((37^4) - \left(\sqrt{5^8} \times 2 \right) \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$3746594 := \left(\left((37^4) - \left((6^5) / 9 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3746694 := \left(\left(37 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(6 + \left((6+9)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3747275 := \left(\left((3^7) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(\left((7^2) \times 7 \right) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$3747628 := \left(\left(- \left((37^4) \right) + \sqrt{7^6} \right) \times (-2) - 8 \right)$$

$$3747636 := \left(\left(- \left((37^4) \right) + \sqrt{7^6} \right) / (-3) \times 6 \right)$$

$$3747644 := \left(\left(\left((37^4) - \sqrt{7^6} \right) + 4 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3747979 := \left(- \left(\left((37^4) \times (7-9) \right) \right) - \left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$3748094 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{-3+7} - \left(\left(-4 \right) \times \left(-8 - \sqrt{0^9} \right) \right)^4 \right) \right)$$

$$3748174 := \left(\left(\left((37^4) - 81 \right) + 7 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3748194 := \left(\left((37^4) + (8 \times (1-9)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3748261 := \left(\left((37^4) \times \sqrt{8/2} \right) - (61) \right)$$

$$3748274 := \left(\left((37^4) - (8 \times \sqrt{2+7}) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3748294 := \left(\left(\left((37^4) - 8 \right) \times 2 \right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times 4 \right) \right)$$

$$3748298 := \left(\left((37^4) \times \sqrt{8/2} \right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-8) \right) \right)$$

$$3748314 := \left(\left(\left(\left((37^4) - 8 \right) + 3 \right) + 1 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3748319 := \left(\left(\left((37^4) \times 8 \right) / (3+1) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$3748324 := \left(\left(\left((37^4) - 8 \right) + (3^2) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3748328 := \left(\left((37^{-4+8}) + 3 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \right)$$

$$3748329 := \left(\left(\left(\left((37^4) + 8 \right) - 3 \right) \times 2 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$3748332 := \left(\left(\left((37^4) + 8 \right) - \sqrt{3 \times 3} \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$3748334 := \left(\left((37^{-4+8}) + (3+3) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3748342 := \left(\left(\left(\left((37^4) + 8 \right) + 3 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - 2 \right)$$

$$3748344 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left((37^4) + 8 \right) + 3 \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-4) \right)$$

$$3748354 := \left(\left(\left(\left((37^4) + 8 \right) + 3 \right) + 5 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3748434 := \left(\left(\left((37^4) - 8 \right) + (4^3) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$3748442 := \left(\left(\left((37^4) + \sqrt{8^4} \right) - 4 \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$3748445 := \left(\left(\left((37^4) + \sqrt{8^4} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$3748462 := \left(\left(\left((37^4) + \sqrt{8^4} \right) + 6 \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$3748482 := \left(\left((37^4) - \left((8 + \sqrt{4}) \times (-8) \right) \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3748500 &:= \left(\sqrt{(3 \times 7)^4} \times 8500 \right) \\
 3749778 &:= \left(3 \times \left(- (74) + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 7)^7 \right) / 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 3757995 &:= \left(\left(- \left((3 - 7)^5 \right) + 7 \right) \times \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 3763827 &:= \left((3^7) \times \left(\sqrt{(6^3 \times 8)^2} - 7 \right) \right) \\
 3764586 &:= \left(\left(- \left((3 - (7^6)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4^5} \right) - (86) \\
 3764648 &:= \left(3 - \left(\left(\left((7^6) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - 6 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times (-8) \\
 3764669 &:= \left(\left((3 - (7^6)) \times (4 - (6 \times 6)) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 3764723 &:= \left(- (3) - \left(- (7) \times \left(- (6) + \left((\sqrt{4} \times 7)^{2+3} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 3764728 &:= \left(\left(- \left((3 - (7^6)) \times 4 \right) \right) + \sqrt{7^2} \right) \times 8 \\
 3764729 &:= \left(3 - \left(- (7) \times \left(- (6) + \left((\sqrt{4} \times 7)^{2+\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 3764747 &:= \left(- (3) + \left((7 \times (6 - 4))^{7-\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times 7 \\
 3764762 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{-3+7} \times (-6) \right) + \left((\sqrt{4} \times 7)^6 \right) \right) / 2 \right) \\
 3764764 &:= \left(\left(- \left((3 - 7) \right) \times \sqrt{64} \right) \times (7^6) \right) - 4 \\
 3764771 &:= \left(3 + \left(\left((7^6) \times 4 \right) \times (\sqrt{7 \times 7} + 1) \right) \right) \\
 3764773 &:= \left(\left((3 + 7) + \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right) \\
 3764774 &:= \left(3 - \left(- \left((7^6) \right) \times (\sqrt{4} + (7 + 7)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 3764784 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((3 - (7^6)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - 7 \right) \times (-8) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 3764814 &:= \left((3 + 7^6 \times \sqrt{4}) \times 8 - 1 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 3764816 &:= \left(3 + 7^6 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times 8 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{16}} \\
 3764829 &:= \left(- (3) - \left(- \left(\left((7^6) \times 4 \right) + 8 \right) \right) \times (2^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \\
 3764842 &:= \left(\left(3 - \left(- \left((7^6) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 8 \right) \times 4 \right) - 2 \\
 3764844 &:= \left(3 - \left(- \left((7^6) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4 \times 4} \\
 3764854 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((3 + (7^6)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times 8 \right) - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3764857 &:= \left(3 + 7^6 \right) \times \sqrt{(-4 + 8)^5} - 7 \\
 3764862 &:= \left(\left((3 + (7^6)) \times (4 \times 8) \right) - \sqrt{6-2} \right) \\
 3771364 &:= \left(\left((3^7) + (7 \times (1 - 36)) \right) \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 3772575 &:= \left(\left((3^7) \times \sqrt{7+2} \right) \times 575 \right) \\
 3774762 &:= 3^7 \times \left(\sqrt{(7 - \sqrt{4} + 7)^6} - 2 \right) \\
 3776652 &:= \left(3 \times \left((7 + \left(- (7) - \sqrt{6^6} \right) \times (-5)) \right)^2 \right) \\
 3776949 &:= \left((3^7) \times \left(- ((7 - 6)) + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 4)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 3778968 &:= \left(\left(- \left((3^7) \right) + \left((78^{\sqrt{9}}) + 6 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 3779136 &:= \sqrt{3^{7+7} \times (9 \times 1 + 3)^6} \\
 3779582 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{-3+7} - \left(\left((7 + (9^5)) \times (8^2) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 3779584 &:= \left(- \left(\left((3 - 7) \times \left((7 + (9^5)) \times 8 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 3779654 &:= \left(\left((37 \times 7) + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 6)^5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 3785697 &:= \left(3 + \sqrt{\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8} + 5}} \right)^6} \right) \times \sqrt{9^7} \\
 3795875 &:= - \left(\left((3 + 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left((5 \times (8 + 7)^5) \right) \right) \\
 3796275 &:= \left(\left((37^{\sqrt{9}}) - \left((6^2) \right) \right) \times 75 \right) \\
 3796855 &:= \left(\left(- \left((3 - 7) \right) - \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \right)^5 \right) \right) \right) \times (-5) \\
 3796873 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{-3+7} - \left(9 \times \left((68 + 7)^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 3796879 &:= \left(- \left((3 - 7) \right) + \left(9 \times \left((68 + 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 3796895 &:= \left(\left((3 - 7) - \left((9 + 6)^{8-\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times (-5) \right) \\
 3796925 &:= \left(\left(- \left((3 + 7) \right) - \left((9 + 6)^{\sqrt{9}+2} \right) \right) \times (-5) \right) \\
 3797666 &:= \left(- \left((3 + 79) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{7^6} - (6^6) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3798603 &:= \left((3^7) + \left((\sqrt{9} \times (- (8 - 60)))^3 \right) \right) \\
 3798819 &:= \left((3^7) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 8)) + 1 \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 3798975 &:= \left((37^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (- ((8 - 9) \times 75)) \right) \\
 3799575 &:= \left(\left(\left((37^{\sqrt{9}}) + \sqrt{9} \right) + 5 \right) \times 75 \right) \\
 3822847 &:= \left(\left(\left((3^{8-2}) + (2 + 8) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 3827978 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 + \sqrt{8/2})^7 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{78}} \right) \\
 3833854 &:= \left(\left((38 \times 3) + 3 \right) \times (8^5) \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 3833859 &:= \left(\left((38 \times 3) + 3 \right) \times (8^5) \right) + \sqrt{9} \\
 3834747 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{38^3}) + \left((4^7) - 4 \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \\
 3837736 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{38^3}) \times 7 \right) + (7^{\sqrt{36}}) \right) \\
 3847500 &:= \sqrt{38} \times 47500 \\
 3849444 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{38} \times 4) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (\sqrt{4} + 4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 3859527 &:= \left(\left(- ((3 - 85))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (5 + 2) \right) \times 7 \\
 3859597 &:= \left(3 + \left(- ((8 + 5) - 95)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times 7 \\
 3859618 &:= \left(\left(- ((3 - 85))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 6 \right) \times (- (1 - 8)) \\
 3868715 &:= (3 + 8)^6 + 8^7 + \sqrt{-1 + 5} \\
 3868745 &:= (3 + 8)^6 + 8^7 + \sqrt{4^5} \\
 3868794 &:= (3 + 8)^6 + 8^7 + \sqrt{9^4} \\
 3868928 &:= (3 - 8)^6 - 8^{\sqrt{9}} \times 2^8 \\
 3871464 &:= \left(\left(3 \times (8 \times 71)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 6 \right) \times 4 \\
 3871488 &:= 3 \times \left(\left((8 \times 71)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \sqrt{8 + 8} \right) \\
 3875093 &:= \left((3 \times 8) + 7 \right) \times \left((50^{\sqrt{9}}) + 3 \right) \\
 3878496 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 + 8) + \sqrt{78} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) / (-9) \right) \times (-6) \\
 3881193 &:= \left(- (3) - \left(\sqrt{8 + 8} \times \left(- ((11 \times 9)^3) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3881199 &:= \left(3 + \left(\sqrt{8 + 8} \times \left((11 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 3886215 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (3) + \sqrt{\sqrt{8 \times 8^6}} \right)^2 \right) \times 15 \right) \\
 3892990 &:= \left(- ((3 - 8)) \times \left((92^{\sqrt{9}}) - (90) \right) \right) \\
 3893395 &:= \left(\left((3 + 89)^{\sqrt{3 \times 3}} \right) - 9 \right) \times 5 \\
 3893475 &:= \left(\left((3 + 89)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^4}}} \right) + 7 \right) \times 5 \\
 3893495 &:= \left(\left(- \left((3 + 89)^3 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) - 9 \times (-5) \\
 3895912 &:= \left((38^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (59 + 12) \right) \\
 3896667 &:= \left(\sqrt{38} \times \left((\sqrt{96} \times 66) - 7 \right) \right) \\
 3897227 &:= \sqrt{38 \times 9^7} \times 22 - 7 \\
 3897234 &:= \left(- ((3 + 8)) \times \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times \left(- (2 \times (3^4)) \right) \\
 3897246 &:= \left(\left((3^8) \times (97 + 2) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 6 \\
 3897322 &:= \left(\left((3^{8+\sqrt{9}}) + (7 - 3) \right) \times 22 \right) \\
 3897366 &:= \left(\left((3^8) \times 9 \right) + \sqrt{7 - 3} \right) \times 66 \\
 3916917 &:= \left(3^9 \right) \times \left(\left((1 \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (17) \right) \\
 3925927 &:= 3^9 - 2 \times \left(-5^9 + \sqrt{2 + 7} \right) \\
 3925943 &:= 3^9 - 2 \times \left(-5^9 - \sqrt{4} - 3 \right) \\
 3925947 &:= 3^9 + 2 \times 5^9 + \sqrt{4} \times 7 \\
 3925949 &:= 3^9 + 2 \times \left(5^9 + \sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}} \right) \\
 3925958 &:= 3^9 + 2 \times \left(5^9 \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \\
 3925969 &:= 3^9 - 2 \times \left(-5^9 - 6 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 3928324 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (3) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((2 + 8)^3 \right) \right) \times 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 3932169 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((3 + 2) \times (\sqrt{16^9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 3936450 &:= \left(3 - \left((\sqrt{9^{3+6}}) \times 4 \right) \right) \times (-50) \\
 3936585 &:= \left(- (3) + \left((\sqrt{9^{3+6}}) \times (5 \times 8) \right) \right) \times 5 \\
 3944306 &:= \left(39 \times 4 + \sqrt{4} \right)^3 + 0 - 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$3944309 := (39 \times 4 + \sqrt{4})^3 - \sqrt{09}$$

$$3944311 := (39 \times 4 + \sqrt{4})^3 - 1 \times 1$$

$$3944312 := (39 \times 4 + \sqrt{4})^3 \times 1^2$$

$$3944313 := (39 \times 4 + \sqrt{4})^3 + 1^3$$

$$3944314 := (39 \times 4 + \sqrt{4})^3 + \sqrt{1 \times 4}$$

$$3944316 := (39 \times 4 + \sqrt{4})^3 + \sqrt{16}$$

$$3944324 := (3 + (\sqrt{9^4} - \sqrt{4})^3 \times 2) \times 4$$

$$3944328 := (39 \times 4 + \sqrt{4})^3 + 2 \times 8$$

$$3944339 := (39 \times 4 + \sqrt{4})^3 + 3 \times 9$$

$$3945242 := \left(\left(3 + \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{4}) + (52)^4 \right) \right) / 2 \right)$$

$$3948745 := \left(\left((-3) + \sqrt{9^4} \right) \times (8 + 7^4) \right) - 5$$

$$3952144 := (3 - 95 \times 21 + 4)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$3956079 := - \left(\left((3 - (9^5)) \times (60 + 7) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$3956124 := \left(3 + \left(9 \times (5 + (6^{1+2})) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$3956283 := \left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \right) \times (((6+2) \times 8) + 3) \right)$$

$$3956484 := - \left((3 + (9^5)) \right) \times \left((-6) / \sqrt{4} - \sqrt{8^4} \right)$$

$$3963476 := \left(\left((3 - \sqrt{9^6}) / (-3) \right) \times (4^7 - 6) \right)$$

$$3968064 := (3 \times 9 \times (6 - 80) + 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$3969405 := \left(\left((3 + 96) \times 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 05 \right)$$

$$3975966 := \left((3 \times \sqrt{9^7}) \times ((5 + 96) \times 6) \right)$$

$$3981312 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9} \times 8} \right)^{1+3} \right) \times 12 \right)$$

$$3981348 := \left(\left(3 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 8)^{1+3} \right) \right) \times (4 + 8) \right)$$

$$3984415 := \left((-3) + (98^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \times 415$$

$$3984477 := \left((3 \times (9 + 8)) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(- \left((\sqrt{4} - 7) \right)^7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3984579 := \left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{9}) + 8 \right) \times (4 + (5^7)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$3984714 := \left((3^{-\sqrt{9}+8}) \times ((4^7) + 14) \right)$$

$$3992973 := \left(3 \times \left(-9 + \left((9 + 2) \times (\sqrt{9} + 7) \right)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$3992979 := \left(\left(\left(((3 + 9) \times 9) + 2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 7 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$3992994 := \left(3 \times \left(\left((9 \times 9) + 29 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$3992995 := \left(\left(\left(((3 + 9) \times 9) + 2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$3994459 := \left((3 \times 99)^{\sqrt{4}} + (\sqrt{4} \times (5^9)) \right)$$

$$3995568 := \left(\left((-39) - \sqrt{9} \right) + (5^5) \right) \times \sqrt{6^8}$$

$$3995649 := \left(3^9 \times (95 + \sqrt{6^4 \times 9}) \right)$$

$$3997474 := \left(- \left(3^9 \right) \times (\sqrt{9} + 7) \right) + (4^{7+4})$$

$$3999964 := \left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{9}) - ((9/9) + 9)^6 \right) \times (-4) \right)$$

$$4019639 := \left(-40 + \left(- \left((1 - (9 \times 6)) \times 3 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$4019679 := \left(\left((40 - 1) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + (6 \times 7) \right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$4031937 := \left(\left((40^3) - 1 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (3 \times 7)$$

$$4079616 := \left(4^{07} \times (\sqrt{9^{6-1}} + 6) \right)$$

$$4088831 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} - 08) \times (-88^3) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$4088834 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} - 08) \times (-88^3) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4095950 := (40 \times (9 - 5))^{\sqrt{9}} - 50$$

$$4095964 := (40 \times (9 - 5))^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{6^4}$$

$$4095979 := (40 \times (9 - 5))^{\sqrt{9}} - 7 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$4095984 := (40 \times (9 - 5))^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4095986 := (40 \times (9 - 5))^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 - 6$$

$$4095989 := (40 \times (9 - 5))^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$4095991 := (40 \times (9 - 5))^{\sqrt{9}} - 9 \times 1$$

$$4095994 := (40 \times (9 - 5))^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9 \times 4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4095995 &:= (40^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-5 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 \\
 4095999 &:= (40 \times (9 - 5))^{\sqrt{9}} - 9/9 \\
 4108799 &:= (\sqrt{4} - ((-((10 - 87))^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-9))) \\
 4112784 &:= (((4 + (11 \times 2)) \times 78)^{\sqrt{4}}) \\
 4117495 &:= ((-((4 \times 11)) + (7^{\sqrt{49}})) \times 5) \\
 4117645 &:= (-((4 - 11)) \times ((-((7^6)) + \sqrt{4}) \times (-5))) \\
 4117685 &:= \left(\left((-((4 - 11))^7) - \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 4117772 &:= (\sqrt{4} + (((11 + (7^7)) \times (7 - 2)))) \\
 4117774 &:= (4 - (-((11 + (7^7))) \times (7 - \sqrt{4}))) \\
 4117784 &:= (((4 + 1) \times (1 + (7^7))) + \sqrt{8^4}) \\
 4118450 &:= (41 \times (1 - 8))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 50 \\
 4128768 &:= \left(\left((4^{1-2+8}) \times 7 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} \right) \\
 4133570 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times (-1)) - (3 \times 3^5) \right) \times (-70) \right) \\
 4134364 &:= (4 \times 13) \times (43^{6/\sqrt{4}}) \\
 4135560 &:= \left(\left((41^3) + \sqrt{5 \times 5} \right) \times 60 \right) \\
 4145152 &:= \left((\sqrt{4}^{14}) \times ((51 \times 5) - 2) \right) \\
 4145292 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(1 - \left(\left((4^5) - (2 \times \sqrt{9}) \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4147202 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times (1 + (4 \times (720^2)))) \\
 4147204 &:= (- (4) \times (- (1) - (\sqrt{4} \times (720^{\sqrt{4}})))) \\
 4147648 &:= (4^{1 \times 4 + 7}) - (6^{-\sqrt{4} + 8}) \\
 4153444 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((4 \times 1)^5 \right) - 3 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4169764 &:= \left(\left(\left((4 \times 1)^6 \right) / (9 - 7) \right) - 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4173279 &:= ((\sqrt{4} \times (-1)) + (((7 \times 3) + 2) \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4173283 &:= (\sqrt{4} + ((1 + (((7 + 3) \times 2) \times 8))^3)) \\
 4175950 &:= ((\sqrt{4} - (17^{-5+9})) \times (-50)) \\
 4177932 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(1 - \left((- (7) + ((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 3))^2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4186114 &:= - \left((\sqrt{4} - ((186 \times 11)^{\sqrt{4}})) \right) \\
 4187738 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times (1 + (8^7))) - ((7 + (3^8))) \right) \\
 4192576 &:= \left((4^{1 \times 9 + 2}) - \sqrt{(5 + 7)^6} \right) \\
 4193408 &:= (4 + 1 - 9^3)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 08 \\
 4193652 &:= \left((\sqrt{4}^{19+3}) - 652 \right) \\
 4193728 &:= \left((\sqrt{4}^{19+3}) - (72 \times 8) \right) \\
 4193792 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{(4 \times 1)^9} - (-((3 - 7)^{9+2})) \right) \right) \\
 4193856 &:= \left((\sqrt{4}^{19+3}) - (8 \times 56) \right) \\
 4193872 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(4 \times 1 \times 9)^3} - (8^7) \right) \times (-2) \right) \\
 4193986 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4}^{19}) - 39 \right) \times 8 \right) - 6 \right) \\
 4193989 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4}^{19}) - 39 \right) \times 8 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 4194048 &:= \left((4^{\sqrt{1 \times 9}}) \times (- (4 - (04^8))) \right) \\
 4194114 &:= \left((4^{11}) - (\sqrt{4} \times (91 + 4)) \right) \\
 4194179 &:= - \left(\left((4 + 1)^{\sqrt{9}} - (4^{1+7+\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \\
 4194214 &:= \left((-((4 + 1) \times 9)) + (\sqrt{4}^{21}) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4194220 &:= (- (4) \times ((19 + \sqrt{4}) - (2^{20}))) \\
 4194222 &:= - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} - 1) + \sqrt{9^4} \right) - (2^{22}) \right) \\
 4194224 &:= \left(\left((-((4^{1+9})) - \sqrt{4}) + 22 \right) \times (-4) \right) \\
 4194228 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(19 - (\sqrt{4}^{2 \times (2+8)}) \right) \right) \\
 4194268 &:= (- (4) \times ((1 \times 9) - (\sqrt{4}^{2 \times 6 + 8}))) \\
 4194276 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times ((1 - 9) + (((4 \times 2)^7) - 6)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$4194277 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((1+9) - \left((4 \times 2)^7 \right) \right) \right) \right) - 7 \right)$$

$$4194278 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((1 \times 9) - \left((4 \times 2)^7 \right) \right) \right) \right) - 8 \right)$$

$$4194279 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((1-9) + \left((4 \times 2)^7 \right) \right) \right) - 9 \right)$$

$$4194283 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (19) \right) - \left(\sqrt{4^{2 \times (8+3)}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4194286 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((1 \times 9) - \left((4 \times 2) \times \left(8^6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4194306 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(- (1) + \sqrt{9} \right)^{4+3 \times 06} \right)$$

$$4194311 := \left(\left(\left(\left(4^{1+9} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (3+1) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$4194314 := \left(\left(\left(\left(4^{1+9} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (3+1) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4194314 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((1-3) - \left(4^{9+1} \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4194342 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 19 \right) + \left(4^{3+4 \times 2} \right) \right)$$

$$4194348 := \left(\left(41 + \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(4^3 \right) \times \left(4^8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4194349 := \left(\left(\left(\left(4^{1+9} \right) + (4 \times 3) \right) \times 4 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$4194368 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{19} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) + \sqrt{36} \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$4194427 := \left(\left(41 \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((4 \times 2)^7 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4194429 := \left(\left((4+1)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(4^{4-2+9} \right) \right)$$

$$4194431 := \left(\left(\left(\left(4^{-1+9} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(4^3 \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$4194434 := \left(\left(\left(\left(4^{-1+9} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(4^3 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4194448 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{19} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) + \left((4 \times 4) \right) \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$4194456 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (19 \times 4) \right) + \left(4^{5+6} \right) \right)$$

$$4194484 := \left(\left(\left((4+1) \times 9 \right) + \left(4^{\sqrt{4}+8} \right) \right) \times 4 \right)$$

$$4194492 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (1 \times 94) \right) + \left(4^{9+2} \right) \right)$$

$$4194494 := \left(- \left((4-194) \right) + \left(4^{9+\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4194496 := \left(\left(\left(4^{1+9} \right) \times 4 \right) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times 96 \right) \right)$$

$$4194498 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(1 + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-4) \right) - \left(4^9 \right) \right) \times (-8) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4194528 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{19} \right) + \left(4 \times (5+2) \right) \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$4194728 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{19} \right) + \left(4 + \left(7^2 \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$4194748 := -4 + (1-9)^{\sqrt{4}} \times (7+4^8)$$

$$4194784 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(4^{1+9} \right) \right) - \sqrt{4^7} \right) + 8 \right) \times (-4) \right)$$

$$4194848 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{19} \right) + 4 \right) + \sqrt{8^4} \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$4194882 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left((1 \times 9) + \left(4^8 \right) \right) \times \left(8^2 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4194884 := \left(4 - \left(- \left(\left((1 \times 9) + \left(4^8 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{8^4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4194888 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(1 - \left(\left(9 + \left(4^8 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$4194976 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((1-9) \times \left(\left(4^9 \right) + \left(7 \times 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4197429 := \left(\sqrt{(4+1)^{\sqrt{9}+7}} + \left(4^{2+9} \right) \right)$$

$$4198880 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (-1) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9}^8 \right) \times (-8) \right) \right) \times 80 \right)$$

$$4199488 := \left(\left(\left(4^{-1+9} \right) + \sqrt{9^4} \right) \times (8 \times 8) \right)$$

$$4213987 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{21} \right) + \left(\left(3^9 \right) + \left(8^7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4214784 := \left((4 \times 21) \times \left(\left((4 \times 7) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4220548 := \left(- (4) \times \left(- \left(\left(2^{20} \right) - \left(\sqrt{5+4^8} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4221303 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{22} \right) - \left(1 - \left(30^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4224193 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{22} \right) + \left(41 \times \left(9^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4225554 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{22} \right) + \left(\left(\left(5^5 \right) \times 5 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4225564 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{22} \right) + \left(\left(5 + \left(5^6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4227128 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{4}^{22}} + (7+1) \right) \right)^2 \right) - 8 \right)$$

$$4229296 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{22} \right) + \left(\left((9 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 6 \right) \right)$$

$$4235364 := \left(\left(\left((42-35)^3 \right) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4237668 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{2 \times 3}} + \left(\left(7^6 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} \right)$$

$$4243674 := \left(- \left((4+2) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left((36-7)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4244832 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left((4^2) - \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 8 \right)^3 \right) / 2 \right)$$

$$4245696 := (4 \times 2) \times \left((4 + 5)^6 - \sqrt{96} \right)$$

$$4248968 := \left(\left(\left((-42) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 8 \right) + (9^6) \right) \times 8$$

$$4251844 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^{2 \times 5}} - ((1 - 8)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4251936 := (4 \times 2) \times \left(51 + (9^{\sqrt{36}}) \right)$$

$$4259559 := \left((-4 + (-(((2 - 5) - 9) - 5))^5) \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$4259569 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((2 + (5 \times \sqrt{9}))^5 \right) \times (- (6 - 9)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4259583 := \left(\left(4 - \left(\left((2 + (5 \times \sqrt{9}))^5 \right) + 8 \right) \right) \times (-3) \right)$$

$$4259589 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((2 + (5 \times \sqrt{9}))^5 \right) + 8 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$4259848 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{25 - \sqrt{9}}} \right) + \left((8 + (4^8)) \right) \right)$$

$$4261896 := (4 \times 2) \times \left(\sqrt{(6 \times 1)^8} + (9^6) \right)$$

$$4269996 := \left(\left((4 - (26^{\sqrt{9}})) \times (-9) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{96}} \right)$$

$$4274888 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{27^4})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} \right) \times 8 \right) \right)$$

$$4276622 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((-2 - \sqrt{76}) \times (-6) \right) - 2 \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$4276624 := \left(\left(\left((4 - 2) + \sqrt{76} \right) \times 6 \right) - 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4276624 := \left(\left(4 \times \left(\sqrt{(2 + 6)^6} + (7 - 2) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4281255 := (-\sqrt{4} + 281)^2 \times 55$$

$$4285785 := (4 + 2^8 - 5) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{78 \times 5}}} \right)$$

$$4292346 := \left(-((4 + 2)) + \left(92 \times \left((3 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4293184 := \left(4 \times \left(\left((2^9) - 3 \right) + 1 \right) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4294932 := \left(\left(\left(\left((4^2) \times 9 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 3 \right) / 2$$

$$4302589 := \left(\left((4 \times 3) + 02 \right)^5 \times 8 \right) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$4334724 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times (3 \times 347))^{-2+4} \right)$$

$$4341969 := \left(\left((-((4 + 3)) \times (41^{\sqrt{9}})) + 6 \right) \times (-9) \right)$$

$$4348359 := \left(4 - \left(3 \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left((8 + 3)^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 9$$

$$4352976 := \left((\sqrt{4} + 35) \times \left((2 - \sqrt{9}) + \left((7^6) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4353492 := \left(43 \times \left(\left(- \left((5 \times 3)^4 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-2) \right)$$

$$4354560 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}}} \right) \times 560 \right)$$

$$4359744 := \left((\sqrt{4} - \left((35 \times 9) - (7^4) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4369774 := \left((\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{36 \times 9^7}) \times 74 \right)$$

$$4373992 := \left(4 + \left(-3 \right) \times \left((7 + 3) \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times (-2)$$

$$4373995 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 3) \times \left((7 + 3) \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$4373996 := \left(-4 + \left((3 \times ((7 \times 3) + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$4374879 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (8 \times 7) \right) - 9$$

$$4374888 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times ((8 \times 8) - 8) \right)$$

$$4374978 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(3 - \left(7 \times \left(-((4 - 9))^7 \right) \right) \right) \times (-8) \right)$$

$$4376464 := \left(4 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{(3 + 7)^6} + 46 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4377743 := - \left((\sqrt{4} - \left((3^{7+7}) - (74^3) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4377749 := \left(4 + (3^{7+7}) \right) - (74^{\sqrt{9}})$$

$$4378434 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(37 \times \left((8 \times 43)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4381825 := \left(\sqrt{(4 + 3)^8} \times 1825 \right)$$

$$4382748 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((3^8) \times (2 - (7 \times 48)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4385664 := \left(((4 + 38) + 5) \times (6^6) \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4385666 := (\sqrt{4} + (((38 + 56) \times (6^6))))$$

$$4389280 := ((4 - ((38^{\sqrt{9}}) - 2)) \times (-80))$$

$$4389440 := (\sqrt{4} \times (((38^{\sqrt{9}}) - 4) \times 40))$$

$$4389764 := (4 - ((38^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (- (76 + 4))))$$

$$4392648 := \left(\left(\left((4 \times 3) + \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{2 \times 6}} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$4394656 := (- (4) \times ((- ((3^9)) + \sqrt{4^6}) \times 56))$$

$$4408992 := ((440 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9^9})) / 2$$

$$4410922 := ((4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}}) - (22)$$

$$4410928 := ((4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}}) - ((2 \times 8))$$

$$4410954 := ((4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}}) - (- (5) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$4410959 := ((4 \times 41)^{\sqrt{09}}) + (5 \times \sqrt{9})$$

$$4423680 := \left((- ((4^4)) \times \sqrt{(2 \times 3)^6}) \times (-80) \right)$$

$$4426812 := -4 + (\sqrt{4} - 26 \times 81)^2$$

$$4426814 := -\sqrt{4} + (\sqrt{4} - 26 \times 81)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4443664 := \left(((44 \times 43) + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4447868 := (-4 + ((44 \times 78) \times \sqrt{6^8}))$$

$$4453268 := (\sqrt{4} \times (((\sqrt{4} \times (5^{3^2})) - (6^8))))$$

$$4456321 := \left(((\sqrt{4} \times (4^5)) + (63))^{2 \times 1} \right)$$

$$4456444 := (-4 + (\sqrt{4} \times ((4^6) \times 544)))$$

$$4456446 := - \left((\sqrt{4} - ((4^{5+6}) + ((4+4)^6))) \right)$$

$$4456449 := (4/4) + ((5 + (6 \times \sqrt{4})) \times (4^9))$$

$$4456499 := (((4 \times 4) - 5) + 6) \times ((4^9) + \sqrt{9})$$

$$4457464 := (((4 \times 4) - 5) \times (74^{6/\sqrt{4}}))$$

$$4460544 := \left((((44 \times 60) / 5) \times 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4460544 := ((44 \times ((50 - 6) + 4))^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4464769 := \left(((4 + \sqrt{46^4}) - 7)^{6/\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$4465664 := (\sqrt{4^{4+6}} \times (5 + (66^{\sqrt{4}})))$$

$$4467312 := (- ((4 \times 4)) \times (- ((6^7)) + \sqrt{3^{12}}))$$

$$4469545 := (((\sqrt{4} \times (4^6)) + 9) \times 545)$$

$$4473238 := (\sqrt{4} \times (((\sqrt{4} - (7^3)) \times (2 - (3^8))))$$

$$4473378 := ((\sqrt{4} + (4^7)) \times (- ((3 - (3^7)) / 8)))$$

$$4476928 := (\sqrt{4} \times ((\sqrt{4^7} - (6^{9-2})) \times (-8)))$$

$$4476944 := (((-4 + \sqrt{4^9}) - ((6^7) \times 4)) \times (-4))$$

$$4477344 := (- ((4 \times 4)) \times (7 - (((7 \times 3) + \sqrt{4})^4)))$$

$$4477434 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times (- (4 + 7))) + \left((\sqrt{7^4} - 3 \right)^4 \right)$$

$$4477447 := -\sqrt{4} + (4 \times 7 - 74)^4 - 7$$

$$4477449 := -4 + (4 \times 7 - 74)^4 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$4477454 := (\sqrt{4} - (4 - (((7/7) + 45)^4)))$$

$$4477744 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) - 77 \right) \times (4 \times 4) \right)$$

$$4477744 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) - 77 \right) \times (4 \times 4) \right)$$

$$4478464 := \left(((\sqrt{4} - \sqrt{4^7}) \times (-8)) + ((46^4)) \right)$$

$$4478814 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) \times 8 \right) - (81) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4478844 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) - 8 \right) \times 8 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4478848 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) - 8 \right) \times ((8/4) \times 8) \right)$$

$$4478888 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) \times (8 + 8) \right) - (88) \right)$$

$$4478928 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{78}}}} \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (2 \times 8) \right) \right)$$

$$4478934 := ((\sqrt{4} + 4) \times (-7) + ((8 \times 9)^3 \times \sqrt{4}))$$

$$4478944 := 4 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{(4 \times 9)^{8 \times 7}} - \sqrt{4}}}} \right) \times 4$$

$$4478949 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) \times 8 \right) - 9 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - 9$$

$$4478968 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) \times 8 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \right) - 8$$

$$4478971 := (-4 - ((-((4^7) / 8)) \times \sqrt{9^7}) + 1)$$

$$4478972 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) \times 8 \right) - (9 - 7) \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$4478974 := \left((4 \times 4) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)^7 \right) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$4478975 := \left(4 + \left(\left((4^7) / 8 \right) \times \sqrt{9^7} \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$4478976 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) \times ((89 + 7) / 6) \right)$$

$$4478978 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(((7 + 8) - 9)^7 \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4478979 := \left((4 \times 4) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)^7 \right) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$4478982 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) \times 8 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{8/2} \right)$$

$$4478994 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) \times 8 \right) + \sqrt{9 \times 9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4479024 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (02^4) \right)$$

$$4479375 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((\sqrt{4^7} + \sqrt{9})^3 \right) \right) - (7^5) \right)$$

$$4479984 := \left(- (4) \times \left(4 + \left(- (7) \times \left((\sqrt{9} + ((9 + 8))^4 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4485924 := \left((\sqrt{4} + (((4 \times 8) + 5) + 9)^2) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4491396 := \left(\left((4^4) - 91 \right)^3 \right) - \sqrt{9^6}$$

$$4492123 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times (9^2)) + (1 + 2) \right)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4492129 := \left(4 + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times (9^2)) + (1 + 2) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$4494402 := (\sqrt{4} + (((49 + 4) \times 40)^2))$$

$$4494404 := \left(4 + \left(((49 + 4) \times 40)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4498944 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 9) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \left(- (4^4) \right) \right)$$

$$4498944 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 9) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \left(- (4^4) \right) \right)$$

$$4498956 := \left(4 \times \left(\left((4 + 9) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{5^6} \right) \right)$$

$$4499448 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times (4 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (4^4) \right) - 8 \right)$$

$$4499452 := \left(-4 - \left(\left((4 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(- \left((4^5) \times 2 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4499453 := \left(\left((4 \times (4 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{4^5} - 3 \right)$$

$$4499454 := \left(\left((4 \times (4 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{4^5} - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4499456 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4 \times 4} + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{4^{5+6}} \right)$$

$$4499459 := \left(\left((4 \times (4 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{4^5} + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$4499464 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4^9 \times (9 + 4)^6} \right) \times 4$$

$$4499488 := \left(4 + \left(\left((4 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{4^8} \right) \right) \times 8$$

$$4499648 := \left(\left((4 \times (4 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 6 \right) \times (4 \times 8)$$

$$4518338 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((51 + 8)^3 \right) \times (3 + 8) \right)$$

$$4528382 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(((5 + 2) \times 8) \times 38 \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$4528384 := \left((((4 + 5) - 2) \times 8) \times 38 \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4536035 := \left((\sqrt{4} + 5) \times \left(3 \times (60^3) \right) + 5 \right)$$

$$4536037 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(5 + (3 \times (60^3)) \right) \times 7 \right) \right)$$

$$4536675 := \left(- (45) \times \left(\sqrt{3^6} - \left(6 \times (7^5) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4537890 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 5) \times 3 \right) \times \sqrt{7^8} \right) \times 90 \right)$$

$$4539969 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times (5 \times 3))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (9^6) \right) \times (-9) \right)$$

$$4545424 := \left(((45 - 4) \times (54 - 2))^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4547795 := \left(\left((4^5) - \sqrt{4} \right) + (77 \times (9^5)) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4551470 &:= \left(4 - (5 \times 51)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times (-70) \\
 4553334 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (5^5)\right)\right) \times \left(-((3 \times 3)^3)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4556254 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((5-2)^6\right) \times (5^5)\right)\right) + 4 \\
 4557289 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 5\right) \times (5^{7+2})\right) - 8\right) / \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 4559166 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (5^5)\right)\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9}^{-1+6}\right) \times 6\right) \\
 4559451 &:= \left(\left(4 + (5 \times 59)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times 51 \\
 4574293 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(4 + 5\right) + 74\right) \times 2\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 3\right) \\
 4574294 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(4 + 5\right) + 74\right) \times 2\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 4574299 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(4 + 5\right) + 74\right) \times 2\right)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 4584925 &:= \left(-\left(\left(4 - (5^8)\right)\right) + \left(4^{\sqrt{9} \times 2 + 5}\right)\right) \\
 4584927 &:= -\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(5^8\right) + \left(4^{9 \times 2 - 7}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 4584931 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(5^8\right) + \left(4^{9+3-1}\right)\right)\right) \\
 4586139 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (5 \times ((8 \times 6) - 1))\right)\right) \times \left(-\left(3^9\right)\right) \\
 4587478 &:= -\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(5 \times \left(8 - \left(7 \times \left(4^7\right) \times 8\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 4587482 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(5 \times \left(8 - \left(7 \times \left(4^8\right) \times 2\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 4587484 &:= \left(4 + \left(-\left(5\right) \times \left(8 - \left(7 \times \left(4^8\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\
 4588164 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(45 \times 8\right) - \sqrt{8+1}\right) \times 6\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4589667 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(5^8\right) + \left(9 + 6\right) \times \left(6^7\right)\right)\right) \\
 4593746 &:= \left(-4 + \left(\left(\left(5^{9-3}\right) \times \sqrt{7^4}\right) \times 6\right)\right) \\
 4594500 &:= \left(\left(-\left(4^5\right) + \sqrt{9}\right) \times (-4500)\right) \\
 4596728 &:= \left(\left(\left(-\left(4\right) \times \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{9}\right) \times (-67)\right)\right)^2\right) - 8\right) \\
 4599669 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(5^9\right) - \left(9 \times \left(6^6\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 4599928 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(45 \times \sqrt{9}\right) - \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times 2\right) - 8\right) \\
 4599932 &:= \left(-4 - \left(\left(\left(\left(5 \times 9\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) - \sqrt{9}\right)^3\right) \times (-2)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4599933 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\left(5 \times 9\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) - \sqrt{9}\right)^3\right)\right) - 3 \\
 4599934 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\left(5 \times 9\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) - \sqrt{9}\right)^3\right)\right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 4599936 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(45 \times \sqrt{9}\right) - \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) / (-3)\right) \times (-6)\right) \\
 4599939 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\left(5 \times 9\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) - \sqrt{9}\right)^3\right)\right) + \sqrt{9} \\
 4599944 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(45 \times \sqrt{9}\right) - \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + 4\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 4609257 &:= \left(\left(-\left(4 - 60\right) + \sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(-\left(2 - \left(5^7\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 4618944 &:= \left(\left(4 + 6\right) + 1\right) \times \left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{9^4}\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4626882 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\left(6/2\right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}\right)^{8/2}\right)\right) \\
 4626894 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 6\right) + \left(2 \times \left(\left(6 \times 8\right) - 9^4\right)\right)\right) \\
 4626954 &:= \sqrt{4} \times \left(6^2 + (6 - 9 \times 5)^4\right) \\
 4627692 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(6 \times \left(\left(2 + 7\right) \times 69^2\right)\right)\right) \\
 4631104 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(6^3\right) - 1\right) \times 10\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4636672 &:= \left(4^6\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{3^6} \times (6 \times 7)\right) - 2\right) \\
 4642997 &:= \left(-4 - \left(\left(\left(6^{4+2}\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) - \left(9^7\right)\right)\right) \\
 4644768 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left(\left(6 \times 4\right)^4\right) - 7\right) \times (6 + 8)\right)\right) \\
 4644774 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\left(\left(6 \times 4\right)^4\right) - 7\right) \times 7\right) + 4\right) \\
 4644782 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(6 \times 4\right)^4\right) \times 7\right)\right) - (82) \\
 4644836 &:= \left(\left(\left(4 \times 6\right)^4\right) - \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(8 + \sqrt{36}\right) \\
 4644872 &:= \left(-\left(4\right) \times \left(\left(\left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{4}\right)^4\right) \times \left(-\left(8 \times 7\right)\right)\right)\right) - 2\right) \\
 4644876 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\left(6^4\right) \times \sqrt{4^8}\right) \times 7\right) + 6\right) \\
 4644892 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(6 \times 4\right)^4\right)\right) \times \left(8 + \left(\sqrt{9} \times 2\right)\right) \\
 4644927 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(6 \times 4\right)^4\right)\right) + \sqrt{9^2}\right) \times 7 \\
 4652649 &:= \left(4 + 6 - (5 - 2)^6\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4663750 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (6^6) \right) - 37 \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 4664950 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (6^6) \right) - (4 + 9) \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 4665102 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left((6^6) - 5 \right) \times (10^2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4665104 &:= \left(4 - \left(- \left(\left((6^6) - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{10^4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4665150 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((6^6) - 5 \right) \right) + 1 \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 4665250 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (6^6) \right) - (5 + 2) \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 4665375 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 6 \right) \times \left(- (6^5) \right) \right) + 3 \right) \times (-75) \right) \\
 4665400 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (6^6) \right) \times (-5) \right) \times \sqrt{400} \right) \\
 4665425 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left((4 \times (6^6)) - 5 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-25) \right) \\
 4665440 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(\left(- \left((6^6) \right) \times \sqrt{5^4} \right) + 40 \right) \right) \\
 4665450 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (6^6) \right) - \sqrt{5 + 4} \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 4665475 &:= \left(\left((4 \times (6^6)) - 5 \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \times (-5) \right) \right) \\
 4665544 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((6^6) \times 5 \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) + 4 \right) \times (-4) \right) \\
 4665564 &:= \left((4 \times \left(\left((6^6) \times 5 \right) \times 5 \right)) - \sqrt{6^4} \right) \\
 4665572 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\left(\left((6^6) \times 5 \right) \times 5 \right) - 7 \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 4665574 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left(\left((6^6) \times 5 \right) \times 5 \right) - 7 \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \\
 4665576 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{6^6} \times 5 \right)^{-5+7} \right) - 6 \right) \right) \\
 4665579 &:= \left((4 \times \left(\left((6^6) \times 5 \right) \times 5 \right)) + \left(- (7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 4665589 &:= \left(\left((4 \times \left(\left((6^6) \times 5 \right) \times 5 \right)) - 8 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 4665594 &:= \left((4 \times \left(\left((6^6) \times 5 \right) \times 5 \right)) - \sqrt{9 \times 4} \right) \\
 4665595 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((6^6) \times (5 + (5 \times 9)) \right) \right) - 5 \right) \\
 4665624 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(- (6) - \left(\left((6 \times 5) \times (6^2) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4665650 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (6^6) \right) - ((5 - 6)) \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 4665750 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((6^6) + 5 \right) \right) - 7 \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 4665850 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (6^6) \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}} \right) \times 50 \right) \right) \\
 4665950 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((6^6) + 5 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 4666150 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((6^6) + 6 \right) \right) - 1 \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 4666350 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((6^6) + 6 \right) \right) + 3 \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 4667479 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{6^6} \times (7^4) \right) - 7 \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4667499 &:= \left(\left(-4 - \left(\left(\sqrt{6^6} \times (7^4) \right) - 9 \right) \right) \times (-9) \right) \\
 4667499 &:= \left(\left(-4 - \left(\left(\sqrt{6^6} \times (7^4) \right) - 9 \right) \right) \times (-9) \right) \\
 4674242 &:= \left(\left(\left((46 \times (\sqrt{7^4} - 2))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 4674244 &:= \left((46 \times (\sqrt{7^4} - 2))^{4-\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4687458 &:= \left(((4 - 6) + 8) \times \left(- (7) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (5^8) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4687464 &:= \sqrt{4} \times 6 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right)^8 - 6/\sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4687582 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (6 + 8) \right) \times \left(- (7 + (5^8)) \right) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 4687586 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((6 - 8) \times \left((7 + (5^8)) \times 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4688734 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(- (6) \times \left((887 - 3)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4691584 &:= \left((4^6) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((1 - (5^8)) \times 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4705274 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^7} - (0 - 5) \right)^{\sqrt{2+7}} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4705958 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(70 \times \left((5 + 9)^5 \right) / 8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4706040 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (7^{06}) \right) \times 040 \right) \\
 4716864 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((4^7) \times 1 \right) - 6 \right) \times 8 \right) \times \sqrt{6^4} \right) \\
 4717359 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (717) \right) \times (3^{5+\sqrt{9}}) \right) \\
 4718448 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 7 \right) \times \left(- (1 \times 8) \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - (4^8) \right) \right) \\
 4718464 &:= \left(\sqrt{4^7} \times \left(- (1) + \left((8 \times 4) \times 6^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4718547 &:= \left(\left(\left((4^{7+1}) \times 8 \right) - 5 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 7 \right) \right) \\
 4718564 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(7 + \left(- \left((1 \times 8)^5 \right) \times \sqrt{6^4} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4718591 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((7+1) \times \left((8^5) \times 9 \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 4718594 &:= \left(\left(4 + \left(\left((7+1) + 8 \right)^5 \times 9 \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4718596 &:= \left(4 + \left(\left((7+1) \times (8^5) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 4718612 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 7 \right) \times \left(1 + (8^6) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 4718638 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left((7-1) \times \left((8^6) \times 3 \right) + 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4718664 &:= \left(\left(\left((4^7) + 1 \right) \times 8 \right) - 6 \right) \times \sqrt{6^4} \\
 4718686 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(7 - \left((1+8) \times \left(6 + (8^6) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4718695 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((7-1) + (8^6) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) - 5 \\
 4718696 &:= \left(-4 - \left(\left((7-1) + (8^6) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \times (-6) \right) \right) \\
 4723920 &:= \left(\left(4 \times \sqrt{7+2} \right) \times \left((3^9) \times 20 \right) \right) \\
 4726836 &:= \left(\left(-4 + \left(- \left((7-2) \times \sqrt{6^8} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(- (3^6) \right) \right) \\
 4733440 &:= \left(\left(\left(4 + \left((7^3) - 3 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 40 \right) \\
 4734949 &:= \left((4^7) - \left(\left(- (3) + \left((4^9) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times (-9) \right) \right) \\
 4734974 &:= \left(\left((4^7) \times \left((94 \times 3) + 7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4734976 &:= \left((4^7) \times \left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{4}) \times (-9) \right) + \sqrt{7^6} \right) \right) \\
 4736697 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4^7} \times 3 \right) - \left((6^6) - (9^7) \right) \right) \\
 4741497 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((7+4) + 1 \right)^4 \right) \right) \right) + \left((9^7) \right) \\
 4741630 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\left((7 \times 4) \times 1 \right) \times 6 \right)^3 + 0 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4741632 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left((7 \times 4) \times 1 \right) \times 6 \right)^3 - 2 \right) \right) \\
 4741634 &:= \left(\left((4 \times 7)^{4-1} \right) \times (6^3) \right) + \sqrt{4} \\
 4741635 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\left((7 \times 4) \times 1 \right) \times 6 \right)^3 + 5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4741636 &:= \left(4 + \left(\left((7 \times 4) \times 1 \right) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{3+6}} \right) \\
 4741637 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\left((7 \times 4) \times 1 \right) \times 6 \right)^3 + 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4741638 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\left((7 \times 4) \times 1 \right) \times 6 \right)^3 + 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4741639 &:= \left(\left(4 + \left(\left((7 \times 4) \times 1 \right) \times 6 \right)^3 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4741679 &:= \left(47 + \left(\left(\left((4 \times 1) \times 6 \right) \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 4743388 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(74 - \left(33^{\sqrt{8+8}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4743664 &:= 4 \times \left(-7 + \sqrt{4} + (3 - 6 \times 6)^4 \right) \\
 4743682 &:= -\sqrt{4} + \left(-7 - \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{3^6+8} \right)^2 \\
 4756947 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (7^5) \right) \times \left((69 \times 4) + 7 \right) \right) \\
 4758443 &:= \left(\left(4 + (7^5) \right) + \left((84 \times \sqrt{4})^3 \right) \right) \\
 4765625 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^7} - 6 \right) \times \left(- (5^6) \right) \right) / (-2) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 4766599 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(7 \times \left((66 - 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4767337 &:= - \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^6 \right) + \left(7 - \left(3 \times 3 \right)^7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4769734 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^7} - 6 \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^7} - 3 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4769848 &:= \left(\left(\left((47 \times 6) - 9 \right) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 8 \right) \\
 4769852 &:= \left(-4 + \left(\left(\left((7+6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (8+5) \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 4769854 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\left((7+6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (8+5) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4769856 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (7 \times 6) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 8 \right) \times 56 \right) \\
 4773497 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4^7} \times \left(7 - (3^4) \right) \right) \right) + \left((9^7) \right) \\
 4773594 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 7 \right)^7 \right) - \left(3 \times (5^{9-4}) \right) \right) \\
 4774217 &:= \left((-4 + 7)^7 - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 - 1 - 7 \\
 4774218 &:= \left((-4 + 7)^7 - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 + 1 - 8 \\
 4774224 &:= \left((-4 + 7)^7 - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 - 2 / \sqrt{4} \\
 4774225 &:= \left((-4 + 7)^7 - \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{-2/2+5}} \\
 4774234 &:= \left((-4 + 7)^7 - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 + \sqrt{3^4} \\
 4774245 &:= \left((-4 + 7)^7 - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 + 4 \times 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$4774267 := ((-4 + 7)^7 - \sqrt{4})^2 + 6 \times 7$$

$$4774274 := ((-4 + 7)^7 - \sqrt{4})^2 + \sqrt{7^4}$$

$$4774969 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^7 \right) - \left((\sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} \times (-6)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$4775436 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + ((7 \times 7)))^{\sqrt{5+4}} \right) \times 36 \right)$$

$$4775924 := \left((\sqrt{4} - ((7 \times ((7 \times 59)^2))) \right) \times (-4)$$

$$4775929 := \left(((4 \times 7) \times ((7 \times 59)^2)) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$4776408 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^7 \right) - \left((6/\sqrt{4})^{08} \right) \right)$$

$$4776489 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^7 \right) - \left((6^4) \times (8 - \sqrt{9}) \right) \right)$$

$$4776825 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^7 \right) - \left(6 \times ((8/2)^5) \right) \right)$$

$$4777344 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^7 \right) - \left((73 + \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4778873 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^7 \right) - \left((8^{8-7+3}) \right) \right)$$

$$4779197 := \left(-((4 + 7)) \times (7^{\sqrt{9}}) + ((1 + (9^7))) \right)$$

$$4779549 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^7 \right) - ((95 \times 4) \times 9) \right)$$

$$4779592 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^7 \right) - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 2 \right) \right)$$

$$4779594 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^7 \right) - \left((\sqrt{9} \times 5)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^4}}} \right) \right)$$

$$4779835 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^7 \right) - \left(9 + ((8 - 3)^5) \right) \right)$$

$$4779855 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(8 - (5^5) \right) \right)$$

$$4779897 := \left((\sqrt{4^7} \times -((7 + 9) + 8)) + ((9^7)) \right)$$

$$4779997 := \left(- (4) \times ((7 + 7) + (9^{\sqrt{9}})) + ((9^7)) \right)$$

$$4781673 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^{8-1} \right) - \left((6^{7-3}) \right) \right)$$

$$4781817 := \left((\sqrt{4^7} \times -(8 + 1)) + \left((8 + 1)^7 \right) \right)$$

$$4781945 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^{8-1^9} \right) - (4^5) \right)$$

$$4782393 := \left((\sqrt{4} + 7) \times \left(- \left((8^2) - (3^{9+3}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4782397 := \left((\sqrt{4} - (7 \times 82)) + \left((3 \times \sqrt{9})^7 \right) \right)$$

$$4782457 := \left((\sqrt{4^7} \times -(8/2)) + \left((4 + 5)^7 \right) \right)$$

$$4782597 := \left(- (4) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} \times 2 \right) - 5 \right) \right) + ((9^7))$$

$$4782745 := \left(-(((4 \times 7) \times 8)) + \left((2 + 7)^{\sqrt{4+5}} \right) \right)$$

$$4782747 := \left(-(((4 \times 7) \times 8) - 2) + \left((7 + \sqrt{4})^7 \right) \right)$$

$$4782769 := - \left((\sqrt{4^7} + \left((8 - (2 + 7)^6 \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$4782797 := \left(-4 - \left(((7 \times 8) \times \sqrt{2+7}) - ((9^7)) \right) \right)$$

$$4782857 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times -(7 \times 8)) + \left((\sqrt{2 \times 8} + 5)^7 \right) \right)$$

$$4782914 := \left((\sqrt{4} + \left((7 - (8^2)) \right) \right) + (\sqrt{9^{14}})$$

$$4782915 := \left((\sqrt{4} + 7) \times \left(- \left((8 - 2) - (9^{1+5}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4782927 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} - 7) \times 8 \right) - 2 \right) + (\sqrt{9^{2 \times 7}}) \right)$$

$$4782933 := \left((\sqrt{4} + 7) \times \left(- \left((8/2) - (9^{3+3}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4782937 := \left(-((4 + ((7 \times 8) / 2))) + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 3)^7 \right) \right)$$

$$4782945 := \left((4 - ((7 \times 8) / 2)) + (9^{\sqrt{4+5}}) \right)$$

$$4782947 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times (-7)) - 8 \right) + \left(\left((2 + \sqrt{9}) + 4 \right)^7 \right) \right)$$

$$4782949 := \left(-((4 \times 7)) + \sqrt{8^2} \right) + (9^{\sqrt{49}})$$

$$4782951 := - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7) \times \left(\sqrt{8/2} - ((9^{5+1})) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4782954 := \left(-(((4 + 7) + (8/2))) + (9^{5+\sqrt{4}}) \right)$$

$$4782957 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^{8 \times 2 - 9} \right) - (5 + 7) \right)$$

$$4782959 := \left(-(((4 - 7) + 8) \times 2) + (\sqrt{9^{5+9}}) \right)$$

$$4782965 := \left(-4 + \left(-((7 - (8 \times 2)))^{\sqrt{9 \times 6 - 5}} \right) \right)$$

$$4782967 := \left((4 / ((7 - 8) \times 2)) + \left((\sqrt{9} + 6)^7 \right) \right)$$

$$4782968 := \left(- (((4 + 7) - 8) - 2) + (\sqrt{9^{6+8}}) \right)$$

$$4782986 := \left((((4 + 7) + 8) - 2) + (\sqrt{9^{8+6}}) \right)$$

$$4782987 := (4 \times 7 + 8) / 2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{8 \times 7}}}}$$

$$4782992 := \sqrt{\sqrt{(\sqrt{4} - 7)^8 - 2 + 9^{9-2}}}$$

$$4782993 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^{8-2} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 9 \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$4782994 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^{8-2} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 9 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4782995 := \left(- (((4 - 7) \times 8) - 2) + (\sqrt{9^{9+5}}) \right)$$

$$4782999 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^{8-2} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 9 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$4783014 := \left(\left(-4 + \sqrt{\sqrt{78}} \right) + \left((3^{014}) \right) \right)$$

$$4783027 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((7 \times 8) + \left((3^{02})^7 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4783067 := \left(\sqrt{4 \times \sqrt{78}} + \left((3 + 06)^7 \right) \right)$$

$$4783097 := \left(\sqrt{4^7} + \left((((8 + 3) \times 0) + 9)^7 \right) \right)$$

$$4783139 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(- \left((7 \times 8) + (3^{13}) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$4783314 := \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{78 \times 3}} + 3^{14}}$$

$$4783345 := \left((47 \times 8) + \left(3^{\sqrt{34+5}} \right) \right)$$

$$4783377 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4^7} + 8) \times 3 \right) + \left((3^{7+7}) \right) \right)$$

$$4783447 := \left(478 + \left(\left((3 + \sqrt{4}) + 4 \right)^7 \right) \right)$$

$$4783469 := \left(-4 - \left(\left(- \left((7 \times 8) \right) - \left(\sqrt{34^6} \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$4783497 := \left(\left((((4 + 7) \times 8) \times 3) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \left((9^7) \right) \right)$$

$$4783592 := \sqrt{(\sqrt{4} - 7)^8} + 3^{5+9} - 2$$

$$4783594 := \sqrt{(\sqrt{4} - 7)^8} + (3^5 \times 9)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4783669 := - \left((\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((78 + \left((3 + 6)^6 \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4783797 := - \left((\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((7 - 837) - (9^7) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4783996 := \left((\sqrt{4^7} \times 8) + \left(3 + (9 \times (9^6)) \right) \right)$$

$$4783997 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(7 - \left((8^3) + 9 \right) \right) \right) + \left((9^7) \right) \right)$$

$$4784697 := \left(\sqrt{((4 + 7 - 8) \times 4)^6} + \left((9^7) \right) \right)$$

$$4784994 := \left(\left(\left(\left(-4 + \sqrt{\sqrt{78}} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \left(9^{9-\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4784997 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times (78 \times (4 + 9))) + \left((9^7) \right) \right)$$

$$4785367 := \left((\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{78}) - \left(5 - \left((3 + 6)^7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4785377 := \left((\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{78}) + \left(5 + \left(3^{7+7} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4785497 := \left(\left(4 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{78}} + \left((5^4) \right)} \right) \right) + \left((9^7) \right) \right)$$

$$4785734 := \left(\left((4 + 7) + (8^5) \right) \times 73 \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4786497 := \left(\sqrt{4 \times \sqrt{78} \times 6^4} + \left((9^7) \right) \right)$$

$$4787344 := \left(\left(\left(\left((4 + 7) - 8 \right)^7 - 3 \right) + 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4789624 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times (7 \times 89)) \times \left(62^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4791721 := \left((\sqrt{4} + \left(- \left((7 - 9) - 1 \right) \right)^7 \right)^{2 \times 1}$$

$$4791724 := \left(- \left((4 - 7) \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{(9 \times 1)^7} + 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4792648 := \left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \times 9 \right)^2 \times (6^4 - 8)$$

$$4792896 := \left((\sqrt{4} - \left((79^2) \times 8 \right)) \times (-96) \right)$$

$$4796145 := \left((\sqrt{4} + 7) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9^6} + 1)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 5 \right) \right)$$

$$4796928 := \left((-4 - (7^{\sqrt{9}})) \times \left(- \left((6 \times 9) \times (2^8) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4797252 := \left(- \left((4^7) \right) + \left((\sqrt{9^7} + (2 + 5))^2 \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4798576 &:= \left((4^{7+\sqrt{9}}) + (8 \times ((5^7) \times 6)) \right) \\
 4799326 &:= \left((4^7) - \left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((3^2)^6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4799344 &:= 4^7 - 9 + \sqrt{9^{(3+4)} \times \sqrt{4}} \\
 4799345 &:= \left(\left((4^7) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((9^{3+4}) - 5 \right) \right) \\
 4799347 &:= \left(\left(\left((4^7) + \sqrt{9} \right) - 9 \right) + \left(\sqrt{34^7} \right) \right) \\
 4799348 &:= \left(\left((4^7) + \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((9^{3+4}) - 8 \right) \right) \\
 4799356 &:= \left(\left((4^7) + \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\sqrt{9^{3+5+6}} \right) \right) \\
 4799359 &:= \left(\left((4^7) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((9 + (3^{5+9})) \right) \right) \\
 4799434 &:= \left((4^7) + \left((9^{9-\sqrt{4}}) + \left((3^4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4799497 &:= \left((4^7) + \left(\left((9 + \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \left((9^7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4799569 &:= \left(\left((4^7) + \left(\sqrt{9^{9+5}} \right) \right) + \left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 4799775 &:= \left(\left(- (4) / \sqrt{7+9} \right) + \left(\left((9^7) + (7^5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4806297 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{4} - 8) \right)^{06} \right) / 2 \right) + \left((9^7) \right) \right) \\
 4813634 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((8 - 1) + \left((3^6) \times 3 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4826729 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (82) \right) + \left(\left((6 + 7)^2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 4826743 &:= -\sqrt{4} - 8^2 + \sqrt{(6+7)^{4 \times 3}} \\
 4826749 &:= \left((4 - (8^2)) + \left((6 + 7)^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \right) \right) \\
 4826761 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{48^2} - \left((6 + 7)^6 \right) \right) \times (-1) \right) \\
 4826766 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^8} + 2 \right) / (-6) \right) + \left(\left((7 + 6)^6 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4826799 &:= \left(- \left((4 + 8) - 2 \right) + \left((6 + 7)^{9-\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 4836198 &:= \left(4 - \left(- \left((8 + (3^6)) \right) \right) \times \left(1 + \left(\sqrt{9^8} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4836969 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 8)^3 \right) \times 6 \right) + \left(9^6 \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 4841280 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} - 8) \times (-41) \right)^2 \right) \times 80 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4841854 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} - (84)) \times \left(- \left((1 + 8)^5 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4841954 &:= \left(- \left(\left((4 \times 8) - (41 \times (9^5)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4841994 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} - 8) \times \left(- (41) \times \left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) + 4 \right) \right) \\
 4843762 &:= \left((4 + 8) - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^7 \right) \times (-62) \right) \right) \\
 4843874 &:= - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} - \sqrt{8^4}) \times \left(- \left((3 - 8) \right)^7 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4847297 &:= \left(\left(\left((4^8) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - \left(7^{-2+9} \right) \right) \times (-7) \right) \\
 4849657 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^8 \sqrt{4}} \right) \times (9 + 65) \right) - 7 \right) \\
 4849662 &:= \left(\left((4^8) \times \left((\sqrt{4 \sqrt{9}}) + 66 \right) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 4849738 &:= \left(\left(\left((4^8) + 4 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(- (7) + \sqrt{3^8} \right) \right) \\
 4849812 &:= \left(\left(- \left((4^8) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left((9 - 81) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 4851495 &:= \sqrt{(48 + 51)^{\sqrt{4 \times \sqrt{9}}}} \times 5 \\
 4853951 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 85)^3 \right) - \left((9^5) \times 1 \right) \right) \\
 4854724 &:= -4 + 8 \times \left(5 - (4 \times 7)^2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4863994 &:= \left(- \left((4 - 86) \right) \times \left((39^{\sqrt{9}}) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4865589 &:= \left((-4 - \left(- (865) \times \sqrt{5^8} \right)) \times 9 \right) \\
 4869497 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (8) + \left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \left((9^7) \right) \right) \\
 4878864 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(- (8) - \left(\sqrt{7^8} \times \left(\sqrt{8^6} - 4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4879172 &:= \left((4^8) + \left(\left(7 + \sqrt{(9 \times 1)^7} \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 4879463 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((8 \times 7) - 9 \right)^4 - (6^3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4879469 &:= \left((4 + \left((8 \times 7) - 9 \right)^4 \right) - (6^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \\
 4879474 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times (-8)) - 7 \right) \times 9 \right) + \left((47^4) \right) \right) \\
 4879679 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((8 \times 7) - 9 \right)^{6+7-9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4879683 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((8 \times 7) - 9 \right)^{\sqrt{6 \times 8/3}} \right) \\
 4879688 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - 87 \times 9 \right)^{-6+8} \times 8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4879691 &:= \sqrt{4} + 8 + (7 - 9 \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}+1} \\
 4879697 &:= \sqrt{4} \times 8 + (7 - 9 \times 6)^{\sqrt{9+7}} \\
 4883368 &:= \left((\sqrt{4^8} - 8) \times ((3^{3+6}) + 8) \right) \\
 4889796 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(88 \times \left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \times (-6) \right) \\
 4892942 &:= \left(\left(\left(4 + \left((8 \times 92) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 2 \right) \\
 4892944 &:= \left(\left(\left((4 \times 8) + 9 \right) + (2^9) \right) \times 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4896975 &:= \left(\left(- \left((4^8) \right) + \sqrt{9^6/9} \right) \times (-75) \right) \\
 4912995 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4^9} - (1 \times 2)) / \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 5 \right) \\
 4912998 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((91 - (2 \times \sqrt{9}))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4914975 &:= \left(\left(\left((4^9) \times 1 \right) / 4 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 75 \\
 4917244 &:= \left(-4 + \left(\left((9 - 1) \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{24}} / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4917750 &:= \left(-4 + (\sqrt{9^{1+7}}) \right) \times 750 \\
 4918784 &:= \left(\sqrt{4^9} \times \left(\sqrt{1+8} - \left(\sqrt{7^8} \times (-4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4919524 &:= \left(\left(4 + \left(9 \times \left((1 + \sqrt{9^5}) + 2 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4921877 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(9 \times \left(- \left((2 + 1) - 8 \right)^7 \times 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4921879 &:= \left(4 - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 2)^{-1+8} \right) \times (- (7 \times 9)) \right) \right) \\
 4923750 &:= \left(\left(4 + \left(\sqrt{9^{23}} \right) \right) \times 750 \right) \\
 4936776 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (-9) \right) - \left(\left((3^6) - (7^7) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \\
 4937284 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{49} + \left(\left((3^7) + 28 \right) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4938390 &:= \left(\left(-4 + \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((38^3) \right) \right) \times 90 \\
 4940776 &:= \left(4 - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^4} + \left(0 - (7^7) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 4941246 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{49^{4+1+2}} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 6 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4941256 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{4})^{1 \times 2 + 5} \right) \times (-6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4941276 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 9 \right) + \left(\left((4 + 1) + 2 \right)^7 \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 4941277 &:= \left(4 - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left((4 + 1) + \left(2 \times (7^7) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4941776 &:= \left(\sqrt{4^9} + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(1 - (7^7) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 4945536 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 4^5 \right) \times (53 \times 6) \right) \right) \\
 4952195 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}} \right) - \left(5 + \left(2 \times (19^5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4952198 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((9 + (5 \times 2))^{-1 \times \sqrt{9} + 8} \right) \right) \\
 4956295 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{49^5} \right) - 6 \right) \times 295 \right) \\
 4957642 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{9+5}} \right) + \left((7^6) \times 42 \right) \right) \\
 4959276 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((9^5) - 9 \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \right) \times (- (7 \times 6)) \\
 4959576 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((9 \times 5) - \left((9^5) \times 7 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 4959726 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (9^5) \right) \right) + 9 \right) \times (-7) \right) - 2 \right) \times 6 \\
 4959773 &:= \left(\left(- \left((4 \times (9^5)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-7) - (7^3) \\
 4959780 &:= \left(-4 + 9^5 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9+7} + 80 \right) \\
 4959784 &:= 4 + \left(9^5 - \sqrt{9+7} \right) \times 84 \\
 4959786 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (9^5) \right) \right) + 9 \right) \times (-7) \right) + 8 \right) \times 6 \\
 4959792 &:= \left(\left((4 - (9^5)) - \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times \left(- (9^2) \right) \right) \\
 4959857 &:= \left(\left(- (4) \times \left(\left(- (9^5) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 8 \right) - 5 \right) \times 7 \\
 4959862 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((9^5) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(- (86 - 2) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4959866 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((9^5) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left((8 + 6) \times 6 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4959892 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(\left(\left((9^5) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 8 \right) \times \left(- (9 - 2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4959927 &:= \left(\left(\left((4 \times (9^5)) - 9 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^2}} \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 4959939 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (9^5) \right) \times (9 - 93) \right) - 9 \right) \\
 4959944 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (9^5) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{9^4} \right) \right) + 4 \right) \right) \\
 4959948 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (9^5) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(- \left((9 \times 4) - 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4961544 &:= \left(49 \times \left(6 + \left((15^4) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4963984 &:= (4 - (96 \times 3 - 9) \times 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4967424 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} + 9) \times ((674 - 2)^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \\
 4968441 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(4+9)^6} + (8 \times 4) \right)^{\sqrt{4 \times 1}} \right) \\
 4969194 &:= \left(\left((4+9) + \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) - 1 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4974219 &:= \left(\left(- \left((4^9) \right) + \sqrt{74+2} \right) \times (-19) \right) \\
 4975744 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + (7^5)) \times (-74) \right) + 4 \right) \right) \\
 4976644 &:= \left(4 - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times (-7)) + 6 \right) \times \left((6 \times 4)^4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4977454 &:= \left((4 + (9^7)) + \left((7 \times \sqrt{4+5})^4 \right) \right) \\
 4979674 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} - \left((\sqrt{9} + (7^{\sqrt{9}})) \times 6 \right)) \times \left(- (7^4) \right) \right) \\
 4979799 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} \times (-7))) \times (\sqrt{9^7} \times 99) \right) \\
 4981824 &:= \left(((4 \times 9) \times (((8 \times 1) \times 8) - 2))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4982075 &:= \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{49^8} \times 2075} \right) \\
 4983492 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((4 - 98) \right)^3 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times 2 \\
 4983497 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((4 - 98) \right)^3 \right) \times \sqrt{4 \times 9} \right) - 7 \right) \\
 4983516 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((4 - 98) \right)^3 \right) + \sqrt{5-1} \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 4983534 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((4 - 98) \right)^3 \right) + 5 \right) \times 3 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4983546 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((4 - 98) \right)^3 \right) + 5 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 6 \\
 4992800 &:= (\sqrt{4} - 9 \times 9)^2 \times 800 \\
 4997547 &:= \left(\left((4^{\sqrt{9}}) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(7 + (5 \times (4^7)) \right) \right) \\
 4997550 &:= \left(\left(- (49) + \left((\sqrt{9} + 7)^5 \right) \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 4997632 &:= (\sqrt{4^9} \times (9763 - 2)) \\
 4998272 &:= - \left(\left(\left((4 \times \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left((8+2)^7 / 2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4998720 &:= \left((4^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - 8) \right)^7 \right) - (20) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4999228 &:= \left(\left(4 - \left((\sqrt{9^9}) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(2 - (2^8) \right) \right) \\
 4999482 &:= \left(\left((4 - (9/9))^9 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4^8} - 2 \right) \right) \\
 4999484 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{9 \times 9}}} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4^8} - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4999699 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4^9} - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + ((9 \times 6))) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4999872 &:= \left((4^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left(\left(\left(- (9) / \sqrt{9} \right) + 8 \right)^7 \right) - 2 \right) \\
 4999965 &:= \left((\sqrt{49} - \left(((9/9) + 9)^6 \right)) \times (-5) \right) \\
 5038689 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (50) - \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{38}}} \right) + (6^8) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 5038839 &:= (5 - 03 - 8)^8 - 3 \times \sqrt{9} \\
 5038898 &:= \left(50 - \left(- (3) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8 \times 9}} \right)^8 \right) \right) \\
 5038968 &:= \left(((5 \times 03) \times 8) - (\sqrt{9} \times \left(- (6^8) \right)) \right) \\
 5088443 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left((088 - \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{4} \right)^3 \right) \right) \\
 5088498 &:= \left(50 - \left(\left((88 - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-8) \right) \right) \\
 5142789 &:= \left(- (51) \times \left(\left(- (42) \times \sqrt{7^8} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 5143758 &:= \left(\left(- (51) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(- \left((3 \times (7^5)) + 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 5143824 &:= \left((51 - \sqrt{4}) \times \left((3^8) \times (2^4) \right) \right) \\
 5143844 &:= \left(\left(5 + \left((14 \times \sqrt{3^8})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 5147744 &:= \left(\left((5+1) + \sqrt{4^7} \right) \times \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^4 \right) \right) \\
 5153634 &:= \left(\sqrt{5-1} + \left(\left(- (5) + \sqrt{3^6} \right)^{3+\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 5153638 &:= \left((5+1) + \left(\left(- (5) + \sqrt{3^6} \right)^{-3+8} \right) \right) \\
 5153683 &:= \left(51 + \left(\left(- (5) + \sqrt{3^6} \right)^{8-3} \right) \right) \\
 5156946 &:= \left(\left((5+1) + \sqrt{5^6} \right) \times \left((9^4) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 5157994 &:= \left(((51 \times 5) + 7) \times \left((\sqrt{9^9}) + 4 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$5173594 := \left((5^{1+7}) + \left((3^5) \times 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$5176468 := \left((\sqrt{5-1} - (7^6)) \times (4 - (6 \times 8)) \right)$$

$$5176564 := \left((\sqrt{5-1} + \left((7^6) \times (5+6) \right)) \times 4 \right)$$

$$5183979 := \left(\left(\left((5 \times 1) \times 8 \right) \times 3 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 7 \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$5184000 := \left(\sqrt{(5+1)^8} \times 4000 \right)$$

$$5196488 := \left((\sqrt{5-1} + (\sqrt{9^{6+4}})) \times 88 \right)$$

$$5215995 := \left(- \left((52 + (1^5)) \right) \right) \times \left((\sqrt{9^9}) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$5217378 := \left(5 + (2173 \times \sqrt{7^8}) \right)$$

$$5221044 := \left(522 \times \left((10^4) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$5234944 := \left(((523 + 49) \times 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$5242875 := \left(- (5) \times \left((2/\sqrt{4}) - \left((2^{8+7+5}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5242877 := \left(- \left((5 \times (2 - (4^{2+8}))) \right) \right) + \sqrt{7 \times 7}$$

$$5242905 := 5 \times \left(2^{\sqrt{4+2 \times 9}} + 05 \right)$$

$$5242928 := \left(\left((5 \times (2^{4^2})) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (2 \times 8) \right)$$

$$5243784 := \left(((5+2)^{\sqrt{4+3}}) \times (78 \times 4) \right)$$

$$5243920 := \left(\left(- (52) - \left((4^3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times (-20) \right)$$

$$5249692 := \left((5+2) \times \left((\sqrt{4} + ((96 \times 9))^2 \right) \right)$$

$$5256139 := \left(- (5) + \left(2 \times \left((\sqrt{5^6} + 13)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5267692 := \left(((5 \times 2) - (6 \times (76^{\sqrt{9}}))) \times (-2) \right)$$

$$5267694 := \left((5-2) \times \left(- (6) + \left((76^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5267699 := \left(5 + \left(2 \times \left((6 \times (76^{\sqrt{9}})) - 9 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5267999 := \left(- \left((5^2) \right) + \left(((67-9) \times \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$5268019 := \left(- (5) + \left((2 \times ((6+80)+1))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$5268029 := \left(5 + \left((2 + ((6+80) \times 2))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$5274997 := \left(\left((5 + (2 \times (7 + (4 \times 9)))) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7 \right)$$

$$5282200 := \left(\sqrt{(5+2)^8} \times 2200 \right)$$

$$5294205 := \left(\left((5 + ((2^9) \times \sqrt{4}))^2 \right) \times 05 \right)$$

$$5294295 := \left(\left((5+2)^{\sqrt{9 \times 4}} + 2 \right) \times (9 \times 5) \right)$$

$$5308416 := \left(((5+3) \times (08 - \sqrt{4}))^{\sqrt{16}} \right)$$

$$5314395 := \left((5 \times 3) \times \left(- (1) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (3 \times (9^5)) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5314410 := \left(\left((5^{3-1} + \sqrt{4})^4 \right) \times 10 \right)$$

$$5314683 := \left(\left(((5+3)-1) + 4 \right)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}}} \times 3 \right)$$

$$5314694 := \left(5 + (3-14)^6 \right) \times \sqrt{9} - 4$$

$$5314698 := \left(5 + (3-14)^6 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}$$

$$5315572 := \left(- (53) - \left(- \left((15^5) \right) \times \sqrt{7^2} \right) \right)$$

$$5315574 := \left(- \left((53 - ((15^5) \times 7)) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$5315667 := \left(\left(((5 \times 3) \times 1)^5 + \sqrt{6 \times 6} \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$5326848 := \left(\left((((5 \times 3) + 2) \times 6) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 8 \right)$$

$$5334349 := \left(- (5) - \left(\left((3 + (3^4))^3 + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-9) \right) \right)$$

$$5336944 := \left(- \left((5^3) - (3^6) \right) \right) \times (94^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$5344844 := \left(\left(- \left((5^3) \right) + \left((\sqrt{4} + ((4 \times 8))^4 \right) \right) \right) \times 4$$

$$5356778 := \left(- \left((53 - ((5^6) \times 7)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}$$

$$5359159 := \left(((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}}) - ((1+5)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$5359247 := \left(((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}}) - \left(- ((2-4)^7) \right) \right)$$

$$5359277 := \left(((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}}) - ((2 \times 7) \times 7) \right)$$

$$5359292 := \left(((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}}) - \left((2 + (9^2)) \right) \right)$$

$$5359294 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{92}}} \right) - (\sqrt{94}) \right)$$

$$5359336 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - ((3 + 36)) \right)$$

$$5359339 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left((3^3) + 9 \right) \right)$$

$$5359341 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (34 \times 1) \right)$$

$$5359345 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left((3 \times \sqrt{4}) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5359348 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{34+8}} \right)$$

$$5359354 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(3 \times (5 + \sqrt{4}) \right) \right)$$

$$5359355 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - ((3 \times 5) + 5) \right)$$

$$5359363 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - ((3 + 6) + 3) \right)$$

$$5359364 := \left(\left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 3 \right) - \sqrt{64} \right)$$

$$5359366 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (((3 - 6) - 6)) \right)$$

$$5359367 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{-3 + 67} \right)$$

$$5359369 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - ((3 - 6) + 9) \right)$$

$$5359371 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (((3 - 7) \times 1)) \right)$$

$$5359372 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{9/3} \right) - \sqrt{7 + 2} \right)$$

$$5359374 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (3 / (7 - 4)) \right)$$

$$5359377 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (3 - (7/7)) \right)$$

$$5359378 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - ((3 \times (7 - 8))) \right)$$

$$5359379 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{9/3} \right) + \sqrt{7 + 9} \right)$$

$$5359393 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (3 \times (9 - 3)) \right)$$

$$5359396 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + ((3 \times 9) - 6) \right)$$

$$5359399 := \left(\left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + ((3 \times 9)) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$5359413 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (41 - 3) \right)$$

$$5359414 := \left(\left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 41 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$5359419 := \left(\left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 41 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$5359423 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left((4^2) \times 3 \right) \right)$$

$$5359425 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times 25 \right) \right)$$

$$5359429 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + ((4 + 2) \times 9) \right)$$

$$5359435 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + ((4 \times 3) \times 5) \right)$$

$$5359439 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(\sqrt{4^{-3+9}} \right) \right)$$

$$5359443 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left((4 + (4^3)) \right) \right)$$

$$5359487 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times (- (8 \times 7)) \right) \right)$$

$$5359627 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left((6^2) \times 7 \right) \right)$$

$$5359645 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (6 \times 45) \right)$$

$$5359718 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(7^{\sqrt{1+8}} \right) \right)$$

$$5359745 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + ((74 \times 5)) \right)$$

$$5359879 := \left(\left((5 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (((8 \times 7) \times 9)) \right)$$

$$5361776 := \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{36}}) + (1 \times 7) \right) \times \sqrt{76} \right)$$

$$5363864 := \left((5 + 3) + \left((6 \times 386)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$5366898 := \left(\left(\left((5^3) \times 6 \right) + 68 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^8} \right) \right)$$

$$5373914 := \left(\left(5 + (3^{7+3}) \right) \times \sqrt{91^{\sqrt{4}}} \right)$$

$$5399925 := \left(\left(\left((5 \times (3 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 25 \right)$$

$$5423429 := \left(((5 + 4) + 2) \times \left(\left((3^4) - 2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$5438224 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{5^4} + \sqrt{3^8}) \times 22 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$5439484 := \left(\left(\left(5 + (\sqrt{4} \times 39) \right) \times (4^8) \right) - 4 \right)$$

$$5451769 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{54 - 5} - (176^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$5451781 := \left(5 + \left((4 \times (51 - 7))^{\sqrt{8+1}} \right) \right)$$

$$5451783 := \left((5 + \sqrt{4}) + \left(\left((5 + 17) \times 8 \right)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$5463635 := \left(\left(\left(- (5) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times ((6+3) \times 6) \right) \right)^3 \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$5464375 := \left(- \left((5^4) \right) \times \left(\left((6 - \sqrt{4}) \times \left(- (3^7) \right) \right) + 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5466244 := \left((5 \times 466) + (2 \times 4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$5467500 := \left(\sqrt{(5+4)^6} \times 7500 \right)$$

$$5467686 := \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{4}+6}) - 76 \right) \times (8+6) \right)$$

$$5468568 := \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{4}+6}) - (8+5) \right) \times (6+8) \right)$$

$$5468675 := \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{4}+6}) \times (8+6) \right) - 75 \right)$$

$$5468696 := \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{4}+6}) \times (8+6) \right) - (9 \times 6) \right)$$

$$5468745 := \left(\left(\left((5^{4 \times (-6+8)}) \times 7 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$5468745 := -5 + \left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right)^8 \times (-6 + 4 \times 5)$$

$$5468861 := \left(\left(\left((5^{\sqrt{4}+6}) + 8 \right) \times (8+6) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$5468862 := \left(\left(\left((5^{\sqrt{4}+6}) + 8 \right) \times \sqrt{(8+6)^2} \right) \right)$$

$$5468864 := \left(\left(\left((5^{\sqrt{4}+6}) + 8 \right) \times (8+6) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$5473587 := \left(\left(- (5) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((7^3) + (5^8) \right) \right) \right) \times (-7) \right)$$

$$5479965 := \left(\left(- ((5 \times 47)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - (6^5) \right) \right)$$

$$5484285 := \left(\left(5 + \left(\left(\sqrt{4^8} - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) \right) \times 85 \right)$$

$$5484867 := \left(\left(\left((5 + \sqrt{4})^8 \right) + \sqrt{-4+8} \right) - (6^7) \right)$$

$$5484964 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \left((8 \times 49) \times 6 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$5487984 := \left(\left(- ((5 \times ((4-8) \times 7)))^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$5487994 := \left(\left(- ((5 \times ((4-8) \times 7)))^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$5493742 := \left(\left(\left((5^4) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left((3^7) \times 4 \right) \right) - 2 \right)$$

$$5493744 := \left(\left(\left((5^4) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (3^7) \right) \times \sqrt{4 \times 4} \right)$$

$$5495992 := (5^4 - \sqrt{9}) \times (5 - 99)^2$$

$$5497928 := \left(\left(\left((54 \times 9) + (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)^2 \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$5504979 := \left((5 - 50) - \left(- \left((4^9) \times 7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$5531949 := \left(\left(- (5) - \left(\left((5^{3-1}) + \sqrt{9} \right)^4 \right) \right) \times (-9) \right)$$

$$5546875 := \left((5^{5+\sqrt{4}}) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8} + (7 \times 5)} \right) \right)$$

$$5564394 := \left(\left(\left((556^{\sqrt{4}}) - 3 \right) \times 9 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$5564448 := \left((556^{\sqrt{4}}) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\sqrt{4} \times (-8) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5565125 := \left(\left(\left(- (5) \times \left(5 - \sqrt{6^{5+1}} \right) \right) \right)^2 \times 5 \right)$$

$$5569675 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- (56) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left((6+7)^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5598665 := \left(- (55) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(8 \times \left((6^6) \times 5 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5598695 := \left(- (5) \times \left(5 + \left(- (9) \times \sqrt{8^6 \times 9^5} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5598720 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{5 \times 5} + (9 - 8) \right)^7 \right) \times 20 \right)$$

$$5598725 := \left(5 - \left(- ((5 \times 9)) \times \sqrt{8 \times 72^5} \right) \right)$$

$$5598995 := \left((55 + \left((9 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{9} \right)) \times 5 \right)$$

$$5622164 := \left(\left(- (5) + \left(- (6) \times \left(22^{\sqrt{16}} \right) \right) \right) \times (-4) \right)$$

$$5624295 := \left(5 \times \left(\left((62 + 42)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5631134 := \left(5 + \left(\left(\left((6^3) \times 11 \right) - 3 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$5639542 := \left(\left((5^6) - 3 \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 5 \right) + 4 \right)^2 \right)$$

$$5646768 := \left(\left((56 - \sqrt{4}) - 6 \right) \times \left((7^6) - 8 \right) \right)$$

$$5647288 := \left(\left(5 + \left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(7^{-2+8} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$5647376 := \left(- (56) \times \left(-4 - \left(\sqrt{7^{3+7}} \times 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5658192 := \left(- (56) - \left((58^{1+\sqrt{9}}) / (-2) \right) \right)$$

$$5662944 := \left(56 \times \left(\left(- (6) + \sqrt{(2 \times 9)^4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$5664400 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{5^6} - 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 400 \right)$$

$$5668693 := \left(- \left((5 + 6) \right) - \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times \left(- \left(6 \times \left(9^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5668699 := \left(- (5) + \left(\left(\sqrt{6 \times 6} \times (8 \times 6) \right) \times \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right)$$

$$5668839 := \left(\left(- (5) + \left(\left(\sqrt{6 \times 6^8} \right) / (-8) \right) \right) \times \left(- (3 \times 9) \right) \right)$$

$$5668857 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{5^6} + ((6 \times 8)) \right) \times (8^5) \right) - 7 \right)$$

$$5668864 := \left(\left(\sqrt{5^6} + ((6 \times 8)) \right) \times \sqrt{8^{6+4}} \right)$$

$$5668954 := \left(\left(\sqrt{5^6} + \left((6 \times 8) \times (9^5) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$5669370 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(5 \times 6)^6} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (3 \times 70) \right)$$

$$5669829 := \left(\left(\sqrt{5^6} + \left((6^9 / 8) / 2 \right) \right) \right) \times 9$$

$$5678999 := \left(- \left((5^6) \right) - \left((78^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left(- (9) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5679674 := \left(\left((5 + (6^7)) + (9^6) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} \right)$$

$$5694634 := \left(\left(5 + \left(6 \times \left((9 + 4) \times 6^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$5695364 := \left(56 + \left(- \left(9 - \left((5 \times 3)^6 \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$5721664 := \left(\left(\left(5 + \left(- (7) \times \left(2 - \sqrt{(1 + 6)^6} \right) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$5726444 := \left(- (5) + \left(\left(\sqrt{7^{2+6}} - (4 + 4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$5734855 := \left((5 \times 7) \times \left(3 - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (8^5) \right) \times (-5) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5735339 := \left(\left((5 \times (7 - 3)) + (53 \times 3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$5740473 := \left(5 - 7^4 \right)^{\sqrt{04}} - 7^3$$

$$5742864 := \left(5 - 7^4 \right)^2 + \sqrt{8^6} \times 4$$

$$5746440 := \left(\left((5^7) + (4^{\sqrt{64}}) \right) \times 40 \right)$$

$$5747538 := \left(- (57) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((7^5) \times 3 \right) \right) \right) + 8 \right) \right)$$

$$5747989 := \left(- (5) - \left(- \left(\left((7^4) \times 798 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5749920 := \left(\left(\left(- \left((5 - 74) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 20 \right)$$

$$5754685 := \left(\left(- \left((5 - (7^5)) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \times 685$$

$$5756645 := \left(\left(\left(- (5) \times \left(7 - \left(5 \times \sqrt{6^6} \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) / 5 \right)$$

$$5758969 := \left(\left(\left((5 \times 7) / 5 \right)^8 \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$5759893 := \left(5 + \left(\left(7^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left((8 + 9)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5762749 := \left(- \left((57 \times (6^2)) \right) + \left(7^{\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}}} \right) \right)$$

$$5763674 := \left(- \left(\left((5 - (7^6)) + (3 \times 6) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{7^4} \right)$$

$$5763767 := \left(- (5) - \left(\sqrt{7^6} \times \left(3 - \left((7^6) / 7 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5764284 := \left(\left(- (5) + \left(7^{\sqrt{64}} \right) \right) - \left((2^8) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$5764286 := \left(- (5) + \left(\left((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + 2 \right) - \sqrt{8^6} \right) \right)$$

$$5764292 := \left(5 + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{64}} \right) - \left((2^9) + 2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5764294 := 5 + 7^{\sqrt{64}} - 2^{\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{4}}}}$$

$$5764398 := \left(- (5) + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{64}} \right) - 398 \right) \right)$$

$$5764403 := \left(5 + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{64}} \right) - 403 \right) \right)$$

$$5764453 := \left(\left(- (5) + \left(7^{\sqrt{64}} \right) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 5 \right)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$5764458 := \left(\left(- \left((5 - (7^6)) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\left(\sqrt{4} + 5 \right)^8}} \right)$$

$$5764477 := \left(5 + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{64}} \right) - (47 \times 7) \right) \right)$$

$$5764506 := \left(5 + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{64}} \right) - (50 \times 6) \right) \right)$$

$$5764551 := \left(5 + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{64}} \right) - \left((5 \times 51) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5764556 := \left(\left(5 - (7^6) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((5 - 56) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5764578 := \left(5 - \left(\left(76 \times \sqrt{4 + 5} \right) - (7^8) \right) \right)$$

$$5764591 := \left(- \left((5 \times 7) \times 6 \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 5 \right)^{9-1} \right) \right)$$

$$5764613 := \left(- (5) + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{64}} \right) - (61 \times 3) \right) \right)$$

$$5764628 := \left(- (5) + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{64}} \right) - (6 \times 28) \right) \right)$$

$$5764662 := \left(5 + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{64}} \right) - \left((6 + 6)^2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5764664 := \left(\left(- (5) + \left(7^{\sqrt{64}} \right) \right) - \left(66 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5764672 &:= (5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) - (67 \times 2))) \\
 5764679 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) - (((6 + 7) \times 9)))) \\
 5764695 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) - ((6 + 95)))) \\
 5764708 &:= ((- (57) - \sqrt{64}) + ((7^{08})) \\
 5764712 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) - ((7 \times 12)))) \\
 5764718 &:= ((- ((5 + 76)) - \sqrt{4}) + ((7 \times 1)^8)) \\
 5764719 &:= ((- (((5 \times 7) + 6)) \times \sqrt{4}) + (7^{-1+9})) \\
 5764722 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) - ((72 + 2)))) \\
 5764727 &:= (5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) - ((72 + 7)))) \\
 5764728 &:= (((5 - 76) - \sqrt{4}) + (\sqrt{72^8})) \\
 5764729 &:= (5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) - ((7 \times (2 + 9)))) \\
 5764733 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) - ((7 \times 3) \times 3))) \\
 5764736 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) - ((7 + 3) \times 6))) \\
 5764743 &:= ((- (((5 \times 7) - 6)) \times \sqrt{4}) + (7^{\sqrt{4^3}})) \\
 5764746 &:= ((- ((5 - ((7^6) + 4))) \times \sqrt{74}) - 6) \\
 5764747 &:= ((- (5) + (7^{\sqrt{64}})) - (\sqrt{\sqrt{74} \times 7})) \\
 5764748 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{-6+\sqrt{4} \times 7}) - (48))) \\
 5764749 &:= ((- ((5 - ((7^6) + 4))) \times \sqrt{74}) - \sqrt{9}) \\
 5764754 &:= (- (5) - (7 \times (\sqrt{\sqrt{64}} - (7^{5+\sqrt{4}})))) \\
 5764757 &:= (5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) - \sqrt{7^5/7})) \\
 5764761 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) - (7 \times (6 - 1)))) \\
 5764762 &:= ((- (((5 \times 7) + 6)) + \sqrt{4}) + ((7^{6+2})) \\
 5764764 &:= (- (((((5 \times 7) + 6) - 4)) + (7^{\sqrt{64}})) \\
 5764771 &:= (5 + (- (7) \times ((6 - \sqrt{4}) - (((7^7) - 1))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5764774 &:= ((- ((5 \times 7)) + \sqrt{64}) + (((7 \times 7)^4))) \\
 5764779 &:= (- ((5 + (7 \times ((6 - 4) - (7^7)))))) - \sqrt{9} \\
 5764790 &:= (5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) - ((7 + 9) + 0))) \\
 5764794 &:= (- ((5 - (7^{6 \times 4 - 7 - 9}))) - \sqrt{4}) \\
 5764795 &:= (- (5) + (((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + \sqrt{7+9}) - 5)) \\
 5764799 &:= (- ((5 - (7^{6 \times 4 - 7 - 9}))) + \sqrt{9}) \\
 5764802 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + (8 - 02))) \\
 5764804 &:= ((5 + (7^{64/8})) - \sqrt{04}) \\
 5764807 &:= (5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + (8 - 07))) \\
 5764808 &:= ((5 + (7^{\sqrt{64}})) + \sqrt{\sqrt{8 + 08}}) \\
 5764809 &:= ((5 + (7^{64/8})) + \sqrt{09}) \\
 5764812 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + ((8 \times 1) \times 2))) \\
 5764813 &:= (5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + (8 - (1^3)))) \\
 5764814 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + \sqrt{81 \times 4})) \\
 5764815 &:= (5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + (8 + (1^5)))) \\
 5764816 &:= ((5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + 8)) + \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}) \\
 5764817 &:= ((- (5) + (7^{\sqrt{64}})) + (\sqrt{8 + 1} \times 7)) \\
 5764818 &:= (5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + \sqrt{8 \times 18})) \\
 5764821 &:= (5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + ((8 \times 2) - 1))) \\
 5764822 &:= (5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + ((8/2)^2))) \\
 5764824 &:= (5 + (((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + ((8 \times 2))) + \sqrt{4})) \\
 5764826 &:= (5 + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + ((8 + (2 \times 6)))) \\
 5764828 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + ((8/2) \times 8))) \\
 5764842 &:= ((5 + (7^{\sqrt{64}})) + ((8 - \sqrt{4})^2)) \\
 5764844 &:= (- (5) + ((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + ((8 + 4) \times 4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$5764852 := (-5) + \left((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + ((8 \times (5 + 2))) \right)$$

$$5764859 := \left(5 + \left((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + (8 + (5 \times 9)) \right) \right)$$

$$5764882 := (-5) + \left((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + ((88 - 2)) \right)$$

$$5764884 := \left((-5) + (7^{\sqrt{64}}) \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{884}}$$

$$5764887 := \left(5 + \left((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + ((88 - 7)) \right) \right)$$

$$5764894 := \left((5 + (7^{\sqrt{64}})) + (8 \times (9 + \sqrt{4})) \right)$$

$$5764913 := (-5) + \left((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + ((9 \times 13)) \right)$$

$$5764927 := (-5) + \left(\left((7^{\sqrt{64}}) + \sqrt{9} \right) + (2^7) \right)$$

$$5764947 := \left((5 + (7^{\sqrt{64}})) + (\sqrt{9} \times 47) \right)$$

$$5764948 := \left((-5) + (76 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) + \left((9 - \sqrt{4})^8 \right)$$

$$5764952 := \left((-5) + (7^{\sqrt{64}}) \right) + (\sqrt{9} \times 52)$$

$$5764978 := \left(((57 + 6) - 4) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + (7^8)$$

$$5764988 := \left((-5) + (7^{\sqrt{64}}) \right) + (\sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 8))$$

$$5764994 := \left((-5) + (7^{\sqrt{64}}) \right) + (99 \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$5767167 := \left(\left((-5) + \sqrt{76} \right) + \left((7^{1+6}) \right) \right) \times 7$$

$$5767168 := \left(((5 + 76) + 7) \times \sqrt{16^8} \right)$$

$$5767197 := (-5) + \left(\sqrt{76} \times (\sqrt{7^{1+9}} + 7) \right)$$

$$5772347 := \left(\left((5^7) + \left((72^3) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$5772885 := \left(577 \times \left(\sqrt{(2 + 8)^8} + 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5774374 := \left(-((5 \times 7)) + \left(\left((7^4) + \sqrt{-3 + 7} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$5774404 := \left(-5 \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{(7 \times 7)^4} + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{04}} \right)$$

$$5774409 := (5 - 7 - 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} + 0 \times 9$$

$$5774421 := 5 + 7 + (7^4 + \sqrt{4})^2 \times 1$$

$$5774436 := (5 - 7 - 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} + \sqrt{3^6}$$

$$5774442 := \left((5 \times 7) + \left(\left(\left((7^4) + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 2 \right) \right)$$

$$5774444 := \left((5 \times 7) + \left(\left(\left((7^4) - \sqrt{4} \right) + 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$5779216 := \left((5 + \left((7^{\sqrt{7+9}}) - 2 \right))^{\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}} \right)$$

$$5781472 := \left(\left((5^7) + \sqrt{8 + 1} \right) \times (\sqrt{4} + 72) \right)$$

$$5784375 := \left(\left(-((5^7)) + \left((8 + \sqrt{4})^3 \right) \right) \times (-75) \right)$$

$$5784479 := \left(-((5 - (7^8))) + \sqrt{(4 \times 4 - 7)^9} \right)$$

$$5784482 := \left(\left((-5) \times \sqrt{7^8} \right) + 4 \right) \times (-482)$$

$$5784489 := \left((5 + (7^8)) + \sqrt{(4/4 + 8)^9} \right)$$

$$5785286 := \left((5 + (7^8)) - \left(-5 \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^6} \right) \right)$$

$$5787396 := \left((5 \times \left((7 + 8) \times 7^3 \right)) - \sqrt{9^6} \right)$$

$$5787677 := \left(\left(\left(\left(5^{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}} \right) \times 7 \right) + (6^7) \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$5788818 := \left(\left((5 + \sqrt{7^8})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} \right) - (18) \right)$$

$$5788827 := \left(\left((5 + \sqrt{7^8})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} \right) - (2 + 7) \right)$$

$$5788828 := \left(\left((5 + \sqrt{7^8})^{8/8 \times 2} \right) - 8 \right)$$

$$5788829 := \left(\left((5 + \sqrt{7^8})^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}} \right) + ((2 - 9)) \right)$$

$$5788833 := \left(\left((5 + \sqrt{7^8})^{\sqrt{8/8+3}} \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$5788834 := \left(\left((5 + \sqrt{7^8})^{\sqrt{8/8+3}} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$5788836 := (5 + \sqrt{7^8})^{8/(8 \times 3/6)}$$

$$5788839 := \left(\left((5 + \sqrt{7^8})^{\sqrt{8/8+3}} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5789179 &:= \left(\left((5 + \sqrt{78})^{\sqrt{9}-1} \right) + (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \\
 5795333 &:= \left(5 - \left(\left((7 \times (\sqrt{9} + 5))^3 \right) \times (-33) \right) \right) \\
 5798464 &:= \left(\left((-57) + \sqrt{98} \right) - (4^6) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 5799645 &:= \left(\left((5 + ((7^{\sqrt{9}}) + \sqrt{96}))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 5803299 &:= \left(\left(- \left((5 + (803^2)) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-9) \\
 5817744 &:= (5 - 8 - 1 - 7 - 7^4)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 5819296 &:= \left((\sqrt{58} + 1) \times 9296 \right) \\
 5819678 &:= \left(5 - \left((-8) \times \sqrt{196} \right) - (7^8) \right) \\
 5821935 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{58} - 2)^{-1+\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (3 \times 5) \right) \\
 5831995 &:= \left((5 \times (((8 - 3) - 1) \times 9))^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 \right) \\
 5838865 &:= \left(\left(- \left((5^8) \times 3 \right) \right) + \sqrt{88} \right) + 6 \times (-5) \\
 5838895 &:= \left(\left(- \left((5^8) \times 3 \right) \right) + ((8 + 8)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times (-5) \\
 5841884 &:= -5 + \left(8 \times \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(1 - 8)^8} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 5841990 &:= \left((\sqrt{58} - (4^{-1+9})) \right) \times (-90) \\
 5843745 &:= \left((\sqrt{58+4} \times 374) - 5 \right) \\
 5845906 &:= \left((5 + 8) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(5 + (9^{06}) \right) \\
 5857479 &:= - \left(\left((\sqrt{58} - ((5^{7+\sqrt{4}}) - 7)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 5857495 &:= - \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{58} - (5^{7+\sqrt{4}})) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 5 \right) \right) \\
 5857599 &:= \left(- \left((585 + 7) - (5^9) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 5857839 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{58}} \times (-5^7) \right) \right) + (8^3) \right) \times (-\sqrt{9}) \\
 5857925 &:= \left(58 + \left(- \left((5^7) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times (-25) \\
 5858895 &:= \left(\left((5 \times 8) - \left((5^8) + 8 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5858943 &:= \left(\left((5^8) \times 5 \right) - \left((8 \times 9) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 3 \\
 5858983 &:= \left(\left((5 \times (8 + (5^8))) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (8^3) \right) \\
 5859085 &:= \left(\left(- \left((5^8) \right) \times \sqrt{09} \right) + (58) \right) \times (-5) \\
 5859194 &:= \left(\left(- \left((58 - ((5^9) - 1)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 4 \\
 5859197 &:= \left(\left(- \left((58 - ((5^9) + 1)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 7 \\
 5859198 &:= \left(- \left((58 - ((5^9) - 1)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{98}}}} \\
 5859249 &:= \left(- \left((5 \times 8) - \left(((5^9) + 2) - 4 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 5859256 &:= \left(- \left((5 - 8) \times ((5^9) + 2) \right) \right) - \sqrt{56} \\
 5859273 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{58}} - \left(((5^9) - 2) - 7 \right) \right) \times (-3) \right) \\
 5859275 &:= \left(\left(- \left((5^8) - 5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} - (2 - 7) \right) \times (-5) \\
 5859293 &:= \left(-58 + \left(- \left((5^9) \right) + (2^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times (-3) \right) \\
 5859294 &:= \left(- \left((5 - 8) \right) \times \left(((5^9) - 29) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 5859295 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((5^8) - 5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} - 2 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-5) \\
 5859298 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{58}} - \left(((5^9) + 2) \right) \right) \times (-\sqrt{9}) \right) - 8 \right) \\
 5859299 &:= \left(-58 - \left(- \left((5^9) \right) + (2 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 5859405 &:= \left(- \left((5 - 8) \right) \times \left((5^9) + (\sqrt{4} \times 05) \right) \right) \\
 5859409 &:= \left((5 \times 8) - \left(- \left((5^9) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{09} \right) \\
 5859417 &:= \left(- \left((5 - 8) \right) \times \left((5^9) + (\sqrt{4} \times (1 \times 7)) \right) \right) \\
 5859419 &:= \left(- \left(\left((5 - 8) \times (5^9) \right) - 41 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \\
 5859425 &:= \left(\left(- \left((5^8) / 5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-25) \\
 5859427 &:= \left((5 \times 8) + \left(\left((5^9) + 4 \right) \times \sqrt{2+7} \right) \right) \\
 5859434 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{58}} + \left(((5^9) - 4) \right) \right) \times 3 \right) - 4 \right) \\
 5859437 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{58}} - \left(- \left((5^9) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 3 \right) - 7 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$5859438 := \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} + \left(\left((5^9) - 4 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}} \right)$$

$$5859439 := \left((5 \times 8) + \left(\left((5^9) + \sqrt{4^3} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$5859445 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left((5^8) + 5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + (4/4) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$5859449 := \left(-(58) - \left(- \left(\left((5^9) + 44 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$5859462 := \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} + \left(\left((5^9) + 4 \right) \right) \right) \times (6/2) \right)$$

$$5859465 := (-5 + 8) \times \left(5^{\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{4}}}} + 6 \times 5 \right)$$

$$5859469 := \left(58 - \left(\left(- \left((5^9) \right) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times 6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$5859475 := \left(\left(\left(\left(- \left(\left((5^8) + 5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) - 7 \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$5859487 := \left(- \left(\left((5 - 8) \times (5^9) \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times (8 \times 7) \right) \right)$$

$$5859489 := \left(\left(- \left(\left((5 \times 8) + (5^9) \right) \right) + \sqrt{-4 + 8} \right) \times (-\sqrt{9}) \right)$$

$$5859495 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(\left((5^8) - 5 \right) + 9 \right) + 4 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$5859534 := \left(\left(58 + \left((5^9) - 5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{3^4}} \right)$$

$$5859539 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} + \left(\left((5^9) + 53 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)} \right)$$

$$5859549 := \left(\left(58 + (5^9) \right) \times \sqrt{(5 - 4) \times 9} \right)$$

$$5859559 := \left(-(5) - \left(- \left(\left(8 + \left((5^9) + 55 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$5859564 := \left(\left(\left(58 + \left((5^9) + 5 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$5859575 := \left(\left(- \left((5 \times 8) \right) - \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (5^7) \right) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$5859589 := \left((5 \times 8) + \left(\left((5^9) + 58 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$5859595 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left((5^8) - 5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (59) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$5859597 := \left(\left(- \left((5 - 8) \right)^5 \right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((5^9) - 7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5859639 := \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} + \left(\left((5^9) + 63 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$5859666 := \left(\left(\left((5^8) + 5 \right) \times (9 + 6) \right) + \sqrt{6^6} \right)$$

$$5859692 := \left(\left(\sqrt{5^8} + \left(\left((5^9) \times 6 \right) + 9 \right) \right) / 2 \right)$$

$$5859718 := \left(- \left(\left((5 - 8) \times (5^9) \right) \right) + \left(7^{\sqrt{1+8}} \right) \right)$$

$$5859759 := \left(- \left((5 - 8) \right) \times \left(\left(\left(5 - \sqrt{9} \right)^7 \right) + \left((5^9) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5859785 := \left(\left((5 - 87) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left(5^8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$5859795 := \left(\left(- \left(\left((5^8) - \left((5 - 9) \times 7 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$5859895 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left((5^8) + 5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (89) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$5859950 := \left(\sqrt{5^8} + \left(\left((5^9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 50 \right) \right)$$

$$5859964 := \left(\sqrt{5^8} + \left(\left((5^9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \sqrt{6^4} \right) \right)$$

$$5859979 := \left(\sqrt{5^8} + \left(\left(\left(5^{\sqrt{9 \times 9}} \right) - 7 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$5859984 := \left(\left(\sqrt{5^8} + \left((5^9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(8 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$5859985 := \left(\sqrt{5^8} - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left(5^8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5859986 := \left(\sqrt{5^8} + \left(\left((5^9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (8 + 6) \right) \right)$$

$$5859989 := \left(\sqrt{5^8} - \left(\left(- \left((5^9) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 8 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$5859991 := \left(\sqrt{5^8} + \left(\left((5^9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (9 \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$5859994 := \left(\sqrt{5^8} - \left(\left(- \left((5^9) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \sqrt{9 \times 4} \right) \right)$$

$$5859995 := \left(\sqrt{5^8} + \left(\left(\left((5^9) \times 9 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5859999 := \left(\sqrt{5^8} + \left(\left((5^9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (9/9) \right) \right)$$

$$5860275 := \left(\left(\left((5^8) + 60 \right) \times \sqrt{2 + 7} \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$5861888 := (5 - 861) \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}} \times 8$$

$$5862213 := \left(\left(\sqrt{5^8} + (6 + 2) \right) \times (21^3) \right)$$

$$5864445 := \left(\left(\left((5 + 8) + 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4 \times 4}} \right) \times 45 \right)$$

$$5864688 := \left(586 \times \left(\sqrt{(4 + 6)^8 + 8} \right) \right)$$

$$5865993 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(5 + 8)^6} + \left(\left((5^9) + 9 \right) \right) \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$5871385 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left((5^8) \times 3 \right) + 1 \right) \right) - \sqrt{7^8} \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$5875094 := \left(\left((5 \times 8) + 7 \right) \times \left(\left(50^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5876763 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{5^8} - \left((7 \times (6^7)) - 6 \right) \right) \times (-3) \right) \\
 5876781 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{5^8} - (7 \times (6^7)) \right) \times \sqrt{8+1} \right) \right) \\
 5882450 &:= \left(\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}} \right)^{2+4} \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 5894978 &:= \left(\left(\left((5^8) - 94 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) + (7^8) \right) \\
 5895184 &:= (58 \times (9 - 51) + 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 5898245 &:= \left(5 + \left(-((8 - 98)) \times \sqrt{2^{\sqrt{4^5}}} \right) \right) \\
 5898255 &:= \left(\left(\left((5^8) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((8 - 2)^5 \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 5904895 &:= \left(-5 + \left(\left((90 + \sqrt{4}) + 8 \right) \times (9^5) \right) \right) \\
 5904895 &:= \left(-5 + \left((98 + \sqrt{4}) \times (9^5) \right) \right) \\
 5911927 &:= \left(\left((5 + 911) + \sqrt{9} \right)^2 \times 7 \right) \\
 5914624 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{(9 \times 1)^4} \right) \times 6 \right) + 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 5921583 &:= \left(\left((5^9) + \sqrt{(2 \times (1 + 5))^8} \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 5926328 &:= \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{9}}) + 2 \right) \times \left(\left((6^3)^2 \right) + 8 \right) \right) \\
 5929445 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times (2 + 9))^4 \right) - \sqrt{4^5} \right) \right) \\
 5937495 &:= \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (73 + \sqrt{9}) \right) - 5 \right) \\
 5943844 &:= \left(\left((-5) \times \left((\sqrt{9} - (4^3)) \times 8 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 5949678 &:= (59 \times ((4 \times 9) + 6)) \times \sqrt{7^8} \\
 5951488 &:= \left(\left(-5 + \sqrt{(9^5+1) \times 4} \right) \times \sqrt{8^8} \right) \\
 5963943 &:= \left(\left((5 + 96) \times (3^9) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 3 \\
 5969295 &:= \left(\left((5 \times 9) + 6 \right)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^2}}} \times (9 \times 5) \right) \\
 5969295 &:= 5 \times \sqrt{(9 + 2^{\sqrt{9}})^6} \times 9^5 \\
 5971964 &:= (5 - \sqrt{9}) \times (7 - 19)^6 - \sqrt{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5971968 &:= (5 - 9)^{7+1} \times \sqrt{9^6} / 8 \\
 5971976 &:= \left((5 + \sqrt{9}) - \left(-((7 - 19))^7 \right) / (-6) \right) \\
 5971989 &:= \left(5 - \left(-((9 + 7)) \times \left(1 + ((9 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5972697 &:= \left(\left(\left(-((5 - 9))^7 \right) + 2 \right) / 6 \right) \times \sqrt{9^7} \\
 5973245 &:= \left(\left(\left((5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 73 \right) - 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 \right) \\
 5974623 &:= \left(\left((5^9) + \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^{6-2} \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 5978694 &:= \left(\left(-5 \times \left(9^{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}} \right) \right) + 69 \right) / (-4) \\
 5978713 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \left(9^{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}} \right) \right) + 7 \right) / (1 + 3) \\
 5978745 &:= \left(-5 \times \left(\left(\left(9^{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}} \right) + 7 \right) / (-4) \right) - 5 \right) \\
 5989495 &:= \left(\left(\left(5 \times (\sqrt{9} + 8) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (4 \times 9) \right) - 5 \right) \\
 5992448 &:= \left(5 + \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 2 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{(4 + 4)^8} \\
 5992704 &:= \left(((5 - 9) \times 9) \times (2 - 70) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 5997651 &:= \left(\left(-((5 \times 9)) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((7^6) \right) \right) \times 51 \\
 5999343 &:= \left(\left((5^9) + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^3 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times 3 \\
 5999568 &:= \left((5 \times 9) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-9 - \left((5^6) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 5999648 &:= \left(\left((5 - \sqrt{9}) + (9 \times 96) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 8 \right) \\
 5999856 &:= \left(-((5 \times 9)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - (8 \times (5^6)) \right) \\
 6022998 &:= \left(\left((6^{02}) - 2 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{9+8}}} \right) \right) \\
 6061444 &:= \left(6 - ((0 - 614) \times 4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 6064848 &:= \left(606 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 8)^4 \right) + 8 \right) \right) \\
 6110784 &:= \left(((61 + 10) + \sqrt{7^8})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 6128493 &:= \left(6 + \left(\left(-((1 + 2)) + \sqrt{8^4} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^3 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6140484 &:= \left((6 \times ((1 + 404) + 8))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 6145149 &:= \left(\left(\left((61 \times \sqrt{4}) + 5 \right)^{-1+4} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 6147429 &:= \left(\left((6 - 1)^{\sqrt{4}+7} \right) + (4^{2+9}) \right) \\
 6168564 &:= \left(61 \times \left(\left((6 \times 8) + 5 \right) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 6171794 &:= \left(\left(\left((6 - 1)^7 \right) - 1 \right) \times 79 \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 6171799 &:= \left(\left(\left((6 - 1)^7 \right) - 1 \right) \times 79 \right) + \sqrt{9} \\
 6182575 &:= \left(\sqrt{(6 + 1)^8 \times 2575} \right) \\
 6199935 &:= \left(\left(6 + \left(\left(\sqrt{1 \times 9^9} \right) \times (-9) \right) \right) \times (-35) \right) \\
 6224272 &:= \left(\left(\left((6 \times 2)^2 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{2+7}} \right) \times 2 \\
 6229494 &:= \left(- (6) + \left(\left(- \left((2 \times (2 - 94)) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 4 \right) \\
 6229497 &:= \left(\left(- \left((6 - 2) - (2 \times 94) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 7 \\
 6229498 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{6^2} + \left(\left(- \left((2 - 94) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-8) \right) \right) \\
 6249504 &:= \left(- (62) \times \left(\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}} \right) \right) + (50^4) \\
 6249958 &:= \left(6 - \left(- \left((2^4) \right) \times \left(\left(- (9) / \sqrt{9} \right) + (5^8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6249964 &:= \left(- \left((6^2) \right) + \left(\left(-4 + \left(\sqrt{9 \times 9 \times 6} \right) \right)^4 \right) \right) \\
 6274665 &:= \left(\left(\left(62 + \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) / (-6) \right) \times (-5) \right) \\
 6279174 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left((2^{7+\sqrt{9}}) - (1^7) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 6285456 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(- \left((2 \times 8)^5 \right) + \sqrt{(\sqrt{4} \times 5)^6} \right) \right) \\
 6288384 &:= \left((6 \times (2^8)) \right) \times \left(\left((8^3) \times 8 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 6291348 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left((2 \times 9) - (1 + 3)^{\sqrt{4}+8} \right) \right) \\
 6291408 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{2^{9+1^4}} \right) - 08 \right) \right) \\
 6291420 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left((2 \times \sqrt{9}) - \left(\sqrt{1 \times 4^{20}} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6291428 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{2^{9+1^4}} \right) \right) - (28) \right) \\
 6291434 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{2^{9+1^4}} \right) - 3 \right) \right) - 4 \right) \\
 6291438 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{2^{9+1^4}} \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 6291446 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{2^{9+1^4}} \right) \right) - (4 + 6) \right) \\
 6291447 &:= \left((6/2) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-1) \right) + \left((4 + 4)^7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 6291449 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{2^{9+1^4}} \right) \right) - \sqrt{49} \right) \\
 6291451 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{2^{9+1^4}} \right) \right) - (5 \times 1) \right) \\
 6291454 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(\left((2 + 9) + 1 \right) + 4^5 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 6291455 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{2^{9+1^4}} \right) \right) - (5/5) \right) \\
 6291459 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(\left((2 + 9) + 1 \right) + 4^5 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 6291461 &:= \left(6 + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{2^{9+1^4}} \right) \times 6 \right) - 1 \right) \right) \\
 6291462 &:= \left(6 + \left(\left(\sqrt{2^{9+1^4}} \right) \times \sqrt{6^2} \right) \right) \\
 6291464 &:= \left(\left(\left((6 - 2)^{9+1} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 6 \right) - 4 \\
 6291467 &:= \left((6 + 2) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(1 + \left((\sqrt{4} + 6)^7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6291468 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{2^{9+1^4}} \right) - ((6 - 8)) \right) \right) \\
 6291474 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{2^{9+1^4}} \right) + (7 - 4) \right) \right) \\
 6291486 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- (2) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((1 - (4 \times (8^6))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6291492 &:= \left((6 \times 2) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((1 \times 4)^9 \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 6291510 &:= \sqrt{6^2} \times \left(9 + (1 - 5)^{10} \right) \\
 6293187 &:= \left(\left((6 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(3 \times \left(1 + (8^7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6294528 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(- \left((2^9) \right) - \left(\sqrt{4^5 \sqrt{2 \times 8}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 6296278 &:= \left((6^2) + \left((9^{\sqrt{6^2}}) + (7^8) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$6298548 := \left(- (6) \times \left(2 - \left((\sqrt{9}^8) \times ((5 \times 4) \times 8) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6298584 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(\left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^8 \right) \times (-5) \right) / 8 \right) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$6298608 := \left(\left(6 + \left(2 \times \left((\sqrt{9}^8) \times 60 \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$6299584 := \left(\left(6 + \left(\left(2 + \left(\sqrt{9}^9 \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{8^4} \right)$$

$$6299840 := \left(\left(- \left((6 - 2) \right) - \left(\sqrt{9}^9 \right) \right) \times \left(- (8 \times 40) \right) \right)$$

$$6328374 := \left(6 \times \left(\left(3 - \left((2^8) \times (3 - 7) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$6328392 := \left(- (6) \times \left(- (3) - \left(\left(\left(2 \times (8^3) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)^2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6329421 := \left(\left(\left((63 - 2) \times 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 21 \right)$$

$$6329664 := \left(- \left(\left(\left((63^2) - (9^6) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$6352998 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(\left(- \left((3 - 52) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-9) \right) + 8 \right) \right)$$

$$6353034 := \left(\left(- (6) + \left(- \left((3 - (5 \times 30)) \right)^3 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$6376944 := \left(\left(\left(6 - \left(3^{7+6} \right) \right) + \sqrt{9^4} \right) \times (-4) \right)$$

$$6376986 := \left(\left(63 + \left((7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times 86 \right)$$

$$6377196 := \left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{-3+7} \right) \times \left(- \left((7+1) - (9^6) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6377244 := \left(\left(6 \times \left(\left(3^{7+7-2} \right) - 4 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$6377286 := \left(- (6) - \left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{7+7}^2} \right) \times (-8) \right) / 6 \right) \right)$$

$$6377294 := \left(\left(6 \times \left(\left(\left(3^{7+7} \right) \times 2 \right) / 9 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$6377316 := \left(\left(6 + \left(\left(3^{7+7} \right) / 3 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{16} \right)$$

$$6396975 := \left(\left((6 + 3) \times \sqrt{9^6} \right) \times 975 \right)$$

$$6434615 := - \left(\left(\left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{4} \right)^3 \right) - \left(\left((4 \times 6) - 1 \right)^5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6436295 := \left(\left(- (6) \times \sqrt{4^3} \right) + \left(- \left((6 - 29) \right)^5 \right) \right)$$

$$6436337 := \left(- (6) + \left(\left(-4 + \sqrt{3^6} \right)^{3+\sqrt{-3+7}} \right) \right)$$

$$6436343 := \left(\left(\left(- (6) + \sqrt{4} \right) + \sqrt{3^6} \right)^{-3+\sqrt{4^3}} \right)$$

$$6436349 := \left(6 + \left(\left(-4 + \sqrt{3^6} \right)^{\sqrt{34-9}} \right) \right)$$

$$6436355 := \left(\left(\sqrt{6^4} / 3 \right) + \left(\left((6 \times 3) + 5 \right)^5 \right) \right)$$

$$6439338 := \left(\left(- (6) + \left(\left(43^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 3 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{3^8} \right)$$

$$6439989 := \left(- (6) - \left(\left(\left(43^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 9 \right) - 8 \right) \times (-9) \right)$$

$$6453888 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 5 \right)^{-3+8} \right) \times \left(- (8 \times 8) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6455296 := \left(\left(\sqrt{64^5} \right) \times \left(5 + (2 \times 96) \right) \right)$$

$$6462597 := \left(\left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(6^{2+5} \right) \right) \right) + \left(9^7 \right) \right)$$

$$6464647 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\left(6/\sqrt{4} \right)^6 + 4} \right)^{6-\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 7 \right) \right)$$

$$6479994 := \left(- (6) + \left(\sqrt{4^7} \times \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9}) + 9 \right)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6485184 := \left(\left(6^4 \right) \times \left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{\left(5 \times 1 \right)^8} \right) + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$6495000 := \left(\left(- \left(6^4 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-5000)$$

$$6495384 := \left(- (6) - \left(- \left(495 \times 3^8 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$6495522 := \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^4} + \left((9^5) \times 5 \right)} \right) \times 22 \right)$$

$$6497792 := \left(\left(6 + \sqrt{4^9} \right) \times \left((7 \times (7 + 9))^2 \right) \right)$$

$$6499893 := \left(- (6) - \left(- (49) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (8 + 9) \right)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6499899 := \left(\left(\left(6^4 \right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-9) \right) \right) \times \left((8 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$6502494 := \left(- (6) + \left((50 \times (2 + 49))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$6510413 := \left(\left(- \left(6 - (5^{10}) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} + 1 \right) / 3$$

$$6510418 := \left(\left(- (6) \times \left(- \left(5^{10} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) / (1 + 8) \right)$$

$$6510419 := \left(\left(6 + \left(\left(5^{10} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + 1 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$6522916 := \left(\left(- (6) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\left(2 + 2 \right)^9} \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}}$$

$$6544962 := \left(\left(\left(\left(65 + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \sqrt{9^6} \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$6553594 := \left(- (6) - \left(- \left((5 \times 5) \right) \times \left((3 + 5)^{\sqrt{9 \times 4}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6560995 := \left(\left(\left(\left((6 \times 5) + 60 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 9 \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$6563844 := \left(\left(\left(\left((6^5) + 6 \right) / 3 \right) - (8 \times 4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$6563970 := \left(\left((6 \times ((5^6) + 3)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 70 \right)$$

$$6569994 := \left(- (6) + \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((69^{\sqrt{9}}) - 9 \right) \times (-4) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6578496 := \left((6^5) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{78}} - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (\sqrt{9} \times 6) \right) \right)$$

$$6584348 := \left(\left(\left((6 + ((5 \times 8) \times (4^3))) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 8 \right)$$

$$6587744 := \left(\left(\left((6 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{58}}) + \left(- \left((7^7) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times (-4) \right) \right)$$

$$6588378 := \left(- (6) + \left(\left(5 + \left((\sqrt{8+8} + 3)^7 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \right)$$

$$6588450 := \left((6 + 5)^{\sqrt{8+8}} \times 450 \right)$$

$$6591024 := \left(\left((65^{\sqrt{9}}) + 1 \right) \times 024 \right)$$

$$6594622 := \left(\left(\left(\left((6^5) / \sqrt{9} \right) - ((4 \times 6)) \right)^2 \right) - 2 \right)$$

$$6594624 := \left(\left(\left((6^5) / \sqrt{9} \right) - ((4 \times 6)) \right)^{-2+4} \right)$$

$$6595877 := \left(\left((6^5) - \sqrt{9^5} \right) + (8 \times (7^7)) \right)$$

$$6644672 := \left(\left(\sqrt{6^6} - (4 + (4 \times 6)) \right)^{\sqrt{7+2}} \right)$$

$$6644738 := \left(66 + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 47)^3 \right) \times 8 \right) \right)$$

$$6644794 := \left(- (6) - \left(- (64) \times \left((47^{\sqrt{9}}) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6676296 := \left((66 \times 76) \times \sqrt{(2+9)^6} \right)$$

$$6684671 := \left(\left((6 \times 68) \times \left(- \left((\sqrt{4} - 6) \right)^7 \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$6684674 := \left(\left((6 \times 68) \times \left(- \left((\sqrt{4} - 6) \right)^7 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$6684684 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- (68) \times (\sqrt{4}^{6+8}) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$6692569 := \left(\left(\left(\left((6^6) / 9 \right) / 2 \right) - 5 \right)^{6/\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$6697744 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{6^6 \times 9} - (7/7)) \times 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$6718359 := \left(\left(\left((6^7) \times 1 \right) \times 8 \right) - 35 \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$6718386 := \left(\left(- \left((6^7) \right) + \sqrt{1+8} \right) \times \left(- (3 \times 8) \right) \right) - 6$$

$$6718389 := \left(\left(- \left((6^7) \right) + \sqrt{1+8} \right) \times \left(- (3 \times 8) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$6718392 := \left(- \left((6^7) \right) + \sqrt{1+8} \right) \times \left(- ((3+9) \times 2) \right)$$

$$6718426 := \left(\left((6^{7+1}) - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4^2} \right) - 6$$

$$6718428 := \left(\left((6^{7+1}) - 8 \right) \times 4 \right) - \sqrt{2 \times 8}$$

$$6718434 := \left(\left(\left((6^7) - 1 \right) \times (8+4) \right) - 3 \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$6718438 := \left(\left(\left((6^7) - 1 \right) \times 8 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 3 - 8$$

$$6718439 := \left(- \left((6 - (7-1)^8) \right) \times 4 \right) - (3/\sqrt{9})$$

$$6718457 := \left(\left((6^7) \times 1 \right) \times 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4+5} - 7$$

$$6718458 := \left(\left((6^7) \times 1 \right) \times 8 \right) - \sqrt{4} \times \left(- (5-8) \right)$$

$$6718459 := \left((6^{7+\sqrt{1+8}}) - 45 \right) / 9$$

$$6718463 := \left(\left((6^{7+1}) \times 8 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) / (6/3)$$

$$6718474 := \left(\left((6^7) + 1 \right) \times (8+4) \right) - 7 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$6718477 := \left(6 + \left((7-1)^8 \times 4 \right) \right) + \sqrt{7 \times 7}$$

$$6718491 := \left((6 + (7-1)^8) \times 4 \right) + \sqrt{9 \times 1}$$

$$6718492 := \left(\left(\left((6^7) + 1 \right) \times 8 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{9} - 2$$

$$6718495 := \left(\left(\left((6^7) + 1 \right) \times 8 \right) + 4 \right) \times \sqrt{9} - 5$$

$$6718496 := (6^{7+1} + 8) \times \sqrt{-\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{9} \times 6}$$

$$6718499 := \left(\left((6^{7+1}) + 8 \right) \times 4 \right) + (9/\sqrt{9})$$

$$6718516 := \left((6^{7+1}) + (8+5) \right) \times \sqrt{16}$$

$$6718599 := \left(\left((6^7) \times 1 \right) \times 8 \right) + (5 \times 9) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$6718659 := \left(\left((6^7) \times 1 \right) \times 8 \right) + 65 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$6718816 := \left((6^{7+1}) + 88 \right) \times \sqrt{16}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6718893 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((6^7) + 18 \right) \times 8 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 3 \right) \\
 6718894 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((6^7) + 18 \right) \times 8 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 6718899 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((6^7) + 18 \right) \times 8 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 6718964 &:= \left(6^{7+1} + \sqrt{(8 - \sqrt{9})^6} \right) \times 4 \\
 6718976 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((6^7) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-8) \right) + \sqrt{(1+7)^6} \right) \\
 6719193 &:= \left(\left(\left((6^{7+1}) \times (\sqrt{9} + 1) \right) \right) + \left((9^3) \right) \right) \\
 6724296 &:= \left(\left((6^7) \times 24 \right) + \sqrt{(2 \times 9)^6} \right) \\
 6743256 &:= \left(6 - \left(- (74) \times \sqrt{(3^2 \times 5)^6} \right) \right) \\
 6744577 &:= \left(\left(\left((6^7) / \sqrt{4} \right) + \left((\sqrt{4} + 5)^7 \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 6744684 &:= \left(\left(6 - \left(\left((7 + \sqrt{4})^4 \right) + (6^8) \right) \right) \times (-4) \right) \\
 6749256 &:= \left(\left(\left((6 \times 7) - 4 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(- (2) + \sqrt{5^6} \right) \right) \\
 6749568 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- (7) - \sqrt{4} \right) + \left((9 \times (5^6)) \right) \right) \times (-8) \right) \\
 6749604 &:= \left(\left(\left((6^{7-\sqrt{4}}) / \sqrt{9} \right) + 6 \right)^{\sqrt{04}} \right) \\
 6749984 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(- (6) \times \left(- ((7 \times 4)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 6749994 &:= \left(- (6) + \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{7^4 \times 9} + \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 6751263 &:= \left(- (6) + \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{(5 \times 1 - 2)^6} \right)^3 \right) \right) \\
 6751269 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((6 + 7) \times 5 \right) \times (1 + 2) \right) - 6 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 6764154 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(- \left((7 \times \left(((6 + 4) + 1)^5 \right)) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 6765119 &:= \left(- ((6 + 76)) + (51^{1+\sqrt{9}}) \right) \\
 6765128 &:= \left(- ((67 + 6)) + (51^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}}) \right) \\
 6768992 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(6 \times 7)^6} - (8^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times 92 \right) \\
 6777491 &:= \left(\left(- (6) \times \left((7^7) - \left((7 - \sqrt{4})^9 \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 6777492 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left((7^7) - \left((7 - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9^2}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 6777494 &:= \left(\left(- (6) \times \left((7^7) - \left((7 - \sqrt{4})^9 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 6777534 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left((7^7) - 7 \right) - (5^{\sqrt{3^4}}) \right) \right) \\
 6782976 &:= \left(\left((6 + (7 \times 9)) \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^7} \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 6785472 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left((\sqrt{7^8} - 5) \times (-472) \right) \right) \\
 6792099 &:= \left(6 + \left(7 \times \left((9 + 2) \times 09^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 6792699 &:= \left(- (6) - \left(\left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) + 2 \right) \times \left(- (6) - \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 6797875 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{6^{7+\sqrt{9}}} - 7 \right) \times 875 \right) \\
 6815448 &:= \left(681 \times \left(\left((5 \times \sqrt{4})^4 \right) + 8 \right) \right) \\
 6822544 &:= \left(\left(\left((6^{8/2}) \times 2 \right) + (5 \times 4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 6826464 &:= \left(\left((6^8) + \sqrt{(26 + 4)^6} \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 6835927 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} - \left((3 + (5^9)) \right) \right) \right) / (-2) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 6842880 &:= \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times ((4 + 2) \times 880) \right) \\
 6843448 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{6^8} + (4 \times 3)) \times \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 8 \right) \\
 6843464 &:= \left(\left(- \left((6^8) \right) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((3 + \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) \right) \times (-4) \right) \\
 6847995 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((6 + \sqrt{8^4}) + 7 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 6849544 &:= \left(\left((6^8) + \left(\left((\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}})^5 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 6849766 &:= \left((6 + (8^{-4+9})) \times \left(- (7) + \sqrt{6^6} \right) \right) \\
 6854640 &:= \left(\left(- (6) \times \sqrt{(8 + 5)^{\sqrt{4+6}}} \right) \times (-40) \right) \\
 6856205 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{6^8} - \sqrt{5^6})^2 \right) \times 05 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$6858959 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} - (-5) - (-8) \times (95^{v^9}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6865488 := \left(686 \times \left(\sqrt{(5 \times \sqrt{4})^8} + 8 \right) \right)$$

$$6874884 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{6^8} + 7) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + ((8+8)) \right)^{v^4} \right)$$

$$6881280 := \left((-6) \times \sqrt{8^8} \right) \times (-1 \times 280)$$

$$6889964 := \left(\left((6^8) + \sqrt{(8+9 \times \sqrt{9})^6} \right) \times 4 \right)$$

$$6899897 := \left(\left(\left(-((6 - (8 \times 9)))^{v^9} \right) \times 8 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 7$$

$$6916252 := \left(\left(\left(-6 + \sqrt{(9+1)^6} \right)^2 \right) \times (5+2) \right)$$

$$6927424 := \left(\left((6 \times 9) + 2 \right) \times (\sqrt{7^4} - 2) \right)^{v^4}$$

$$6928438 := \left(\left(\left((6^9/2) / 8 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (3+8) \right)$$

$$6928944 := \left((6 \times (9+2)) \times \left(8 + \left((9 \times \sqrt{4})^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6943725 := \left(\left((6^{9-\sqrt{4}}) - (3^7) \right) \times 25 \right)$$

$$6945762 := \left(\left(6 + \sqrt{9^4 \times (5 \times 7)^6} \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$6945798 := \left(6 \times \left(\left((-9) + (\sqrt{4} \times 57) \right)^{v^9} + 8 \right) \right)$$

$$6946816 := \left(\left(\left((6^{v^9}) + \sqrt{4} \right) - 6 \right) \times (8^{-1+6}) \right)$$

$$6965994 := \left((6^9 - 6) - \left((5 \times 9) - \sqrt{9} \right)^4 \right)$$

$$6968448 := \left((6 + \sqrt{9}) \times \left(\left((6^8) / \sqrt{4} \right) - (4^8) \right) \right)$$

$$6979584 := \left(-((6-9)) + (7 \times \sqrt{9^5}) \right) \times (8^4)$$

$$6984576 := \left(-\left((6 \times 9) - (8^4) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{(5+7)^6}$$

$$6985449 := \left(\left(\left(\left((6/\sqrt{9})^8 \right) + ((5^4)) \right) \right)^{v^4} \right) \times 9$$

$$6993848 := \left(6 + (\sqrt{9} - 938)^{v^4} \right) \times 8$$

$$6994749 := \left(-6 + \left((9^{v^9}) \times \left((4 \times (7^4)) - 9 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6997350 := \left(\left((6^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 7 \right) \times (3 \times 50) \right)$$

$$6998367 := \left(6^9 + \left((\sqrt{9} + 8) \times \left(-3 + (6^7) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6998400 := \left(\left((6^{v^9}) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 400 \right)$$

$$6998454 := \left(-6 \times \left(-9 - \left((\sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 45))^{v^4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6998467 := \left(\left(\left((6^{v^9}) + \sqrt{9} \right) - \left((8 + \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) \times (-7) \right)$$

$$7068627 := \left((\sqrt{7^{06}} - (8^6)) \times (-27) \right)$$

$$7082950 := \left(\sqrt{7^{08}} \times 2950 \right)$$

$$7087484 := \left(\left((70 \times (8+7)^4) - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$7087494 := \left(\left((70 \times (8+7)^4) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$7092899 := \left(\left((70 + \sqrt{9})^2 \right) \times \left((8 + \sqrt{9})^{v^9} \right) \right)$$

$$7137144 := \left(-((7 \times (1-3))) \times (714^{v^4}) \right)$$

$$7139584 := \left(\left((7 \times 13) + \sqrt{9^5} \right) \times 8 \right)^{v^4}$$

$$7144929 := \left(\sqrt{(7 \times 1 + 4)^4} \times (9^{2+v^9}) \right)$$

$$7158220 := \left((71^{\sqrt{5+8/2}}) \times 20 \right)$$

$$7168035 := \left(-7 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}} \times \left(-(80^3) \right) \right) - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$7169729 := \left((7 \times 16)^{v^9} + (7^{2v^9}) \right)$$

$$7176461 := \left(-((7-1)) + \left(-((7^6) + \sqrt{4}) \times (-61) \right) \right)$$

$$7186259 := \left(\left(\left((7^{\sqrt{1+8}}) + 6 \right)^2 \right) \times 59 \right)$$

$$7212884 := \left(721 \times \left(\sqrt{(2+8)^8} + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$7216489 := \left(721 \times \left(\sqrt{(6+4)^8} + 9 \right) \right)$$

$$7225342 := \left(\left((7 \times ((2^{2+5}) \times 3))^{v^4} \right) - 2 \right)$$

$$7225344 := \left((\sqrt{7^2} \times ((2^5) \times 3) \times 4) \right)^{v^4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7225848 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(\left(\left(2+2\right)^5 - 8\right)^{\sqrt{4}} + 8\right)\right)\right) \\
 7226597 &:= \left(-7\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{22^6} - 5\right) \times (-97)\right) \\
 7229992 &:= \left(-7\right) \times \left(\left(22^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times (-99 - 2)\right) \\
 7231665 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{7+2} - \left(31 \times \left(6^6\right)\right)\right) \times (-5)\right) \\
 7239213 &:= \left(\sqrt{7+2} \times \left(3 \times \left(\left(92+1\right)^3\right)\right)\right) \\
 7247295 &:= \left(\left(\left(7 + \sqrt{2^4}\right)^{7-2}\right) \times (9 \times 5)\right) \\
 7253974 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(7 \times 2\right)^5\right) - \left(3^9\right)\right) \times 7\right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 7263025 &:= \left(\sqrt{7^{2+6}} \times 3025\right) \\
 7263392 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\left(7+2\right)^6} + 3\right) / 3\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) / 2\right) \\
 7267392 &:= \left(\left(\left(7 \times 2\right)^6\right) - \left(\sqrt{7-3^{9 \times 2}}\right)\right) \\
 7267394 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(7 \times 2\right)^6\right) - \left(7-3\right)^9\right) + \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 7268800 &:= \left(-7\right) \times \left(\left(-2 - \sqrt{6^8}\right) \times 800\right) \\
 7274496 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{7+2} \times 74\right) \times \sqrt{4^{9+6}}\right) \\
 7282688 &:= \left(-7\right) \times \left(\left(\left(2^8\right) - \sqrt{-2+6}\right) \times \left(-\sqrt{8^8}\right)\right) \\
 7290045 &:= \left(7+2\right) \times \left(\left(900^{\sqrt{4}}\right) + 5\right) \\
 7294032 &:= \left(72 \times \left(\left(-\left(\left(\sqrt{9}-40\right)\right)^3\right) \times 2\right)\right) \\
 7294238 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(7^2\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \times (23+8)\right) \\
 7294331 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(7^2\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) + 3\right) \times 31\right) \\
 7294973 &:= \left(\left(7^2\right) \times \left(-\left(\left(\sqrt{9}-\left(49+7\right)\right)\right)^3\right)\right) \\
 7297934 &:= 7 \times 2 \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + \left(7-9^3\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 7298795 &:= \left(-\left(\left(7^2\right)\right) \times \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8\right) + 7\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times (-5)\right)\right) \\
 7299975 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(7^2\right) - \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \sqrt{9}\right) \times 75\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7311616 &:= \left(\left(7 - \left(3 \times \left(1 - 16\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{16}}\right) \\
 7344949 &:= -\left(\left(\left(\left(\left(7^3\right) + 4\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(4^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 7357448 &:= \left(7 \times \left(3 - 5 \times 7 \times 4\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 8 \\
 7359744 &:= \left(\left(7 \times 3\right) \times \left(\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{9}\right) \times 74\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right) \\
 7361466 &:= \left(\left(73 \times \sqrt{\left(6+1\right)^{4+6}}\right) \times 6\right) \\
 7375879 &:= \left(7 + \left(\left(37+5\right) \times \left(\left(8 \times 7\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right)\right) \\
 7388168 &:= \left(\left(\left(7 + \left(3 \times 8\right)\right)^{8-\sqrt{16}}\right) \times 8\right) \\
 7391323 &:= \left(\left(73^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times \left(\left(1+3\right)^2 + 3\right)\right) \\
 7391342 &:= \left(\left(\left(73^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + 1\right) \times \left(3 + \left(4^2\right)\right)\right) \\
 7397536 &:= \left(73 + \sqrt{9}\right) \times \sqrt{\left(7-53\right)^6} \\
 7411874 &:= \left(\left(\left(7 + \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(-1 + \left(-\left(1-8\right)^7\right)\right)\right) - 4\right) \\
 7411878 &:= \left(\left(7 + \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(-1 + \left(-\left(1-8\right)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}}\right)\right)\right) \\
 7411879 &:= \left(\left(\left(-7 - \sqrt{4}\right) + 1\right) + \left(\left(-\left(1-8\right)^7\right) \times 9\right)\right) \\
 7411959 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(7^{-4+11}\right) + \sqrt{9}\right) + 5\right) \times 9\right) \\
 7411977 &:= \left(\left(7 + \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(\left(1 \times 1\right) + 9\right) + \left(7^7\right)\right) \\
 7412769 &:= \left(-7\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(12 + \left(7^6\right)\right)\right)\right) \times (-9)\right) \\
 7414949 &:= \left(74 + \left(-\left(1 - \left(49 \times 4\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \\
 7425920 &:= \left(\left(-\left(\left(\left(7+4\right) + 2\right)^5\right) - \sqrt{9}\right) \times (-20)\right) \\
 7429996 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(2 - \left(\left(9^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \left(9^6\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 7437976 &:= \left(-\left(\left(\left(7^4\right) + 3\right)\right) \times \left(-7 - \left(9 \times \sqrt{7^6}\right)\right)\right) \\
 7439572 &:= \left(-7\right) \times \left(\left(43 - \left(\sqrt{9}^{5+7}\right)\right) \times 2\right) \\
 7439677 &:= \left(-7\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-\left(3 + \left(9^6\right)\right)\right)\right) + 77\right) \\
 7439684 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(-\left(\left(3 - \left(9^6\right)\right) + \left(8 \times 4\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 7439796 &:= \left(\left(7 + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(3^9\right)\right) \times (-7)\right)\right) \times \left(9 \times 6\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7439838 &:= \left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{4}) \times 3 \right) \times \left((\sqrt{9^{8+3}}) - 8 \right) \right) \\
 7439964 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 3) + (9 - (9^6)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 7439992 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left((-4 + ((3^{9+\sqrt{9}}) - 9)) \times (-2) \right) \right) \\
 7440727 &:= \left(7 + 4^{-\sqrt{4+07}} \right)^2 \times 7 \\
 7441984 &:= ((7 \times 4 - 41 \times 9) \times 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 7443100 &:= \left(\sqrt{74+4} \times 3100 \right) \\
 7443419 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{74} + (- (4) \times ((3 \times 41)^{\sqrt{9}})) \right) \right) \\
 7443850 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{74} + 4)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{38}}} \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 7444417 &:= \left((7^{4+4}) + \left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^{1+7} \right) \right) \\
 7463824 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 - ((3 \times 8) / 2)} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 7464953 &:= \left(- (7) + \left((4 + 6) \times \left(\left((4 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 7464955 &:= \left(\left(\left((7 - \sqrt{4}) \times 6 \right) \times \left((4 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \right) \right) - 5 \right) \\
 7464960 &:= \left((7 + \sqrt{4}) \times \left(\left((6 \times 4)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 60 \right) \right) \\
 7464995 &:= \left(\left(7 + \left(4 \times \left((\sqrt{64} \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 7465230 &:= \left(\left(7 + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 6)^5 \right) + 2 \right) \right) \times 30 \right) \\
 7465536 &:= \left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) - \sqrt{(5 \times (5 + 3))^6} \right) \\
 7468559 &:= - \left(\left(\left((7 + \sqrt{4})^6 \right) - \left((8 \times 5) \times 5^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 7477423 &:= (7 + \sqrt{4}) \times 7^7 + 4^{2^3} \\
 7489365 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(7 \times \sqrt{4})^8 - 9} \right) \times (3 \times 65) \right) \\
 7494939 &:= \left(\left((7 + \sqrt{4}) \times (94^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) + (3^9) \right) \\
 7495579 &:= \left(- \left((7^4) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left((5^5) \right) \right) \right) - (7^{\sqrt{9}})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7495916 &:= \left(- \left((7^4) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{5^{9+1}} \right) \right) - 6 \\
 7495919 &:= \left(- \left((7^4) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{5^{9+1}} \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 7495921 &:= \left(- \left((7^4) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - (5^{\sqrt{9}+2}) \right) \right) - 1 \\
 7495922 &:= \left(- \left((7^4) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left((5^{9-2-2}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 7495924 &:= \left(- \left((7^4) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - (5^{\sqrt{9}+2}) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \\
 7496637 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 6 \right)^{6/3} \right) - 7 \right) \\
 7496642 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 6 \right)^{6-4} \right) - 2 \right) \\
 7512729 &:= \left(- \left((7^5) \right) + \left(\left((1 \times 2) \times 7 \right)^2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 7516890 &:= \left(\sqrt{(7 + 5 - 1 + 6)^8 \times 90} \right) \\
 7518564 &:= \left((7 + ((5 \times 18) \times 5)) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 7529468 &:= \left(\left((7 + 5) + 2 \right)^{\sqrt{9 \times 4}} - 68 \right) \\
 7529476 &:= \left(\left((7 + 5) \times (-2 - \sqrt{9}) \right) + \left((\sqrt{4} \times 7)^6 \right) \right) \\
 7529522 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{5^2} + 9)^5 \right) \times (-2) \right) + 2 \right) \right) \\
 7529524 &:= \left(- (7) - \sqrt{5^2} + \left((9 + 5)^{2+4} \right) \right) \\
 7529526 &:= -7 - 5 + 2 + \sqrt{(9 + 5)^{2 \times 6}} \\
 7529529 &:= \left(- (7) + \left((\sqrt{5^2} + 9)^{-5+2+9} \right) \right) \\
 7529534 &:= \left(\left((7 + 5) + 2 \right) \times (9 + 5) \right)^3 - \sqrt{4} \\
 7529539 &:= \left(\left((7 + 5) + 2 \right) \times (9 + 5) \right)^3 + \sqrt{9} \\
 7529543 &:= \left(7 + \left((\sqrt{5^2} + 9)^{5+4-3} \right) \right) \\
 7529544 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left((\sqrt{5^2} + 9)^5 \right) \right) + 4 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 7529546 &:= -7 - 5 + 2 + \sqrt{(9 + 5)^{2 \times 6}} \\
 7529548 &:= \left(\sqrt{(7 + 5)^2} + \left((9 + 5)^{-\sqrt{4}+8} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$7529571 := \left(\sqrt{(7 \times 5)^2} + (9 + 5)^{7-1} \right)$$

$$7529596 := \left((7 + 5) \times (2 + \sqrt{9}) + (5 + 9)^6 \right)$$

$$7529746 := \left((((7 \times 5) \times 2) \times \sqrt{9}) + \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right)$$

$$7529984 := \left(\left(7 + \left((52 - \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{8^4} \right)$$

$$7539846 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times 53) \times \sqrt{9} + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$7548995 := \left(\left(- \left((7^5) \right) + \left(- (4) \times \left((8 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$7551504 := (7 - 551 \times 5)^{\sqrt{04}}$$

$$7556994 := \left(- (7) + \left(\left(5 + \left((5 + 6) + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$7558299 := \left(\left(\left((7 - (5/5))^8 \right) / 2 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$7559995 := \left(\left((7 \times 5) \times \left(- (5) \times \left(- (9) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$7563375 := \left(\left(- \left((7^5) \times 6 \right) - \sqrt{3 \times 3} \right) \times (-75) \right)$$

$$7564950 := \left(\left(\left((7^5) + 6 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 \times 50) \right)$$

$$7568533 := \left(- (7) \times \left(\sqrt{5^6} - \left((8^5) \times 33 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7573785 := \left(757 \times \left(\sqrt{(3 + 7)^8} + 5 \right) \right)$$

$$7577955 := 7 \times \sqrt{(-5 + 7 + 7)^9} \times 55$$

$$7577997 := \left(7 - \left(- (5) \times \left((77 \times \sqrt{9^9}) + 7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7578797 := \left(- (7) - \left(\left(\left(5\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} \right) + 7 \right) \times (-97) \right) \right)$$

$$7579957 := \left((7^5) \times \left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) + ((9 \times (5 + 7))) \right) \right)$$

$$7589376 := \left(\sqrt{(7 + 5)^8} \times \left((9 + (3^7)) / 6 \right) \right)$$

$$7593192 := \left(\left((75^{\sqrt{9}}) - (31) \right) \times (9 \times 2) \right)$$

$$7593675 := \left(\left((75^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (3 \times 6) \right) - 75 \right)$$

$$7593693 := \left(\left(\left(\left((75^{\sqrt{9}}) - 3 \right) \times 6 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$7593694 := \left(\left(\left(\left((75^{\sqrt{9}}) - 3 \right) \times 6 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$7593696 := \left(\left((75^{\sqrt{9}}) - 3 \right) \times (6 \times (9 - 6)) \right)$$

$$7593699 := \left(\left(\left(\left((75^{\sqrt{9}}) - 3 \right) \times 6 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$7593792 := \left(\left(\left(\left((75^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-3) \right) - 7 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-2) \right)$$

$$7593846 := \left(\left(\left((75^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-3) \right) - (8 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \times (-6) \right)$$

$$7593894 := \left(\left(\left((75^{9/3}) + 8 \right) \times 9 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$7594275 := \left(\left(7 + \left(\left((5 \times \sqrt{9})^4 \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \times 75 \right)$$

$$7628644 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{7^6} + 2) \times 8 \right) + (6 - 4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$7638462 := \left(\left(\left((7^{6-3}) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 62 \right)$$

$$7644743 := \left(- \left((7^6) \right) + \left((\sqrt{4} + (4 \times \sqrt{7^4}))^3 \right) \right)$$

$$7646969 := \left(- \left(\left((7^6) \times (4 - 69) \right) \right) - (6^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$7647055 := \left(\left(- \left((7^6) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(- (70) + \sqrt{5 \times 5} \right) \right)$$

$$7649265 := \left(\left(- \left((7^6) \right) - \left((4^{\sqrt{9}}) / 2 \right) \right) \times (-65) \right)$$

$$7664752 := \left(76 \times \left(\left(6 \times (\sqrt{4} + (7^5)) \right) - 2 \right) \right)$$

$$7666728 := \left(- \left((76 \times 6) \right) \times \left(- (6) - \sqrt{7^{2+8}} \right) \right)$$

$$7673463 := \left(- (7) \times \left(\left(\left(6 + (7^3) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \left(- (6 + 3) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7683984 := \left((7 \times ((6 - 8) + 398))^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$7743225 := \left(\sqrt{(7 \times 7)^4} \times 3225 \right)$$

$$7746354 := \left((77 \times 46) \times (3^{5+\sqrt{4}}) \right)$$

$$7762399 := \left(7 + \left(\left((7 + 62) \times 3 \right) - 9 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$7764786 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{7 \times 7^6}) \times (4 + 7) \right) - 8 \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$7764792 := \left(\left(\left(7 - \left((7^6) \times (4 + 7) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-2) \right)$$

$$7764834 := \left((\sqrt{7 \times 7^6}) \times ((4 \times 8) + 34) \right)$$

$$7764841 := \left(7 - \left(\left(- \left((7^6) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times ((8 \times 4) + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$7764911 := \left((-7) + \left(- \left((7^6) \right) \times \sqrt{4 \times 9} \right) \right) \times (-11)$$

$$7764933 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{7 \times 7^6} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 33 \right)$$

$$7764973 := \left(7 + \left(\left(- \left((7^6) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(- \left((9 \times 7) + 3 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7765296 := \left(\left(7 + (7^6) \right) \times \left(\left(5 + (2 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \times 6 \right) \right)$$

$$7772944 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times 7) + (72 \times 9) \right) \times 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$7779485 := \left(\left(- \left((7 \times 7) \right) - \left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{9})^4 \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$7794688 := \left(\left(7 + \left((79 \times 4) \times 6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{8^8} \right)$$

$$7795264 := \left((77 \times 9 + 5) \times (2 - 6) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$7798784 := \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{(7+9)^8} \right) \times \left((7+8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$7803250 := \left(\sqrt{7^8} \times 03250 \right)$$

$$7814686 := \left(781 \times \left(\sqrt{(4+6)^8} + 6 \right) \right)$$

$$7836694 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times 8) \times 3 \right) \times \left((6^6) - 9 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$7836696 := \left(\left((7 \times 8) \times 3 \right) \times \left(\left((6^6) - \sqrt{9} \right) - 6 \right) \right)$$

$$7836699 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times 8) \times 3 \right) \times \left((6^6) - 9 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$7836864 := \left(\sqrt{7^8} \times \left((3 + (6 \times 8)) \times 64 \right) \right)$$

$$7839737 := \left(- (7) + \left(\left((8^3) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((7 \times (3^7)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7840245 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} \times \left(\left((40/2)^4 \right) + 5 \right) \right)$$

$$7861947 := \left(\left((7^8) - 6 \right) + \left(\left(- (1) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 4 \right)^7 \right)$$

$$7862416 := \left(\left(\left((78 \times (6^2)) - 4 \right)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}} \right) \right)$$

$$7864230 := \left(\left(\left(7 - (8^6) \right) - \sqrt{4^2} \right) \times (-30) \right)$$

$$7864253 := \left(- (7) + \left(\left(- \left((8^6) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(- \left((2 \times 5) \times 3 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7864295 := \left(\left(7 + \left(\left(- \left((8^6) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-2) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$7864299 := \left(\left(- (7) - \left((8^6) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} / (-2) \right) - 9 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$7864310 := \left(\left(7 - \left(\left((8^6) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \times (-10) \right)$$

$$7864334 := \left(\left(7 + \left((8^6) \times \left((4 \times 3) + 3 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$7864345 := \left(\left(- (7) - \left(\left(- \left((8^6) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-3) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$7864361 := \left(\left(\left(7 + \left((8^6) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 3 \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$7864362 := \left(\left(7 + \left((8^6) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 3 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{6^2} \right)$$

$$7864364 := \left(\left(\left(7 + \left((8^6) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 3 \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$7864373 := \left(- (7) - \left(\left((8^6) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(- \left((3+7) \times 3 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7864385 := \left(\left(\left(- (7) + \left(- \left((8^6) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times (-3) - 8 \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$7864395 := \left(\left((7+8) - \left(- (6) \times \left((4^3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$7864447 := \left(7 - \left(- \left(\left((8^6) + 4 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((4 \times 7) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7864465 := \left(\left(- (7) + \left(\left(\left((8^6) + 4 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$7864525 := \left(\left(\left(7 + (8^6) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4^5} - 2 \right) \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$7864565 := \left(\left(7 - \left(\left(\left((8^6) + \sqrt{4} \right) + 5 \right) \times (-6) \right) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$7864566 := \left(\left(\left(\left(- (7) - \left(\sqrt{8^6 \sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times (-5) \right) + 6 \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$7864830 := \left(\left(\left(\left(7 + (8^6) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) + 8 \right) \times 30 \right)$$

$$7875392 := \left(- \left((7 \times 8) \right) \times \left(- (7) - \left(\left((5^3) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7879242 := \left(- (7) + \left(\left(\left(\left((8 \times 7) - \sqrt{9} \right)^2 - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7880599 := \left(\left(7 + \left((8 \times 8) \times \sqrt{0 \times 5 + 9} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$7884864 := \left(\sqrt{788 \times 4 / 8} \times (6^4) \right)$$

$$7885955 := \left(- (7) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{8^8} \times (-5) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 55 \right) \right)$$

$$7889475 := \left(\left(\sqrt{7^8} + 8 \right) \times \left(- \left((9 - (4^7)) / 5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7890463 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times 8) - \sqrt{9} \right)^{04} \right) - \left((6 \times 3) \right) \right)$$

$$7890472 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times 8) - \sqrt{9} \right)^{04} \right) - (7 + 2) \right)$$

$$7890474 := \left(- (7) + \left(\left(8 + \left(9 \times \left((0 - \sqrt{4}) + 7 \right) \right) \right)^4 \right) \right)$$

$$7890479 := \left(\left((7 \times 8) - \sqrt{9} \right)^{04} + ((7 - 9)) \right)$$

$$7890481 := (7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9})^{-04+8 \times 1}$$

$$7890488 := \left(7 + \left(\left(8 + \left(90/\sqrt{4} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{8+8}} \right) \right)$$

$$7890534 := \left(\left((7 \times 8) - \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(0 - (53^4) \right) \right)$$

$$7896470 := \left(\left((7^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - 6 \right) \times 470 \right)$$

$$7899322 := \left((7^8) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left((9^3) \times 2 \right) \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$7907344 := \left(\left((7 \times 90) + 73 \right) \times 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$7928697 := \left(\left(\left((7 + \sqrt{9}) + 2 \right) \times (8^6) \right) + \left((9^7) \right) \right)$$

$$7929848 := \left(\left(\left((7 + 9)^2 \right) \times (\sqrt{9} + 8) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 8 \right)$$

$$7941124 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(7+9)^4} \times 11 \right) + 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$7944335 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times 9) - 4 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)^3 \right) \times 35$$

$$7958041 := \left(7 \times (\sqrt{9} + (5 \times 80)) \right)^{\sqrt{4 \times 1}}$$

$$7962245 := - \left(\left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) + \left((6^2) - (24^5) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7962435 := \left(\left(- (7) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{96}} \right) + \left((2 \times 4) \times 3^5 \right) \right)$$

$$7962498 := \left(\left(- (7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \right) + (24^{-\sqrt{9}+8})$$

$$7962584 := \left(\left(- (7) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((6 \times 2)^5 \times 8 \right) \right) \times 4$$

$$7962599 := \left(- (7) + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times (6+2))^5 \right) - ((9+9)) \right) \right)$$

$$7962614 := \left(\left(- (7) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(((6-2) \times 6)^{1+4} \right) \right)$$

$$7962622 := \left(\left((\sqrt{7+9} \times 6)^{2+6/2} \right) - 2 \right)$$

$$7962631 := \left(7 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times (6+2))^{\sqrt{-6+31}} \right) \right)$$

$$7962634 := \left((7 + \sqrt{9}) + \left(((6-2) \times 6)^{3+\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$7962635 := \left(- (7) - \left((\sqrt{9} \times (-6)) - \left(((2+6) \times 3^5) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7962985 := \left(\left((7 - \sqrt{96}) / (-2) \right) + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 8)^5 \right) \right)$$

$$7964880 := \left(- (7) \times \left((\sqrt{9} - (6^4)) \times 880 \right) \right)$$

$$7967935 := \left(\left(- (7) + \left((\sqrt{9}^{6+7}) - \left((9^3) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$7969795 := \left(\left(\left(- \left((7 - (9^6)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$7971555 := \left(\left(7 - \left((\sqrt{9}^{7+1+5}) - 5 \right) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$7971592 := \left(\left(- \left((7 - \left((9^{7-1}) \times 5 \right)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 2 \right)$$

$$7971594 := \left(- \left((7 - \left((9^{7-1}) \times 5 \right)) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9 \times 4}} \right)$$

$$7971595 := \left(\left((7 - \left((9^7) \times 1 \right) - 5 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$7971619 := \left((7 + \left((9^7) + 1 \right) \times (6-1)) \right) / \sqrt{9}$$

$$7971695 := \left((7 + \left((\sqrt{9}^{7 \times 1+6}) + 9 \right)) \times 5 \right)$$

$$7988455 := \left(\left((79 \times (8+8))^{\sqrt{4}} - 5 \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$7988480 := \left(\left((79 \times \sqrt{8+8})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 80 \right)$$

$$7988495 := \left(\left((79 \times (8+8))^{\sqrt{4}} + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$7996868 := \left(\left((7^{\sqrt{9}} - (6 \times 8)) \right) \times 68 \right)$$

$$7999327 := \left(\left(\left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((9^3) \right) \right)^2 \right) \times 7$$

$$7999368 := \left(\left(79 - \left((9 + (\sqrt{9}/3))^6 \right) \right) \times (-8) \right)$$

$$7999488 := \left(- ((7 \times 9)) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times (-9)) - 4 \right) \times \sqrt{8^8} \right) \right)$$

$$7999928 := \left(\left(\left((7 + \sqrt{9})^{9-\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{9^2} \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$7999968 := \left((\sqrt{7+9} - ((9/9) + 9)^6) \right) \times (-8)$$

$$7999976 := \left(- ((7 + (9/9))) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left((\sqrt{9} + 7)^6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7999995 := \left(\left(\left(- (7) + \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 9 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$8054244 := \left(\left(- \left((80 - (54^2)) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$8064564 := \left((\sqrt{8^{06}} + 4) \times \left((5^6) + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$8067595 := \left(\left(80 \times \left((6 \times (7^5)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$8116488 := \left(811 \times \left(\sqrt{(6+4)^8} + 8 \right) \right)$$

$$8120593 := \left(- (8) + \left(\left(- ((1-205)) - \sqrt{9} \right)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$8128448 := \left(8 \times \left(\left((12 \times 84)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 8 \right) \right)$$

$$8179927 := \left(\left(\left(\left(81 + \left((7 + \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)^2 \right) \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$8191984 := \left(\left(\left((8 \times (19+1))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$8191994 := \left(\left(\left((8 \times (19+1))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$8192000 := \left((8^{1+\sqrt{9}}) \times 2000 \right)$$

$$8217389 := \left(821 \times \left(\sqrt{(7+3)^8} + 9 \right) \right)$$

$$8248384 := \left(\left(\left((8^2) \times (48-3) \right) - 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$8249922 := \left(\left(\left(- (8) + \left((2^{\sqrt{4}+9}) - 9 \right) \right)^2 \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$8257464 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}} \times 7 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{6^4} \right)$$

$$8258048 := \left(\left(\left(\left((8/2)^5 \right) - 8 \right)^{\sqrt{04}} \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$8281845 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(8-2)^8} - (1+8) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$8294325 := \left(\sqrt{(8^2 \times 9)^4} - 3 \right) \times 25$$

$$8294392 := \left(- (8) + \left(\left((2 + \sqrt{9}) \times \left((4^3) \times 9 \right) \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$8294400 := \left(\sqrt{(8 \times 2 \times 9)^4} \times 400 \right)$$

$$8294525 := \left(\sqrt{(8^2 \times 9)^4} + 5 \right) \times 25$$

$$8299685 := \left(\left(\left(- ((8/2)) + \sqrt{9^9} \right) - (6^8) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$8311681 := \left(- (8) - \left((31^{\sqrt{16}}) \times (- (8+1)) \right) \right)$$

$$8311689 := \left(\left(8 + \left((31^{\sqrt{16}}) - 8 \right) \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$8317448 := \left(\left(\left(\left((8 - (3^{-1+7})) \times (-4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 8 \right) \right)$$

$$8353249 := \left(\left((8 \times 3)^5 \right) + \left((3+2)^{\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}}} \right) \right)$$

$$8363664 := \left(\left(\left(\left((8^3) + 6 \right) - 36 \right) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$8365378 := \left(\left((8 + (3 \times 65))^3 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} \right)$$

$$8365427 := \left((8 + (3 \times 65))^{\sqrt{4^2-7}} \right)$$

$$8367894 := \left((83 \times 6) \times \left((7^{8-\sqrt{9}}) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$8372224 := \left((8^{-3+7}) \times (\sqrt{2^{22}} - 4) \right)$$

$$8379872 := \left(8 \times \left(\left(- \left((3^7) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) + (8^7) \right) / 2 \right)$$

$$8384488 := \left(- \left((8 \times (3 - ((8 \times 4)^4))) \right) - \sqrt{8^8} \right)$$

$$8384528 := \left(\left(- \left((8^3) \right) + \left(\left((8 \times \sqrt{4})^5 \right) + 2 \right) \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$8386464 := \left(8 \times \left(\left((3 - (8^6)) + \sqrt{4^6} \right) \times (-4) \right) \right)$$

$$8387328 := \left(\left(- ((8-3)) + \sqrt{8^{7+3}} \right) \times (2^8) \right)$$

$$8387955 := \left(\left(- (8) \times \left(\sqrt{3^8} - ((7+9)^5) \right) \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$8388096 := \left(- \left((8^3) \right) + \left(\left(- \left((8^8) \right) \times \sqrt{09} \right) / (-6) \right) \right)$$

$$8388284 := \left(\left(\left(- (8) \times \sqrt{3^8} \right) + \left(\sqrt{8^{2^8}} \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$8388352 := \left(- \left(\left((8^3) - (8^8) \right) \right) / \sqrt{(3+5)/2} \right)$$

$$8388354 := \left(\left(\left((8^3) - (8^8) \right) / (3-5) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$8388416 := \left(8 \times \left(- ((3 \times 8)) + \left((8 \times 4)^{\sqrt{16}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$8388441 := \left(\left(- \left((83 - ((8^8) / 4)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} - 1 \right)$$

$$8388444 := \left(\left(- \left((83 - ((8^8) / 4)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$8388448 := \left(\left((8-3) - (8^{8-\sqrt{4}}) \right) \times (- (4 \times 8)) \right)$$

$$8388459 := \left(\left(- ((8 \times 3)) - \left(- \left((8^8) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - (5^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$8388485 := \left(- (83) + \left(\left((8^8) / \sqrt{4} \right) - (8 \times 5) \right) \right)$$

$$8388487 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(8+3)^8} - ((8-4) \times (8^7))} \right) \right)$$

$$8388492 := (-((8 \times 3)) + (((8^8) / \sqrt{4}) - (92)))$$

$$8388498 := \left((-((8 \times 3) - (8^8))) / \sqrt{4} - 98 \right)$$

$$8388549 := \left(- \left((8 \times (3 - ((8+8)^5) - 4)) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$8388574 := \left((8 \times (3 + ((8+8)^5) - 7)) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$8388579 := \left((8 \times (3 + ((8+8)^5) - 7)) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$8388581 := \left(- \left((8 \times (3 - ((8+8)^5))) \right) - \sqrt{8+1} \right)$$

$$8388588 := \left(\left((8^3) \times \sqrt{8^8} - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{8+8} \right)$$

$$8388589 := \left((8 - ((3 - ((8+8)^5)) \times 8)) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$8388593 := \left(- \left((8 \times (3 - ((8+8)^5))) \right) + (\sqrt{9} \times 3) \right)$$

$$8388594 := \left(- \left(((8 \times 3) - (((8^8) + 5) - 9)) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$8388599 := \left((8 \times ((3 \times 8) - 8^5)) - \sqrt{9 \times 9} \right)$$

$$8388704 := \left((8 \times ((3 \times 8) + (8^7))) / \sqrt{04} \right)$$

$$8388742 := \left((83 + (-((8 - (8^7))) \times \sqrt{4})) \times 2 \right)$$

$$8388747 := \left(83 + (8 \times (((8^7) / \sqrt{4}) + 7)) \right)$$

$$8388749 := \left(- \left((8 - ((38 + (8^7)) \times 4)) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$8388776 := \left(\sqrt{8 \times 3 - 8} \times ((8^7) + (7 \times 6)) \right)$$

$$8388924 := \left(- (8) + ((\sqrt{3^8} + (8^{9-2})) \times 4) \right)$$

$$8389632 := \left((8^3) \times (\sqrt{8^9 \times 6/3} + 2) \right)$$

$$8396825 := \left(\left((83 \times \sqrt{9}) - (((6^8) - 2)) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$8396845 := \left(\left(\left((83 \times \sqrt{9}) - (6^8) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$8396865 := \left(\left((- (83) \times \sqrt{9}) + ((6^8) + 6) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$8397568 := \left(- \left((8^3) \right) - \left((\sqrt{9} + (7 - 5)) \times (- (6^8)) \right) \right)$$

$$8397685 := \left(\left((- (83) - \sqrt{9}) + (7 + (6^8)) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$8397930 := \left((- (8) + \left((- ((3 - 9))^7 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times 30 \right)$$

$$8398125 := \left((8 + (3 - 9)^8 + 1) \times \sqrt{25} \right)$$

$$8398168 := \left(83 + \left((\sqrt{9} - 8) \times (- (1 + (6^8))) \right) \right)$$

$$8398568 := \left((8^3) - \left((\sqrt{9} \times 8) - (5 \times (6^8)) \right) \right)$$

$$8398685 := \left(\left((- ((8+3)) \times (\sqrt{9} + 8)) - (6^8) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$8398848 := \left((8^3) \times \left((\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{8^8}) \times 4 + 8 \right) \right)$$

$$8418575 := \left(\sqrt{(8+4-1)^8} \times 575 \right)$$

$$8421376 := \left(\left((8^4) \times 2 \right) \times (- (1) + (3 \times \sqrt{7^6})) \right)$$

$$8425795 := \left(\left(((8 \times (4 + (2 \times 5))) + 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$8436845 := \left(\left((8 \times 4) - \left((3 + \sqrt{6^8})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$8437832 := 8 \times \left(4 \times \sqrt{(3-7)^8 + 3} \right)^2$$

$$8439228 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{8^4} - 3) \times 9 \right)^2 \right) \times 28 \right)$$

$$8454137 := \left(\left((8 + (4^5)) \times \sqrt{4^{13}} - 7 \right) \right)$$

$$8454144 := \left((8 + (4^5)) \times \sqrt{4^{14}/4} \right)$$

$$8454264 := \left(\left(8 \times \left(((4^5) + 4)^2 \right) \right) - \sqrt{64} \right)$$

$$8454266 := \left(\left(8 \times \left(((4^5) + 4)^2 \right) \right) - \sqrt{6 \times 6} \right)$$

$$8454272 := \left(8 \times \left(\left((4^5) + 4 \right)^{\sqrt{2 \times 7 + 2}} \right) \right)$$

$$8454293 := \left(\left(8 \times \left(\left(((4^5) + 4)^2 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 3 \right) \right)$$

$$8454294 := \left(\left(8 \times \left(\left(((4^5) + 4)^2 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$8454299 := \left(\left(8 \times \left(((4^5) + 4)^2 \right) \right) + (9 \times \sqrt{9}) \right)$$

$$8454464 := \left(8 \times \left(\left(((4^5) + 4)^{\sqrt{4}} + ((6 \times 4)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$8456464 := \left(\left(- (8) + \sqrt{((4+5) \times 6)^4} \right)^{6-4} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8459624 &:= \left(\left((84 + 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (6 \times 2) \right) - 4 \\
 8459628 &:= \left((84 + 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times ((6 - 2) + 8) \\
 8459634 &:= \left(\left(\left((84 + 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 6 \right) + 3 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 8459712 &:= \left(\left((84 + 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 7 \right) \times 12 \\
 8470694 &:= \left(- \left(\left(8 \times \left(4 - \left((7^{06}) \times 9 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 8470696 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((7^{06}) \times 9 \right) - 6 \right) \right) \right) \\
 8470699 &:= \left(- \left(\left(8 \times \left(4 - \left((7^{06}) \times 9 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 8470728 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 7 \right) \right) \times \left(07^{-2+8} \right) \right) \\
 8470736 &:= \left(8 + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (70) \right) \times \left(7^{\sqrt{36}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 8471064 &:= \left(- (84) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{7^{10}} \times (-6) \right) - 4 \right) \right) \\
 8476798 &:= \left(\left((8^4) + 7 \right) \times \left(\left(6 \times \left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) + 8 \right) \right) \\
 8477283 &:= \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{8^4} - 7 \times 7} \right)^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \times 3 \\
 8479744 &:= \left(\left((8^4) - \left((7 + 9) \times 74 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 8483373 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(8 - \sqrt{4})^8} - 3 \right) \times \left((3^7) \times 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 8489632 &:= \left(- (8) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((8 + 9) \times 6^3 \right) - 2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 8489634 &:= \left(- \left(\left(8 \times \left(4 - \left((8 + 9) \times 6^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 8489639 &:= \left(- (8) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left((8 + 9) \times 6^3 \right) \right) \right) - 9 \\
 8489672 &:= \left(8 + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((8 + 9) \times 6 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{7+2}} \right) \right) \\
 8489693 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(4 + \left((8 + 9) \times 6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right) - 3 \\
 8489694 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(4 + \left((8 + 9) \times 6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 8489699 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(4 + \left((8 + 9) \times 6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \\
 8496784 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(9^6 \right) \right) - 784 \right) \right) \\
 8497225 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{8^4} \times 9 \right) + 7 \right)^2 \right) \times 25 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8549784 &:= \left(8 + \left(\left((54^{9-7}) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 8552439 &:= \left(\left((8^5) \times \left(5 + \left(2^{\sqrt{4^3}} \right) \right) \right) \right) - 9 \\
 8564985 &:= \left(-8 + \sqrt{5^6} \right) \times \sqrt{\left(\sqrt{4} + 9 \right)^8} \times 5 \\
 8573224 &:= \left(8 \times \left(5 - \left(- \left((732^2) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 8585216 &:= \left((8^5) \times \left(\sqrt{8^5 \times 2} + (1 \times 6) \right) \right) \\
 8593758 &:= \left(8 + \left(\left((57/3) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(5^8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 8594648 &:= \left(\left((8^5) + (9 \times 4) \right) \times \left(6 + \sqrt{4^8} \right) \right) \\
 8597722 &:= \left(\left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 7 \right) - (7 \times 2) \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 8597725 &:= \left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (7 + 7) \right) - (25) \right) \\
 8597728 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-7) \right) + 7 \right) \times (-2) \right) - 8 \right) \\
 8597735 &:= \left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (7 + 7) \right) - (3 \times 5) \right) \\
 8597736 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-7) \right) + 7 \right) / (-3) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 8597742 &:= \left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (7 + 7) \right) - (4 \times 2) \right) \\
 8597743 &:= \left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (7 + 7) \right) - (4 + 3) \right) \\
 8597744 &:= \left(\left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (7 + 7) \right) - 4 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 8597745 &:= \left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{7 \times 7 \times 4} \right) - 5 \right) \\
 8597746 &:= \left(\left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (7 + 7) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) - 6 \right) \\
 8597747 &:= \left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (7 + 7) \right) + ((4 - 7)) \right) \\
 8597748 &:= \left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (7 + 7) \right) - \sqrt{-4 + 8} \right) \\
 8597749 &:= \left(\left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (7 + 7) \right) - 4 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 8597762 &:= \left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (7 + 7) \right) + (6 \times 2) \right) \\
 8597764 &:= \left(\left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-7) \right) - 7 \right) \times (- (6 - 4)) \right) \\
 8597792 &:= \left(\left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-7) \right) + \left(- (7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times (-2) \right) \\
 8597795 &:= \left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (7 + 7) \right) + (9 \times 5) \right) \\
 8597848 &:= \left(\left((85^{\sqrt{9}}) + 7 \right) \times \left((8 - \sqrt{4}) + 8 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8597894 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(85^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 7 \right) + (8 \times 9) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 8597974 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(85^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + ((7+9)) \right) \times 7 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 8604754 &:= \left(- \left(\left(860 - \left((4 \times 7)^5 \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 8605184 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((8+6)^{05} \right) \times 1 \right) \times 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 8609792 &:= \left(\sqrt{8^6} \times \left(09 + \left(7^{\sqrt{9}+2} \right) \right) \right) \\
 8612583 &:= \left(861 \times \left(\sqrt{(2 \times 5)^8} + 3 \right) \right) \\
 8632589 &:= \left(863 \times \left(\sqrt{(2 \times 5)^8} + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 8633945 &:= \left(\left(\left(8^6 \right) \times 33 \right) - \left(\left(9 - \sqrt{4} \right)^5 \right) \right) \\
 8650749 &:= \left(\left(\left(8^6 \right) \times (5 + (07 \times 4)) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 8653959 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(6^{5+3} \right) \right) - \left(\sqrt{9^{5+9}} \right) \right) \\
 8654696 &:= \left(8 - \left(- \left(\left(6^5 \right) + \left(4^6 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9^6} \right) \\
 8654848 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{65^4} \right) + 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4^8} \right) \\
 8659992 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(- (6) + \left(5 \times \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \times (9+2) \right) \right) \\
 8669444 &:= \left(\left(- (8) + \left((6 \times 694)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 8677931 &:= \left(8 + \left(\left(\left(6^{\sqrt{7 \times 7}} \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 31 \right) \right) \\
 8688382 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (8) \times \sqrt{6^8} \right) \times (-838) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 8688384 &:= 8 \times \sqrt{6^8 \times 838^{\sqrt{4}}} \\
 8696664 &:= \left(86 \times \left(\left(\left((9 \times 6) \times 6 \right) - 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 8699664 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(8^6 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right)^6 \right) \right) / 4 \right) \\
 8732699 &:= \left(8 - \left(\left((73+26)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-9) \right) \right) \\
 8749764 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((8 \times 7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 + (7 \times 6)) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 8751645 &:= \left(-8 + \sqrt{(7+5-1)^6} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 \\
 8754966 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{(8 \times 7 - 5)^{4 \times \sqrt{9}}}} \times 66
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8756439 &:= \left(- (8) - \left(- \left(\left(7^5 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{64^3} + 9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8794654 &:= \left(\left(\left((87 \times (9+4)) \times \left(6^5 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 8794659 &:= \left(\left(\left((87 \times (9+4)) \times \left(6^5 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 8796672 &:= \left(\left(\left(8^7 \right) \times 9 \right) - \left(\sqrt{6 \times 6^{7+2}} \right) \right) \\
 8796684 &:= \left(\left(\left(8^7 \right) \times 9 \right) - \left(- (6) \times \left(- \left(\left(6^8 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8797950 &:= \left(\left(\left((8 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 8815286 &:= \left(881 \times \left(\sqrt{(5 \times 2)^8} + 6 \right) \right) \\
 8821874 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 \times \left(82^{\sqrt{1+8}} \right) \right) - 7 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 8821888 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(82^{\sqrt{1+8}} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}} \right) \\
 8821894 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 \times \left(82^{\sqrt{1+8}} \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 8837444 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{8^8} + 3 \right) \times \sqrt{7^4} \right) \times 44 \right) \\
 8857836 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{8+8} - \left(5 \times \left(7 + \left((8+3)^6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8869239 &:= \left(\left(8 - \sqrt{8^6} \right) + \left(9 \times 23 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 8869679 &:= \left(- \left((8 \times 8) \right) + \left(\left(6 + \left(\sqrt{9} \times 67 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 8869739 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{8+8} - \left(\left((6 + (9 \times 7)) \times 3 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 8896512 &:= \left(\sqrt{8^8} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^6} - 5 \right) \times (1+2) \right) \right) \\
 8912896 &:= \left((8+9) \times \left((1 \times 2)^{-8+\sqrt{9^6}} \right) \right) \\
 8925184 &:= \left(\left(- (8) + \sqrt{9^{2+5}} \right) \times \left((1 \times 8)^4 \right) \right) \\
 8928144 &:= \left(\left(\left((8 \times 9) \times (2+81) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 8937466 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(- (8) + \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(3^7 \right) \right) \times \left(4^6 \right) \right) - 6 \right) \\
 8937469 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(- (8) + \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(3^7 \right) \right) \times \left(4^6 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 8941476 &:= \left(\left((8 \times 9) + 4 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{1 \times 4} + \left((7^6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8947849 &:= \left(8^{\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{4}}}} + 7 \right) / \left(8 + \sqrt{49} \right); \\
 8949784 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times \left(- (8^4) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8952064 &:= \left(-8 + \sqrt{9 \times (5 \times 2)^{06}}\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 8954912 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(8 + (\sqrt{9} \times 5)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right)^{\sqrt{9}+1}\right) \times 2\right) \\
 8957686 &:= \left(-8 + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(5 + 7\right)^6 - 86\right)\right)\right) \\
 8957690 &:= \left(8 + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(5 + 7\right)^6 - 90\right)\right)\right) \\
 8957863 &:= -89 + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{(5+7)^{8 \times 6}} \times 3}} \\
 8957889 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{9}\right)^5 - (7 \times 8)\right) / (-8)\right) \times (-9)\right) \\
 8957926 &:= \left(-8 + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\left(5 + 7\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right)^2 - 6\right)\right)\right) \\
 8957937 &:= \left(-8 + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(5 + 7\right)^{9-3}\right) - 7\right)\right) \\
 8957941 &:= \left(-8 + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(5 + 7\right)^{\sqrt{9 \times 4}} - 1\right)\right)\right) \\
 8957942 &:= \left(-8 + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(5 + 7\right)^{\sqrt{9 \times 4}}\right) - 2\right)\right) \\
 8957945 &:= \left(8 + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(5 + 7\right)^{\sqrt{9 \times 4}} - 5\right)\right)\right) \\
 8957949 &:= \left(\left(8 - 9 + \left(5 + 7\right)^{\sqrt{9 \times 4}}\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 8957952 &:= 8 \times 9 \times \sqrt{(5+7)^9 \times (5-2)} \\
 8957954 &:= \left(\left(-\left(\left(8 + 9 - 5\right)^7\right) - \sqrt{9}\right) - 5\right) / (-4) \\
 8957973 &:= \left(\left(-\left(\left(8 \times 9\right) \times \left(5 - 7\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}} + 7\right) \times 3 \\
 8957984 &:= \left(8 + \left(9 \times \left(5 + 7\right)^{-\sqrt{9}+8}\right)\right) \times 4 \\
 8957996 &:= \left(8 + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(5 + 7 + \left(9 + \sqrt{9}\right)^6\right)\right)\right) \\
 8958469 &:= \left(\left(8^{\sqrt{9}} + 5\right) - \left(-\left(\left(8 + 4\right)^6\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\
 8959888 &:= \left(-8 + \left(\sqrt{9^5} \times \left(9 \times \sqrt{8^8} + 8\right)\right)\right) \\
 8963784 &:= \left(8 \times \sqrt{9^6} + \left(\left(3^7\right) \times \left(8^4\right)\right)\right) \\
 8966496 &:= \left(89 + \left(6^6 \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times 96 \\
 8969976 &:= \left(\left(8 \times 9 + \left(-6\right) \times \sqrt{9^9}\right) \times (-76)\right) \\
 8974336 &:= \left(8^{\sqrt{9+7}} \times \left(4 + \left(3 \times \left(3^6\right)\right)\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8975294 &:= \left(-89 + \left(-\left(\left(7^5\right) \times 2\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) - 4\right) \\
 8979139 &:= \left(\left(8^{\sqrt{9+7}} - 9\right) \times \left(13^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \\
 8983823 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{9} - \left(\left(8 - 3\right)^8\right)\right) \times (-23)\right) \\
 8984234 &:= \left(\left(-8 + \left(-\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(84 \times 2\right)\right)^3\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 8984329 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 - \sqrt{9}\right)^8 - \sqrt{4}\right) \times (32 - 9)\right) \\
 8984375 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 - \sqrt{9}\right)^8\right) \times \left(-\left(4 \times 3 - \left(7 \times 5\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 8984421 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 - \sqrt{9}\right)^8 + \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + (21)\right)\right) \\
 8996568 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(9 \times \left(6 - \left(5^6\right) \times 8\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 8996864 &:= 8^{\sqrt{9}} \times \left(\sqrt{\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 + 8\right)^6 - 4}\right) \\
 8998897 &:= \left(-8 + \left(\left(\left(9 + 9 + 8\right) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 7\right)\right) \\
 8998906 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 + 9 + 9\right) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{9}} + (0 - 6)\right) \\
 8998909 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 + 9 + 9\right) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{09}\right) \\
 8998911 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 + 9 + 9\right) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - (1 \times 1)\right) \\
 8998913 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 + 9 + 9\right) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{9}} + \left(1^3\right)\right) \\
 8998914 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 + 9 + 9\right) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{1 \times 4}\right) \\
 8998916 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 + 9 + 9\right) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{16}\right) \\
 8998928 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 + 9 + 9\right) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{9}} + \left(2 \times 8\right)\right) \\
 8998939 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 + 9 + 9\right) \times 8\right)^{\sqrt{9}} + \left(3 \times 9\right)\right) \\
 8999199 &:= \left(89 - \left(9 + 91\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times (-9) \\
 8999568 &:= \left(8 \times 9 \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(9 - \left(5^6\right) \times 8\right)\right)\right) \\
 8999846 &:= \left(8 - \left(9 \times \left(9 + 9 - \left(8 + \sqrt{4}\right)^6\right)\right)\right) \\
 8999976 &:= \left(\left(-8\right) \times \sqrt{9} - \left(-9\right) \times \left(\left(9 / \sqrt{9} + 7\right)^6\right)\right) \\
 8999992 &:= \left(-8 + \left(\left(\left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}} / 9\right)^2\right)\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$8999995 := \left(\left(\left(- \left((8 - 9) - 99 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$9034497 := \left(- \left((9 \times 03)^4 \right) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times (9^7) \right) \right)$$

$$9058976 := \left(\sqrt{9} - \left((0 - 5) - (8 \times 9) \right) \times (7^6) \right)$$

$$9058977 := \left((9 - 05) + \left((8 + \sqrt{9}) \times (7^7) \right) \right)$$

$$9075960 := \left(\left((9 \times (0 - (7^5))) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-60) \right)$$

$$9094545 := \left(909 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 5)^4 \right) + 5 \right) \right)$$

$$9114930 := \left(\sqrt{(9 \times 11)^4} \times 930 \right)$$

$$9129329 := \sqrt{(91 \times 2 + 9 \times 3)^{2 \times \sqrt{9}}};$$

$$9135984 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(13 \times \left((5 + 9) + 8^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9139572 := \left(- \left((9 \times 13) \right) \times \left(9 - \sqrt{(5^7)^2} \right) \right)$$

$$9139574 := \left(- \left(\left((9 \times 13) \times \left(9 - (5^7) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$9144576 := \left(\sqrt{(9 \times 14)^4} \times 576 \right)$$

$$9145875 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(145^{(8+7)/5} \right) \right)$$

$$9145929 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(145^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left((2 \times 9) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9145965 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(145^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left((6 \times 5) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9147456 := \left(9 \times \left(\left((1 \times 4)^7 \right) + \left((\sqrt{4} \times 5)^6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9148592 := \left(\left((9 \times 14) + (8 \times 5) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 2 \right)$$

$$9150616 := -9 + (1 - 50 - 6)^{\sqrt{16}}$$

$$9150622 := -\sqrt{9} + (1 - 50 - 6)^{2+2}$$

$$9150628 := \sqrt{9} + (1 - 50 - 6)^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}}$$

$$9162729 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(9+1)^6} + (2+7) \right)^2 \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9174585 := 917 \times \left(\sqrt{(\sqrt{4} \times 5)^8} + 5 \right)$$

$$9174865 := \left((\sqrt{9} + ((1+7) \times 4)) \times ((8^6) - 5) \right)$$

$$9174985 := \left((\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((1 \times 7) \times (4^9) \right) - 8 \right)) \times (-5) \right)$$

$$9176625 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(1 - \left((7^6) \times (6 - (2^5)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9176726 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times (-(1 - (7^6)))) \right) + 7 \right) \times 26$$

$$9176856 := \left((\sqrt{9} + (1 \times 7)^6) \right) \times ((8+5) \times 6)$$

$$9176934 := - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + (1 + (7^6))) \times (\sqrt{9} - ((3^4))) \right) \right)$$

$$9195275 := - \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} + (19))^5 \right) - \left((27^5) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9195864 := \left((\sqrt{9} \times (-(1-9))) \times \left((\sqrt{5^8} - 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$9218289 := \left(921 \times \left(\sqrt{(8+2)^8} + 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9229444 := \left((9+22) \times (94+4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$9234184 := \left(- \left(\left((9^2)^3 \right) \right) + \left((4+1)^{8+\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$9234852 := \left((\sqrt{9} + (23^4)) \times (8 + (5^2)) \right)$$

$$9237891 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((2 \times 3)^7 \right) \times (8 + \sqrt{9}) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$9237894 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((2 \times 3)^7 \right) \times (8 + \sqrt{9}) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$9246359 := \left(- \left((9+2)^4 \right) + \left((6 \times 35)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9253944 := \left(\left((-9) \times \sqrt{25} \right) - \left((39^4) \right) \right) \times (-4)$$

$$9260995 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times (-2)) + (6^{\sqrt{09}}) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$9272709 := \left(9 \times \left(\left((2^7) - 27 \right)^{\sqrt{09}} \right) \right)$$

$$9277464 := 92 \times 7 \times \sqrt{(7^4 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}}$$

$$9282325 := \left(\left((9 + \sqrt{2 \times 8})^{2+3} \right) \times 25 \right)$$

$$9289719 := \left(\left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{2 \times 8^9}) \times (-7) \right) + 1 \right) \times (-9) \right)$$

$$9289728 := \left(- \left((9^2) \right) \times \left((8^{\sqrt{9+7}}) \times (-28) \right) \right)$$

$$9294276 := \left((\sqrt{9} + 2) - \left((\sqrt{9^4} - 2) \times (-(7^6)) \right) \right)$$

$$9294497 := - \left(\left(\left((9 + (2^9))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - (\sqrt{4} \times (9^7)) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9304325 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + ((30 \times 4)) \right)^3 \right) - 2 \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 9304335 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + ((30 \times 4)) \right)^{\sqrt{3 \times 3}} \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 9304345 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + ((30 \times 4)) \right)^3 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 9304365 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + ((30 \times 4)) \right)^3 \right) + 6 \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 9315586 &:= \left(931 \times \left(\sqrt{(5+5)^8 + 6} \right) \right) \\
 9329739 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((3 \times 79) \times 2 \right) \times (3^9) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9329796 &:= \left(\left(- (9) + \left(\sqrt{3^{2 \times 9}} \times (-79) \right) \right) \times (-6) \right) \\
 9329979 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(- \left((3 \times 2) \right) \times \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \times 79 \right) \\
 9334359 &:= \left(\left(\left((9 + 33)^4 \right) - (3^5) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9334764 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left(\left((3^3) \times 4 \right) - \left((7 \times 6)^4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9334839 &:= \left(\left(\left((9 + 33)^4 \right) - 83 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9334994 &:= \left(\left(\left((9 + 33)^4 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (94) \right) \\
 9343431 &:= \left(9 \times \left(3 - 4^3 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 31 \\
 9345249 &:= \left(9 \times \left(3 - 4^5 + 2 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} / 9 \\
 9345252 &:= \sqrt{9} + \left(3 \times \left(4^5 - \sqrt{25} \right) \right)^2 \\
 9374685 &:= 937 \times \left(\sqrt{(4+6)^8 + 5} \right) \\
 9374988 &:= \sqrt{9} \times \left(3 - 7 + \left((4 - 9)^8 \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 9375084 &:= \left((9 + 3) \times \left(7 + \left((5^{08}) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9375844 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left((3 - 7) \right)^5 \right) \right) - \left(8 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 9375882 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((37 + (5^8)) \times 8 \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 9375884 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((37 + (5^8)) \times 8 \right) \right) \right) - 4 \right) \\
 9375888 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(37 + (5^8) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{8 \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9384920 &:= \left(\sqrt{(93+8)^4} \times 920 \right) \\
 9388791 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{3+8}} \right) \times \left((8 \times 7) - \sqrt{9 \times 1} \right) \right) \\
 9407973 &:= \left(\left(9 - \left(\left((40 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / 7 \right) \right) \times (-3) \right) \\
 9407997 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\left((40 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 9411680 &:= \left(-\sqrt{9} + (4 - 11)^6 \right) \times 80 \\
 9432549 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(\left((4^5)^2 \right) - 3 \right) - \sqrt{4^9} \right) \right) \\
 9434997 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((4 \times 3) \times (4^9) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9^7} \right) \\
 9435447 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (43 \times (5 + 4)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 9436968 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left((4^{3+6}) - 9 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} \right) \\
 9437059 &:= \left(\left(9 \times (4^{3+7}) \right) - (05^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \\
 9437154 &:= \left(\left(9 \times (4^{3+7}) \right) - (15 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 9437158 &:= \left(\left(\left(9 \times (4^{3+7}) \right) - 1 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) \\
 9437168 &:= \left(\left(9 \times (4^{3+7}) \right) + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}} \times (-8) \right) \right) \\
 9437179 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \left((4^{3+7}) - 1 \right) \right) + \sqrt{7+9} \right) \\
 9437181 &:= \left(\left(9 \times (4^{3+7}) \right) - \sqrt{1 \times 8 + 1} \right) \\
 9437187 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((4^{3+7}) + 1 \right) + (8^7) \right) \right) \\
 9437188 &:= \left(\left(9 \times (4^{3+7}) \right) + \sqrt{1 \times 8 + 8} \right) \\
 9437189 &:= \left(\left(\left(9 \times (4^{3+7}) \right) + (1 \times 8) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9437190 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \left((4^{3+7}) + 1 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9+0} \right) \\
 9437194 &:= \left(\left(\left(9 \times (4^{3+7}) \right) - (1 - 9) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 9437195 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \left((4^{3+7}) + 1 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9-5} \right) \\
 9437197 &:= 9 \times \left(4^{3+7} + 1 \right) + \sqrt{9+7} \\
 9437198 &:= \left(\left(\left(9 \times \left((4^{3+7}) + 1 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) + 8 \right) \\
 9437199 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((4^{3+7}) + 1 \right) \times 9 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9437204 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \left((4^{3+7}) + 2 \right) \right) + \sqrt{04} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9437238 &:= (9 \times ((4^{3+7}) + \sqrt{-2+38})) \\
 9437246 &:= (((9 \times (4^{3+7})) - 2) + \sqrt{4^6}) \\
 9437256 &:= 9 \times (\sqrt{4} + (3-7)^{2 \times 5} + 6) \\
 9437259 &:= (((\sqrt{9} \times (4^{3+7})) + (25)) \times \sqrt{9}) \\
 9437283 &:= (9 \times ((\sqrt{4}^{(3+7) \times 2}) + (8+3))) \\
 9437284 &:= ((9 \times (4^{3+7})) + \sqrt{(2+8)^4}) \\
 9437292 &:= (9 \times ((4^{3+7}) + ((2 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 2))) \\
 9437328 &:= (9 \times ((4^{3+7}) + \sqrt{32 \times 8})) \\
 9437364 &:= (9 \times (((4^{3+7}) + (3 \times 6)) + \sqrt{4})) \\
 9437373 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times (((4^{3+7}) + (3 \times 7)) \times 3)) \\
 9437427 &:= 9 \times (\sqrt{4^{(3+7) \times \sqrt{4}} + 27}) \\
 9437436 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times ((4 \times 3) \times (7 + (4^{3+6})))) \\
 9437454 &:= (9 \times (((4^{3+7}) + \sqrt{4^5}) - \sqrt{4})) \\
 9437589 &:= (9 \times ((4^{3+7}) + (\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \times 9}))) \\
 9437877 &:= (9 \times ((4^{\sqrt{-3+7+8}}) + 77)) \\
 9437994 &:= (9 \times (((4^{3+7}) + 9) + \sqrt{9^4})) \\
 9438489 &:= (9 - (\sqrt{\sqrt{(4 \times 3)^8} \times (-((4^8) + 9))})) \\
 9439704 &:= (9 \times (((4^3)^{\sqrt{9}}) + (70)) \times 4) \\
 9443329 &:= (((9 \times (4^{\sqrt{4+3}})) + 3)^2) / 9) \\
 9445590 &:= (((9 \times \sqrt{4})^4) - ((5 \times 5)) \times 90) \\
 9446559 &:= (((\sqrt{9} \times (4^{4+6})) + ((5^5))) \times \sqrt{9}) \\
 9447735 &:= (((9 \times \sqrt{4})^{-\sqrt{4+7}}) - ((7 \times 3)) \times 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9447795 &:= (((9 \times \sqrt{4})^{4+7/7}) - 9) \times 5) \\
 9447835 &:= (((9 \times \sqrt{4})^4) \times (7+83)) - 5) \\
 9447855 &:= ((\sqrt{9} + ((-4 + ((\sqrt{4} \times 7) + 8))^5)) \times 5) \\
 9447875 &:= (((9 \times \sqrt{4})^{4-7+8}) + 7) \times 5) \\
 9447895 &:= (((9 \times \sqrt{4})^{-\sqrt{4+7}}) + (8 + \sqrt{9})) \times 5) \\
 9448848 &:= ((\sqrt{9^4} + (4^8)) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(8+4)^8}}) \\
 9449466 &:= (((\sqrt{9} + ((4^4) \times 9))) \times (4^6)) - 6) \\
 9449469 &:= (((\sqrt{9} + ((4^4) \times 9))) \times (4^6)) - \sqrt{9}) \\
 9453125 &:= (((9 + \sqrt{4}) \times (5^{3+1}))^2) / 5) \\
 9455616 &:= (((9 \times \sqrt{4})^5) \times 5) + (6^{-1+6}) \\
 9455634 &:= (9 + (((4^5) - 5) + 6) \times 3)^{\sqrt{4}}) \\
 9463784 &:= (946 \times (\sqrt{(3+7)^8 + 4})) \\
 9479148 &:= ((-94) \times \sqrt{7^9+1}) \times (\sqrt{4} - 8) \\
 9483273 &:= (9 + (\sqrt{4} \times (-((8-32) \times 7)^3))) \\
 9483950 &:= \sqrt{(9 - \sqrt{4})^8} \times 3950 \\
 9486494 &:= (94 + ((8 + (6 \times \sqrt{4^9}))^{\sqrt{4}})) \\
 9487368 &:= \sqrt{9^4} \times 8 \times \sqrt{(7-3 \times 6)^8} \\
 9492289 &:= ((9^{\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}}}) - (2^{2 \times 8+9})) \\
 9492298 &:= 9 - \sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}+22}} + 9^8 \\
 9492489 &:= (((\sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{4^9} \times 2))^{\sqrt{4}}) - 8) \times 9) \\
 9492549 &:= (((9 + (4^5))^2) \times \sqrt{9}) - 4) \times \sqrt{9})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$9498724 := \left(\left((-9) \times \sqrt{4 \times 9} \right) + \left((8 \times 7)^2 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$9529476 := \left(-((95 - 2)) + \left(\sqrt{9^4} \times (7^6) \right) \right)$$

$$9529794 := \left(\left(9 \times (5^2) \right) + \left(\left(9 \times (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$9529974 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^5} \times 2 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^9} - 74 \right) \right)$$

$$9533135 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\sqrt{5^{3+3}} - 1 \right)^3 \right) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$9535197 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((5 + 3)^5 \right) - 1 \right) \times 97 \right)$$

$$9539694 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^5} \times \left((3^9) - (6 \times 9) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$9539712 := \left(\sqrt{9 - 5} \times \left(\left(-3 \right) + \sqrt{9^7} \right)^{1 \times 2} \right)$$

$$9539728 := \left(\sqrt{9 - 5} \times \left(\left(\left(-3 \right) + \sqrt{9^7} \right)^2 \right) + 8 \right)$$

$$9539742 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 5 \right) + \left(\left(-3 \right) + \sqrt{9^7} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times 2$$

$$9554284 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\left((5^5) - 42 \right) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$9556947 := \left(\sqrt{9^5} \times \left(5 + \left(6 \times \left((9^4) - 7 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9557694 := \left(\left(9 \times (5^5) \right) + \left((7^6) \times \sqrt{9^4} \right) \right)$$

$$9559682 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left((5^5) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\sqrt{9^{6+8}} \right) \right) \times (-2)$$

$$9559694 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((5^5) - \left((9^6) \times 9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$9562866 := \left(\sqrt{9^{5+6+2}} - \sqrt{8^6} \right) \times 6$$

$$9563994 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^5} \times (6/3) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^9} - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$9564696 := \left(\left(\left((9^5) \times 6 \right) - 46 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} \right)$$

$$9564813 := \left(-9 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{5^6} + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(81^3 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9564939 := \left(\left(\left(\left(- \left((9^5) - 6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-9) \right) - 3 \right) \times 9$$

$$9564966 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((56 - \sqrt{4}) - (9^6) \right) \times (-6) \right) \right)$$

$$9564974 := \left(-956 \right) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((9^7) - 4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9564976 := \left(-956 \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (9^7) \right) - 6 \right)$$

$$9564979 := \left(-956 \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (9^7) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9565668 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^{5+6}} \right) - 5 \right) \times \left(6 + (6 \times 8) \right) \right)$$

$$9565916 := \left(\sqrt{9 - 5} \times \left(- \left((6 + 5) - (9^{1+6}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9565926 := \left(\left(\left(- \left((9^{5+6-5}) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 2 \right) \times (-6) \right)$$

$$9565942 := \left(\left((9^{5+6+5-9}) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$9565947 := \left(9 + \left(\sqrt{5 - 6 + 5} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{4}}} \right)^7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9565974 := \left(\left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{5 - 6 + 5} \right) + \left((9^7) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$9565976 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 5 \right) - \left(-6 \right) \times \left(5 + \left(\sqrt{9^{7+6}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9565986 := \left(\sqrt{9^{5-6+5+9}} + 8 \right) \times 6$$

$$9565992 := \left(\left((9^{5+6-5}) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (9 \times 2) \right)$$

$$9565997 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (56) \right) + \left((5 - \sqrt{9}) \times (9^7) \right) \right)$$

$$9566313 := \left(\sqrt{9 \times 5^6} + \left(6 \times (3^{13}) \right) \right)$$

$$9566496 := \left(9 \times \left((56 + 6) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (9^6) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9566919 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left((9^5) + 6 \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 1 \right) \times (-9)$$

$$9566974 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 5)^6} + \left((6 + (9^7)) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$9583442 := \left(\left(\left((9^{-5+8}) \times 3 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 2$$

$$9599625 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((5^{\sqrt{9}}) - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 6) + 2 \right)^5 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9599985 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-5 \right) + \left(\left((9/\sqrt{9}) + ((9 + 8))^5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9612883 := \left(961 \times \left(\sqrt{(2 + 8)^8 + 3} \right) \right)$$

$$9632889 := \left(963 \times \left(\sqrt{(2 + 8)^8 + \sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9647976 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (6 - 4) \right)^{7+\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left((7^6) \right) \right)$$

$$9653564 := \left(- \left((9 \times 6) \right) + \left(\left((5 + 3) + 5 \right)^6 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$9655296 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-6) \right) - \left((5^5) \right) \right) \times \left(- \left((2^9) \times 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9657792 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 6)^{5-7/7} \right) \times 92 \right)$$

$$9659664 := \left(\left(\left(\left(- \left((9-6) - 5 \right) \right)^9 + 6 \right) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$9663344 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((\sqrt{6^6} - 3)^3 \right) - (4^4) \right) \right)$$

$$9663352 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - \left((3^5) + 2 \right) \right)$$

$$9663354 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{3^{5 \times 4}}} \right)$$

$$9663457 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - ((4 \times 5) \times 7) \right)$$

$$9663489 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - ((4+8) \times 9) \right)$$

$$9663527 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - ((5 \times 2) \times 7) \right)$$

$$9663537 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - (53 + 7) \right)$$

$$9663543 := \left(-((9 \times 6)) + \left(\left((6^3) - \sqrt{5+4} \right)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$9663546 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - (5 + 46) \right)$$

$$9663548 := \left(-\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{6^6} \right)^3 - \sqrt{\sqrt{(5 + \sqrt{4})^8}}$$

$$9663551 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + ((5 - 51)) \right)$$

$$9663557 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - (5 + (5 \times 7)) \right)$$

$$9663566 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + ((5 - (6 \times 6))) \right)$$

$$9663572 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - (5 \times (7 - 2)) \right)$$

$$9663574 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + ((5 - (7 \times 4))) \right)$$

$$9663579 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + (((5 - 7) \times 9)) \right)$$

$$9663582 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - ((5 + 8) + 2) \right)$$

$$9663584 := \left(- (9) + \left(\left((\sqrt{6^6} - 3)^{-5+8} \right) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$9663586 := \left(\left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}} \right) - 6 \right)$$

$$9663587 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((\sqrt{6^6} - 3)^{-5+8} \right) - 7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9663588 := \left(- (9) + \left((\sqrt{6^6} - 3)^{-5+\sqrt{8 \times 8}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663589 := \left(\left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}} \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9663592 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - (5 \times (\sqrt{9} - 2)) \right)$$

$$9663593 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - (- (5) + (\sqrt{9} \times 3)) \right)$$

$$9663598 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + ((5 + \sqrt{9}) / 8) \right)$$

$$9663599 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + \sqrt{5 - 9/9} \right)$$

$$9663603 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + (6 + (0 \times 3)) \right)$$

$$9663627 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) - ((6 \times (2 - 7))) \right)$$

$$9663633 := \left((\sqrt{9} \times (6 + 6)) + \left(- \left((3 - (6^3)) \right)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$9663656 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + (65 - 6) \right)$$

$$9663659 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + (65 - \sqrt{9}) \right)$$

$$9663669 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + \sqrt{6^6/9} \right)$$

$$9663669 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + \sqrt{6^6/9} \right)$$

$$9663687 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + ((6 \times (8 + 7))) \right)$$

$$9663699 := \left((96 + 6) + \left((- (3) + (6^{\sqrt{9}}))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663829 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + (8 \times 29) \right)$$

$$9663849 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + (84 \times \sqrt{9}) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9678321 &:= \left(-\sqrt{9} + 6 \times (7 + 8^3)\right)^2 \times 1 \\
 9682440 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left((6 \times 82)^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right) \times (-40)\right) \\
 9684486 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (6^8)\right) - \sqrt{4}\right) - (4^8)\right) \times 6\right) \\
 9684544 &:= \left(\left((9 \times 68) + (4 \times (5^4))\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 9694845 &:= \left(969 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 8\right)^4\right) + 5\right)\right) \\
 9699345 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{96} + \left(-\left((99^3)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times (-5)\right) \\
 9719769 &:= \left(- (9) - \left(\left(71^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + (7 - 6^9)\right)\right) \\
 9721924 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (9) + \sqrt{(7 - 2)^{1+9}}\right) + 2\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 9721944 &:= \left(- (972) \times \left(- \left(\left((1 + 9)^4\right)\right) - \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 9724050 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7\right)^{\sqrt{2^4}}\right) \times 050\right)\right) \\
 9728095 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7\right) - 2\right) \times \left(\left(80^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + 5\right)\right) \\
 9743085 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{7+4}}\right) \times \left(\left(3 + 08\right) \times 5\right)\right) \\
 9743584 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(7 + 4\right)^{3 \times 5 - 8}\right)\right)\right) / \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 9744384 &:= \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{(7 \times 4)^4}\right) \times \left(3 \times (8^4)\right)\right) \\
 9745568 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9^7} + 4\right) \times (556 \times 8)\right) \\
 9745939 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7\right) + 4\right)^5\right) - \sqrt{9}\right) - (3^9)\right) \\
 9745942 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^{7+\sqrt{4}}}\right) - \left(5^{(9-4) \times 2}\right)\right)\right) \\
 9746884 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(7 - \sqrt{4}\right)^{6-8/8}\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 9747423 &:= \left(\left(\left((97 - 4) \times 7\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times 23\right) \\
 9748475 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + ((74 \times 8))\right) \times (4^7)\right) - 5\right) \\
 9759344 &:= \left(- \left(\left(9 - \left(\left((7 \times 5) + 9\right) + 3\right)^4\right)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 9761528 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{(9 + 7)^6} + \left(1 - (5^{2+8})\right)\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9762538 &:= \left(\left(- (9) \times \sqrt{76}\right) + \left(25^{-3+8}\right)\right) \\
 9763895 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{76}\right) - \left(- \left((3 - 8)^9\right)\right)\right) \times (-5)\right) \\
 9764584 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\sqrt{76} + 4\right)\right) - \left(5^{8+\sqrt{4}}\right)\right)\right) \\
 9764595 &:= \left(\left(\left((97 + 6) \times \sqrt{4}\right) - \left((5^9)\right)\right) \times (-5)\right) \\
 9764854 &:= \left(- (9) + \left(\left(- \left((7^6)\right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - (85)\right)\right) - 4\right)\right) \\
 9764857 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(- \left((7^6)\right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - (85)\right)\right) - 7\right)\right)\right) \\
 9764858 &:= \left(- (9) + \left(\left(7^6\right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(8 - 5)^8}\right)\right)\right) \\
 9764864 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(76 \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times \left(- \left((8^6) / 4\right)\right)\right) \\
 9764995 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- (7 \times 6)\right)\right) + \left(- \left((4 - 9)^9\right)\right)\right) \times 5\right) \\
 9765247 &:= -9 \times 7 \times 6 + 5^{2 \times (-\sqrt{4} + 7)} \\
 9765273 &:= \left(\left(- (9) - \sqrt{76}\right) + \left(\sqrt{52^{7+3}}\right)\right) \\
 9765279 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{76}\right) - \left(5 \times \left(- \left((2 - 7)^9\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 9765285 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\left(7^6\right) + 5\right) \times (2 - 85)\right)\right) \\
 9765291 &:= \left(\left(9 - \sqrt{76}\right) + 5^{2+9-1}\right) \\
 9765325 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7\right) \times 6\right) - \left((5^3)^2\right)\right) \times (-5)\right) \\
 9765397 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-76)\right) + \left(5^{\sqrt{3+97}}\right)\right) \\
 9765499 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- (7 \times 6)\right)\right) + \left(5^{\sqrt{49+\sqrt{9}}}\right)\right) \\
 9765522 &:= \left(- \left((97 + 6)\right) + \left(5^{\sqrt{(5 \times 2)^2}}\right)\right) \\
 9765524 &:= \left(- \left(\left((97 + 6) - \left((5^5)^2\right)\right)\right) + \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 9765529 &:= \left(- \left(\left((9 + 7) \times 6\right) + \left(5^{5+2+\sqrt{9}}\right)\right)\right) \\
 9765534 &:= \left(- \left((97 - 6)\right) + \left(5^{5+3+\sqrt{4}}\right)\right) \\
 9765551 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(76 - \left(\left(5 \times 5\right)^5\right) - 1\right)\right)\right) \\
 9765552 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 76\right) + \left(5^{\sqrt{(5+5)^2}}\right)\right) \\
 9765564 &:= \sqrt{9+7} - 65 + 5^{6+4} \\
 9765565 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7\right) \times (-6)\right) + \left(\left(5^{5+6}\right) / 5\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9765574 &:= \left(- \left((9 + (7 \times 6)) \right) + \left(5^{5+7-\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 9765579 &:= \left(- \left((9 + ((7 \times 6) - 5)) \right) + \left(5^{7+\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9765586 &:= \sqrt{9} - 7 \times 6 + 5^{5 \times (8-6)} \\
 9765592 &:= 9 - 7 \times 6 + \sqrt{(5 \times 5^9)^2} \\
 9765595 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{76+5} \right) + \left((5^9) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 9765597 &:= \left((9 - ((7 \times 6) - 5)) + \left(5^{\sqrt{9}+7} \right) \right) \\
 9765622 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (- (7 - 6)) \right) + \left(5^{6+2+2} \right) \right) \\
 9765627 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((7 - 6) - \left(5^{6/2+7} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9765628 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(((7 - 6) \times 5)^{-6+2 \times 8} \right) \right) \\
 9765652 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7 \right) + \left(6 + \left(\left((5^6) / 5 \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 9765658 &:= \left(- \left((9 - (7 \times 6)) \right) + \left((5^6) \times \sqrt{5^8} \right) \right) \\
 9765664 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (7 + 6) \right) + \left(5^{\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 4} \right) \right) \\
 9765685 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right) \times 6 \right) + \left(5^{(-6+8) \times 5} \right) \right) \\
 9765694 &:= \left((9 \times 7) + 6 \right) + \left(5^{\sqrt{6+94}} \right) \\
 9765698 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 76 \right) - \left(5^{6/\sqrt{9}+8} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9765739 &:= \left(\left((9 \times (7 + 6)) + \left(5^{7+3} \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9765742 &:= \left((9 \times (7 + 6)) + \left(5^{(7-\sqrt{4}) \times 2} \right) \right) \\
 9765745 &:= \left(\sqrt{9+7} \times 6 + 5^{7+\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 5 \\
 9765753 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((7 - 6) + \left(5^7 \right) \right) \times \left(5^3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 9765759 &:= \left(9 - \left(- \left(\left((7 - 6) + \left(5^7 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(5^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9765853 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 76 \right) + \left(5^{8+5-3} \right) \right) \\
 9765925 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right) \times 6 \right) + \left((5^9) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{25} \right) \\
 9765945 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right) \times (-6) \right) - \left(\left((5^9) + 4 \right) \right) \right) \times (-5) \right) \\
 9765965 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{76} \right) - \left((5^{9+6-5}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9765971 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{76} \right) + \left(5^{\sqrt{9}+7 \times 1} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9765977 &:= \left((9 + \sqrt{76}) + \left(5^{9+7/7} \right) \right) \\
 9767295 &:= \left(\left(\left((9 - \sqrt{76}) - \left((7 - 2)^9 \right) \right) \right) \times (-5) \right) \\
 9768285 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left((7 \times 6) \times 8 \right) \right) \right)^2 \right) \times 85 \right) \\
 9774885 &:= \left(977 \times \left(\sqrt{\left(\sqrt{4} + 8 \right)^8 + 5} \right) \right) \\
 9784384 &:= \left(\left((97 \times 8) \times 4 \right) + \left(3 \times 8 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 9794435 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left((7 + 9) + 4 \right) \right) \right)^4 \times 35 \right) \\
 9796414 &:= \left(- (9) + \left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left(\left((6 \times \sqrt{4}) + 1 \right)^4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 9797675 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left((7 \times (9 - 7) - (6^7)) \right) \right) \right) \times (-5) \\
 9797755 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (- (7 - 9)) \right) \right)^7 \right) \times (7 \times 5) \right) - 5 \\
 9825984 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((9 + 8) \times 2 \right) \times 5 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 9825994 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((9 + 8) \times 2 \right) \times 5 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 9834469 &:= \left(- \left((9 - (8 \times (3 + 4)^4)) \right) + \left(- (6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 9834478 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((8 \times (3 + 4)^4 \right) - (7 + 8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9834564 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 3) \right) - \left((4 - (56^4)) \right) \right) \\
 9834594 &:= \left(98 + \left(\left((3 + 4) \times (5 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \right)^4 \right) \\
 9834784 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times ((8 \times 3) \times 4) \right) + \left((7 \times 8)^4 \right) \right) \\
 9843750 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(9^8) \times 4 + 3} \right) \times 750 \right) \\
 9843785 &:= \left(\left((9 + (8^4)) \right) \times \left(- (3) + \sqrt{7^8} \right) \right) - 5 \\
 9846783 &:= \left(- ((9 - 8)) + \left((4^6) \times \left(\sqrt{7^8} + 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 9846784 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (8 - 4)^6 \right) + \left((7 \times 8)^4 \right) \right) \\
 9846789 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 8 \right) - \left((4^6) \times \left(\sqrt{7^8} + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9847545 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 8 \right) \times \left(- \left((4^7) + \left(5^{4+5} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9847895 &:= \left((9 + (8^4)) \times \left(\sqrt{7^8} - \sqrt{9-5} \right) \right) \\
 9858192 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-8) \right) \times \left(\left((58 + 1)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-2) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$9869563 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left((8+6) \times \left((95-6)^3 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9869569 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((8+6) \times \left((95-6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9872164 := \left(\left((9+8) + \left((7-2)^{-1+6} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$9874305 := \left(\sqrt{9^8} \times \left((7 \times 43) \times 05 \right) \right)$$

$$9877545 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(87^{(7+5)/4} \right) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$9882516 := \left(\sqrt{9 \times (8+8)} \times \left((2+5)^{1+6} \right) \right)$$

$$9882675 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 8 \right)^{8/2} \right) \times 675 \right)$$

$$9882774 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((88-2) + \left((7^7) \times 4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9894970 := \left(\left(\left((98 + \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 970 \right) \right)$$

$$9911982 := \left(991 \times \left(\sqrt{(1+9)^8} + 2 \right) \right)$$

$$9915749 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (9-1) \right)^5 \right) + \left((7 - \sqrt{4})^9 \right) \right)$$

$$9919728 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} - 1 \right) \times \left(- \left((9-72) \times 8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9920286 := \left(\left(9 + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{20}}} \times 28 \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$9920456 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^{9+2}} \right) - (0-4) \right) \times 56 \right)$$

$$9920484 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{20}} \times 4} \right) \times 84$$

$$9921984 := \left(992 \times \left(\sqrt{(1+9)^8} + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$9935104 := \left(\left(\left((9 \times 9) / 3 \right) + \sqrt{5^{10}} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$9938226 := \left(\left(\left(-9 + \sqrt{(9-3)^8} \right)^2 + 2 \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$9939897 := \left(- \left((9+9) \right) + \left((3^9) \times \left((8^{\sqrt{9}}) - 7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9939915 := \left(\sqrt{9^9} \times \left(\left((3+99) - 1 \right) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$9945344 := \left(\left(\left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 4 \right) \times \left(53 \times (4^4) \right) \right)$$

$$9946233 := \left(\left(\left(- (9) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{4^6} \right) \right) \right)^2 \times 33 \right)$$

$$9948411 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 948 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 11 \right)$$

$$9949749 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} - \sqrt{4^9} \right) \times \left(7 + \sqrt{4^9} \right) \right)$$

$$9953190 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (9 \times 5) \right)^3 \right) - 1 \right) \times 90 \right)$$

$$9953240 := \left(\left(\left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9} \right)^5 \right) - (3-2) \right) \times 40 \right)$$

$$9953248 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9} \right)^5 \right) \times (3+2) \right) - 4 \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$9953640 := \left(\left(\left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9} \right)^5 \right) + (3+6) \right) \times 40 \right)$$

$$9954722 := \left(\sqrt{9} - 95 \times 47 \right)^2 / 2$$

$$9955440 := \left(\left(\left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9} \right)^5 \right) + (54) \right) \times 40 \right)$$

$$9959112 := \left((9 + \sqrt{9}) \times \left(5 + (911^2) \right) \right)$$

$$9963648 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\sqrt{9} \times 63 \right) \right) \times (-6) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$9966798 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9 \times 9} + 6 \right)^6 \right) \times 7 \right) + 9 \right) / 8 \right)$$

$$9977877 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\sqrt{(9+7)^7} \times (-87) \right) \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$9979284 := \sqrt{9} + \left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{7^{\sqrt{9} \times 2}} + 8 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$9980317 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} - \left(\left((8+03) - 1 \right)^7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9985162 := \left(\left(\left((9/\sqrt{9}) + 8 \right)^5 \right) \times (1 \times 62) \right)$$

$$9996735 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{(9+9)^6} \right) \times \left(- \left((7^3) \times 5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9996777 := \left(\left(\left((9 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left((6^7) \times 7 \right) \right) \times (-7) \right)$$

$$9998244 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 99 \times 8 \times 2 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$9998271 := - \left(\left(\left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left((8+2)^7 - 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9998272 := - \left(\left(\left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (8+2)^{\sqrt{7^2}} \right) \right)$$

$$9998274 := - \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (8+2)^7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$9998957 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \times \left(- (9) + \left((8^{\sqrt{9}}) + 5 \right) \right) \right) - 7 \right)$$

$$9998964 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{9 \times 9}}} \right) \times \left((8^{9-6}) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$9998973 := \left(9 + \left(\sqrt{9^9} \times \left((8^{\sqrt{9}}) - (7-3) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9999271 := \left(\left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) - \left((\sqrt{9} + (9-2))^7 \right) \right) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$9999557 := \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^9 \right) - \left((9+5) + (5^7) \right) \right)$$

$$9999568 := \left(\left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^9 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - \sqrt{5^{6+8}} \right)$$

$$9999571 := \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9 \times 9}} \right) - \left((5^7) \times 1 \right) \right)$$

$$9999572 := \left(\left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^9 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) - \left((5^7) + 2 \right) \right)$$

$$9999574 := (9 - \sqrt{9})^9 + \sqrt{9} - \sqrt{5^7 \times \sqrt{4}}$$

$$9999575 := \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^9 \right) + \left(9 - \left((5^7) + 5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9999757 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- (9 \times 9) \right) \right) + \left(((9-7) \times 5)^7 \right) \right)$$

$$9999777 := - \left(\left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left((\sqrt{9} + 7)^7 - 7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9999847 := \left(9 - ((9+9) \times 9) \right) + \left((8 + \sqrt{4})^7 \right)$$

$$9999979 := \left(- (9) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(((9/9) + 9)^7 - 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9999991 := \left(- (9) + \left(((9/9) + 9)^{9-\sqrt{9}+1} \right) \right)$$

$$9999994 := \left((\sqrt{9} - 9) + \left(((9/9) + 9)^{9-\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$9999997 := \left((9 - \sqrt{9}) - \left(9 - \left(((9/9) + 9)^7 \right) \right) \right)$$

3 Reverse Order of Digits

This section brings **selfie numbers** written in reverse order of Digits. The results are up to 7-digits numbers. It is divided in three subsections. One with symmetric and consecutive. Second symmetric and nonconsecutive and third general values.

3.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$46660 := 0 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 4$$

$$46661 := 1 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 4$$

$$46662 := 2 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 4$$

$$46663 := 3 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 4$$

$$46664 := 4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 4$$

$$46665 := 5 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 4$$

$$46666 := 6 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 4$$

$$46667 := 7 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 4$$

$$46668 := 8 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 4$$

$$46669 := 9 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + 4$$

$$010240 := 0 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 10}$$

$$010241 := 1 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 10}$$

$$010242 := 2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 10}$$

$$010243 := 3 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 10}$$

$$010244 := 4 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 10}$$

$$010245 := 5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 10}$$

$$010246 := 6 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 10}$$

$$010247 := 7 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 10}$$

$$010248 := 8 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 10}$$

$$010249 := 9 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 10}$$

$$031590 := 0 + \sqrt{9^5} \times 130$$

$$031591 := 1 + \sqrt{9^5} \times 130$$

$$031592 := 2 + \sqrt{9^5} \times 130$$

$$031593 := 3 + \sqrt{9^5} \times 130$$

$$031594 := 4 + \sqrt{9^5} \times 130$$

$$031595 := 5 + \sqrt{9^5} \times 130$$

$$031596 := 6 + \sqrt{9^5} \times 130$$

$$031597 := 7 + \sqrt{9^5} \times 130$$

$$031598 := 8 + \sqrt{9^5} \times 130$$

$$031599 := 9 + \sqrt{9^5} \times 130$$

$$032740 := 0 - 4 \times 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032741 := 1 - 4 \times 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032742 := 2 - 4 \times 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032743 := 3 - 4 \times 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032744 := 4 - 4 \times 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032745 := 5 - 4 \times 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032746 := 6 - 4 \times 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032747 := 7 - 4 \times 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032748 := 8 - 4 \times 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032749 := 9 - 4 \times 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$034830 := 0 + \sqrt{3^8} \times 430$$

$$034831 := 1 + \sqrt{3^8} \times 430$$

$$034832 := 2 + \sqrt{3^8} \times 430$$

$$034833 := 3 + \sqrt{3^8} \times 430$$

$$034834 := 4 + \sqrt{3^8} \times 430$$

$$034835 := 5 + \sqrt{3^8} \times 430$$

$$034836 := 6 + \sqrt{3^8} \times 430$$

$$034837 := 7 + \sqrt{3^8} \times 430$$

$$034838 := 8 + \sqrt{3^8} \times 430$$

$$034839 := 9 + \sqrt{3^8} \times 430$$

$$038670 := 0 + (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 30$$

$$038671 := 1 + (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 30$$

$$038672 := 2 + (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 30$$

$$038673 := 3 + (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 30$$

$$038674 := 4 + (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 30$$

$$038675 := 5 + (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 30$$

$$038676 := 6 + (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 30$$

$$038677 := 7 + (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 30$$

$$038678 := 8 + (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 30$$

$$038679 := 9 + (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 30$$

$$279940 := 0 + \sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$279941 := 1 + \sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$279942 := 2 + \sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$279943 := 3 + \sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$279944 := 4 + \sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$279945 := 5 + \sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$279946 := 6 + \sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$279947 := 7 + \sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$279948 := 8 + \sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$279949 := 9 + \sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$466540 := 0 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6^6 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$466541 := 1 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6^6 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$466542 := 2 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6^6 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$466543 := 3 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6^6 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$466544 := 4 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6^6 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$466545 := 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6^6 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$466546 := 6 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6^6 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$466547 := 7 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6^6 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$466548 := 8 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6^6 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$466549 := 9 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6^6 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$589840 := 0 + \sqrt{4} \times (8 + 9 \times 8^5)$$

$$589841 := 1 + \sqrt{4} \times (8 + 9 \times 8^5)$$

$$589842 := 2 + \sqrt{4} \times (8 + 9 \times 8^5)$$

$$589843 := 3 + \sqrt{4} \times (8 + 9 \times 8^5)$$

$$589844 := 4 + \sqrt{4} \times (8 + 9 \times 8^5)$$

$$589845 := 5 + \sqrt{4} \times (8 + 9 \times 8^5)$$

$$589846 := 6 + \sqrt{4} \times (8 + 9 \times 8^5)$$

$$589847 := 7 + \sqrt{4} \times (8 + 9 \times 8^5)$$

$$589848 := 8 + \sqrt{4} \times (8 + 9 \times 8^5)$$

$$589849 := 9 + \sqrt{4} \times (8 + 9 \times 8^5)$$

$$0010240 := 0 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 100}$$

$$0010241 := 1 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 100}$$

$$0010242 := 2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 100}$$

$$0010243 := 3 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 100}$$

$$0010244 := 4 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 100}$$

$$0010245 := 5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 100}$$

$$0010246 := 6 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 100}$$

$$0010247 := 7 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 100}$$

$$0010248 := 8 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 100}$$

$$0010249 := 9 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 100}$$

$$0043940 := 0 + (4 + 9)^3 \times \sqrt{400}$$

$$0043941 := 1 + (4 + 9)^3 \times \sqrt{400}$$

$$0043942 := 2 + (4 + 9)^3 \times \sqrt{400}$$

$$0043943 := 3 + (4 + 9)^3 \times \sqrt{400}$$

$$0043944 := 4 + (4 + 9)^3 \times \sqrt{400}$$

$$0043945 := 5 + (4 + 9)^3 \times \sqrt{400}$$

$$0043946 := 6 + (4 + 9)^3 \times \sqrt{400}$$

$$0043947 := 7 + (4 + 9)^3 \times \sqrt{400}$$

$$0043948 := 8 + (4 + 9)^3 \times \sqrt{400}$$

$$0043949 := 9 + (4 + 9)^3 \times \sqrt{400}$$

$$0093750 := 0 + \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 900}$$

$$0093751 := 1 + \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 900}$$

$$0093752 := 2 + \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 900}$$

$$0093753 := 3 + \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 900}$$

$$0093754 := 4 + \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 900}$$

$$0093755 := 5 + \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 900}$$

$$0093756 := 6 + \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 900}$$

$$0093757 := 7 + \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 900}$$

$$0093758 := 8 + \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 900}$$

$$0093759 := 9 + \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 900}$$

$$0117670 := 0 + 7^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{-1 + 10}$$

$$0117671 := 1 + 7^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{-1 + 10}$$

$$0117672 := 2 + 7^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{-1 + 10}$$

$$0117673 := 3 + 7^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{-1 + 10}$$

$$0117674 := 4 + 7^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{-1 + 10}$$

$$0117675 := 5 + 7^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{-1 + 10}$$

$$0117676 := 6 + 7^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{-1 + 10}$$

$$0117677 := 7 + 7^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{-1 + 10}$$

$$0117678 := 8 + 7^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{-1 + 10}$$

$$0117679 := 9 + 7^6 + 7 \times \sqrt{-1 + 10}$$

$$0122880 := 0 + \sqrt{8^8} \times (-2 + \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

$$0122881 := 1 + \sqrt{8^8} \times (-2 + \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

$$0122882 := 2 + \sqrt{8^8} \times (-2 + \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

$$0122883 := 3 + \sqrt{8^8} \times (-2 + \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

$$0122884 := 4 + \sqrt{8^8} \times (-2 + \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

$$0122885 := 5 + \sqrt{8^8} \times (-2 + \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

$$0122886 := 6 + \sqrt{8^8} \times (-2 + \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

$$0122887 := 7 + \sqrt{8^8} \times (-2 + \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

$$0122888 := 8 + \sqrt{8^8} \times (-2 + \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

$$0122889 := 9 + \sqrt{8^8} \times (-2 + \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

$$0168750 := 0 + 5 \times \sqrt{(7+8)^6} \times 10$$

$$0168751 := 1 + 5 \times \sqrt{(7+8)^6} \times 10$$

$$0168752 := 2 + 5 \times \sqrt{(7+8)^6} \times 10$$

$$0168753 := 3 + 5 \times \sqrt{(7+8)^6} \times 10$$

$$0168754 := 4 + 5 \times \sqrt{(7+8)^6} \times 10$$

$$0168755 := 5 + 5 \times \sqrt{(7+8)^6} \times 10$$

$$0168756 := 6 + 5 \times \sqrt{(7+8)^6} \times 10$$

$$0168757 := 7 + 5 \times \sqrt{(7+8)^6} \times 10$$

$$0168758 := 8 + 5 \times \sqrt{(7+8)^6} \times 10$$

$$0168759 := 9 + 5 \times \sqrt{(7+8)^6} \times 10$$

$$0172530 := 0 + \sqrt{3^{5 \times 2}} \times 710$$

$$0172531 := 1 + \sqrt{3^{5 \times 2}} \times 710$$

$$0172532 := 2 + \sqrt{3^{5 \times 2}} \times 710$$

$$0172533 := 3 + \sqrt{3^{5 \times 2}} \times 710$$

$$0172534 := 4 + \sqrt{3^{5 \times 2}} \times 710$$

$$0172535 := 5 + \sqrt{3^{5 \times 2}} \times 710$$

$$0172536 := 6 + \sqrt{3^{5 \times 2}} \times 710$$

$$0172537 := 7 + \sqrt{3^{5 \times 2}} \times 710$$

$$0172538 := 8 + \sqrt{3^{5 \times 2}} \times 710$$

$$0172539 := 9 + \sqrt{3^{5 \times 2}} \times 710$$

$$0196560 := 0 + \sqrt{6^5 \times 6} \times 910$$

$$0196561 := 1 + \sqrt{6^5 \times 6} \times 910$$

$$0196562 := 2 + \sqrt{6^5 \times 6} \times 910$$

$$0196563 := 3 + \sqrt{6^5 \times 6} \times 910$$

$$0196564 := 4 + \sqrt{6^5 \times 6} \times 910$$

$$0196565 := 5 + \sqrt{6^5 \times 6} \times 910$$

$$0196566 := 6 + \sqrt{6^5 \times 6} \times 910$$

$$0196567 := 7 + \sqrt{6^5 \times 6} \times 910$$

$$0196568 := 8 + \sqrt{6^5 \times 6} \times 910$$

$$0196569 := 9 + \sqrt{6^5 \times 6} \times 910$$

$$0236220 := 0 + (2 + 2) \times (6 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236221 := 1 + (2 + 2) \times (6 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236222 := 2 + (2 + 2) \times (6 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236223 := 3 + (2 + 2) \times (6 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236224 := 4 + (2 + 2) \times (6 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236225 := 5 + (2 + 2) \times (6 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236226 := 6 + (2 + 2) \times (6 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236227 := 7 + (2 + 2) \times (6 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236228 := 8 + (2 + 2) \times (6 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236229 := 9 + (2 + 2) \times (6 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236340 := 0 + 4 \times (36 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236341 := 1 + 4 \times (36 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236342 := 2 + 4 \times (36 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236343 := 3 + 4 \times (36 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236344 := 4 + 4 \times (36 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236345 := 5 + 4 \times (36 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236346 := 6 + 4 \times (36 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236347 := 7 + 4 \times (36 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236348 := 8 + 4 \times (36 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0236349 := 9 + 4 \times (36 + \sqrt{3^{20}})$$

$$0276480 := 0 + \sqrt{8^4} \times 6 \times 720$$

$$0276481 := 1 + \sqrt{8^4} \times 6 \times 720$$

$$0276482 := 2 + \sqrt{8^4} \times 6 \times 720$$

$$0276483 := 3 + \sqrt{8^4} \times 6 \times 720$$

$$0276484 := 4 + \sqrt{8^4} \times 6 \times 720$$

$$0276485 := 5 + \sqrt{8^4} \times 6 \times 720$$

$$0276486 := 6 + \sqrt{8^4} \times 6 \times 720$$

$$0276487 := 7 + \sqrt{8^4} \times 6 \times 720$$

$$0276488 := 8 + \sqrt{8^4} \times 6 \times 720$$

$$0276489 := 9 + \sqrt{8^4} \times 6 \times 720$$

$$0295250 := 0 + 5 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9^{20}}}$$

$$0295251 := 1 + 5 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9^{20}}}$$

$$0295252 := 2 + 5 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9^{20}}}$$

$$0295253 := 3 + 5 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9^{20}}}$$

$$0295254 := 4 + 5 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9^{20}}}$$

$$0295255 := 5 + 5 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9^{20}}}$$

$$0295256 := 6 + 5 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9^{20}}}$$

$$0295257 := 7 + 5 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9^{20}}}$$

$$0295258 := 8 + 5 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9^{20}}}$$

$$0295259 := 9 + 5 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9^{20}}}$$

$$0295270 := 0 + (7 - 2) \times (5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{20}}})$$

$$0295271 := 1 + (7 - 2) \times (5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{20}}})$$

$$0295272 := 2 + (7 - 2) \times (5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{20}}})$$

$$0295273 := 3 + (7 - 2) \times (5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{20}}})$$

$$0295274 := 4 + (7 - 2) \times \left(5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{920}} \right)$$

$$0295275 := 5 + (7 - 2) \times \left(5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{920}} \right)$$

$$0295276 := 6 + (7 - 2) \times \left(5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{920}} \right)$$

$$0295277 := 7 + (7 - 2) \times \left(5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{920}} \right)$$

$$0295278 := 8 + (7 - 2) \times \left(5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{920}} \right)$$

$$0295279 := 9 + (7 - 2) \times \left(5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{920}} \right)$$

$$0337920 := 0 + 2^{\sqrt{9}+7} \times 330$$

$$0337921 := 1 + 2^{\sqrt{9}+7} \times 330$$

$$0337922 := 2 + 2^{\sqrt{9}+7} \times 330$$

$$0337923 := 3 + 2^{\sqrt{9}+7} \times 330$$

$$0337924 := 4 + 2^{\sqrt{9}+7} \times 330$$

$$0337925 := 5 + 2^{\sqrt{9}+7} \times 330$$

$$0337926 := 6 + 2^{\sqrt{9}+7} \times 330$$

$$0337927 := 7 + 2^{\sqrt{9}+7} \times 330$$

$$0337928 := 8 + 2^{\sqrt{9}+7} \times 330$$

$$0337929 := 9 + 2^{\sqrt{9}+7} \times 330$$

$$0349860 := 0 + \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times 9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 30$$

$$0349861 := 1 + \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times 9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 30$$

$$0349862 := 2 + \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times 9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 30$$

$$0349863 := 3 + \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times 9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 30$$

$$0349864 := 4 + \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times 9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 30$$

$$0349865 := 5 + \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times 9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 30$$

$$0349866 := 6 + \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times 9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 30$$

$$0349867 := 7 + \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times 9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 30$$

$$0349868 := 8 + \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times 9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 30$$

$$0349869 := 9 + \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times 9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 30$$

$$0349920 := 0 + (2 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \times 30$$

$$0349921 := 1 + (2 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \times 30$$

$$0349922 := 2 + (2 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \times 30$$

$$0349923 := 3 + (2 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \times 30$$

$$0349924 := 4 + (2 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \times 30$$

$$0349925 := 5 + (2 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \times 30$$

$$0349926 := 6 + (2 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \times 30$$

$$0349927 := 7 + (2 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \times 30$$

$$0349928 := 8 + (2 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \times 30$$

$$0349929 := 9 + (2 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \times 30$$

$$0368640 := 0 + 4 \times 6 \times \sqrt{8^6} \times 30$$

$$0368641 := 1 + 4 \times 6 \times \sqrt{8^6} \times 30$$

$$0368642 := 2 + 4 \times 6 \times \sqrt{8^6} \times 30$$

$$0368643 := 3 + 4 \times 6 \times \sqrt{8^6} \times 30$$

$$0368644 := 4 + 4 \times 6 \times \sqrt{8^6} \times 30$$

$$0368645 := 5 + 4 \times 6 \times \sqrt{8^6} \times 30$$

$$0368646 := 6 + 4 \times 6 \times \sqrt{8^6} \times 30$$

$$0368647 := 7 + 4 \times 6 \times \sqrt{8^6} \times 30$$

$$0368648 := 8 + 4 \times 6 \times \sqrt{8^6} \times 30$$

$$0368649 := 9 + 4 \times 6 \times \sqrt{8^6} \times 30$$

$$0491640 := 0 + (4^6 + 1) \times \sqrt{9} \times 40$$

$$0491641 := 1 + (4^6 + 1) \times \sqrt{9} \times 40$$

$$0491642 := 2 + (4^6 + 1) \times \sqrt{9} \times 40$$

$$0491643 := 3 + (4^6 + 1) \times \sqrt{9} \times 40$$

$$0491644 := 4 + (4^6 + 1) \times \sqrt{9} \times 40$$

$$0491645 := 5 + (4^6 + 1) \times \sqrt{9} \times 40$$

$$0491646 := 6 + (4^6 + 1) \times \sqrt{9} \times 40$$

$$0491647 := 7 + (4^6 + 1) \times \sqrt{9} \times 40$$

$$0491648 := 8 + (4^6 + 1) \times \sqrt{9} \times 40$$

$$0491649 := 9 + (4^6 + 1) \times \sqrt{9} \times 40$$

$$0648960 := 0 + \sqrt{(6 + 98)^4} \times 60$$

$$0648961 := 1 + \sqrt{(6 + 98)^4} \times 60$$

$$0648962 := 2 + \sqrt{(6 + 98)^4} \times 60$$

$$0648963 := 3 + \sqrt{(6 + 98)^4} \times 60$$

$$0648964 := 4 + \sqrt{(6 + 98)^4} \times 60$$

$$0648965 := 5 + \sqrt{(6 + 98)^4} \times 60$$

$$0648966 := 6 + \sqrt{(6 + 98)^4} \times 60$$

$$0648967 := 7 + \sqrt{(6 + 98)^4} \times 60$$

$$0648968 := 8 + \sqrt{(6 + 98)^4} \times 60$$

$$0648969 := 9 + \sqrt{(6 + 98)^4} \times 60$$

$$0699840 := 0 + \sqrt{4} \times 8 \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times 60$$

$$0699841 := 1 + \sqrt{4} \times 8 \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times 60$$

$$0699842 := 2 + \sqrt{4} \times 8 \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times 60$$

$$0699843 := 3 + \sqrt{4} \times 8 \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times 60$$

$$0699844 := 4 + \sqrt{4} \times 8 \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times 60$$

$$0699845 := 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 8 \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times 60$$

$$0699846 := 6 + \sqrt{4} \times 8 \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times 60$$

$$0699847 := 7 + \sqrt{4} \times 8 \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times 60$$

$$0699848 := 8 + \sqrt{4} \times 8 \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times 60$$

$$0699849 := 9 + \sqrt{4} \times 8 \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times 60$$

$$0999910 := 0 + (1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 90$$

$$0999911 := 1 + (1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 90$$

$$0999912 := 2 + (1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 90$$

$$0999913 := 3 + (1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 90$$

$$0999914 := 4 + (1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 90$$

$$0999915 := 5 + (1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 90$$

$$0999916 := 6 + (1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 90$$

$$0999917 := 7 + (1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 90$$

$$0999918 := 8 + (1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 90$$

$$0999919 := 9 + (1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 90$$

$$1166450 := 0 + \sqrt{5^4} \times (6^6 + 1 + 1)$$

$$1166451 := 1 + \sqrt{5^4} \times (6^6 + 1 + 1)$$

$$1166452 := 2 + \sqrt{5^4} \times (6^6 + 1 + 1)$$

$$1166453 := 3 + \sqrt{5^4} \times (6^6 + 1 + 1)$$

$$1166454 := 4 + \sqrt{5^4} \times (6^6 + 1 + 1)$$

$$1166455 := 5 + \sqrt{5^4} \times (6^6 + 1 + 1)$$

$$1166456 := 6 + \sqrt{5^4} \times (6^6 + 1 + 1)$$

$$1166457 := 7 + \sqrt{5^4} \times (6^6 + 1 + 1)$$

$$1166458 := 8 + \sqrt{5^4} \times (6^6 + 1 + 1)$$

$$1166459 := 9 + \sqrt{5^4} \times (6^6 + 1 + 1)$$

$$1632960 := 0 + 6^{\sqrt{9} \times 2} \times (36 - 1)$$

$$1632961 := 1 + 6^{\sqrt{9} \times 2} \times (36 - 1)$$

$$1632962 := 2 + 6^{\sqrt{9} \times 2} \times (36 - 1)$$

$$1632963 := 3 + 6^{\sqrt{9} \times 2} \times (36 - 1)$$

$$1632964 := 4 + 6^{\sqrt{9} \times 2} \times (36 - 1)$$

$$1632965 := 5 + 6^{\sqrt{9} \times 2} \times (36 - 1)$$

$$1632966 := 6 + 6^{\sqrt{9} \times 2} \times (36 - 1)$$

$$1632967 := 7 + 6^{\sqrt{9} \times 2} \times (36 - 1)$$

$$1632968 := 8 + 6^{\sqrt{9} \times 2} \times (36 - 1)$$

$$1632969 := 9 + 6^{\sqrt{9} \times 2} \times (36 - 1)$$

$$1679860 := 0 + 6^8 + \sqrt{9+7} \times 61$$

$$1679861 := 1 + 6^8 + \sqrt{9+7} \times 61$$

$$1679862 := 2 + 6^8 + \sqrt{9+7} \times 61$$

$$1679863 := 3 + 6^8 + \sqrt{9+7} \times 61$$

$$1679864 := 4 + 6^8 + \sqrt{9+7} \times 61$$

$$1679865 := 5 + 6^8 + \sqrt{9+7} \times 61$$

$$1679866 := 6 + 6^8 + \sqrt{9+7} \times 61$$

$$1679867 := 7 + 6^8 + \sqrt{9+7} \times 61$$

$$1679868 := 8 + 6^8 + \sqrt{9+7} \times 61$$

$$1679869 := 9 + 6^8 + \sqrt{9+7} \times 61$$

$$1718750 := 0 + 5^7 \times (\sqrt{8+1} \times 7 + 1)$$

$$1718751 := 1 + 5^7 \times (\sqrt{8+1} \times 7 + 1)$$

$$1718752 := 2 + 5^7 \times (\sqrt{8+1} \times 7 + 1)$$

$$1718753 := 3 + 5^7 \times (\sqrt{8+1} \times 7 + 1)$$

$$1718754 := 4 + 5^7 \times (\sqrt{8+1} \times 7 + 1)$$

$$1718755 := 5 + 5^7 \times (\sqrt{8+1} \times 7 + 1)$$

$$1718756 := 6 + 5^7 \times (\sqrt{8+1} \times 7 + 1)$$

$$1718757 := 7 + 5^7 \times (\sqrt{8+1} \times 7 + 1)$$

$$1718758 := 8 + 5^7 \times (\sqrt{8+1} \times 7 + 1)$$

$$1718759 := 9 + 5^7 \times (\sqrt{8+1} \times 7 + 1)$$

$$1771490 := 0 + (9 + \sqrt{4})^{-1+7} - 71$$

$$1771491 := 1 + (9 + \sqrt{4})^{-1+7} - 71$$

$$1771492 := 2 + (9 + \sqrt{4})^{-1+7} - 71$$

$$1771493 := 3 + (9 + \sqrt{4})^{-1+7} - 71$$

$$1771494 := 4 + (9 + \sqrt{4})^{-1+7} - 71$$

$$1771495 := 5 + (9 + \sqrt{4})^{-1+7} - 71$$

$$1771496 := 6 + (9 + \sqrt{4})^{-1+7} - 71$$

$$1771497 := 7 + (9 + \sqrt{4})^{-1+7} - 71$$

$$1771498 := 8 + (9 + \sqrt{4})^{-1+7} - 71$$

$$1771549 := 9 + (9 + \sqrt{4})^{-1+7} - 71$$

$$1944790 := 0 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1944791 := 1 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1944792 := 2 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1944793 := 3 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1944794 := 4 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1944795 := 5 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1944796 := 6 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1944797 := 7 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1944798 := 8 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1944799 := 9 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 + 1)$$

$$1953190 := 0 + (\sqrt{9} + 1)^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953191 := 1 + (\sqrt{9} + 1)^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953192 := 2 + (\sqrt{9} + 1)^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953193 := 3 + (\sqrt{9} + 1)^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953194 := 4 + (\sqrt{9} + 1)^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953195 := 5 + (\sqrt{9} + 1)^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953196 := 6 + (\sqrt{9} + 1)^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953197 := 7 + (\sqrt{9} + 1)^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953198 := 8 + (\sqrt{9} + 1)^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953199 := 9 + (\sqrt{9} + 1)^3 + 5^9 + 1$$

$$1953250 := 0 + \sqrt{5^{2 \times 3}} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953251 := 1 + \sqrt{5^{2 \times 3}} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953252 := 2 + \sqrt{5^{2 \times 3}} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953253 := 3 + \sqrt{5^{2 \times 3}} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953254 := 4 + \sqrt{5^{2 \times 3}} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953255 := 5 + \sqrt{5^{2 \times 3}} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953256 := 6 + \sqrt{5^{2 \times 3}} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953257 := 7 + \sqrt{5^{2 \times 3}} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953258 := 8 + \sqrt{5^{2 \times 3}} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$1953259 := 9 + \sqrt{5^{2 \times 3}} + 5^9 \times 1$$

$$2097150 := 0 + \sqrt{(5-1)^{7 \times \sqrt{9}}} - 02$$

$$2097151 := 1 + \sqrt{(5-1)^{7 \times \sqrt{9}}} - 02$$

$$2097152 := 2 + \sqrt{(5-1)^{7 \times \sqrt{9}}} - 02$$

$$2097153 := 3 + \sqrt{(5-1)^{7 \times \sqrt{9}}} - 02$$

$$2097154 := 4 + \sqrt{(5-1)^{7 \times \sqrt{9}}} - 02$$

$$2097155 := 5 + \sqrt{(5-1)^{7 \times \sqrt{9}}} - 02$$

$$2097156 := 6 + \sqrt{(5-1)^{7 \times \sqrt{9}}} - 02$$

$$2097157 := 7 + \sqrt{(5-1)^{7 \times \sqrt{9}}} - 02$$

$$2097158 := 8 + \sqrt{(5-1)^{7 \times \sqrt{9}}} - 02$$

$$2097159 := 9 + \sqrt{(5-1)^{7 \times \sqrt{9}}} - 02$$

$$2239490 := 0 + 9 \times (4 \times \sqrt{9})^{3+2} + 2$$

$$2239491 := 1 + 9 \times (4 \times \sqrt{9})^{3+2} + 2$$

$$2239492 := 2 + 9 \times (4 \times \sqrt{9})^{3+2} + 2$$

$$2239493 := 3 + 9 \times (4 \times \sqrt{9})^{3+2} + 2$$

$$2239494 := 4 + 9 \times (4 \times \sqrt{9})^{3+2} + 2$$

$$2239495 := 5 + 9 \times (4 \times \sqrt{9})^{3+2} + 2$$

$$2239496 := 6 + 9 \times (4 \times \sqrt{9})^{3+2} + 2$$

$$2239497 := 7 + 9 \times (4 \times \sqrt{9})^{3+2} + 2$$

$$2239498 := 8 + 9 \times (4 \times \sqrt{9})^{3+2} + 2$$

$$2239499 := 9 + 9 \times (4 \times \sqrt{9})^{3+2} + 2$$

$$2785280 := 0 + \sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}} \times (87 - 2)$$

$$2785281 := 1 + \sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}} \times (87 - 2)$$

$$2785282 := 2 + \sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}} \times (87 - 2)$$

$$2785283 := 3 + \sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}} \times (87 - 2)$$

$$2785284 := 4 + \sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}} \times (87 - 2)$$

$$2785285 := 5 + \sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}} \times (87 - 2)$$

$$2785286 := 6 + \sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}} \times (87 - 2)$$

$$2785287 := 7 + \sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}} \times (87 - 2)$$

$$2785288 := 8 + \sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}} \times (87 - 2)$$

$$2785289 := 9 + \sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}} \times (87 - 2)$$

$$2829751 := 0 + (5 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (2 + 8^2)$$

$$2829751 := 1 + (5 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (2 + 8^2)$$

$$2829752 := 2 + (5 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (2 + 8^2)$$

$$2829753 := 3 + (5 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (2 + 8^2)$$

$$2829754 := 4 + (5 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (2 + 8^2)$$

$$2829755 := 5 + (5 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (2 + 8^2)$$

$$2829756 := 6 + (5 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (2 + 8^2)$$

$$2829757 := 7 + (5 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (2 + 8^2)$$

$$2829758 := 8 + (5 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (2 + 8^2)$$

$$2829759 := 9 + (5 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (2 + 8^2)$$

$$2994750 := 0 + (5 \times (7 + 4))^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \times 2$$

$$2994751 := 1 + (5 \times (7 + 4))^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \times 2$$

$$2994752 := 2 + (5 \times (7 + 4))^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \times 2$$

$$2994753 := 3 + (5 \times (7 + 4))^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \times 2$$

$$2994754 := 4 + (5 \times (7 + 4))^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \times 2$$

$$2994755 := 5 + (5 \times (7 + 4))^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \times 2$$

$$2994756 := 6 + (5 \times (7 + 4))^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \times 2$$

$$2994757 := 7 + (5 \times (7 + 4))^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \times 2$$

$$2994758 := 8 + (5 \times (7 + 4))^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \times 2$$

$$2994759 := 9 + (5 \times (7 + 4))^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9 \times 2$$

$$3529470 := 0 + 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \times 2 \times 5 \times 3$$

$$3529471 := 1 + 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \times 2 \times 5 \times 3$$

$$3529472 := 2 + 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \times 2 \times 5 \times 3$$

$$3529473 := 3 + 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \times 2 \times 5 \times 3$$

$$3529474 := 4 + 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \times 2 \times 5 \times 3$$

$$3529475 := 5 + 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \times 2 \times 5 \times 3$$

$$3529476 := 6 + 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \times 2 \times 5 \times 3$$

$$3529477 := 7 + 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \times 2 \times 5 \times 3$$

$$3529478 := 8 + 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \times 2 \times 5 \times 3$$

$$3529479 := 9 + 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \times 2 \times 5 \times 3$$

$$3869890 := 0 - \sqrt{9} + (89 + 68)^3$$

$$3869891 := 1 - \sqrt{9} + (89 + 68)^3$$

$$3869892 := 2 - \sqrt{9} + (89 + 68)^3$$

$$3869893 := 3 - \sqrt{9} + (89 + 68)^3$$

$$3869894 := 4 - \sqrt{9} + (89 + 68)^3$$

$$3869895 := 5 - \sqrt{9} + (89 + 68)^3$$

$$3869896 := 6 - \sqrt{9} + (89 + 68)^3$$

$$3869897 := 7 - \sqrt{9} + (89 + 68)^3$$

$$3869898 := 8 - \sqrt{9} + (89 + 68)^3$$

$$3869899 := 9 - \sqrt{9} + (89 + 68)^3$$

$$4194320 := 0 + 2^3 \times (4^9 + 1) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4194321 := 1 + 2^3 \times (4^9 + 1) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4194322 := 2 + 2^3 \times (4^9 + 1) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4194323 := 3 + 2^3 \times (4^9 + 1) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4194324 := 4 + 2^3 \times (4^9 + 1) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4194325 := 5 + 2^3 \times (4^9 + 1) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4194326 := 6 + 2^3 \times (4^9 + 1) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4194327 := 7 + 2^3 \times (4^9 + 1) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4194328 := 8 + 2^3 \times (4^9 + 1) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4194329 := 9 + 2^3 \times (4^9 + 1) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4539620 := 0 + (2^6 - \sqrt{9})^3 \times 5 \times 4$$

$$4539621 := 1 + (2^6 - \sqrt{9})^3 \times 5 \times 4$$

$$4539622 := 2 + (2^6 - \sqrt{9})^3 \times 5 \times 4$$

$$4539623 := 3 + (2^6 - \sqrt{9})^3 \times 5 \times 4$$

$$4539624 := 4 + (2^6 - \sqrt{9})^3 \times 5 \times 4$$

$$4539625 := 5 + (2^6 - \sqrt{9})^3 \times 5 \times 4$$

$$4539626 := 6 + (2^6 - \sqrt{9})^3 \times 5 \times 4$$

$$4539627 := 7 + (2^6 - \sqrt{9})^3 \times 5 \times 4$$

$$4539628 := 8 + (2^6 - \sqrt{9})^3 \times 5 \times 4$$

$$4539629 := 9 + (2^6 - \sqrt{9})^3 \times 5 \times 4$$

$$4556250 := 0 + (5 - 2)^6 \times 5^5 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4556251 := 1 + (5 - 2)^6 \times 5^5 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4556252 := 2 + (5 - 2)^6 \times 5^5 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4556253 := 3 + (5 - 2)^6 \times 5^5 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4556254 := 4 + (5 - 2)^6 \times 5^5 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4556255 := 5 + (5 - 2)^6 \times 5^5 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4556256 := 6 + (5 - 2)^6 \times 5^5 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4556257 := 7 + (5 - 2)^6 \times 5^5 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4556258 := 8 + (5 - 2)^6 \times 5^5 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4556259 := 9 + (5 - 2)^6 \times 5^5 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4587520 := \sqrt{0^2} + 5 \times 7 \times 8^5 \times 4$$

$$4587521 := \sqrt{1^2} + 5 \times 7 \times 8^5 \times 4$$

$$4587522 := \sqrt{2^2} + 5 \times 7 \times 8^5 \times 4$$

$$4587523 := \sqrt{3^2} + 5 \times 7 \times 8^5 \times 4$$

$$4587524 := \sqrt{4^2} + 5 \times 7 \times 8^5 \times 4$$

$$4587525 := \sqrt{5^2} + 5 \times 7 \times 8^5 \times 4$$

$$4587526 := \sqrt{6^2} + 5 \times 7 \times 8^5 \times 4$$

$$4587527 := \sqrt{7^2} + 5 \times 7 \times 8^5 \times 4$$

$$4587528 := \sqrt{8^2} + 5 \times 7 \times 8^5 \times 4$$

$$4587529 := \sqrt{9^2} + 5 \times 7 \times 8^5 \times 4$$

$$4787340 := 0 - 4 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4787341 := 1 - 4 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4787342 := 2 - 4 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4787343 := 3 - 4 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4787344 := 4 - 4 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4787345 := 5 - 4 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4787346 := 6 - 4 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4787347 := 7 - 4 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4787348 := 8 - 4 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4787349 := 9 - 4 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4920750 := 0 + (-5 + 70 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4920751 := 1 + (-5 + 70 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4920752 := 2 + (-5 + 70 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4920753 := 3 + (-5 + 70 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4920754 := 4 + (-5 + 70 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4920755 := 5 + (-5 + 70 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4920756 := 6 + (-5 + 70 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4920757 := 7 + (-5 + 70 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4920758 := 8 + (-5 + 70 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4920759 := 9 + (-5 + 70 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4977450 := 0 + (5 + 4)^7 + (7 \times \sqrt{9})^4$$

$$4977451 := 1 + (5 + 4)^7 + (7 \times \sqrt{9})^4$$

$$4977452 := 2 + (5 + 4)^7 + (7 \times \sqrt{9})^4$$

$$4977453 := 3 + (5 + 4)^7 + (7 \times \sqrt{9})^4$$

$$4977454 := 4 + (5 + 4)^7 + (7 \times \sqrt{9})^4$$

$$4977455 := 5 + (5 + 4)^7 + (7 \times \sqrt{9})^4$$

$$4977456 := 6 + (5 + 4)^7 + (7 \times \sqrt{9})^4$$

$$4977457 := 7 + (5 + 4)^7 + (7 \times \sqrt{9})^4$$

$$4977458 := 8 + (5 + 4)^7 + (7 \times \sqrt{9})^4$$

$$4977459 := 9 + (5 + 4)^7 + (7 \times \sqrt{9})^4$$

$$5242890 := 0 + (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (2 + 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242891 := 1 + (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (2 + 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242892 := 2 + (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (2 + 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242893 := 3 + (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (2 + 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242894 := 4 + (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (2 + 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242895 := 5 + (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (2 + 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242896 := 6 + (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (2 + 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242897 := 7 + (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (2 + 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242898 := 8 + (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (2 + 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5242899 := 9 + (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (2 + 4^{2 \times 5})$$

$$5468750 := 0 + 5^7 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(8 + 6)^4}} \times 5$$

$$5468751 := 1 + 5^7 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(8 + 6)^4}} \times 5$$

$$5468752 := 2 + 5^7 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(8 + 6)^4}} \times 5$$

$$5468753 := 3 + 5^7 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(8 + 6)^4}} \times 5$$

$$5468754 := 4 + 5^7 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(8 + 6)^4}} \times 5$$

$$5468755 := 5 + 5^7 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(8 + 6)^4}} \times 5$$

$$5468756 := 6 + 5^7 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(8 + 6)^4}} \times 5$$

$$5468757 := 7 + 5^7 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(8 + 6)^4}} \times 5$$

$$5468758 := 8 + 5^7 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(8 + 6)^4}} \times 5$$

$$5468759 := 9 + 5^7 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(8 + 6)^4}} \times 5$$

$$5598660 := 0 + (-6 + 6^8 / \sqrt{9}) \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598661 := 1 + (-6 + 6^8 / \sqrt{9}) \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598662 := 2 + (-6 + 6^8 / \sqrt{9}) \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598663 := 3 + (-6 + 6^8 / \sqrt{9}) \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598664 := 4 + (-6 + 6^8 / \sqrt{9}) \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598665 := 5 + (-6 + 6^8 / \sqrt{9}) \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598666 := 6 + (-6 + 6^8 / \sqrt{9}) \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598667 := 7 + (-6 + 6^8 / \sqrt{9}) \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598668 := 8 + (-6 + 6^8 / \sqrt{9}) \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598669 := 9 + (-6 + 6^8 / \sqrt{9}) \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598690 := 0 + (-9 + 6^8) / \sqrt{9} \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598691 := 1 + (-9 + 6^8) / \sqrt{9} \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598692 := 2 + (-9 + 6^8) / \sqrt{9} \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598693 := 3 + (-9 + 6^8) / \sqrt{9} \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598694 := 4 + (-9 + 6^8) / \sqrt{9} \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598695 := 5 + (-9 + 6^8) / \sqrt{9} \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598696 := 6 + (-9 + 6^8) / \sqrt{9} \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598697 := 7 + (-9 + 6^8) / \sqrt{9} \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598698 := 8 + (-9 + 6^8) / \sqrt{9} \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5598699 := 9 + (-9 + 6^8) / \sqrt{9} \times (5 + 5)$$

$$5664330 := 0 + \sqrt{3^{3 \times 4}} \times (-6 + 6^5)$$

$$5664331 := 1 + \sqrt{3^{3 \times 4}} \times (-6 + 6^5)$$

$$5664332 := 2 + \sqrt{3^{3 \times 4}} \times (-6 + 6^5)$$

$$5664333 := 3 + \sqrt{3^{3 \times 4}} \times (-6 + 6^5)$$

$$5664334 := 4 + \sqrt{3^{3 \times 4}} \times (-6 + 6^5)$$

$$5664335 := 5 + \sqrt{3^{3 \times 4}} \times (-6 + 6^5)$$

$$5664336 := 6 + \sqrt{3^{3 \times 4}} \times (-6 + 6^5)$$

$$5664337 := 7 + \sqrt{3^{3 \times 4}} \times (-6 + 6^5)$$

$$5664338 := 8 + \sqrt{3^{3 \times 4}} \times (-6 + 6^5)$$

$$5664339 := 9 + \sqrt{3^{3 \times 4}} \times (-6 + 6^5)$$

$$5764760 := 0 - 6 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764761 := 1 - 6 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764762 := 2 - 6 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764763 := 3 - 6 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764764 := 4 - 6 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764765 := 5 - 6 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764766 := 6 - 6 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764767 := 7 - 6 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764768 := 8 - 6 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764769 := 9 - 6 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5859250 := 0 + (-5^2 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859251 := 1 + (-5^2 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859252 := 2 + (-5^2 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859253 := 3 + (-5^2 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859254 := 4 + (-5^2 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859255 := 5 + (-5^2 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859256 := 6 + (-5^2 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859257 := 7 + (-5^2 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859258 := 8 + (-5^2 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859259 := 9 + (-5^2 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859310 := 0 + (-13 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859311 := 1 + (-13 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859312 := 2 + (-13 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859313 := 3 + (-13 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859314 := 4 + (-13 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859315 := 5 + (-13 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859316 := 6 + (-13 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859317 := 7 + (-13 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859318 := 8 + (-13 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859319 := 9 + (-13 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859320 := 0 + (-2 + 3 \times (-\sqrt{9} + 5^8)) \times 5$$

$$5859321 := 1 + (-2 + 3 \times (-\sqrt{9} + 5^8)) \times 5$$

$$5859322 := 2 + (-2 + 3 \times (-\sqrt{9} + 5^8)) \times 5$$

$$5859323 := 3 + (-2 + 3 \times (-\sqrt{9} + 5^8)) \times 5$$

$$5859324 := 4 + (-2 + 3 \times (-\sqrt{9} + 5^8)) \times 5$$

$$5859325 := 5 + (-2 + 3 \times (-\sqrt{9} + 5^8)) \times 5$$

$$5859326 := 6 + (-2 + 3 \times (-\sqrt{9} + 5^8)) \times 5$$

$$5859327 := 7 + (-2 + 3 \times (-\sqrt{9} + 5^8)) \times 5$$

$$5859328 := 8 + \left(-2 + 3 \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^8\right)\right) \times 5$$
$$5859329 := 9 + \left(-2 + 3 \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^8\right)\right) \times 5$$

$$5859330 := 0 + \sqrt{3 \times 3} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859331 := 1 + \sqrt{3 \times 3} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859332 := 2 + \sqrt{3 \times 3} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859333 := 3 + \sqrt{3 \times 3} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859334 := 4 + \sqrt{3 \times 3} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859335 := 5 + \sqrt{3 \times 3} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859336 := 6 + \sqrt{3 \times 3} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859337 := 7 + \sqrt{3 \times 3} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859338 := 8 + \sqrt{3 \times 3} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859339 := 9 + \sqrt{3 \times 3} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^8\right) \times 5$$

$$5859340 := 0 + \left(-4 - 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859341 := 1 + \left(-4 - 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859342 := 2 + \left(-4 - 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859343 := 3 + \left(-4 - 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859344 := 4 + \left(-4 - 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859345 := 5 + \left(-4 - 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859346 := 6 + \left(-4 - 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859347 := 7 + \left(-4 - 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859348 := 8 + \left(-4 - 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859349 := 9 + \left(-4 - 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$

$$5859350 := 0 + 5 \times \left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}} \times 5^8 - 5\right)$$
$$5859351 := 1 + 5 \times \left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}} \times 5^8 - 5\right)$$
$$5859352 := 2 + 5 \times \left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}} \times 5^8 - 5\right)$$
$$5859353 := 3 + 5 \times \left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}} \times 5^8 - 5\right)$$
$$5859354 := 4 + 5 \times \left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}} \times 5^8 - 5\right)$$
$$5859355 := 5 + 5 \times \left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}} \times 5^8 - 5\right)$$
$$5859356 := 6 + 5 \times \left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}} \times 5^8 - 5\right)$$
$$5859357 := 7 + 5 \times \left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}} \times 5^8 - 5\right)$$
$$5859358 := 8 + 5 \times \left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}} \times 5^8 - 5\right)$$
$$5859359 := 9 + 5 \times \left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}} \times 5^8 - 5\right)$$

$$5859360 := 0 + \left(-6 + 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859361 := 1 + \left(-6 + 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859362 := 2 + \left(-6 + 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859363 := 3 + \left(-6 + 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859364 := 4 + \left(-6 + 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859365 := 5 + \left(-6 + 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859366 := 6 + \left(-6 + 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859367 := 7 + \left(-6 + 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859368 := 8 + \left(-6 + 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$
$$5859369 := 9 + \left(-6 + 3 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8\right) \times 5$$

$$5859390 := 0 + \sqrt{9} \times (3/\sqrt{9} + 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859391 := 1 + \sqrt{9} \times (3/\sqrt{9} + 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859392 := 2 + \sqrt{9} \times (3/\sqrt{9} + 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859393 := 3 + \sqrt{9} \times (3/\sqrt{9} + 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859394 := 4 + \sqrt{9} \times (3/\sqrt{9} + 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859395 := 5 + \sqrt{9} \times (3/\sqrt{9} + 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859396 := 6 + \sqrt{9} \times (3/\sqrt{9} + 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859397 := 7 + \sqrt{9} \times (3/\sqrt{9} + 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859398 := 8 + \sqrt{9} \times (3/\sqrt{9} + 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859399 := 9 + \sqrt{9} \times (3/\sqrt{9} + 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859450 := 0 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times \sqrt{9} \times (5^8 + 5)$$

$$5859451 := 1 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times \sqrt{9} \times (5^8 + 5)$$

$$5859452 := 2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times \sqrt{9} \times (5^8 + 5)$$

$$5859453 := 3 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times \sqrt{9} \times (5^8 + 5)$$

$$5859454 := 4 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times \sqrt{9} \times (5^8 + 5)$$

$$5859455 := 5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times \sqrt{9} \times (5^8 + 5)$$

$$5859456 := 6 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times \sqrt{9} \times (5^8 + 5)$$

$$5859457 := 7 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times \sqrt{9} \times (5^8 + 5)$$

$$5859458 := 8 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times \sqrt{9} \times (5^8 + 5)$$

$$5859459 := 9 + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times \sqrt{9} \times (5^8 + 5)$$

$$6718440 := 0 + 4 \times \left((-\sqrt{4} + 8)^{1+7} - 6 \right)$$

$$6718441 := 1 + 4 \times \left((-\sqrt{4} + 8)^{1+7} - 6 \right)$$

$$6718442 := 2 + 4 \times \left((-\sqrt{4} + 8)^{1+7} - 6 \right)$$

$$6718443 := 3 + 4 \times \left((-\sqrt{4} + 8)^{1+7} - 6 \right)$$

$$6718444 := 4 + 4 \times \left((-\sqrt{4} + 8)^{1+7} - 6 \right)$$

$$6718445 := 5 + 4 \times \left((-\sqrt{4} + 8)^{1+7} - 6 \right)$$

$$6718446 := 6 + 4 \times \left((-\sqrt{4} + 8)^{1+7} - 6 \right)$$

$$6718447 := 7 + 4 \times \left((-\sqrt{4} + 8)^{1+7} - 6 \right)$$

$$6718448 := 8 + 4 \times \left((-\sqrt{4} + 8)^{1+7} - 6 \right)$$

$$6718449 := 9 + 4 \times \left((-\sqrt{4} + 8)^{1+7} - 6 \right)$$

$$6945750 := 0 + (5 \times 7 \times \sqrt{5+4})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6$$

$$6945751 := 1 + (5 \times 7 \times \sqrt{5+4})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6$$

$$6945752 := 2 + (5 \times 7 \times \sqrt{5+4})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6$$

$$6945753 := 3 + (5 \times 7 \times \sqrt{5+4})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6$$

$$6945754 := 4 + (5 \times 7 \times \sqrt{5+4})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6$$

$$6945755 := 5 + (5 \times 7 \times \sqrt{5+4})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6$$

$$6945756 := 6 + (5 \times 7 \times \sqrt{5+4})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6$$

$$6945757 := 7 + (5 \times 7 \times \sqrt{5+4})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6$$

$$6945758 := 8 + (5 \times 7 \times \sqrt{5+4})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6$$

$$6945759 := 9 + (5 \times 7 \times \sqrt{5+4})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6$$

$$7962680 := 0 + 8 \times \left((6 \times 2)^6 / \sqrt{9} + 7 \right)$$

$$7962681 := 1 + 8 \times \left((6 \times 2)^6 / \sqrt{9} + 7 \right)$$

$$7962682 := 2 + 8 \times \left((6 \times 2)^6 / \sqrt{9} + 7 \right)$$

$$7962683 := 3 + 8 \times \left((6 \times 2)^6 / \sqrt{9} + 7 \right)$$

$$7962684 := 4 + 8 \times \left((6 \times 2)^6 / \sqrt{9} + 7 \right)$$

$$7962685 := 5 + 8 \times \left((6 \times 2)^6 / \sqrt{9} + 7 \right)$$

$$7962686 := 6 + 8 \times \left((6 \times 2)^6 / \sqrt{9} + 7 \right)$$

$$7962687 := 7 + 8 \times \left((6 \times 2)^6 / \sqrt{9} + 7 \right)$$

$$7962688 := 8 + 8 \times \left((6 \times 2)^6 / \sqrt{9} + 7 \right)$$

$$7962689 := 9 + 8 \times \left((6 \times 2)^6 / \sqrt{9} + 7 \right)$$

$$8388620 := 0 + 2 \times \left(6 + \sqrt{8 + 8^{3+8}} \right)$$

$$8388621 := 1 + 2 \times \left(6 + \sqrt{8 + 8^{3+8}} \right)$$

$$8388622 := 2 + 2 \times \left(6 + \sqrt{8 + 8^{3+8}} \right)$$

$$8388623 := 3 + 2 \times \left(6 + \sqrt{8 + 8^{3+8}} \right)$$

$$8388624 := 4 + 2 \times \left(6 + \sqrt{8 + 8^{3+8}} \right)$$

$$8388625 := 5 + 2 \times \left(6 + \sqrt{8 + 8^{3+8}} \right)$$

$$8388626 := 6 + 2 \times \left(6 + \sqrt{8 + 8^{3+8}} \right)$$

$$8388627 := 7 + 2 \times \left(6 + \sqrt{8 + 8^{3+8}} \right)$$

$$8388628 := 8 + 2 \times \left(6 + \sqrt{8 + 8^{3+8}} \right)$$

$$8388629 := 9 + 2 \times \left(6 + \sqrt{8 + 8^{3+8}} \right)$$

$$8398650 := 0 + 5 \times \left(6^8 + \sqrt{9} \times 38 \right)$$

$$8398651 := 1 + 5 \times \left(6^8 + \sqrt{9} \times 38 \right)$$

$$8398652 := 2 + 5 \times \left(6^8 + \sqrt{9} \times 38 \right)$$

$$8398653 := 3 + 5 \times \left(6^8 + \sqrt{9} \times 38 \right)$$

$$8398654 := 4 + 5 \times \left(6^8 + \sqrt{9} \times 38 \right)$$

$$8398655 := 5 + 5 \times \left(6^8 + \sqrt{9} \times 38 \right)$$

$$8398656 := 6 + 5 \times \left(6^8 + \sqrt{9} \times 38 \right)$$

$$8398657 := 7 + 5 \times \left(6^8 + \sqrt{9} \times 38 \right)$$

$$8398658 := 8 + 5 \times \left(6^8 + \sqrt{9} \times 38 \right)$$

$$8398659 := 9 + 5 \times \left(6^8 + \sqrt{9} \times 38 \right)$$

$$8593750 := 0 + \left(57/3 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5^8$$

$$8593751 := 1 + \left(57/3 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5^8$$

$$8593752 := 2 + \left(57/3 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5^8$$

$$8593753 := 3 + \left(57/3 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5^8$$

$$8593754 := 4 + \left(57/3 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5^8$$

$$8593755 := 5 + \left(57/3 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5^8$$

$$8593756 := 6 + \left(57/3 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5^8$$

$$8593757 := 7 + \left(57/3 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5^8$$

$$8593758 := 8 + \left(57/3 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5^8$$

$$8593759 := 9 + \left(57/3 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5^8$$

$$9586980 := 0 + \left(8^{\sqrt{9}+6} - 8 \right) / (5 + 9)$$

$$9586981 := 1 + \left(8^{\sqrt{9}+6} - 8 \right) / (5 + 9)$$

$$9586982 := 2 + \left(8^{\sqrt{9}+6} - 8 \right) / (5 + 9)$$

$$9586983 := 3 + \left(8^{\sqrt{9}+6} - 8 \right) / (5 + 9)$$

$$9586984 := 4 + \left(8^{\sqrt{9}+6} - 8 \right) / (5 + 9)$$

$$9586985 := 5 + \left(8^{\sqrt{9}+6} - 8 \right) / (5 + 9)$$

$$9586986 := 6 + \left(8^{\sqrt{9}+6} - 8 \right) / (5 + 9)$$

$$9586987 := 7 + (8^{\sqrt{9+6}} - 8) / (5 + 9)$$

$$9586988 := 8 + (8^{\sqrt{9+6}} - 8) / (5 + 9)$$

$$9586989 := 9 + (8^{\sqrt{9+6}} - 8) / (5 + 9)$$

$$9684480 := 0 - (8 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 6^9$$

$$9684481 := 1 - (8 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 6^9$$

$$9684482 := 2 - (8 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 6^9$$

$$9684483 := 3 - (8 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 6^9$$

$$9684484 := 4 - (8 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 6^9$$

$$9684485 := 5 - (8 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 6^9$$

$$9684486 := 6 - (8 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 6^9$$

$$9684487 := 7 - (8 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 6^9$$

$$9684488 := 8 - (8 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 6^9$$

$$9684489 := 9 - (8 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4^8 + 6^9$$

$$9797760 := 0 + 6^7 \times 7 \times \sqrt{9+7+9}$$

$$9797761 := 1 + 6^7 \times 7 \times \sqrt{9+7+9}$$

$$9797762 := 2 + 6^7 \times 7 \times \sqrt{9+7+9}$$

$$9797763 := 3 + 6^7 \times 7 \times \sqrt{9+7+9}$$

$$9797764 := 4 + 6^7 \times 7 \times \sqrt{9+7+9}$$

$$9797765 := 5 + 6^7 \times 7 \times \sqrt{9+7+9}$$

$$9797766 := 6 + 6^7 \times 7 \times \sqrt{9+7+9}$$

$$9797767 := 7 + 6^7 \times 7 \times \sqrt{9+7+9}$$

$$9797768 := 8 + 6^7 \times 7 \times \sqrt{9+7+9}$$

$$9797769 := 9 + 6^7 \times 7 \times \sqrt{9+7+9}$$

$$9843750 := 0 + 5^7 \times (34 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9843751 := 1 + 5^7 \times (34 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9843752 := 2 + 5^7 \times (34 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9843753 := 3 + 5^7 \times (34 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9843754 := 4 + 5^7 \times (34 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9843755 := 5 + 5^7 \times (34 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9843756 := 6 + 5^7 \times (34 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9843757 := 7 + 5^7 \times (34 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9843758 := 8 + 5^7 \times (34 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9843759 := 9 + 5^7 \times (34 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

3.2 Symmetric and Nonconsecutive

$$00164 := \sqrt{4^6} + 100$$

$$00264 := \sqrt{4^6} + 200$$

$$00364 := \sqrt{4^6} + 300$$

$$00464 := \sqrt{4^6} + 400$$

$$00564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 500$$

$$00664 := \sqrt{4^6} + 600$$

$$00764 := \sqrt{4^6} + 700$$

$$00864 := \sqrt{4^6} + 800$$

$$00964 := \sqrt{4^6} + 900$$

$$001164 := \sqrt{4^6} + 1100$$

$$002264 := \sqrt{4^6} + 2200$$

$$003364 := \sqrt{4^6} + 3300$$

$$004464 := \sqrt{4^6} + 4400$$

$$005564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 5500$$

$$006664 := \sqrt{4^6} + 6600$$

$$007764 := \sqrt{4^6} + 7700$$

$$008864 := \sqrt{4^6} + 8800$$

$$009964 := \sqrt{4^6} + 9900$$

$$0001625 := \sqrt{5^{2+6}} + 1000$$

$$0002625 := \sqrt{5^{2+6}} + 2000$$

$$0003625 := \sqrt{5^{2+6}} + 3000$$

$$0004625 := \sqrt{5^{2+6}} + 4000$$

$$0005625 := \sqrt{5^{2+6}} + 5000$$

$$0006625 := \sqrt{5^{2+6}} + 6000$$

$$0007625 := \sqrt{5^{2+6}} + 7000$$

$$0008625 := \sqrt{5^{2+6}} + 8000$$

$$0009625 := \sqrt{5^{2+6}} + 9000$$

$$0001729 := 9^{\sqrt{2+7}} + 1000$$

$$0002729 := 9^{\sqrt{2+7}} + 2000$$

$$0003729 := 9^{\sqrt{2+7}} + 3000$$

$$0004729 := 9^{\sqrt{2+7}} + 4000$$

$$0005729 := 9^{\sqrt{2+7}} + 5000$$

$$0006729 := 9^{\sqrt{2+7}} + 6000$$

$$0007729 := 9^{\sqrt{2+7}} + 7000$$

$$0008729 := 9^{\sqrt{2+7}} + 8000$$

$$0009729 := 9^{\sqrt{2+7}} + 9000$$

$$0010164 := \sqrt{4^6} + 10100$$

$$0011164 := \sqrt{4^6} + 11100$$

$$0012164 := \sqrt{4^6} + 12100$$

$$0013164 := \sqrt{4^6} + 13100$$

$$0014164 := \sqrt{4^6} + 14100$$

$$0015164 := \sqrt{4^6} + 15100$$

$$0016164 := \sqrt{4^6} + 16100$$

$$0017164 := \sqrt{4^6} + 17100$$

$$0018164 := \sqrt{4^6} + 18100$$

$$0019164 := \sqrt{4^6} + 19100$$

$$0020264 := \sqrt{4^6} + 20200$$

$$0021264 := \sqrt{4^6} + 21200$$

$$0022264 := \sqrt{4^6} + 22200$$

$$0023264 := \sqrt{4^6} + 23200$$

$$0024264 := \sqrt{4^6} + 24200$$

$$0025264 := \sqrt{4^6} + 25200$$

$$0026264 := \sqrt{4^6} + 26200$$

$$0027264 := \sqrt{4^6} + 27200$$

$$0028264 := \sqrt{4^6} + 28200$$

$$0029264 := \sqrt{4^6} + 29200$$

$$0030364 := \sqrt{4^6} + 30300$$

$$0031364 := \sqrt{4^6} + 31300$$

$$0032364 := \sqrt{4^6} + 32300$$

$$0033364 := \sqrt{4^6} + 33300$$

$$0034364 := \sqrt{4^6} + 34300$$

$$0035364 := \sqrt{4^6} + 35300$$

$$0036364 := \sqrt{4^6} + 36300$$

$$0037364 := \sqrt{4^6} + 37300$$

$$0038364 := \sqrt{4^6} + 38300$$

$$0039364 := \sqrt{4^6} + 39300$$

$$0040464 := \sqrt{4^6} + 40400$$

$$0041464 := \sqrt{4^6} + 41400$$

$$0042464 := \sqrt{4^6} + 42400$$

$$0043464 := \sqrt{4^6} + 43400$$

$$0044464 := \sqrt{4^6} + 44400$$

$$0045464 := \sqrt{4^6} + 45400$$

$$0046464 := \sqrt{4^6} + 46400$$

$$0047464 := \sqrt{4^6} + 47400$$

$$0048464 := \sqrt{4^6} + 48400$$

$$0049464 := \sqrt{4^6} + 49400$$

$$0050564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 50500$$

$$0051564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 51500$$

$$0052564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 52500$$

$$0053564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 53500$$

$$0054564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 54500$$

$$0055564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 55500$$

$$0056564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 56500$$

$$0057564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 57500$$

$$0058564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 58500$$

$$0059564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 59500$$

$$0060664 := \sqrt{4^6} + 60600$$

$$0061664 := \sqrt{4^6} + 61600$$

$$0062664 := \sqrt{4^6} + 62600$$

$$0063664 := \sqrt{4^6} + 63600$$

$$0064664 := \sqrt{4^6} + 64600$$

$$0065664 := \sqrt{4^6} + 65600$$

$$0066664 := \sqrt{4^6} + 66600$$

$$0067664 := \sqrt{4^6} + 67600$$

$$0068664 := \sqrt{4^6} + 68600$$

$$0069664 := \sqrt{4^6} + 69600$$

$$0070764 := \sqrt{4^6} + 70700$$

$$0071764 := \sqrt{4^6} + 71700$$

$$0072764 := \sqrt{4^6} + 72700$$

$$0073764 := \sqrt{4^6} + 73700$$

$$0074764 := \sqrt{4^6} + 74700$$

$$0075764 := \sqrt{4^6} + 75700$$

$$0076764 := \sqrt{4^6} + 76700$$

$$0077764 := \sqrt{4^6} + 77700$$

$$0078764 := \sqrt{4^6} + 78700$$

$$0079764 := \sqrt{4^6} + 79700$$

$$0080864 := \sqrt{4^6} + 80800$$

$$0081864 := \sqrt{4^6} + 81800$$

$$0082864 := \sqrt{4^6} + 82800$$

$$0083864 := \sqrt{4^6} + 83800$$

$$0084864 := \sqrt{4^6} + 84800$$

$$0085864 := \sqrt{4^6} + 85800$$

$$0086864 := \sqrt{4^6} + 86800$$

$$0087864 := \sqrt{4^6} + 87800$$

$$0088864 := \sqrt{4^6} + 88800$$

$$0089864 := \sqrt{4^6} + 89800$$

$$0090964 := \sqrt{4^6} + 90900$$

$$0091964 := \sqrt{4^6} + 91900$$

$$0092964 := \sqrt{4^6} + 92900$$

$$0093964 := \sqrt{4^6} + 93900$$

$$0094964 := \sqrt{4^6} + 94900$$

$$0095964 := \sqrt{4^6} + 95900$$

$$0096964 := \sqrt{4^6} + 96900$$

$$0097964 := \sqrt{4^6} + 97900$$

$$0098964 := \sqrt{4^6} + 98900$$

$$0099964 := \sqrt{4^6} + 99900$$

$$1890549 := (9 \times \sqrt{4})^5 + 0981$$

$$1891549 := (9 \times \sqrt{4})^5 + 1981$$

$$1892549 := (9 \times \sqrt{4})^5 + 2981$$

$$1893549 := (9 \times \sqrt{4})^5 + 3981$$

$$1894549 := (9 \times \sqrt{4})^5 + 4981$$

$$1895549 := (9 \times \sqrt{4})^5 + 5981$$

$$1896549 := (9 \times \sqrt{4})^5 + 6981$$

$$1897549 := (9 \times \sqrt{4})^5 + 7981$$

$$1898549 := (9 \times \sqrt{4})^5 + 8981$$

$$1899549 := (9 \times \sqrt{4})^5 + 9981$$

$$2368429 := -92 + (\sqrt{4^8} \times 6 + 3)^2$$

$$2368438 := -83 + (\sqrt{4^8} \times 6 + 3)^2$$

$$2368447 := -74 + (\sqrt{4^8} \times 6 + 3)^2$$

$$2368456 := -65 + (\sqrt{4^8} \times 6 + 3)^2$$

$$2368465 := -56 + (\sqrt{4^8} \times 6 + 3)^2$$

$$2368474 := -47 + (\sqrt{4^8} \times 6 + 3)^2$$

$$2368483 := -38 + (\sqrt{4^8} \times 6 + 3)^2$$

$$2368492 := -29 + (\sqrt{4^8} \times 6 + 3)^2$$

$$4477359 := -95 + (-3 + 7 \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$4477368 := -86 + (-3 + 7 \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$4477377 := -77 + (-3 + 7 \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$4477386 := -68 + (-3 + 7 \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$4477395 := -59 + (-3 + 7 \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$4783003 := 30 + \sqrt{\sqrt{03^{8 \times 7}}} + 4$$

$$4783014 := 41 + \sqrt{\sqrt{03^{8 \times 7}}} + 4$$

$$4783025 := 52 + \sqrt{\sqrt{03^{8 \times 7}}} + 4$$

$$4783036 := 63 + \sqrt{\sqrt{03^{8 \times 7}}} + 4$$

$$4783047 := 74 + \sqrt{\sqrt{03^{8 \times 7}}} + 4$$

$$4783058 := 85 + \sqrt{\sqrt{03^{8 \times 7}}} + 4$$

$$4783069 := 96 + \sqrt{\sqrt{03^{8 \times 7}}} + 4$$

$$4787304 := -40 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4787313 := -31 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4787322 := -22 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4787331 := -13 + (3^7 + 8 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$5153539 := -93 + (-5 + \sqrt{3^{5+1}})^5$$

$$5153548 := -84 + (-5 + \sqrt{3^{5+1}})^5$$

$$5153557 := -75 + (-5 + \sqrt{3^{5+1}})^5$$

$$5153566 := -66 + (-5 + \sqrt{3^{5+1}})^5$$

$$5153575 := -57 + (-5 + \sqrt{3^{5+1}})^5$$

$$5153584 := -48 + (-5 + \sqrt{3^{5+1}})^5$$

$$5153593 := -39 + (-5 + \sqrt{3^{5+1}})^5$$

$$5764706 := -60 + 7^{\sqrt{4}+6} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764715 := -51 + 7^{\sqrt{4}+6} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764724 := -42 + 7^{\sqrt{4}+6} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764733 := -33 + 7^{\sqrt{4}+6} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764742 := -24 + 7^{\sqrt{4}+6} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764751 := -15 + 7^{\sqrt{4}+6} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764760 := -06 + 7^{\sqrt{4}+6} - 7 \times 5$$

$$5764709 := -90 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 + 5$$

$$5764718 := -81 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 + 5$$

$$5764727 := -72 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 + 5$$

$$5764736 := -63 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 + 5$$

$$5764745 := -54 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 + 5$$

$$5764754 := -45 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 + 5$$

$$5764763 := -36 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 + 5$$

$$5764772 := -27 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 + 5$$

$$5764781 := -18 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 + 5$$

$$5764790 := -09 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} - 7 + 5$$

$$5764779 := -97 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} + 75$$

$$5764788 := -88 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} + 75$$

$$5764797 := -79 + 7^{\sqrt{4+6}} + 75$$

$$9663601 := 10 - 6 + \left(-3 + \sqrt{6^6}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9663612 := 21 - 6 + \left(-3 + \sqrt{6^6}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9663623 := 32 - 6 + \left(-3 + \sqrt{6^6}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9663634 := 43 - 6 + \left(-3 + \sqrt{6^6}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9663645 := 54 - 6 + \left(-3 + \sqrt{6^6}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9663656 := 65 - 6 + \left(-3 + \sqrt{6^6}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9663667 := 76 - 6 + \left(-3 + \sqrt{6^6}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9663678 := 87 - 6 + \left(-3 + \sqrt{6^6}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9663689 := 98 - 6 + \left(-3 + \sqrt{6^6}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

3.3 General Representations - Up to 6 Digits

$$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$$

$$625 := \sqrt{5^{2+6}}$$

$$729 := 9^{\sqrt{2+7}}$$

$$0243 := \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^{4 \times 20}}}}}$$

$$0685 := \sqrt{5^8} + 60$$

$$0799 := 9^{\sqrt{9}} + 70$$

$$1024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}}} \times 1$$

$$1296 := \sqrt{6^{9-2+1}}$$

$$2189 := \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2$$

$$3159 := \sqrt{9^5} \times 13$$

$$3483 := \sqrt{3^8} \times 43$$

$$3867 := \left(-7 + \sqrt{6^8}\right) \times 3$$

$$4394 := (4 + 9)^3 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4489 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{8^4}\right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4624 := \sqrt{(4 + 2^6)^4}$$

$$6655 := 5 \times \sqrt{(5 + 6)^6}$$

$$9375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3}} \times 9$$

$$00184 := \sqrt{4} \times (-8 + 100)$$

$$00194 := \sqrt{4} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 100\right)$$

$$00243 := \sqrt{\sqrt{3\sqrt{\sqrt{4 \times 200}}}}$$

$$00492 := 2^9 - \sqrt{400}$$

$$01186 := \sqrt{6^8} - 110$$

$$01296 := \sqrt{6^{9 \times 2 - 10}}$$

$$01928 := 8 \times \left(-2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{10}}}\right)$$

$$01944 := 4 \times \sqrt{4 \times \sqrt{9^{10}}}$$

$$07846 := \sqrt{6^{\sqrt{4+8}}} + 70$$

$$12289 := \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1$$

$$15488 := \sqrt{88^4 \times (5 - 1)}$$

$$15564 := \sqrt{4} \times (6^5 + 5 + 1)$$

$$15568 := (8 + 6^5) \times \sqrt{5 - 1}$$

$$15623 := (3 + 2)^6 - \sqrt{5 - 1}$$

$$15627 := (7 - 2)^6 + \sqrt{5 - 1}$$

$$15629 := (\sqrt{9} + 2)^6 + 5 - 1$$

$$16448 := \sqrt{8^4} + 4^{6+1}$$

$$16797 := -7 - \sqrt{9} + 7^{6-1}$$

$$16875 := 5 \times \sqrt{(7 + 8)^6} \times 1$$

$$17253 := \sqrt{3^{5 \times 2}} \times 71$$

$$17496 := (6 \times \sqrt{9})^4 / (7 - 1)$$

$$19656 := \sqrt{6^5 \times 6} \times 91$$

$$19683 := \sqrt{3^{(8-6) \times 9}} \times 1$$

$$19693 := \sqrt{(3 \times 9)^6} + 9 + 1$$

$$19699 := \sqrt{9^9} + 6 + 9 + 1$$

$$24332 := 23^3 \times \sqrt{4} - 2$$

$$24964 := (\sqrt{4^6} + 94)^2$$

$$27648 := \sqrt{8^4} \times 6 \times 72$$

$$27783 := \sqrt{3^8} \times 7 \times 7^2$$

$$28559 := \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 5 + 5)^8} - 2$$

$$28563 := \sqrt{(3 \times 6 - 5)^8} + 2$$

$$29523 := (3^{2 \times 5} - \sqrt{9}) / 2$$

$$29529 := (\sqrt{9^{2 \times 5}} + 9) / 2$$

$$29584 := (4 \times (8 \times 5 + \sqrt{9}))^2$$

$$29789 := (\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7)^{\sqrt{9}} - 2$$

$$32758 := \sqrt{(8^5 - 7)^2} - 3$$

$$32849 := \sqrt{9^4} + 8^{2+3}$$

$$33792 := 2^{\sqrt{9+7}} \times 33$$

$$34295 := 5 \times (\sqrt{9} + 2^4)^3$$

$$34986 := (\sqrt{6^8} \times 9 - \sqrt{4}) \times 3$$

$$34992 := \sqrt{2 \times (9 + 9)^{4+3}}$$

$$34994 := \sqrt{4} + (9 + 9)^4 / 3$$

$$36882 := (2 + \sqrt{8^8}) \times (6 + 3)$$

$$38419 := \sqrt{(9 + 1 + 4)^8} + 3$$

$$39364 := -\sqrt{4} + 6 \times 3^9 / 3$$

$$39374 := \sqrt{4} \times (7 + 3^9 - 3)$$

$$42436 := \sqrt{(6 \times 34 + 2)^4}$$

$$42875 := \sqrt{(5 \times 7)^{8+2-4}}$$

$$43681 := \sqrt{(1 - 8 + 6^3)^4}$$

$$43923 := 3 \times (2^{\sqrt{9}} + 3)^4$$

$$44517 := 71 \times (5^4 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$44944 := \sqrt{((4 + 49) \times 4)^4}$$

$$45369 := (\sqrt{9} + 6 \times 35)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$45796 := (6^{\sqrt{9}} - 7 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$46636 := -6 \times 3 + 6^6 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$46637 := -7 \times 3 + 6^6 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$46642 := -2^4 + 6^6 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$46643 := -\sqrt{3^4} + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46645 := -5 - \sqrt{4} + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46646 := -6 \times \sqrt{4} + 6^6 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$46647 := -7 + \sqrt{4} + 6^6 - 4$$

$$46649 := -9 - \sqrt{4} + 6^6 + 4$$

$$46654 := (-4 + 5) \times 6^6 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$46655 := 5/5 + 6^6 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$46671 := 17 + 6^6 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$46672 := 2 \times 7 + 6^6 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$46674 := \sqrt{4} \times 7 + 6^6 + 4$$

$$46679 := \sqrt{9} \times 7 + 6^6 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$46682 := 28 + 6^6 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$46685 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} + 6^6 + 4$$

$$46692 := (2 \times \sqrt{9})^6 + \sqrt{6^4}$$

$$46693 := 39 + 6^6 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$46694 := 4 \times 9 + 6^6 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$48664 := (\sqrt{46^6} - 8) / \sqrt{4}$$

$$49164 := (4^6 + 1) \times \sqrt{9} \times 4$$

$$49928 := 8 \times (-2 + 9 \times 9)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$58959 := 9 \times (-5 + \sqrt{9^8} - 5)$$

$$58997 := -7 + 9 \times (\sqrt{9^8} - 5)$$

$$59019 := -\sqrt{9} \times 10 + 9^5$$

$$59043 := -3 \times \sqrt{4} + 09^5$$

$$59046 := -6 / \sqrt{4} + 09^5$$

$$59051 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} + 09^5$$

$$59324 := (42 - 3)^{\sqrt{9}} + 5$$

$$64896 := \sqrt{(6 + 98)^4} \times 6$$

$$65125 := 521 \times \sqrt{5^6}$$

$$65542 := \sqrt{2\sqrt{4\sqrt{5 \times 5}}} + 6$$

$$68921 := \sqrt{(1 + (2 + \sqrt{9}) \times 8)^6}$$

$$69984 := 4 \times 8 \times \sqrt{9 \times 9^6}$$

$$82944 := 4 \times (4 \times \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}}$$

$$83521 := \sqrt{(1 \times 2 + 5 \times 3)^8}$$

$$84092 := \sqrt{290^4} - 8$$

$$87846 := 6 \times \sqrt{(-4 + 8 + 7)^8}$$

$$91125 := (5 \times (-2 + 11))^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$97336 := (6 + 3 + 37)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$97755 := 5 \times 57 \times 7^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$98286 := (-6 + \sqrt{8^{2+8}}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$98328 := (8^{2+3} + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$98415 := 5 \times \sqrt{(1^4 + 8)^9}$$

$$001196 := \sqrt{6^{9-1}} - 100$$

$$002189 := (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (-1 + 200)$$

$$002364 := \sqrt{4} \times 6 \times (-3 + 200)$$

$$002784 := \sqrt{4} \times (-8 + 7 \times 200)$$

$$002794 := \sqrt{4} \times (-\sqrt{9} + 7 \times 200)$$

$$004179 := \sqrt{9} \times (-7 + 1400)$$

$$004195 := -5 + \sqrt{9} \times 1400$$

$$005495 := -5 + (9 + \sqrt{4}) \times 500$$

$$005964 := \sqrt{4} \times 6 \times (-\sqrt{9} + 500)$$

$$007384 := \sqrt{4} \times (-8 + 3700)$$

$$007394 := \sqrt{4} \times (-\sqrt{9} + 3700)$$

$$009984 := \sqrt{4^8} \times (9 + \sqrt{900})$$

$$010935 := 5 \times 3^{-\sqrt{9}+010}$$

$$012264 := \sqrt{4} \times 6 \times (-2 + 2^{10})$$

$$013255 := 55 \times (-2 + \sqrt{3^{10}})$$

$$013851 := (-1 + 58) \times \sqrt{3^{10}}$$

$$015552 := 2 \times \sqrt{(5/5 + 5)^{10}}$$

$$015645 := 5 \times (-\sqrt{4} + 6 + \sqrt{5^{10}})$$

$$015865 := 5 \times (6 \times 8 + \sqrt{5^{10}})$$

$$015874 := 4\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}} - 510$$

$$015945 := 5 \times (4^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{5^{10}})$$

$$015985 := 5 \times (8 \times 9 + \sqrt{5^{10}})$$

$$016197 := \sqrt{7^{9+1}} - 610$$

$$016344 := 4 \times (4^{\sqrt{36}} - 10)$$

$$016394 := 4^{\sqrt{9}/3+6} + 10$$

$$016424 := \sqrt{4} \times 2 \times (4^6 + 10)$$

$$017319 := (9 - 1)^3 + \sqrt{7^{10}}$$

$$017432 := (2 + 3)^4 + \sqrt{7^{10}}$$

$$019197 := 79 \times 1 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{10}}}$$

$$019826 := \sqrt{(6 \times 2)^8} - 910$$

$$019926 := (6/2)^9 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{10}}}$$

$$019968 := \sqrt{8^6 \times 9} \times (\sqrt{9} + 10)$$

$$023549 := -\sqrt{9} + 4^5 \times (3 + 20)$$

$$024576 := 6 \times \sqrt{(7 - 5)^{4+20}}$$

$$024596 := 6 \times (\sqrt{9} + 5)^4 + 20$$

$$025475 := -5 + \sqrt{7^4} \times 520$$

$$028581 := \sqrt{(1 \times 8 + 5)^8} + 20$$

$$031744 := 4^{-\sqrt{4}+7} \times (1 + 30)$$

$$032039 := -9^3 + \sqrt{02^{30}}$$

$$032525 := -(5 - 2)^5 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032587 := -\sqrt{-7 + 8^5} + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032643 := -\sqrt{(3 + \sqrt{4})^6} + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032677 := -7 \times (7 + 6) + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032678 := -(8 + 7) \times 6 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032681 := -1 - 86 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032684 := \sqrt{4} - 86 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032726 := -\sqrt{6^2} \times 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032728 := 8 \times (2 - 7) + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032731 := -1 \times 37 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032753 := -3 - 5 - 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032754 := -\sqrt{4} - 5 - 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032756 := 6 \times (5 - 7) + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032758 := -8 + 5 - 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032759 := \sqrt{9} - 5 - 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032761 := -1^6 \times 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032763 := -\sqrt{3 \times 6 + 7} + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032764 := 4 \times (6 - 7) + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032767 := (-7 + 6)^7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032772 := \sqrt{2 + 7 + 7} + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032773 := -\sqrt{-3+7} + 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032776 := -6 + 7 + 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032779 := \sqrt{9+7} + 7 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032782 := \sqrt{28 \times 7} + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032816 := 6 \times 1 \times 8 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032817 := 7 \times (-1 + 8) + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032824 := \sqrt{4} \times 28 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032828 := \sqrt{8^{2+8}} + 2 \times 30$$

$$032832 := 2^3 \times 8 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032848 := (8 + \sqrt{4}) \times 8 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032856 := (6 + 5) \times 8 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032864 := \sqrt{4} \times 6 \times 8 + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032889 := \sqrt{\sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^8}} + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032966 := 66 \times \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$032984 := (-\sqrt{4} + 8)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{2^{30}}$$

$$033792 := 2^{\sqrt{9+7}} \times (3 + 30)$$

$$037179 := \sqrt{9^7} \times 17 + 3 \times 0$$

$$038413 := -3 + \sqrt{14^8} + 3 \times 0$$

$$038414 := -\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{14^8} + 3 \times 0$$

$$038416 := \sqrt{((6+1) \times \sqrt{4})^8} + 3 \times 0$$

$$038419 := \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{14^8} + 3 \times 0$$

$$038446 := \sqrt{(6+4+4)^8} + 30$$

$$039344 := \sqrt{4} \times (4 + 3^9) - 30$$

$$039925 := -5 + (2 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 30$$

$$041984 := \sqrt{4} \times (8^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (1 + 40)$$

$$043824 := \sqrt{4} \times (28^3 - 40)$$

$$043883 := \sqrt{(3+8)^8} \times 3 - 40$$

$$046614 := -\sqrt{4} \times 1 + 6^6 - 40$$

$$046619 := \sqrt{9} + 1 \times 6^6 - 40$$

$$046688 := -\sqrt{8 \times 8} + 6^6 + 40$$

$$046696 := 6^9 / \sqrt{6^6} + 40$$

$$046699 := 9 / \sqrt{9} + 6^6 + 40$$

$$047488 := 8 \times 8 \times (\sqrt{4} + 740)$$

$$057999 := \sqrt{9} \times (\sqrt{9^9}) - 7 \times 50$$

$$058199 := \sqrt{9^{9+1}} - 850$$

$$058564 := 4 \times \sqrt{(6+5)^8} + 5 \times 0$$

$$058649 := \sqrt{9^{4+6}} - 8 \times 50$$

$$058999 := \sqrt{9^{9+9-8}} - 50$$

$$059099 := \sqrt{9^9 \times 09} + 50$$

$$059199 := \sqrt{9} \times \sqrt{(9 \times 1)^9} + 50$$

$$059269 := (\sqrt{9} + 6^2)^{\sqrt{9}} - 50$$

$$059319 := (\sqrt{9} \times 13)^{\sqrt{9}} + 5 \times 0$$

$$059999 := \sqrt{9^9 \times 9} + 950$$

$$078685 := \sqrt{5^{8+6}} + 8 \times 70$$

$$089133 := 3 \times (31^{\sqrt{9}}) - 80$$

$$094774 := \sqrt{(4 \times 77)^4} - 90$$

$$104968 := -8 + (6 \times \sqrt{9})^4 \times 01$$

$$114688 := (8 + 8 \times 6) \times \sqrt{4^{11}}$$

$$116424 := \sqrt{42^4} \times 6 \times 11$$

$$116645 := 5 \times (\sqrt{4} + 6^6) / (1 + 1)$$

$$117645 := (5 + \sqrt{4})^6 + 7 - 11$$

$$117647 := \sqrt{7^{4+6}} \times 7 - 1 - 1$$

$$117652 := (2 + 5)^6 + \sqrt{7+1+1}$$

$$117654 := (\sqrt{4} + 5)^6 + 7 - 1 - 1$$

$$117667 := 7^{\sqrt{6 \times 6}} + 7 + 11$$

$$127985 := ((5 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}} - 7) \times 2 - 1$$

$$131584 := \sqrt{4^8} \times (513 + 1)$$

$$134375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3}} \times 43 \times 1$$

$$135685 := 5 \times (\sqrt{8^6} \times 53 + 1)$$

$$136296 := 6^{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^2}}} \times 631$$

$$137544 := 44 \times (\sqrt{5^{7+3}} + 1)$$

$$137799 := (\sqrt{9^9} + 7) \times 7 - 31$$

$$137844 := \sqrt{4} \times ((48 - 7)^3 + 1)$$

$$137979 := 9 \times (7 \times \sqrt{9^7} + 3) + 1$$

$$139947 := (-7 + (4 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 3 \times 1$$

$$139962 := (-2 + 6^{9-\sqrt{9}}) \times 3 \times 1$$

$$139968 := 8 \times (6^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9^{3-1})$$

$$139969 := \sqrt{9 \times 6^{9+9/3}} + 1$$

$$139994 := ((4 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} + 9) \times 3 - 1$$

$$139996 := (6^{9-\sqrt{9}} + 9) \times 3 + 1$$

$$140822 := 22 \times (\sqrt{80^4} + 1)$$

$$143749 := (\sqrt{9} \times (4 + 7))^3 \times 4 + 1$$

$$147439 := \sqrt{9} \times 3 \times (4^7 - \sqrt{4}) + 1$$

$$147447 := (7 + \sqrt{4}) \times (\sqrt{4^{7 \times \sqrt{4}}} - 1)$$

$$147454 := (4 + 5) \times 4^7 - \sqrt{4} \times 1$$

$$147456 := (6 + 54 \times 7)^{\sqrt{4 \times 1}}$$

$$147474 := (\sqrt{4} + 7) \times (4^7 + \sqrt{4}) \times 1$$

$$147483 := \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \times (4^7 + 4 - 1)$$

$$147493 := (3 \times \sqrt{9}) \times (4^7 + 4) + 1$$

$$147494 := \sqrt{4} + 9 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 1$$

$$148176 := (6 \times 7)^{\sqrt{1+8}} \times \sqrt{4} \times 1$$

$$148877 := (7 \times 7 + \sqrt{8+8})^{4-1}$$

$$149769 := (9 \times 6 \times 7 + 9)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 1$$

$$149783 := 3 \times 8 \times \sqrt{79^4} - 1$$

$$153728 := 8^2 \times (\sqrt{7^{3+5}} + 1)$$

$$154275 := \sqrt{(57 - 2)^4} \times 51$$

$$154884 := 4 \times (\sqrt{88^4} \times 5 + 1)$$

$$157437 := 7^3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 7) \times 51$$

$$157464 := 4 \times 6 \times (\sqrt{4} + 7)^{5-1}$$

$$157546 := 6^4 + 5^7 \times \sqrt{5-1}$$

$$160867 := \sqrt{(1 + 6)^{08}} \times 67$$

$$163296 := 6^{\sqrt{9+2}} \times 3 \times (6 + 1)$$

$$163875 := 5 \times (7 + \sqrt{8^{3+6+1}})$$

$$164944 := \sqrt{(4 \times (4 + 9))^4} \times 61$$

$$166957 := (-7 + \sqrt{(5 + 9)^6}) \times 61$$

$$177139 := \sqrt{9^{3+1+7}} - 7 - 1$$

$$177674 := (-\sqrt{4} + 76) \times \sqrt{7^{7+1}}$$

$$183744 := 4 \times (\sqrt{4} + 7 \times (3^8 + 1))$$

$$184877 := 7 \times \sqrt{7^8} \times (4 + 8 - 1)$$

$$185193 := (3 + 9 \times (1 + 5))^{\sqrt{8+1}}$$

$$186622 := 2 \times \left(2 \times 6^{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}}} - 1 \right)$$

$$186628 := 8/2 \times \left(6^{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}}} + 1 \right)$$

$$186633 := 3 \times 3 \times \left(\sqrt{(6+6)^8} + 1 \right)$$

$$186642 := 2 \times \left(\sqrt{4} \times 6^6 \right) + 8 + 1$$

$$186649 := -\sqrt{9} + 4 \times (6^6 + 8 - 1)$$

$$186669 := 9 \times \left(6 + \sqrt{(6+6)^8} - 1 \right)$$

$$189035 := \left(5 + 30^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (8 - 1)$$

$$189567 := 7 \times \left((6 \times 5)^{\sqrt{9}} + 81 \right)$$

$$194473 := (3 \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{49} - 1$$

$$194477 := (7 - 7 \times 4)^4 - \sqrt{9} - 1$$

$$194479 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4 \times 4}} - \sqrt{9} + 1$$

$$194481 := 1 \times (84/4)^{\sqrt{9}+1}$$

$$194485 := \left(5 + 8 \times \sqrt{4} \right)^4 + \sqrt{9} + 1$$

$$194491 := \left(19 + \sqrt{4} \right)^4 + 9 + 1$$

$$194497 := \left(7 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^4 + \sqrt{4} \times (9 - 1)$$

$$194664 := \sqrt{46^6 \times 4} - 9 + 1$$

$$194672 := 2 \times (7 \times 6 + 4)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 1$$

$$194674 := \sqrt{4} \times \left((7 \times 6 + 4)^{\sqrt{9}} + 1 \right)$$

$$195113 := (3 + 11 \times 5)^{\sqrt{9}} + 1$$

$$195364 := 4 \times (6^3 + 5)^{\sqrt{9}-1}$$

$$196584 := (-4 + 8^5) \times \sqrt{6^{\sqrt{9}-1}}$$

$$196749 := 9 \times \left(\sqrt{(4 \times 7)^6} - 91 \right)$$

$$196882 := \sqrt{(1^9 + 6)^8} \times 82$$

$$199472 := 274 \times \left(9^{\sqrt{9}} - 1 \right)$$

$$199927 := \left(7 + 2 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 91$$

$$199955 := 5^5 + \sqrt{9^9} \times (9 + 1)$$

$$215995 := -5 + \left((9 + \sqrt{9}) \times 5 \right)^{1+2}$$

$$219488 := (-8 + 84)^{\sqrt{9}} / (1 \times 2)$$

$$221184 := 48^{\sqrt{11-2}} \times 2$$

$$224674 := \left(476 - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 - 2$$

$$224676 := \left(6 \times \left(7 + \sqrt{6^4} \times 2 \right) \right)^2$$

$$229378 := \sqrt{8^{7+3}} \times (9 - 2) + 2$$

$$233265 := 5 \times \left(6^{2 \times 3} - \sqrt{3^2} \right)$$

$$233295 := 5 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + (2 \times 3)^{3 \times 2} \right)$$

$$234253 := (-3 + 5^2)^4 - \sqrt{3^2}$$

$$234259 := \left(-\sqrt{9} + 5^2 \right)^4 + \sqrt{3^2}$$

$$234365 := \left(5^6 \times 3 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (3 + 2)$$

$$234759 := \sqrt{9} \times (5^7 + 4 \times 32)$$

$$235292 := 2 \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + (2 + 5)^{3 \times 2} \right)$$

$$236194 := 4 \times \sqrt{9^{1+6+3}} - 2$$

$$238328 := 8 \times \sqrt{(23 + 8)^{3 \times 2}}$$

$$238464 := \sqrt{(2 \times 3)^8} \times 46 \times 4$$

$$245025 := \left(520 - \sqrt{5^4} \right)^2$$

$$248368 := 86 \times \sqrt{38^4} \times 2$$

$$248831 := \left(\sqrt{2^4} + 8 \right)^{8-3} - 1$$

$$249696 := 6 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 6 \times 9 \right) \times 4 \right)^2$$

$$249952 := \left(25^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 4^2$$

$$249998 := (8^{\sqrt{9}} - 9 - \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{4}} - 2$$

$$254368 := 8^6 - (3 \times \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{5^2}}$$

$$255879 := \sqrt{9^7} \times (-8 + 5 \times 5^2)$$

$$255894 := (\sqrt{4^{9+8}} - 5^5) \times 2$$

$$258064 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6 \times 085)^2$$

$$261982 := \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^9} - 162$$

$$262137 := -7 + ((3 + 1) \times 2)^{\sqrt{6^2}}$$

$$262139 := -\sqrt{9} + ((3 + 1) \times 2)^6 - 2$$

$$262149 := \sqrt{9} + (4 \times 1 \times 2)^6 + 2$$

$$262394 := 4^9 + \sqrt{(3 + 2)^6} \times 2$$

$$264386 := \sqrt{6^8} \times 34 \times 6 + 2$$

$$265225 := (5 \times (22 - \sqrt{5^6}))^2$$

$$265625 := \sqrt{5^{2 \times 6}} \times (5 + 6 \times 2)$$

$$266248 := -8 + (4 + \sqrt{(2 + 6)^6})^2$$

$$268322 := -2 + (2 \times 3 + \sqrt{8^6})^2$$

$$268667 := \sqrt{7^6} + (6 + \sqrt{8^6})^2$$

$$272484 := (\sqrt{4} + 8 + 4 \times 2^7)^2$$

$$273625 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^{2 \times 6}}} \times (3^7 + 2)$$

$$274625 := (5 + 2^6 - 4)^{\sqrt{7+2}}$$

$$279568 := 8^6 + (5^{\sqrt{9}} + 7)^2$$

$$279876 := 6^7 - 8 - \sqrt{9} - 7^2$$

$$279926 := -6 - 2 + (9 - \sqrt{9})^7 - 2$$

$$279927 := -7 + \sqrt{(2 \times (9 + 9))^7} - 2$$

$$279928 := -8 + \sqrt{(2 \times (9 + 9))^{\sqrt{7^2}}}$$

$$279929 := -9 + \sqrt{(2 \times (9 + 9))^7} + 2$$

$$279931 := -1 \times 3 + (9 - \sqrt{9})^7 - 2$$

$$279932 := -2 \times 3 - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$279933 := -3 + \sqrt{(3 \times 9 + 9)^{\sqrt{7^2}}}$$

$$279939 := \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{(3 \times 9 + 9)^{\sqrt{7^2}}}$$

$$279941 := -1 + 4 + (9 - \sqrt{9})^7 + 2$$

$$279942 := 2 \times 4 - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 - 2$$

$$279951 := 15 - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^{\sqrt{7^2}}$$

$$279953 := 3 \times 5 - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$279954 := 4 \times 5 - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 - 2$$

$$279962 := 26 + (9 - \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{7^2}}$$

$$279963 := \sqrt{3^6} - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^{\sqrt{7^2}}$$

$$279966 := 6 \times (6^{9-\sqrt{9}} + 7 - 2)$$

$$279973 := 37 - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^{\sqrt{7^2}}$$

$$279976 := 6 \times 7 - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 - 2$$

$$279984 := 48 - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^{\sqrt{7^2}}$$

$$279986 := 6 \times 8 - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^7 + 2$$

$$279987 := \sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} + (9 - \sqrt{9})^7 + 2$$

$$279995 := 59 - (\sqrt{9} - 9)^{\sqrt{7^2}}$$

$$279997 := 7 \times 9 + (9 - \sqrt{9})^7 - 2$$

$$\begin{aligned} 287496 &:= 6^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{(4+7)^{8-2}} \\ 289444 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times (4^4 + 9) + 8\right)^2 \\ 289737 &:= 73 \times \sqrt{(7 \times 9)^{8/2}} \\ 292681 &:= \left(\sqrt{1 \times 8^6} + 29\right)^2 \\ 293764 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + 6 \times (7+3) \times 9\right)^2 \\ 294849 &:= 9 \times 4^8 / \sqrt{4} - 9 + 2 \\ 294858 &:= \left(8^5 - 8 + \sqrt{4}\right) \times \sqrt{9^2} \\ 294864 &:= 4 \times 6 \times \left(8^4 \times \sqrt{9} - 2\right) \\ 294874 &:= \left(\sqrt{4^{7+8}} - 4\right) \times 9 - 2 \\ 294914 &:= \sqrt{4} \times \left(1 + \left(9 \times \left(4^{9-2}\right)\right)\right) \\ 294928 &:= 8 \times \left(\left(\left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}}\right)^4\right) \times 9\right) + 2\right) \\ 294984 &:= \left(4 + \sqrt{8^9 \times \sqrt{4}}\right) \times 9 \times 2 \\ 295239 &:= 9^{3+2} \times 5 - \sqrt{9} \times 2 \\ 295275 &:= 5 \times \left((7+2)^5 + \sqrt{9} \times 2\right) \\ 296344 &:= 4 \times \left(\left((4+3) \times 6\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 2\right) \\ 296595 &:= 5 \times (9 + 5 \times 6)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^2}}} \\ 297747 &:= -7 + (4 + 7 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 2 \\ 297992 &:= 2 \times \left(9^{\sqrt{9}} - 7^{\sqrt{9}}\right)^2 \\ 311469 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (6 + 41 \times 1)^3 \\ 314431 &:= -1 + \left(34 \times \sqrt{4}\right)^{1 \times 3} \\ 314434 &:= \sqrt{4} + \left(34 \times \sqrt{4}\right)^{1 \times 3} \\ 314929 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (2 \times 9)^4 + 1^3 \\ 314946 &:= \left(6 + \left(\sqrt{4} \times 9\right)^4\right) \times (1 \times 3) \\ 319488 &:= \sqrt{8^8 \times 4 \times 9} \times 13 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 321489 &:= \sqrt{9^8} \times (41 + 2^3) \\ 324723 &:= \left(327 + \sqrt{4}\right)^2 \times 3 \\ 326557 &:= 7 \times \left(-\sqrt{5 \times 5} + 6^{2 \times 3}\right) \\ 326627 &:= \sqrt{7^2} \times (6^6 + 2 + 3) \\ 331774 &:= -\sqrt{4} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\ 331779 &:= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\ 332367 &:= \sqrt{7^6} \times 323 \times 3 \\ 342744 &:= -4^4 + \left(72 - \sqrt{4}\right)^3 \\ 342995 &:= -5 + \left(-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4}\right)^3 \\ 345747 &:= 7^4 \times \sqrt{(7+5)^4} + 3 \\ 346794 &:= \left(-\sqrt{4} + \left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{7^6}\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times 3 \\ 346795 &:= -5 + \left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{7^6}\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 3 \\ 349524 &:= \left(4^{2+5+\sqrt{9}} - 4\right) / 3 \\ 352974 &:= \left(4 + \left(7^{\sqrt{9}}\right)^2 + 5\right) \times 3 \\ 352977 &:= \left((7 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} + 2 \times 5\right) \times 3 \\ 353674 &:= -\sqrt{4} + (7^6 + 3^5) \times 3 \\ 353679 &:= \sqrt{9} + (7^6 + 3^5) \times 3 \\ 354279 &:= \left(9^{7-2} \times \sqrt{4} - 5\right) \times 3 \\ 354294 &:= \sqrt{4} \times 9^{2 \times \sqrt{4+5}} / 3 \\ 354571 &:= 1 \times 7 \times \left(5 + \sqrt{4^5}\right)^3 \\ 357696 &:= \sqrt{6^9 \times 6} \times (-7 + 53) \\ 357696 &:= \sqrt{6^9 \times 6} \times (-7 + 53) \\ 357911 &:= 1 \times \left(-1 - \sqrt{9} + 75\right)^3 \\ 357917 &:= 71^{\sqrt{9}} + (7 - 5) \times 3 \\ 365835 &:= 5 \times \sqrt{(3 \times 8 + 5)^6} \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$373227 := \sqrt{72^{2 \times 3}} - 7 \times 3$$

$$373249 := (\sqrt{9} + 4 \times (2 \times 3)^7) / 3$$

$$374979 := \sqrt{9} \times (-7 + (\sqrt{9} + 47)^3)$$

$$374995 := -5 + \sqrt{9} \times (\sqrt{9} + 47)^3$$

$$379453 := -3 + (5^4 - 9)^{\sqrt{7-3}}$$

$$379454 := -\sqrt{4} + (5^4 - 9)^{\sqrt{7-3}}$$

$$379456 := (-6 + 5^4 - \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{7-3}}$$

$$384145 := 5 \times (\sqrt{4 \times 14^8} - 3)$$

$$384154 := \sqrt{4} \times (5 \times \sqrt{14^8} - 3)$$

$$389344 := 4 \times (\sqrt{4} \times 3 \times 9 - 8)^3$$

$$389899 := -9^{\sqrt{9}} + (8 - \sqrt{9})^8 + 3$$

$$390685 := 5^8 + 60 \times \sqrt{9} / 3$$

$$393234 := (\sqrt{\sqrt{4^{32}} + 3}) \times (9 - 3)$$

$$394385 := (\sqrt{5^8} + 3)^{\sqrt{4}} + \sqrt{9} / 3$$

$$394752 := 257 \times \sqrt{4^9} \times 3$$

$$397953 := (35 + 9 + 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 3$$

$$408321 := (1 - 2^3 \times 80)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$410881 := 1 \times (8 \times 80 + 1)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$411774 := (4 + 7^7 + 1 \times 1) / \sqrt{4}$$

$$411775 := (5 + 7^7 + 1 + 1) / \sqrt{4}$$

$$411777 := (7 + 7^7) / (1 + 1) + \sqrt{4}$$

$$419796 := 69 \times \sqrt{(79 - 1)^4}$$

$$419897 := -7 + \sqrt{9^8 \times (9 - 1)^4}$$

$$419949 := 9 \times ((4 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} + 1 + 4)$$

$$421873 := (-3 + 78)^{1+2} - \sqrt{4}$$

$$421879 := (-\sqrt{9} + 78)^{1+2} + 4$$

$$422498 := (8 \times \sqrt{9^4} + 2)^2 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$425944 := 44^{\sqrt{9}} \times 5 + 24$$

$$428738 := (8^3 - \sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}})^2 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$432964 := (4 + (6^{\sqrt{9}} + 2) \times 3)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$438244 := (-\sqrt{4} + 4 \times 2 \times 83)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$438967 := 76^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 + 3 - 4$$

$$438967 := 76^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 + 3 - 4$$

$$438972 := (2 - 7 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}})^3 - 4$$

$$438974 := (4 \times 7 \times \sqrt{9} - 8)^3 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$438976 := (67 + 9)^{\sqrt{8-3+4}}$$

$$438978 := (87 - \sqrt{9} - 8)^3 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$438983 := 38^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 + 3 + 4$$

$$439569 := ((9 + 65) \times 9 - 3)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$440898 := (8 \times (\sqrt{9} + 80))^{\sqrt{4}} + \sqrt{4}$$

$$442384 := (48^3 + \sqrt{2^4}) \times 4$$

$$443556 := (6 \times 55 + 3)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 4$$

$$444885 := (-5 + 8 \times 84)^{\sqrt{4}} - 4$$

$$444889 := (-9 + 8 \times 84 + 4)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$446224 := (4 \times 2 - \sqrt{26^4})^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$451584 := ((4 + 8) \times (51 + 5))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$452893 := (3^9 + 8) \times (25 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$453952 := \left((2 + 59)^3 - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$453972 := \left((-2 + 7 \times 9)^3 + 5 \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$455625 := (5 - 2)^6 \times \sqrt{(5 \times 5)^4}$$

$$455654 := \left(\sqrt{45^6} + 5 \right) \times 5 + 4$$

$$456529 := -4 + ((5 + 6) \times (5 + 2))^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$456974 := -\sqrt{4} + (7 \times (9 - 6) + 5)^4$$

$$456979 := \sqrt{9} + (7 \times (9 - 6) + 5)^4$$

$$458329 := ((9^2 + 3) \times 8 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$458444 := (-44 + 4^8) \times (5 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$458668 := (8 + 6) \times \sqrt{(-6 + 8^5)^{\sqrt{4}}}$$

$$458672 := (2 + 7 \times (-6 + 8^5)) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$458722 := -2 + 2 \times 7 \times (8^5 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$458724 := 4/2 \times 7 \times (8^5 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$458738 := -8 + (-3 + 7 \times 8^5) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$458742 := -2 + (-4 + 7 \times 8^5) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$458743 := -\sqrt{3^4} + 7 \times 8^5 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$458744 := 4/\sqrt{4} \times (7 \times 8^5 - 4)$$

$$458745 := -5 + \sqrt{4} \times 7 \times 8^5 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$458747 := -7 + \sqrt{4} \times 7 \times 8^5 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$458749 := -\sqrt{9} + 4^7 \times (8 + 5 \times 4)$$

$$458751 := -1^5 + 7 \times 8^5 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$458752 := (2 \times (-5 + 7))^8 \times (5 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$458754 := \sqrt{4} \times (5 + 7 \times 8^5 - 4)$$

$$458756 := -6 + (5 + 7 \times 8^5) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$458758 := (8^5 \times 7 + 8 - 5) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$458759 := -\sqrt{9} + (5 + 7 \times 8^5) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$458762 := 2 \times (6 + 7 \times 8^5) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$458764 := 4 \times (6 + 7 \times 8^5) / \sqrt{4}$$

$$458773 := 3 \times 7 + (7 \times 8^5) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$458774 := (4 + 7 + 7 \times 8^5) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$458774 := \sqrt{4} \times (7 + 7 \times 8^5 + 4)$$

$$458775 := -5 + (7 + 7) \times (8^5 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$458784 := 4 \times (8 + (7 \times 8^5) / \sqrt{4})$$

$$458876 := (6 + 7 \times (8 + 8^5)) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$459999 := 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times (9 - \sqrt{9} + 5^4)$$

$$466345 := 5 \times (-43 + 6^6 \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$466495 := 5 \times (-9 + \sqrt{4} \times 6^6 - 4)$$

$$466515 := -5 \times (-1 + (5 - 6^6) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$466533 := -3^3 + 5 \times 6^6 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$466534 := \sqrt{4} \times (-3 + 5 \times (6^6 - \sqrt{4}))$$

$$466538 := (-8 - 3 + 5 \times 6^6) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$466551 := 1 + (-5 + 5 \times 6^6) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$466552 := 2 \times (-5 + 5 \times 6^6) + \sqrt{4}$$

$$466554 := (\sqrt{4} - 5 + 5 \times 6^6) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$466555 := -5 + \sqrt{5 \times 5} \times 6^6 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$466558 := 8 + (-5 + 5 \times 6^6) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$466559 := \sqrt{9} + (5 + 5) \times 6^6 - 4$$

$$466572 := 2 \times (7 + 5 \times 6^6) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$466574 := 4 \times (7 + 5 \times 6^6) / \sqrt{4}$$

$$466575 := 5 \times (-7 + (5 + 6^6) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$466584 := \sqrt{4} \times (8 + 5 \times 6^6 + 4)$$

$$466585 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} + 5 \times 6^6 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$466594 := \sqrt{4} \times (-\sqrt{9} + 5 \times (6^6 + 4))$$

$$466595 := 5 \times (-\sqrt{9} + (-5 + 6^6) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$466596 := (6 \times \sqrt{9} + 5 \times 6^6) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$466615 := 5 \times (-1 + (6^6 + 6) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$466635 := 5 \times (3 + (6^6 + 6) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$466695 := 5 \times (\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} + 6^6 \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$467856 := ((6 - 5 + 8) \times 76)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$468494 := \sqrt{4} \times (-9 + (\sqrt{4} \times 8 + 6)^4)$$

$$468512 := 2 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(1-5)^8} + 6} \right)^4$$

$$468726 := 6 \times \left(\sqrt{(-2+7)^{8+6}} - 4 \right)$$

$$468746 := 6 \times \sqrt{(\sqrt{4}-7)^{8+6}} - 4$$

$$468798 := \left((8 - \sqrt{9})^7 + 8 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^4}}$$

$$471969 := (\sqrt{9} + 691 - 7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$472389 := -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 3^{2 \times 7 - 4}$$

$$472392 := 2 \times \sqrt{9} \times 3^{2+7} \times 4$$

$$472396 := (6 \times 9)^3 \times \sqrt{2+7} + 4$$

$$473344 := (4 \times 43 \times (-3 + 7))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$478864 := (\sqrt{4} - 6 + 8 \times 87)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$479979 := \sqrt{9} \times (-7 + (9 \times \sqrt{9} - 7)^4)$$

$$479995 := -5 + \sqrt{9} \times (9 \times \sqrt{9} - 7)^4$$

$$484384 := 4 \times (-8 + 348^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$484416 := \left((6 + (1 - 4)^4) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$485809 := (9 \times 08 + \sqrt{5^8})^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$489636 := 63 \times (6^{-\sqrt{9}+8} - 4)$$

$$489969 := 9^6 - \sqrt{(9 + \sqrt{9})^8} \times 4$$

$$492075 := (5 + \sqrt{70^2}) \times 9^4$$

$$492125 := 5^2 \times ((1 + 2)^9 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$492804 := ((4 + 0 - 82) \times 9)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$493832 := (-2 + 38^3) \times 9 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$493834 := (-\sqrt{4} + 38^3) \times 9 + 4$$

$$493838 := -8 + 38^3 \times 9 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$493839 := 9 \times (38^3 - \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{4})$$

$$493846 := (6 + 4 \times 8)^3 \times 9 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$494648 := (-8 + 4^6) \times (\sqrt{4} + 9)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$496125 := 5 \times (21 \times (6 + 9))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$497648 := 8 \times (\sqrt{4} \times 6^7 / 9 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$497662 := 2^6 \times \sqrt{6^7 + \sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{4}$$

$$497664 := \sqrt{4^6} \times 6^7 / (9 \times 4)$$

$$498436 := (634 + 8 \times 9)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$499447 := \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^4 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (9 + 4)$$

$$499849 := (-94 + 89 \times 9)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$499964 := ((-4 + 6 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9) \times 4$$

$$518395 := \left(5 \times \sqrt{(9 + 3)^8} - 1 \right) \times 5$$

$$521017 := \sqrt{7^{10}} \times (-1 + 2^5)$$

$$524264 := 4 \times \left(-6 + 2 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{25}}} \right)$$

$$524268 := 8^6 \times 2 - \sqrt{4} \times 2 \times 5$$

$$524278 := 8^7 / \sqrt{2^4} - 2 \times 5$$

$$524289 := (\sqrt{9} + 8^{2+4}) \times 2 - 5$$

$$524328 := 8 \times (\sqrt{2^{34-2}} + 5)$$

$$524488 := 8 \times \left((8 \times \sqrt{4})^4 + 25 \right)$$

$$529979 := \left((\sqrt{9^7} - \sqrt{9}) / \sqrt{9} \right)^2 - 5$$

$$529989 := \left((\sqrt{9^8} - 9) / 9 \right)^2 + 5$$

$$531434 := -\sqrt{4} + (3^4 \times 1)^3 - 5$$

$$531446 := (6/\sqrt{4})^{4 \times 1 \times 3} + 5$$

$$531449 := \sqrt{9^{4 \times (4-1)}} + 3 + 5$$

$$531459 := (9^5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (1 + 3 + 5)$$

$$531683 := \sqrt{\sqrt{3^{8 \times 6}}} - 1 + 3^5$$

$$534375 := 57 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)^5$$

$$537574 := (\sqrt{4} \times 7)^5 - 7 - 3^5$$

$$544639 := (9 + 3^6)^{4 - \sqrt{4}} - 5$$

$$546750 := \sqrt{(5 + 4)^6} \times 750$$

$$556574 := (\sqrt{4} \times 7)^5 + 6 \times 5^5$$

$$559817 := (7 - 1)^8 / \sqrt{9} - 55$$

$$559861 := -1 + 6^8 / \sqrt{9} - 5 - 5$$

$$559862 := 2 \times (6^{-8 + \sqrt{9} \times 5} - 5)$$

$$559863 := (3 + 6^8) / \sqrt{9} - 5 - 5$$

$$559863 := (3 + 6^8) / \sqrt{9} - 5 - 5$$

$$559864 := \sqrt{4} + 6^8 / \sqrt{9} - 5 - 5$$

$$559866 := -6 + 6^8 / \sqrt{9} - 5 + 5$$

$$559869 := \sqrt{9} \times (6^8 / 9 - 5 / 5)$$

$$559871 := (1 - 7)^8 / \sqrt{9} - 5 / 5$$

$$559882 := (-2 + 8)^8 / \sqrt{9} + 5 + 5$$

$$567644 := -4 + \sqrt{4} \times 6^7 + 6^5$$

$$583443 := (3 + 4)^4 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^{8 \times 5}}}}$$

$$588245 := (5 + \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{28+8}} \times 5$$

$$589754 := \sqrt{4} \times (-5 \times 7 + 9 \times 8^5)$$

$$589779 := 9 \times (7/7 + \sqrt{9})^8 - 5$$

$$589782 := (-2 + 8) \times (-7 + \sqrt{9} \times 8^5)$$

$$589819 := 9 \times (1^8 + \sqrt{9})^8 - 5$$

$$589822 := -2 + (-2 + 8) \times \sqrt{9} \times 8^5$$

$$589829 := 9 \times 2 \times \sqrt{8^9 \times 8} + 5$$

$$589834 := \sqrt{4} \times (-3 + 8 + 9 \times 8^5)$$

$$589866 := -6 + 6 \times (8 + \sqrt{9} \times 8^5)$$

$$589869 := -\sqrt{9} + 6 \times (8 + \sqrt{9} \times 8^5)$$

$$589935 := 5 \times (3^9 + \sqrt{9} \times 8^5)$$

$$589956 := 6 \times (-5 + \sqrt{9} \times (9 + 8^5))$$

$$589992 := 2 \times (\sqrt{9} + 9 \times (9 + 8^5))$$

$$590485 := -5 + (8 + \sqrt{4}) \times (0 + 9^5)$$

$$592699 := (9 \times 9 + 6/2)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5$$

$$606528 := (8 + \sqrt{25}) \times 6^{06}$$

$$614648 := -8 + (4 \times 6 + 4)^{\sqrt{16}}$$

$$614652 := (2 - 5 \times 6)^4 - \sqrt{16}$$

$$614654 := -\sqrt{4} + 56^4 / 16$$

$$614656 := (6 - 5 \times 6 - 4)^{\sqrt{16}}$$

$$620289 := 9 \times \sqrt{(82/02)^6}$$

$$632684 := (4 + 8 \times 6) \times \sqrt{23^6}$$

$$637847 := 7 \times \left(-4 + \sqrt{((8 + 7) \times 3)^6} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 642972 &:= 2 \times (7 \times 9^2)^{\sqrt{4}} - 6 \\
 644198 &:= (8 + \sqrt{9})^{1+4} \times 4 - 6 \\
 649533 &:= (3 \times 3)^5 \times (9 + \sqrt{4}) - 6 \\
 649539 &:= (9 - 3 + 5) \times \sqrt{9^{4+6}} \\
 649545 &:= (5 + 4)^5 \times (9 + \sqrt{4}) + 6 \\
 649594 &:= (\sqrt{4} + 9) \times (5 + \sqrt{9^{4+6}}) \\
 658378 &:= \left(87^{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{38}}}}\right) - \sqrt{5^6} \\
 658464 &:= \sqrt{4} \times 6 \times \sqrt{(\sqrt{4} - 8 \times 5)^6} \\
 658839 &:= 9 \times \sqrt{(3 + 8)^8} \times 5 - 6 \\
 658899 &:= 9 \times \left(\sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^8} \times 5 + 6\right) \\
 663546 &:= 6^4 \times \sqrt{(5 + 3)^6} - 6 \\
 663549 &:= -\sqrt{9} + (4^5 \times 3) \times \sqrt{6^6} \\
 663552 &:= 2^{5+5} \times 3 \times \sqrt{6^6} \\
 666791 &:= -1 + 9 \times \sqrt{7^6} \times \sqrt{6^6} \\
 666792 &:= 2 \times \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} \times 7)^6} \times 6 \times 6 \\
 666794 &:= \sqrt{4} + \left(9 \times (\sqrt{7^6} \times \sqrt{6^6})\right) \\
 671744 &:= \sqrt{(4 \times 4)^7} \times (-1 + 7 \times 6) \\
 681478 &:= (8 \times (7 + 4))^{\sqrt{1+8}} + 6 \\
 684288 &:= 88 \times \sqrt{(2 + 4)^8} \times 6 \\
 685464 &:= 4 \times \sqrt{(\sqrt{64} + 5)^8} \times 6 \\
 688128 &:= 8 \times 21 \times \sqrt{(8 + 8)^6} \\
 695478 &:= 87 \times (4 \times 5)^{\sqrt{9}} - 6 \\
 699735 &:= 5 \times 3 \times \left(-7 + (9 - \sqrt{9})^6\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 728995 &:= (5 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 + 2 - 7 \\
 729009 &:= 90^{\sqrt{09}} + 2 + 7 \\
 734832 &:= 2 \times 3^8 \times \sqrt{4^3} \times 7 \\
 746489 &:= (9 \times 8)^4 / \sqrt{6^4} - 7 \\
 746493 &:= -3 + \sqrt{(9 \times \sqrt{4})^6} \times \sqrt{4^7} \\
 746494 &:= -\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(9 \times \sqrt{4})^6} \times \sqrt{4^7} \\
 746496 &:= (6^{\sqrt{9}} \times 4)^{6/(-4+7)} \\
 746499 &:= \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{(9 \times \sqrt{4})^6} \times 4^7 \\
 746624 &:= 4^2 \times 6^6 + \sqrt{4^7} \\
 747392 &:= ((2 \times 9)^3 + 7) \times \sqrt{4^7} \\
 751599 &:= 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times ((5 - 1)^5 + 7) \\
 759359 &:= -9 + \left(5 \times \sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}}\right)^5 - 7 \\
 759364 &:= -4 + \sqrt{(6^3 + 9)^5} - 7 \\
 759375 &:= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9-5+7}} \\
 759382 &:= \sqrt{((28 - 3) \times 9)^5} + 7 \\
 759384 &:= \sqrt{4} + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7 \\
 759597 &:= (-7 + 95)^{\sqrt{9}} + 5^7 \\
 765279 &:= -\sqrt{9} + 7^2 \times (5^6 - 7) \\
 765667 &:= 7 \times (\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 5^6 \times 7) \\
 781264 &:= \sqrt{4} \times ((6 - 2 + 1)^8 + 7) \\
 786429 &:= \sqrt{9} \times ((2 \times 4)^6 - 8 + 7) \\
 786431 &:= -1 + 3 \times 4^{\sqrt{-6+87}} \\
 786434 &:= \sqrt{4} + 3 \times 4^{\sqrt{-6+87}} \\
 786439 &:= (9 + 3) \times (\sqrt{4} - 6)^8 + 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$786449 := \sqrt{9} \times ((4+4)^6 + 8) - 7$$

$$786463 := 3 \times (\sqrt{64^6} + 8) + 7$$

$$794624 := \sqrt{4} \times (2+6)^4 \times 97$$

$$823477 := 7^7 - 4^3 - \sqrt{\sqrt{2} \times 8}$$

$$823527 := 7^{2+5} - \sqrt{32 \times 8}$$

$$823543 := (3+4)^{5+\sqrt{32/8}}$$

$$823547 := 7^{\sqrt{4}+5} + 32/8$$

$$823778 := -8 + 7^7 + \sqrt{3^{2+8}}$$

$$830592 := (2 \times (-\sqrt{9} + 50))^3 + 8$$

$$831875 := 5 \times (7 \times 8 - 1)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}}$$

$$838784 := \sqrt{(-4+8)^7} \times (-8 + 3^8)$$

$$839764 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6^7) \times \sqrt{9} - 38$$

$$839765 := -5 + 6^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 38$$

$$839766 := (-6 + 6^7) \times \sqrt{9} - 3 \times 8$$

$$839776 := (6^7 - 7) \times \sqrt{9} - 3 - 8$$

$$839784 := -(\sqrt{4} - 8)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 3 \times 8$$

$$839799 := (9 - \sqrt{9})^7 \times \sqrt{9} - \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}$$

$$851968 := 8^6 \times \sqrt{9} + (-1 + 5)^8$$

$$854375 := (-5 + 7^3 \times 4) \times \sqrt{5^8}$$

$$859265 := (5^6 - 2) \times (-\sqrt{9} + 58)$$

$$884736 := (-6 + 3 \times 74) \times \sqrt{8^8}$$

$$884736 := \sqrt{6^{3+7-4} \times 8^8}$$

$$885369 := 96^3 + \sqrt{5^8} + 8$$

$$885743 := 3^{4+7} \times 5 + \sqrt{8 \times 8}$$

$$885816 := 6^{\sqrt{1+8}} \times (5 + \sqrt{8^8})$$

$$892296 := (69 \times 2 - 2) \times \sqrt{9^8}$$

$$907924 := \sqrt{4} \times 2 \times (-9 + 70)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$917494 := 4^9 / \sqrt{4} \times 7 - 1 - 9$$

$$925965 := 5 \times (6 \times 9 + 5 - 2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$927369 := 963^{7-2-\sqrt{9}}$$

$$928557 := 7 \times (55 - 8/2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$934407 := (\sqrt{7^{04}} - \sqrt{4})^3 \times 9$$

$$937514 := \sqrt{4} + (1 + 5^7) \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937534 := -\sqrt{4} + (3 + 5^7) \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937542 := (2 + 4 \times (5^7 + 3)) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$937564 := \sqrt{4^6} + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937569 := -\sqrt{9} + (6 + 5^7) \times (3 + 9)$$

$$937584 := 4 \times ((8 + 5^7) \times 3 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$940785 := -5 + (8 \times 70)^{\sqrt{4}} \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$941186 := -6 + ((8 - 1) \times 14)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$941189 := 98^{-1 \times 1 + 4} - \sqrt{9}$$

$$941192 := (2 + 91 + 1 + 4)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$943284 := ((4 + 8^2)^3 - 4) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$943293 := -3 + \sqrt{9} \times (2 \times 34)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$943294 := -\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{9} \times (2 \times 34)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$943296 := (6 + 9 \times 2) \times 34^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$943299 := \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{9} \times (2 \times 34)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$944781 := 18^{7-\sqrt{4}} / \sqrt{4} - \sqrt{9}$$

$$944782 := -2 + (8 \times 7 - \sqrt{4})^4 / 9$$

$$944793 := 3^{\sqrt{9}+7} \times 4 \times 4 + 9$$

$$944847 := (7 + (\sqrt{4} + 8 \times \sqrt{4})^4) \times 9$$

$$944928 := 8 \times (2 \times 9^4 + \sqrt{4}) \times 9$$

$$944973 := \left(3 \times 7 + \left(9 \times \sqrt{4}\right)^4\right) \times 9$$

$$946239 := 9^3 \times (2 + 6^4) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$957996 := \left(6 \times 9 + \sqrt{9}\right) \times 7^5 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$958464 := 4^6 \times \sqrt{4} \times (8 + 5) \times 9$$

$$979766 := 6^6 \times 7 \times \sqrt{9} - 7 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$994599 := \left(9 + \sqrt{9}\right)^5 \times 4 - 9^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$995319 := 9 \times \left(-1 + (3 + 5 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}}\right)$$

$$995328 := \left(8 + 2^3 \times 5\right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 9$$

$$995364 := \left(4 + (6 \times (3 + 5))^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times 9$$

$$996625 := (5 \times 2)^6 - (6 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$997568 := -8^6 + ((5 + 7) \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$999744 := -4^4 + \left(7 + \sqrt{9}\right)^{9-\sqrt{9}}$$

$$999901 := \left(10^{9-\sqrt{9}}\right) - 99$$

$$999919 := (91 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9 \times 9$$

$$999973 := (3 + 7)^{9-\sqrt{9}} - 9 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$999982 := (2 + 8)^{9-\sqrt{9}} - 9 - 9$$

$$999991 := (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9$$

$$999995 := -5 + (9/9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$999997 := \left(7 + \sqrt{9}\right)^{9-\sqrt{9}} - 9/\sqrt{9}$$

3.4 General Representations - 7 digits

Below are **selfie numbers** with **square-root** having 7 digits. Due que high quantity of numbers there many brackets "(...)". These simplified very easily.

$$0001744 := \sqrt{4} \times \left(-\sqrt{4^7} + 1000\right)$$

$$0001864 := \sqrt{4} \times (-68 + 1000)$$

$$0001964 := \sqrt{4} \times \left(-6 \times \sqrt{9} + 1000\right)$$

$$0001982 := \sqrt{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \times (-9 + 1000)$$

$$0001994 := \sqrt{4} \times \left(-9/\sqrt{9} + 1000\right)$$

$$0012388 := \sqrt{8^8 \times 3^2} + 100$$

$$0012544 := 4 \times \sqrt{4^5} \times (-2 + 100)$$

$$0012636 := 6 \times \left(\sqrt{36} + 2100\right)$$

$$0012954 := \left(\sqrt{4} + 5^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times (2 + 100)$$

$$0013184 := \sqrt{4^{(8-1)}} \times (3 + 100)$$

$$0013924 := \left(4 \times 2 \times \sqrt{9}\right)^3 + 100$$

$$0014395 := -5 + \sqrt{(9+3)^4} \times 100$$

$$0014784 := \sqrt{4} \times (-8 + 74 \times 100)$$

$$0014794 := \sqrt{4} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 74 \times 100\right)$$

$$0014994 := 49 \times \sqrt{9} \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 100\right)$$

$$0015279 := -\sqrt{9} \times \left(\sqrt{7^2} - 5100\right)$$

$$0015292 := -2 + \sqrt{9} \times (-2 + 5100)$$

$$0015295 := -5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^2}} \times 5100$$

$$0015298 := -8 + \sqrt{9} \times (2 + 5100)$$

$$0015644 := \sqrt{4} \times \left(-4 + 6^5\right) + 100$$

$$0015646 := -6 + \sqrt{4} \times 6^5 + 100$$

$$0015649 := -\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{4} \times 6^5 + 100$$

$$0015664 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(6 + \left(6^5\right)\right)\right)\right) + 100$$

$$0015884 := 4 \times \sqrt{8^8} - 5 \times 100$$

$$0016984 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4} \times 8^9} + 6 \times 100$$

$$0019383 := 3^8 \times 3 - \sqrt{9} \times 100$$

$$0019583 := \sqrt{(3 \times (8-5))^9} - 100$$

$$0019793 := 3^9 + 7 + \sqrt{9} + 100$$

$$0019799 := \sqrt{9^9} + 7 + 9 + 100$$

$$0019968 := \sqrt{8^6} \times (9 + \sqrt{9 \times 100})$$

$$0019983 := 3^8 \times \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{9} \times 100$$

$$0023954 := \sqrt{4} \times 59 \times (3 + 200)$$

$$0024354 := (\sqrt{4} - 5^3) \times (\sqrt{4} - 200)$$

$$0025625 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^{2 \times 6}}} \times (5 + 200)$$

$$0025945 := 5 \times (-\sqrt{4} - 9 + 5200)$$

$$0025955 := \sqrt{5 \times 5} \times (-9 + 5200)$$

$$0025985 := \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}} \times (-\sqrt{9} + 5200)$$

$$0028361 := \sqrt{(16 - 3)^8} - 200$$

$$0028761 := \sqrt{(1 \times 6 + 7)^8} + 200$$

$$0028871 := -1 + 7 \times \sqrt{8^8} + 200$$

$$0028874 := \sqrt{4} + 7 \times \sqrt{8^8} + 200$$

$$0029694 := 49 \times (6 + \sqrt{9} \times 200)$$

$$0031468 := \sqrt{8^{6+4}} - 1300$$

$$0034448 := 8 \times (\sqrt{4} + 4 + 4300)$$

$$0036595 := -5 + (-\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{5^6}) \times 300$$

$$0037495 := -5 + (-\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{4^7}) \times 300$$

$$0038716 := \sqrt{(6 + 1 + 7)^8} + 300$$

$$0039604 := (40 - 6)^{\sqrt{9}} + 300$$

$$0039982 := 2 \times (8 + \sqrt{9^9}) + 300$$

$$0042475 := \sqrt{(5 \times 7)^{4+2}} - 400$$

$$0043275 := \sqrt{(5 \times 7)^{2 \times 3}} + 400$$

$$0043795 := -5 + (\sqrt{9^7} + 3) \times \sqrt{400}$$

$$0044964 := (-4 + 6^{\sqrt{9}})^{\sqrt{4}} + \sqrt{400}$$

$$0044969 := (\sqrt{9} - 6^{\sqrt{9}})^{\sqrt{4}} - 400$$

$$0046576 := \sqrt{6^{7+5}} - \sqrt{6400}$$

$$0046627 := -7^2 + 6^6 + \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046628 := -\sqrt{8^2} + 6^6 + \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046629 := -9 + 2 + 6^6 - \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046634 := -\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{36^6} + \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046636 := 6^{36/6} - \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046639 := 9/3 + 6^6 - \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046665 := -5 + 6^6 - 6 + \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046668 := -8 + \sqrt{(6 \times 6)^6} + \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046676 := 6^{(7-6) \times 6} + \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046677 := 7/7 + 6^6 + \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046682 := -2 + 8 + 6^6 + \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046694 := \sqrt{4} \times 9 + 6^6 + \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046695 := 59 + 6^6 - \sqrt{400}$$

$$0046697 := 7 \times \sqrt{9} + 6^6 + \sqrt{400}$$

$$0047875 := -5 + (\sqrt{7^8} - 7) \times \sqrt{400}$$

$$0048727 := 7 \times (\sqrt{(2+7)^8} + 400)$$

$$0049489 := (\sqrt{9} + 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \times (9 + 400)$$

$$0049625 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^{2 \times 6}}} \times (-\sqrt{9} + 400)$$

$$0049649 := \sqrt{9^{4+6}} - 9400$$

$$0058549 := 9 \times \sqrt{(4+5)^8} - 500$$

$$0059411 := \sqrt{11^4} \times (-9 + 500)$$

$$0063584 := \sqrt{4} \times (-8 + 53 \times 600)$$

$$0063594 := \sqrt{4} \times (-\sqrt{9} + 53 \times 600)$$

$$0067184 := \sqrt{4} \times 8 \times (-1 + 7 \times 600)$$

$$0068379 := \sqrt{9} \times (-7 + 38 \times 600)$$

$$0068395 := -5 + \sqrt{9} \times 38 \times 600$$

$$0068848 := 8 \times (-\sqrt{4} + 8 + 8600)$$

$$0069595 := -5 + (-9 + 5^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 600$$

$$0077425 := 5^{\sqrt{2+4^7}} - 700$$

$$0078295 := -5 + \sqrt{9^2} \times 8700$$

$$0078825 := \sqrt{5^{-2+8+8}} + 700$$

$$0079384 := \sqrt{4} \times (-8 + 39700)$$

$$0079394 := \sqrt{4} \times (-\sqrt{9} + 39700)$$

$$0081584 := \sqrt{4} \times (-8 + 51 \times 800)$$

$$0081594 := \sqrt{4} \times (-\sqrt{9} + 51 \times 800)$$

$$0084535 := 53 \times (-5 + \sqrt{4} \times 800)$$

$$0086379 := \sqrt{9} \times (-7 + 36 \times 800)$$

$$0086395 := -5 + \sqrt{9} \times 36 \times 800$$

$$0086436 := 6 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 6 \times 800)$$

$$0095589 := \sqrt{9} \times (8^5 - 5 - 900)$$

$$0098274 := 4^7 \times (-2 + 8) - \sqrt{900}$$

$$0098297 := -7 + \sqrt{9 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(2 \times 8)^{\sqrt{900}}}}}$$

$$0101024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} + \sqrt{10^{10}}}$$

$$0104963 := -3 + (6 \times \sqrt{9})^4 - 010$$

$$0104964 := -\sqrt{4} + (6 \times \sqrt{9})^4 - 010$$

$$0104969 := \sqrt{9} + (6 \times \sqrt{9})^4 - 010$$

$$0104976 := 6^7 \times \sqrt{9} / (-\sqrt{4} + 010)$$

$$0112995 := 5 \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times (21 + 10)$$

$$0114688 := \sqrt{8^8} \times (6 \times (4 - 1) + 10)$$

$$0115776 := 67 \times (7 + 5)^{\sqrt{-1+10}}$$

$$0117607 := 7 \times (-06 + \sqrt{(7 \times 1)^{10}})$$

$$0117639 := (\sqrt{9}/3 + 6)^{7-1} - 10$$

$$0117645 := (5 + \sqrt{4})^6 - \sqrt{7-1+10}$$

$$0117747 := 7 \times (\sqrt{4} \times 7 + \sqrt{(7 \times 1)^{10}})$$

$$0117936 := 6 \times (-3 + \sqrt{9^7}) \times (-1 + 10)$$

$$0117996 := 6 \times (\sqrt{9^9} - 7 \times 1 - 10)$$

$$0118082 := 2 \times (-8 + \sqrt{(08 + 1)^{10}})$$

$$0118092 := 2 \times (-\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{(08 + 1)^{10}})$$

$$0121856 := ((-6) + (5^{\sqrt{8+1}})) \times (2^{10})$$

$$0124424 := (-4) \times (-2 - (4 \times \sqrt{(4+2)^{10}}))$$

$$0124448 := (8 \times (4 + \sqrt{4 \times (4+2)^{10}}))$$

$$0124852 := (\sqrt{(2+5)^8} \times (42 + 10))$$

$$0124928 := (((8^2) - \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{4}) \times (2^{10})$$

$$0125688 := (8 \times (86 + \sqrt{5^{2+10}}))$$

$$0125982 := (2 \times (((8 + \sqrt{9^5})^2) - 10))$$

$$0127459 := (((\sqrt{9} - 54) \times (-7))^2) + 10$$

$$0129024 := ((42 \times \sqrt{09}) \times (2^{10}))$$

$$0129375 := -(5^{7-3}) \times (\sqrt{9} - 210)$$

$$0132192 := ((2 \times 9) - 1) \times \sqrt{(2 \times 3)^{10}}$$

$$0133893 := ((39 + (8^3)) \times \sqrt{3^{10}})$$

$$0134136 := -(6^3) \times (-1 - (\sqrt{4} \times 310))$$

$$0134424 := (4 \times 2) \times (-4 + \sqrt{(4+3)^{10}})$$

$$0134448 := (8 \times (-((4/4)) + \sqrt{(4+3)^{10}}))$$

$$0134474 := ((4^7) - (\sqrt{4} \times (4 - (3^{10}))))$$

$$0134482 := (2 \times (((8^4) \times \sqrt{4}) + (3^{10})))$$

$$0134484 := (-4 + (8 \times (4 + \sqrt{(4+3)^{10}})))$$

$$0134488 := (8 \times ((8 - 4) + \sqrt{(4+3)^{10}}))$$

$$0134648 := (8 \times ((4 \times 6) + \sqrt{(4+3)^{10}}))$$

$$0137174 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} - 7) \times (-1) \right)^7 \right) + (3^{10}) \right)$$

$$0137499 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9^9} + 4) \times 7 \right) - (310) \right)$$

$$0137781 := \left(\sqrt{(1+8)^7} \times (73-10) \right)$$

$$0137793 := \left(\left(\left((3^9) \times 7 \right) + \sqrt{7-3} \right) + 10 \right)$$

$$0138365 := \left(\sqrt{5^6} + \left((3 \times 8)^3 \right) \times 10 \right)$$

$$0138848 := \left((8 \times 4) \times (\sqrt{8^8} + \sqrt{3^{10}}) \right)$$

$$0138969 := \left(\sqrt{9^6} + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 8) \right)^3 \right) \times 10 \right)$$

$$0139482 := \left((-2) + (\sqrt{8^4} \times 9) \right) \times \sqrt{3^{10}}$$

$$0139661 := \left(\left((1 + (6^6)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (310) \right)$$

$$0139664 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + (6^6)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (310) \right)$$

$$0139949 := \left(\left(\left((9 \times 4)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 3 \right) - 10$$

$$0139961 := \left(\left((-1) - (6^{9-\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times (-3) \right) - 10$$

$$0139968 := \left(((8-6) \times 9) \times \sqrt{(9-3)^{10}} \right)$$

$$0139984 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(8 + \left(9 \times \sqrt{(9-3)^{10}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0142855 := 5 \times \left(\sqrt{(5+8)^{2 \times 4}} + 10 \right)$$

$$0142874 := \left(\left(((47 \times 8) + 2)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 10 \right)$$

$$0145934 := \left(\left(((43 \times 9) - 5)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 10 \right)$$

$$0146334 := \sqrt{(-4+33)^6} \times (-4+10)$$

$$0146656 := \left(\left((6^5) \times 6 \right) + \sqrt{(6+4)^{10}} \right)$$

$$0147436 := \left(\left((6+3) \times (4^7) \right) - (\sqrt{4} \times 10) \right)$$

$$0147438 := \left(-8 + \left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{4^7}) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 10 \right)$$

$$0147446 := \left((\sqrt{6^4} \times ((4^7)/4)) - 10 \right)$$

$$0147499 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((9 \times (4^7)) + (4 \times 10) \right) \right)$$

$$0147595 := \left(\left((5 \times ((9^5) - 7)) / \sqrt{4} \right) - 10 \right)$$

$$0147968 := \left(\sqrt{8^6} \times (9 + ((7 \times 4) \times 10)) \right)$$

$$0151263 := \left((3+6) \times \sqrt{(2 \times 1+5)^{10}} \right)$$

$$0151885 := \left(\sqrt{5^8 \times (8+1)^5} + 10 \right)$$

$$0153125 := \sqrt{(5+2)^{1+3} \times 5^{10}}$$

$$0153271 := \left(-1 - \left(-((7^2)) \times (3 + \sqrt{5^{10}}) \right) \right)$$

$$0153274 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(-((7^2)) \times (3 + \sqrt{5^{10}}) \right) \right)$$

$$0156295 := \left(-5 + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 2)^6 \right) + 5 \right) \times 10 \right)$$

$$0156754 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times (5^7)) - (6 - 510) \right)$$

$$0158499 := \left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{(\sqrt{9} \times 4)^8} - (\sqrt{5^{10}}) \right) \right)$$

$$0158967 := \left(((7 \times 6) + 9) \times (-8 + \sqrt{5^{10}}) \right)$$

$$0159375 := \left(((5+7) + 39) \times \sqrt{5^{10}} \right)$$

$$0159834 := \left((43+8) \times (9 + \sqrt{5^{10}}) \right)$$

$$0163276 := \left(-6 - \left(-7 \times \left(-2 - \left(-3 \times \sqrt{6^{10}} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0163279 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(-7 \times \left(-2 - \left(-3 \times \sqrt{6^{10}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0163293 := \left(-3 - \left(-((9 \times 2) + 3) \times \sqrt{6^{10}} \right) \right)$$

$$0163294 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(-((9 \times 2) + 3) \times \sqrt{6^{10}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0163296 := \left((6 + ((9 \times 2) - 3)) \times \sqrt{6^{10}} \right)$$

$$0163299 := \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(-((9 \times 2) + 3) \times \sqrt{6^{10}} \right) \right)$$

$$0163317 := \left(-7 \times \left(-((1 \times 3)) + \left(-3 \times \sqrt{6^{10}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0163737 := \left(-((7 \times 3)) \times \left(-((7 \times 3)) - \sqrt{6^{10}} \right) \right)$$

$$0163795 := \left(-5 \times \left(9 - \sqrt{(\sqrt{7-3} + 6)^{10}} \right) \right)$$

$$0163825 := \left(-((5^2)) \times (8 - \sqrt{3^{6+10}}) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 0164025 &:= \left((5 + \sqrt{20^4}) \sqrt{\sqrt{6+10}} \right) \\
 0164569 &:= \left(\sqrt{9^6} + \left(5 \times \sqrt{(\sqrt{4+6})^{10}} \right) \right) \\
 0164997 &:= \left((7 \times \sqrt{9}) \times (\sqrt{9^4} + \sqrt{6^{10}}) \right) \\
 0166464 &:= \left(((4+64) \times 6) \sqrt{\sqrt{6+10}} \right) \\
 0167727 &:= \left(- \left((7^2) \right) \times \left(7 + (\sqrt{7^6} \times (-10)) \right) \right) \\
 0168735 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(3 - \left(\sqrt{(7+8)^6} \times 10 \right) \right) \right) \\
 0168795 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(- (9) - \left(\sqrt{(7+8)^6} \times 10 \right) \right) \right) \\
 0172871 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(\sqrt{7^8} \times (- (2 + (7 \times 10))) \right) \right) \\
 0172874 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\sqrt{7^8} \times (- (2 + (7 \times 10))) \right) \right) \\
 0173259 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{5^2}}} \right) \times (3 + 710) \right) \\
 0174955 &:= -5 + \sqrt{5 \times \left((9 \times \sqrt{4})^7 \right) \times 10} \\
 0178944 &:= \left(- \left((4^4) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + ((8 - 710)) \right) \right) \\
 0179335 &:= \left(5 \times \left((33^{\sqrt{9}}) - (7 \times 10) \right) \right) \\
 0179676 &:= \left(((6 \times 7) \times 6) \times (\sqrt{9} + 710) \right) \\
 0184923 &:= \left((3^{2+9}) + \sqrt{(\sqrt{4} - 8)^{10}} \right) \\
 0184957 &:= \left(\left((7^5) \times (9 + \sqrt{4}) \right) + ((8 \times 10)) \right) \\
 0186614 &:= \left(\left(4 \times \left((1 \times 6) \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \right) \right) - 10 \right) \\
 0186642 &:= \left((\sqrt{2^4} \times (6^6)) + ((8 + 10)) \right) \\
 0186649 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((4 \times ((6^6) + 8)) - 10 \right) \right) \right) \\
 0186654 &:= \left(\left(- (4) \times \left(- (5) - \left(6 \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \right) \right) \right) + 10 \right) \\
 0186659 &:= 9 \times \left(5 + \sqrt{(6+6)^8} \right) - 10
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 0186664 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(\left(- ((6 \times 6)) \times \sqrt{6^8} \right) - 10 \right) \right) \\
 0186944 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\sqrt{(4 \times 9)^6} + ((8 \times 10)) \right) \right) \\
 0189864 &:= 4 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8 \times \sqrt{9}}} + 810 \right) \\
 0191834 &:= \left((438^{-1+\sqrt{9}}) - 10 \right) \\
 0192496 &:= \left(\left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) - 4 \right) \times (- (2 - 910)) \right) \\
 0193957 &:= \left(\left((7^5) + \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(- (3) \times \sqrt{9^{10}} \right) \right) \\
 0194325 &:= -5^2 \times \left(3 - \sqrt{\sqrt{(4 \times 9)^{10}}} \right) \\
 0194451 &:= \left(\left((1 + (5 \times 4))^4 \right) - (\sqrt{9} \times 10) \right) \\
 0194479 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4} + 91 \times 0 \\
 0194497 &:= \left(\left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{9})^4 \right) + \sqrt{4 \times 9} \right) + 10 \right) \\
 0194525 &:= 5^2 \times \left(5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{(4 \times 9)^{10}}} \right) \\
 0194682 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \left(((8 \times 6) - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) + 10 \right) \\
 0195315 &:= \left((\sqrt{5^{1+3}} + ((5^9))) / 10 \right) \\
 0195325 &:= \left((\sqrt{5^{2 \times 3}} + ((5^9))) / 10 \right) \\
 0195767 &:= \left(\left((7^6) - 7 \right) + (5^{-\sqrt{9}+10}) \right) \\
 0196448 &:= \left((8 \times \sqrt{4}) \times \left(((4^6) \times \sqrt{9}) - 10 \right) \right) \\
 0196582 &:= \left(\left((2 \times ((8^5) - 6)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 10 \right) \\
 0196583 &:= \left(\left(- \left(((3 - (8^5)) \times 6) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) - 10 \right) \\
 0196585 &:= \left(\left(- \left(((5 - (8^5)) \times 6) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) + 10 \right) \\
 0196586 &:= \left(\left(- (6) \times \left(- ((8^5)) + (6/\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - 10 \right) \\
 0196595 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((5 + \sqrt{9})^5 \right) \times 6 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - 10 \right) \\
 0196895 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9^8} \times (-6)) - \sqrt{9} \right) - 10 \right) \right) \\
 0198597 &:= \left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (589 - 10) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$0198936 := \left((6^3) \times (\sqrt{9} + ((8 + 910))) \right)$$

$$0199674 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} - 7) \right)^6 \right) \times 9 \right) + \sqrt{9^{10}} \right)$$

$$0199746 := \left((6 \times (\sqrt{4^7} + 9)) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{10}}} \right)$$

$$0199984 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (8) + \sqrt{(9/9 + 9)^{10}} \right) \right)$$

$$0199994 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{(9/9 + 9)^{10}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0223232 := \left((2 + ((3 \times 2)^3)) \times \sqrt{2^{20}} \right)$$

$$0225496 := \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) + ((4^5) \times 220) \right)$$

$$0227328 := \left(((8 - 2) \times 37) \times \sqrt{2^{20}} \right)$$

$$0228352 := \left(\left(- (2) + \sqrt{\sqrt{(5 \times 3)^8}} \right) \times \sqrt{2^{20}} \right)$$

$$0233964 := \left(- (4) \times \left((6 \times 93) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0234259 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} - ((5^2))) \right)^4 \right) + (3 + (2 \times 0)) \right) \right)$$

$$0234355 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(5 \times 5)^{3+4}} \times 3 \right) - (20) \right)$$

$$0234499 := \left(\left(((9 + 9) + 4)^4 \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{3^{20}}} \right)$$

$$0234665 := \left((56^{\sqrt{4}}) + \sqrt{3^{20}} \right)$$

$$0235848 := \left(- (8) + \left(- (4) \times (85 - \sqrt{3^{20}}) \right) \right)$$

$$0235863 := \left(((3 + 6) \times (8^5)) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right)$$

$$0235953 := \left(- \left((3^5) \right) - \left(- ((9 - 5)) \times \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0235975 := \left(\left((5^7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + (5 \times 320) \right)$$

$$0235984 := \left(- (4) \times \left((8 + (9 \times 5)) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236124 := \left(- (4) \times \left((2 + 16) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236147 := - \left((\sqrt{7^4} - \sqrt{16 \times 3^{20}}) \right)$$

$$0236164 := \left(- (4) \times \left(\left(6 + \sqrt{\sqrt{16}} \right) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236169 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} - \sqrt{16 \times 3^{20}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0236172 := \left(\sqrt{2 \times (7 + 1)} \times \left(- (6) + \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236184 := \left(- ((4 + 8)) + \sqrt{16 \times 3^{20}} \right)$$

$$0236188 := \left(- (8) - \left(\left(- (8) + \sqrt{16} \right) \times \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236193 := \left(- (3) + \sqrt{(9 + 1 + 6) \times 3^{20}} \right)$$

$$0236199 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{(9 + 1 + 6) \times 3^{20}} \right)$$

$$0236204 := \left(- (4) \times \left((0 - 2) - \sqrt{(6 - 3)^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236242 := \left(-2 - \left(- (4) \times \left((2 \times 6) + \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0236244 := \left(- (4) \times \left(- \left((4 - 2) \times 6 \right) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236284 := \left(- (4) \times \left(- \left((8 \times 2) + 6 \right) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236304 := \left(- (4) \times \left(\left(0 - \sqrt{3^6} \right) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236364 := \left(- (4) \times \left(- \left((6 + 36) \right) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236436 := \left((6^3) + \left(- (4) \times \left(- (6) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0236444 := \left(- (4) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \sqrt{4^6} \right) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236446 := \left(- (6) + \left(4 \times \left(\sqrt{4^6} + \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0236449 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(4 \times \left(\sqrt{4^6} + \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0236484 := \left(- (4) \times \left(- \left((8 + 4) \times 6 \right) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236529 := \left(- (9) \times \left(\sqrt{2^{5 \times 6}} - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0236645 := - \left(\left(\left(\left((5 + \sqrt{4})^6 \right) + \left(- (6) \times \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0237024 := \left(- (4) \times \left(- (207) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0237564 := \left(- (4) \times \left(- \left((6 \times 57) \right) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0238244 := \left(- (4) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (2^8) \right) \right) - \sqrt{3^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0239499 := \left(9 \times \left(- (9) + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 9)^3 \right) \times 20 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0239672 := \left(2 \times \left((7^6) + \left(9 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{3^{20}}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0241056 := \left((6^5) \times \left((0-1) + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}}}} \right) \right)$$

$$0245005 := \left((500-5)^{\sqrt{4}} - (20) \right)$$

$$0246989 := \left(\left((-9) + \left((8^{\sqrt{9}}) - 6 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - (20) \right)$$

$$0248568 := \left(- (8) - \left(- \left((6^5) - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}}}} \right) \right)$$

$$0248832 := \left(\sqrt{(2 \times 3)^8} \times (8 \times (4+20)) \right)$$

$$0249967 := \left((\sqrt{7^6} \times (9^{\sqrt{9}})) - ((4 \times 20)) \right)$$

$$0252994 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4^9} - 9)^2 \right) + ((5-20)) \right)$$

$$0254368 := \left((8^6) - \left((3 \times \sqrt{4})^{5+2 \times 0} \right) \right)$$

$$0254505 := \left((505^{\sqrt{4}}) - 520 \right)$$

$$0255899 := \left((\sqrt{9^9} \times (8 + \sqrt{5 \times 5})) + (20) \right)$$

$$0262024 := \left((\sqrt{4^{20-2}}) - ((6 \times 20)) \right)$$

$$0262184 := \left((4^{8+1}) + (\sqrt{-2+6} \times 20) \right)$$

$$0262188 := \left(\left((\sqrt{8^8} + 1) \times (2^6) \right) - (20) \right)$$

$$0262272 := 2^7 + 2^{-\sqrt{-2+6+20}}$$

$$0262467 := \left(\sqrt{7^6} + \left(\left((4 \times 2)^6 \right) - 20 \right) \right)$$

$$0262664 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 6)^6 \right) + (26 \times 20) \right)$$

$$0262764 := \left((\sqrt{4^{6 \times \sqrt{7+2}}}) + (620) \right)$$

$$0263168 := 8^6 + \sqrt{\sqrt{(1-3+6)^{20}}}$$

$$0265645 := \left(\left((5 + (\sqrt{4} \times 6)) \times (5^6) \right) + (20) \right)$$

$$0266468 := \left(\left((8^6) + 4 \right) - (\sqrt{6^6} \times (-20)) \right)$$

$$0266976 := \left((6^7) - (\sqrt{9 \times 6^6} \times 20) \right)$$

$$0268299 := 9 \times \left(\sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 28)^6} + 20 \right)$$

$$0273355 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(5 \times 5)^3} \times (3^7) \right) - (20) \right)$$

$$0277376 := \left((6^7) + \left(\sqrt{(-3+7)^7} \times (-20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279476 := \left((6^7) + \left((\sqrt{4} - (\sqrt{9} \times (-7))) \times (-20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279793 := \left(\left(-((3-9)^7) - \sqrt{9} \right) - (7 \times 20) \right)$$

$$0279799 := \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) - (7 \times 20)$$

$$0279908 := \left(- (8) + \left(\left((09 - \sqrt{9})^7 \right) - (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279913 := \left(- (3) + \left(\left((-1 + \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^7 - (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279914 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times (-1)) + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^7 - (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279919 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((-1 + \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^7 - (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279924 := \left((4 \times 2) + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^7 - (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279926 := \left(\left((6^{-2+9}) - \sqrt{9} \right) - (7 + (2 \times 0)) \right)$$

$$0279928 := \left(- (8) + \left(\sqrt{(2 \times (9+9))^{7+2 \times 0}} \right) \right)$$

$$0279933 := \left(- (3) + \left(\sqrt{(3 \times 9+9)^{7+2 \times 0}} \right) \right)$$

$$0279937 := \left((7 \times 3) + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^7 - (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279939 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\sqrt{(3 \times 9+9)^{7+2 \times 0}} \right) \right)$$

$$0279946 := \left(\left((6^{\sqrt{49}}) - \sqrt{9} \right) - ((7-20)) \right)$$

$$0279948 := \left(- (8) + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 9) / \sqrt{9} \right)^7 + (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279951 := \left(15 + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^{7+2 \times 0} \right) \right)$$

$$0279955 := \left(-((5/5)) + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^7 + (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279959 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((5 + (9/9))^7 + 20 \right) \right)$$

$$0279961 := \left(-((1-6)) + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^7 + (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279962 := \left(26 + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^{7+2 \times 0} \right) \right)$$

$$0279963 := \left(\sqrt{3^6} + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^{7+2 \times 0} \right) \right)$$

$$0279964 := \left((\sqrt{4} + 6) + \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^7 \right) + (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279973 := \left(37 + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^{7+2 \times 0} \right) \right)$$

$$0279976 := \left(\left((6^7) - \sqrt{9} \right) + ((9 \times 7) - 20) \right)$$

$$0279979 := \left((9 \times 7) + \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^7 \right) - (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0279984 := \left(48 + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^{7+2 \times 0} \right) \right)$$

$$0279995 := \left(59 + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^{7+2 \times 0} \right) \right)$$

$$0281576 := \left((6^7) - (\sqrt{5-1} \times (-820)) \right)$$

$$0289564 := \left((4 \times (6 + 5)) \times (\sqrt{9^8} + (20)) \right)$$

$$0290125 := \left(- (5) \times \left((2^{10}) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0292685 := \left(- (5) \times \left((8^{6/2}) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0294165 := \left(- (5) \times \left((6^{-1+4}) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0294285 := \left(- (5) \times \left((8 \times 24) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0294347 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{74^3}) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0294435 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((3^4) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0294748 := \left(\left(\left((8 - (4^7)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-9) \right) - (20) \right)$$

$$0294825 := \left(\sqrt{5^2} \times \left(- (84) + \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0294845 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- ((4 - 84)) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0294858 := \left(\left(\left((8^5) - 8 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (9 + (2 \times 0)) \right)$$

$$0294874 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4^{7+8}} - \sqrt{4}) \times 9 \right) - (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0294875 := \left(- (5) \times \left((78 - 4) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0294885 := \left(- (5) \times \left((8 + \sqrt{8^4}) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0294889 := \left(\left(\left((9 \times 8) \times (8^4) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - (20) \right)$$

$$0294895 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((9 \times 8) - \sqrt{4} \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0294945 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((4^{\sqrt{9}}) - 4 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0294958 := \left(\left((8^5) \times 9 \right) + (\sqrt{4} \times (\sqrt{9} + (20))) \right)$$

$$0295045 := \left(- ((5 \times 40)) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295145 := \left(- (5) \times \left(((4 \times 1) \times 5) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295172 := \left(- ((2 + 71)) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295175 := \left(- (5) \times \left((7 \times \sqrt{-1+5}) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295185 := \left((5 \times ((8 + 1)^5)) - (\sqrt{9} \times 20) \right)$$

$$0295195 := \left(- (5) \times \left((9 + (1^5)) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295215 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((1^2) + 5 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295221 := \left(- ((12 \times 2)) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295224 := \left(- ((42/2)) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295225 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- ((2/2) - 5) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295227 := \left(- (((7 + 2) \times 2)) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295229 := \left(- \left(((9 \times 2) - 2 \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295233 := \left(- \left(((3 + 3) \times 2 \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295234 := \left(- \left(((\sqrt{4} + (3^2)) \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295236 := \left(- \left((6 + 3) \right) + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295237 := \left(- \left(((7 + 3) - 2 \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295238 := \left(- \left(((8 - 3) + 2 \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295241 := \left(- \left((1 \times 4) \right) + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295242 := \left(- \left(((2 + 4) / 2 \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295244 := \left(- \left((4 / 4) \right) + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295245 := \left(5 \times \sqrt{(4 - 2 \times 5 + 9)^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295246 := \left(((6 - 4) / 2 \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295247 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7 \times \sqrt{4} + 2}} - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295248 := \left(((8 - \sqrt{4}) / 2 \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295249 := \left((\sqrt{9 \times 4} - 2 \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295261 := \left(16 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295263 := \left((3 \times 6) + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295265 := \left(- (5) \times \left((6 - (2 \times 5)) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295269 := \left((\sqrt{9} \times (6 + 2) \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295281 := \left((18 \times 2) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295283 := \left(38 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295285 := \left((5 \times 8) + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295287 := \left((7 \times (8 - 2)) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295294 := \left(49 + \sqrt{25 \times \sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295295 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((\sqrt{9} + (2 + 5) \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295299 := \left((\sqrt{9} \times (9 \times 2) \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295315 := \left(- (5) \times \left((1 - (3 \times 5)) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295325 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((2 \times (3 + 5)) \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295329 := \left(((9^2) + 3 \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right)$$

$$0295375 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((7 \times 3) + 5 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295395 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((9 - 3) \times 5 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295405 := \left(- (5) \times \left((0 - \sqrt{4^5}) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295429 := \left((92 \times \sqrt{4}) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295441 := \left(\sqrt{14^4} - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295445 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((4 + 4) \times 5 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295495 := \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295497 := \left(\left((7 \times 9) \times 4 \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295515 := \left(- (5) \times \left((1 - 55) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295535 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- ((3 + 55)) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295545 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((4 + 5)^5 \right) - (\sqrt{9} \times 20) \right) \right)$$

$$0295595 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((9 + 5) \times 5 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295685 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((8 \times (6 + 5)) \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295695 := \left(- (5) \times \left((\sqrt{9} \times (- (6 \times 5))) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0295974 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0296285 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((8 \times 26) \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0296325 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{(2 \times 3)^6} \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0296525 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- (256) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0296595 := 5 \times (9 \times 5 - 6)^{\sqrt{9+2 \times 0}}$$

$$0296685 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((8 \times 6) \times 6 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0296695 := \left(5 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + (6 \times 6))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (20) \right) \right)$$

$$0297485 := \left(- (5) \times \left((\sqrt{8^4} \times (-7)) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0298685 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((86 \times 8) \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0299376 := \left(\left((6^7) + (3^9) \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}}} \right)$$

$$0299455 := \left((\sqrt{55^4} \times 99) - (20) \right)$$

$$0299565 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((6^5) / 9 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{20}} \right) \right)$$

$$0314899 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9^9} \times 8) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + (1 - 30) \right)$$

$$0314929 := \left((\sqrt{9} \times ((2 \times 9)^4)) + (1^{30}) \right)$$

$$0319488 := \left(\sqrt{8^8} \times ((49 - 1) + 30) \right)$$

$$0319855 := \left(5 \times \left(\left((5 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (1 - 30) \right) \right)$$

$$0326592 := \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \right) \times ((6 \times 2) + 30) \right)$$

$$0326657 := \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{(5 + 6^6)^2} \right) + (30) \right)$$

$$0327337 := \left(- \left((7^3) \right) + \left((3 + 7) \times \sqrt{2^{30}} \right) \right)$$

$$0327592 := \left(2 \times \left(- (9) + \left(- (5) \times \left(7 - \sqrt{2^{30}} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0327845 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- \left((4^8) \right) - \sqrt{7+2} \right) - 30 \right) \right)$$

$$0331695 := \left((5 \times \sqrt{9^6}) \times (1 + (3 \times 30)) \right)$$

$$0335979 := \left((9 \times 7) \times (\sqrt{9} + 5330) \right)$$

$$0344569 := \left(\left((9 \times 65) + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4+3 \times 0}} \right)$$

$$0344673 := \left(3 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{7^6} - 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 30 \right) \right)$$

$$0346142 := \left((2 \times (416^{\sqrt{4}})) + (30) \right)$$

$$0346891 := \left(\left((1 + (98 \times 6))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 30 \right)$$

$$0347733 := \left((3 \times (3^7)) \times \left(- (7) + (\sqrt{4} \times 30) \right) \right)$$

$$0349844 := \left(44 \times (\sqrt{89^4} + (30)) \right)$$

$$0349968 := \left(8 \times \left(6 - \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-30) \right) \right)$$

$$0352737 := \left(- (7) \times \left(\left(- (3) \times \sqrt{7^2 \times 5} \right) + (30) \right) \right)$$

$$0352967 := \left(\left((7^6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \left((2 \times 5) - 30 \right) \right)$$

$$0352977 := \left(\left((7^7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / (2 + 5) + (30) \right)$$

$$0354234 := (\sqrt{4} \times ((3^{2+4+5}) - 30))$$

$$0354299 := (((\sqrt{9}^{9+2}) \times \sqrt{4}) + (5 + (3 \times 0)))$$

$$0354324 := ((4 + 2) \times \sqrt{3^{4 \times 5}}) + (30)$$

$$0355894 := \left(4^{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) + \left(5^5\right) \times 30$$

$$0358795 := (-5) - ((9 - \sqrt{7^8}) \times (5 \times 30))$$

$$0364544 := ((\sqrt{4} \times (-4^5)) \times (\sqrt{4} - (6 \times 30)))$$

$$0368664 := (-4) \times (-6) - ((-6) \times \sqrt{8^6}) \times (-30))$$

$$0376829 := -(\sqrt{9} + (((2^{8+6}) \times (7 - 30))))$$

$$0376832 := \left(2^{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}}\right) \times (6 + 730)$$

$$0378368 := \left(\sqrt{8^6} \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} + (730)\right)\right)$$

$$0379694 := ((\sqrt{4^9} + 6) \times (\sqrt{9} + (730)))$$

$$0382945 := \left(5^{\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}}}\right) - \left(2^8\right) \times 30$$

$$0384994 := (\sqrt{4^9} \times (94 \times 8)) - 30$$

$$0386672 := \left(\sqrt{(2 \times (7 + 6))^6} \times (-8 - 30)\right)$$

$$0389257 := ((75 - 2)^{\sqrt{9}}) + ((8 \times 30))$$

$$0389785 := (((5^8) - 7) - \sqrt{9}) - (830)$$

$$0389795 := 5^{(9-7)^{\sqrt{9}}} - 830$$

$$0390535 := \left(5^{3+5}\right) + \left(\sqrt{09} \times (-30)\right)$$

$$0390585 := \left((5^8) + 50\right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-30)\right)$$

$$0390715 := \left(5^{1+7}\right) - \left(\sqrt{09} \times (-30)\right)$$

$$0390785 := \left((5^8) + 70\right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-30)\right)$$

$$0393495 := (-5) \times (\sqrt{9} - ((4 \times (3^9)) - 30))$$

$$0394345 := \left(5^{\sqrt{4^3}}\right) + (4 \times 930)$$

$$0398796 := \left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{(9 + 7)^8} + 930\right)\right)$$

$$0419862 := \left(-2 - \left(-\left(6^8\right) / \left(\sqrt{9} + 1\right)\right) + 40\right)$$

$$0419864 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(6^8 / (9 - 1)\right)\right) - 40$$

$$0419944 := \left(4 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 9\right)^{\sqrt{9}+1}\right)\right) + 40$$

$$0447958 := \left(\left(\left(8 \times 5\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times 7\right) - \sqrt{4} - 40$$

$$0448385 := \left(5^8\right) - \left(\sqrt{38^4} \times (-40)\right)$$

$$0449673 := \left(-3\right) \times \sqrt{7^6} \times \left(\sqrt{9} - (440)\right)$$

$$0454476 := \left(674^{\sqrt{4}}\right) + (5 \times 40)$$

$$0458471 := \left(-1\right) + \left(-7\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-8^5\right)\right) + 40\right)$$

$$0458474 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(-7\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-8^5\right)\right) + 40\right)\right)$$

$$0458714 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(1 + \left(7 \times \left(8^5\right)\right)\right)\right) - 40$$

$$0458744 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-4 - \left(7 \times \left(8^5\right)\right) + (4 \times 0)\right)\right)$$

$$0458764 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(6 + \left(7 \times \left(8^5\right)\right) + (4 \times 0)\right)\right)$$

$$0458797 := \left(7 \times \sqrt{(9 + 7)^8}\right) + (5 + 40)$$

$$0466574 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(7 + \left(5 \times \left(6^6\right)\right) + (4 \times 0)\right)\right)$$

$$0468516 := \left(-6\right) \times \left(-1 - \sqrt{5^{8+6}}\right) + 40$$

$$0468798 := \left(\left(\left(8 - \sqrt{9}\right)^7\right) + 8\right) \times (6 + (4 \times 0))$$

$$0489075 := (5 + 70) \times (\sqrt{9^8} - 40)$$

$$0492544 := \left(-\left(\left(4^4\right) \times 52\right)\right) \times (\sqrt{9} - 40)$$

$$0492999 := \left(\left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{9 \times 9}\right) - 2\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - 40$$

$$0493079 := \left(\left(9 + 70\right)^{\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}}}\right) + 40$$

$$0499165 := \left(\left(\left(56 - 1\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) + 40$$

$$0499974 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(7 \times 9\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-40)\right)$$

$$0518766 := \left(\sqrt{6^6 \times 7^8} + (150)\right)$$

$$0524268 := \left(\left(8^6\right) \times 2\right) - \sqrt{4 \times 2 \times 50}$$

$$0524292 := \left(\left(\left((2^9)^2 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (2 + (5 \times 0)) \right)$$

$$0524334 := \left(\left(\left(- \left((4^3)^3 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-2) \right) + 50$$

$$0524342 := \left((2 \times (4^{\sqrt{34}}) + 2) \right) + 50$$

$$0524388 := \left(\left((8 \times 8)^3 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + ((2 \times 50))$$

$$0524394 := \left(\left((4^9) + 3 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + ((2 \times 50))$$

$$0529934 := \left(\left(-((4-3)) + (9^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)^2 \right) - 50$$

$$0531389 := \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{98}^3} \right) + (((1-3) - 50)) \right)$$

$$0531489 := \left((\sqrt{9^{8+4}}) + ((1-3) + 50) \right)$$

$$0537474 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 7)^{-\sqrt{4+7}} \right) - (350) \right)$$

$$0537774 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 7)^{7-\sqrt{7-3}} \right) - 50 \right)$$

$$0537874 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 7)^{(8+7)/3} \right) + 50 \right)$$

$$0541696 := \left(\left((6 + \sqrt{96}) + 1 \right)^{\sqrt{4+5 \times 0}} \right)$$

$$0547547 := \left(- (7) \times \left((4 - (5^7)) + (\sqrt{4} \times (-50)) \right) \right)$$

$$0548764 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((67 \times (8^4)) - 50 \right) \right)$$

$$0556274 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(72 \times \left((6^5) - 50 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0559764 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((6^7) - 9 \right) + 5 \right) - 50 \right)$$

$$0559817 := \left(\left((7-1)^8 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) - ((5+50))$$

$$0583443 := \left(\left((3+4)^4 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{3 \times 8 \times 50}} \right)$$

$$0583929 := \left((92 - \sqrt{9}) \times \left((3^8) + (5 \times 0) \right) \right)$$

$$0584297 := \left(7 \times \left(\sqrt{(9+2 \times 4)^8} - 50 \right) \right)$$

$$0584597 := \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} \times 5 + \sqrt{4})^8} \right) - 50 \right)$$

$$0584697 := 7 \times \sqrt{(9 + \sqrt{64})^8} + 50$$

$$0589744 := \left(- (4) \times \left(- \left((4^7) \times 9 \right) + \sqrt{8 \times 50} \right) \right)$$

$$0589774 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7) \times \sqrt{(7+9)^8} \right) - 50 \right)$$

$$0589804 := \left(\left((4^{08}) \times 9 \right) - \sqrt{8 \times 50} \right)$$

$$0589844 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(4 \times 4)^8} \times 9 \right) + \sqrt{8 \times 50} \right)$$

$$0592654 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 5) \times (6 \times 2) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 50$$

$$0594441 := \left(\sqrt{(1 + 4^4)^4} \times (9 + (5 \times 0)) \right)$$

$$0629596 := \left(\left((6 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) - 260$$

$$0629796 := \left(\left(6^9 / \sqrt{(7+9)^2} \right) - (60) \right)$$

$$0629916 := \left(\left(\sqrt{6^{1+9}} \times (9^2) \right) + (60) \right)$$

$$0635994 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left((9 \times 9) + 5 \right)^3 - 60 \right) \right)$$

$$0635996 := \left(\left((- (6) - \sqrt{9}) + (95) \right)^3 \right) - (60)$$

$$0635999 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((9 \times 9) + 5 \right)^3 - 60 \right)$$

$$0637695 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(5 \times 9)^6} \times 7 \right) - ((3 \times 60)) \right)$$

$$0639744 := \left(- \left((4^4) \times 7 \right) \right) \times (\sqrt{9} - 360)$$

$$0646476 := \left(\left((67 \times \sqrt{4}) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + (60)$$

$$0649599 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(9 \times 9)^5} \times (9 + \sqrt{4}) \right) + (60) \right)$$

$$0655795 := \left(- (5) + \left((\sqrt{97} \times 5) - 5 \right) \times 60 \right)$$

$$0659968 := \left(\sqrt{86} \times \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) + 560 \right) \right)$$

$$0668564 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (6^5) \right) \times (- (86 + (6 \times 0))) \right)$$

$$0668736 := \left(\sqrt{6^{3+7}} \times (86 + (6 \times 0)) \right)$$

$$0668796 := \left(\left(\sqrt{6^{\sqrt{9}+7}} \times 86 \right) + (60) \right)$$

$$0687495 := \left(- (5) \times \left((9^4) - (\sqrt{78} \times 60) \right) \right)$$

$$0699728 := \left(-((8 \times 2)) \times \left(7 + \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-60) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0699834 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (3) + \left(8 \times \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 60 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0699984 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (-8) \right) \times \left(- (9) + \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-60) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0746493 := \left(- (3) - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 4)^6 \right) / (- (4 + (7 \times 0))) \right) \right)$$

$$0746494 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 4)^6 \right) / (- (4 + (7 \times 0))) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0746496 := \left(\left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 4 \right)^{6-4+7 \times 0} \right)$$

$$0746498 := \left(\left(8 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 4)^6 \right) \right) / (4 + (7 \times 0)) \right)$$

$$0746499 := \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 4)^6 \right) / (- (4 + (7 \times 0))) \right) \right)$$

$$0746566 := \left(\left(\left((6+6)^5 \right) \times 6 \right) / \sqrt{4} + (70) \right)$$

$$0746678 := \left(\left((8 \times (7 + (6^6))) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + (70) \right)$$

$$0759305 := \left(5 \times \sqrt{0 \times 3 + 9} \right)^5 - 70$$

$$0759375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 9^5} + 7 \times 0$$

$$0778896 := \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (\sqrt{8^8} - (7 \times 70)) \right)$$

$$0786368 := \left(\left(\left((8^6) \times 3 \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \right) - (70) \right)$$

$$0786494 := \left(\left((4^9) / \sqrt{4} \right) \times 6 \right) - (8 - 70)$$

$$0823457 := \left((7^{5+\sqrt{4}}) - ((3 \times 2) + 80) \right)$$

$$0823777 := \left((7^{\sqrt{7 \times 7}}) - ((3 \times (2 - 80))) \right)$$

$$0824377 := \left((7^7) + (- (3) \times (\sqrt{4} - 280)) \right)$$

$$0824677 := \left(- (7) \times \left(- \left((7^6) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) - (2 \times 80) \right)$$

$$0831488 := \left(\sqrt{8^8} \times ((41 \times 3) + 80) \right)$$

$$0839769 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((6^7) - 93 \right) + 80 \right)$$

$$0839799 := \left(\left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^7 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (3 + (8 \times 0)) \right)$$

$$0844928 := \left((8^2) \times \left((9^4) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + 80 \right)$$

$$0848864 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} - \sqrt{6^8}) \times (-8) \right) \times (\sqrt{4} + 80) \right)$$

$$0858975 := \left(\left((5^7) \times (\sqrt{9} + 8) \right) - (5 \times 80) \right)$$

$$0869616 := \left((6^{\sqrt{16}}) \times (- (9 - 680)) \right)$$

$$0874795 := \left(- (5) - \left(\sqrt{9^7} \times \left((\sqrt{4} - 7) \times 80 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$0888935 := \left(5 \times \left((3^{\sqrt{9+8}}) + (8 \times 80) \right) \right)$$

$$0912977 := \left(\left((77^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 2 \right) + (1 - 90) \right)$$

$$0915759 := \left((957^{\sqrt{5-1}}) - (90) \right)$$

$$0943386 := \left(\left((68^3) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{3^4}} \right) + (90) \right)$$

$$0944694 := \left(\left((4 \times \sqrt{9^{6+4}}) \times 4 \right) - (90) \right)$$

$$0979686 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \times (\sqrt{9} \times 7) \right) \right) - (90) \right)$$

$$0979866 := \left(\left((6^{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}}) \times (\sqrt{9} \times 7) \right) + (90) \right)$$

$$0999901 := \left((10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - ((9 + 90)) \right)$$

$$0999919 := \left(((91 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}}) + (9 - 90) \right)$$

$$1028893 := \left(- \left((3^9) \right) + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}^{20 \times 1}} \right) \right)$$

$$1043199 := \left(\sqrt{9^9} \times ((13 \times 4) + 01) \right)$$

$$1048561 := \left((16^5) - \left((8 \times \sqrt{4}) - 01 \right) \right)$$

$$1048574 := \left((4^{7-5+8}) - \sqrt{4 \times 01} \right)$$

$$1048582 := \left(\left((2 \times 8)^5 \right) + 8 \right) - \sqrt{4 \times 01}$$

$$1048584 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 8)^5 \right) + (8 + ((4 \times 0) \times 1)) \right)$$

$$1048589 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + ((8^5) \times 8)) \times 4 \right) + 01 \right)$$

$$1048829 := - \left((\sqrt{9} - \left((2^8) \times ((8^4) + 01) \right)) \right)$$

$$1049765 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- \left((6^7) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / 4 \right) - 01 \right)$$

$$1057893 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(3+9)^8} + 7 \right) \times (50 + 1) \right)$$

$$1062893 := \left(\left(\left(\left(3^{\sqrt{9+8}} \right) + 2 \right) \times 6 \right) - 01 \right)$$

$$1062894 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(9^{8-2} \right) + (6 \times 01) \right) \right)$$

$$1062943 := \left(\left(\left(\left(3^4 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \right) + ((60 + 1)) \right)$$

$$1062999 := \left(9 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} + 2 \right) \times 6 \right) + 01 \right) \right)$$

$$1078125 := \left(\left(5^{\sqrt{2 \times 18}} \right) \times (70 - 1) \right)$$

$$1119733 := \left(\left(\left((3 + 3)^7 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right) \right) - 11 \right)$$

$$1119742 := \left(\left(\left((2 + 4)^7 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right) \right) - (1 + 1) \right)$$

$$1119743 := \left(\left(\left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{4} \right)^7 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right) \right) - (1 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1119744 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 4 \right)^7 \right) \times ((9 - 1) / (1 + 1)) \right) \right)$$

$$1119746 := \left(\left(\left(6^{\sqrt{4+7}} \right) / 9 \right) + ((1 \times 1) + 1) \right)$$

$$1119765 := \left(\left(\left(5 + (6^7) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right) \right) + (1 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1119766 := \left(\left(\left(6 + (6^7) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right) \right) - (1 + 1) \right)$$

$$1119769 := \left(\left(\left(9 + (6^7) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right) \right) - 11 \right)$$

$$1125576 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^7+5}} \times 5211 \right)$$

$$1126455 := \left(\left(5 + \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{4^6} \right)^2 \right) \right) \times 11 \right)$$

$$1130496 := \left(69 \times \sqrt{4^{03+11}} \right)$$

$$1133595 := \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{9^5} \right) \times (3 \times 311) \right)$$

$$1134895 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{8^4} \right) \right)^3 \right) - (1 + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1134916 := \left(\left(\left(61^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 3 \right) \right) + 11 \right)$$

$$1143578 := \left(\left(- \left(\left((8 + 75)^3 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (- (1 + 1)) \right)$$

$$1145772 := \left(\sqrt{2+7} \times \left(\left(\left(7 - (5^4) \right) \right)^{1+1} \right) \right)$$

$$1145799 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(9 + \left(\left(\left(7 - (5^4) \right) \right)^{1+1} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1146875 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- (7) \times \sqrt{8^{6+4}} \right) + (1 \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1146888 := \left(8 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{8^8} \times (- (6 - 41)) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1149973 := \left(\left(\left(\left(3 + (7 \times 9) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 4 \right) - 11 \right)$$

$$1149986 := \left(\left(\left(- \left((6 - (8 \times 9)) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 4 \right) + (1 + 1) \right)$$

$$1154681 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{1+8} \times 6 \right)^4 \right) - 5 \right) \times 11 \right)$$

$$1154736 := \left(\left((6 \times 3)^{\sqrt{7+4+5}} \right) \times 11 \right)$$

$$1159929 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-5) \right) \right) \right)^{1+1} \right) \right)$$

$$1166345 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 3 \right) \times \left(- (6^6) \right) \right) + 11 \right) \right)$$

$$1166375 := \left(\sqrt{5^7-3} \times \left(\left((6^6) \times 1 \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1168768 := \left(8 \times \left(\left((6 - \sqrt{7^8}) \times (-61) \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1169287 := \left(\sqrt{7^8} \times \left((2 \times \sqrt{9^{6-1}}) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1171687 := \left(\left(\sqrt{7^8} \times (61 \times (7 + 1)) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1171856 := \left(\left(- \left((6 - (5^8)) \right) \times \sqrt{(1 + 7 + 1)} \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1171857 := \left(- \left((7 - ((5^8) + 1)) \right) \times \sqrt{7+1+1} \right)$$

$$1171859 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (5^8) \right) - ((17 \times 1) - 1) \right)$$

$$1171872 := \left(\left(\left((2 - 7) \right)^8 - 1 \right) \times \sqrt{7+1+1} \right)$$

$$1171874 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times \sqrt{(1 + 7 + 1)} \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1179594 := \left(\left(\left(4^{\sqrt{9+5}} \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (7 + 11) \right)$$

$$1179649 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((4^6) \times (97 - 1) \right) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1179684 := \left(\left((4^8) + (6/\sqrt{9}) \right) \times (7 + 11) \right)$$

$$1179864 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{6+8}} + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (71 + 1) \right)$$

$$1187995 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- (99) \times \left(\sqrt{7^8} - 1 \right) \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1191015 := \left(\left((5 + 101)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (1 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1193849 := \left(\left(9 \times \left(\left((48 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 1 \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1193869 := \left(\left(9 \times \left(\left((6 \times 8) + 3 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} + 1 \right) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1194283 := \left(\left(\left(\left((3^8) \times 2 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 91 \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1225449 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^4} + \left((4^5) + 2 \right) \right)^{2 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1228799 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 7) \times (8^2) \right)^2 \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1229314 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((1 + (3 \times 9))^{2+2} \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1236493 := \left(\left(3 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times (\sqrt{4} - ((6^3)))) \right)^2 \right) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1239399 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times (- (9 - (3^9)))) \right) - 3 \right) \times 21$$

$$1239798 := \left(\left(- (8) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{7+\sqrt{9}}} \right) - 3 \right) \right) \times 21 \right)$$

$$1239966 := \left(\left((6/6) - \sqrt{9^9} \right) \times (- (3 \times 21)) \right)$$

$$1239976 := \left(\left((- (6) + (7 \times \sqrt{9^9})) \right) \times (3^2) \right) + 1$$

$$1239997 := \left(\left((7 \times 9) \times \sqrt{9^9} \right) - (32 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1240659 := \left(\left((9^5) + (60/\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 21 \right)$$

$$1241887 := \left(\left((788^{\sqrt{1 \times 4}}) \times 2 \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1245222 := \left(\left(-2 - \sqrt{2^{2 \times 5}} \right) \times (\sqrt{4} - (21)) \right)$$

$$1245457 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times 5) \times \sqrt{4^5} \right) - 4 \right)^2 \right) + 1$$

$$1246589 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9^8} \times 5) \times (\sqrt{6^4} + 2) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1249924 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times (2^9)) + (94) \right)^{2 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1259394 := \left(\left((4^{\sqrt{9}}) \times ((3^9) - 5) \right) + (2 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1259496 := \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 9)^{5-2} \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1259648 := - \left((\sqrt{8^4} - ((6^9 / ((5+2)+1)))) \right)$$

$$1259669 := \left((9 \times ((6^6) \times \sqrt{9}) - 5) \right) + (2 \times 1)$$

$$1259694 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (9 + (6^9 / (5 - 21))) \right) \right)$$

$$1259696 := \left(\left(\left((- (6) \times \sqrt{9}) \times (-6) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + ((5 - 21)) \right)$$

$$1259714 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(- ((1 - 7))^9 \right) / ((5 + 2) + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1264896 := \left(\left(\left((- (6) \times \sqrt{9}) \times (-8) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times (62 - 1) \right)$$

$$1265383 := \left(\left(\sqrt{3^8} \times \left(- (3 - (5^6)) \right) \right) \right) + (2 - 1)$$

$$1265463 := \left(\sqrt{(3+6)^4} \times \left(\left((5^6) - 2 \right) \times 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1265499 := \left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(- ((4 - 56))^{2+1} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1265623 := \left(\left(\sqrt{3^{2+6}} \times (5^6) \right) - (2 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1265625 := \left(\sqrt{(5-2)^6} \times \left((5^6) \times (2+1) \right) \right)$$

$$1265626 := \left(\left(\left((6/2) + 6 \right) \times \sqrt{5^6} \right)^2 \right) + 1$$

$$1265875 := \left(- \left((5^7) \right) + \left(\sqrt{(8 \times 5)^6} \times 21 \right) \right)$$

$$1265949 := \left(\sqrt{9^4} \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((5^6) + 2 \right) - 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1265967 := \left(\sqrt{7^6} + \left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{5^6})^2 \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1268835 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((- (3) + \sqrt{8^8}) \times (-62) \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1272384 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 8)^3 \right) + (2^7) \right)^{2 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1272834 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((3^8) \times \left((2 \times (7^2)) - 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1295999 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((9 + \sqrt{9}) \times 5 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \right) \right) - 1$$

$$1299122 := \left(- (22) \times \left(- (1) - \left((9^{\sqrt{9}+2}) + 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1299276 := \left(- ((6 - 72)) \times \left(\sqrt{9^9} + (2 + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1299595 := \left(- (5) - \left(\left((- (95) \times (- (9) - \sqrt{9}))^2 \right) \times (-1) \right) \right)$$

$$1327598 := \left((8 + 9) \times \left(\sqrt{5^{7 \times 2}} - (31) \right) \right)$$

$$1327832 := \left((2 - \sqrt{3^8}) \times \left(- \left((7^{2+3}) + 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1329696 := \left(\sqrt{(6 \times \sqrt{9})^6} \times \left(- (\sqrt{9} - (231)) \right) \right)$$

$$1336328 := \left(- (8) + \left((2 - 36)^{\sqrt{3 \times 3 + 1}} \right) \right)$$

$$1339892 := \left(\left(\left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) - \sqrt{9} \right)^3 \right) / 3 \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1339894 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4 \times \sqrt{9^8}} - \sqrt{9} \right)^3 \right) / 3 \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1344559 := \left(\left(\left(\left((9+5)^5 \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \times (\sqrt{4}+3) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1347921 := \left((129 \times (7 + \sqrt{4}))^{3-1} \right)$$

$$1349995 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{9}) + \sqrt{9} \right)^4 \right) / (-3) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1354297 := \left((79^2) \times ((\sqrt{4}+5) \times 31) \right)$$

$$1362944 := \left((44^{\sqrt{9}}) \times ((2 \times 6) + 3) + 1 \right)$$

$$1363968 := \left(\left((8 \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / (-3) \right) \times (- (6 + 31))$$

$$1364689 := \left((\sqrt{9^8} \times ((- (6) - \sqrt{4}) + ((6^3)))) \right) + 1$$

$$1368488 := \left(- (88) \times \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4}-8) \right)^6 \right) / (-3) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1369599 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((95 + (\sqrt{9} \times (-6)))^{3 \times 1} \right) \right)$$

$$1369617 := \left(\left((71+6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 6 \right) \times (3 \times 1)$$

$$1374989 := \left((\sqrt{9}+8) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9}+47) \right)^3 \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1375643 := \left((\sqrt{34^6} \times (5 \times 7)) + (3 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1376258 := \left((\sqrt{8^{5 \times 2}} \times (6 \times 7)) + (3 - 1) \right)$$

$$1377928 := \left(- (82) \times (\sqrt{9} - ((7^{7-3+1}))) \right)$$

$$1382974 := \left((\sqrt{4} - ((7 \times 9) \times (28^3))) \right) \times (-1)$$

$$1382976 := \left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(7+9-2)^8}} \right)^{3-1} \right)$$

$$1382977 := \left((\sqrt{7 \times 7} \times (9 \times (28^3))) \right) + 1$$

$$1382979 := \left(\sqrt{9} + ((7 \times 9) \times ((28^3) \times 1)) \right)$$

$$1382997 := \left(- (7) \times \left((\sqrt{9} + (9 \times (28^3))) \right) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1384449 := \left(\left(\sqrt{((9+4) \times 4)^4} \times (8^3) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1394761 := \left(((16 \times 74) - \sqrt{9})^{3-1} \right)$$

$$1399656 := \left(- (6) \times \left(- (5) \times (6^{9-\sqrt{9}}) \right) + (3+1) \right)$$

$$1399679 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9}+7) \times ((6^{9-\sqrt{9}}) \times 3) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1399695 := \left(5 \times (\sqrt{9} + (6^{(9+9)/3+1})) \right)$$

$$1407456 := \left((6^5) \times ((\sqrt{4} \times 70) + 41) \right)$$

$$1411776 := \left((6 \times ((7^{7-1}) - 1)) \times \sqrt{4 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1411779 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((7^{7-1}) - 1 \right) \times 4 \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1414561 := \left(\left((1 - (6 \times 5)) \right)^4 \times \sqrt{1 \times 4} \right) - 1$$

$$1414562 := \left(2 \times \left(\left((6 \times 5) - \sqrt{4} \right) + 1 \right)^{4 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1414564 := \left(\left((4 \times 6) + 5 \right)^4 + 1 \right) \times \sqrt{4 \times 1}$$

$$1417495 := \left(\left(\left((5 \times \sqrt{9}) \right)^4 \times 7 \right) - 1 \right) \times 4 - 1$$

$$1419848 := \left(- (8) - \sqrt{4} \right) + \left((8+9)^{1+4} + 1 \right)$$

$$1419849 := \left(- (9) + \sqrt{4} \right) + \left((8+9)^{1+4} - 1 \right)$$

$$1419852 := \left((\sqrt{25} - (8+9)^{1+4}) \right) \times (-1)$$

$$1419854 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(5 - (8+9)^{1 \times 4 + 1} \right) \right)$$

$$1419858 := \left(\left((8 + (-((5-8) \times \sqrt{9})) \right)^{1+4} \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1419859 := \left(\sqrt{9-5} + (8+9)^{1 \times 4 + 1} \right)$$

$$1419863 := \left(\sqrt{36} + (8+9)^{1 \times 4 + 1} \right)$$

$$1419864 := \left(\sqrt{4} + (6 + ((8+9)^{1+4} - 1)) \right)$$

$$1419871 := \left((17^{8-\sqrt{9}}) + (14 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1419879 := \left((\sqrt{9} \times 7) + ((8+9)^{1+4} + 1) \right)$$

$$1419898 := \left((8+9)^{8-\sqrt{9}} + (1 \times 41) \right)$$

$$1429967 := \left(\left(-((7-69))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (2+4) \right) - 1$$

$$1429968 := \left(((8 + (6 \times 9))^{\sqrt{9}}) \times ((2+4) \times 1) \right)$$

$$1431645 := \left(\left(\left((5 \times \sqrt{4}) + (61) \right)^3 \right) \times 4 \right) + 1$$

$$1431745 := \left(\left((\sqrt{5^4} + (71^3)) \right) \times 4 \right) + 1$$

$$1434669 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\left(\left(6^6 \right) / 4 \right) \times 3 \right) \times 41 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1434699 := \left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\left(6^4 \right) \times 3 \right) \times 41 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1436485 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left(8 \times \left(4 + 63 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1437667 := \left(- \left(7 \right) \times \left(- \left(\left(\left(66 - 7 \right)^3 \right) - \sqrt{4 \times 1} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1441748 := \left(\left(\left(8^{-\sqrt{4+7}} \right) - 1 \right) \times \left(44 \times 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1444797 := \left(- \left(7 \right) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(7^4 \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4 \times 1}} \right) \right)$$

$$1445888 := \left(\sqrt{8^8} + \left(\left(\left(\left(8^5 \right) \times 44 \right) \times 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1448817 := \left(\left(- \left(7 \right) + \sqrt{188^4} \right) \times 41 \right)$$

$$1449423 := \left(\left(3^2 \right) \times \left(-4 + \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{4} \right)^{4+1} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1449549 := \left(9 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 5 \right) + \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{4} \right)^{4+1} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1449983 := \left(\left(3 \times \left(\left(8^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 944 \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1453966 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(6^6 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(\left(35^4 \right) \times 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1456849 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(9^4 \right) + 8 \right) - \left(6^5 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4 \times 1}} \right)$$

$$1458798 := \left(\left(- \left(89 \right) \times \left(- \left(7 \right) + \left(- \left(\left(8^5 \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1469583 := \left(\sqrt{3^8} \times \left(\left(\left(5 + 9 \right) \times \left(6^4 \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1469595 := \left(\left(\left(\left(5 + 9 \right) \times \left(- \left(5 \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right)^4 \right) \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1469664 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(6 + 6 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right)^{4 \times 1} \right) \right)$$

$$1469665 := \left(\left(56 \times \left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1469667 := \left(\left(\left(7 \times \left(\left(6^6 \right) \times 9 \right) \right) + 6 \right) / \sqrt{4 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1470464 := \left(\left(4^6 \right) \times \left(\left(40 \times \left(7 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1474379 := \left(\left(\left(9 \times \left(7 + 3 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(4^7 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1474547 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(7 - \left(45 \times \left(4^7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + 1$$

$$1474558 := \left(\left(\left(85 + 5 \right) \times \left(4^7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1474559 := \left(\left(\left(\left(95 - 5 \right) \times \left(4^7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1474585 := \left(- \left(5 \right) \times \left(\left(- \left(\left(8^5 \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 7 \right) \right) - \left(4 + 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1474594 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(9 \times \left(\left(5 \times \left(4^7 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1474596 := \left(\left(- \left(6 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(- \left(\left(5 \times \left(4^7 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4 \times 1} \right) \right)$$

$$1474739 := \left(\left(\left(9 \times \left(3 + 7 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(4^7 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1475995 := \left(- \left(5 \right) \times \left(\left(- \left(\left(9 - \left(9^5 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(7 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1476225 := \left(\sqrt{\left(5 + 22 \right)^6} \times \left(74 + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1478488 := \left(88 \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(8 - \left(7^{4+1} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1478968 := \left(8 \times \left(- \left(6 \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 8 \right) \times \left(- \left(7^{4+1} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1478983 := \left(- \left(\left(3 + 8 \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(8 \times \left(7^{4+1} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1480599 := \left(\left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(\left(508 \times 4 \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1481544 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(4^5 \right) \right) / \left(1 + 8 \right) \right) \right)^{4-1} \right)$$

$$1481765 := \left(- \left(5 \right) \times \left(\left(\left(\left(6 \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{1+8}} \right) \times \left(-4 \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1484449 := \left(\left(\sqrt{94^4} \times 4 \times 84 \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1485169 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} - 1 \right) \right)^5 \right) / 8 \right) - \left(4 - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1485184 := \left(4 \times \left(\sqrt{8+1} + \left(5 + 8 \right)^{4+1} \right) \right)$$

$$1486849 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(86 \right) \right) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1487456 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(6 - \left(5^4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{7^8} + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - 1$$

$$1492928 := \left(\left(8^2 \right) \times \left(\left(\left(9 \times 2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 4 \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1492984 := 4 \times \left(\sqrt{\left(8 \times 9 \right)^{2 \times \sqrt{9}}} - \sqrt{4 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1492986 := -6 + \sqrt{\left(8 \times 9 \right)^{2 \times \sqrt{9}}} \times 4 \times 1$$

$$1492988 := \left(\left(8 - \left(\left(\left(8 \times 9 \right) \times 2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) / \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1492989 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(9 \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 2 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 4 \right) + 1$$

$$1492991 := \left(\left(\left(\left(1 \times 9 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(\left(2^9 \right) \times 4 \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1492993 := \left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left((2^9) \times 4 \right) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1492994 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left(\left((2^9) \times 4 \right) \times 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1492996 := \left(\left(\left(\left(6 + \left(\left((9 + \sqrt{9})^2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1492998 := \left(\left(\left((8 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4 \times 1}$$

$$1494784 := \left(\sqrt{4^8} \times \left(7 + \left((\sqrt{4} \times 9)^{4-1} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1495728 := \left((8 + ((27 \times 5) \times 9))^{\sqrt{4}} - 1 \right)$$

$$1495909 := \left((\sqrt{9^{09}} \times (-5 + \sqrt{9^4})) + 1 \right)$$

$$1497845 := 5 \times (48 \times \sqrt{79^4} + 1)$$

$$1498176 := \left((\sqrt{6^{7+1}} - (8 \times 9))^{\sqrt{4 \times 1}} \right)$$

$$1498745 := \left(\left((5^4) \times (\sqrt{7^8} - \sqrt{9}) \right) - (4 + 1) \right)$$

$$1499796 := \left(-(6) \times \left(\left((9 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9^4} \right) \times (-1) \right) \right)$$

$$1517568 := (\sqrt{8^6} \times (57 \times (1 + 51)))$$

$$1518744 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(4 - \left(\left((7 + 8) \times 1 \right)^5 + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1518745 := \left(-(5) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((7 + 8) \times 1 \right)^5 \times 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1518746 := \left(-(6) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(\left((7 + 8) \times 1 \right)^5 + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1518749 := - \left((\sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{4} \times (- \left(\left((7 + 8) \times 1 \right)^5 + 1 \right)))) \right)$$

$$1518751 := \left((\sqrt{-1 + 5} \times \left((7 + 8) \times 1 \right)^5 \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1518764 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(6 + \left(\left((7 + 8) \times 1 \right)^5 + 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1518786 := \left(-(6) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(8 + 7)^8} + 1 \right) \times (-5) \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1520875 := \left(((5 \times 7) + 80)^{\sqrt{2 \times 5 - 1}} \right)$$

$$1529437 := \left(\left((7^3)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \left(((9 - 2) + 5) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1532644 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times (- (4 - 623)))^{\sqrt{5 - 1}} \right)$$

$$1536048 := \left(8 \times \left((\sqrt{40^6} \times 3) + (5 + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1539648 := \left(\left((8 - \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \times \left(((9 \times 3) + 5) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1542564 := \left((46 \times ((5^2) + \sqrt{4}))^{\sqrt{5 - 1}} \right)$$

$$1544497 := \left(((7^{\sqrt{9}}) + 4) \times 4451 \right)$$

$$1556249 := \left(((\sqrt{9^4} + 2) \times (6 \times (5^5))) - 1 \right)$$

$$1561967 := \left(- \left((7^6) \right) + \left((9 \times \sqrt{16})^{5-1} \right) \right)$$

$$1562476 := \left(\left(-(6) + \left((7 - \sqrt{4})^{2+6} \right) \right) \times (5 - 1) \right)$$

$$1562519 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 1) \times \left((5^{2+6} + 5) \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1562564 := \left(\sqrt{4^6} + \left(\left((5^{2+6}) \times (5 - 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1568658 := \left(\sqrt{(8 + 5)^6} \times ((8 + 6) \times 51) \right)$$

$$1572668 := \left(\left((8^6) \times 6 \right) - \sqrt{(2 \times 7)^{5-1}} \right)$$

$$1572834 := \left(\left(\left(4^{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) + (2 - 7) \right) \times (5 + 1) \right)$$

$$1572848 := \left(8 \times \left(\left((4^8) \times \sqrt{2 + 7} \right) - \sqrt{5 - 1} \right) \right)$$

$$1572849 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((\sqrt{4}^{-8+27}) - (5 \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1572894 := \left(\left(\left((4^9) + 8 \right) - \sqrt{2 + 7} \right) \times (5 + 1) \right)$$

$$1572946 := \left((6 \times ((4^9) + (2 \times 7))) - \sqrt{5 - 1} \right)$$

$$1574946 := \left(-(6) \times \left(- \left(\left((4^9) + 4 \right) - \sqrt{7^5 + 1} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1575025 := \left(5 + \sqrt{20 \times 5^7} \right)^{\sqrt{5 - 1}}$$

$$1579764 := \left((\sqrt{4} - ((6 \times (7 + 9)))) \times \left(- \left((7^5) - 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1579952 := \left((\sqrt{25} - 99) \times \left(- \left((7^5) + 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1579954 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((5 - 99) \times \left((7^5) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1585947 := \left(\left(7 - \left(\left((4 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \right) / 8 \right) \right) \times (-51) \right)$$

$$1586898 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(8 + 9)^8} \times ((6 + 8) + 5) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1592644 := \left(4 \times \left((\sqrt{4} + (629))^{\sqrt{5 - 1}} \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1593592 &:= \left(-2 - \left(\sqrt{9^5} \times \left(3 - \left(9^{5-1}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1593593 &:= \left(\left(\left(-3 + \sqrt{9^{5+3}}\right) \times \sqrt{9^5}\right) - 1\right) \\
 1593599 &:= -\left(\left(\left(9^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \left(\left(5 + \left(3^{9+5-1}\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1593669 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(9^6\right) - \left(6^3\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) - (5 + 1)\right) \\
 1593975 &:= \left(-5 - \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \left(\left(3^{9+5-1}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594083 &:= \left(-3 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{80^4} - \left(\left(9^{5+1}\right)\right)}\right)\right) \\
 1594089 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(-80 + \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(\left(9^{5+1}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594233 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(-32 + \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(\left(9^{5+1}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594239 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-\left(\left(32 - 4\right) - \left(9^{5+1}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594269 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(6 - 24\right) + \left(9^{5+1}\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594271 &:= \left(-1 + \left(\left(\sqrt{7 + 2^{4+9}}\right) - (51)\right)\right) \\
 1594274 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\sqrt{7 + 2^{4+9}}\right) - (51)\right)\right) \\
 1594279 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{7+2+4}}\right) - \left(\left(9 \times 5\right) - 1\right)\right) \\
 1594294 &:= -\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (24)\right) \times \left(-\left(\left(9^5\right) - 1\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594297 &:= \left(\left(-\left(\left(7 - \left(9^{2+4}\right)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) - (5 \times 1)\right) \\
 1594299 &:= \left(\left(9 / \sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(-\left(\left(2 \times 4\right) - \left(9^{5+1}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594302 &:= -20 + 3^{\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}+5}} - 1 \\
 1594343 &:= \left(\left(3 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left(3^4\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + 5\right)\right)\right) - 1\right) \\
 1594345 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(\left(3 \times \left(4 + \left(9^{5+1}\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594346 &:= 6 \times 4 + 3^{\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}+5}} - 1 \\
 1594349 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(4 + \left(\left(\left(3^4\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + 5\right)\right)\right) - 1\right) \\
 1594357 &:= 7 \times 5 + 3^{\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}+5}} - 1 \\
 1594376 &:= \left(\left(\left(6 + \left(7 \times 3\right)\right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(9^5\right)\right)\right) - 1\right) \\
 1594378 &:= 8 \times 7 + 3^{\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}+5}} - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1594384 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(8 + \left(\left(3^{4+9}\right) + 51\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594388 &:= 8 \times 8 + 3^{\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}+5}} + 1 \\
 1594398 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{9}\right) + \left(\left(\left(3^{4+9}\right) + 51\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594449 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(44 - \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(\left(9^{5+1}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594499 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{9+4}}\right) + \left(4 \times \left(\left(9 \times 5\right) - 1\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594533 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(35 \times \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(\left(9^{5+1}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594659 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(56 \times \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(\left(9^{5+1}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594699 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(9^6\right)\right) + \left(\left(4 \times \left(95 - 1\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1594809 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{08} + \sqrt{4}}\right) \times \sqrt{9^5 \times 1}\right) \\
 1594899 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\sqrt{9 \times 8^4} + \left(\left(9^{5+1}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1595539 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^{3+5}} + 5\right) \times \sqrt{9^5}\right) + 1\right) \\
 1596474 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \sqrt{7^{4+6}}\right) \times (-95)\right) - 1\right) \\
 1597536 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(3 + \left(57 \times 9\right)\right)^{\sqrt{5-1}}\right)\right) \\
 1597959 &:= \left(-9 - \left(\left(-5 - \sqrt{9^7}\right) \times \sqrt{9^{5+1}}\right)\right) \\
 1598932 &:= \left(\left(-\left(\left(2^3\right) + \sqrt{9^8}\right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^5} + 1\right)\right)\right) \\
 1599984 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(8 \times \left(\left(\left(9/9\right) + 9\right)^5 - 1\right)\right)\right) \\
 1613469 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\left(6 + \sqrt{4^3}\right)^{-1+6}\right) - 1\right)\right) \\
 1613472 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times 7\right)^{\sqrt{4+3}}\right) \times \left(\sqrt{16} - 1\right)\right) \\
 1613473 &:= \left(\left(3 \times \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{4}\right)^{\sqrt{31-6}}\right)\right) + 1\right) \\
 1613998 &:= \left(-8 + \left(\sqrt{9^9} \times \left(\left(3^{\sqrt{16}}\right) + 1\right)\right)\right) \\
 1633938 &:= \left(-83 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(3^{3+6}\right)\right)\right) \times (-1)\right)\right) \\
 1635841 &:= \left(-1 + \sqrt{4^8} \times 5\right)^{-3+6-1} \\
 1637856 &:= \left(-6 \times \left(-\left(\left(5^8\right)\right) - \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{36}}\right) \times (-1)\right)\right)\right) \\
 1646593 &:= \left(\left(3 \times \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{5^6}\right) \times \left(4^6\right)\right)\right) + 1\right) \\
 1646764 &:= \left(\left(-46 - \left(-\left(\left(7^6\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \times (6 + 1)\right) \\
 1646848 &:= \left(8 - \sqrt{4}\right)^8 - \sqrt{64^{6-1}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1646878 := \left(\left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{(7+8)^6} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 61 \right)$$

$$1647025 := \left(\left((5+2)^{07} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - (61)$$

$$1647073 := \left(\left(- \left(3 - (7^{07}) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - (6+1)$$

$$1647074 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (7^{07}) \right) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times -(6 \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1647077 := \left(\left((7^7) - 07 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + (6-1)$$

$$1647079 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - (7^{07}) \right) \right) \times (4-6) - 1$$

$$1647081 := \left(\left(- \left((1-8)^{07} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - (6-1)$$

$$1647086 := \left((6+8)^{07} \right) / \sqrt{4^6 \times 1}$$

$$1647092 := \left(\left(- \left((2-9)^{07} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + (6 \times 1)$$

$$1647147 := 7^{(\sqrt{4}-1) \times 7} \times \sqrt{4} + 61$$

$$1647342 := \left(2 \times \left((4+3)^7 + \sqrt{4^{6+1}} \right) \right)$$

$$1647767 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{7^6} + (7^7) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - (6-1)$$

$$1647774 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((7^7) + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}^6}} \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1648384 := \left(\sqrt{4^8} \times \left((3^8) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times (-61) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1648649 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-4) \right) + \sqrt{6^8} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - (6+1) \right)$$

$$1648657 := \left(\left(- \left((7+5) \right) + \sqrt{6^8} \right)^{-4+6} + 1 \right)$$

$$1648662 := \left(\left(- \left((2 \times 6) \right) + \sqrt{6^8} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + (6 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1649273 := \left((3^7) + \left(2 \times \left((9 - \sqrt{4})^{6+1} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1649487 := \left(\sqrt{7^8} + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((9 - \sqrt{4})^{6+1} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1662567 := \left(\left((7 - (6^5)) \right) \times \left(2 - \sqrt{6^6} \right) \right) + 1$$

$$1664466 := \left(\left(\left((6 - (6^4)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + ((6 \times 61)) \right)$$

$$1664928 := (82 \times 94) \times \sqrt{6^6 \times 1}$$

$$1666494 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((9^4) \times (66 + 61) \right) \right)$$

$$1666975 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{(7 \times \sqrt{9})^6} \times -(6 \times 6) \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1669264 := \left(-4 + \sqrt{6^{2 \times 9}} \right)^{6/6+1}$$

$$1676544 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{4+5}} - (6^7) \right) \times -(6 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1678286 := \left(\left((6^8) - \sqrt{(\sqrt{2 \times 8} + 7)^6} \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1678586 := \left((6^8) - \left(- \left((5-8) \right) \times \sqrt{7^6} \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1678863 := \left(\left(\sqrt{36^8} \right) + ((8 - 761)) \right)$$

$$1678886 := \left(\left((6^8) - \sqrt{(8+8-7)^6} \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1679266 := \left(- (6) + \left((6^{2 \times 9}) - (\sqrt{7^6} + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1679267 := \left(- (7) + \left((6^{2 \times 9}) - (\sqrt{7^6} - 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1679269 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left((6^{2 \times 9}) - (\sqrt{7^6} + 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1679275 := \left(\left(- (57) + \left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^7 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) + 1$$

$$1679423 := \left(\left(- (32) + \left(\sqrt{4 \times 9^7} \right) \right) \times 6 \right) - 1$$

$$1679447 := \left(\left((7 \times 4) - \left(\sqrt{4 \times 9^7} \right) \right) \times (-6) \right) - 1$$

$$1679488 := \left(\left((8 \times 8) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left((\sqrt{9^7} \times 6) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1679539 := \left((9-3)^{5+\sqrt{9}} - ((76+1)) \right)$$

$$1679548 := \left(\left((8 - \sqrt{4})^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) - ((7+61)) \right)$$

$$1679561 := \left(- (1) + \left((6^{5+\sqrt{9}}) + ((7-61)) \right) \right)$$

$$1679564 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((6^{5+\sqrt{9}}) + ((7-61)) \right) \right)$$

$$1679567 := \left(- (7) + \left((6^{5+\sqrt{9}}) - ((7 \times 6) \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1679596 := 6^{\sqrt{9}+5} - \sqrt{9+7} \times (6-1)$$

$$1679599 := \left(-\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{((9-5) \times 9)^7} \right) \times 6 + 1$$

$$1679611 := \left(-1 + \sqrt{(\sqrt{16} \times 9)^7} \right) \times 6 + 1$$

$$1679618 := (\sqrt{8+1} + ((6^{9-7+6}) - 1))$$

$$1679619 := \sqrt{9} + 1 \times 6^{9-7+6 \times 1}$$

$$1679645 := \left(\left(\left(5 + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (- (6-9)) \right)^7 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1679646 := \left(6 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (- (6-9)) \right)^7 \right) + (6-1) \right) \right)$$

$$1679742 := \left(\left((2+4)^7 \right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-7) \right) \right) \times (6 \times 1)$$

$$1679743 := \left(\left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{4})^7 \right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-7) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1679744 := \left(\left((4 - \sqrt{4})^7 \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^7} \times 6 \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1679766 := 6 \times (6^7 + \sqrt{9+7} \times 6 + 1)$$

$$1679843 := \left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{4})^8 \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-76) \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1679844 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^8 \right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times (76 \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1679886 := \left(\left((6^8) - (8 \times 9) \right) + \sqrt{76} \right) - 1$$

$$1679935 := \left(\left(\left(53 + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^7 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1679956 := \left((6^{5+\sqrt{9}}) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{76} \right) \times (-1) \right) \right)$$

$$1679976 := \left(\left((6^7) - \sqrt{9} \right) + ((9 \times 7)) \right) \times (6 \times 1)$$

$$1679982 := \left(-((2-8)) \times \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^7 \right) + (61) \right) \right)$$

$$1689039 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + (30))^{v_9} \right) \times ((8 \times 6) - 1) \right)$$

$$1692586 := \left(\left((\sqrt{6^8} + 5)^2 \right) - ((9+6) \times 1) \right)$$

$$1694397 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{9})^3 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times 61$$

$$1694763 := \left(3 \times \left(\left((6 \times 7) / \sqrt{4} \right)^{v_9} \right) \times 61 \right)$$

$$1699299 := \left(\sqrt{9^9} + \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^9 \right) / (6 \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1718976 := \left(\left(- \left((6^7) \right) - \sqrt{9^8} \right) + 1 \right) \times (- (7-1))$$

$$1727999 := \left(\left((9 + \sqrt{9}) \times (\sqrt{9} + 7) \right)^{\sqrt{2+7}} - 1 \right)$$

$$1728725 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{(2 \times 7)^8} \times (- (2+7)) \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1728729 := \left(9 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{(2 \times 7)^8} \times (- (2-7)) \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1738659 := \left(\left((9^5) + (6^8) \right) - \sqrt{37-1} \right)$$

$$1741823 := \left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{2 \times 8})^{1+4} \right) \times 7 \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1742994 := \left(\left((499^2) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 7 \right) + 1$$

$$1744888 := \left(- (8) + \left(\sqrt{8^8} \times \left((\sqrt{4} + 4) \times 71 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1744893 := \left(- (3) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (- (8^4)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times 71 \right)$$

$$1744894 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (- (8^4)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times 71 \right) \right)$$

$$1744896 := \left(- \left((6-9) \times (8^4) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times 71$$

$$1744899 := \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (- (8^4)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times 71 \right)$$

$$1745464 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left((6 \times (4^5)) \right) \right) \times (4 \times 71) \right)$$

$$1746884 := \left(\left((4 + \sqrt{8^8}) \times (-6) - 4 \right) \times (-71) \right)$$

$$1747625 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((2+6)^7 - \sqrt{4} \right) / (- (7-1)) \right) \right)$$

$$1756879 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((7 \times (8^6)) - ((5^7) + 1) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1764674 := \left(- \left((4 - (7^6)) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + (6+7) \right) \right) - 1$$

$$1764753 := \left(3 \times \left(\left(5 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} \right) \right) + (7-1) \right) \right)$$

$$1764759 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(5 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} \right) \right) + (7+1) \right) \right)$$

$$1769384 := \left(\left((4^8) - 3 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} - (7 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1769464 := \left(\left((4^{v_{64}}) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} \right) - (7+1) \right)$$

$$1769478 := \left(\left((8^{7-\sqrt{4}}) \times (9 \times 6) \right) + (7-1) \right)$$

$$1769479 := \left(\left((9+7)^4 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} \right) + (7 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1769484 := \left(\left((48^4) / \sqrt{9} \right) + ((6+7) - 1) \right)$$

$$1769486 := \left(\left((6 \times 8)^4 / \sqrt{9} \right) + ((6+7) + 1) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1769499 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 9 \times (4^{9+6-7} + 1) \\
 1769537 &:= (\sqrt{7^{3+5}} \times (\sqrt{9^6} + (7 + 1))) \\
 1769849 &:= ((9 \times ((4^8) \times \sqrt{9}) + (6 \times 7))) - 1) \\
 1769958 &:= (((8^5) + 9) \times 9) \times \sqrt{6 \times (7 - 1)} \\
 1771499 &:= (9 + (((9 + \sqrt{4})^{-1+7}) - 71)) \\
 1771554 &:= -((\sqrt{4} + ((5 - (((5 - 1) + 7)^{7-1})))))) \\
 1771559 &:= (\sqrt{9} - ((5 - (((5 - 1) + 7)^{7-1})))) \\
 1771649 &:= (((9 + \sqrt{4})^6) + (17 + 71)) \\
 1771875 &:= (5 \times 7) \times \sqrt{(8 \times 1 + 7)^{7+1}} \\
 1774842 &:= ((-2) + \sqrt{48^4}) \times 771 \\
 1776384 &:= (\sqrt{4^8} \times ((3 + 6) \times 771)) \\
 1784656 &:= ((-6) - \sqrt{56^4}) \times (-8 \times 71)) \\
 1791972 &:= (((2 + 7) \times 91) \times (\sqrt{9^7} + 1)) \\
 1791999 &:= (9 \times (\sqrt{9} + (91 \times (\sqrt{9^7} + 1)))) \\
 1793613 &:= ((-(((3^{16}) / 3)) + \sqrt{9}) / (-7 + 1)) \\
 1796984 &:= -(((4 - 8) \times \sqrt{9})^6 - (((9^7) - 1))) \\
 1796986 &:= -\sqrt{(\sqrt{6^8} / 9)^6} + 9^7 + 1 \\
 1799424 &:= (\sqrt{4^{2 \times 4}} \times (99 \times 71)) \\
 1801855 &:= (55 \times (\sqrt{8^{10}} - (8 - 1))) \\
 1815848 &:= (((8 \times \sqrt{4}) \times 8) - (5 + 1))^{\sqrt{8+1}} \\
 1824065 &:= (-5) \times (-((604^2)) + \sqrt{8+1}) \\
 1824759 &:= (((-95) \times \sqrt{7^{4 \times 2}}) \times (-8)) - 1) \\
 1833496 &:= (((6^{\sqrt{9}}) - ((4^3)^3)) \times (-8 - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1834889 &:= (((9 + 8) - (\sqrt{8^4^3})) \times (-8 - 1)) \\
 1834924 &:= (\sqrt{4^{2 \times 9}} - 4 \times 3) \times (8 - 1) \\
 1834927 &:= ((7 \times ((2^9)^{\sqrt{4}})) + (\sqrt{3^8} \times (-1))) \\
 1834945 &:= ((5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (-9) + ((4^3)^{\sqrt{8+1}})) \\
 1834946 &:= (-6) - ((-((4^9)) + \sqrt{4^3}) \times (8 - 1)) \\
 1834947 &:= (((7 \times (4^9)) - (4^3)) + \sqrt{8+1}) \\
 1834949 &:= -((\sqrt{9} + ((-((4^9)) + \sqrt{4^3}) \times (8 - 1)))) \\
 1834952 &:= (2 + 5) \times (-9) + ((4^{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}}) + 1) \\
 1834973 &:= (((-((3 - 7))^9) - \sqrt{4}) - 3) \times (8 - 1) \\
 1834975 &:= (-5) + (-7) \times (\sqrt{9} - ((4^{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}}) - 1)) \\
 1834978 &:= (-8) + ((-7) \times (\sqrt{9} - (4^{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}})) - 1) \\
 1834979 &:= (-9) + ((-7) \times (\sqrt{9} - (4^{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}})) + 1) \\
 1834987 &:= (7 \times (8^{\sqrt{9 \times 4}})) - (3 \times (8 - 1)) \\
 1843968 &:= (((8 - (6 \times (9 - 3)))^4) \times \sqrt{8+1}) \\
 1844479 &:= (((\sqrt{9} \times (7^4)) + \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{4^8}) - 1) \\
 1849372 &:= (2 + \sqrt{(7 - 3)^9})^{\sqrt{4}} \times (8 - 1) \\
 1849427 &:= ((7 \times (((2 + \sqrt{4^9})^{\sqrt{4}}) + 8)) - 1) \\
 1849428 &:= ((8 + ((2 + \sqrt{4^9})^{\sqrt{4}})) \times (8 - 1)) \\
 1859799 &:= (9 \times ((9 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}})) - (((5^8) - 1)) \\
 1865577 &:= (\sqrt{(7 \times 7)^5} \times ((5 \times 6) + 81)) \\
 1865952 &:= -(((2^5) \times 9)) \times ((-5) \times \sqrt{6^8}) + 1) \\
 1866155 &:= (-5) \times (((\sqrt{5-1} - (6^6)) \times 8) + 1) \\
 1866185 &:= (-5) \times ((8 \times (1 - (6^6))) + \sqrt{8+1})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1866229 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 2 \right) \times \left(- \left(2 - \left(\left(6^6 \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1866297 := \left(\left(\left(7 - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 2 \right) \times \left(- \left(6^6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1866325 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\left(-2 - \sqrt{36^6} \right) \times 8 \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1866435 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\left(\left(- (3) - \sqrt{4} \right) - \left(6^6 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1866965 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\left(\left(- (6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(6^6 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1874146 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{6^4} + 1 \right)^4 \right) - \left((7 + 8) \times 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1874161 := \left(1 + \sqrt{\left(6 \times 1 \right)^4} \right)^{\sqrt{7+8+1}}$$

$$1874949 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(9 - 4 \right)^7 \right) \right) \times (-8) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1874975 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(5^7 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(4 - 7 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1874979 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left(7 - \left(\left(\left(9 - 4 \right)^7 \right) \times 8 \right) \times 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1874985 := \left(- \left(\left(5 - \left(8 \times \left(9 - 4 \right)^7 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{8+1} \right)$$

$$1874991 := \left(\left(\left(- (1) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(9 - 4 \right)^7 \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \right) - 1$$

$$1874995 := \left(- (5) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\left(9 - 4 \right)^7 \right) \times 8 \right) \times 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1874999 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\left(9/9 \right) + 4 \right)^7 \right) \times 8 \right) \right) - 1$$

$$1875024 := \left((4 + 20) \times \left(\left(5^{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}} \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1875048 := \left(8 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(05^7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{8+1} \right) \right)$$

$$1875049 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(05^7 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1875168 := \left(\left(8 \times \left((6 + 1) + \left(5^7 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{8+1} \right)$$

$$1875169 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((6 + 1) + \left(5^7 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1875189 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(8 \times \left(\left((1 \times 5)^7 \right) + 8 \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1875688 := \left(8 \times \left(86 - \left(- \left(\left(5^7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{8+1} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1875863 := \left(\left(3 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} + \left(5^7 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1875939 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\left(39 + \left(5^7 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1879569 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right)^5 \right) - \sqrt{\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right)^8} \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1879896 := \left(\left(6 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times \left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{7^8} \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1879982 := \left(\left(- \left(\left((2 - 89) \times 9 \right) \times \sqrt{7^8} \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1879984 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (89) \right) \times (-9) \right) \times \sqrt{7^8} \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1882387 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}^3 \right) \times (2 \times 8) \right) + \sqrt{8+1} \right) \right)$$

$$1882389 := \left(\left(\left(\left(98^3 \right) \times 2 \right) + 8 \right) - \sqrt{8+1} \right)$$

$$1882447 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(7^{\sqrt{4+4}} \right) \times (-2) \right) - 8 \right) \times (-8) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1882727 := \left(\left(7^2 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{\left(7 \times 2 \right)^8 + (8 - 1)} \right) \right)$$

$$1882777 := \left(\left((7 \times 7) \times \left(\sqrt{\left(7 \times 2 \right)^8 + 8} \right) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1884995 := \left(\left(59^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 8 \right) \right)^{8 \times 1} \right) \right)$$

$$1885472 := \left(\left(\left((2 \times 7) + 4 \right)^5 \right) - \sqrt{8^8 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1886561 := \left(- (1) - \left(- (6) \times \left(- (5) + \left(68^{\sqrt{8+1}} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1886564 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(- (6) \times \left(- (5) + \left(68^{\sqrt{8+1}} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1886592 := \left(\left((2 + 9) - 5 \right) \times \left(68^{\sqrt{8+1}} \right) \right)$$

$$1886616 := \left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{16} + \left(68^{\sqrt{8+1}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1886628 := \left((8 - 2) \times \left(6 + \left(68^{\sqrt{8+1}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1889496 := \left(\left(\left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^{-4+9} \right) - (8 \times (8 + 1)) \right) \right)$$

$$1889529 := \left(\left((9 \times 2)^5 \right) - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 8 \right) \times (-8) \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1889536 := \left(\left((6 \times 3)^5 \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right) + (8 \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1889549 := \left(\left(\left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right)^5 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - \left((8 + 8) \times 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1889562 := \left(\left(-2 - \left(- \left(\left(6^5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{8+1} \right)$$

$$1889563 := \left(\left((3 \times 6)^5 \right) - \sqrt{9 + 8 + 8 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1889564 := \left(-4 - \left(\left(\left(6^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) / (-8) \right) \times (8 + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1889567 := \left(\left(\left((7 + 6) + 5 \right)^{\sqrt{9+8+8}} \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1889568 := \left((8 - 6)^5 \times \sqrt{9^8 \times 81} \right)$$

$$1889569 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 6)^5 \right) + \left((9 - 8)^8 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1889576 := \left(\left((6 + 7) + 5 \right)^{-\sqrt{9+8}} + (8 \times 1) \right)$$

$$1889581 := \left(\left((18^5) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((8 + 8) \times 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1889587 := \left(\sqrt{7^8} \times \left(- (5 - ((9 \times 88) \times 1)) \right) \right)$$

$$1889594 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 9)^5 \right) + \left(((9 + 8) + 8) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1889596 := \left(\left((6 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \right) + \sqrt{98 \times 8 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1889599 := \left((9 + 9)^5 + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 8) + (8 - 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1889616 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(1 - \left(- (6) \times \sqrt{9^8} \right) \right) \times \left(- (8 \times 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1889639 := \left(\left(- (9) - \left(36 \times \sqrt{9^8} \right) \right) \times \left(- (8) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1889649 := \left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{4})^{6-9+8} \right) + (81) \right)$$

$$1889658 := \left(\left(- \left((8 - (5^6)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^8}} + 1 \right)$$

$$1889946 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left((4 + \sqrt{9^9}) \times \left(- (8 + 8) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1890549 := \left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{4})^5 \right) - (0 - 981) \right)$$

$$1893664 := \left((4^6) + \left((6 \times 3)^{-\sqrt{9+8 \times 1}} \right) \right)$$

$$1893995 := \left((5^9) - \left((\sqrt{9} \times (3^9)) + (81) \right) \right)$$

$$1896129 := \left(\left((9 \times 2)^{-1+6} \right) + \sqrt{9^8 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1906622 := \left(-2 - \left(\left((2^6) + 60 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(-1 \right) \right)$$

$$1906624 := \left(\left((4 - 2)^6 + 60 \right)^{\sqrt{9 \times 1}} \right)$$

$$1906625 := \left(\left((5 \times 26) - 6 \right)^{\sqrt{09}} + 1 \right)$$

$$1908168 := \left(\left(86^{\sqrt{1+8}} \right) \times \sqrt{09 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1908169 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((6 \times 1) + 80 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1913597 := \left(- (7) \times \left(\left(- \left((9 \times 5)^3 - 1 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1920986 := \left(\left((\sqrt{6^8} + (90))^2 \right) - (9 + 1) \right)$$

$$1924723 := \left(\left((327^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (2 \times 9) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1925616 := \left(616 \times \left((5^{2+\sqrt{9}}) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1928262 := \left(\left(- (2) + \sqrt{(6 \times 2)^8} \right) \times (2 + 91) \right)$$

$$1928439 := \left(- (9) + \left(\sqrt{(3 \times 4)^8} \times (2 + 91) \right) \right)$$

$$1928448 := \left(- \left((8 - (4^4)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{(8 - 2)^{9+1}}$$

$$1928934 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (3^9) \right)) \times \left(- ((8 \times 2)) \times \sqrt{9} - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1928976 := \left((6 \times 7) \times \left((\sqrt{9^8} \times \left(- (2 - 9) \right)) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1929375 := \left(- \left((5 \times 7)^3 \right) \right) \times \left((\sqrt{9} + 2) \times \left(- (9 \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1932589 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 8)^5 - 2 \right) \times (3 + 9) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1935349 := \left((9 + 4) \times \left(- (3) + \left((53^{\sqrt{9}}) - 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1935388 := \left(((8 + 8) - 3) \times \left((53^{\sqrt{9}}) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1937664 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + ((66 \times 7))) \times 3 \right)^{\sqrt{9}-1} \right)$$

$$1943999 := \left((9 \times \left(((9 + 9) - 3) \times 4 \right)^{\sqrt{9}}) - 1 \right)$$

$$1944392 := \left(\left((29 \times 34)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times (\sqrt{9} - 1) \right)$$

$$1944799 := \left(9 - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 7)^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(- (9 + 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1944932 := \left(\left((2 + 3)^9 - \sqrt{4^{4+9}} \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1944934 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^9 - \sqrt{4^{4+9}} \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$1945085 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((80 - 5) - \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(-1 \right) \right)$$

$$1947995 := \left((5^9) - \left((\sqrt{9} + 7) \times (\sqrt{4^9} + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1949747 := \left(\left((7 \times (4^7)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left((\sqrt{4} \times 9) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1950939 := \left(\left(- \left((9^3) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} - \left(0 - \left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1951399 := - \left(\left(\left((9 + \sqrt{9})^3 \right) - \left((1 + ((5^9) + 1)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1951589 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9 \times 8^{5+1}} - ((5^9)) \right) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1951776 := \left(\left((6^7) \times 7 \right) - \sqrt{(1+5)^{9+1}} \right)$$

$$1951794 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(\sqrt{4+9})^{7-1}} - ((5^9)) \right) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1951795 := \left((5^9) - \left(((7-1) + 5)^{\sqrt{9}} - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1951829 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(\sqrt{9} \times 2)^8} \times (-1) \right) + \left(((5^9) \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1951845 := \left((-5) \times \sqrt{4^8} - (1 - ((5^9) + 1)) \right)$$

$$1951974 := \left(\sqrt{4^7} \times (-9) + \left(((1 \times 5)^9 + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1952437 := \left((-((7^3)) \times \sqrt{4}) - (2 - ((5^9) \times 1)) \right)$$

$$1952449 := \left(\left(\left((9+4) \times \sqrt{4} \right)^2 - ((5^9)) \right) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1952478 := \left((-8) \times \left((7 + \sqrt{4})^2 \right) + \left(((5^9) + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1952498 := \left(\left(\left((8 - \sqrt{9})^4 \right) + (2 - (5^9)) \right) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1952499 := - \left(\left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{9}) - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 - \left(((5^9) - 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952548 := - \left(\left(\left((8 \times \sqrt{4+5})^2 \right) - \left(((5^9) - 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952596 := \left(\left(\left((6 \times \sqrt{9}) + 5 \right)^2 - ((5^9)) \right) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1952614 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times (-16^2) + \left(((5^9) + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1952625 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(5 \times 2)^6} / (-2) \right) + \left(((5^9) \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1952639 := \left((-9) \times \sqrt{3^6} \times 2 + \left(((5^9) \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1952734 := \left(\sqrt{4^3} \times (-7^2) + \left(((5^9) + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1952743 := \left((-3) \times \sqrt{4^7} + \left((2 + ((5^9) \times 1)) \right) \right)$$

$$1952764 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 6) + 7 \right)^2 - ((5^9)) \right) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1952767 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{7^6} + \left((7 \times 2) - \left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952775 := \left(\left((5^7) - (7 \times 2) \right) \times (5^{\sqrt{9}-1}) \right)$$

$$1952779 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left((7 \times (7^2)) - (5^9) \right) \right) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1952789 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-((8 \times 7) \times 2)) + \left(((5^9) \times 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952797 := - \left(\left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) - (7 \times 2) + \left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952875 := \left(\left((5^7) - 8 \right) - 2 \right) \times (5^{\sqrt{9}-1})$$

$$1952881 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(1+8)^{8+2}}} - \left(((5^9) - 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952883 := \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(3+8)^8} \times (-2)} + \left(((5^9) \times 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952884 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4^8} - (8 \times 2) + \left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952895 := \left((5^9) - \left((82 - 5) \times \sqrt{9} - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1952906 := - \left(\left((6^{\sqrt{09}}) + \left((2 - ((5^9) - 1)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952925 := \left(\left(\sqrt{5^2^9} \right) - (25 \times (9 - 1)) \right)$$

$$1952928 := - \left(\left(\left((8 + (2 \times \sqrt{9}))^2 \right) - \left(((5^9) - 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952929 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} + (2 + 9))^2 \right) - ((5^9)) \right) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1952934 := \left((-((4^3)) \times \sqrt{9}) + \left((2 + ((5^9) - 1)) \right) \right)$$

$$1952936 := \left((-63) \times \sqrt{9} - \left((\sqrt{25^9}) \times (-1) \right) \right)$$

$$1952941 := \left(\sqrt{1 \times 4} \times (-92) + \left(((5^9) \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1952943 := \left(3 - \left((\sqrt{4} \times 92) - \left(((5^9) - 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952944 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left((\sqrt{4} \times 92) - \left(((5^9) + 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952945 := \left((-5) \times \sqrt{(4 \times 9)^2} + \left(((5^9) \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1952947 := \left(7 - \left((\sqrt{4} \times 92) - \left(((5^9) - 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952955 := - \left(\left(\left((5 + 5) + \sqrt{9} \right)^2 - \left(((5^9) - 1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1952959 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-5 \times (9 + 2)) + \left(((5^9) - 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1952962 := \left((-2) \times \left((6 + \sqrt{9})^2 \right) + \left(((5^9) - 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1952977 := \left(-((7 \times 7) \times \sqrt{9}) - (2 - ((5^9) + 1)) \right)$$

$$1952996 := - \left(\left(\left((6/\sqrt{9})^{9-2} \right) - \left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1953019 := \left((\sqrt{9} + (103 - (5^9))) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1953034 := - \left((\sqrt{4} + ((30 \times 3) - ((5^9) + 1))) \right)$$

$$1953039 := \left(\sqrt{9} - \left((30 \times 3) - ((5^9) + 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1953086 := \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8} + (03 - (5^9))} \right) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1953098 := \left(-(8 \times \sqrt{9}) - (03 - ((5^9) \times 1)) \right)$$

$$1953109 := \left((\sqrt{9} + (013 - (5^9))) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1953151 := \left(\sqrt{(1 \times 5)^{1+3} + ((5^9) + 1)} \right)$$

$$1953161 := \left(-(1) + \sqrt{6^{1+3}} + ((5^9) + 1) \right)$$

$$1953184 := \left((-4 + \sqrt{8^{1+3}}) + ((5^9) - 1) \right)$$

$$1953208 := \left(\sqrt{80^2} + (3 + ((5^9) \times 1)) \right)$$

$$1953219 := \left(\sqrt{91^2} + (3 + ((5^9) \times 1)) \right)$$

$$1953244 := \left(((\sqrt{4} - 42) \times (-3)) + ((5^9) - 1) \right)$$

$$1953247 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(7+4)^{23}} + ((5^9) + 1)} \right)$$

$$1953249 := \left(\left((9 + \sqrt{4})^2 \right) + (3 + ((5^9) \times 1)) \right)$$

$$1953263 := \left((\sqrt{36} \times 23) + ((5^9) \times 1) \right)$$

$$1953264 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((6 \times 23) + ((5^9) - 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1953268 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(8 \times 6)^2} \times 3 \right) + ((5^9) - 1) \right)$$

$$1953274 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(((7^2) \times 3) + ((5^9) \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1953283 := \left((\sqrt{3^8} \times 2) - (3 - ((5^9) - 1)) \right)$$

$$1953286 := \left((\sqrt{6^8} / (2^3)) + ((5^9) - 1) \right)$$

$$1953294 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times ((9^2) + 3)) + ((5^9) + 1) \right)$$

$$1953306 := \left((60 \times \sqrt{3 \times 3}) + ((5^9) + 1) \right)$$

$$1953318 := \left((\sqrt{8^{1+3}} \times 3) + ((5^9) + 1) \right)$$

$$1953343 := \left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{4})^3 \right) + (3 + ((5^9) - 1)) \right)$$

$$1953344 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^3 \right) + (3 + ((5^9) \times 1)) \right)$$

$$1953345 := \left(5 + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 3)^3 \right) + ((5^9) - 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1953347 := \left((74 \times \sqrt{3 \times 3}) + ((5^9) \times 1) \right)$$

$$1953348 := \left(8 + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 3)^3 \right) + ((5^9) - 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1953349 := \left(9 + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 3)^3 \right) + ((5^9) - 1) \right) \right)$$

$$1953359 := \left(\sqrt{9^5} - (3 \times 3) - ((5^9) \times 1) \right)$$

$$1953365 := \left(\left((5^{6+3}) + (3^5) \right) - \sqrt{9 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1953427 := \left((\sqrt{7^2} \times 43) + ((5^9) + 1) \right)$$

$$1953445 := \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{(4 \times 4)^3} \right) + ((5^9) \times 1) \right)$$

$$1953455 := \left(\left((55 \times \sqrt{4}) \times 3 \right) + ((5^9) \times 1) \right)$$

$$1953459 := \left(-(9) - \left(\left((5 + \sqrt{4})^3 \right) + ((5^9)) \right) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1953468 := \left(\left(((8 + 6) / \sqrt{4})^3 \right) + ((5^9) \times 1) \right)$$

$$1953475 := \left((5^{7+\sqrt{4}}) + (35 \times (9 + 1)) \right)$$

$$1953489 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 3 \right) + ((5^9) + 1) \right)$$

$$1953495 := \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{4}) \times 3 \right) + ((5^9) + 1) \right)$$

$$1953499 := \left((\sqrt{9} \times (9 - 4)^3) + ((5^9) - 1) \right)$$

$$1953574 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times (75 \times 3)) + ((5^9) - 1) \right)$$

$$1953599 := \left((\sqrt{9} - (9 \times 53) + (5^9)) \times (-1) \right)$$

$$1953634 := \left(\sqrt{4^{3+6}} - (3 - ((5^9) \times 1)) \right)$$

$$1953635 := \left(\sqrt{(5+3)^6} - (3 - ((5^9) + 1)) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1953637 &:= \left(\sqrt{(7-3)^{6+3}} + \left(\left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1953693 &:= \left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 63 \right) + \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1953694 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((9 \times 63) + \left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1953764 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4^6} \times (7+3) \right) + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1953783 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \times 73 \right) + \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1953794 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (9 - (7^3)) \right) \right) + \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1953853 &:= \left(\sqrt{3^{5+8}/3} + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1953899 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + (83) \right) \right) + \left(\left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954084 &:= \left((480 \times \sqrt{4}) + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954086 &:= \left(\left((6 \times 80) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954149 &:= \left(\left(- ((9-41))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \left(\left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954213 &:= \left(\sqrt{(31+2)^4} + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954278 &:= \left(\left((8 \times 72) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954375 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{5^{7+3}} + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{5^{9-1}} \right) \\
 1954386 &:= \left(\sqrt{6^8} - \left(\left(34 - \left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954456 &:= \left(\sqrt{(6+5)^{\sqrt{4}+4}} + \left(\left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954493 &:= \left(\left((39 - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954497 &:= \left(\left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{4 \times 4} \right) + \left(\left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954568 &:= \left(\sqrt{(8+6 \times 5)^4} + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954596 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{9^5} + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954647 &:= \left(\left(- ((7-46))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954677 &:= \left((776 \times \sqrt{4}) + \left(\left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1954917 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left((1 + \sqrt{9})^4 \right) \right) + \left(\left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1954945 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{5^{4 \times 9}}} + 4 \times 5 \times 91 \\
 1955174 &:= \left(\sqrt{4^{7-1+5}} + \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1955279 &:= \left(\sqrt{9^7} - \left((2^5) - \left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1955364 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4^6} \times 35 \right) + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1955429 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{2^{\sqrt{4^5}}}} \right) + \left(\left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1955527 &:= \sqrt{7^{-2+5+5}} + 5^9 + 1 \\
 1955625 &:= \sqrt{5^{2+6}} \times (5^5 + \sqrt{9} + 1) \\
 1955681 &:= \left(\left((1 - \sqrt{8^6}) \times (-5) \right) + \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1955682 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(\left(\sqrt{8^6} \times 5 \right) + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1955683 &:= \left(- (3) - \left(\left(\sqrt{8^6} \times (-5) \right) - \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1955684 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\sqrt{8^6} \times (-5) \right) - \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1955685 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{8^6} \right) + \left(\left(5 \times (5^{9-1}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1955689 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\sqrt{8^6} \times (-5) \right) - \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1955935 &:= \left(\sqrt{53^{9-5}} + \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1956196 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{(9-1)^6} \right) + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1956198 &:= \left(\left((8^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (1 \times 6) \right) + \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1956499 &:= \left(\sqrt{(9 + \sqrt{9 \times 4})^6} + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1956874 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(\sqrt{4}-7)^8} \times 6 \right) + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1957214 &:= \left(\sqrt{4^{12}} - \left(7 - \left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1957485 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{5^8} - \sqrt{4}) \times 7 \right) + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1958749 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{(\sqrt{4}-7)^8} \right) + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1958949 &:= \left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(8 - \left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1959551 &:= \left(\left((1+5)^5 \right) \times (\sqrt{9^5} + 9) \right) - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1959566 := \left(\left(\left(\left((6^6) \times (5+9) \right) + 5 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1959689 := \left(\sqrt{9^8} - \left(\left((6-9) - \left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1959874 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((7+8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) + \left(\left((5^9) - 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1959984 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left((8+9) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(\left((5^9) \times 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1959985 := \left(\left(\left(- (5) - \left(- (8) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(\left((5^9) + 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1964736 := \left(\left(\left((6^3) \times 7 \right) + 4 \right) \times \sqrt{6^{9-1}} \right)$$

$$1965895 := \left(- (5) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - (8^5) \right) \times (6 \times (9+1)) \right) \right)$$

$$1967328 := \left(\left((82 \times 3) + 7 \right) \times \sqrt{6^{9+1}} \right)$$

$$1967483 := \left(\left(\left((38^4) - (7^6) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1968299 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \times \left((2+8)^{6/\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1968617 := \left(- (7) \times \left(1 - \left(\sqrt{6^8} \times \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1974995 := \left((5^9) - \left(\sqrt{\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{4}}} \right)^7} \times \left(- (9+1) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1978767 := \left(- (7) \times \left(- \left((6^7) \right) - \left((8 \times (7^{\sqrt{9}})) + 1 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1979649 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 469 \right)^{-7+9 \times 1} \right)$$

$$1982464 := \left(\left(\left((4 \times 6) - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) \times \sqrt{8^{9-1}} \right)$$

$$1982465 := \left(\sqrt{(5+6)^4 \times 2 \times 8^9 + 1} \right)$$

$$1985894 := \left(\left((4^9) / 8 \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}} \right) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1986767 := \left(\left(- (7) \times \left(- \left((6^7) \right) - \sqrt{(6^8) \times 9} \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1987983 := \left((3^8) \times \left(- (9) + (78 \times (\sqrt{9} + 1)) \right) \right)$$

$$1989988 := \left(\left(\sqrt{8^8} \times 9 \right) + \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - 8) \right)^9 \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1989989 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - 8) \right)^9 \right) - \left(- (9) \times \sqrt{8^{9-1}} \right) \right)$$

$$1990656 := \left((6^5) \times \left(\left(6 / \sqrt{09} \right)^{9-1} \right) \right)$$

$$1992495 := \left(\left((5^9) + 4 \right) + \left(2 \times \sqrt{9^9 \times 1} \right) \right)$$

$$1993744 := \left(\left(4 + \left(4 \times \left((7^3) + 9 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9-1}} \right)$$

$$1994544 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (4+5) \right)^4 \right) \times \left((9+9) + 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1996499 := \left(\left((9 + \sqrt{9}) \times \left((46 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1997445 := \left(- (5) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left((4 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times (-91) \right) \right)$$

$$1997626 := \left(- (6) - \left(\left(- \left((2-6) \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-91) \right) \right)$$

$$1997629 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(- \left((2-6) \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-91) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$1997632 := \left(\left(\left(- (2) + \sqrt{36} \right) \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 91 \right)$$

$$1998848 := \left((8^4) \times \left(\left((8 \times 8) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (9-1) \right) \right)$$

$$1998858 := \left(\left((8^5) \times \left((8 \times 8) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + (9+1) \right)$$

$$1999872 := \left((2^7) \times \left(\left((8 - \sqrt{9})^{9-\sqrt{9}} \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$1999982 := \left(\left((2+8)^{9-\sqrt{9}} - 9 \right) \times (\sqrt{9} - 1) \right)$$

$$2031614 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{16}} \times (1+30) \right) - 2 \right)$$

$$2039184 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (81 \times 9) \right) - 30 \right)^2 \right)$$

$$2055188 := \left(\left(\sqrt{8^8} - \sqrt{-1+5} \right) \times 502 \right)$$

$$2056186 := \left(- (6) + \left(\left(8^{\sqrt{16}} \right) \times 502 \right) \right)$$

$$2056189 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(8^{\sqrt{16}} \right) \times 502 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2056191 := \left(- (1) + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 1)^6 \right) \times 502 \right) \right)$$

$$2056192 := \left(\sqrt{(2 \times (9-1))^6} \times 502 \right)$$

$$2056194 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 1)^6 \right) \times 502 \right) \right)$$

$$2064384 := \left(\left(- \left((4^8) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^4} + (60)} \right) \right) / (-2) \right)$$

$$2064969 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left((6 + (9 \times \sqrt{4})) \times 60 \right) \right) \right)^2 \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2082249 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - ((4 - 22) \times 80) \right)^2 \right) \\
 2088978 &:= \left((8^7) - \left((9 - \sqrt{88}) \times (0 - 2) \right) \right) \\
 2094592 &:= \left((2^9) \times \left(- (5) + \left((4^{\sqrt{9}})^{02} \right) \right) \right) \\
 2095972 &:= \left(\left((2^7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (590 \times 2) \right) \\
 2095978 &:= \left((8^7) + \left((\sqrt{9} - 590) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 2097062 &:= \left((2 + 6)^{07} - \sqrt{90^2} \right) \\
 2097064 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 6)^{07} \right) - ((90 - 2)) \right) \\
 2097147 &:= \left((- (7) + \sqrt{4}) + \left((1 + 7)^{9-02} \right) \right) \\
 2097149 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + (4 + 1))^7 \right) - \sqrt{9 + 0 \times 2} \right) \\
 2097164 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times 6) + \left((1 + 7)^{9-02} \right) \right) \\
 2097194 &:= \left(- \left((4^{9+1}) \right) + \left(- (7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times (0 - 2) \\
 2097197 &:= \sqrt{(7 \times 9 + 1)^7} + 90/2 \\
 2097329 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((2^3)^7 \right) + (90 \times 2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2097497 &:= \left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4^7}^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 02 \right) \right) \\
 2097899 &:= \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) + \left((8^7) + (9 \times 02) \right) \right) \\
 2098178 &:= \left((8^7) + \left((1 + (8^{\sqrt{9}})) \times 02 \right) \right) \\
 2098446 &:= \left(\left((6^4) - \sqrt{4} \right) + \left((8^{9-02}) \right) \right) \\
 2098448 &:= \left(\left((8 - \sqrt{4})^4 \right) + \left((8^{9-02}) \right) \right) \\
 2099665 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((6^6) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-9) - 02 \right) \right) \\
 2101245 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((2^{10}) + 1 \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2116549 &:= \left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{4})^5 \right) + (61^{1+2}) \right) \\
 2117679 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((7^6) \times (7 - 1) \right) - (1^2) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2119928 &:= \left(- (8) + \left((2 \times \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) - 1 \right))^{1 \times 2} \right) \right) \\
 2119944 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) - 1 \right)^{1 \times 2} \right) \right) \right) \\
 2122849 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{9^4} \times ((8 \times 2) + 2)) - 1 \right)^2 \right) \\
 2125744 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(7 - \left((5 - 2)^{12} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2125798 &:= \left(\left(\left((8 + (\sqrt{9}^{7+5})) \right) \times 2 \right) + 1 \right) \times 2 \\
 2125824 &:= \left(\sqrt{(4 \times 2)^8 \times (521 - 2)} \right) \\
 2128681 &:= \left(\sqrt{18^6 / (8 \times 2) + 1} \right)^2 \\
 2136549 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(9 \times 4 + 5)^6 \times 31} \right) - 2 \right) \\
 2137454 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times 5) + \left((4 \times (731^2)) \right) \right) \\
 2137459 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} \times 5) + \left((4 \times (731^2)) \right) \right) \\
 2137484 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(\left(- (8) - \sqrt{4} \right) - \left((731^2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2140369 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9^6} + 3) \times \sqrt{04} \right) - 1 \right)^2 \right) \\
 2145447 &:= \left(\left(- \left((7 + (4 \times 4))^5 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) / \left(- (1 + 2) \right) \right) \\
 2146688 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{8^6} + 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 12 \right) \right) \\
 2154888 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(8 + \left((8^{\sqrt{4+5}}) - 1 \right) \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 2163841 &:= \left(\left(- (1) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(8 + \left((3^6) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \right)^2 \right) \\
 2169729 &:= \left(\left(9 + \left((27 - \sqrt{9}) \times 61 \right) \right)^2 \right) \\
 2177709 &:= \left((907 \times \sqrt{7^7+1}) + 2 \right) \\
 2178576 &:= \left(\left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- (7) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) - 71 \right) \right)^2 \right) \\
 2185454 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 54) - 5 \right)^{\sqrt{8+1}} \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 2186952 &:= \left(\left(- (2) + \sqrt{(5 \times 9)^6} \right) \times (8 \times (1 + 2)) \right) \\
 2187582 &:= \left(\left(- (28) \times \left(- \left((5^7) \right) - \sqrt{8+1} \right) \right) - 2 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2194875 := \left(5 \times \left(\left((78 - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (1^2) \right) \right)$$

$$2194885 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(-((8 - 84))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (1^2) \right) \right)$$

$$2194895 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(((9 \times 8) + 4)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (1 + 2) \right) \right)$$

$$2196988 := \left(\left(((8 \times (8 + 9)) - 6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 12 \right)$$

$$2199289 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 8) - \left((-2) \times (9^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) - 1 \right) \right)^2 \right)$$

$$2204496 := \left(\left(\left((6 \times \sqrt{9})^4 \right) \times ((40 + 2) / 2) \right) \right)$$

$$2214144 := \left(\left(\left((-4 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{14}}}) \times 12 \right) \right)^2 \right)$$

$$2228732 := \left((2 \times \sqrt{37^{8-2}}) \times 22 \right)$$

$$2238728 := \left(8 \times \left(\left(2 + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} \times 3} \right) \right) \right)^{2+2} \right)$$

$$2239464 := \left(-4 \times \left(\left((6^{\sqrt{49}}) - \sqrt{3^2} \right) \times (-2) \right) \right)$$

$$2239468 := \left((8 \times \left((6^{\sqrt{49}}) - 3 \right)) + (2 + 2) \right)$$

$$2239499 := \left(9 + \left(\left(9 \times \left((4 \times \sqrt{9})^{3+2} \right) \right) + 2 \right) \right)$$

$$2239768 := \left(8 \times \left(\left((6^7) + \sqrt{9} \right) + \sqrt{32^2} \right) \right)$$

$$2243862 := \left(\left(-2 - \sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} \right) \times \left(- (3^{4 \times 2 + 2}) \right) \right)$$

$$2248367 := \left((\sqrt{7^6} \times \left(\left((3^8) - 4 \right) - 2 \right)) + 2 \right)$$

$$2249737 := \left((7^3) \times \left(\left((79 + \sqrt{4})^2 \right) - 2 \right) \right)$$

$$2249998 := \left(\left(\left(\left((8^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (9 \times 4) \right)^2 \right) - 2 \right)$$

$$2274064 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} - 60) \right) \times \left(-((4 \times 7) - 2) \right) \right) \right)^2$$

$$2275875 := \left((5 \times 7) \times \left(\left(85 \times \sqrt{7+2} \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2275959 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((5 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \right) - (722) \right) \right)$$

$$2286146 := \left(\left(\left((6^{4-1}) + \sqrt{6^8} \right)^2 \right) + 2 \right)$$

$$2289789 := \left(\sqrt{9^8} \times \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + ((8/2) + 2) \right) \right)$$

$$2294784 := \left((\sqrt{4^8} - 7) \times \left((4 + 92)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2296726 := \left(\left(-62 \right) \times \left(\left((7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / (-2) \right) \right) - 2$$

$$2296728 := \left(\sqrt{\left((8 - 2) \times 7 \right)^6 \times (9 + 22)} \right)$$

$$2296869 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((6 + 869)^2 \right) - 2 \right) \right)$$

$$2298368 := \left(\sqrt{8^6} \times \left(\left((3 - ((8 \times 9) - 2)) \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2299946 := \left(\left((6 \times ((4 + 9) + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (22) \right)$$

$$2299957 := \left(\left(\left((7 + (5^{\sqrt{9}}))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{(9 + 2)^2} \right) \right)$$

$$2299964 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times (69 - \sqrt{9}))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (2 + 2) \right) \right)$$

$$2299966 := \left(\left((66^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left((9 - \sqrt{9}) + 2 \right) \right) - 2 \right)$$

$$2299968 := \left(8 \times \left((69 - \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9 \times 2 / 2}} \right) \right)$$

$$2299969 := \left(\left(\left((9 + 6) \times 9 - \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (2/2) \right)$$

$$2299972 := \left(\left(\left(2 \times \left((7 \times 9) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (2 + 2) \right)$$

$$2304324 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(42 - 3)^4} - 03 \right) \right)^2$$

$$2313441 := \left(\left((1 \times 4) - 43 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{(1+3)^2}}$$

$$2313473 := \left(\left((37 + \sqrt{4})^{3+1} \right) + 32 \right)$$

$$2316484 := \left((\sqrt{4^8} - \sqrt{4}) \times 6 - \sqrt{1+3} \right)^2$$

$$2326528 := \left(\sqrt{8^{2 \times 5}} \times \left(62 + (3^2) \right) \right)$$

$$2328485 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{5^8} + \sqrt{4^8})^2 \right) \times 3 \right) + 2 \right)$$

$$2341454 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 541)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 3 \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$2343456 := \left(6 \times \left(\left(5^{\sqrt{4^3}} \right) - \left((4 + 3)^2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2343852 := \left(\left((2 \times (5^8)) + 34 \right) \times \sqrt{3^2} \right)$$

$$2343856 := \left((-6) \times \left(- \left((5^8) \right) - \left((3 \times \sqrt{4}) \times 3 \right) \right) \right) - 2$$

$$2344366 := \left(\left((663 \times 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) / 3 \right) - 2$$

$$2346687 := \left(7 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{8^6} + (64 + 3) \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2352637 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times 3) \times 6 \right) + 2 \right) + 5 \right)^{\sqrt{3^2}}$$

$$2352974 := \left(\left(-4 \right) \times \left(\left((7^{\sqrt{9}})^2 \right) \times (-5) \right) \right) - (3 \times 2)$$

$$2352989 := \left(\left(\left((98^{\sqrt{9}}) / (-2) \right) \times (-5) \right) + (3^2) \right)$$

$$2358789 := \left(- \left((9 \times 8) \times \left(7 - (8^5) \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{3^2}$$

$$2358792 := \left((2^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left(- \left((7 - (8^5)) \times (3^2) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2359249 := \sqrt{9} \times \left(\sqrt{4^{2 \times 9}} - 5 \right) \times 3 - 2$$

$$2359299 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(9 \times \left((2 \times (9 - 5))^{3 \times 2} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2359343 := \left(\left(3 \times \left(\left((4^3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 5 \right) \times 3 \right) \right) + 2$$

$$2359349 := \left(\left(9 \times \left((4^3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) + \sqrt{53^2} \right)$$

$$2359394 := \left(\left((4^9) - 3 \right) \times 9 \right) + \sqrt{(5^3)^2}$$

$$2359429 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^2} \times \left((4^9) + (5 \times 3) \right) \right) \right) - 2$$

$$2359584 := \left((4 + (8^5)) \times \sqrt{(9 \times (5 + 3))^2} \right)$$

$$2359629 := \left(9 \times \left(\left((2^6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (5 + 32) \right) \right)$$

$$2361945 := \left(\left((54^{\sqrt{9}}) - 1 \right) \times \left(6 + (3^2) \right) \right)$$

$$2361958 := \left(\left((8 \times 5) \times \sqrt{9^{1+6+3}} \right) \right) - 2$$

$$2365444 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4^{4+5} \times (6 + 3)} \right)^2$$

$$2367488 := \left(\left((8 \times (8 + \sqrt{4^7}))^{6/3} \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$2371844 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((4 \times 8) + 1 \right)^{7-3} \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$2375998 := \left(\left((8 + \sqrt{9}) \times \left((\sqrt{9} + (57))^3 \right) \right) \right) - 2$$

$$2379456 := \left(\left((6 \times 5) + 4 \right) \times \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times 32$$

$$2383887 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} - \left((8 + (3 \times (8^3)))^2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2383928 := \left(-8 \right) + \left(\left((2^{\sqrt{9}}) + (3 \times (8^3)) \right)^2 \right)$$

$$2383936 := \left(\left((6/3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (3 \times (8^3)) \right)^2$$

$$2386594 := \left(\sqrt{49^5} \times ((68 + 3) \times 2) \right)$$

$$2387879 := \left(\left((9^7) - 8 \right) - (\sqrt{7^8} \times 3) \right) / 2$$

$$2391489 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9^{8+4+1}}) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-3) \right) / (-2)$$

$$2414916 := \left(-6 \right) \times \left(\left(-1 \right) \times \sqrt{9} - \left((4 \times 1)^4 \right) \right)^2$$

$$2421133 := \left(-3 \right) + \left((3112/\sqrt{4})^2 \right)$$

$$2421134 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left((3112/\sqrt{4})^2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2421139 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((3112/\sqrt{4})^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2433598 := \left(\left(\left((8^{\sqrt{9}}) + (5 + 3) \right) \times 3 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 2 \right)$$

$$2434596 := \left(-6 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((5^4) + (3 \times 4) \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2437631 := \left(-1 \right) + \left(\left(\left((3^6) + 7 \right) \times 3 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} / 2 \right)$$

$$2437634 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left((3^6) + 7 \right) \times 3 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} / 2 \right) \right)$$

$$2439837 := \left(\left(-7 \right) + \left((38 + (\sqrt{9} \times 3))^4 \right) \right) / 2$$

$$2439839 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left((38 + (\sqrt{9} \times 3))^4 \right) \right) \right) / (-2)$$

$$2449225 := \left(\left((522 \times \sqrt{9}) - (4/4) \right)^2 \right)$$

$$2449926 := \left(\left((62 + 9) \times 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times (4 + 2) \right)$$

$$2449998 := \left(\left((8 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 44 \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$2455489 := \left((\sqrt{9^{8/4}} + 5^5) / \sqrt{4} \right)^2$$

$$2457458 := \left(\left(- \left((8^5) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-75) \right) + (4 \times 2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2457558 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{8^{5+5}} \times 75 \right) - 42 \right) \\
 2457588 &:= \left(- \left(\left(8 - \left(\left(8^5 \right) \times 75 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4^2} \right) \\
 2457594 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}} \right)^5 \right) \times 75 \right) - (4 + 2) \right) \right) \\
 2458624 &:= \left(-4 \times (2 + 6) + \sqrt{(8 \times 5)^4} \right)^2 \\
 2459385 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\left(8 - (3^9) \right) \times \sqrt{5^4} \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 2459995 &:= \left(- (5) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{9^9} \right) \times \sqrt{5^{4+2}} \right) \right) \\
 2465286 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left((8 \times 2) + \left(5^{6-\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 2470619 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((1 + 6)^{07} \right) - 4 \right) \right) + 2 \right) \\
 2470749 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(7^{07} \right) + 42 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2470776 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(\left(7^7 \right) + \sqrt{07^4} \right) / (-2) \right) \right) \\
 2471184 &:= \left(4 + 8 \times \sqrt{\left((1 + 1) \times 7^4 \right)} \right)^2 \\
 2472662 &:= \left(\left(2 - (6^6) \right) \times \left(\left(-2 - \sqrt{7^4} \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 2472766 &:= \left(\left((6^6) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{7^2} \times 7 \right) + 4 \right) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 2472984 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 8 \right) \times \left(\left((92 \times 7) - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2473984 &:= \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{4} \times 8^9 \times (3 + 74 \times 2)} \right) \\
 2477799 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left(\left(9 - (7^7) \right) - \left((7^4) - 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2479375 &:= 5^{7-3} \times \left(\sqrt{(9 \times 7)^4 - 2} \right) \\
 2479377 &:= \left(\left(\left(7^7 \right) \times 3 \right) + \sqrt{9^7 \times 4^2} \right) \\
 2479776 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- (7) \times \left(- (7) + \left(9^{7-\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 2479931 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(\left(3 - \left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{9+7}}} \right) \right) \times 42 \right) \right) \\
 2479934 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(3 - \left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{9+7}}} \right) \right) \times 42 \right) \right) \\
 2479974 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(\left(9^{7-\sqrt{4}} \right) - 2 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2479976 &:= \left(\left((6 \times 7) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{9+7}}} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + 2 \right) \\
 2479986 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \times (-7) \right) + 4 \right) \right) / (-2) \right) \right) \\
 2479994 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(-4 - \left(- (9) \times \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \times (-7) \right) + 4 \right) \times (-2) \right) \\
 2483776 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (6) \times \left(- (7) - \sqrt{(7-3)^8} \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) \\
 2486929 &:= \left(\left(929 + \sqrt{6^8 / 4} \right)^2 \right) \\
 2488416 &:= 6 \times \left(\sqrt{(1-4)^8} \times 8 - 4 \right)^2 \\
 2489975 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(7 + \left(\left(998^{\sqrt{4}} \right) / (-2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2489995 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(998^{\sqrt{4}} \right) / (-2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2490084 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (800 - 9) \right) - 4 \right)^2 \right) \\
 2490368 &:= \left(\left(\left(8^6 \right) \times \left(- \left((30 - 9) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) / (-2) \right) \\
 2491389 &:= \left(- (9) - \left(\left((8 + 31)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-42) \right) \right) \\
 2492856 &:= \left(\left(\left(6^5 \right) - 82 \right) \times \left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 2494877 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(\left((7 \times 84) + 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 2 \right) \right) \\
 2495535 &:= \left((5 \times 3) \times \left(\left(55^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (4 + 2) \right) \right) \\
 2495559 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(5 \times \left(\left(55^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 4 \right) \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 2495565 &:= \left(\left((5 \times 6) \times \left(\left(55^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 4 \right) \right) / 2 \right) \\
 2495595 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(\left(55^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (4 - 2) \right) \right) \\
 2499235 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(5^3 \right) + 2 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^9} - 4 \right) \right) + 2 \right) \\
 2499741 &:= \left(-1 + \sqrt{4^7} \right) \times \sqrt{9 \times 9^{4 \times 2}} \\
 2499743 &:= \left(-3 + \sqrt{4^7 \times 9} \right) \times 9^4 + 2 \\
 2519394 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(4^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(3^9 \right) \right) - 15 \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 2519429 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\left((2 + 4)^9 \right) / (1 - 5) \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 2519454 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 54 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 15 \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 2519469 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(6^{\sqrt{49}} \right) + \sqrt{(1 \times 5)^2} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2534464 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 6 \right) \times \left(- \left(44 - \left(3^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)^2 \\
 2534976 &:= \left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) \times 9 \right) - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 3 \right)^5 \right) \times (-2) \right) \right) \\
 2537649 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-6) \right) + \left(7 \times \left(3^5 \right) \right) \right) \right)^2 \\
 2544968 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(\left(6 \times 94 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \left(\left(5^2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2548982 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(2 + \left(89 \times 8 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 5 \right) + 2 \right) \\
 2552448 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{8^4} + 4 \right)^2 \right) \times 552 \right) \\
 2554676 &:= \left(\left(- (6) + \left(- (76) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 5 \right)^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (-2) \\
 2559975 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(5 \times (7+9) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{5^2} \right) \\
 2559977 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(77 + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 5 \right) \times 5 \right) + 2 \right) \\
 2559998 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(89 - 9 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{5 \times 5} \right) - 2 \right) \\
 2566404 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{40^4} + \sqrt{-6/6+5} \right)^2 \right) \\
 2571489 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(\left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{4} \right) + 1 \right) \times \left(7^5 \right) \right) + 2 \right) \right) \\
 2572288 &:= \left(\sqrt{8^8} \times \left(- \left(\left(\left(2 - \left(2^7 \right) \right) \times 5 \right) + 2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2573872 &:= \left(\sqrt{\left(2 \times 7 \right)^8} \times \left(- \left(3 - \left(\left(7 \times 5 \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2576816 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(6 + \sqrt{1+8} \right) + \left(6 + 7 \right) \right)^5 \right) / 2 \right) \right) \\
 2576819 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(1 + 8 \right) + 6 \right) + 7 \right)^5 \right) / 2 \right) \right) \\
 2579236 &:= \left(\left(6 + \left(32 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \right) \right)^2 \\
 2585664 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\left(4 + 6 \right)^6} + 5 \right) \times (-8) \right) / (-5) \right) \right)^2 \right) \\
 2595575 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(57 - 5 \right) - 5 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(5^2 \right) \right) \\
 2595585 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(8 - 55 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-5) \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 2596167 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(\left(61 \times 6 \right) + \sqrt{9^5} \right)^2 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2596499 &:= \left(\sqrt{9^9} - \left(\left(\left(4 - \left(- (6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^5 \right) / (-2) \right) \right) \\
 2597784 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 8 \right) \times \left(\left(7 - \left(7 \times 95 \right) \right) \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2597846 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{6^4} + 8 \right) \times \left(- \left(7 - \left(9^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 2598158 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(8 + \sqrt{\sqrt{\left(5 + 1 \right)^8}} \right) \times \left(9^5 \right) \right) + 2 \right) \right) \\
 2598166 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(- (66) \times \sqrt{\left(1 + 8 \right)^9} \right) - 5 \right) \times (-2) \right) \right) \\
 2599037 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(\left(\left(30 / \sqrt{9} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)^5 \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 2611456 &:= \left(\left(- (65) + \sqrt{41\sqrt{16}} \right)^2 \right) \\
 2613645 &:= \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times \left(\left(\left(6 - \left(3 \times 1 \right)^6 \right) \right) \right)^2 \right) \\
 2614689 &:= 9 \times \left(\sqrt{8^6} + \sqrt{\left(4 - 1 \right)^6} \right)^2 \\
 2617344 &:= \left(\left(4^{\sqrt{4}+3} \right) \times \left(71 \times \left(6^2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2617839 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(3^8 \right) \times \left(71 + 62 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2630884 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(8 + 803 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{6-2}} \right) \\
 2633838 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 \times \left(38^3 \right) \right) - 3 \right) \times \sqrt{6^2} \right) \\
 2633856 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(65 + 8 \right) + 3 \right)^3 \right) \times \sqrt{6^2} \right) \\
 2633874 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 78 \right) \right)^3 \right) + 3 \right) \times \sqrt{6^2} \right) \\
 2642635 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left(\left(3^6 - 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - \sqrt{6-2} \right) \right) \right) \\
 2642645 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(6 \times 2 \right) / 4 \right)^6 \right) \right) \right)^2 \right) \\
 2644992 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(2^9 \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(4 \times 6 \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2645163 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(- (61) + \sqrt{\left(5 \times \sqrt{4} \right)^6} \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 2646965 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left(6 + \sqrt{9} \right)^6 \right) - \left(\left(\left(4^6 \right) / 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2653884 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(4^8 - 8 \right) \times \left(3^5 \right) \right) / \sqrt{6^2} \right) \right) \\
 2654129 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(9^2 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(1 - \sqrt{\sqrt{4}^{5 \times 6}} \right) \right) + 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2654196 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{6^{9-1}} \times (4^5) \right) - 6 \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$2654209 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(0 - (24^5) \right) \right) / (6/2) \right)$$

$$2654289 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} + \left(\left((24^5) / 6 \right) \times 2 \right) \right)$$

$$2654464 := \left(\left(- \left((4 \times 6)^4 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4^5} \right) \times (- (6 + 2))$$

$$2654695 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((9^6) \right) + \left((4 \times \sqrt{5^6}) + 2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2656192 := \left(\sqrt{(29-1)^6} \times (5+6)^2 \right)$$

$$2656895 := 5 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{98 \times 6}}} \right) - 5 \times 62$$

$$2656945 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((4 + (9^6)) \right) \right) + \sqrt{56^2} \right)$$

$$2656955 := \left(\left(\sqrt{5 \times 5} \times (9^6) \right) + \left(\sqrt{5^6} \times (-2) \right) \right)$$

$$2656959 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^5} - \left(\left((9^6) \times 5 \right) - (6/2) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2657185 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{8+1}^{7+5} \right) - (6-2) \right) \right)$$

$$2657193 := \left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{9})^{-1+7} \right) \times 5 \right) - (6 \times 2) \right)$$

$$2657199 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9 \times 9}^{-1+7} \right) \times 5 \right) - \sqrt{6^2} \right)$$

$$2657205 := 5 \times \sqrt{(02 \times 7 - 5)^{6 \times 2}}$$

$$2657235 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{32^{7+5}} \right) + \sqrt{6^2} \right) \right)$$

$$2657259 := \left(9 \times \left(\left(5 \times \left((2+7)^5 \right) \right) + \sqrt{6^2} \right) \right)$$

$$2657269 := \left(\left(\left((9^6) + (2 \times 7) \right) \times 5 \right) - \sqrt{6^2} \right)$$

$$2657295 := \left((5 \times 9) \times \left(\left((2+7)^5 \right) + \sqrt{6-2} \right) \right)$$

$$2657385 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \times \left((3^{7+5}) + (6^2) \right)} \right)$$

$$2658126 := 62 \times \left(\sqrt{\left((1-8) \times 5 \right)^6 - 2} \right)$$

$$2658936 := \left(\left(\sqrt{6^{3+9}} - 8 \right) \times (- (5 - 62)) \right)$$

$$2659392 := \left(\left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+9} \right) \times (- (5 - 62)) \right) \right)$$

$$2659695 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((9^6) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^5} + 6 \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2659888 := \left(- (88) \times \left(\left((8^{\sqrt{9}}) - (5^6) \right) \times 2 \right) \right)$$

$$2659995 := \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{9 \times 9} \right) \times \left((9^5) + 62 \right) \right)$$

$$2666689 := \left(\left(- \left((9 + 86) \right) + \sqrt{(6+6)^6} \right)^2 \right)$$

$$2666736 := \left(- \left((6^3) \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{7^6} \times (- (6 \times 6)) \right) + 2 \right) \right)$$

$$2667156 := \left(\left((6^5) \times \sqrt{(1 \times 7)^6} \right) - (6 \times 2) \right)$$

$$2667159 := \left(- (9) + \left(\sqrt{\left((5+1) \times 7 \right)^6} \times (6^2) \right) \right)$$

$$2667164 := \left(-4 + \left(\sqrt{(6 \times 1 \times 7)^6} \times (6^2) \right) \right)$$

$$2667166 := \left(\left((6^{6-1}) \times \sqrt{7^6} \right) - \sqrt{6-2} \right)$$

$$2667168 := \left(\sqrt{(8 \times 6 + 1 - 7)^6} \times (6^2) \right)$$

$$2667672 := \left(\left((2 \times 7) + \sqrt{(6 \times 7)^6} \right) \times (6^2) \right)$$

$$2669359 := \left(\left((9 \times 5) \times \sqrt{39^6} \right) + (6 - 2) \right)$$

$$2669395 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- (9) \times \sqrt{39^6} \right) - (6 + 2) \right) \right)$$

$$2673225 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\left(2 \times (2^3) \right) - \sqrt{7^6} \right) \right)^2 \right)$$

$$2674463 := \left(\left(\sqrt{3^6} - 4 \right) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} - \sqrt{7^6}) \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2674688 := \sqrt{8^8 \times (647 + 6)^2}$$

$$2674944 := \left((4 + \sqrt{4^9}) \times \left((4 - 76)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2677298 := \left((89^2) \times \left(\left(- (7) + \sqrt{7^6} \right) + 2 \right) \right)$$

$$2682127 := \left(7 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{(2+1+2)^8} - 6 \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2682368 := \sqrt{(8 - 6^3)^{2 \times 8}} \times 62$$

$$2684434 := \left((43 - \sqrt{4}) \times \left((4^8) - 62 \right) \right)$$

$$2685619 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{16}}} \right) + (58) \right)^{6/2} \right)$$

$$2685828 := 82 \times \sqrt{(8^5 - 8 - 6)^2}$$

$$2688288 := (8 \times 82) \times (\sqrt{8^8} + \sqrt{6-2})$$

$$2692485 := (-5) \times (-((84^2) - (9^{\sqrt{6^2}})))$$

$$2695842 := \left(2 \times \left(\left((48 - 5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}\right)^2\right)\right)$$

$$2699449 := \left(\left(-\left(\left(\sqrt{9^4} + 4\right)\right) + \sqrt{\left(9 + \sqrt{9}\right)^6}\right)^2\right)$$

$$2699487 := \left(7 \times \left(-\left(\left(8 + 4\right) \times 9\right) + \sqrt{9^6}\right)^2\right)$$

$$2699845 := \left(-5\right) \times \left(\sqrt{4^8} - \left(\left(9^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + 6\right)^2\right)$$

$$2714796 := \left(\left(\left(6 \times 9\right) \times 7\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times (17 + 2)$$

$$2719744 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 4^7\right)\right) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{1+7}} + 2}\right)$$

$$2728448 := \left(8 \times \left(-4 + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 82\right) \times 7\right)\right)^2\right)$$

$$2733568 := \left(\sqrt{8^6} \times (5337 + 2)\right)$$

$$2734277 := \left(7 \times \left(\left(7 - 2\right)^{\sqrt{4^3}} - (7 \times 2)\right)\right)$$

$$2734347 := \left(-7\right) \times \left(4 - \left(\left(3 + \sqrt{4}\right)^{3+7-2}\right)\right)$$

$$2734373 := \left(\left(\left(\left(3 + \sqrt{7-3}\right)^{\sqrt{4^3}}\right) \times 7\right) - 2\right)$$

$$2734377 := \left(\left(\left(\left(7 - \sqrt{7-3}\right)^{\sqrt{4^3}}\right) \times 7\right) + 2\right)$$

$$2734394 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (9 \times 3)\right)\right)^4\right) + 3\right) \times 7\right) - 2$$

$$2734459 := \left(9 + \left(5^{4+4}\right) + 3\right) \times \sqrt{7^2}$$

$$2734552 := \left(\left(25 + \left(5^{\sqrt{4^3}}\right)\right) \times 7\right) + 2$$

$$2734585 := \left(\left(5^8\right) + \left(-5\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \times (-3) \times \sqrt{7^2}$$

$$2734823 := \left(\left(\left(3 + 2\right)^8\right) + \left(4^3\right)\right) \times \sqrt{7^2}$$

$$2734825 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{5^{2^8}}\right) + \left(4^3\right)\right) \times 7\right) + 2\right)$$

$$2734935 := \left(5 \times 3\right) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(4^3\right)\right) \times (-7)\right)^2\right)$$

$$2736448 := \left(8 \times 44\right) \times \left(\sqrt{6^{3+7}} - 2\right)$$

$$2737923 := \left(-\left(32 - \left(97^3\right)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{7+2}$$

$$2737977 := \left(-\left(\left(7 + 7\right) - \left(97^3\right)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{7+2}$$

$$2737979 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-\left(7 - \left(\left(97^3\right) - 7\right)\right)\right)\right) + 2\right)$$

$$2737991 := \left(-1\right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-\left(\left(\left(97^3\right) - 7\right) - 2\right)\right)\right)$$

$$2737993 := \left(-3\right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-\left(\left(97^3\right) - 7\right)\right)\right) + 2\right)$$

$$2737994 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-\left(\left(\left(97^3\right) - 7\right) - 2\right)\right)\right)\right)$$

$$2737995 := \left(\left(-5 - \sqrt{9}\right) + \left(97^3\right)\right) \times \sqrt{7+2}$$

$$2737997 := \left(-7\right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-\left(\left(\left(97^3\right) - 7\right) + 2\right)\right)\right)$$

$$2737999 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-\left(9 - \left(97^3\right)\right)\right)\right) + \sqrt{7^2}\right)$$

$$2738019 := \left(-\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{\sqrt{10^8}}\right)^3 \times \sqrt{7+2}$$

$$2739184 := \left(\left(\left(-\left(4 - 81\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times 3\right) - 7 \times 2$$

$$2741856 := \left(6 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 1}\right)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{4+7 \times 2}}}\right)\right)$$

$$2743132 := \left(-2\right) \times \sqrt{313^4} \times (-7 \times 2)$$

$$2743134 := \left(\left(-4\right) \times \sqrt{313^4}\right) \times (-7) + 2$$

$$2745649 := \left(\left(\left(\left(9 + \sqrt{4}\right) \times 6\right) \times \sqrt{5^4}\right) + 7\right)^2$$

$$2748964 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(69 \times 8\right) \times \left(4 - 7\right)\right)\right)\right)^2$$

$$2752426 := \left(\left(-6\right) \times \left(\left(2 - \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{2^5}}}\right) \times 7\right)\right) - 2$$

$$2752496 := \left(\left(-6\right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{4^{2^5}}}\right) \times 7\right)\right) + 2$$

$$2759043 := \left(3 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 0957\right)^2\right)\right)$$

$$2765625 := \left(-\left(\left(5 - \left(2^6\right)\right) \times \left(5^6\right)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{7+2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2765944 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times (- (4 - (9 \times ((56 \times 7)^2)))))) \\
 2765946 &:= (- (6) + (\sqrt{4} \times (9 \times ((56 \times 7)^2)))) \\
 2765949 &:= - ((\sqrt{9} - (\sqrt{4} \times (9 \times ((56 \times 7)^2)))))) \\
 2765964 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times (6 + (9 \times ((56 \times 7)^2)))) \\
 2772225 &:= \left((- (522) + \sqrt{(2+7)^7} \right)^2 \\
 2774974 &:= (47 \times ((9^{-\sqrt{4}+7}) - \sqrt{7^2})) \\
 2777895 &:= ((5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times ((8 + (7 \times 7))^{\sqrt{7+2}})) \\
 2787993 &:= ((39^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (((7 \times 8) - 7) - 2)) \\
 2792241 &:= \left((((- ((1 - 42))^2) - \sqrt{9}) - 7)^2 \right) \\
 2794986 &:= ((68 + \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{4 \times 9^{7+2}}) \\
 2794994 &:= ((-4 - (\sqrt{9^9} \times ((4^{\sqrt{9}}) + 7))) \times (-2)) \\
 2799295 &:= (- (5) \times (9 - (2 \times (((9 - \sqrt{9})^7) - 2)))) \\
 2799328 &:= (((8 + 2) \times (- (3) + ((9 - \sqrt{9})^7))) - 2) \\
 2799345 &:= (\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times (- (3) - (((9 - \sqrt{9})^7) \times (-2)))) \\
 2799355 &:= -5 + 5 \times \sqrt{(3 \times 9 + 9)^7} \times 2 \\
 2799358 &:= \left((((8 + 5) - 3) \times ((9 - \sqrt{9})^7)) - 2 \right) \\
 2799375 &:= (- (5) + ((7 + 3) \times (((9 - \sqrt{9})^7) + 2))) \\
 2799385 &:= (- (5) \times (- ((8 - 3)) + (((9 - \sqrt{9})^7) \times (-2)))) \\
 2799535 &:= (- (5) \times (- (35) + (((9 - \sqrt{9})^7) \times (-2)))) \\
 2809872 &:= (((((2 \times 7) \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}}) + 08) \times 2) \\
 2815684 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} + (((8 \times 6) \times 5) \times (1 - 8))) \right)^2 \\
 2818134 &:= (43 \times (((1 + \sqrt{8+1})^8) + 2))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2819854 &:= ((- (4) \times (5 - (89^{\sqrt{1+8}}))) - 2) \\
 2819864 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times (- (6) + ((89^{\sqrt{1+8}}) \times 2))) \\
 2819876 &:= \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(6+7)^8} + 9} \right)^{\sqrt{1+8}} / 2 \\
 2819884 &:= (- ((4 - 8)) \times ((89^{\sqrt{1+8}}) + 2)) \\
 2819894 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times (9 + ((89^{\sqrt{1+8}}) \times 2))) \\
 2823574 &:= ((\sqrt{4} \times (((7^5) \times 3) \times 28)) - 2) \\
 2823579 &:= (\sqrt{9} + (((7^5) \times 3) \times 28) \times 2) \\
 2825759 &:= \left((((\sqrt{9} \times (5 + 7)) + 5)^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}}) - 2 \right) \\
 2825763 &:= \left(((\sqrt{36} + (7 \times 5))^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}}) + 2 \right) \\
 2830896 &:= ((6^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (- ((8 - (03^8)) \times 2))) \\
 2832998 &:= (((89^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-2)) - (3^8)) \times (-2) \\
 2834344 &:= (- (4) \times (\sqrt{4} - ((3 \times 4) \times (3^{8+2})))) \\
 2834349 &:= - ((\sqrt{9} - (((4 \times 3) \times 4) \times (3^{8+2})))) \\
 2834356 &:= (6^5 \times \sqrt{3^{4 \times 3}} + 8) / 2 \\
 2834373 &:= (3 \times (7 + (((3 \times 4) \times \sqrt{3^8})^2))) \\
 2834448 &:= (((8 + 4) \times 4) \times (\sqrt{4} + ((3^{8+2})))) \\
 2834784 &:= (- (48) \times ((- (7) - \sqrt{4}) - ((3^{8+2})))) \\
 2834942 &:= (- 2 - (((- ((4^9)) + ((\sqrt{4} \times 3)^8)) \times (-2))) \\
 2834944 &:= ((\sqrt{4} \times (- (4^9))) - (((\sqrt{4} \times 3)^8) \times (-2))) \\
 2836944 &:= \left(((\sqrt{4} + 4)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times ((6 + (3^8)) \times 2) \right) \\
 2836946 &:= \left((((- ((6^4)) / \sqrt{9}) \times (- (6 + (3^8)))) + 2 \right) \\
 2839714 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} - (((1 - 7) - 9))^{-3+8}) \times 2 \right) \\
 2839726 &:= \left((- (6) - (((2 \times 7) + \sqrt{9})^{-3+8})) \times (-2) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2842596 := \left(\left(6 \times \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 5) + 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 8 \right) \right) \right)^2$$

$$2847474 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7) \right)^4 \right) \times (-7) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - (8^2) \right) \right)$$

$$2847659 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 5) \right)^6 \right) + (7 + 4) \right) / (8/2)$$

$$2858247 := \left(7 \times \left(\left(\left((4 + 2) + 8 \right) + \sqrt{58} \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2858925 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left(2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{98}} \right)^{-5+8} \right) - 2 \right) \right)$$

$$2858945 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{\sqrt{98}} \right)^{-5+8} \right) + 2 \right) \right)$$

$$2859481 := \left(-184 + \sqrt{9 \times 58} \right)^2$$

$$2862864 := \left(\sqrt{\left(\sqrt{4} \times 6 \right)^{8-2}} - \sqrt{\sqrt{68}} \right)^2$$

$$2864886 := \left(6 \times \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{88} + \sqrt{4}) / 6 \right) + 8 \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2865456 := 6^5 \times \left(\sqrt{(4+5)^6} + 8 \right) / 2$$

$$2866249 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (-2) \right) + \sqrt{66} \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \right)^2 \right)$$

$$2869344 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4) \times 3 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (6 \times 82) \right) \right)$$

$$2869584 := \left(- (48) \times \left(- (5) - \left(\sqrt{96} \times 82 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2869779 := \left(\left(\left(\left(9^7 \right) - \sqrt{7+9} \right) \times 6 \right) / (8+2) \right)$$

$$2871648 := \left(8 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (61) \right) \times \left(- (78^2) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2873997 := \left(-\sqrt{79+\sqrt{9}/3} + 78 \right) / 2$$

$$2875839 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(3^8 \right) - \left(\left(5 + (7^8) \right) / 2 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2876413 := \left(- (3) + \left(\left(\left(1 + (4^6) \right) - \sqrt{78} \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2876414 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\left(1 + (4^6) \right) - \sqrt{78} \right)^2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2876419 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\left(1 + (4^6) \right) - \sqrt{78} \right)^2 \right) \right)$$

$$2877489 := \left(\left(\sqrt{98} - \left(\left(\left(4^7 \right) - (7^8) \right) \right) \right) / 2 \right)$$

$$2877861 := \left(\left(\left(\left(1 + \sqrt{68} \right) \times 7 \right) - (7^8) \right) / (-2) \right)$$

$$2877863 := \left(\left(- (3) - \left(\left(\sqrt{68} \times 7 \right) - (7^8) \right) \right) / 2 \right)$$

$$2877869 := \left(\left(- (9) + \left(\left(\sqrt{68} \times 7 \right) - (7^8) \right) \right) / (-2) \right)$$

$$2878796 := \left(\left(\left(- (6) - \sqrt{9 \times 78} \right) + (7^8) \right) / 2 \right)$$

$$2878799 := \left(\left(\left(\left(9 / \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{78} \right) - (7^8) \right) / (-2) \right)$$

$$2878958 := \left(\left(\left(\left(85 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{98}} \right) - (7^8) \right) \right) / (-2) \right)$$

$$2878995 := - \left(\left(\left(5^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{98} - (7^8) \right) / 2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2879485 := 5 \times \left(84^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{78+2} \right)$$

$$2879488 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{88} - \left(\left(\left(4^9 \right) \times \left(7 + (8/2) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2879944 := \left(\left(\left(\left((4+4) + 9 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (7^8) \right) / (-2) \right)$$

$$2879988 := \left(\left(\sqrt{88} + \left(\left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (7^8) \right) \right) / (-2) \right)$$

$$2882396 := \left(\left(\left(6 + \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(\left(\left(3 - 2 \right) - 8 \right)^8 \right) \right) / (-2) \right)$$

$$2882398 := \left(\left(\left(8 - \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(\left(\left(3 - 2 \right) - 8 \right)^8 \right) \right) / (-2) \right)$$

$$2882399 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\left(9 + \left(3 \times 2 \right) - 8 \right)^8 \right) \right) \right) / (-2) \right)$$

$$2882437 := \left(\left(- (73) - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} / (-2) \right) + 8 \right)^8 \right) \right) / (-2) \right)$$

$$2882769 := \left(\left(\sqrt{96} + \left(\left(\sqrt{72^8} \right) + 8 \right) \right) / 2 \right)$$

$$2883474 := \left((4+7) \times \left(\left(4^{\sqrt{\sqrt{38}}} \right) - (8+2) \right) \right)$$

$$2883494 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 9 \right) \times \left(\left(4^{\sqrt{\sqrt{38}}} \right) - 8 \right) \right) - 2 \right)$$

$$2883498 := \left(\left(\left(8 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(\left(4^{\sqrt{\sqrt{38}}} \right) - 8 \right) \right) + 2 \right)$$

$$2883589 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\left(8^5 \right) \times \left(\left(3 + 8 \right) \times 8 \right) + 2 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$2883617 := \left((7 + \sqrt{16}) \times \left(3 + (8^{8-2}) \right) \right)$$

$$2883648 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{84}} \right) \times (3+8) \right) + (8^2) \right) \right)$$

$$2883758 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(8^5 \right) \right) - \sqrt{7-3} \right) \times (-88) \right) - 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2883848 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(8^4 \right) \times 8 \right) + 3 \right) \times \sqrt{88^2} \right) \\
 2892656 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(6^5 \right) \times 62 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 8 \right) \times (-2) \\
 2892669 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(6^6 \right) \times \left(\left(\left(2^9 \right) / 8 \right) - 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2892676 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(6^7 \right) \times 62 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) + 8 \right) / 2 \right) \\
 2892699 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(62 \times \left(9 \times 8^2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2893254 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 5 \right)^2 \right) \times \left(- (3) + \sqrt{98^2} \right) \right) \\
 2893399 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \times \left(- (3) - \sqrt{\sqrt{(3+9)^8}} \right) \right) \right) - 2 \\
 2897664 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 66 \right) \times \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(8^2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2898918 &:= \left((8+1) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 8 \right)^{-\sqrt{9+8}} \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 2898999 &:= \left(9 \times \left(9 - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 8 \right)^{-\sqrt{9+8}} \right) \times (-2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2899888 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{8^8} + \left(\sqrt{9}^{\sqrt{9+8}} \right) \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 2899962 &:= \left(\left(2 + \left(\left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^8} \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 2907025 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(2 - \left(07^{\sqrt{09}} \right) \right) \right) \right)^2 \\
 2910899 &:= \left(\left(\left(99^{\sqrt{8+01}} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 2 \right) \\
 2915995 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (9+51) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / 2 \right) \right) \\
 2917264 &:= \left(\left(4 + \left(\left((6+2) \times 71 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)^2 \\
 2918528 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(\left(- (2) + \sqrt{5^8} \right) - (19) \right) \right)^2 \right) \\
 2924095 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(- (90) \times \left(- \left(\left(4^2 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)^2 \\
 2929558 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(85 - \left(5^9 \right) \right) / 2 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 2 \right) \\
 2929685 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(\left(5^8 \right) \times (6+9) \right) - 2 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) / (-2) \right) \\
 2929695 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(5^9 \right) - 6 \right) + 9 \right) + 2 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / (-2) \right) \\
 2929713 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(17 + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 2 \right)^9 \right) \right) \right) / 2 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2929959 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(5^9 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) / (-2) \right) + (92) \right) \right) \\
 2930944 &:= \left(\left(- \left((4 \times 4) \right) + \left((9+03)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)^2 \\
 2934549 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 45 \right) \right)^4 \right) - \left(\left(3^{9+2} \right) \right) \right) \\
 2939377 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(- (7) - \left(\left(\left(- \left((3-9) \right)^3 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 2939529 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\sqrt{25^9} \right) \right) + \left(3^9 \right) \right) / 2 \right) \\
 2941445 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left(\left(4^4 \right) - 1 \right) + \sqrt{4^9} \right) \right)^2 \right) \\
 2944648 &:= \left(- (8) + \left(\left(\left(-4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 4)^4} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^2 \right) \\
 2944658 &:= \left(\left(\left((8+564)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 9 \right) + 2 \right) \\
 2945889 &:= \left(\sqrt{9^8} \times \left(8 + \left(\left((5+\sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2947959 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9}^{5+9} \right) - \left((7 \times (4^9)) + 2 \right) \right) \\
 2948089 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 8 \right) - \left((08+4)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right)^2 \\
 2948895 &:= \left((5 \times 9) \times \left(\left(\left((8+8)^4 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 2949115 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(1 - \left(\left(\left((1+\sqrt{9})^4 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 2949135 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(- (3) - \left(\left(\left((1+\sqrt{9})^4 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 2949658 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(8^5 \right) + 6 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^4} + 9 \right) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 2952459 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(9^5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-25) \right) + \sqrt{9^2} \right) \\
 2953127 &:= \left((7 \times \left(\left((2+13) \times 5 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)) + 2 \right) \\
 2954961 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(- \left(\left((1-6) - 9 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 5 \right) \times 9 \right) \right)^2 \\
 2956579 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \left(\left(\left((7-5)^6 \right) + 5 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) - 2 \\
 2956599 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(\left((9-5) + 65 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 2 \right) \right) \\
 2957984 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (-8) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(7^5 \right) \times (9+2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2958236 &:= \left((6 \times \left(\left((3 \times 28) - 5 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)) + 2 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2958246 &:= (6 \times ((-(((4+2) - 85))^{\sqrt{9}}) + 2)) \\
 2958417 &:= (- (7) \times ((\sqrt{14^8} + 5) \times (- (9 + 2)))) \\
 2961841 &:= (((1^4) - (8 \times (1 - (6^{\sqrt{9}}))))^2) \\
 2962656 &:= 6^5 \times \sqrt{(62 \times 6 + 9)^2} \\
 2963088 &:= (((((8+8) + 03) \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 2) \\
 2963485 &:= (((5 \times ((84^3) - 6)) - \sqrt{9}) - 2) \\
 2964871 &:= (1 + \sqrt{(-7 + 8 \times 4^6)^{\sqrt{9}}}) / 2 \\
 2965284 &:= ((\sqrt{4} - ((8 - (((2^5) \times 6) \times 9))))^2) \\
 2966299 &:= -(((\sqrt{9^9} + 2) - (((6+6)^{\sqrt{9}})^2))) \\
 2968729 &:= (((9 - (2 \times 7)) + (8 \times (6^{\sqrt{9}})))^2) \\
 2974839 &:= (93 + 84) \times (7^{\sqrt{9}+2}) \\
 2974884 &:= ((-4 + \sqrt{8^8}) \times (((\sqrt{4} + 7)^{\sqrt{9}}) - 2)) \\
 2975625 &:= (((5^2) \times ((6 \times 5) - 7)) \times \sqrt{9})^2) \\
 2976897 &:= (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{8679^2} \\
 2981888 &:= (\sqrt{8^8} \times (8 \times ((1 \times 89) + 2))) \\
 2982339 &:= (-((9^3)) \times (3 - (((2 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}}) - 2))) \\
 2984686 &:= \sqrt{6^8} + \sqrt{\sqrt{(6 \times \sqrt{4})^{8 \times \sqrt{9}}} - 2} \\
 2984984 &:= -((((\sqrt{4} + 8)^{\sqrt{9}}) - (((4+8)^{\sqrt{9}})^2))) \\
 2985387 &:= (((7 \times 8)^3) - 5) \times \sqrt{(8+9)^2} \\
 2985664 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (6^6 - 5) \times \sqrt{8^{\sqrt{9}} \times 2} \\
 2985694 &:= (((4 \times \sqrt{9})^6) - (58 \times (\sqrt{9} + 2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2985766 &:= -\sqrt{6^6} + \sqrt{\sqrt{(7+5)^{8 \times \sqrt{9}}} - 2} \\
 2985936 &:= (((6 \times (3+9)^5)) + (- (8) \times \sqrt{9})) \times 2) \\
 2985952 &:= (-((2^5)) + (((9-5) + 8)^{\sqrt{9}})^2) \\
 2985969 &:= (-((9+6)) + (((9-5) + 8)^{\sqrt{9}})^2) \\
 2985975 &:= (((5+7)^{9+5-8}) - \sqrt{9^2}) \\
 2985977 &:= (- (7) + (((\sqrt{7+9} \times (- (5-8)))^{\sqrt{9}})^2)) \\
 2985979 &:= (((((9+7) \times 9)^{-5+8}) - \sqrt{9}) - 2) \\
 2985981 &:= (- (1) + (((((8 \times \sqrt{9})^5) / 8) \times \sqrt{9}) - 2)) \\
 2985983 &:= (- (3) + (((((8 \times \sqrt{9})^5) / 8) \times \sqrt{9}) + 2)) \\
 2985986 &:= (((6 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-((5-8) \times 9)) + 2) \\
 2985988 &:= (\sqrt{8+8} + (((9-5) + 8)^{\sqrt{9}})^2) \\
 2985989 &:= (\sqrt{9} + (((((8 \times \sqrt{9})^5) / 8) \times \sqrt{9}) + 2)) \\
 2985992 &:= (2^{\sqrt{9}}) + (((9-5) + 8)^{\sqrt{9}})^2) \\
 2985993 &:= (((3+9)^{9+5-8}) + \sqrt{9^2}) \\
 2985996 &:= (- (6) \times (((9 + \sqrt{9})^5) - ((8-9))) \times (-2)) \\
 2986487 &:= (-((7 - (8+4)^6)) + ((8^{\sqrt{9}}) - 2)) \\
 2986488 &:= -8 + (8+4)^6 + \sqrt{8^{\sqrt{9} \times 2}} \\
 2986489 &:= (-((9 - (8+4)^6)) + ((8^{\sqrt{9}}) + 2)) \\
 2986492 &:= ((- (2) + ((\sqrt{9} \times 4)^6)) + ((8^{\sqrt{9}}) - 2)) \\
 2986493 &:= -3 + (\sqrt{9} \times 4)^6 + \sqrt{8^{\sqrt{9} \times 2}} \\
 2986494 &:= ((-4 + ((\sqrt{9} \times 4)^6)) + ((8^{\sqrt{9}}) + 2)) \\
 2986496 &:= ((6-9) \times 4)^6 + \sqrt{8^{\sqrt{9} \times 2}} \\
 2986498 &:= (((8 \times \sqrt{9}) / \sqrt{4})^6) + ((8^{\sqrt{9}}) + 2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2986499 &:= \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} \times 4)^6 + \sqrt{8\sqrt{9} \times 2} \\
 2986629 &:= - \left((\sqrt{9} - ((2 \times 6)^6) + (8 \times (9^2))) \right) \\
 2986648 &:= (8 \times (\sqrt{4} + (((6^6) \times 8) + (9^2)))) \\
 2986848 &:= \left((\sqrt{(8+4)^8} + 6) \times ((8 \times 9) \times 2) \right) \\
 2986999 &:= \left((-9) + ((9 + \sqrt{9})^6) \right) + ((8\sqrt{9}) \times 2) \\
 2988169 &:= ((\sqrt{9^6} \times (\sqrt{1 \times 8^8} + \sqrt{9})) - 2) \\
 2988173 &:= ((3^7) + (((18 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}}) + 2)) \\
 2988189 &:= (9 \times ((81 \times (\sqrt{8^8} + \sqrt{9})) + 2)) \\
 2988495 &:= ((5 - (9 \times (4 + \sqrt{8^8}))) \times (-9^2)) \\
 2988895 &:= (-5) \times ((\sqrt{9^8} + 8) \times (-89 + 2)) \\
 2989441 &:= \left((\sqrt{144\sqrt{9}} - ((8-9)))^2 \right) \\
 2991676 &:= ((6 - (76 \times (1 - \sqrt{9^9}))) \times 2) \\
 2991816 &:= (((6-1) - 81) \times \sqrt{9^9}) \times (-2) \\
 2991818 &:= ((8 \times (18+1)) \times \sqrt{9^9}) + 2 \\
 2991983 &:= ((-3) + \sqrt{8^{9-1}}) \times ((9\sqrt{9}) + 2) \\
 2992714 &:= (((4^{-1+7}) - 2) \times ((9\sqrt{9}) + 2)) \\
 2994173 &:= (-3) + (((7+1)^4) \times ((9\sqrt{9}) + 2)) \\
 2994174 &:= (((4^{7-1}) \times (\sqrt{4} + (9\sqrt{9}))) - 2) \\
 2994178 &:= ((\sqrt{8^{7+1}} \times (\sqrt{4} + (9\sqrt{9}))) + 2) \\
 2994179 &:= (\sqrt{9} + (((7+1)^4) \times ((9\sqrt{9}) + 2))) \\
 2996289 &:= -((9 \times 8) + (((2 \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}}) + \sqrt{9})^2) \\
 2996352 &:= (2 \times (((5 \times \sqrt{3^6}) \times 9) + 9)^2) \\
 2996361 &:= (((1 + (((6/3)^6) \times 9)) \times \sqrt{9})^2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2999822 &:= \left(-(2) + \left((\sqrt{2 \times 8} + ((9 + \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}})^2 \right) \right) \\
 2999919 &:= (((91+9)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{9}) - ((9^2)) \\
 2999973 &:= (3 \times (((7 + \sqrt{9})^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - \sqrt{9^2})) \\
 2999977 &:= \left(((-7) + ((7 + \sqrt{9})^{9-\sqrt{9}})) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 2 \\
 2999978 &:= \left(((-8) + ((7 + \sqrt{9})^{9-\sqrt{9}})) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 2 \\
 2999979 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times (-7) + (((9/9) + 9)^{\sqrt{9}})^2) \\
 2999982 &:= (((2+8)^{9-\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{9}) - ((9 \times 2)) \\
 2999991 &:= (((1+99)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{9}) - \sqrt{9^2} \\
 2999995 &:= (-5) + (\sqrt{9} \times (((9/9) + 9)^{\sqrt{9}})^2) \\
 2999997 &:= \left(((7 + \sqrt{9})^{9-\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9^2}} \\
 2999998 &:= (((-((8-9) - 99))^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{9}) - 2 \\
 3011499 &:= (\sqrt{9^9} \times ((41+10) \times 3)) \\
 3049984 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times (8 \times 9))^{\sqrt{9}} + ((40^3)) \right) \\
 3079296 &:= \left((6\sqrt{9})^2 \times ((9 \times 7) + 03) \right) \\
 3122289 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 222)))^{\sqrt{1+3}}) \\
 3125824 &:= (((42 - 8) \times 52)^{\sqrt{1+3}}) \\
 3144489 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times (((8 \times 4)^4) - 413)) \\
 3145449 &:= ((-94) + ((\sqrt{4}^{5 \times 4}) + 1)) \times 3 \\
 3145668 &:= (((8\sqrt{6 \times 6}) - 5) \times ((4 \times 1) \times 3)) \\
 3145689 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times (((8-6)^5)^4) - 13) \\
 3145725 &:= \left(((5 - \sqrt{2+7})^{5 \times 4}) - 1 \right) \times 3 \\
 3145729 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times ((27+5)^4)) + (1^3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$3145743 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{3^4} + 7 \right)^5 \right) + (4 + 1) \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$3145851 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{-1 + 5} \times 8 \right)^5 \right) + 41 \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$3161284 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^8} - 2 \right) \times (1 + 6) \right)^{\sqrt{1+3}} \right)$$

$$3162456 := \sqrt{(6 + 5)^{4 \times 2}} \times (6 \times 1)^3$$

$$3176499 := \left(\left(\left(9 \times \left((9 - \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) - (7 + 1) \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$3184896 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - 8) \right)^4 \right) - \left((81^3) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3185288 := \left(8 \times \left(\left((8 - 2) + \sqrt{5^8} \right)^{\sqrt{1+3}} \right) \right)$$

$$3186459 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^{5+\sqrt{4}}} \right) - \left((6 \times (81^3)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3188496 := \left(- (6) \times \left(9 - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (-8) \right) + \left((81^3) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3188592 := \left(2 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{5+8}} \right) - (81/3) \right) \right)$$

$$3188616 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- (1) + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \right) - \left((81^3) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3188634 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(3 \times \left((6 - 8) + (81^3) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3188641 := \left(- \left((1 + 4) \right) + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \times (81^3) \right) \right)$$

$$3188642 := \left(2 \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left(6 / \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}} \right)^{13} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3188644 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left((4 - 6) + 8 \right) \times (81^3) \right) \right)$$

$$3188645 := \left(- \left((5 - 4) \right) + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \times (81^3) \right) \right)$$

$$3188647 := \left(\sqrt{7^4} - \left((6 \times (8 - (81^3))) \right) \right)$$

$$3188648 := \left((8/4) + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \times (81^3) \right) \right)$$

$$3188649 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((4 - 6) + 8 \right) \times (81^3) \right)$$

$$3188651 := \left((1 \times 5) + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \times (81^3) \right) \right)$$

$$3188674 := \left((4 \times 7) + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \times (81^3) \right) \right)$$

$$3188682 := \left(- \left((2 - 8) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} + \left((81^3) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3188684 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left((8 - (6 \times (8 + (81^3)))) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3188687 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}} - (6 \times (8 + (81^3))) \right) \right)$$

$$3188689 := \left(\sqrt{9} - \left((8 - (6 \times (8 + (81^3)))) \right) \right)$$

$$3188691 := \left(- (1) \times \sqrt{9} + (6 \times (8 + (81^3))) \right)$$

$$3188693 := \left(- (3) / \sqrt{9} + (6 \times (8 + (81^3))) \right)$$

$$3189618 := \left((81 \times 6) \times \left(\sqrt{9^8} + \sqrt{1+3} \right) \right)$$

$$3189699 := \left(- \left((9 \times 9) \right) \times \left(- (6) \times \sqrt{9^8} - 13 \right) \right)$$

$$3189945 := \left(\left(- (54) \times \left(\sqrt{9^9} + 8 \right) - 1 \right) \times (-3) \right)$$

$$3189969 := \left(9 \times \left(\left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{9^9} + 8 \right) + 1 \right) \times 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3192344 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((43^2) + \left(\sqrt{9^{13}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3195727 := \left((7 \times \left((2 + 75)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)) - (1 + 3) \right)$$

$$3195787 := \left(- (7) \times \left(- (8) - \left(\left((75 + \sqrt{9}) - 1 \right)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3199997 := \left(\left(- (7) + (9 \times \sqrt{9}) \right)^{9 - \sqrt{9} - 1} - 3 \right)$$

$$3213675 := \left(\left((5 + \left((\sqrt{7^6} \times 3) + 1 \right))^2 \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$3234053 := \left(- (3) - \left((50 + \sqrt{4})^3 \right) \right) \times (-23)$$

$$3239287 := \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} - 2 \right) \times \left((9 + 32)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$3241786 := \left(- (6) + \left((8 + \left((71 \times \sqrt{4}) - 2 \right))^3 \right) \right)$$

$$3241789 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left((8 + \left((71 \times \sqrt{4}) - 2 \right))^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3241791 := \left(- (1) + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 71) \times (4 - 2) \right)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$3241794 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 71) \times (4 - 2) \right)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$3255199 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times (-9)) - \left(1 - \left((5^5)^2 \right) \right) \right) / 3 \right)$$

$$3255437 := \left(\left(\left((7^3) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \left((5^5)^2 \right) \right) / 3 \right)$$

$$3257292 := \left(\left(\left((-2) + \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(-(2-7)^5 \right) \right)^2 / 3 \right)$$

$$3268861 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(1 \times 6)^8} + \sqrt{8^6} \right)^2 \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$3277788 := - \left(\left((\sqrt{8^8} - (7^7)) \right) \times (\sqrt{7^2} - 3) \right)$$

$$3284515 := \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{(15 - \sqrt{4})^8} \right) \times 23 \right)$$

$$3286064 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((6 \times 06) + 82 \right)^3 \right)$$

$$3292525 := \left(- (5) \times \left(-2 - \left(- \left((\sqrt{5^2} - (92)) \right)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3294164 := \left(\left(4 \times \left((6 + 1)^{\sqrt{49}} \right) \right) - (2^3) \right)$$

$$3294167 := \left(\left(\left((7^{6+1}) \times 4 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) - (2^3) \right)$$

$$3294172 := \left((27 + 1) \times (\sqrt{49}^{2 \times 3}) \right)$$

$$3294297 := \left(\left((7^{9-2}) \times 4 \right) + \left((\sqrt{9} + 2)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$3295494 := \left(\left(\left(4 \times \left((9 + 4) \times 5 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 2 \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$3307949 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times 49 + \sqrt{7 - 03} \right)^3$$

$$3308214 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(1 + \left(2 + 80 \right)^3 \right) \times 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3312576 := \sqrt{6^{7+5}} \times 213 / 3$$

$$3326458 := \left(- \left((8^5) \right) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((6^{2^3}) - 3 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3327786 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} \times \left((7^{7-2}) \times 33 \right)} \right)$$

$$3333474 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(- \left((7 - (4^3)) \right) \right)^3 \right) \times (3 \times 3) \right)$$

$$3341637 := \left(\left(\left((7 + \sqrt{36})^{1+4} \right) \times (3 \times 3) \right) \right)$$

$$3348864 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(6^8 \right) - \left((8 + 4)^3 \times 3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3358482 := \left(2 \times \left(\left((8 - \sqrt{4})^8 \right) - \left((5^3) \times 3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3359222 := \left(2 \times \left(- (2) + \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^{5+3} \right) - 3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3359223 := \left(- (3) + \left(2 \times \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^{5+3} \right) - 3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3359224 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(2 \times \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^{5+3} \right) - 3 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3359226 := \left(\sqrt{6-2} \times \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^{5+3} \right) - 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3359229 := \left(\left(\left((9^2)^2 \right) \times \left((\sqrt{9} + 5)^3 \right) \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$3359233 := \left(\left(- (3) - \left((3 \times 2)^{\sqrt{9^{5-3}}} \right) \right) / (-3) \right)$$

$$3359242 := \left(2 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^{5+3} \right) + 3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3359244 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((4 + 2)^{\sqrt{9+5}} \right) + (3 + 3) \right) \right)$$

$$3359264 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(6^{2^{\sqrt{9}}} \right) \right) + \left(5 + (3^3) \right) \right)$$

$$3359396 := \left(\left((6^9 - 3) / \sqrt{9} \right) + (5 \times 33) \right)$$

$$3359562 := \left(2 \times \left(\left(6^{5+\sqrt{9}} \right) + (5 \times 33) \right) \right)$$

$$3359796 := \left(\left(\left(- (6^9) - (7 \times \sqrt{9^5}) \right) / (-3) \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$3374488 := \left(- (8) \times \left(\sqrt{8^4} - \left((\sqrt{4} + 73)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3374589 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(8 \times \left((5 + 47)^3 \right) \right) \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$3374591 := \left(- (1) - \left(\left(\left((95 + \sqrt{4}) + 7 \right)^3 \right) \times (-3) \right) \right)$$

$$3374594 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\left((95 + \sqrt{4}) + 7 \right)^3 \right) \times (-3) \right) \right)$$

$$3374628 := \left((82 \times 6) \times \left(- \left((\sqrt{4} - (7 \times 3)) \right)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$3374865 := \left(\left(\left(\left((5^6) \times 8 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) - 7 \right) \times (3^3) \right)$$

$$3374872 := \left(- \left((2^7) \right) - \left(- (8) \times \left((\sqrt{4} + 73)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3374928 := \left(\sqrt{8^2} \times \left(- (9) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 73 \right)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3374979 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left(7 - \left(9 \times \left((47 + 3)^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3374984 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (-8) \right) + \left(\left((9 + (47 \times 3))^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3374989 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(8 - \left((9 + (47 \times 3))^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3374992 := - \left(\left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(\left((9 + (47 \times 3))^3 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3374994 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(9 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 47 \right)^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (-3)$$

$$3381147 := -7 \times \left(4 - \sqrt{11^8} \right) \times 33$$

$$3394872 := \left(\left(- (2) \times \sqrt{78^4} \right) \times \left(- (93 \times 3) \right) \right)$$

$$3415467 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times 6) + \left((4^5) + 1 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$3418798 := \left(\left(\left(\left((8 - \sqrt{9}) \times 7 \right) + 8 \right)^{1 \times 4} \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$3418804 := \left(\left(\left((40 + \sqrt{8+8}) - 1 \right)^4 \right) + 3 \right)$$

$$3428971 := \left(\left((1 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(\left((8 + 2)^4 \right) - 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3429997 := \left(\left(\left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (9 - 2) \right)^4 \right) \right) \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$3437544 := \left(- \left(\left(4 + \left(4 \times (5^7) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(- (3) - \sqrt{4^3} \right)$$

$$3441123 := \left(\left(\left((3211 + \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) / 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3442656 := \left(\left((656^2) - 4 \right) \times \sqrt{4^3} \right)$$

$$3444764 := \left(-4 + \left(\left(6^{7-\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 443 \right) \right)$$

$$3445647 := \left(- (7) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6^5) \right) \times 443 \right) \right)$$

$$3448965 := \left((5 \times 69) \times \left(\left((8 + \sqrt{4})^4 \right) - 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3449946 := \left(\left(\left(\left((6 \times (\sqrt{4} + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-4) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-3) \right)$$

$$3453987 := \left(\left(\left((7 - ((8 \times 9) \times 3) \times 5) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$3455984 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (8) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times ((5 + 5) \times 4) \right)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3455994 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times ((5 + 5) \times 4) \right)^3 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3456936 := \left(63 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right) + ((5 \times 4))^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3458873 := \left(\left(\left((3 \times (7^8)) - 8 \right) / 5 \right) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3458879 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- (7^8) \right) \right) + 8 \right) / \left(- (5 \times (4 - 3)) \right) \right)$$

$$3466875 := \left(\left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- ((7 - 8) - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$3474499 := \left(\left(\left((9 + ((9 + (4^4)) \times 7))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3483627 := \left(7 \times \left(\left(\left((2 \times 6)^{-3+8} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3498656 := \left(- \left((6 - (5^6)) \right) \right) \times \left(8 + \sqrt{(9 \times 4)^3} \right)$$

$$3498849 := \left(- (9) \times \left(\sqrt{4^8} - \left(\left(- (8) + \sqrt{9^4} \right)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3524845 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + ((84 - 2) + 5) \right)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$3524885 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- (8) - \left(\left(\sqrt{8^4} + (25) \right)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3527496 := \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left(\sqrt{4^{7 \times 2}} - (53) \right) \right)$$

$$3529677 := \left(\left(\left((7 + (7^6)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (2 \times 5) \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$3538444 := \left(4 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 48 \right)^3 \right) - \left((5^3) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3542934 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\left((3^9) \times 2 \right) \times 45 \right) - 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3542983 := \left(\left(\left((3^{8+\sqrt{9}}) + 2 \right) \times (4 \times 5) \right) + 3 \right)$$

$$3543114 := \left(\left(-4 + \left((11^3)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \times (5 - 3)$$

$$3543116 := \left(- (6) + \left(\left((11^3)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times (5 - 3) \right) \right)$$

$$3543119 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((11^3)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times (5 - 3) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3543247 := \left(\left(\left(\left((7 + 4)^2 \right)^3 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \left((5^3) \right) \right)$$

$$3543876 := \left((6 \times \sqrt{7^8}) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^{4 \times 5}} + 3} \right) \right)$$

$$3549456 := \left(\left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- \left((5^4) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right)^{5-3} \right)$$

$$3552489 := \left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{8^{4 \times 2}} + \left(5^{5+3}\right)\right)\right)$$

$$3556224 := \sqrt{\sqrt{42^{2 \times 6}} \times (-5 + 53)}$$

$$3557449 := \left(\left(9^4\right) - \sqrt{4^7}\right) \times 553$$

$$3566683 := \sqrt{38^{\sqrt{6 \times 6}}} \times 65 + 3$$

$$3569184 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 8\right) + 1\right) \times \left(9 \times \left(6^5\right) \times 3\right)\right)$$

$$3569186 := \left(\left(6^8\right) - 1\right) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6\right)^5\right) + 3\right)$$

$$3579174 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\left(71^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + 7\right) \times 5\right) - 3\right)$$

$$3601989 := \left(\sqrt{9^8} \times \left(91 \times 06\right) + 3\right)$$

$$3628577 := \left(-7\right) + \left(\sqrt{\left(7^5 - 8\right)^2} \times \left(6^3\right)\right)$$

$$3629875 := \left(-5\right) - \left(\left(\left(7^{8-\sqrt{9}}\right) - 2\right) \times \left(-6^3\right)\right)$$

$$3631648 := \left(8 \times \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(\left(61^3\right) - 6\right) + 3$$

$$3631696 := \left(\left(\left(6/\sqrt{9}\right) \times 61\right)^3\right) \times (6/3)$$

$$3640464 := \left(\left(\left(4 - 640\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times (6 + 3)$$

$$3644964 := \left(\left(4 \times \left(6 + 9\right)^4\right) - \sqrt{4}\right) \times (6 \times 3)$$

$$3644995 := \left(-5\right) - \left(\left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9^4}\right)^4\right) / \left(-6 \times 3\right)\right)$$

$$3644999 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{9^4}\right)^4\right) / \left(-6\right)\right)\right) / \left(-3\right)$$

$$3645144 := \left(-4\right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(15^4\right)\right) \times \left(-6 \times 3\right)\right)$$

$$3656247 := \left(\left(7 + \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(26 \times \left(5^6\right)\right) - 3\right)$$

$$3662496 := \left(\left(6 \times 942\right) \times \sqrt{6^6}\right) \times 3$$

$$3667599 := \left(9^{9-5}\right) \times \left(\sqrt{7^6} + \left(6^3\right)\right)$$

$$3673384 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(8 \times 3\right)\right)^3\right) \times \left(-7 - \left(6^3\right)\right)\right)$$

$$3675129 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(2 + \left(15 \times 7\right)^{6-3}\right)\right)$$

$$3678534 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(3^5\right) \times \left(87^{6/3}\right)\right)\right)$$

$$3684784 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(8 \times 7\right)\right)^4\right) - \left(8^6\right)\right) / 3\right)$$

$$3684873 := \left(3 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{7^8} - \sqrt{4}\right) \times \sqrt{8^6}\right) + 3\right)\right)$$

$$3686403 := \left(\left(\left(30 \times \sqrt{4^6}\right)^{8-6}\right) + 3\right)$$

$$3687253 := \left(\left(\left(35^{\sqrt{2+7}}\right) \times 86\right) + 3\right)$$

$$3687918 := \left(\left(\left(8^{\sqrt{1 \times 9}}\right) \times \sqrt{7^8}\right) - 6\right) \times 3$$

$$3687921 := \left(\left(-1\right) + \left(\left(-\left(2^9\right)\right) \times \sqrt{7^8}\right) + 6\right) \times \left(-3\right)$$

$$3687924 := \left(\left(4 - \left(2^9\right) \times \sqrt{7^8}\right) \times \left(-6 - 3\right)\right)$$

$$3687928 := \left(-8\right) - \left(-\left(2^9\right) \times \sqrt{7^8 \times \left(6 + 3\right)}\right)$$

$$3687938 := \left(\left(8^3\right) \times \sqrt{9 \times 7^8}\right) + (6/3)$$

$$3687942 := \left(\left(2 + \sqrt{4^9 \times 7^8}\right) \times \left(6 - 3\right)\right)$$

$$3687947 := \left(-7\right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4^9 \times 7^8} + 6\right) \times \left(-3\right)\right)$$

$$3687978 := \left(\left(\left(8 \times 7\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times \left(-7\right) - \left(8 + 6\right)\right) \times \left(-3\right)$$

$$3689472 := \left(\left(-\left(2 - \left(7^4\right)\right)\right) + \sqrt{9}\right) \times \sqrt{8^6} \times 3$$

$$3696678 := \left(\left(8 - \left(-\left(7 - 66\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times \left(-6 \times 3\right)\right)$$

$$3697929 := \left(\left(\left(-92\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(-7\right) - 9\right)^{6/3}$$

$$3705696 := \left(6^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times \left(6 + \left(50 \times \left(7^3\right)\right)\right)$$

$$3715988 := -\left(\left(\sqrt{8^8} - \left(\left(9^{5+1}\right) \times 7\right) - 3\right)\right)$$

$$3718389 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^8} - 3\right) \times \left(81 \times 7\right) + 3\right)$$

$$3719898 := \left(\left(8 - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{8+\sqrt{9}}}\right) - 1\right)\right) \times \left(-7 \times 3\right)\right)$$

$$3719919 := \left(\left(9 \times \left(1 - \sqrt{9^9}\right)\right) - 1\right) \times \left(-7 \times 3\right)$$

$$3721386 := \left(\sqrt{6^8} + \left(\left(3^{12}\right) \times 7\right) + 3\right)$$

$$3721734 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(3 - 7\right) + 127\right)^3\right)$$

$$3723878 := \left(\left(\left(8 + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} \times 3\right)\right)^{\sqrt{2+7}}\right) + 3\right)$$

$$3736985 := \left(-5\right) \times \left(\left(-8\right) + \left(\sqrt{9^6} \times 3\right)\right) \times \left(-7^3\right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3738357 &:= (\sqrt{7^{5+3}} \times (((8^3) + 7) \times 3)) \\
 3747275 &:= (- (5) \times ((\sqrt{(7+2)^7} - \sqrt{4}) \times (- (7^3)))) \\
 3748075 &:= (-5 + \sqrt{\sqrt{7^{08}}})^4 - 7 \times 3 \\
 3748086 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8} + 08} \right)^4 \right) - (7+3) \right) \\
 3748088 &:= (- (8) + ((80+8) / \sqrt{4})^{7-3}) \\
 3748093 &:= (- (3) + (((\sqrt{9} + 08) \times 4)^{7-3})) \\
 3748094 &:= (((4 \times 9) + 08)^4) - \sqrt{7-3} \\
 3748099 &:= (\sqrt{9} + (((\sqrt{9} + 08) \times 4)^{7-3})) \\
 3748314 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times (((1-38)^4) - (7-3))) \\
 3748316 &:= (- (6) + (((1-38)^4) \times \sqrt{7-3})) \\
 3748319 &:= - ((\sqrt{9} - (((1-38)^4) \times \sqrt{7-3}))) \\
 3748447 &:= (((74^4) / 8) + \sqrt{4^7}) - 3 \\
 3749997 &:= (((7+9) \times \sqrt{9}) \times (9-4)^7) - 3 \\
 3750144 &:= (- (4) \times ((\sqrt{4} + 10) \times (- ((5^7) + 3)))) \\
 3751734 &:= ((\sqrt{4} - (((3^7) + 1) \times 5)) \times (- (7^3))) \\
 3764747 &:= (7 \times (((\sqrt{4} \times 7)^{4-6+7}) - 3)) \\
 3764752 &:= \left(\left(- ((2^5)) + \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right) \\
 3764753 &:= \left(- ((3 \times 5)) + \left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right) \right) \\
 3764759 &:= \left(- (9) + \left(\left((5+7) + \sqrt{4} \right)^6 / \sqrt{7-3} \right) \right) \\
 3764761 &:= \left(- ((1+6)) + \left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right) \right) \\
 3764762 &:= \left(\left(- ((2 \times 6)) + \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3764764 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} - 6) + \left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right) \right) \\
 3764765 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- (6) + \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) / (- (7+3)) \right) \right) \\
 3764767 &:= \left(- ((7-6)) + \left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right) \right) \\
 3764771 &:= \left(\left(- ((1-7)) + \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right) \\
 3764773 &:= \left(\left((3+7) + \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right) \\
 3764782 &:= \left(\left(28 + \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right) \\
 3764784 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times 8) + \left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right) \right) \\
 3764786 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} + \left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) \right) / \sqrt{7-3} \right) \\
 3767448 &:= (8 \times (((- (4) \times (\sqrt{4} - ((7^6)))) + (7^3)))) \\
 3767845 &:= (- (5) \times (\sqrt{4} - (((8+76) + 7^3)))) \\
 3767945 &:= (- (5) \times ((\sqrt{4} \times (-9)) - (((7+6) \times 7^3)))) \\
 3768656 &:= (((6^5) + ((6+8)^6)) / \sqrt{7-3}) \\
 3779136 &:= \left(\left(\left((6^3) \times 1 \right) \times 9 \right)^{\sqrt{7/7+3}} \right) \\
 3779264 &:= (\sqrt{4^6} \times (2 + (9^{7-\sqrt{7-3}}))) \\
 3786875 &:= (- (5) \times ((7 - (- (8) \times \sqrt{6^8})) \times (-73))) \\
 3792576 &:= \left(\left(- ((6^7)) + \left((52^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-7) \right) \right) \times (-3) \right) \\
 3794832 &:= \left(\sqrt{(2 \times 38)^4} \times (9 \times 73) \right) \\
 3795655 &:= \left(- (5) - \left(- \left(\left((5^6) - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^7+3}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 3795875 &:= \left((5 \times (7+8)^5) - \left((\sqrt{9} + 7)^3 \right) \right) \\
 3796413 &:= \left(- (3) + \left(\left((146 + \sqrt{9}) + 7 \right)^3 \right) \right) \\
 3796414 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((146 + \sqrt{9}) + 7 \right)^3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 3796418 &:= \left(\left(\left((81 \times \sqrt{4}) - 6 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \sqrt{7-3} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3796419 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((146 + \sqrt{9}) + 7 \right)^3 \right) \right) \\
 3796426 &:= \left(\left((6 \times (2 + (4 \times 6)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (7 + 3) \right) \\
 3796448 &:= \left(8 \times \left(4 + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + ((69 + 7)) \right)^3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 3796489 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 73 \right) \\
 3796531 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left((3 \times 5)^6 / \sqrt{9} \right) - (7^3) \right) \right) \\
 3796533 &:= \left(\left((3 + (3 \times 5)^6) / \sqrt{9} \right) - (7^3) \right) \\
 3796534 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((3 \times 5)^6 / \sqrt{9} \right) - (7^3) \right) \right) \\
 3796759 &:= \left(\left(- \left((9 - (5 \times 7)) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (7^3) \right) \\
 3796839 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{38} - 6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (7 - 3) \right) \right) \\
 3796854 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + (5 + 8))^6 / \sqrt{9} \right) - ((7 \times 3)) \right) \right) \\
 3796871 &:= \left(\left(((1 \times 7) + 8)^6 / \sqrt{9} \right) - (7 - 3) \right) \\
 3796873 &:= \left(3 \times \left((7 + 8)^6 / 9 \right) - \sqrt{7-3} \right) \\
 3796876 &:= \left(- (6) - \left(\left((7 + 8)^6 - (\sqrt{9} \times (-7)) \right) / (-3) \right) \right) \\
 3796877 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{7 \times 7} + 8)^6 / \sqrt{9} \right) + \sqrt{7-3} \right) \right) \\
 3796879 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} \times \left((7 + 8)^6 / 9 \right)) + (7 - 3) \right) \\
 3796896 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{(6+9)^{8 \times 6}} / \sqrt{9}} + 7 \times 3} \\
 3796948 &:= \left(\left(\left((8 + \sqrt{49})^6 / \sqrt{9} \right) + 73 \right) \right) \\
 3827975 &:= \left(\left((5^7) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{7 \sqrt{2 \times 8}} - 3 \right) \\
 3834747 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(- \left((4^7) - 4 \right) - (\sqrt{38^3}) \right) \right) \\
 3843184 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(8 + \left((1 - (3 + 4)^8) / 3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 3843194 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((9 + 1) - \left((3 + 4)^8 \right) / 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 3843198 &:= \left((8 - \left((\sqrt{9} - 1) \times (3 + 4)^8 \right)) / (-3) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3843287 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left((7^8) \times 2 \right) + 3 \right) - \sqrt{4^8} \right) / (-3) \right) \\
 3844669 &:= \left(\left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \left((4^8) - 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 3852288 &:= \left((\sqrt{8^8} / 2) \times \left((-2 - \sqrt{5^8}) \times (-3) \right) \right) \\
 3857868 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{(8+6)^8} \times (7 \times 5 - 8)^3} \\
 3859574 &:= - \left((\sqrt{4} - (7 \times (-((5 - 95) + 8))^3)) \right) \\
 3859579 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + (7 \times (-((5 - 95) + 8))^3) \right) \\
 3859597 &:= \left(7 \times (\sqrt{9} + (-((5 - 95) + 8))^3) \right) \\
 3866955 &:= \left(\left((5^{5+\sqrt{9}}) + (6 - (6^8)) \right) \times (-3) \right) \\
 3869899 &:= \left((9 - \sqrt{9}) + (89 + 68)^3 \right) \\
 3871867 &:= \left(\left(7 - \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}^{-1+7}} \right) \times (-83) \right) \\
 3872448 &:= \left(\left((8 - \sqrt{4})^{42/7} \right) \times 83 \right) \\
 3872946 &:= \left((- (6) - (4 \times 9)^{\sqrt{2+7}}) \times (-83) \right) \\
 3873792 &:= \left((2^{\sqrt{9}+7}) \times 3783 \right) \\
 3890625 &:= \sqrt{5^{2 \times 6} \times 09} \times 83 \\
 3892866 &:= \left(\left((6^6) + (82 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \times 83 \right) \\
 3892985 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(8 - \left((92^{\sqrt{9}}) - (83) \right) \right) \right) \\
 3897234 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((3^{2+7}) \times 9 \right) \times (8 + 3) \right) \right) \\
 3897322 &:= \left(- (22) \times \left((3 - 7) - (\sqrt{9}^{8+3}) \right) \right) \\
 3897366 &:= \left(66 \times \left(\sqrt{-3+7} + (9^{8-3}) \right) \right) \\
 3897436 &:= \left(\left(\left((6 + 3) + \sqrt{4} \right)^7 + 9 \right) / (8 - 3) \right) \\
 3906244 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} / (-2) + 6 \right)^{09} \right) - 3 \right) \right) \\
 3916815 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((- (1) + \sqrt{8^6})^{-1+\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-3) \right) \right) \\
 3926667 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(7 \times 6)^6} \times (62 - 9) \right) + 3 \right) \\
 3932145 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- \left((4^{(1+2) \times 3} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 3 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$3932154 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(5 \times \left(\left((1^2) + 3 \right)^9 \right) \right) \right) \times (-3) \right)$$

$$3932175 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- \left(\left((7+1)^2 \right)^3 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} - 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3934656 := \left((6^5) \times \left(- (6) + \sqrt{4^{3 \times 9/3}} \right) \right)$$

$$3944309 := \left(\left(\left(90 + (34 \times \sqrt{4}) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$3944314 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(- \left((1 - (3 \times (4 + 49)))^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3944315 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{5-1} \times (3^4) \right) - 4 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 3 \right)$$

$$3944324 := \left(- (4) \times \left(\left(- (2) \times \left(\left((3^4) - \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) - 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3944328 := \left(8 \times \left(2 + \left(\left((3^4) - \sqrt{4} \right)^{9/3} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3947535 := 5 \times \sqrt{(3 \times 57)^4 \times 9^3}$$

$$3950784 := \left(\left(- \left((4 \times ((8 - 70) + 5)) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / 3 \right)$$

$$3956283 := \left(\sqrt{3^8} \times \left((2 + 65) \times (9^3) \right) \right)$$

$$3966489 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} + 4} \right) \times (6^6) \right) + \left((9^3) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3972969 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-2) \right) \right) \times \left((7 \times \sqrt{9})^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3986631 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(1 - 36)^6} - 8 \right) \times 93 \right)$$

$$3992973 := \left(\left(\left((3 + 7) \times (9 + 2) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9 \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$3992979 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left(7 - \left((9 + 2) + 99 \right)^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$3992991 := \left(\left(\left((1 + 9) \times (9 + 2) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$3992994 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left((9 \times 9) + 29 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-3) \right)$$

$$3992995 := \left(- (5) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((9 + 2) + 99 \right)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$3992997 := \left(\left(\left(\left((7 + \sqrt{9}) \times (9 + 2) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$3995649 := \left((9^4) \times \left(\left((65 + \sqrt{9}) \times 9 \right) - 3 \right) \right)$$

$$3997836 := \left(\left(- \left((63 \times 87) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(- (9^3) \right) \right)$$

$$4028864 := \left(- (4) \times \left(- \left((6^8) \right) + \left(820^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4036457 := - \left(\left(\left(7^{5+\sqrt{4}} \right) - \left(6 \times (30^4) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4040102 := \left(\left(2010^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \sqrt{04} \right)$$

$$4043763 := \sqrt{(3 + 6)^7 \times (3 + 40)^4}$$

$$4063232 := \left(\left(2 \times (32^3) \right) \times \left(60 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4064256 := \left(\left(6 \times ((52 + 4) \times 6) \right)^{\sqrt{04}} \right)$$

$$4072324 := \left(\left(\left((42 + 3)^2 \right) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{04}} \right)$$

$$4083297 := \left(\left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^{2+3} \right) - 804 \right)$$

$$4084179 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7 \right)^{1+4} \right) + 80 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4084579 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7 \right)^5 \right) + 480 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4085187 := \left(\left((7^8) - (1 + 5)^8 \right) + \sqrt{04} \right)$$

$$4096766 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{6^6} - \sqrt{7^6} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{04} \right)$$

$$4099896 := \left(\sqrt{(6 + 9)^8} - 9 \right) \times \sqrt{904}$$

$$4108779 := \left(9 \times \left(\left(77^{\sqrt{8+01}} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4112784 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{4} \times 8^7} - 21 + 1 \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4116175 := \left(- \left((5^7) \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{16^{11}} \right) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4117495 := \left(5 \times \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{4})^7 \right) - (11 \times 4) \right) \right)$$

$$4117685 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \times \left(- \left(6 - (7^{11-4}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4117772 := \left(- \left(\left((2 - 7) \times \left((7^7) + 11 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4117774 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \times \left(- \left((7^7) + 11 \right) \right) \right) + 4 \right)$$

$$4124956 := \left(\left(\left(6 + \sqrt{(5 \times 9)^4} \right)^2 \right) - (1 + 4) \right)$$

$$4128453 := \left(- \left(\left(3 \times (5 - (4^8)) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{21^4}}$$

$$4128459 := (\sqrt{9} \times (-((5 - (4^8)) \times 21)) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$4128684 := (((((4^8) \times 6) - 8) \times 21) / \sqrt{4})$$

$$4135688 := (8 \times (((((8 \times 6) \times 5) \times 3) - 1)^{\sqrt{4}}))$$

$$4137156 := (((6 \times ((5 - 1) - (7^3))))^{\sqrt{1 \times 4}})$$

$$4139527 := (7 \times (((2^{5+\sqrt{9}}) \times 3) + 1)^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4145152 := (-((2 - (51 \times 5))) \times \sqrt{4^{14}})$$

$$4148874 := (\sqrt{4} - (-7) \times (-8) + (84^{-1+4}))$$

$$4148907 := (-7) \times (\sqrt{09} - (84^{-1+4}))$$

$$4148949 := ((9 - \sqrt{4}) \times (\sqrt{9} + (84^{-1+4})))$$

$$4149369 := (((9 \times (6^3)) + (94 - 1))^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4153444 := (4 \times (((4^{\sqrt{4}+3}) - 5)^{\sqrt{1 \times 4}}))$$

$$4167845 := (5 \times (((4 + 8) \times 76) + 1)^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4169764 := (((((4^6) / (7 - 9)) + 6))^{\sqrt{1 \times 4}})$$

$$4169984 := (-((4 \times 8)) \times (9 - (((\sqrt{9} \times 6) + 1)^4)))$$

$$4173849 := (((\sqrt{9} \times (-48)) + (3^7))^{\sqrt{1 \times 4}})$$

$$4176433 := (-(((3 - ((3 + 4)^6)) \times 71)) / \sqrt{4})$$

$$4176779 := (-9) - (-(((7 + (7^6)) \times 71)) / \sqrt{4})$$

$$4177497 := ((\sqrt{7+9^{4+7}}) - (7^{1+4}))$$

$$4177936 := ((6 + (((3 \times 97) \times 7) + 1))^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4178302 := (-(((20^3) - ((8^7) - 1))) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$4178665 := (-((5^6)) + (-((6 - ((8^7) - 1)))) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$4182025 := ((5 \times (((20^2) + 8) + 1))^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4186179 := (9 \times (7 + ((1 + 681)^{\sqrt{4}})))$$

$$4193278 := (((8^7) - (((2^3)^{\sqrt{9}}) + 1)) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$4193818 := (((8^{-1+8}) - \sqrt{39+1}) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$4194048 := (\sqrt{84} \times ((04^{9-1}) - 4))$$

$$4194114 := ((4^{11}) - (\sqrt{4} \times (91 + 4)))$$

$$4194122 := (((2^{21}) \times \sqrt{4}) - (91 \times \sqrt{4}))$$

$$4194254 := (\sqrt{4} - (52 - ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)))$$

$$4194258 := (-(((8 \times (5 - 2) - (4^9))) - 1)) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$4194262 := ((2^{6+2^4}) - (\sqrt{9} \times 14))$$

$$4194269 := -((\sqrt{9} + (((6 + 2) - (4^{9+1})) \times 4)))$$

$$4194273 := (-3) - ((\sqrt{7^2} - ((4^{9+1}))) \times 4)$$

$$4194278 := (((8^{\sqrt{7^2}}) - (4 + 9)) \times \sqrt{1 \times 4})$$

$$4194279 := (\sqrt{9} - ((\sqrt{7^2} - ((4^{9+1}))) \times 4))$$

$$4194291 := (-1) + ((\sqrt{9} - (\sqrt{2^{4^{9+1}}})) \times (-4))$$

$$4194293 := ((-3) \times \sqrt{9}) - ((2 - ((4^{9+1}) \times 4)))$$

$$4194295 := (-5) - ((\sqrt{9} - ((2 + (4^{9+1})))) \times 4)$$

$$4194296 := ((6/\sqrt{9}) \times (((2 \times (4^9)) - 1) \times 4))$$

$$4194297 := (-7) + ((\sqrt{9} - 2) \times ((4^{9+1}) \times 4))$$

$$4194298 := (((8^{9-2}) \times \sqrt{4}) - ((9 + 1) - 4))$$

$$4194314 := (\sqrt{4} - (((1 - 3) - (4^{9+1})) \times 4))$$

$$4194319 := (\sqrt{9} + (((1 \times 3) + (4^{9+1})) \times 4))$$

$$4194349 := ((9 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)) + (((4^{9+1}) \times 4)))$$

$$4194364 := (((\sqrt{4} \times 6) + ((3 + (4^{9+1})))) \times 4)$$

$$4194374 := (((\sqrt{4}^{7 \times 3}) + ((4 \times 9) - 1)) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$4194378 := (((8^7) + 34) + \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{1 \times 4})$$

$$4194398 := (((8 \times (9 - 3) + (4^9))) - 1) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4194428 &:= \left(\left((8^2) \times (\sqrt{4} + (4^{9-1})) \right) - 4 \right) \\
 4194434 &:= \left(\left((4^3) \times (\sqrt{4} + (4^{9-1})) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4194478 &:= \left((87 \times \sqrt{4}) + \left((4^{9+1}) \times 4 \right) \right) \\
 4194488 &:= \left(\left((8^8) / 4 \right) + \left((\sqrt{4} \times 91) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4194494 &:= \left((4^{9+\sqrt{4}}) + (\sqrt{4} \times (91 + 4)) \right) \\
 4194498 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left((\sqrt{9} \times 4) + (4^9) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4194647 &:= \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} + \left((4^{9+1}) \times 4 \right)} \right) \\
 4194668 &:= \left(\left(\left((8^{\sqrt{6 \times 6}}) \times 4 \right) + (91) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 4194748 &:= \left((\sqrt{8^4} \times (7 + (4^{9-1}))) - 4 \right) \\
 4194752 &:= \left(\left((2^5) \times (7 + (4^{9-1})) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4194782 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left((8^7) - 4 \right) + \sqrt{9^{1+4}} \right) \right) \\
 4194864 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} + \left((4^9) - 1 \right) \right) \times (-4) \right) \right) \\
 4194878 &:= \left(\left((8^7) + \left((8 \times 4) \times 9 - 1 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4195478 &:= \left(\left(\left((8^7) - 4 \right) + 591 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4195584 &:= \left(\sqrt{4^8} \times \left(5 + \left((5 - \sqrt{9})^{14} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4196248 &:= \left(\left(- \left((8^4)^2 \right) - \sqrt{6^{9+1}} \right) / (-4) \right) \\
 4197695 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left((\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left((6^7) - 91 \right) \right)) - 4 \right) \right) \\
 4198697 &:= - \left(\left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) - \left(\left((6^8) \times (9 + 1) \right) / 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4199488 &:= \left(\left((8^8) / 4 \right) + \sqrt{(9 \times (9 - 1))^4} \right) \\
 4199769 &:= \left(\sqrt{9^6} \times (7 \times ((9 \times 91) + 4)) \right) \\
 4202498 &:= \left(\left(\left((8^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 4 \right) + 2 \right)^{02} - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4204998 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) - 4 \right)^{02} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4209856 &:= \left(\left((6^5) + (8^{9-02}) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4218916 &:= \left(6 + (-1 + \sqrt{9})^{8+1+2} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4222867 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(7+6)^8} + (2^{22}) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4223526 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(\left((2^5) - 3 \right)^2 - 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4228232 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(\left((3^{-2+8}) - 2 \right) \times 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4231249 &:= \left(\left(9 + \left(\left((4^2) \times 1 \right)^3 / 2 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4235264 &:= \left((4^6) \times \left((2 \times 5) + \sqrt{32^4} \right) \right) \\
 4235366 &:= \left(\left(\left(6 \times \left((6/3) + 5 \right)^3 \right) \right)^2 + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4239481 &:= \left((-1) + \left((8 \times (\sqrt{4^9} + 3)) / 2 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4239866 &:= \left(\left((6^6) / 8 \right) \times \left((9^3) - 2 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4239888 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left((8/8) - (9^3) \right) \right)^2 + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4245694 &:= \left((4 + 9) \times \left((6^5) \times 42 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4245696 &:= \left(\sqrt{6^9} \times 6 \times (542 + 4) \right) \\
 4247721 &:= \left(((1 + 2) + ((7 \times 7) \times 42))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4251527 &:= \left(\left(\left((7^2) + 5 \right)^{-1+5} - 2 \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4251844 &:= \left(\left((-4) \times (-4 - \sqrt{8^{1+5}}) - 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4255969 &:= \left((9 + 6) + \left((9 - 5)^5 \times 2 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4258304 &:= \left((40^3) - \left((8^{5+2}) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4259499 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((9 + (\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}})^5) - (24) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4259523 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left((2 + (5 \times \sqrt{9}))^5 - (2^4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4259619 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((-1) - (-6 \times \sqrt{9}) \right)^5 + (2^4) \right) \right) \\
 4259643 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + (6 + 9))^5 + (24) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4263158 &:= \left(- \left(\left(8 \times \left(5 - \left(\left(1 + (3^6) \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4263168 &:= \left(8 \times \left(- \left(\left(6 - \left(\left(1 + (3^6) \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4263182 &:= \left(-2 - \left(8 \times \left(- \left(\left(\left(1 + (3^6) \right)^2 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4263184 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(8 - \left(\left(\left(1 + (3^6) \right)^2 \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4263189 &:= \left(- \left(\left(9 - \left(8 \times \left(\left(1 + (3^6) \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4263194 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\left(1 + (3^6) \right)^2 \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4264225 &:= \left(\left(\left((5 - 22) - \left((4^6) / 2 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4268348 &:= \left(- (8) + \left(\left((43 \times 8) \times 6 \right) + 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4272489 &:= \left(\left(9 + \left((84/2) \times (7^2) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4276624 &:= \left(\left(4 \times \left(\sqrt{(2+6)^6} + (7-2) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4285736 &:= \left((637 \times (58^2)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4286592 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^5} \times 6 \right) + (8-2) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4291627 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(\left(261 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^2 \right) \right) + 4 \right) \\
 4292164 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \sqrt{6^{12}} \right) \times (-92) \right) - 4 \right) \\
 4292166 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((6^6) \times 1 \right) - 2 \right) \times 92 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4292348 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(8 - \sqrt{4} \right)^{3 \times 2} \right) \times 92 \right) - 4 \right) \\
 4293184 &:= \left(\left(- (4) \times \left(\left(- (8) - \sqrt{(1+3)^9} \right) + 2 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4293374 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^7} + (3/3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 2 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4293376 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((6 \times 7) \times 3 \right) + 3 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 2 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4293378 &:= \left(\left((87 \times 3) - 3 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} / \sqrt{2^4} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4293456 &:= \left(\left(\left((6^5) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (3 \times 92) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4295555 &:= \left(55 \times \left(\sqrt{5^{5+9}} - (24) \right) \right) \\
 4295666 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(\left(6 + (6^5) \right) \times 92 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4296674 &:= \left(\left(\left(47 + (6^6) \right) \times 92 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4296855 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{5^{8+6}} \times (- (9+2)) \right) + 4 \right) \right) \\
 4296945 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(5^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} \right) + 6 \right) \times (9+2) \right) + 4 \right) \\
 4297329 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left((2+3) + \left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 2 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4298328 &:= \left(8 \times \left(2 + \left((3 - (8 \times 92))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4309768 &:= \left(- (8) + \left(\left(6 \times \left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) + 03 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4309776 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{7 \times 7^{\sqrt{9}}} \right) + 03 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4312957 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left((59^{2+1}) \times 3 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4312959 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((59^{2+1}) \times (3+4) \right) \right) \\
 4319996 &:= \left(\left(\left((69-9)^{\sqrt{9}+1} \right) / 3 \right) - 4 \right) \\
 4323597 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}+5} \right) - ((3+2)) \right) \times (-3) \right) / (-4) \right) \\
 4324848 &:= \left(-8 + 4^8 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{2^{3 \times 4}} \right) \\
 4333568 &:= \sqrt{8^6 \times (5^3 - 33)^4} \\
 4344384 &:= (48 + 3) \times \sqrt{44^{3 \times \sqrt{4}}} \\
 4344386 &:= \left(\left(\left((6 \times 8) + 3 \right) \times (44^3) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4347648 &:= \sqrt{(8+4)^6} \times 74 \times 34 \\
 4349952 &:= 2 \times 59 \times 9 \times \sqrt{4^{3 \times 4}} \\
 4351396 &:= \left((69 \times 31) - 53 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4357647 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left((4 \times 67) - 5 \right) \times 3 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4359742 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(4 \times \left(\left(\left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) + 5 \right) \times 3 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4359744 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 7 \right) \times \left(- (9 - (5^3)) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4368384 &:= \left(- \left(\left((4 - 83) \times (8 \times 6^3) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4373958 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(8 \times (5 \times 9)^3 \right) - 7 \right) \times 3 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4373966 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(6 \times \left(6 - \left(9 \times (3 + 7) \right)^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4373979 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- (7) - \left(- \left(\left(9 \times (3 + 7) \right)^3 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4373992 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(9 \times (3 + 7) \right)^3 \right) - 4 \right) \right) \\
 4373995 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(9 \times (3 + 7) \right)^3 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4374978 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(\left(7 \times \left(9 - 4 \right)^7 \right) - 3 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4375278 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 \times 7 \right) \times \left(2 + \left(\left(5^7 \right) + 3 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4376464 &:= \left(-4 \times 6 + \sqrt{46^{7-3}} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4384836 &:= \left(6 + \left(\left(\left(3 + 84 \right) \times 8 \right) \times 3 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4385664 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(6^6 \right) \times \left((5 + 8) + 34 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4385666 &:= \left(\left(\left(6^6 \right) \times \left((6 + 5) + 83 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4392648 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(\left((4 \times 6) / 2 \right) + \left(9^3 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4393568 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(\left(65^3 \right) - \left(9 \times 3 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4394529 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(2 + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \right) - 3 \right) \right) / 4 \right) \right) \\
 4394531 &:= \left(\left(- (1) + \left(3 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \right) / 4 \right) \\
 4394535 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (5) - \left(3 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 3 \right) / (-4) \\
 4397409 &:= \left(9 \times \left((0 - 4) + (79 \times 3) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4398592 &:= \left(2^9 \times \left(- (58) + \sqrt{93^4} \right) \right) \\
 4416386 &:= \left(- (6) - \left(- (8) \times \left(\left(3^6 \right) + 14 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4416389 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(- (8) \times \left(\left(3^6 \right) + 14 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4416392 &:= \left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \times \left(\left(3^6 \right) + 14 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4428286 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(6 \times \left(8 - \left(2^8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)^2 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - \sqrt{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4429955 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\sqrt{9^{9+2}} \right) \right) - \left(4^4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4434647 &:= \left(\left(7^4 \right) \times \left(\left(- (6) + \sqrt{43^4} \right) + 4 \right) \right) \\
 4435233 &:= \left(- (3) + \left(\left(\left(3^{2+5} \right) - \left(3^4 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4435234 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\left(3^{2+5} \right) - \left(3^4 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4435236 &:= \left(\left(\left(6 \times \left(3^2 \right) \right) \times \left(5 + 34 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4435239 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\left(3^{2+5} \right) - \left(3^4 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4437576 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(\left(7^5 \right) + \sqrt{7-3} \right) \times (-44) \right) \right) \\
 4439449 &:= \left(\left(\left(9 - \sqrt{4} \right)^4 \right) \times \sqrt{\left(9 + 34 \right)^4} \right) \\
 4443664 &:= \left(\left(\left(46^{6/3} \right) - (4 + 4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4455492 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(2 - \left(9 + 4 \right)^5 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{5+4} \right) \times 4 \\
 4455496 &:= \left(\left(\left(6 \times \left(9 + 4 \right)^5 \right) \right) + \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4455576 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(6 + 7 \right)^5 \right) + 5 \right) \times \sqrt{5+4} \right) \times 4 \\
 4456444 &:= \left(-4 + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(4^6 \right) \times 544 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4456871 &:= \left(\left(- (17) \times \left(- \left(\left(8^6 \right) - \sqrt{5^4} \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4460544 &:= \left(44 \times \left((50 - 6) + 4 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4464769 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (6 - 7) \right) + \sqrt{46^4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4465503 &:= \left(\left(305 \times \left((5 + 6)^4 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4466688 &:= \sqrt{8^8} \times \left(6 + \sqrt{66^4} \right) / 4 \\
 4468996 &:= \left(\left(- (6) + \left(\left((9 + 9) + \sqrt{8^6} \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4470662 &:= \left(2 + (6 \times 6) \right) \times \left(07^{\sqrt{4}+4} \right) \\
 4473227 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{72^2} - \left(3^7 \right) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \sqrt{4} \\
 4473229 &:= \left(\left(\left(9 \times (2 - 237) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4476789 &:= -\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{8 \times 7}} + 6^7} \times 4 \times 4}} \\
 4476928 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(8/2)^9} - ((6^7) \times 4) \right) \times (-4) \right) \\
 4476942 &:= \left((-2 - \sqrt{4^9}) + (((6 \times 7) + 4)^4) \right) \\
 4476944 &:= \left(\left((-4 + \sqrt{4^9}) - ((6^7) \times 4) \right) \times (-4) \right) \\
 4477394 &:= -\left(\left((4^{\sqrt{9}}) - (((3 - (7 \times 7)))^4) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4477447 &:= \left((-7) - \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(((4 \times 7) - 74)^4 \right) \\
 4477449 &:= \left((-9) + \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(((4 \times 7) - 74)^4 \right) \\
 4477451 &:= \left(-1 \right) + \left(\left(\left((-5) + \sqrt{4} \right) + ((7 \times 7))^4 \right) - 4 \right) \\
 4477454 &:= \left((4 - (((5 - 4) - 7) \times 7))^4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4477455 &:= \left(-5 \right) + \left(\left(\left((-5) + \sqrt{4} \right) + ((7 \times 7))^4 \right) + 4 \right) \\
 4477458 &:= \left(((8 - 54)^{7-7+4}) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4477459 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((5 - 4) + ((7 \times 7) - 4)^4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4477744 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 4)^7 \right) - 77 \right) \times (4 \times 4) \right) \\
 4477968 &:= \left(\sqrt{8^6} + \left(\left((9 + 7) + 7 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)^4 \right) \\
 4478576 &:= \left(\left(-((6^7)) + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) \times \left((-7) \times \sqrt{4} - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4478764 &:= \left(-\left(\left((4 - (6^7)) \times 8 \right) + 74 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4478876 &:= \left(\left(\left((6^7) - 8 \right) \times 8 \right) + (7 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4478944 &:= 4 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{(4 \times 9)^{8 \times 7}} - \sqrt{4}}}} \right) \times 4 \\
 4478974 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left((7 - 9) + 8 \right)^7 \times 4 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 4478978 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left((7 - 9) + 8 \right)^7 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \sqrt{4} \\
 4478979 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\left((7 - 9) + 8 \right)^7 \times 4 \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \\
 4478986 &:= \left(\left(\left(-((6^8)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-8) \right) / (7 - 4) \right) + \sqrt{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4478992 &:= \left(2^9 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{8 \times 7}} + 4}} \right) \times 4 \\
 4479456 &:= \left(\left((6 \times 5) + (\sqrt{4 \times 9^7}) \right) \times (4 \times 4) \right) \\
 4479488 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{8^8} + \left((4 \times \sqrt{9})^7 \right) \right) / (4 + 4) \right) \\
 4479976 &:= \left(\left(6 - \left(7 \times \left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{9}) - 7 \right)^4 \right) \right) \right) \times (-4) \right) \\
 4481689 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left((\sqrt{8^6} + (18)) \times (-4) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4485924 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9}) + (5 \times 8) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4485996 &:= \left(\left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left((5 \times (8^4)) + 4 \right) \right) \\
 4487168 &:= \left(\left((8 \times ((6 \times 1)^7)) + (8^4) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4488976 &:= \left(6^7 + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} - 8)^8} \right) \times 4 \times 4 \\
 4492381 &:= \left(\left(-((1 - (83 \times 2)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (4^4) \right) \\
 4492496 &:= \left(\sqrt{69^4} - 2 \right) \times 944 \\
 4494404 &:= \left(\left((40 \times (4 + 49))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 4 \right) \\
 4496182 &:= \left(\left(\left((2^8) \times 1 \right) + 6 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} / \sqrt{4 \times 4} \right) \\
 4496184 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4^8} + (1 \times 6))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / 4 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4498641 &:= \left((1 + (4 \times ((6 \times 89) - 4)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4498944 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 9) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \left(-(4^4) \right) \right) \\
 4499448 &:= \left(-8 \right) - \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times (4 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(-(4^4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4499454 &:= \left(\left((4^5) \times \left((4 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4499456 &:= \left(\left((6 \times 5) - 4 \right)^{9/\sqrt{9}} \times (4^4) \right) \\
 4499458 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 \times \left((5 \times \sqrt{4}) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 4 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4499464 &:= \left(\left(\left((-4 + \sqrt{6^4 \times 9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 4499472 &:= \left(\left(\left((2 \times (\sqrt{7^4} + \sqrt{9}))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 4 \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 4499474 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times (7 \times 49)) \times ((9^4) - \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 4499488 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left((8 \times (4 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / \sqrt{4} + 4 \right) \right) \\
 4499736 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(- (3) + (79 \times (9 + \sqrt{4})) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4499817 &:= - \left(\left((7^{\sqrt{1+8}}) \times (\sqrt{9} + (-((9^4)) \times \sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 4509477 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(- (7) + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 9)^{05} \right) \times (-4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4515625 &:= \left(\left((5 + (2 \times 6)) \times \sqrt{5^{1+5}} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4515872 &:= \left(\sqrt{(2 \times 7)^8} + ((51 - 5)^4) \right) \\
 4526796 &:= 6 \times 97 \times (\sqrt{6^{2 \times 5}} + \sqrt{4}) \\
 4528382 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(((8 \times 38) \times (2 + 5))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4528384 &:= \left(\left((4 \times (8^3)) + ((8 \times 2) \times 5) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4528387 &:= \left(\left((7 \times 8) \times 38 \right)^2 + \sqrt{5+4} \right) \\
 4534656 &:= \left((6 \times \sqrt{56^4}) \times ((3^5) - \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 4543543 &:= \left(\left((34^5) + (3 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) / (5 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 4546773 &:= \left((3 \times 77) \times \left((6/\sqrt{4})^{5+4} \right) \right) \\
 4547494 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times 947) \times \left((\sqrt{4} + 5)^4 \right) \right) \\
 4548956 &:= \left(\left((65 \times 9) \times \left((8 - \sqrt{4})^5 \right) \right) - 4 \right) \\
 4549679 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{9^7} - ((6 \times 9)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + (- (5) \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 4549689 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{8+6}} - (9 + 45) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4553334 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times (-((3 \times 3)^3))) \times (-((5^5)) + \sqrt{4}) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4555926 &:= \left(\sqrt{6^2} \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 5)^5 \right) - (54) \right) \right) \\
 4555956 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left((5 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \right) + ((5 - 54)) \right) \right) \\
 4556386 &:= \left((68 + ((3^6) \times (5^5))) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4558225 &:= \left((((((52 + 2) \times 8) - 5) \times 5)^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \\
 4559945 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left((4 \times 9) - (955^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right) \\
 4562488 &:= \left(- (8) + \left((8 \times (\sqrt{4} + 265))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4562496 &:= \left(\left(6 \times (9 \times 4) + ((2^6) \times 5) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4574296 &:= \left(((692/4) - 7)^{\sqrt{5+4}} \right) \\
 4575455 &:= \left(\left((55^4) + (57 \times 5) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4582969 &:= \left(\left((9^6) \times 9 \right) + \left(- \left((2 + 8)^5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4583881 &:= \left((((((1 + 88) \times 3) \times 8) + 5)^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \\
 4586349 &:= \left((9^{4+3}) + \left(- (6) \times \left((8^5) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4586379 &:= \left((9^7) - \left(3 \times \left(- (6) + \left((8^5) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4587455 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(5 - \left((\sqrt{4} - (7 \times (8^5))) \times (-4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4587456 &:= \left(\left(6 + (5 \times (\sqrt{4} - (7 \times (8^5)))) \right) \right) \times (-4) \\
 4587478 &:= \left(\left(\left((8 \times 7) \times (4^7) \right) - 8 \right) \times 5 - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4587484 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((4^8) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times 7 \right) - 8 \right) \times 5 + 4 \right) \\
 4587497 &:= \left(\left(- (7) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left((4^7) \times 8 \right) \times 5 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4587514 &:= \left(- \left(4 \times \left(1 - \left(5 \times 7 \times (8^5) \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4587519 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(1 - \left(5 \times 7 \times (8^5) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \\
 4587532 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \left(3 + \left(5 \times 7 \times (8^5) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4587534 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(3 + \left(5 \times 7 \times (8^5) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \\
 4587544 &:= \left(\left((-4 - \sqrt{4}) - \left(5 \times 7 \times (8^5) \right) \right) \times (-4) \right) \\
 4587545 &:= \left(\sqrt{5^4} + \left(5 \times 7 \times \left((8^5) \times 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4587584 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times (-8)) - \left(5 \times 7 \times (8^5) \right) \right) \times (-4) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$4587595 := (- (5) \times ((\sqrt{9} \times (-5)) - ((7 \times ((8^5) \times 4))))))$$

$$4588075 := (- (5) - (- (70) \times (8 + ((8^5) \times \sqrt{4}))))$$

$$4588467 := (- (((7^6) + 4)) \times (- ((8 \times 8)) + \sqrt{5^4}))$$

$$4596736 := (((6 + (3^7)) - ((6 \times 9) - 5))^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4599445 := (- (5) - (((44^{\sqrt{9}}) - 9) \times (-54)))$$

$$4599936 := (((63 + \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}}) \times ((9 - 5) \times 4))$$

$$4599944 := (((((44 \times \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}}) + (9 - 5)) \times \sqrt{4}))$$

$$4599946 := (((((6 \times ((4 + 9) + 9))^{\sqrt{9}}) + 5) \times \sqrt{4}))$$

$$4609375 := ((5^7) \times (3 + (9 \times 06)) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$4613904 := (((((40 \times 9) - 3) + 1) \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4614778 := (((((877^{\sqrt{4}}) + 1) \times 6) - \sqrt{4}))$$

$$4626876 := (- (6) + ((78^{6-2}) / \sqrt{64}))$$

$$4626879 := - ((\sqrt{9} - ((78^{6-2}) / \sqrt{64})))$$

$$4626882 := (2 \times (((8 - 86) / 2))^{6-\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4626898 := ((8 + ((9 - (8 \times 6)))^{-2+6}) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$4635409 := (9 + (04 \times 536))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4638732 := ((23 \times ((7^{8-3}) \times 6)) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$4639716 := (((6 \times (1 - (((7 \times 9) - 3) \times 6))))^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4644297 := (- (7) \times ((9^2) - (\sqrt{4} \times ((4 \times 6)^4))))$$

$$4644498 := (((((8 + 9)^4) \times \sqrt{4}) + ((46^4)))$$

$$4644783 := - ((\sqrt{3^8} + ((7 \times \sqrt{4}) \times (- ((4 \times 6)^4))))))$$

$$4644867 := (((7 \times (((6 \times 8)^4) / 4)) + 6) / \sqrt{4})$$

$$4644892 := (\sqrt{2 \times 98} \times (\sqrt{4} + ((4 \times 6)^4)))$$

$$4644927 := (\sqrt{7^2} \times (9 + (\sqrt{4} \times ((4 \times 6)^4))))$$

$$4651749 := ((9^4) \times \sqrt{(715 - 6)^{\sqrt{4}}})$$

$$4652649 := (((((9^4) / (6/2)) - (5 \times 6))^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4657463 := (- ((3 - ((6 + (4 \times 7)) \times 5)))^{6/\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4657824 := (\sqrt{4} \times (((((2^8) \times 7) + 5) \times (6^4))))$$

$$4661281 := (((1 - 8) + 2166)^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4664397 := 79 \times \sqrt{(3^{4+6} - 6)^{\sqrt{4}}}$$

$$4665344 := (- (4) \times ((4^3) - ((5 \times \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{4}})))$$

$$4665425 := (- ((5^2)) \times (\sqrt{4} + (5 - ((6^6) \times 4))))$$

$$4665472 := (- ((2^7)) + (((\sqrt{4} \times 5) \times \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{4}}))$$

$$4665475 := (- (5) \times ((7 - \sqrt{4}) \times (5 - ((6^6) \times 4))))$$

$$4665502 := (- ((20 \times (5 - (5 \times (6^6)))))) + \sqrt{4}$$

$$4665544 := (- (4) \times (4 - (- (5) \times (- ((5 \times (6^6))) + \sqrt{4}))))$$

$$4665572 := (- ((2 \times (7 - ((5 \times 5) \times (6^6)))))) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4665574 := (\sqrt{4} - ((7 - ((5 \times 5) \times (6^6))) \times 4))$$

$$4665579 := ((\sqrt{9} \times (-7)) + (((5 \times 5) \times ((6^6) \times 4))))$$

$$4665589 := - ((\sqrt{9} + (((8 - ((5 \times 5) \times ((6^6) \times 4))))))$$

$$4665594 := (- ((4 - ((95 + 5) \times (6^6)))) - \sqrt{4})$$

$$4665624 := (\sqrt{4^2} \times (6 + ((5 \times \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{4}})))$$

$$4667793 := (- (3) - (- ((9 \times 7)) \times (\sqrt{(7 \times 6)^6 + 4})))$$

$$4667794 := - ((\sqrt{4} + (- ((9 \times 7)) \times (\sqrt{(7 \times 6)^6 + 4}))))$$

$$4667796 := (((6 + \sqrt{9}) \times 7) \times (\sqrt{(7 \times 6)^6 + 4}))$$

$$4667799 := (\sqrt{9} - (- ((9 \times 7)) \times (\sqrt{(7 \times 6)^6 + 4})))$$

$$4669921 := ((1 + (((- (2) + \sqrt{9}) + 9) \times \sqrt{6^6}))^{\sqrt{4}})$$

$$4674856 := \left(\left(\left(6^5 \right) + \left(\left(8 + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(- \left(7^6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (-4) \right)$$

$$4678569 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-6) \right) + \left(\left(- \left((5-8)^7 \right) - 6 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4682896 := \left(\left(\left(\left((6 \times 9) - 8 \right)^2 \right) + (8 \times 6) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4682969 := \left(\left(\left(9^6 \right) \times 9 \right) - \sqrt{(2+8)^{6+4}} \right)$$

$$4685292 := \left(- \left(\left(\left((2 \times 92) - (5^8) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4685452 := \left(-\sqrt{2^{5 \times 4}} + 5^8 \times 6 \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4685484 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 84 \right) - (5^8) \right) \times (-6) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4686746 := \left(- (6) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4^7} - 6 \right) \times \left(- \left((8+6)^4 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4686749 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\sqrt{4^7} - 6 \right) \times \left(- \left((8+6)^4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4687244 := \left(- \left((4^4) \right) + \left(\left(\left((2-7) \right)^8 \right) \times 6 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4687416 := \left(\left((6+1) - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \right) \times \left(- (6) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4687426 := \left(\left((6 \times 2) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) - 6 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$4687428 := \left((8-2) \times \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) - 6 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4687444 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\left(4 - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \right) \right) \times (-6) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4687446 := \left(- (6) - \left(\left(4 - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \right) \times \left(6 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4687448 := \left(\left(\left(- (8) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 - 4 \right)$$

$$4687449 := \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(\left(4 - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \right) \times \left(6 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4687464 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 6 \right) \times \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) - \left(6/\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4687472 := \left(\left((2 \times 7) - \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \times \left(-\sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4687478 := \left(- (8) - \left(\left(7 - \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4687479 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-7) \right) + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times \left(6 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4687482 := \left(-2 - \left(\left(- (8) + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-\sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4687484 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (-8) \right) + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times \left(6 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4687486 := \left(- \left((6+8) \right) + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times \left(6 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4687488 := \left(\left(- \left((8/8) \right) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \right) \times \left(6 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4687489 := \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 8 \right) \right) + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times \left(6 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4687491 := \left(- \left((1 \times 9) \right) + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times \left(6 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4687492 := \left(2 \times \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 4 \right) - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times 6 - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4687494 := \left(- \left(\sqrt{4 \times 9} \right) + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times \left(6 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4687495 := \left(- (5) - \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 4 \right) - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times (-6) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4687496 := \left(\left(6/\sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times 6 - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4687498 := \left(8 - 9 + \left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right)^8 \times 6 \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4687499 := \left(- \left((9/9) \right) + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right)^8 \right) \times \left(6 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4687524 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(2^5 - 7)^8} \right) \times 6 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$4687546 := \left(\left(\left(\left((6+4) \times (5^7) \right) + 8 \right) \times 6 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4687548 := \left(\left(\left((8 + \sqrt{4}) \times (5^7) \right) + 8 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^4}} \right)$$

$$4688524 := \left(\left(\left((4+2) \times (5^8) \right) + \sqrt{8^6} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4688532 := \left(\left((2 \times 3) \times \left((5^8) + 86 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4688534 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(3 \times \left(\left((5^8) + 86 \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4688736 := \left(6 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{-3+7} - 886 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4691556 := \left(\left(\left((6 - (5 \times 5)) \times (19 \times 6) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4695889 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-8) \right) + \left(\left((8+5)^{\sqrt{9}} - 6 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4697668 := -8 + 6 \times \left(-6^7 + 9^6 \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4709976 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(-7\right) \times \sqrt{9} + 907\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4713241 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(1 \times 4\right)^2 - \left(3 \times 1\right)^7\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4715613 &:= \left(31 + 6\right) \times \left(51 \times 7\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4717359 &:= \left(\sqrt{9^{5+3}} \times \left(717 + \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 4717584 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(8 - 5\right)^7 - 17\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4718287 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(8/2\right) + 817\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4718439 &:= \left(9 \times \left(-3\right) + \left(\left(4^{8+1} - 7\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 4718448 &:= \left(\left(-8\right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(4^8\right)\right)\right) \times \left(1 \times 7 + \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 4718466 &:= \left(\left(6 \times 6\right) \times \left(\left(4^{8+1} - 7\right)\right) / \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 4718484 &:= \left(4 - \left(8 \times \left(\left(4^8 - 1\right)\right)\right)\right) \times \left(-7 - \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 4718494 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(9 \times \left(4^{8+1}\right)\right) - \sqrt{74}\right)\right) \\
 4718496 &:= \left(-6\right) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-\left(4^8 + 1\right)\right)\right) + 7\right) \times 4\right) \\
 4718547 &:= \left(\left(7 + \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(-5 - \left(\left(8 \times 1\right)^7 / 4\right)\right)\right) \\
 4718591 &:= \left(-1\right) - \left(9 \times \left(\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{8+1}\right)^7\right) / \left(-4\right)\right)\right) \\
 4718592 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{\left(9-5\right)^8} \times \left(-1-7\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4718594 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(4^9\right) \times \left(5-8\right)\right) \times \left(1-7\right)\right) + \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 4718628 &:= \left(-\left(8-26\right)\right) \times \left(\left(8^{-1+7}\right) + \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 4718686 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(6 + \left(8^6\right)\right) \times \left(8+1\right)\right) - 7\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 4718695 &:= \left(-5\right) - \left(9 \times \left(\left(-6\right) - \left(8^{-1+7}\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 4718696 &:= \left(\left(\left(-6\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(-6 - \left(8^{-1+7}\right)\right)\right) - 4 \\
 4718718 &:= \left(8+1\right) \times \left(\left(7 + \left(8^{-1+7}\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 4718799 &:= \left(9 \times \left(9 + \left(\left(7 + \left(8^{-1+7}\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\
 4719492 &:= \left(-\left(2 \times 9\right)\right) \times \left(-\left(\left(4^9 + 1\right)\right) - \sqrt{74}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4721668 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{86} \times 6\right) + 1\right)^2\right) + 7\right) / \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 4721929 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^{-2+9}}\right) - \left(1 \times 2\right) \times 7\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4725854 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(4 - 585\right)\right)^2\right) \times 7\right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4726276 &:= \left(\left(\left(-6 - \sqrt{72}\right) + \left(6/2\right)^7\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4727569 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-657\right)\right) + 2\right) \times \left(-7^4\right)\right) \\
 4734927 &:= \left(-\left(7^2\right)\right) + \left(\left(\left(-9 - \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(3^7\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4734964 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-6\right)\right) + \left(\left(\left(-9 - \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(3^7\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right) \\
 4734965 &:= \left(-\left(5+6\right)\right) + \left(\left(\left(-9 - \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(3^7\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4734968 &:= \left(-8\right) + \left(\left(\left(\left(6+9\right) - 4\right) - \left(3^7\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4734973 &:= \left(-3\right) + \left(\left(7 + \left(\left(-9 \times \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(3^7\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4734974 &:= \left(\left(4^7\right) \times \left(\left(94 \times 3\right) + 7\right) - \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 4734976 &:= \left(6 + \left(7 \times \left(9 + \left(43 \times 7\right)\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4734977 &:= \left(7/7\right) + \left(\left(\left(-9 - \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(3^7\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4734979 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(7 + \left(\left(-9 \times \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(3^7\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right) \\
 4734982 &:= \left(-\left(2-8\right)\right) + \left(\left(\left(-9 - \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(3^7\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4734994 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 9\right) + \left(\left(\left(-9 - \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(3^7\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right) \\
 4734997 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{9}\right) + \left(\left(\left(-9 - \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(3^7\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right) \\
 4735846 &:= \left(-6\right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(8 \times 5\right)^3\right) \times \left(-74\right)\right) \\
 4735849 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(8 \times 5\right)^3\right) \times \left(-74\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 4736313 &:= \left(-\left(\left(\left(3-1\right) \times 3\right)^6\right)\right) + \left(\left(3^7\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 4739329 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(9^2\right) \times 3\right) \times 9\right) - 3\right) - 7\right)^{\sqrt{4}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4741629 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left((2 \times 6) \times 14 \right)^{7-4} \right) \right) \\
 4741636 &:= \left(\left(\left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{36} + 1 \right) \right)^{-4+7} \right) + 4 \right) \\
 4741648 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((6 \times 14)^{7-4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4741926 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(- \left((2-9) \right) \times \left(- (1) + \sqrt{4^7} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4743388 &:= \left(\sqrt{8+8} \times \left((33^4) - 74 \right) \right) \\
 4743639 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(\left(\left((3^6) - 3 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 7 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4743654 &:= \left(\left(4 \times \left(\left((5+6) \times 3 \right)^4 - 7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4743659 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\left((5+6) \times 3 \right)^4 - 7 \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \\
 4743664 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((6 \times 6) - 3 \right)^4 - 7 \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 4743673 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((3^7) - 6 \right) - 3 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - (7+4) \right) \\
 4743679 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^7} - (6+3) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 7 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4743693 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((3 - \sqrt{9^6}) \times (-3) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 7 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4743733 &:= \left(\left((33^{7-3}) \times 4 \right) + \sqrt{7^4} \right) \\
 4744549 &:= \left(\left((9^{\sqrt{4}+5}) - 4 \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7 \right)^4 \right) \right) \\
 4744553 &:= \left(\left(3^{5+5+4} \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7 \right)^4 \right) \right) \\
 4747986 &:= \left(- (6) + \left(\left(\left(- (8) + \sqrt{9^7} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - \sqrt{7^4} \right) \right) \\
 4747989 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\left(- (8) + \sqrt{9^7} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - \sqrt{7^4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4747992 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((2^{\sqrt{9}}) - \sqrt{9^7} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - \left(\sqrt{7^4} \right) \right) \\
 4752379 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-7) \right) + \left(\left((3^{2+5}) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4752384 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (-8) \right) + \left(\left((3^{2+5}) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4752386 &:= \left(- \left((6+8) \right) + \left(\left((3^{2+5}) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4752389 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 8 \right) - \left(\left((3^{2+5}) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4752391 &:= \left(- \left((1 \times 9) \right) + \left(\left((3^{2+5}) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4752392 &:= - \left(\left(\left((2^{\sqrt{9}}) - \left(\left((3^{2+5}) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4752394 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4 \times 9} - \left(\left((3^{2+5}) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4752395 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(\left((9/3)^{2+5} \right) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4752399 &:= \left(- \left((9/9) \right) + \left(\left((3^{2+5}) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4754176 &:= \left(\left((6^7) + \left(- \left((1-4) - 5 \right)^7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4756536 &:= \left(\left(6 + \left((3^5) \times 6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{57^4} \right) \\
 4756761 &:= \left(-1 \times 6 + \sqrt{\sqrt{(76+5)^7}} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4756763 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(3+6)^7} - 6 \right)^{-5+7} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4761124 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((2+1)^{1+6} \right) - 7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4765489 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((9 + \sqrt{8^4}) \times (5 \times 6) \right) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4766426 &:= \left(\left(- (62) + \sqrt{46^6} \right) \times \sqrt{7^4} \right) \\
 4769464 &:= \sqrt{46^4 \times 9/6 \times 7^4} \\
 4769687 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} - \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \times \left(- \left((6+7)^4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4769848 &:= \left(- (8) + \left((4 \times \left((8 \times 9) + 6 \right) \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4769853 &:= \left(- (3) + \left(\left((5-8) + \left((9-6)^7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4769854 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((5-8) + \left((9-6)^7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4769856 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((6+5) - 8 \right) - \left((9-6)^7 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4769859 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((5-8) + \left((9-6)^7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4772969 &:= \left(\left((9^6) \times 9 \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{2+7} + 7 \right)^4 \right) \right) \\
 4774217 &:= \left(-((7+1)) + \left(\left(- (2) + \left(- ((4-7))^7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4774218 &:= \left(-((8-1)) + \left(\left(- (2) + \left(- ((4-7))^7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4774224 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} / (-2) \right) + \left(\left(- (2) + \left(- ((4-7))^7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4774225 &:= \left(\left(5 + \left(\left(- ((2/2) - 4) \right)^7 - 7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4774245 &:= \left((5 \times 4) + \left(\left(- (2) + \left(- ((4-7))^7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4774267 &:= \left((7 \times 6) + \left(\left(- (2) + \left(- ((4-7))^7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4777579 &:= \left((9^7) + \left(- ((5 \times 7) \times 77) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4778588 &:= \left(- (8) + \left(\left(- (8) + \left(\left(- ((5-8))^7 + 7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4778596 &:= \left(\left(6 + \left(\left(- ((9 / (5-8)))^7 - 7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4779387 &:= \left(- \left((7 \times (8^3)) \right) + \left((9^{\sqrt{7 \times 7}}) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4779495 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{59^4} - \left((9^7) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} \right) \\
 4779544 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{(4 \times 4)^5} - \left((9^7) - (7^4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4779795 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{5^{\sqrt{9+7}}} - \left((9^7) - \sqrt{7^4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4779835 &:= - \left(\left(\left((5^{-3+8}) - \left((9^7) - 7 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4779839 &:= \left(\left(- (9) \times \sqrt{3^8} \right) + \left((9^7) - (7^4) \right) \right) \\
 4779946 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (6) \times \sqrt{4^9} \right) + \left((9^7) \right) \right) + \sqrt{7^4} \right) \\
 4781179 &:= \left(\left((9^7) - \left((1+1)^8 \times 7 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4781379 &:= \left((9^7) - (318 \times (7 - \sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 4781638 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{(8+3)^6} - \left(\sqrt{(1+8)^7} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4781954 &:= \left(- \left((4^5) \right) + \left(\left((9^{-1+8}) + 7 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4781973 &:= - \left(\left(\left((3+7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(\left((1+8)^7 + 4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4781979 &:= \left((9^7) - \left(- ((9 \times (1 - (8 \times 7)))) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4782379 &:= \left(\left((9^7) - ((3 \times 28) \times 7) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4782459 &:= \left((9^{5+\sqrt{4}}) + \left((2 - (8^{7-4})) \right) \right) \\
 4782479 &:= \left((9^7) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((2^8) - 7 \right) - 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4782579 &:= \left(\left((9^7) - ((5+2) \times 8) \times 7 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4782689 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{8+6}} \right) - ((2+8) \times 7) \times 4 \right) \\
 4782718 &:= \left(\left((8+1)^7 - \left((2^8) - 7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4782727 &:= \left(\left((7+2)^7 - (2^8) \right) + (7 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 4782737 &:= \left(- \left(\left(7 - \left((3^7)^2 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{(8+7)^4} \right) \\
 4782743 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{3^4} \right)^7 - (2 + ((8 \times 7) \times 4)) \right) \\
 4782745 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{5+4} \right)^{7 \times 2} - ((8 \times 7) \times 4) \right) \\
 4782747 &:= \left(\left((7 + \sqrt{4})^7 \right) + ((2 - ((8 \times 7) \times 4))) \right) \\
 4782769 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 6)^7 \right) - ((28 \times 7) + 4) \right) \\
 4782773 &:= \left((3^{7+7}) - \sqrt{2 \times 8 \times 7^4} \right) \\
 4782789 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (8 \times ((7 - (2^8)) \times (7^4))) \right) \right) \\
 4782792 &:= \left((2^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left(- \left((7 - (2^8)) \times (7^4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4782793 &:= \left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{9})^7 \right) - ((2 \times 8) \times (7+4)) \right) \\
 4782795 &:= \left(- \left((5 - (9^7)) \right) - \left(- ((2-8) - 7) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4782799 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9 \times 9^7} \right) - ((2 \times 87) - 4) \right) \\
 4782879 &:= \left(\left((9^7) - \sqrt{8^2} \right) - ((8+74)) \right) \\
 4782915 &:= \left(\left((5+1) - (9^{-2+8}) \right) \times \left(- (7) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4782936 &:= \left(- (6) + \left(\left(- (3) + (9^{-2+8}) \right) \times (7 + \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 4782939 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{3+9+2}} \right) - ((8+7) \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 4782941 &:= \left(\left((1-4) \right)^{\sqrt{9 \times 2+8}} - ((7 \times 4)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$4782947 := \left(\left(\left((7 + \sqrt{4})^{9-2} \right) - 8 \right) - (7 \times \sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$4782951 := \left(\left(\sqrt{-1+5} - \left((9^{-2+8}) \right) \right) \times \left(-(7) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4782954 := \left(\left((4+5)^{9-2} \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{(8+7)^4}} \right)$$

$$4782955 := \left(-((5+5)) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{28 \times 7}}} \right) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4782956 := \left(-((6+5)) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{28 \times 7}}} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4782958 := \left(-((8+5)) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{28 \times 7}}} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4782959 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{5+9}} \right) - (2 \times ((8-7) + 4)) \right)$$

$$4782961 := \left(-((1 \times 6)) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{28 \times 7}}} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4782963 := \left(\left((3+6)^{9-2} \right) - \sqrt{8+7 \times 4} \right)$$

$$4782966 := \left((6/6) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{28 \times 7}}} \right) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4782967 := \left(\left(\left((7-6)^9 \right) 2 + 8 \right)^7 - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4782971 := \left(\left(\left((1^7 92) + 8 \right)^7 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4782974 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 7 \right)^{9-2} \right) + ((8-7) + 4) \right)$$

$$4782975 := \left(-((5-7)) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{28 \times 7}}} \right) + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4782978 := \left(\left(-((8-7)) - (9^{-2+8}) \right) \times \left(-(7) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4782981 := \left(\sqrt{1+8} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{-2+8+7}} \right) + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4782983 := \left(\left(\left((3^8) / \sqrt{9} \right)^2 \right) + ((8 \times 7) / 4) \right)$$

$$4782989 := \left(\left((9^8) / \sqrt{9^2} \right) - ((8 - (7 \times 4))) \right)$$

$$4782991 := \left(\left(\left((1 \times 9)^{9-2} \right) + 8 \right) + (7 \times \sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$4782994 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(-(9) \times \left((9^{-2+8}) + (7-4) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4782996 := \left((6 + \sqrt{9}) \times \left((9^{-2+8}) + (7-4) \right) \right)$$

$$4782999 := \left(\left((9^9) / (9^2) \right) + ((8+7) \times \sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$4783015 := \left((5 \times 10) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4783029 := \left((\sqrt{9} \times 20) + (3^{8 \times 7/4}) \right)$$

$$4783043 := \left((3^{\sqrt{4} \times 03+8}) + 74 \right)$$

$$4783139 := \left((\sqrt{9} \times ((3^{13}) + (8 \times 7))) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4783193 := \left((3 \times (\sqrt{9^{13}})) + ((8 \times 7) \times 4) \right)$$

$$4783285 := \left((5 \times (8^2)) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4783316 := \left(((6+1)^3) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4783412 := \left(\sqrt{21^4} + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4783453 := \left(\left((3^5) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4783459 := \left((9 \times 54) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4783465 := \left((\sqrt{5^6} \times 4) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4783479 := \left((9^7) - \left((\sqrt{4} \times 3) \times \left(-(87) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4783585 := \left((\sqrt{5^8} - 5) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4783692 := \left(\left(-(2) + \sqrt{9^6} \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4783693 := \left(\left(-(3) + \sqrt{9^6} \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4783694 := \left(\left(-4 + \sqrt{9^6} \right) + (3^{8 \times 7/4}) \right)$$

$$4783695 := \left(\left(-(5) + \sqrt{9^6} \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4783696 := \left(\left(-(6) + \sqrt{9^6} \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4783699 := \left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{9^6}) \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4783743 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{3^4} \right)^7 + \left(387 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4783783 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right)^7 + \left((3+8) \times 74 \right) \right) \\
 4783973 &:= \left(\left((3+7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right)^7 + 4 \right) \right) \\
 4783979 &:= \left(\left(9^7 \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(9+3)^8}} \times 7 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4784079 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 70) \times (4^8) \right) - \sqrt{74} \right) \\
 4784137 &:= \left(\left((73 \times (1 \times 4)^8) \right) + 7 \right) + \sqrt{4} \\
 4784279 &:= \left(\left((9^7) + \sqrt{(2+4)^8} \right) + (7 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 4784637 &:= \left(\left(73 \times \left((6 - \sqrt{4})^8 \right) + 7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 4784733 &:= \left(\left((3 \times 3)^7 \right) + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} - 8) \times (-7) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4784763 &:= \left(\left((3+6)^7 \right) + \left((\sqrt{4^8} \times 7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4785179 &:= \left(\left((9^7) + 1 \right) + \sqrt{(5 \times 8 + 7)^4} \right) \\
 4785579 &:= \left(9^7 \right) + \left((5 \times 58) \times (7 + \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 4787328 &:= \left(-((8 \times 2)) + \left(\left((3^7) + 8 \right) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4787337 &:= \left(-7 \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{(3 \times 3)^7} + (8 - 7) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4787354 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times 5) + \left(\left((3^7) + 8 \right) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4787359 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} \times 5) + \left(\left((3^7) + 8 \right) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4787679 &:= \left(9^7 \right) - \left(-(6) \times (787 - \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 4789479 &:= \left(\left((9^7) - \sqrt{4} \right) + \sqrt{9^8} \right) - \sqrt{74} \\
 4790889 &:= \left((9 \times 880) + \left(\sqrt{9^7} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4791429 &:= \left(\sqrt{92^4} + \left(\left((1 \times 9)^7 \right) - 4 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4791718 &:= \left(\left((8+1)^7 \right) + 1 \right) + \left(\sqrt{9^7} \times 4 \right) \\
 4791721 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((1+2)^7 \right) \times 1 \right) + 9 \right) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4791732 &:= \left(\left((2 + (3^7))^{-1+\sqrt{9}} \right) + (7+4) \right) \\
 4791969 &:= \left(\left(-(9^6) \right) - \left((9+1)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \left(-(7) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4792369 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} \times (6^3)) + \left((2 + \sqrt{9^7})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4792379 &:= \left(\left((9^7) + 3 \right) - 2 \right) + \sqrt{97^4} \\
 4792969 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 6)^{9-2} \right) + \left((\sqrt{9} + 7)^4 \right) \right) \\
 4793484 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times \left(-(8 - (4^{3+9})) / 7 \right)) \right) - 4 \\
 4793485 &:= \left(-(5) + \left(\left(-(8) + (\sqrt{4}^{3 \times 9}) \right) / (7 \times 4) \right) \right) \\
 4793486 &:= \left(\left((6 - (8^{\sqrt{4^3}}) - 9) \right) / (-7) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4793492 &:= \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9}) + (4^{3+9}) \right) / 7 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4793494 &:= \left(\left((4+9) + (4^{3+9}) \right) / 7 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4793498 &:= \left(\left((8^9) + \left((\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) / (7 \times 4) \right) \\
 4793622 &:= \left((\sqrt{22^6} + \left((3 + (9^7)) \right)) \right) + \sqrt{4} \\
 4794425 &:= \left(\sqrt{52^4} + \left((\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{9^7})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4794629 &:= \left(\sqrt{(9 \times 2)^6 \times 4} + \left((9^7) - 4 \right) \right) \\
 4794649 &:= \left((9 \times (\sqrt{4} + (6^4))) \right) - \left(-(9^7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4794779 &:= \left((9^7) + (7^4) \right) + \sqrt{97^4} \\
 4795132 &:= \left(\sqrt{23^{1+5}} + \left((9^7) - 4 \right) \right) \\
 4795844 &:= \left(-(4^4) \right) + \left(\left((8-5) + \sqrt{9^7} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4796079 &:= \left(9^7 \right) + \left(06 \times (\sqrt{9^7} - \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 4796095 &:= \left(-(5) + \left((\sqrt{9} + \left((0-6) + 9 \right)^7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4796685 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{(8+6)^6} \right) + \left((9^7) - 4 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4796789 &:= \left(\sqrt{(9+8+7)^6} + \left(((9^7) - 4) \right) \right) \\
 4796793 &:= \sqrt{(3 + \sqrt{9} \times 7)^6} + \sqrt{9^{7 \times \sqrt{4}}} \\
 4798248 &:= \left((84 \times 2) \times \left((-8) - (\sqrt{9} \times (-7)) \right)^4 \right) \\
 4798565 &:= \left(\left((5^6) - \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) + \left(((9^7) - 4) \right) \right) \\
 4799344 &:= \left(\left((4^{4+3}) - 9 \right) + \left(\sqrt{9^{7 \times \sqrt{4}}} \right) \right) \\
 4799757 &:= \left((7^5) - \left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{9}) - ((9^7)) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4799767 &:= \left(\left(((7^6) / 7) - 9 \right) + \left(\sqrt{9^{7 \times \sqrt{4}}} \right) \right) \\
 4799771 &:= \left((-1) + \sqrt{7 \times 7^9} + \left(((9^7) - 4) \right) \right) \\
 4799772 &:= \left(\left((-2) + \sqrt{7 \times 7^9} \right) + \left((9^7) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4799773 &:= \left((-3) + \sqrt{7 \times 7^9} + \left(\sqrt{9^{7 \times \sqrt{4}}} \right) \right) \\
 4799774 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{7 \times 7^9}) + \left(((9^7) - 4) \right) \right) \\
 4799775 &:= \left((-5) + \sqrt{7 \times 7^9} + \left(((9^7) + 4) \right) \right) \\
 4799779 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{7 \times 7^9}) + \left(\sqrt{9^{7 \times \sqrt{4}}} \right) \right) \\
 4799787 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{7^8} \times 7) + (9 + (9^7)) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4804864 &:= \left((((46 - (8 \times 40)) \times 8) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4813633 &:= \left(-3 + \left(\left(\left(\left((3^6) \times 3 \right) - 1 \right) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4813634 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\left(\left((3^6) \times 3 \right) - 1 \right) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4813639 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\left(\left((3^6) \times 3 \right) - 1 \right) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4815774 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^7 \right) + \left(5 \times ((1+8)^4) \right) \right) \\
 4816749 &:= - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} - ((4^7) \times 6)) \times ((1-8))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4817985 &:= \left(-((5 \times 8)) + \left((\sqrt{9^7} + (1 \times 8))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4818025 &:= \left(\left(((5-2)^{08-1} + 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4826297 &:= \left(\left((7 + (\sqrt{9} \times 2))^6 \right) - \left((2^8) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4826549 &:= \left(\left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{4}) - 5 \right)^6 \right) - \left(((2^8) + 4) \right) \right) \\
 4826553 &:= \left(\left(((3+5) + 5)^6 \right) - \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^4} \right) \\
 4826641 &:= \left(\left((1 + (\sqrt{4} \times 6))^6 \right) - (2 \times 84) \right) \\
 4826667 &:= \left(\left(\left((7+6)^6 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{(6 \times 2)^8}} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4826681 &:= \left(\left(((1-8) - 6)^6 \right) - (2 \times \sqrt{8^4}) \right) \\
 4826743 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{4}) + 7 \right)^6 \right) - 2 \right) - \sqrt{8^4} \\
 4826783 &:= \left(-((3 \times 8)) + \left((7+6)^{-2+8} - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4826789 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} \times (-8)) + \left((7+6)^{-2+8} + 4 \right) \right) \\
 4826794 &:= \left(-((4+9)) + \left((7+6)^{-2+8} - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4826796 &:= \left(-((6+9)) + \left((7+6)^{-2+8} + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4826798 &:= \left((-8) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((7+6)^{2+8-4} \right) \\
 4826799 &:= \left(9 + \sqrt{9+7} \right)^6 + 2 - 8 - 4 \\
 4826807 &:= \left(\left((70+8) / 6 \right)^{-2+8} - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4826809 &:= \left(\left((9+08) - 6 \right) + 2 \right)^{8-\sqrt{4}} \\
 4826811 &:= \left(\left((1+18) - 6 \right)^{-2+8} + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4826812 &:= \left((21-8)^6 \right) + \left(-(2-8) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4826814 &:= \left(\left((4+1) + 8 \right)^6 \right) + \left((2+8) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4826825 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{5^2} + 8)^6 \right) + \left((2^8-4) \right) \right) \\
 4826827 &:= \left(\left(((7-2) + 8)^6 \right) + (2 \times 8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4826829 &:= \left(\left((9 + \sqrt{2 \times 8})^6 \right) + ((2 \times 8) + 4) \right) \\
 4826837 &:= \left(\left((7 \times 3) - 8 \right)^6 \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{28^4}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$4826843 := \left(\left(\left((3 + \sqrt{4}) + 8 \right)^6 \right) + (2 + (8 \times 4)) \right)$$

$$4826845 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4} + 8} \right)^6 \right) + \left(-((2-8)^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right)$$

$$4826937 := \left(\left((7-3) + 9 \right)^6 + (2 \times \sqrt{8^4}) \right)$$

$$4829832 := \left(2 \times \left(\left(3 \times \left((8^{\sqrt{9}}) - ((2-8)) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4831793 := \left(\left(- (3) + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 71)^3 \right) - 8 \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4831799 := \left(\left(9 + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 71)^3 \right) - 8 \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4839931 := \left(\left(13^{9-\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(- \left((3^8) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4844385 := \left(\left(\left((5+8)^3 \right) + 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - (8 \times \sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$4844473 := \left(\left((3^7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \sqrt{(4^4 - 8)^4} \right)$$

$$4845979 := \left(\left((9^7) + 9 \right) + \left(- (5) + \sqrt{4^8} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4847297 := \left(- (7) \times \left(- \left((9-2)^7 \right) \right) + \left((4^8) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4847399 := \left(\left((99^3) \times (7 - \sqrt{4}) \right) - (8^4) \right)$$

$$4848499 := \left((9^{9-\sqrt{4}}) - \left((8 - (4^8)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4849648 := \left(- \left((8 - ((46-9) \times (4^8))) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4849656 := \left(- \left((6 - ((5+69) \times (4^8))) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4849657 := \left(- (7) - \left(- ((5+69)) \times \left(\sqrt{4^8}^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4849658 := \left(- \left((8 - ((5+69) \times (4^8))) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4849662 := \left(\left((2 + \sqrt{6^6/9}) \times (4^8) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4849664 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times (66 \times 9)) - 4 \right) \times (8^4) \right)$$

$$4849666 := \left(\left((666/9) \times (4^8) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4849812 := \left((2 + ((1 \times 8) \times 9)) \times \left((4^8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4853995 := \left((5 \times (99^3)) + (\sqrt{5^8} \times 4) \right)$$

$$4853997 := \left(79 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((3 \times 5) \times (8^4) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4855488 := \left(\sqrt{88^4} \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5 \times 5^8} + \sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4855627 := - \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{7^2} - (6^5)) \times \sqrt{5^8} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4855629 := \left(\left(- \left((9-2) - (6^5) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{5^8} + 4 \right)$$

$$4857616 := \left(\left((61 \times (6^{7-5})) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4859136 := \left(- \left((6^3) \right) \times \left((1 + (-9) \times \sqrt{5^8}) \times 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4859616 := \left((6 \times 16) \times \left(\sqrt{(\sqrt{9} \times 5)^8 - 4} \right) \right)$$

$$4859968 := \left((8 + \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-9) \right) \times \sqrt{5^8}) \times (-4) \right)$$

$$4859976 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- ((7+9)) \times \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} \times 5)^8} \right) + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4859984 := \left(- (4) \times \left(\left(- (8) \times \sqrt{9 \times (\sqrt{9} \times 5)^8} \right) + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4859996 := \left(\sqrt{6^{9/9+9} \times 5^8} - 4 \right)$$

$$4859998 := \left(\left((8 \times (9 + \sqrt{9})) \times \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} \times 5)^8} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4861699 := \left((\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left((9^{6-1}) - (6^8) \right) \right)) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4862025 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(5-20+2)^6} + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4866428 := \left(- (8) + \left((2 - ((46 \times 6) \times 8)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4866436 := \left(\left((6/3) - ((46 \times 6) \times 8) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4871789 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 8)^7 \right) \times (-1) \right) + (7+8) \right) / (-4)$$

$$4871791 := \left(\left(- (1) - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + (7+1))^7 \right) - 8 \right) \right) \right) / (-4)$$

$$4871792 := \left(\left(- \left((2+9)^7 \right) \right) + \sqrt{17-8} \right) / (-4)$$

$$4871794 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 9)^7 \right) + \sqrt{17+8} \right) / 4 \right)$$

$$4874879 := \left(\left((9 - (7 \times 8))^4 \right) - \sqrt{7^8 \times 4} \right)$$

$$4875264 := \left((4 \times \left((6 \times 2) + 57 \right) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4879168 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{8^6} + 1 \right) - \left((9 - (7 \times 8))^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4879474 := \left(\left(47^4 \right) - \left(9 \times \left(7 + \left(8 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4879489 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9 \times 8^4} - \left((9 - (7 \times 8))^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4879654 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(4+5)^6} - \left((9 - (7 \times 8))^4 \right)} \right) \right)$$

$$4879669 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-6) \right) + 6 \right) + \left((9 - (7 \times 8))^4 \right) \right)$$

$$4879673 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{-3+7} + \left(6 - \left((9 - (7 \times 8))^4 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4879675 := \left(\left(\left((5 + (7 \times 6))^{\sqrt{9+7}} \right) - 8 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4879678 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{8+7-6} - \left((9 - (7 \times 8))^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4879683 := \left(\sqrt{3 \times 8/6} + \left((9 - (7 \times 8))^4 \right) \right)$$

$$4879745 := \left(\left((54 - 7)^{\sqrt{9+7}} \right) + \sqrt{8^4} \right)$$

$$4879765 := \left(\left((5 + (6 \times 7))^{\sqrt{9+7}} \right) + (84) \right)$$

$$4879877 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(7+7)^8} + \left((9 - (7 \times 8))^4 \right)} \right)$$

$$4879969 := \left(\left(96 \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((9 - (7 \times 8))^4 \right) \right)$$

$$4882969 := \left(\left((9^6) \times 9 \right) + \sqrt{(2+8)^{8+\sqrt{4}}} \right)$$

$$4884478 := \left(\left(8 \times \left((7 \times 4)^4 \right) - \sqrt{8^8} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4884857 := \left(\left(- (7) + \left((5^{8+\sqrt{4}}) + \sqrt{8^8} \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4884859 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left((5^{8+\sqrt{4}}) + \sqrt{8^8} \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4886457 := \left(- (7) - \left(- \left((5^4) + 6 \right) \times \sqrt{88^4} \right) \right)$$

$$4889796 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-88) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4892942 := \left(- (2) + \left(\left(4 + \left((-92) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-8) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4892944 := \left(\left(\left((44 + \sqrt{9})^2 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)^{8/4} \right)$$

$$4897369 := \left(\left(9 + \left(\left((6-3)^7 \right) + 9 \right) + 8 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4900171 := \left(- (1) + \left(\left((7 + 100)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4900172 := \left(\left((2 \times (7 + 100))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4900174 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((7 + 100)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4904712 := \left(2 \times \left((174 \times 09)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4910656 := \left(\left(- \left((6 - 560) \right) \times \left(1 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4912968 := \left(8 \times \left(\left(- \left((6 - 92) + 1 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4912998 := \left(\left((8 + (9 \times 9) \times 2) \right)^{\sqrt{1 \times 9}} - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4914847 := \left((7^4) \times \left(\left((8^4) + 1 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4914938 := \left(\left((83 \times 9) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(1 + (9^4) \right) \right)$$

$$4917232 := \left((2^3) \times \left(- (2) + \left(\left(- (7) \times \left(- (1) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4917244 := \left(-4 + \left(\left((4 \times 2) \times 7 \right)^{1+\sqrt{9}} / \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4917264 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 6 \right) \times \left(2 + \left(\left(- (7) \times \left(- (1) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4919373 := \left(- (3) - \left(- \left((7 \times 3) \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (19) \right)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4919374 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(- \left((7 \times 3) \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (19) \right)^4 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4919379 := \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(- \left((7 \times 3) \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (19) \right)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4919397 := \left(7 \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(- (3) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (19) \right)^4 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4919524 := \left(\left(\left((42 + 5)^{\sqrt{9}-1} \right) + 9 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$4921857 := \left(\left((7 \times (5^{8-1})) - 2 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4925426 := \left(\left(\left((62^4) - 52 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4926795 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right)^6 \right) - \left((2+9)^4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4927635 := \left((5 \times 3) \times \left((67 + 2)^{\sqrt{9\sqrt{4}}} \right) \right)$$

$$4927695 := \left((5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times \left(\left((67 + 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4929454 &:= \left(\left(\left(4 + (\sqrt{5^4} \times 9) \right)^2 \right) \times 94 \right) \\
 4932841 &:= \left(\left((148^2) - (3^9) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4934787 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left((87 + \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}}} \right) \right) + 4 \right) \\
 4934797 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left((97 - \sqrt{4^3})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4937284 &:= \left(\left(\left((48^2) - 73 \right) - 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4941177 &:= \left(\left((7^7) \times ((1+1)+4) \right) - \sqrt{9^4} \right) \\
 4941246 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left((4 \times 2) - 1 \right)^{\sqrt{4^9}} - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4941256 &:= \left(6 \times \left((5+2)^{\sqrt{1 \times 4^9}} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4941267 &:= \left(\left(\left((7^6) \times 21 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{4}}} \right) \right) \\
 4941276 &:= \left(6 \times (7^{2+1+4}) + (9 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 4941277 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((7^7) \times 2 \right) + 1 \right) + 4 \right) \times \sqrt{9} + 4 \right) \\
 4941729 &:= \left(\left(\left((9 - (2^{7+1})) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \sqrt{9^4} \right) \\
 4941776 &:= 6 \times (7^7 + 1) + \sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{4}}}}} \\
 4942368 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(- (6) \times \left(- ((32 \times 4)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4942969 &:= \left(\left((9^6) \times 9 \right) + \left(\left(2 + (\sqrt{4} \times 9) \right)^4 \right) \right) \\
 4947819 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} \times \left(- ((1-8))^7 \right) \times \sqrt{4}) + (9^4) \right) \\
 4948864 &:= 46 \times \left((8 \times ((8 \times 4) + 9))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4949505 &:= \left(505 \times \left(\left((9 + \sqrt{4}) \times 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4952174 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((7+12)^5 \right) - (\sqrt{9} \times 4) \right) \right) \\
 4952175 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(\left((7+12)^5 \right) - 9 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4952192 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((2 \times 9) - 1 \right) + 2 \right)^5 - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4952204 &:= \left(\left(\left((40 - 2) / 2 \right)^5 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4952234 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times \left(- ((3-22)^5) \right)) + (9 \times 4) \right) \\
 4952292 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - (22)) \right)^5 \right) \right) + (94) \right) \\
 4953557 &:= \left((755 \times (3^{5+\sqrt{9}})) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4954824 &:= \left((4^{2+8}) + \left((\sqrt{4} \times (5^9)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4954826 &:= \left(\left(((6-2) \times 8)^4 \right) + \left((5^9) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4955664 &:= \left((\sqrt{4^6} + 65) \times (5+9)^4 \right) \\
 4957686 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{8^6} - 7) / 5 \right) \times 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4959276 &:= \left((6 \times 7) \times \left((2 \times ((9^5) - 9)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4959529 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 2) - \left(- (5) - \sqrt{9^5} \right) \times (-9) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4959756 &:= \left(\left(- \left((6 \times 5) - (7 \times (9^5)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times 4 \\
 4959857 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(5 + \left((8 + \left(- ((9^5)) \times \sqrt{9} \right)) \times 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4959866 &:= \left(\left(- ((6 \times (6+8))) \times \left(- ((9^5)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4959892 &:= \left(- ((2-9)) \times \left((8 + \left(- ((9^5)) \times \sqrt{9} \right)) \times (-4) \right) \right) \\
 4959936 &:= \left(\left((63 \times \sqrt{9^9}) - (5 \times 9) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 4959948 &:= \left(- (84) \times \left((9 - ((9^5) + 9)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4960723 &:= \left(- \left((3+2)^7 \right) - \left((0-6^9) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4962314 &:= \left(\left((41^3) \times ((2+6) \times 9) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4962328 &:= \left(\left(\left((82^3) + 2 \right) \times (6 + \sqrt{9}) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 4962672 &:= \left(- \left((276^2) \right) - \left(- (6^9) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 4963762 &:= \left(- \left((2 - ((6 \times 7)^3)) \right) \times (69 - \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 4963984 &:= \left((4 \times (8 + ((93 \times 6) - 9)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 4964319 &:= -\sqrt{(91 \times 3)^4} + 6^9 / \sqrt{4} \\
 4964864 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{(4 \times 68)^4} + \left(- (6^9) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 4976831 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(- (3) \times \left(\left(- (8) + (6^{\sqrt{7+9}}) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$4976834 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(- (3) \times \left(\left(- (8) + \left(6^{\sqrt{7+9}} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4977361 := \left(\left(1 - \left(- \left(\left((6^3) + 7 \right) \right) \times \left(7 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4979293 := \left(- \left(\left((3^9) - 2 \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{(7+9)^4} \right) \right)$$

$$4979586 := \left(\left(\left((6 \times (8^5)) + (9^7) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{4}}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4979658 := \left(\left(\left((8^5) \times 6 \right) + (9^7) \right) + \sqrt{9^4} \right)$$

$$4979799 := \left(\sqrt{9^9} \times \left(- \left((7 \times 9) - (79 \times 4) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4981822 := \left(- (2) + \left(\left(\left((2^8) \times 1 \right) - 8 \right) \times 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4981824 := \left(\left(\left(\left((4-2)^8 \right) \times 1 \right) - 8 \right) \times 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4983492 := \left(\left(- \left(\left((2 - (94^3)) \times 8 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / 4 \right)$$

$$4983496 := \left(\left(6 \times \left(\left((94^3) + 8 \right) - 9 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4983497 := \left(- (7) + \left(\left(\left((94^3) \times 8 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / 4 \right) \right)$$

$$4983498 := \left(\left(\left((8 \times (94^3)) - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / 4 \right)$$

$$4984563 := \left(\sqrt{3+6} \times \left(\left((5 \times \sqrt{4^8}) + 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4985454 := \left((4 + (5^4)) \times (5 + \sqrt{89^4}) \right)$$

$$4986289 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} - (26 \times 89) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$4991673 := \left(3 \times \left(\left((7^{6-1}) \times 99 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4991679 := \left(- \left((9 \times (7^{6-1})) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - (9 \times 4) \right) \right)$$

$$4993582 := \left(\left(2 \times \left((8 + 53)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \left(9 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$4995225 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((2 \times 25) \times 9 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$4996375 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((7+3)^6 \right) + \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) - 4 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4998974 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left((7-9)^8 \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^9} - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$4999484 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^8} - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{9 \times 9}}} \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4999955 := \left(\left(\left((5+5)^{9-\sqrt{9}} \right) - 9 \right) \times (9-4) \right)$$

$$4999975 := \left(5 \times \left(\left((7 + \sqrt{9})^{9-\sqrt{9}} \right) - (9-4) \right) \right)$$

$$5015625 := \left(\left(\left((5 \times 2)^6 \right) + \sqrt{5^{10}} \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$5019585 := \left(- (5) - \left(- (85) \times \left(\sqrt{9^{10}} + 5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5038694 := \left(-4 - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- (6^8) \right) \right) + (30 \times 5) \right) \right)$$

$$5038829 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 2)^8 \right) - 8 \right) \times 3 \right) - (0-5) \right)$$

$$5038842 := \left(\left(- (2) + \left(\left((\sqrt{4} - 8) \right)^8 \right) \right) \times (3 + (0 \times 5)) \right)$$

$$5038843 := \left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{8 \times 8}} \right) \times 3 \right) + (0-5) \right)$$

$$5038844 := \left(-4 - \left(\sqrt{(4+8)^8} \times \left(- (3^{0^5}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5038848 := \left(\left((8 - \sqrt{4})^8 \right) \times (8 - ((3 \times 0) + 5)) \right)$$

$$5038869 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((6^8) - 8 \right) + (3 \times 0^5) \right) \right)$$

$$5038923 := \left(3 \times \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^8 \right) + (30 - 5) \right) \right)$$

$$5038943 := \left(\left(3 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4 \times 9^8} \right) + (30) \right) \right) + 5 \right)$$

$$5088448 := \left(-84 + \sqrt{4^8} \right)^{8-0^5}$$

$$5143822 := \left(- (2) + \left(\left((28 \times (3^4))^{\sqrt{-1+5}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5143824 := \left(\left(- \left((4 - (2^8)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{3^4} \right)^{\sqrt{-1+5}}$$

$$5145075 := \left(\left(- (5) - \left(70^{\sqrt{5+4}} \right) \right) \times (-15) \right)$$

$$5153629 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left((2 \times (((6/3) \times 5) + 1))^5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5153634 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((3+6) \times 3 - 5 \right) \times 1 \right)^5 \right)$$

$$5153648 := \left((8 \times \sqrt{4}) + \left(\left((6 \times 3) + 5 - 1 \right)^5 \right) \right)$$

$$5157994 := \left((4 + \sqrt{9^9}) \times (7 + (51 \times 5)) \right)$$

$$5171445 := \left(5 \times \left(\left((4^{4+1}) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{-1+5}} \right) \right)$$

$$5175625 := \left(\left(\left(5 + \left((2^6) \times 5 \right) \right) \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{-1+5}} \right)$$

$$5177344 := \left(\left(4^{\sqrt{4^3}} \right) \times \left(77 + \sqrt{-1+5} \right) \right)$$

$$5183985 := \left(\left(\left((5 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{3^8} \right) - 15 \right)$$

$$5184729 := \left(\left(- (9) \times \left(\sqrt{2+7} - \sqrt{4^8} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{-1+5}} \right)$$

$$5189284 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^8} - 2 \right) \times 9 \right) - 8 \right)^{\sqrt{-1+5}} \right)$$

$$5199844 := \left(- \left((4 + 48) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left((9 + 1)^5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5225472 := \left(\left(\left((27 \times \sqrt{4^5})^2 \right) \times (2 + 5) \right) \right)$$

$$5232645 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(5 \times \sqrt{4})^6} + (23) \right)^2 \right) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5242368 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{8^6} - \left((3 + 2) \times (4^{2 \times 5}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5242475 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((7 + \sqrt{4})^2 \right) - (4^{2 \times 5}) \right) \right)$$

$$5242795 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((7 \times 2) - (4^{2 \times 5}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5242865 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(6 / \sqrt{8/2} \right) - (4^{2 \times 5}) \right) \right)$$

$$5242899 := \left(9 + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 8 \right) \times \left(- \left(2 + (4^{2 \times 5}) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5242905 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(0 - \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(2 + (4^{2 \times 5}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5242928 := \left((8 \times 2) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((2^4) \times 5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5242935 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- (3) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(2 + (4^{2 \times 5}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5242955 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- (5) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \left((2 \times 4) \times 2^5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5242975 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- (7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(2 - (4^{2 \times 5}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5245967 := \left(\left(\sqrt{7^6} \times 9 \right) + \left(5 \times (4^{2 \times 5}) \right) \right)$$

$$5248676 := \left(-6 - 7 + \sqrt{(6 \times 8)^4} \right)^2 - 5$$

$$5249692 := \left(\left((2 + (96 \times 9))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times (2 + 5) \right)$$

$$5249697 := \left(\left(7 \times \left((96 \times 9) + \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) + 5 \right)$$

$$5249995 := \left(\left(\left((59 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 42 \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$5250987 := \sqrt{7^8 \times 9^{0 \times 5 + 2 + 5}}$$

$$5259735 := \left(\left(5 \times (3^7) \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^5} \times 2 \right) - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5267694 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (9) - \left(- (6) \times (76^{-2+5}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5268024 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (2 \times 086) \right)^{-2+5} \right)$$

$$5274997 := \left(7 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9 \times 9} + 4 \right) \times 7 \right)^{-2+5} \right) \right)$$

$$5294205 := \left(\left(\left(5 + (02 \times \sqrt{4^9}) \right)^2 \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$5294596 := \left(\left(\left(\left((6 \times (\sqrt{9} + 5))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)^2 \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$5295456 := \left((6^5) \times \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \right) - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5299735 := \left(53 \times \left(\left((7 + \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9+2}} \right) - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5308416 := (6 \times 1)^4 \times \sqrt{8^{03+5}}$$

$$5314689 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 8)^6 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left((1 - 3) + 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5314694 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 9)^6 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (1 \times 3) \right) + 5$$

$$5314698 := \left(\left((8 + \sqrt{9})^6 \right) \times (4 - 1) \right) + (3 \times 5)$$

$$5318784 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{4} - 8) \right)^7 \right) \times \left((8 \times 1) \times 3 - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5326864 := \left(\left(4 + \sqrt{(6 \times 8)^{6-2}} \right)^{-3+5} \right)$$

$$5334349 := \left(\left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((3^4) + 3 \right)^3 \right) \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$5334822 := \left(2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{28^4 \times 3}} \right) \times 3^5$$

$$5341184 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times 81 + 1 \right) \times \sqrt{4^{3 \times 5}}$$

$$5349984 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4^8} \times 9) + 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + (3 \times 5) \right)$$

$$5366587 := \sqrt{\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8} - 5} \right)^6} \times 63 - 5$$

$$5379955 := \left(\left(- \left((5^5) + 9 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(- \left((7^3) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5384375 &:= (\sqrt{5^{7+3}} \times ((4+8)^3) - 5) \\
 5399985 &:= (((\sqrt{5^8} \times ((9+\sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}})) - 3) \times 5) \\
 5399995 &:= (-5) + (((\sqrt{9} \times 99) + \sqrt{9})^3) / 5) \\
 5419264 &:= (\sqrt{4^6} \times (\sqrt{291^4} - 5)) \\
 5420789 &:= ((\sqrt{9} + 8) \times ((702^{\sqrt{4}}) - 5)) \\
 5423429 &:= (((9^2) - \sqrt{4})^3) \times ((2+4) + 5) \\
 5432324 &:= (-((4 \times 23)) \times (2 - \sqrt{3^{4 \times 5}})) \\
 5432499 &:= (-9) + ((94 - 2) \times \sqrt{3^{4 \times 5}}) \\
 5438464 &:= (((4^{\sqrt{64}}) \times 83) - (4^5)) \\
 5439488 &:= (\sqrt{8^8} \times (((\sqrt{4} + 9)^3) - \sqrt{4+5})) \\
 5445473 &:= ((-((3 \times 7)^4)) \times ((5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (-4))) + 5) \\
 5451771 &:= (((177 - 1)^{\sqrt{5+4}}) - 5) \\
 5463635 &:= ((-(5 - (36 \times 3)))^{6/\sqrt{4}}) \times 5) \\
 5468547 &:= (-7) \times ((\sqrt{4} \times (-5^8)) + ((6 \times 4) + 5)) \\
 5468568 &:= (8 + 6) \times (((5^8) - \sqrt{64}) - 5) \\
 5468572 &:= (2 \times ((-7) \times (-((5^8)) + (6 \times \sqrt{4}))) - 5) \\
 5468575 &:= (5 \times 7) \times (\sqrt{5^{8+6} \times 4} - 5) \\
 5468577 &:= ((7 + 7) \times ((5^8) - (6 \times \sqrt{4}))) - 5) \\
 5468745 &:= (-5) - (((\sqrt{4} - 7)^8) \times (6 - (4 \times 5))) \\
 5468834 &:= ((\sqrt{4} \times (((3 - 8)^8) + 6)) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)) \\
 5468859 &:= -((\sqrt{9} + (((5^8) + 8) \times (6 - (4 \times 5)))))) \\
 5475595 &:= ((5 \times ((95 \times 5) - 7))^{\sqrt{4}}) - 5) \\
 5483136 &:= (-6) \times ((3 - \sqrt{13^8}) \times \sqrt{4^5}) \\
 5484672 &:= (\sqrt{276^4} \times (8 \times (4 + 5)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5529599 &:= ((((-((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{9^5}))^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-2)) + 5) / (-5)) \\
 5537797 &:= ((\sqrt{(7+9)^7} \times ((7^3) - 5)) + 5) \\
 5549849 &:= ((-94) \times (8 - ((\sqrt{9\sqrt{4}})^5))) - 5) \\
 5549859 &:= (((9^5) - 8) \times 94) + \sqrt{5 \times 5} \\
 5569365 &:= (-5) \times (6 - (3 \times (((\sqrt{9} \times 6) - 5)^5))) \\
 5569395 &:= ((5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times (((3+9) + 6) - 5)^5) \\
 5574984 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times (-894 \times (7 - (5^5)))) \\
 5579924 &:= (4 \times (2 + (9 \times 9))) \times \sqrt{7^{5+5}} \\
 5579944 &:= (-4) \times (((\sqrt{4} + ((9 \times 9))) \times (-7^5)) - 5) \\
 5585864 &:= -((\sqrt{4} - ((6^8) + ((5^8) \times (5+5)))))) \\
 5585866 &:= ((\sqrt{6 \times 6^8}) + ((5^8) \times (5+5))) \\
 5585869 &:= (\sqrt{9} + ((6^8) + ((5^8) \times (5+5)))) \\
 5587599 &:= ((\sqrt{9} \times (-9^5)) + (((7^8) - 55)) \\
 5587659 &:= -(((\sqrt{9^{5+6}}) - (7^8)) - \sqrt{5 \times 5}) \\
 5596875 &:= ((-(5 - (7 \times 86))) \times \sqrt{9}) \times (5^5) \\
 5598645 &:= (-5) \times ((\sqrt{4} \times ((-(6^8)) / \sqrt{9}) + 5) + 5) \\
 5598699 &:= (9 - (((9 - (6^8)) / \sqrt{9}) \times (5+5))) \\
 5598715 &:= (-5) + (((((1-7)^8) / \sqrt{9}) \times (5+5))) \\
 5598725 &:= (((5-2)^7) \times ((8^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 5)) + 5) \\
 5598745 &:= (((\sqrt{(5+4)^7} \times (8^{\sqrt{9}})) + 5) \times 5) \\
 5598995 &:= (5 \times ((\sqrt{9} \times (9 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}}) + (55))) \\
 5617997 &:= ((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (\sqrt{(9+7)^{1+6}} - 5)) \\
 5625663 &:= (((3^6) - 6) \times (\sqrt{5^2} + (6^5))) \\
 5631996 &:= ((-6) + ((9^{\sqrt{9}}) + 1)) \times (3 + (6^5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5632088 &:= \left(\left(- (8) - \left(\sqrt{802^3} \right) \right) \times (- (6 + 5)) \right) \\
 5635899 &:= \left(\left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left((8 - 53) + \left(6^5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 5639752 &:= \left(\left((25 \times 7) + \sqrt{9} \right)^{3 \times (6-5)} \right) \\
 5639757 &:= \left(\left(\left(7 + (57 \times \sqrt{9}) \right)^{\sqrt{3+6}} \right) + 5 \right) \\
 5639968 &:= \left(\left((8 + 6)^{9-\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(\left((3 \times 6)^5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 5647147 &:= \left(\left((7 + 41) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{74}^6} \right) \right) - 5 \right) \\
 5647157 &:= \left(- \left(\left(7^{5+1} \right) \right) + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{4+6}} \right) + 5 \right) \right) \\
 5657769 &:= \left(\sqrt{9^6} \times (7756 + 5) \right) \\
 5660919 &:= \left(- (9) + \left(\left(- (1) + \sqrt{906} \right) \times \left(6^5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 5668192 &:= \left(- \left(\left(2^9 \right) \right) - \left(\sqrt{(1+8)^6} \times \left(- \left(6^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5668639 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(9^3 \right) \times \sqrt{6^8} \right) \times 6 \right) - 65 \right) \\
 5668663 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(3^6 \right) \times \sqrt{6^8} \right) - 6 \right) \times 6 \right) - 5 \right) \\
 5668699 &:= 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{6^8 \times 6 \times 6} - 5 \\
 5668709 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (07 + 8) \right)^6 \right) / 6 \right) + 5 \right) \\
 5668724 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\sqrt{(2+7)^8 \times 6^6} + 5 \right) \right) \\
 5669433 &:= \left(\sqrt{3^{3 \times 4}} - \left(\sqrt{9^6} \times \left(- \left(6^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5669728 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(2^7 \right) \right) - \left(\sqrt{9^6} \times \left(- \left(6^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5672349 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9\sqrt{4}} \right)^3 \right) \times \left(- \left((2-7) - \left(6^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5679139 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(9^3 \right) - 1 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(- \left(7 - \left(6^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5679428 &:= \left((8/2) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 9 \right) - (7-6) \right)^5 \right) \right) \\
 5679444 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(-4 - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 9 \right) - (7-6) \right)^5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 5679639 &:= \left(- \left(\left(9^3 \right) \right) \times \left(6 + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (-7) \right) - \left(6^5 \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5699799 &:= \left(-9 + \sqrt{9+7} + 9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 6^5 \\
 5699808 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{8+08} + \left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \left(6^5 \right) \right) \\
 5724535 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(535 \times \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) + 7 \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 5726447 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(7^4 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) - 6 \right)^2 \right) - (7-5) \right) \\
 5726449 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(9 - \sqrt{4} \right)^4 \right) - (6+2) \right)^{7-5} \right) \\
 5739486 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{8^4} - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 3 \right)^7 \right) \right) / 5 \right) \right) \\
 5746097 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(906^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + (7 \times 5) \right) \right) \\
 5747977 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(7^7 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 7 \right) + \left(\left(4 - \left(7^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5747992 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(- \left((2-9) \right)^9 \right) / 7 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) - \left(7^5 \right) \right) \\
 5748337 &:= \left(\left(7^3 \right) \times \left(\left(- \left((3 \times 8) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(7^5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 5749885 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((58+8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-4) \right) + 7 \right) \times (-5) \right) \\
 5756987 &:= \left(\left(\left(7^8 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(\left(6^5 \right) + (7 \times 5) \right) \right) \\
 5764287 &:= \left(\left(\left(7^8 \right) - \sqrt{(2 \times 4)^6} \right) - (7-5) \right) \\
 5764347 &:= \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{4^3}} \right) - (4 + (6 \times 75)) \right) \\
 5764387 &:= \left(\left(7^8 \right) - \left((3 \times \sqrt{4}) \times \left(- (6-75) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5764717 &:= 7 \times \left(\left(-1 + \sqrt{\sqrt{74 \times 6}} \right) \times 7 - 5 \right) \\
 5764718 &:= \left(- (8) + \left(\left((1 \times 7)^{\sqrt{4+6}} \right) - 75 \right) \right) \\
 5764722 &:= \left(- \left((2+2) \right) + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{4+6}} \right) - 75 \right) \right) \\
 5764723 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{3^2} - \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{4+6}} \right) - 75 \right) \right) \right) \\
 5764728 &:= \left(\sqrt{8/2} + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{4+6}} \right) - 75 \right) \right) \\
 5764732 &:= \left((2 \times 3) + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{4+6}} \right) - 75 \right) \right) \\
 5764733 &:= \left(- (33) + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{4+6}} \right) - (7 \times 5) \right) \right) \\
 5764734 &:= \left(\sqrt{4^3} + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{4+6}} \right) - 75 \right) \right) \\
 5764739 &:= \left(- \left((9 \times 3) \right) + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{4+6}} \right) - (7 \times 5) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$5764742 := \left((2^4) + \left((7^{\sqrt{4+6}}) - 75 \right) \right)$$

$$5764754 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 5) \times 7 \right)^4 \right) - ((6 \times 7) + 5) \right)$$

$$5764756 := (6 \times 5) + \left((7^{\sqrt{4+6}}) - 75 \right)$$

$$5764774 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left((7 \times 7)^4 \right) + 6 \right) - (7 \times 5) \right) \right)$$

$$5764778 := \left(\left(\left(\left((8 - (7^7)) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) - 6 \right) \times (-7) \right) + 5$$

$$5764782 := (2 \times 8) + \left((7^{\sqrt{4+6}}) - (7 \times 5) \right)$$

$$5764789 := \left(\left((9 - 8) \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4+6}} \right) - (7 + 5)$$

$$5764792 := \left(\left(\left((2 - 9) \times 7 \right)^4 \right) - \sqrt{6+75} \right)$$

$$5764793 := (3 - 9) + \left((7^{\sqrt{4+6}}) - (7 - 5) \right)$$

$$5764794 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(9 - (7^{4+6-7+5}) \right) \right)$$

$$5764795 := \left((-5) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((7^{\sqrt{4+6}}) + (7 - 5) \right)$$

$$5764796 := (6 - 9) + \left((7^{\sqrt{4+6}}) - (7 - 5) \right)$$

$$5764798 := (8 \times 9) + \left((7^{\sqrt{4+6}}) - 75 \right)$$

$$5764799 := \left(\left((9 - 9) + 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4+6}} \right) - (7 - 5)$$

$$5764807 := \left((7^{08}) + \sqrt{4 \times 6 + 7 + 5} \right)$$

$$5764827 := \left(\left(\sqrt{72^8} \right) + \left((4 \times 6) + 7 \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$5764845 := \left(\left((5 + \sqrt{4})^8 \right) + ((46 - 7) + 5) \right)$$

$$5764847 := \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{74^8}} \right) + \sqrt{46^{7-5}} \right)$$

$$5764849 := \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{4})^8 \right) + ((46 + 7) - 5) \right)$$

$$5764861 := \left(\left((1 + 6)^8 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) + ((67 - 5))$$

$$5764887 := \left(\left((7^8) + 84 \right) + \sqrt{6 - 7 + 5} \right)$$

$$5765487 := 7^8 + \sqrt{(-\sqrt{4} + 5 \times 6) \times 7^5}$$

$$5765687 := \left(\left((7^8) + 6 \right) - \left((\sqrt{5^6} \times (-7)) - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5765881 := \left(\left(((1 - 8))^8 \right) - \left(- (5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^{7+5}}} \right) \right)$$

$$5766859 := \sqrt{\sqrt{(9 + 5 \times 8)^6} \times (6 + 7^5)}$$

$$5767197 := \left((7^{9-1}) + \left((\sqrt{7^6} \times 7) - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5768387 := \left(\left((7^8) - 3 \right) - \left((\sqrt{8^6} \times (-7)) - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5781599 := \left(- (9) + \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{5-1})^8 \right) + (7^5) \right) \right)$$

$$5781689 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} + \left(\left((6 + 1)^8 \right) + (7^5) \right) \right)$$

$$5788125 := \left((5 \times 21)^{\sqrt{8+8-7}} \times 5 \right)$$

$$5789497 := \left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left((4^{\sqrt{9}}) + (8 + (7^5)) \right) \right)$$

$$5797564 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 6)^5 \right) + \left(\left((7^9) / 7 \right) - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5799478 := \left(\left((8 \times 7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(- (9) + \left((\sqrt{9} + 7)^5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5799787 := \left((7^8) + \left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (97 + 5) \right) \right)$$

$$5823845 := \left(\left((5 + \sqrt{4})^8 \right) + \left((3^{2+8}) - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$5830995 := \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{9}}) - (90^3) \right) \times (-8) - 5 \right)$$

$$5835758 := \left(\left(- \left((8 - ((5 \times 7)^5)) \right) / \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$5837174 := \left((\sqrt{4^7} - 1) \times (7 \times ((3^8) + 5)) \right)$$

$$5838895 := \left(\left((5^9) + \sqrt{8^8} \right) \times 3 - (8^5) \right)$$

$$5845769 := \left(\left(- \left((9^6) - 7 \right) \right) \times \left((-5) + \sqrt{4} - 8 \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$5848414 := \sqrt{4} \times \left(-1 + \sqrt{(4 + 8)^4} \right)^{8-5}$$

$$5857443 := \left(3 \times \left(-4 - \left((\sqrt{4^7} - (5^8)) \times 5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5857449 := - \left((\sqrt{9} \times (\sqrt{4} + ((\sqrt{4^7} - (5^8)) \times 5))) \right)$$

$$5857995 := \left((5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times \left(- (97 - ((5^8) + 5)) \right) \right)$$

$$5858649 := - \left((\sqrt{9} \times (\sqrt{4} + (((6 \times 8) - (5^8)) \times 5))) \right)$$

$$5858919 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left((19 \times 8) - ((5^8) \times 5) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$5858943 := (3 \times ((\sqrt{4} \times (-9 \times 8)) + ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859085 := (((-((5^8)) \times \sqrt{09}) + (58)) \times (-5))$$

$$5859115 := (((51 + 1) + (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8))) \times (-5))$$

$$5859145 := (((5 + 41) + (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8))) \times (-5))$$

$$5859175 := (((-((5^{7+1})) \times \sqrt{9}) + (5 \times 8)) \times (-5))$$

$$5859246 := ((6/\sqrt{4}) \times (2 - ((9 - (5^8)) \times 5)))$$

$$5859249 := ((\sqrt{9} \times (-42)) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859269 := (-96) + (((-2 - (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8))) \times 5))$$

$$5859273 := (3 \times (-((7^2)) - ((\sqrt{9} + (5^8)) \times (-5))))$$

$$5859275 := (-5) \times ((7 - 2) - (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) - 5)))$$

$$5859277 := (-((7 \times 7) \times 2)) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5))$$

$$5859278 := (-87) + (((-2 - (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8))) \times 5))$$

$$5859279 := (\sqrt{9} \times (-7) + ((2 + \sqrt{9}) \times ((5^8) - 5)))$$

$$5859287 := (-78) + (((-2 - (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8))) \times 5))$$

$$5859292 := (-((2 + (9^2))) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859295 := (((5^{\sqrt{9^2}}) \times \sqrt{9}) + (5 - 85))$$

$$5859296 := (-69) + (((-2 - (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8))) \times 5))$$

$$5859305 := (-5) \times ((03 \times (\sqrt{9} - (5^8))) + 5)$$

$$5859306 := (-60) + (-3) \times (\sqrt{9} - (((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859371 := (-(((1^7) + 3)) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859372 := (\sqrt{2+7} \times ((-3)/\sqrt{9}) + (((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859373 := -((\sqrt{-3+7} - (\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5)})))$$

$$5859376 := ((-((6-7)^3)) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859377 := (\sqrt{7/7+3} + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859378 := (((8-7) \times 3) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859379 := \sqrt{9+7} + \sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9} \times 5^8 \times 5}$$

$$5859399 := (((-9)/\sqrt{9}) + (3 \times (9 + ((5^8) \times 5))))$$

$$5859403 := 30 - \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8 \times 5$$

$$5859405 := 50 + (-4 + \sqrt{9} \times (5^8)) \times 5$$

$$5859415 := (\sqrt{5^{14} \times 9 \times 5 + 8}) \times 5$$

$$5859416 := (61 - (((-4 - (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8))) \times (-5)))$$

$$5859419 := ((\sqrt{9} \times (((1+4)^9) + 5) + 8) + 5)$$

$$5859423 := ((3 \times (2^4)) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859425 := 52 - \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8 \times 5$$

$$5859426 := ((6/2) \times (\sqrt{4} - ((\sqrt{9} + (5^8)) \times (-5))))$$

$$5859427 := 72 + (-4 + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8) \times 5$$

$$5859429 := (\sqrt{9} \times (-((2-4) \times 9) - ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859431 := (-1) - (3 \times (-4 + ((\sqrt{9} + (5^8)) \times (-5))))$$

$$5859434 := (\sqrt{4} - (3 \times (-4 + ((\sqrt{9} + (5^8)) \times (-5))))$$

$$5859435 := (5 \times 3) \times ((-4 + \sqrt{9}) + (((5^8) + 5)))$$

$$5859436 := ((63 - \sqrt{4}) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859438 := (83 - (((-4 - (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8))) \times (-5)))$$

$$5859443 := ((34 \times \sqrt{4}) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859445 := (-5) - ((\sqrt{4} + (4+9)) \times (-((5^8) + 5)))$$

$$5859447 := 74 - \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{9} \times 5^8 \times 5$$

$$5859449 := (94 - (((-4 - (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8))) \times (-5)))$$

$$5859465 := (-5) \times (((-6)/\sqrt{4}) - (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) + 5)))$$

$$5859469 := ((96 - \sqrt{4}) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859475 := (-5) \times (((-7) + \sqrt{4}) - (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) + 5)))$$

$$5859487 := (((7 \times 8) \times \sqrt{4}) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5)))$$

$$5859489 := (\sqrt{9} \times (8 + ((\sqrt{4 \times 9} + (5^8)) \times 5)))$$

$$5859494 := (-4 - (\sqrt{9} \times (4 - ((9 + (5^8)) \times 5))))$$

$$5859495 := ((5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times (4 + 9) + ((5^8) - 5))$$

$$5859497 := (-7) - (\sqrt{9} \times (\sqrt{4} - (((9 + (5^8)) \times 5))))$$

$$5859535 := ((-(((5-3)^5)) + (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8))) \times (-5))$$

$$5859554 := ((\sqrt{4+5} \times ((5^9) + 58)) + 5)$$

$$5859559 := ((\sqrt{9} \times (5 + ((5^9) + 58))) - 5)$$

$$5859566 := (\sqrt{6^6} + (-5) \times ((\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8)) + 5))$$

$$5859575 := (((((5^7) \times 5) \times \sqrt{9}) + (5 \times 8)) \times 5)$$

$$5859595 := (((5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times ((5 \times \sqrt{9}) + (5^8))) - 5)$$

$$5859596 := ((6^{\sqrt{9}}) - (((5^9) \times (5 - 8)) - 5))$$

$$5859655 := (5 \times 56) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5))$$

$$5859663 := (3 \times (6 - (((6 \times \sqrt{9}) + (5^8)) \times (-5))))$$

$$5859666 := (\sqrt{6^6} + ((6 + 9) \times ((5^8) + 5)))$$

$$5859695 := (((((5 - \sqrt{9})^6) - (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8)))) \times 5)$$

$$5859725 := ((-(((5 \times 2) \times 7)) + (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8))) \times (-5))$$

$$5859755 := (((5 + (5^7)) \times \sqrt{9 \times \sqrt{5^8}}) + 5)$$

$$5859785 := ((5 - 87) + (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8))) \times (-5)$$

$$5859879 := (\sqrt{9} \times (((7 \times 8) \times \sqrt{9}) + (((5^8) \times 5))))$$

$$5859954 := -(((\sqrt{4} - (5^9)) \times \sqrt{9}) - 585))$$

$$5859955 := (-5) - ((-((5^9)) \times \sqrt{9}) - 585))$$

$$5859969 := (\sqrt{9^6} + (\sqrt{9} \times (-((9 - (5^8)) \times 5))))$$

$$5859985 := (\sqrt{5^8} - ((\sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} \times (-5^8)))) \times 5)$$

$$5859995 := (((((5^9) \times 9) / \sqrt{9}) + \sqrt{5^8}) - 5)$$

$$5859996 := (69 \times 9) + (\sqrt{9} \times ((5^8) \times 5))$$

$$5871385 := ((-(((5^8) \times 3) + 1)) - \sqrt{7^8}) \times (-5)$$

$$5872024 := (((\sqrt{4^{20+2}} \times (-7)) + 8) / (-5))$$

$$5874995 := (((5^{9-\sqrt{9}}) \times (47 \times 8)) - 5)$$

$$5878473 := (3 \times ((7 \times ((-\sqrt{4-8})^7) - 8)) - 5)$$

$$5878644 := (4 \times (\sqrt{4} + (((6^8) \times 7) / 8) - 5))$$

$$5878661 := ((\sqrt{16} \times (((6^8) \times 7) / 8)) + 5)$$

$$5878677 := \left(\left(7 - \left(-7 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (8 - 5)$$

$$5898234 := (\sqrt{4} \times (-3 - ((2 + 8) \times 9) \times (8^5)))$$

$$5898265 := (-5) \times ((-6^2) \times \sqrt{8^9 \times 8}) - 5$$

$$5898275 := (-5) \times (-7) - (\sqrt{2 \times 8} \times (9 \times (8^5)))$$

$$5904895 := (-5) + ((98 + \sqrt{4}) \times (09^5))$$

$$5905924 := (\sqrt{4} \times ((2^9) + (50 \times (9^5))))$$

$$5925847 := \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} \right) - (5 - ((2 + 9)^5)) \right)$$

$$5925852 := ((2 + 5)^8) + ((5 + (2 \times \sqrt{9}))^5)$$

$$5929736 := ((-((6 - (((3 \times 7) \times 9) - 2)))^{\sqrt{9}}) - 5)$$

$$5929758 := \sqrt{(8^5 - 7)^{\sqrt{9}}} + 2 + \sqrt{9} \times 5$$

$$5937495 := (((5^{9-\sqrt{4}}) \times (73 + \sqrt{9})) - 5)$$

$$5942475 := ((-5) \times \sqrt{7^4 \times 2}) \times (-495)$$

$$5949678 := ((8 + \sqrt{7^6}) + \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{49^5}$$

$$5958481 := (((-((1 - 8)^4) + (8 \times 5))^{\sqrt{9-5}})$$

$$5958846 := (-6) \times (((4 - \sqrt{8^8}) + 5) \times \sqrt{9^5})$$

$$5963949 := (\sqrt{9^4} \times ((9^3) \times (6 + 95)))$$

$$5969295 := 5 \times \sqrt{(9 + 2^{\sqrt{9}})^6 \times 9^5}$$

$$5969565 := (((56 - 5)^{\sqrt{9}}) + 6) \times (9 \times 5)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5971482 &:= \left(- \left(\left(2 + \left(\left(8^4 \right) \times (1 - 7) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9^5} \right) \\
 5971648 &:= \left(\sqrt{8^4} \times \left(\left(\left((6 \times 1)^7 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) - 5 \right) \right) \\
 5971928 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(2 \times \left((9 \times (1 + 7))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) - 5 \right) \right) \\
 5971966 &:= \left(\left(\left(6^6 \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 1 \right)^7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9 - 5} \right) \\
 5971968 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{8^6} \times 9 \right) \times \left((1 - 7)^{9-5} \right) \right) \\
 5971989 &:= \left(\left(\left((9 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 1 \right) \times (7 + 9) \right) + 5 \\
 5991687 &:= \left(7^8 \right) + \left(\left(61^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (95) \right) \\
 5992448 &:= \left(8^4 \right) \times \left(\left((4 - 2) \times (9^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) + 5 \right) \\
 5996754 &:= \left((457 \times 6) \times 9 \right) \times \sqrt{9^5} \\
 5996875 &:= \left(- \left(5^7 \right) \right) + \left(8 \times \left(\left(6 + \sqrt{9 \times 9} \right)^5 \right) \right) \\
 5997317 &:= \left(\left((71 + 3)^{\sqrt{7+9}} \right) + 9 \right) / 5 \\
 5999694 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{9^5} \right) \right) \right) \\
 5999916 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left((1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (9 + 5) \right) \right) \\
 5999976 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left((7 + \sqrt{9})^{9-\sqrt{9}} \right) - (9 - 5) \right) \right) \\
 6022998 &:= (8 + 9) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{2 \times 20}}} \times 6} \\
 6064848 &:= \left(\left(- (8) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 8 \right)^4 \right) \right) \times (-606) \right) \\
 6094848 &:= \left(\left(8^4 \right) \times 8 \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 90 \right) + 6 \right) \\
 6145783 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((3^8) - 7 \right) + 5 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) / (1 + 6) \right) \\
 6169176 &:= \left(\left((6 + 7)^{1+\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{(6 \times 1)^6} \right) \\
 6176457 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left((5 \times \sqrt{4})^6 \right) - (7 \times 1)^6 \right) \right) \\
 6193152 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((2^5) \times 1 \right) \times 3 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (1 + 6) \right) \\
 6217944 &:= \left(\sqrt{4 \times 4^9} - 7 + 1 \right)^2 \times 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6223392 &:= \left(2 \times \left((9 + 33)^{\sqrt{22-6}} \right) \right) \\
 6225968 &:= \left(8 \times \left(6 - \left(- (95) \times \sqrt{2^{26}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 6225984 &:= 4^8 \times 95 + \sqrt{(2 + 2)^6} \\
 6229488 &:= \left(\left(\left((8 + 84)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 2 \right) \times (2 + 6) \right) \\
 6235397 &:= \left(\left(7^{9-3} \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{53^{-2+6}}} \right) \\
 6243584 &:= \sqrt{4^8 \times (5 + 3 \times 4 \times 2)^6} \\
 6249994 &:= \left(\left((49 + (9/9))^{\sqrt{4^2}} \right) - 6 \right) \\
 6249995 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (9 + 9) \right) - 4 \right)^{-2+6} \right) \right) \\
 6254634 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((3 - 6) + (4^5) \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) \times (-6) \\
 6289488 &:= \left(\sqrt{8 + 8} \times \left(\left((4^9) - 82 \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 6291378 &:= \left(\left((8^7) \times 3 \right) - \left(\sqrt{1 \times 9} \times 26 \right) \right) \\
 6291408 &:= \left(\left(8 - \left(\sqrt{04}^{(1+9) \times 2} \right) \right) \times (-6) \right) \\
 6291429 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((2 - \left((4^{1+9}) - 2 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6291436 &:= \left(- \left(\left(6 \times (3 - (4^{1+9})) \right) \right) - \sqrt{-2+6} \right) \\
 6291451 &:= \left(- \left((1 \times 5) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{19} \right) \times \left(- (2 \times 6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6291452 &:= \left(\left(\left(2^{5 \times 4 + 1} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((2 - 6) \right) \right) \\
 6291454 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 5 \right) + \left(\left((4^{1+9}) - 2 \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 6291455 &:= \left(- \left((5/5) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{19} \right) \times \left(- (2 \times 6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6291456 &:= \sqrt{\left((6 - 5) \times 4 \right)^{19} \times 2 \times 6} \\
 6291458 &:= \left(\left(\left(8^{5+\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \sqrt{1 \times 9} \right) + \sqrt{-2+6} \right) \\
 6291459 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left(5 - \left(\left((4^{1+9}) \times 2 \right) + 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6291484 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 8 \right) + \left(\left((4^{1+9}) + 2 \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 6291489 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(8 + \left((4^{1+9}) - 2 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \right) \\
 6291491 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\sqrt{4}^{19} \right) \right) \times (2 \times 6) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$6291492 := \left(\left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(\left(4^{1+9} \right) - 2 \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$6291498 := \left(\left(\left(8 - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(4^{1+9} \right) + 2 \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$6291584 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(- \left(\left(8^5 \right) \times \sqrt{1 \times 9} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(2^6 \right) \right)$$

$$6291648 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(8 \times \left(4^6 \right) \right) + 1 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(2^6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6291688 := \left(8 \times \left(\left(\left(\left(8^6 \right) + 1 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(26 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6291942 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{24^{9+1}} \right) + \left(\left(9^2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$6291944 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left(4^{9+1} \right) + \left(9^2 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right)$$

$$6292789 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(8^7 \right) \right) + 2 \right) + \sqrt{\left(9 + 2 \right)^6} \right) \right)$$

$$6292992 := \left(\left(2^9 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(2^{9+2} \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6294528 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(8 \times 2 \right)^5 \right) + \left(\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9^2}}} \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$6298965 := \left(- \left(5 \right) \times \left(- \left(\left(6^9 / 8 \right) \right) - \left(\sqrt{9^{-2+6}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6299456 := \left(\left(- \left(6 \right) + \left(- \left(5 \right) \times \left(-4 - \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(2^6 \right) \right)$$

$$6299584 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 8 \right) + \left(5 \times \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \times \left(2^6 \right) \right)$$

$$6322419 := \left(\left(\left(\left(91 + \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) \times \left(2 + \left(3^6 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6324966 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(66 / \sqrt{9} \right)^4 \right) + 2 \right) \times \sqrt{3^6} \right) \right)$$

$$6328125 := \sqrt{\left(5 \times \left(2 + 1 \right) \right)^8 \times \left(2 + 3 \right)^6}$$

$$6329583 := \left(\sqrt{3^8} \times \left(\left(5^{9-2} \right) + \left(3 \times 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6331619 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(1 - \left(61 \times 3 \right) \right) \right) \right)^3 \right) - 6 \right) \right)$$

$$6331634 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(3 \times 61 \right) \right)^3 \right) + \left(3 + 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6359796 := \left(\left(- \left(6 \right) + \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times \left(\left(9 - 5 \right) \times \left(3^6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6371568 := \left(86 \times \left(\left(\left(5 + 1 \right) \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{3+6}} \right) \right)$$

$$6374988 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(8 \times 8 \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9^{4+7}} \right) \right) \times 36 \right)$$

$$6376949 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(4 \times \left(9^6 \right) \right) \right) - \left(7^{\sqrt{3+6}} \right) \right)$$

$$6376994 := \left(\left(- \left(4 \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left(9^6 \right) \right) \right) + 73 \right) \right) - 6 \right)$$

$$6377244 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(\left(4 - \left(27^{7-3} \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6377286 := \left(- \left(6 \right) - \left(- \left(\left(8 \times \left(\left(2 + 7 \right)^7 \right) \right) / \sqrt{36} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6377289 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(- \left(\left(8 \times \left(\left(2 + 7 \right)^7 \right) \right) / \sqrt{36} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6377291 := \left(- \left(1 \right) - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{27-7}}} \right) \times \left(-36 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6377294 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{27-7}}} \right) \times \left(-36 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6378786 := \left(- \left(6 \right) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\left(8 + 7 \right)^8} \times \left(- \left(7 \times 3 \right) \right) \right) - 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6379479 := \left(\sqrt{9^7} - \left(\left(4 \times \left(9^7 \right) \right) / \left(3 - 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6386679 := \left(- \left(9 \right) + \left(\left(7 \times 66 \right) \times \sqrt{\left(8 \times 3 \right)^6} \right) \right)$$

$$6394794 := \left(\left(\left(\left(4 \times \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(9^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + 6 \right)$$

$$6396975 := \left(\left(\left(5 + 7 \right) \times \left(9^6 \right) \right) + \sqrt{\left(9 \times 3 \right)^6} \right)$$

$$6398542 := \left(2 \times \left(\left(\left(4 \times 5 \right)^{8-\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(\left(3^6 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6423648 := \left(\left(8 - \left(46^3 \right) \right) \times \left(-2 - \sqrt{4^6} \right) \right)$$

$$6424176 := \left(\left(67 - 1 \right) \times \sqrt{\left(42 + 4 \right)^6} \right)$$

$$6434792 := \left(\left(\left(2 \times \left(97 - 4 \right) \right)^3 \right) - \sqrt{4^6} \right)$$

$$6434832 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(23 \times 8 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right)^3 \right) - \left(\left(4 \times 6 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6434856 := \left(\left(\left(6 \times \left(58 + 4 \right) \right)^3 \right) / \left(\sqrt{4} + 6 \right) \right)$$

$$6434858 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(85 + 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)^3 \right) - \left(\left(4 - 6 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6436337 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(7 - 3 \right) \right) + \sqrt{3^6} \right)^{3+\sqrt{4}} \right) - 6 \right)$$

$$6436341 := \left(\left(1 + \left(4 \times \sqrt{3^6} \right) \right) \times \left(3^{4+6} \right) \right)$$

$$6436343 := \left(\left(\left(\left(3 + \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left(3 \times 6 \right) \right) \right)^{3-4+6} \right) \right)$$

$$6436349 := \left(\left(\left(\left(9 - 4 \right) + \left(3 \times 6 \right) \right)^{3+\sqrt{4}} \right) + 6 \right)$$

$$6439773 := \left(- \left(3 \right) - \left(\left(\left(7 + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 3 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \left(-6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6439774 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left(7 + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 3 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times (-6) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6439776 := \left(6 \times \left(\left(7 + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 3 \right) \right)^{-4+6} \right) \right)$$

$$6439779 := \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(\left(7 + \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 3 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times (-6) \right) \right)$$

$$6448968 := \left(\left(\left(\left(8^6 \right) + \sqrt{9^8} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (4 \times 6) \right)$$

$$6451594 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^9} - (5 - 1) \right) \times 5 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 6 \right)$$

$$6452736 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(3 - \sqrt{7^2 \times 5} \right) \times \sqrt{4^6} \right) \right)$$

$$6453888 := \left(\left(\left(\left((88/8) + 3 \right)^5 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$6454144 := \left(\left(4^4 \right) - \left(\left(\left(14^5 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-6) \right) \right)$$

$$6454164 := \left(\left(46 + \left(\left(14^5 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$6464647 := \left(7 \times \left(\left(4 + \sqrt{\left(6/\sqrt{4} \right)^6} \right)^{-\sqrt{4}+6} \right) \right)$$

$$6475497 := \left(7^{\sqrt{9\sqrt{4}}} - (5 \times 7)^4 \right) / 6$$

$$6479979 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- (7) + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - (9 \times 7) \right) \right)^4 \right) / 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6479987 := \left(- (7) + \left(\left(8 \times \left(\left(9 - \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-7) \right) \right)^4 \right) \right) - 6 \right) \right)$$

$$6479994 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}} \right) \times \left(\left(9 - \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-7) \right) \right)^4 \right) \right) - 6 \right)$$

$$6479995 := \left(- (5) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - (9 \times 7) \right) \right)^4 \right) / (-6) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6499899 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (9 + 8) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + 46 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6539328 := \left(\left(\left((8 \times 23) + \sqrt{9} \right)^3 \right) + \sqrt{5^6} \right)$$

$$6546875 := \left(\left(\left(5^7 \right) \times \left(86 - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(5^6 \right) \right)$$

$$6553644 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(4^{6+3} \right) \right) \right) \times (5 \times 5) - 6 \right)$$

$$6554439 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 34 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4 + 5^{5+6}} \right) \right)$$

$$6569225 := \left(\left(\left(5^2 \right) \times \left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right)^6 \right) \right) \right) + \left(5^6 \right)$$

$$6572719 := \left(\left((9 - 1) \times \left(\sqrt{7^2} \right)^7 \right) \right) - \left(5^6 \right)$$

$$6587769 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(67 \times \left(7 + \left(8^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - 6$$

$$6588378 := \left(\left(8 \times \left(\left(7^{3+\sqrt{8+8}} \right) + 5 \right) \right) \right) - 6$$

$$6588477 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(7^7 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 8 \right) - 8 \right) + \sqrt{5^6} \right)$$

$$6589679 := \left(- (9) + \left(\left(\left(7^6 \right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-8) \right) \right) \times 56 \right) \right)$$

$$6593799 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \times \left(\left(\left(7^3 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - 5 \right) \right) \right) - 6$$

$$6644316 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- (13) \times \sqrt{44^6} \right) + 6 \right) \right)$$

$$6644352 := \left(\left((2 - (5 \times 3)) \times \sqrt{44^6} \right) \times (-6) \right)$$

$$6653694 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(6^3 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(\left(5^6 \right) - 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6655964 := \left(4 \times \left(\left(6^{\sqrt{9}+5} \right) - \sqrt{5^{6+6}} \right) \right)$$

$$6656245 := \left(- (5) + \left(426 \times \sqrt{5^{6+6}} \right) \right)$$

$$6667915 := \left(- (5) \times \left(1 + \left(\sqrt{9 \times (7 \times 6)^6} \times (-6) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6667935 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- (3) + \left(\sqrt{9 \times (7 \times 6)^6} \times (-6) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6667956 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- (5) \times \sqrt{9 \times (7 \times 6)^6} \right) - 6 \right) \right)$$

$$6667968 := \left(\left(8 - \left(- \left((6 + 9) \right) \times \sqrt{(7 \times 6)^6} \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$6679586 := \left(\left(6^8 \right) + \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right)^6 \right) - 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$6689728 := \left(\left(- \left(\left((8 - 2)^7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((8 + 6)^6 \right) \right)$$

$$6705987 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (50 + 7) \right) \right) - 6$$

$$6711903 := \left(- \left(\left(3^{09} \right) \right) \times \left((1 + 1) - \sqrt{7^6} \right) \right)$$

$$6718434 := \left(\left(4 \times \left(\left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{4} \right)^8 \right) + \left((1 - 7) \right) \right) \right) \right) - 6$$

$$6718462 := -2 + \sqrt{\sqrt{\left(6 \times \sqrt{4} \right)^8} \times (1 - 7)^6}$$

$$6718484 := \left(4 \times \left(\left(\left(8 - \sqrt{4} \right)^8 \right) - \left(\left((1^7) - 6 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6718488 &:= \left(\sqrt{8+8} \times \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4}-8) \right)^{1+7} \right) + 6 \right) \right) \\
 6718494 &:= \left(\left(4 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{(9 \times 4)^8} \right) - ((1-7)) \right) \right) + 6 \right) \\
 6718976 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((6^7) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-8) \right) + \sqrt{(1+7)^6} \right) \\
 6725597 &:= \left(\left(- \left((7^9) \right) + \left(\sqrt{5 \times 5} \times (- (2-7)) \right) \right) / (-6) \right) \\
 6738921 &:= \left(\left((12 - \sqrt{9^8}) \times (-3) \right) \times \sqrt{7^6} \right) \\
 6739968 &:= \left(\sqrt{8^6} \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times (9^3)) + 7 \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 6749958 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (8) \times \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) + 7 \right) \times (-6) \right) \\
 6751269 &:= \sqrt{9^{6/2+1+5} \times 7^6} \\
 6754699 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} + ((6-4) \times 5) \right) \times \sqrt{7^6} \right) \\
 6758095 &:= \left(- ((5-90)) \times \sqrt{(8+5 \times 7)^6} \right) \\
 6764394 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4}+9)^{3+\sqrt{4}} \right) + 6 \right) \times (7 \times 6) \right) \\
 6774435 &:= \left(- \left((5 \times (3^4)) \right) \times \left(- \left((4^7) \right) - \sqrt{7^6} \right) \right) \\
 6777456 &:= \left(6 \times \left((5^{\sqrt{4+7}}) - \left((7^7) + 6 \right) \right) \right) \\
 6777492 &:= \left(\left(\left((2 + \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{4+7}} \right) - \left((7^7) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 6782964 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(- (69) \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^7} \right) \right) \times (-6) \right) \\
 6782968 &:= \left(- (8) - \left(\left(- (69) \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^7} \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 6782976 &:= \left(\left((6 + (7 \times 9)) \times \sqrt{(2 \times 8)^7} \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 6792099 &:= \left(\left((99^{\sqrt{0 \times 2+9}}) \times 7 \right) + 6 \right) \\
 6797875 &:= \left(\left((5^7) \times 87 \right) + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9}+7)^6} \right) \\
 6815562 &:= \left(- (26) \times \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{5-1} \right) - (8^6) \right) \right) \\
 6815742 &:= \left(-2 - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((7+5) + 1 \right) \times (8^6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6815754 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(5 + \left((7+5) + 1 \right) \times (8^6) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6834369 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \left((6 + \sqrt{3^4})^{-3+8} \right) \right) - 6 \right) \\
 6834375 &:= \left((5^{\sqrt{7 \times 3+4}}) \times \sqrt{3^{8+6}} \right) \\
 6848512 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 + \sqrt{(1 \times 5)^8} \right) \times \left(- (4^8) \right) \right) / (-6) \right) \\
 6848689 &:= \left(\left(9 + \left((8 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right)^{8-6} \right) \\
 6848716 &:= \left(- (6) + \left(\sqrt{17^8} \times \left(- (4-86) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6848719 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\sqrt{17^8} \times \left(- (4-86) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6848728 &:= 82 \times \sqrt{(7+8+\sqrt{4})^8} + 6 \\
 6858994 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 99) - 8 \right)^{-5+8} \right) - 6 \right) \\
 6859091 &:= \left((190^{\sqrt{9}}) + (5+86) \right) \\
 6874994 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{4}+9) \times \left((9-4)^7 \times 8 \right) \right) - 6 \right) \\
 6889536 &:= \left((6^{-3+5+\sqrt{9}}) \times 886 \right) \\
 6899697 &:= \left((7 \times \sqrt{9}) \times \left((69^{\sqrt{9}}) + ((8 \times 6)) \right) \right) \\
 6935781 &:= \left(- \left((1+8)^7 \right) + \left((5^3)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 6940329 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9^2} + (30))^4 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 6 \right) \\
 6940419 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} \times ((1-40)^4)) + 96 \right) \\
 6945762 &:= \left(\left(-2 - \left(((6 \times 7) \times 5) / \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times (-6) \\
 6945786 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left((8+7) \times (5 + \sqrt{4}) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} + 6 \right) \right) \\
 6945798 &:= \left(8 + \sqrt{\left(9 \times \sqrt{(7 \times 5)^4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}}} \right) \times 6 \\
 6949584 &:= \left(\left((4^8) \times 5 \right) + (94^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times 6 \\
 6954744 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} + (4 \times (7^4))) \times \left(- (5) + \sqrt{9^6} \right) \right) \\
 6984576 &:= \left(\left((6^7) \times \sqrt{5^4} \right) - \sqrt{(8 \times \sqrt{9})^6} \right) \\
 6994749 &:= \left(\left(- \left((9 - (4 \times (7^4))) \right) \right) \times (9^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) - 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$6994897 := \left(7 \times \left(\left(\left(98 + \sqrt{4}\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \sqrt{96}\right)\right)$$

$$6994944 := \left(\left(\left(-\left(4^4\right) + \sqrt{9}\right) \times \sqrt{4^9}\right) \times \left(-\left(9 \times 6\right)\right)\right)$$

$$6998095 := \sqrt{\sqrt{\left(5+9\right)^{08 \times \sqrt{9}} - 9^6}}$$

$$6999937 := \left(-\left(7\right) \times \left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{9}\right) - \left(\left(9/9\right) + 9\right)^6\right)\right)$$

$$7012346 := -6 + \sqrt{\sqrt{4^3 2} \times 107}$$

$$7012349 := \left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{4^3 2} \times \left(-107\right)}\right)\right)$$

$$7176467 := \left(\left(-\left(7^6\right) + \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(-\left(67+1\right) - 7\right)\right)$$

$$7214913 := \left(\left(\left(3^{-1+9}\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) - \left(12^7\right)\right)$$

$$7239159 := \left(9 \times \left(-\left(5+1\right) + \left(93^{\sqrt{2+7}}\right)\right)\right)$$

$$7239197 := \left(-\left(7\right) - \left(9 \times \left(1 - \left(93^{\sqrt{2+7}}\right)\right)\right)\right)$$

$$7239213 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{31^2 \times 9}\right)^3\right) / \sqrt{2+7}\right)$$

$$7239249 := \left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{4^2} + \left(93^{\sqrt{2+7}}\right)\right)\right)$$

$$7239429 := \left(9 \times \left(24 + \left(93^{\sqrt{2+7}}\right)\right)\right)$$

$$7239699 := \left(9 \times \left(9 \times 6 + \left(93^{\sqrt{2+7}}\right)\right)\right)$$

$$7244694 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^9} + 6\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) - \sqrt{4}\right) \times 27\right)$$

$$7247295 := \left(5 \times 9\right) \times \left(\left(2+7\right) + \sqrt{4}\right)^{-2+7}$$

$$7254261 := \left(\left(1 - \left(-\left(6\right) + \sqrt{2^4 \times 5}\right)^2\right)\right) \times \left(-7\right)$$

$$7254264 := \left(-4 + \left(\left(-\left(6\right) + \sqrt{2^4 \times 5}\right)^2\right) \times 7\right)$$

$$7254268 := \left(\left(\left(-\left(8\right) + \sqrt{6-2}\right) + \left(4^5\right)\right)^2\right) \times 7$$

$$7254289 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\left(8-2\right) - \left(4^5\right)\right)\right)^2\right)\right) \times 7$$

$$7265439 := \left(-\left(93\right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(5^6\right) \times \left(2-7\right)\right)\right)\right)$$

$$7280914 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(1908^2\right) - 7\right)\right)$$

$$7282688 := \left(\left(-\left(8\right) \times \sqrt{8^6}\right) \times \left(-\left(\left(2^8\right) - 2\right) \times 7\right)\right)$$

$$7301377 := \left(\left(\left(-\left(7 \times 7\right) + \sqrt{3^{10}}\right)^3\right) - 7\right)$$

$$7304514 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(154^{03}\right) - 7\right)\right)$$

$$7327849 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(-\left(4 - \left(8 \times 7\right)\right)\right)^2\right)\right)^{\sqrt{-3+7}}$$

$$7340032 := \left(\left(2^{\sqrt{300 \times 4/3}}\right) \times 7\right)$$

$$7378448 := \left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{4}\right) \times \left(\left(4^8\right) + \left(7^3\right)\right) \times 7\right)$$

$$7381125 := \left(\left(5^{2+1}\right) \times \sqrt{\left(1+8\right)^{3+7}}\right)$$

$$7399673 := \left(\left(376 \times \left(\sqrt{9^9} - 3\right)\right) - 7\right)$$

$$7409277 := \left(\left(7^7\right) - 290\right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 7\right)$$

$$7411874 := \left(-4 + \left(\left(7^{8-1}\right) - 1\right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 7\right)\right)$$

$$7411959 := \left(9 \times \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{9}\right) + \left(11 - 4\right)^7\right)\right)$$

$$7411977 := \left(\left(\left(7^7\right) + 9\right) + 1\right) \times \left(\sqrt{1 \times 4} + 7\right)$$

$$7419727 := \left(-\left(7\right) \times \left(\left(-\left(2^7\right)\right) \times \sqrt{91^4}\right) + 7\right)$$

$$7419874 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7\right) \times \left(\left(8 \times 91\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) + 7\right)$$

$$7421952 := \left(-2 + 5 \times 91\right) \times \sqrt{2^4 \times 7}$$

$$7421954 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(5 \times 91\right) - 2\right) \times \left(4^7\right)\right)$$

$$7427913 := \left(3 \times \left(\left(19^{7-2}\right) - \sqrt{4^7}\right)\right)$$

$$7438382 := \left(\left(-\left(2^8\right)\right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{3^8 3}\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times 7$$

$$7439544 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-\left(\left(45 - \left(9 \times 3\right)^4\right)\right) \times 7\right)\right)$$

$$7439796 := \left(-\left(6 \times 9\right)\right) \times \left(7 - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{\sqrt{3^4}}}\right) \times 7\right)\right)$$

$$7439838 := \left(\left(-\left(8\right) + \left(3^{8+\sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times \left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{4}\right) \times 7\right)\right)$$

$$7439964 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-\left(\left(6+9\right) - \left(9 \times 3\right)^4\right)\right) \times 7\right)$$

$$7440169 := \left(\left(\left(9^6\right) \times \left(10+4\right) + \sqrt{4}\right) - 7\right)$$

$$7440174 := \left(\left(\left(\left(4 \times 7\right) - 1\right)^{04}\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \times 7$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7443465 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{56} - \sqrt{4} \right)^3 \right) \times 4 \right) + ((4 - 7)) \right) \\
 7449246 &:= \left(\left(- \left((6^4) \right) + \left(- (2) \times \left(9^{\sqrt{4}+4} \right) \right) \right) \times (-7) \right) \\
 7455168 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(8 + \left(\left(6 - \sqrt{-1+5} \right)^5 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 7455182 &:= \left(\left(2 + \left(\left(8 + \left(- \left((1 - 5) \right)^5 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 7455189 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(8 + \left(- \left((1 - 5) \right)^5 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 7458368 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left((8 + 6) \right)^3 - 8 \right) - 5 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 7 \right) \\
 7459864 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (6^8) \right) + \left((9 \times 5)^4 + 7 \right) \right) \\
 7464885 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(8 - \left(\left((8 + 4) \right)^6 / \sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 7464925 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9 \times 4}) \right)^6 / \sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 7464945 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(-4 - \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 4) \right)^6 / \sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 7464952 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (2) + \left(5 \times \left((\sqrt{9} \times 4) \right)^6 \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \\
 7464954 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(5 \times \left((\sqrt{9} \times 4) \right)^6 \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \\
 7464956 &:= \left(\left(\left(6 + \left(5 \times \left((\sqrt{9} \times 4) \right)^6 \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \\
 7464965 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(6 - \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 4) \right)^6 / \sqrt{4} + 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 7464995 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \left(- (4^6) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} - 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 7468794 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (9^7) \right) + 8 \right) - \left(\sqrt{64^7} \right) \right) \\
 7475249 &:= \left(\left((94^{-2+5}) \times (7 + \sqrt{4}) \right) - 7 \right) \\
 7485689 &:= \left(\left((9 \times 8) \times ((6 \times 5) + 8) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 7 \right) \\
 7492608 &:= \left(\sqrt{806} \times \left((2 + 9)^4 - 7 \right) \right) \\
 7498575 &:= \left(\left((57 + 58) \times 9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 7 \right) \\
 7499995 &:= \left(- (5) + \left((99 - \sqrt{9}) \times (9 - 4)^7 \right) \right) \\
 7527744 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4^7} - \left((7 \times 2)^5 \right) \right) \right) \times (-7) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7529472 &:= \left(\left((2 \times 7)^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} - \sqrt{2^{5+7}} \right) \right) \\
 7529477 &:= \left(\left((7 + 7)^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}} - (2 + 57) \right) \right) \\
 7529479 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} + (7 + 4))^{\sqrt{9}} \right)^2 \right) - (57) \right) \right) \\
 7529487 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{8^4} \times \left(- \left((9 - 2)^5 \right) \right) \right) + 7 \right) \right) \\
 7529494 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(- \left((4 - (9 \times 2))^5 \right) \right) \right) \times (-7) \right) \right) \\
 7529522 &:= \left(\left(2 - \left(2 \times \left((5 + 9)^{\sqrt{25}} \right) \right) \right) \times (-7) \right) \\
 7529524 &:= \left(\left(\left((4 + (2 \times 5))^{\sqrt{9}} \right)^2 - (5 + 7) \right) \right) \\
 7529528 &:= \left(- (8) - \left(2 \times \left(\left((5 + 9)^{\sqrt{25}} \right) \times (-7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 7529529 &:= \left(\left((9 + \sqrt{25})^{9+2-5} - 7 \right) \right) \\
 7529543 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{3^4} + 5)^{9+2-5} + 7 \right) \right) \\
 7529544 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(4 - \left((5 + 9)^{\sqrt{25}} \times (-7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 7529548 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 \times \left((\sqrt{4} + 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)^2 + (5 + 7) \right) \right) \\
 7529593 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{9} + 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)^2 + (57) \right) \right) \\
 7529647 &:= \left(\left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{4})^6 - \sqrt{9} \right) + ((2 \times 57)) \right) \right) \\
 7529674 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 7)^6 + ((9^2) + 57) \right) \right) \\
 7546847 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 8)^6 - (4 - (5^7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 7555947 &:= \left((7^4) \times \left((\sqrt{9} \times 5) + ((5^5) + 7) \right) \right) \\
 7556976 &:= \left(\left((6 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (6 \times ((5 + 5) + 7)) \right) \right) \\
 7558269 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((6^{2+8}) / ((5/5) + 7) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 7559288 &:= \left(88 \times \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^5 + (5^7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 7559825 &:= \left(\left((52 + 8)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 \right) \times (5 \times 7) \right) \\
 7569984 &:= \left(\left((4 \times 8) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^6} + (5^7) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$7577955 := \left((55 \times \sqrt{9^{7+7-5}}) \times 7 \right)$$

$$7577997 := \left(\left((7 + (\sqrt{9^9} \times 77)) \right) \times 5 \right) + 7$$

$$7579497 := \left(\left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 4 \right) + (97 \times (5^7)) \right)$$

$$7592569 := \left((9 \times 6) \times \left((52^{\sqrt{9}}) - 5 \right) \right) + 7$$

$$7595455 := \left(\left(\left(\left((5^5)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 5 \right) / 9 \right) - 5 \right) \times 7$$

$$7596652 := \left(2 \times \left(\left((5^6) + 6 \right) \times \sqrt{9^5} - 7 \right) \right)$$

$$7619968 := \left(\left((8^6) \times \left((9 \times \sqrt{9}) + 1 \right) \right) + (6^7) \right)$$

$$7654465 := \left(- (5) + \left(6 \times \sqrt{4 \times 45^6} \right) \right) \times 7$$

$$7654479 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left((7 \times 4) \times \sqrt{45^6} \right) - 7 \right) \right)$$

$$7654493 := \left(\left((3 + \sqrt{9^4}) \times \sqrt{45^6} \right) - 7 \right)$$

$$7654495 := \left(- (5) + \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 4) \times \sqrt{45^6} \right) \times 7 \right) \right)$$

$$7656264 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((6 + (2^6)) \times (5^6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$7691679 := \left(\left(\left((9^7) \times (6 - 1) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) - (6^7) \right)$$

$$7719138 := \left(\left((83 - 1)^{\sqrt{9}} - 1 \right) \times (7 + 7) \right)$$

$$7733484 := \left(- \left((4^8) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times - \left((3 \times 37) + 7 \right)$$

$$7762399 := \left(\left((99^3) \times (2 + 6) \right) + \sqrt{7 \times 7} \right)$$

$$7764786 := \left(- (6) \times \left(8 + \left(\sqrt{7^{4+6}} \times (-77) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7764834 := \sqrt{(4 + 3)^{8 + \sqrt{4}}} \times 6 \times 77$$

$$7765749 := \left(- (9) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (7^5) \right) \times (6 \times 77) \right) \right)$$

$$7791582 := \left(\left(\left((2^8) - 51 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left((7^7) \right) \right)$$

$$7794469 := \left(\left(\left((9^6) \times 44 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) + (7/7) \right)$$

$$7836694 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((9 - (6^6)) \times ((3 \times 8) \times 7) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7836696 := \left(\left((6 + \sqrt{9}) - (6^6) \right) \times - \left((3 \times 8) \times 7 \right) \right)$$

$$7836699 := \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((9 - (6^6)) \times ((3 \times 8) \times 7) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7837641 := \left(\left(\left((1 \times 4) \times (6^7) \right) - \sqrt{3^8} \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$7838166 := \left(\left(- (6) - \left(- \left((6^{1+8}) \right) / \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$7841792 := \left(2 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9^7} + 1) \times \sqrt{4^8} \right) \times 7 \right) \right)$$

$$7854554 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((55^4) / 5 \right) + (8^7) \right) \right)$$

$$7861947 := \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}}} \right) - \left((1 \times 6) - (8^7) \right) \right)$$

$$7861957 := \left((7^{5 + \sqrt{9}}) + (\sqrt{16} + (8^7)) \right)$$

$$7864245 := \left((5 - (\sqrt{4} \times ((2 \times 4)^6))) \times - (8 + 7) \right)$$

$$7864285 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- \left((8^{2+4}) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \right) + 7 \right) \right)$$

$$7864656 := \left(- (6) \times \left(- (5) \times (\sqrt{64^6}) - ((8 \times 7)) \right) \right)$$

$$7865767 := \left((7 + 6) \times \left(\left((7^5) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} \right) + 7 \right) \right)$$

$$7885694 := - \left((\sqrt{4} - \left(\left((9^6) - (5^8) \right) \times (8 \times 7) \right)) \right)$$

$$7885696 := \left(\left(\left((6 + \sqrt{9})^6 \right) - (5^8) \right) \times (8 \times 7) \right)$$

$$7885699 := \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((9^6) - (5^8) \right) \times (8 \times 7) \right) \right)$$

$$7885955 := \left(- (55) \times \left((\sqrt{9} + (5 \times \sqrt{8^8})) \times (-7) \right) \right)$$

$$7888399 := \left(\left((993^{\sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}}}) \times 8 \right) + 7 \right)$$

$$7889695 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- \left((9^6) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \sqrt{(8 + 8)^7} \right) \right)$$

$$7929856 := \left((6 + 5) \times \left((8 + \sqrt{9}) \times (2^{9+7}) \right) \right)$$

$$7949745 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{9^7} \right) \right)$$

$$7949795 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9^7} - \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) + 7 \right) \right)$$

$$7951689 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 8)^{6-1} \right) - (5 \times \sqrt{9^7}) \right)$$

$$7962489 := \left(9 \times \left(- (8) + \left(\left((4^2) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7962589 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 8)^5 \right) - \left((2 - 6) + 9 \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7962598 &:= \left(\left((8 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \right) - \sqrt{26^{9-7}} \right) \\
 7962617 &:= \left(\left((7+1) \times \left((6 \times 2)^6 \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} - 7 \right) \\
 7962622 &:= \left(- (2) + \left((2 \times 6) \times 2^{-6/\sqrt{9+7}} \right) \right) \\
 7962624 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (2 \times 6) \right)^{(26+9)/7} \right) \\
 7962648 &:= \left(8 \times \left(-4 - \left(- \left((6 \times 2)^6 \right) / \sqrt{9} - 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 7966449 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (4^6) \right) \times (6^{\sqrt{9}}) - 7 \right) \right) \\
 7971595 &:= 5 \times \left(\sqrt{9^{5+1+7}} - \sqrt{9+7} \right) \\
 7971635 &:= 5 \times \left(3^{6 \times 1+7} + \sqrt{9+7} \right) \\
 7971695 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9}^{6 \times 1+7} \right) + ((9+7)) \right) \right) \\
 7973714 &:= \left(41 \times \left((7 \times 3)^{\sqrt{7+9}} \right) - 7 \right) \\
 7973795 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \left((9^7) / 3 \right) \right) - 7 \right) + \sqrt{9^7} \\
 7997859 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + ((58 \times 7) \times 9) \right) \times \sqrt{9^7} \right) \\
 7999488 &:= \left(\sqrt{8^8} \times \left((4 + (9 \times \sqrt{9})) \times (9 \times 7) \right) \right) \\
 8097792 &:= \left(2^{\sqrt{9+7}} \times 7908 \right) \\
 8126457 &:= \left(- (7) - \left(\left(\sqrt{5^4} + 6 \right) \times \left(- (2^{18}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8126472 &:= \left(\sqrt{2^{7 \times 4}} \times 62 + 1 \right) \times 8 \\
 8168194 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (- (1-8)) \right)^{6-1} \right) \right) - 8 \right) \\
 8171316 &:= 61^3 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(1 \times 7 - 1)^8}} \\
 8191984 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((8 \times (9+1))^{\sqrt{9}} - 1 \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 8191992 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \left((9 \times 9 - 1)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 1 \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 8193524 &:= \left(\left(4 \times \left((2 + (5^3))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) - (1 \times 8) \right) \\
 8193544 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + ((5^3)) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{1+8} \right) \right) \right) \\
 8225568 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{8^6} - \sqrt{5 \times 5} \right) \times 2 \right)^2 \right) \times 8 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8248384 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (8) + \sqrt{38^4} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{2 \times 8}}} \right) \\
 8258466 &:= \left(\left((6^6) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left((8+5)^2 + 8 \right) \right) \\
 8265617 &:= \left(\left((7+16) \times \sqrt{5^6} \right)^2 - 8 \right) \\
 8274312 &:= \left(\left(\left(2^{1+\sqrt{3^4}} - 7 \right)^2 \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 8274344 &:= \left(\left(-4 - \left(\left(4^{3+\sqrt{4}} - 7 \right)^2 \right) \right) \times (-8) \right) \\
 8290304 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{030}}} \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 2^8 \right) \\
 8294408 &:= \sqrt{80^4} \times (4 \times 9)^2 + 8 \\
 8297856 &:= \left(6^{-5+8} \times \sqrt{(7+9-2)^8} \right) \\
 8338377 &:= \left(\left(- \left((7^7) \right) \times \sqrt{3^8} - 33 \right) / (-8) \right) \\
 8356608 &:= \left(806 \times \sqrt{6^{5+3}} \right) \times 8 \\
 8359375 &:= \left(5^7 \right) \times \left((3+95) + \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) \\
 8365419 &:= \left(\left(91 + \left(\sqrt{4} \times 56 \right) \right)^3 - 8 \right) \\
 8384488 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{8^8} - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \sqrt{4^8} - 3 \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 8384528 &:= \left(\left(- \left((8 \times 2)^5 \right) - \sqrt{4} + (8^3) \right) \times (-8) \right) \\
 8385784 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(- \left((8^7) \right) + \sqrt{5^8} + \sqrt{3^8} \right) \right) \\
 8387942 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(\left(4^{\sqrt{9+7}} - (83) \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 8387944 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{4+9+7} - (83) \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 8388284 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(\left((8^{-2+8}) \times (-8) + \sqrt{3^8} \right) \right) \right) \\
 8388464 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(6 - \left((4^8) \times 8 - 3 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 8388588 &:= \left(\sqrt{8+8} \times \left(- \left(5 - \left((8 \times 8)^3 \times 8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8388597 &:= \left(\left((7+9)^5 \times \sqrt{8 \times 8} - (3+8) \right) \right) \\
 8388612 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}} + \left(\left(\sqrt{8+8}^{3+8} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8388614 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left((16^8) / (8^3) + 8 \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$8388619 := (\sqrt{9} + (((16^8) / (8^3)) + 8))$$

$$8388644 := (- (4) \times (((((\sqrt{4} + 6)^8) / (-8)) - \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}})))$$

$$8388782 := (2 \times (87 + (\sqrt{8 + 8^{3+8}})))$$

$$8388912 := ((2^{-1+\sqrt{9} \times 8}) + (8 \times 38))$$

$$8389784 := \left(- (4) \times \left(- ((8^7)) - \left(98 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$8394435 := ((5 \times ((3 \times 4)^4) - 9)) \times \sqrt{3^8}$$

$$8394784 := (- (4) \times (- ((8^7)) + ((\sqrt{4^9} \times (-3)) - 8)))$$

$$8396865 := ((5 \times (6^8)) + (- ((6 + 9)) \times \sqrt{3^8}))$$

$$8397475 := (- (5) \times ((- (7) + \sqrt{4^7}) - ((9 - 3)^8)))$$

$$8397568 := - ((\sqrt{8^6} + (- (5) \times (((7 - 9) \times 3)^8))))$$

$$8397865 := (- (5) \times (\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}} + ((7 - (9 - 3)^8))))$$

$$8397975 := (- (5) \times (\sqrt{7 \times 9 \times 7} - ((9 - 3)^8)))$$

$$8398035 := (- (5) \times (\sqrt{\sqrt{3^{08}}} - ((9 - 3)^8)))$$

$$8398095 := (5 \times (\sqrt{9} - ((0 \times 8) - ((9 - 3)^8))))$$

$$8398285 := (- (5) \times (((- ((8 - 2)^8)) - \sqrt{9}) - 38))$$

$$8398485 := (5 \times (((8 - \sqrt{4})^8) + \sqrt{(9/3)^8}))$$

$$8398592 := \left((2^9) - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}} \times (- ((9 - 3)^8)) \right) \right)$$

$$8398635 := (- (5) \times ((3 - (6^8)) - (\sqrt{9} \times 38)))$$

$$8398695 := (- (5) \times (- ((9 + (6^8))) - (\sqrt{9} \times 38)))$$

$$8398836 := (- (6) \times (((- (3) + \sqrt{8^8}) \times (- (9 \times 38))))$$

$$8399295 := (- (5) \times (((- ((9^2)) \times \sqrt{9}) - ((9 - 3)^8)))$$

$$8399765 := (- (5) \times (6 - ((7^{\sqrt{9}}) + ((9 - 3)^8))))$$

$$8399955 := (5 \times (((5^{\sqrt{9}}) \times \sqrt{9}) + ((9 - 3)^8)))$$

$$8418575 := (575 \times \sqrt{(8 - 1 + 4)^8})$$

$$8429472 := (((((2 \times 7) \times 4)^{\sqrt{9}}) - 2) \times 48)$$

$$8429657 := (- (7) + (((56^{\sqrt{9}}) + 2) \times 48))$$

$$8433224 := (((4 \times 22) \times 33)^{\sqrt{4}} + 8)$$

$$8436965 := (5 \times (((\sqrt{6^9/6} + 3)^{\sqrt{4}}) - 8))$$

$$8437599 := (9 \times (\sqrt{9} + (((5^7) \times 3) \times 4) + 8))$$

$$8437832 := \left(\left(\left(-2 - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}} \times (- (7^3)) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 8$$

$$8439592 := ((2 + (\sqrt{9} \times (593^{\sqrt{4}}))) \times 8)$$

$$8453499 := ((9/\sqrt{9}) \times (- (43 \times (5 - (4^8))))))$$

$$8454266 := (- (6) + (((6 - 2) + (4^5))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 8)$$

$$8454269 := - ((\sqrt{9} - (((6 - 2) + (4^5))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 8))$$

$$8454272 := (((\sqrt{2 \times 7 + 2} + (4^5))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 8)$$

$$8454464 := (((4 \times 6) + ((4 + (4^5))^{\sqrt{4}})) \times 8)$$

$$8457696 := (6^9 + (((6 \times 75)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (-8)))$$

$$8466336 := 6^3 \times (\sqrt{(3 \times 66)^4} - 8)$$

$$8467274 := (\sqrt{4} + (72 \times ((7^6) - 48)))$$

$$8469256 := (((- ((65^2)) - (- ((9^6)) \times \sqrt{4})) \times 8)$$

$$8470724 := (-4 - (- ((2 + 70)) \times (7^{-\sqrt{4}+8})))$$

$$8470728 := ((8 \times (2 + 7)) \times (07^{-\sqrt{4}+8}))$$

$$8477283 := (3 \times (((\sqrt{8^2} - ((7 \times 7)))^{-4+8})))$$

$$8483373 := (((3^7) \times 3) \times (- (3) + \sqrt{(8 - \sqrt{4})^8}))$$

$$8486944 := (- (4) \times (((\sqrt{4^9} + 6) \times (- (8^4)))) - 8))$$

$$8487364 := ((\sqrt{4} \times (6 \times ((37 - 8)^4))) - 8)$$

$$8488984 := ((\sqrt{4^8} + \sqrt{9}) \times (8 + ((8^4) \times 8)))$$

$$8489152 := (((2 \times 51)^{\sqrt{9}}) - \sqrt{8^4}) \times 8$$

$$8489664 := \sqrt{(\sqrt{4} \times 6)^6 \times (9 + 8)^{-\sqrt{4}+8}}$$

$$8489696 := (((6 + 96)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 8) + ((4 \times 8))$$

$$8496489 := - (((\sqrt{9^8} - \sqrt{4}) - (((6 \times 9)^4) - 8))))$$

$$8496495 := ((5 \times (9^4)) \times (- ((6 - 9)) + \sqrt{4^8}))$$

$$8499176 := - (((\sqrt{6^{7+1}} \times (\sqrt{9} - (9^4))) - 8))$$

$$8502336 := - ((6 \times 3) \times ((\sqrt{3^{20}} - 5) \times (-8)))$$

$$8545792 := ((2^9) \times ((7^5) - (\sqrt{4} \times 58)))$$

$$8564985 := (589 - 4) \times \sqrt{(6 + 5)^8}$$

$$8571554 := (\sqrt{4} \times (((5 \times 51) \times (7^5)) - 8))$$

$$8584684 := - (((((\sqrt{4^8} + 6) \times (\sqrt{4} - (8^5)))) + 8))$$

$$8588377 := (((7 \times 7)^3) \times (- (8) + \sqrt{(8 - 5)^8}))$$

$$8593486 := ((6 + (8 \times \sqrt{4})) \times (- ((3 + 9) - (5^8))))$$

$$8593554 := (\sqrt{4} - (((5 \times 5) - 3) \times (9 - (5^8))))$$

$$8593684 := (((4 - 8) - (6 \times 3)) \times (\sqrt{9} - (5^8)))$$

$$8593728 := ((8 + (2 \times 7)) \times ((- (3) / \sqrt{9}) + (5^8)))$$

$$8593742 := (2 \times (-4 - ((\sqrt{7-3} + 9) \times (- (5^8))))))$$

$$8593762 := (2 \times (6 - ((\sqrt{7-3} + 9) \times (- (5^8))))))$$

$$8593814 := (\sqrt{4} \times (- (1) - (- ((8 + 3)) \times (\sqrt{9} + (5^8))))))$$

$$8593948 := (((8 + \sqrt{4}) + (9 + 3)) \times (9 + (5^8)))$$

$$8596875 := (- (5) \times ((- (7) - ((8 + 6)^{\sqrt{9}})) \times \sqrt{5^8}))$$

$$8614125 := 5^{2+1} \times (\sqrt{41^6} - 8)$$

$$8617458 := ((- ((8^5)) + \sqrt{4}) \times (- (7) - \sqrt{\sqrt{16^8}}))$$

$$8617984 := (((4 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (7 + \sqrt{\sqrt{16^8}}))$$

$$8619939 := ((\sqrt{9} \times (39^{\sqrt{9}+1})) + (6^8))$$

$$8653959 := - (((\sqrt{9^{5+9}}) - ((3 + 5) \times (6^8))))$$

$$8659992 := ((2 + 9) \times (((\sqrt{9^9} \times 5) - 6) \times 8))$$

$$8677613 := \left(- (31) \times \left(- ((6^7)) + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{(7+6)^8}}} \right) \right)$$

$$8679424 := (((4 \times 2)^4) \times (\sqrt{9^7} - 68))$$

$$8679637 := (((((7 + 3)^6) + \sqrt{9}) \times 7) + (6^8))$$

$$8679679 := (((((\sqrt{9} + 7)^6) + 9) \times 7) + (6^8))$$

$$8688382 := (-2 - (- ((838 \times 8)) \times \sqrt{6^8}))$$

$$8693295 := (- (5) \times ((\sqrt{9} \times (2 - (3^9))) - (6^8)))$$

$$8693325 := (\sqrt{5^2} \times ((3 \times (3^9)) + (6^8)))$$

$$8749468 := \left(((86 \times (4 + 9))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}} \right)$$

$$8749552 := (2 \times (((\sqrt{5^{5+9}} - 4) \times (7 \times 8))))$$

$$8751645 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(5 + 4)^6} \times (1 \times 5) \right) \times \sqrt{7^8} \right)$$

$$8758935 := ((5 \times (3^9)) \times ((8 \times 5) + \sqrt{\sqrt{7^8}}))$$

$$8775546 := (((\sqrt{6^4} \times (5^5)) + 7) \times 78)$$

$$8781824 := \sqrt{4^{2 \times 8}} \times (18 \times 7 + 8)$$

$$8814589 := - (((((\sqrt{9} \times 8)^5) + ((4 - 1) - (8^8))))$$

$$8817984 := (((4 + 8)^9) \times 7) / \sqrt{1 \times 8^8}$$

$$8817992 := \left(\left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^9 \right) \times (-7) \right) / (- (1 \times 8)) \right) + 8$$

$$8823667 := ((- ((7^6)) \times (6 - (3^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}}))) - 8)$$

$$8846496 := \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-4 - ((6+4) \times \sqrt{8^8})) \right)$$

$$8852976 := \left((-((6^7)) \times (\sqrt{9} - ((2^5) \times 8))) / 8 \right)$$

$$8853694 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 9)^6 \right) - 3 \right) \times 5 \right) - \sqrt{8^8} \right)$$

$$8854692 := \left(\left(\left((2^9) + 6 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 8} \right) \right)$$

$$8863744 := \left(\sqrt{(4 \times 4)^7} \times (- (3 - (68 \times 8))) \right)$$

$$8912896 := \left(((6 \times 9) + 82) \times \left((1 + \sqrt{9})^8 \right) \right)$$

$$8928144 := \left(\left((4 + (41 \times 8))^2 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right)$$

$$8938269 := \sqrt{9} \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(6 \times 2)^{8 \times 3}} - \sqrt{9^8}} \right)$$

$$8943748 := \left((8 - (4 \times (7^3))) \times (4 - \sqrt{9^8}) \right)$$

$$8946126 := \left((621 \times 6) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{49^8}} \right)$$

$$8957664 := \left(- (4) \times \left(\left((6 \times \sqrt{6^{7+5}}) - 9 \right) \times (-8) \right) \right)$$

$$8957864 := \left(\left(\left(- (4) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} \right) - 5 \right) \right) - 9 \right) \times (-8) \right)$$

$$8957942 := \left(- (2) + \left(\left(\left((4 \times \sqrt{9})^7 \right) / (- (5 - 9)) \right) - 8 \right) \right)$$

$$8957943 := -\sqrt{3^4} + \sqrt{9^7 \times (5 + \sqrt{9})^8}$$

$$8957944 := \sqrt{(4 \times 4 \times 9)^7} / (-5 + 9) - 8$$

$$8957945 := -5 - \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{9^7 \times (5 + \sqrt{9})^8}$$

$$8957946 := \left(- (6) + \left(\left((4 \times \sqrt{9})^7 \right) / ((5 - 9) + 8) \right) \right)$$

$$8957947 := -7 + \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{9^7 \times (5 + \sqrt{9})^8}$$

$$8957948 := \left(\left((8^4) \times \sqrt{9^7} \right) - ((5 - 9) + 8) \right)$$

$$8957949 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left((4 \times \sqrt{9})^7 \right) / ((5 - 9) + 8) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$8957951 := -1^5 + \sqrt{9^7 \times (5 + \sqrt{9})^8}$$

$$8957964 := 4^6 \times \sqrt{9^7} - 5 + 9 + 8$$

$$8957968 := \left(\sqrt{8^6 \times 9^7} + 5 - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 8$$

$$8957973 := 3 \times 7 + \sqrt{9^7 \times (5 + \sqrt{9})^8}$$

$$8957976 := \left(\left(\left((6^7) / \sqrt{9} \right) \times (- (7 + 5)) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-8)$$

$$8957984 := 4 \times \left(\left((8 + \sqrt{9 + 7})^5 \right) \times 9 + 8 \right)$$

$$8964513 := \left(\left(3 \times \left((1 + 5) \times \sqrt{4} \right)^6 \right) + \sqrt{9^8} \right)$$

$$8964864 := \left(\left(- (4) \times \sqrt{6^8} \right) - 4 \right) \times \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) \times (-8) \right)$$

$$8975448 := \left((8 + (4 \times 4)) \times 57 \right) \times \sqrt{9^8}$$

$$8975496 := \left((6 - (- ((9^4) \times 57)) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \times 8$$

$$8978843 := \left((3 + (4^8)) \times \left((8 \times 7) + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \right)$$

$$8984421 := \left(- ((1 - 24)) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((8 - \sqrt{9})^8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$8992364 := 4 \times \left(6 + (3 + 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}$$

$$8994816 := 61 \times 8^4 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{(9 - \sqrt{9})^8}}$$

$$8996568 := \left(\left((8 \times ((6 - (5^6)) \times 9)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-8) \right)$$

$$8997369 := \left(\left((9^6) - (3^7) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (9 + 8)$$

$$8998831 := \left(\left((13 \times (8 + 8))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right)$$

$$8998848 := \left(8 \times \left(\left((4 \times 8) + (8 \times 9) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \right) \right)$$

$$8998888 := \left(\left(\left((8 + 8) + 88 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$8998912 := \left(- \left(\left((2 + 1) - 98 \right) - 9 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8$$

$$8998915 := \left(\left(\left((5 + 1)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)$$

$$8998917 := \left(\left(\left((7 + 19) \times 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9} \right) + 8 \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8998923 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left((3 - 29) \times 8 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{9} \right) + 8 \right) \\
 8998929 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (9 + 8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8998936 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^3+9}} - 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times (-8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8998944 &:= \left(\left(-4 - \left((4 \times ((9 + 8) + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times (-8) \right) \\
 8998984 &:= \left(\left(\left((4 \times 8) + (9 \times 8) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} + 9 \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 8998993 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(- \left((3 - 9) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \right) \\
 8999488 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left((8 \times (4 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} + (9 \times 8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8999919 &:= \left(\left(\left((91 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 9 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \\
 8999928 &:= \left(\left(\left((8 + 2)^{9-\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 9 \right) - (9 \times 8) \right) \\
 8999973 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 + 7)^{9-\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \right) \\
 8999974 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left((7 + \sqrt{9})^{9-\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times (-9) \right) - 8 \right) \\
 8999991 &:= \left(\left(\left((1 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 9 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \\
 8999992 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(- (2) + \sqrt{9} \right) + 99 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 9 \right) - 8 \\
 8999997 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left((7 + \sqrt{9})^{9-\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 9 \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) \right) \\
 9058977 &:= \left(\left((7^7) \times (\sqrt{9} + 8) \right) - ((5 - 09)) \right) \\
 9068724 &:= \left(42 \times \left(- (78) + (60^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \\
 9068976 &:= \left((6 \times 7) \times \left(- ((9 \times 8)) + (60^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \\
 9079275 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(- (7) - \left(- ((2 \times (9 - 70))^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9084137 &:= \left((731^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (8 + 09) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9094545 &:= \left(\left(- (5) - \left((\sqrt{4} \times 5)^4 \right) \right) \times (-909) \right) \\
 9129329 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 2 \right)^3 - (9 - 2) \right)^{\sqrt{1 \times 9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9129367 &:= \left(\left(- \left((7 - (6^3)) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (2 \times 19) \right) \\
 9144578 &:= \left(\left(\left((8 \times 7) \times 54 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 1 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9148592 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9 - 5} \times (84 - 1) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9148688 &:= \left(- ((8 + 8)) \times \left(- (6) - \left((84 - 1)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9150585 &:= \left(- ((5 \times 8)) + (50 + 5)^{1+\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 9150617 &:= \left(- ((7 + 1)) + (60 - 5)^{1+\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 9150618 &:= \left(- ((8 - 1)) + (60 - 5)^{1+\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 9150624 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} / (-2) \right) + (60 - 5)^{1+\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 9150625 &:= \left(\left((5 \times 2) \times 6 - 05 \right)^{1+\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 9150634 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (3 - 60) \right) \right)^{5-1} \right) + 9 \right) \\
 9150645 &:= \left((5 \times 4) + (60 - 5)^{1+\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 9150667 &:= \left((7 \times 6) + (60 - 5)^{1+\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 9178638 &:= \left(- (83) \times \left(6 - \left((8 \times (7 - 1))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9181203 &:= \left(\left((302^{\sqrt{1+8}}) + 1 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9194653 &:= \left(\left((35 - 6)^4 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + (1 + 9) \right) \right) \\
 9229447 &:= \left(\left((7^4) \times \left(\left((4^{\sqrt{9}}) - 2 \right)^2 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9237844 &:= \left(-4 + \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} - 8 \right) \right)^7 \times 3 \right) \times (2 + 9) \\
 9237888 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(8 - \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}} \right)^7 \right) \times (3 \times (2 + 9)) \right) \right) \\
 9237921 &:= \left(\left(- (1) - \left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^7 \right) \right) \times \left(- (3 \times (2 + 9)) \right) \right) \\
 9246857 &:= \left(\left((7 \times 5) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{8^6} + \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9246875 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- (7) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{8^6} + \sqrt{4} \right)^2 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$9253764 := \left(\left(\left((46 - 7)^3 \right) \times 52 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9259846 := \left(\left(\left(\left(- (6) \times (4 - (8^{\sqrt{9}})) \right) \right) - 5 \right)^2 - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9260744 := \left(- \left((4^4) \right) + \left((70 \times 6) / 2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$9260995 := \left(- (5) + \left((99 + 06) \times 2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$9277464 := \left(\left((46 \times 4) \times (7^{7-2}) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9282243 := \left(\left(\left(3 + \left((42^2) - 8 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9282325 := \left((5^2) \times \left((3 + 2) + 8 \right)^{2 + \sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$9289742 := \left(\left(- (2) + \left(- \left((4^7) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \right) \times (2 - 9) \right)$$

$$9289749 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(- \left((4^7) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \right) \times (- (2 - 9)) \right)$$

$$9293797 := \left(79 \times \left((7^{-3+9}) - (2 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \right)$$

$$9294675 := \left(\left(- \left((5 + (7^6)) \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left((9^2) \right) \right) \right) + 9$$

$$9304325 := \left(- (5) \times \left(2 - \left((3 \times 40) + 3 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9304335 := \left(5 \times \left(\left((3/3) + 40 \right) \times 3 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$9304345 := \left(5 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((3 \times 40) + 3 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9304365 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- (6) - \left((3 \times 40) + 3 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9307656 := \left(\left((6^5) \times 6 \right) + \left((70 \times 3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9326943 := \left(\left(\left((3 - \sqrt{4^9}) \times (-6) \right)^2 \right) + \left((3 \times 9) \right) \right)$$

$$9329739 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left((3 \times 79) \times 2 \times (3^9) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9329742 := \left(\sqrt{\left((2 + 4) \times 79 \right)^2 \times (3^9)} \right)$$

$$9329796 := \left(- (6) \times \left(- (9) + \left(\sqrt{79^2} \times (-3^9) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9336387 := \left(- \left(\left(7 - \left((83 + 63)^3 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9336408 := \left(\left((8 + (046 \times 3))^3 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9336414 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(146^{\sqrt{3 \times 3}} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9337437 := \left(\left(\left((7^3) + \left((\sqrt{4} \times 73)^3 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9348696 := \left(6^9 - \left((6 \times ((8 + 4) + 3))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9349425 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left((2/\sqrt{4}) + (94) \right) \times \left(- (3^9) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9354352 := \left((2 + 5) \times \left(34^{-5+3 \times \sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9365376 := \left(6 \times \left(\left(\left((7^3) + 5 \right) / (6 - 3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9374985 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((8 \times \left((9 - 4)^7 \right) \times 3 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9375585 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((8 \times \left((5 + (5^7)) \times 3 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9379251 := \left(\left((1 + 52)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (7 \times 3) \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9379359 := \left(9 \times \left(\left((53^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 7 \right) + (3 + 9) \right) \right)$$

$$9393922 := \left(\left(\left(- (2) + \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^3 - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^3 \right) - 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9393925 := \left(\left(\left(- (5) + \left((2 \times \sqrt{9})^3 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left((3 - 9) \right) \right)$$

$$9393928 := \left(\left(\left((8 \times (29 - 3)) + \sqrt{9} \right)^3 - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9393931 := \left((1 + ((39 \times 3) + 93))^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$9393934 := \left(\left(\left(4 + \left(- ((3 - 9))^3 - 9 \right) \right)^3 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9418761 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{16^7}} \times 8 \right) - 1 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9432423 := \left(- \left((32^4) \right) + \sqrt{23^4} \right) \times (-9)$$

$$9432549 := \left(9 \times \left(\left((4^5)^2 - 3 \right) - \sqrt{4^9} \right) \right)$$

$$9436842 := \left(- (2) + \left(- (4) \times \left(- \left((8^6) \right) + \sqrt{3^4} \right) \right) \right) \times 9$$

$$9436844 := \left(- (4) \times \left(4 + \left(- \left((8^6) \right) + \sqrt{3^4} \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9436884 := \left(- \left((4 + \left((8 - (8^6)) \times (3 \times 4) \right)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9436888 := \left(- (8) - \left(\left((8 - (8^6)) \times (3 \times 4) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9436914 := \left(\left((4^{1+9}) - \left(- (6) \times \left(- (3) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9436944 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left((4^9) - 6 \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \times (-4) \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9436947 := \left(- \left(\left(7 - \left(\left(\left(4^9 \right) - 6 \right) \times 3 \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9437158 := \left(- (8) + \left(\left(\left((5-1)^{7+3} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9437166 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- (6) \times \left(\left((1+7)^3 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9437175 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(5 - \left(\left((7+1)^7 \right) + 3 \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9437181 := \left(\left(- (1) + \left(\left(8^{-1+7} \right) \times (3 \times 4) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9437193 := \left((3 \times \sqrt{9}) \times \left(1 + \left((7-3) \times (4^9) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9437196 := \left(- (6) + \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right)^{7+3} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9437199 := \left(\left(9 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right)^{7+3} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9437202 := \left(\left(\left((2+02)^{7+3} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9437238 := \left(\left(\left(8 + (32^{7-3}) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9437248 := \left(\sqrt{8^4} - \left(\left(\left((2^7)^3 \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-9) \right) \right)$$

$$9437283 := \left(\left((3+8) + \left(\left((2^7)^3 \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9437294 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((9+27) \times (3 + (4^9)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9437445 := \left(\left(\sqrt{5^4} + \left((4^{7+3}) + 4 \right) \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9437454 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^5} + (4^{7+3}) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9437463 := \left(\left(\sqrt{3^6} + \left((4^{7+3}) + 4 \right) \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9437913 := \left(\left(\left((3+1)^{\sqrt{9}+7} \right) + \left((3^4) \right) \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9439479 := \left(\sqrt{9^7} + \left(\left((4^9) + 3 \right) \times 4 \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9439488 := \left(\left(\left((8 \times 8) + (4^9) \right) \times (3 \times 4) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9439668 := \left(\left(\left(\left((8^6) + 69 \right) \times 3 \right) \times 4 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9445968 := \left(\left(\left(\left((8^6) + \sqrt{9^5} \right) \times 4 \right) + 4 \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9446559 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (5^5) \right) - \left(\sqrt{6^4} \times \left(- (4^9) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9447815 := \left(5 \times \left(\left(18^{7-\sqrt{4}} \right) + \left((4-9) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9448848 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(8-\sqrt{4})^8} + \left((8 \times 4)^4 \right) \right) \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9449464 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6 \times \sqrt{4^9}) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - (4 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \right)$$

$$9449485 := \left(\left((58 \times (49+4))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 9 \right)$$

$$9452696 := \left(6^9 - \left((6+2) \times (5^{\sqrt{49}}) \right) \right)$$

$$9452883 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(3+8)^8}} \times \left(- (2) + (5^{\sqrt{49}}) \right) \right)$$

$$9454976 := \left((6^7) + \left((9-\sqrt{4}) \times (5 \times (4^9)) \right) \right)$$

$$9455616 := \left(\left(\left((616 \times 5) - 5 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 9 \right)$$

$$9455625 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(5 \times 2)^6} + ((5 \times 5)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9463571 := \left(- \left(\left((17 \times 5)^3 \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{6^4}} \right) \right)$$

$$9464967 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{7^6} \times 9 \right) + \left((4^{6+4}) \right) \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9469952 := \left((2^{5 \times \sqrt{9}}) + \left((96^4) / 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9474084 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (8 \times \sqrt{04^7}) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9482688 := \left(- \left((8+8) \right) \times \left((6^2) - (84^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$9483248 := \left((8 \times \sqrt{4}) \times \left((2-3) + (84^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$9483254 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- (5) + \left((2^3) \times (84^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9483264 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((6-2) + 38 \right) \times 4 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$9483267 := \left(\left(\left(\left((7 \times 6) \times 2 \right)^3 \right) \times 8 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$9483312 := \left((2^{1+3}) \times \left(3 + (84^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$9483375 := \left(57 \times \left(\left(- \left((3 \times 3) \right) + \sqrt{8^4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9484992 := \left(2 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9^4}} - 84^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9484994 := \sqrt{(4 \times 9)^9} + \sqrt{4} - 84^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9484996 := \left(\left((6^{\sqrt{9 \times 9}}) + 4 \right) - (84^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$9485686 := \left(- \left(\left((6^8) / 6 \right) \right) + \left((5^{8+\sqrt{4}}) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9486391 := \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(-((1-9))^3 \right) \times 6 \right) + 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 9 \right)$$

$$9487433 := \left(\left(\left((33^4) + 7 \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{84}} \right) + 9 \right)$$

$$9489393 := \left((3^{9+3}) - \left(- \left((9 \times 8^4) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9492543 := \left(\left(\left((3 + (4^5))^2 \right) \times 9 \right) - (\sqrt{4} \times 9) \right)$$

$$9492549 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} + (4^5))^2 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - 4 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9492561 := \left(\left(\left(\left((\sqrt{16}^{\sqrt{52}}) + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9494523 := \left(\left(\left(- \left((32 - (5^4)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9502664 := - \left((\sqrt{46^6} + \left(- \left((20^5) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)) \right)$$

$$9517671 := \left(- (17) \times \left(\left(- \left((6^7) \right) \times \sqrt{-1+5} \right) + 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9517824 := - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left((2-8)^7 \right) \right)) - \left((1+5)^9 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9521875 := \left(- \left((5^7) \right) - \left(- \left((8+12)^5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9525965 := \left(5 \times \left(\left((6 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \right) + (25^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$9526328 := \left(- \left((82^3) \right) + \left((6^{-2+5})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9528128 := \left(\left(\left((8+2) \times 18 \right) + (2^5) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$9529275 := \left(\left((5 \times 7)^2 \right) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times 2)^5 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9529473 := \left(\left(\left((3 \times \sqrt{74})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (2^5) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9529479 := \left(\left((9 \times (7^{\sqrt{4 \times 9}})) - (2 \times 5) \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9529554 := \left(\left(\left(\left((4^5) + 5 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^2 \right) - (5 \times \sqrt{9}) \right)$$

$$9529569 := \left(\left(\left((9 \times 6) - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)^{-2+5} \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9529577 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times (7^5)) \right) \times (9^2) \right) + 5 \right) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$9529677 := \left(\left(- \left((7 + ((7^6) \times 9)) \right) \right) - \sqrt{25} \right) \times (-9)$$

$$9529694 := \left(\left((\sqrt{49^6}) \times (9^2) \right) + (5^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$9529697 := \left(\left(\left((7 \times \sqrt{9})^6 \right) / 9 \right) + \sqrt{2^{5+9}} \right)$$

$$9529745 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\left((4^7) + ((9 \times 2)^5) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9559694 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left((9^6) \times 9 \right) - (5^5) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9559794 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((9^7) - \left((9-5)^5 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9564696 := \left((6 \times \left((9^6) - 4 \right) - 65) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9565479 := \left(\left((9^7) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - \left((56-5) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9565792 := \left(2 \times \left(\left((9^7) - 5 \right) - 65 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9565794 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times (9^7)) - \left((5+6) + 5 \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$9565797 := \left(\left(\left(- (7) + (\sqrt{9^{7+5}}) \right) \times 6 \right) - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9565813 := \left(\left((3^{1 \times 8+5}) \times 6 \right) - (5^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$9565869 := \left(\left(\left(\left((9^6) - 8 \right) + 5 \right) \times 6 \right) - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9565893 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}^{8+5}} \right) \times 6 \right) - (5 \times 9) \right)$$

$$9565898 := \left(\left((8 - (\sqrt{9^{8+5}})) \times (-6) \right) + (5 + \sqrt{9}) \right)$$

$$9565899 := \left(\left((9 - (\sqrt{9^{8+5}})) \times (-6) \right) + (5 \times \sqrt{9}) \right)$$

$$9565923 := \left(\left(\left((3^2) \times ((9^5) \times 6) \right) - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9565926 := \left(- \left(\left((6/2)^{9+5} \right) - 6 \right) \right) \times \left(- (5) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9565936 := \left((6 \times \left((3^{9+5}) - (6-5) \right)) / \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9565938 := \left(- \left((8 \times (3^{9+5})) \right) \right) / \left(- \left((6-5) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9565942 := \left(2 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((9^{5+6+5-9}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9565953 := 3^{5+\sqrt{9}+5} \times 6 + 5 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9565983 := \left(\left(\left((3^8) \times \sqrt{9^5} \right) \times 6 \right) + (5 \times 9) \right)$$

$$9565986 := \left(- (6) \times \left(- (8) + \left(- \left((9^{5+6-5}) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9565992 := \left(2 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9^{9+5}}) + ((6 \times 5)) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9565994 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times (\sqrt{9^{9+5}})) + (65-9) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9566279 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(9^7 \right) \times 2 \right) + \sqrt{6^6} \right) + \left(5^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9566469 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(9^6 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - (6 - 65) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 9567234 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(3^{2 \times 7} \right) \right) \right) + \left(6^{-5+9} \right) \right) \\
 9567375 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(5 \times 7 \right) \times \left(3^7 \right) \right) - 6 \right) \times \left(5^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9572499 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(27^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9576448 &:= \left(\left(8^4 \right) \times \left(\left(467 \times 5 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 9578125 &:= \left(\left(\left(5 \times 2 \right)^{-1+8} \right) - \left(75^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9585216 &:= \left(\left(\left(61^2 \right) - \sqrt{5^8} \right)^{5-\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 9586888 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(8^8 \right) \times 8 \right) \right) + \sqrt{6^8} \right) / \left(- (5 + 9) \right) \\
 9594795 &:= \left(\left(- (5) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right)^4 \right) \right) \times (-959) \right) \\
 9599744 &:= \left(- \left(4^4 \right) + \left(\left(- (7) + \left(9 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^5 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9599748 &:= \left(\left(- (84) + \left(\left(- (7) + \left(9 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9599872 &:= \left(- \left(2^7 \right) + \left(\left(\left(8 + \sqrt{9} \right) + 9 \right)^5 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9599985 &:= \left(\left(- (5) + \left(\left(\left(8 + \sqrt{9} \right) + \sqrt{9 \times 9} \right)^5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9599994 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(99/9 \right) + 9 \right)^5 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9599995 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(\left(99/9 \right) + 9 \right)^5 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9607875 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \left(\left(7^8 \right) - 70 \right) - 6 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9609375 &:= \left(\left(5^7 \right) \times \left(- \left(3 + 90 \right) \right) + \left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9611875 &:= \left(\left(5 \times 7 \right) \times \left(81 - 16 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 9618944 &:= \left(\left(\left(4^{\sqrt{4 \times \sqrt{9}}} \right) \times \left(- (8 - 1) \right) \right) + 6^9 \right) \\
 9624424 &:= \left(- (4) \times \left(- 2 - \left(\left(\left(4^4 \right) / 2 \right) + 6 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9626752 &:= \left(\left(2 \times 5 \right)^7 - \left(\left(6 \times 2 \right) \times 6 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 9628899 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} + 8 \right) \times \left(82 \times 6 - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9645696 &:= \left(6^9 - \left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{(5 \times 4)^6} \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 9653449 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(9 + 4 \right) \times \left(4 - \left(3^5 \right) \right) \right) \right)^{6/\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 9653584 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(8 - \left(\left(\left(5 + 3 \right) + 5 \right)^6 - 9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9653594 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(9 - \left(\left(\left(5 + 3 \right) + 5 \right)^6 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 9653612 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(\left(\left(1 \times 6 \right) \times 3 \right) - 5 \right)^6 - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 9653614 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(1 + \left(\left(6 \times 3 \right) - 5 \right)^6 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 9653615 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{5-1} \times \left(\left(6 \times 3 \right) - 5 \right)^6 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9653616 &:= \left(- \left(\left(6 \times \left(1 - \left(\left(6 \times 3 \right) - 5 \right)^6 \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9653621 &:= \left(\left(1 \times 2 \right) \times \left(\left(6 \times 3 \right) - 5 \right)^6 + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9653622 &:= \left(- 2 - \left(2 \times \left(- \left(\left(6 \times 3 \right) - 5 \right)^6 - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9653624 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\left(2 + 63 \right) / 5 \right)^6 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 9653644 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(4 + \left(\left(\left(6 \times 3 \right) - 5 \right)^6 + 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 9656964 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(- \left(\left(6 - \left(9 \times 6^5 \right) \right) \times 69 \right) \right) \right) \\
 9657792 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(2 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^7 \right) / \left(7 - 5 \right) \right) \times 69 \right) \\
 9663344 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(4^4 \right) - 3 \right) \right) + \left(\left(- (3) + \sqrt{6^6} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9663457 &:= \left(- \left(\left(7 \times 5 \right) \times 4 \right) + \left(\left(- (3) + \sqrt{6^6} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9663489 &:= \left(- \left(9 \times (8 + 4) \right) + \left(\left(- (3) + \sqrt{6^6} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9663497 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\left(7 + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - \left(\left(- (3) + \sqrt{6^6} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9663527 &:= \left(- \left(\left(7 \times 2 \right) \times 5 \right) + \left(\left(- (3) + \sqrt{6^6} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9663528 &:= \left(- \left(\left(8^2 \right) + 5 \right) + \left(\left(- (3) + \sqrt{6^6} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9663546 &:= \left(- \left(6 + 45 \right) + \left(\left(- (3) + \sqrt{6^6} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9663549 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 45 \right) - \left(\left(- (3) + \sqrt{6^6} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$9663557 := \left(- \left(((7 \times 5) + 5 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663566 := \left(- \left(((6 \times 6) - 5 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663572 := \left(((2 - 7) \times 5 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$9663574 := \left(- \left(((4 \times 7) - 5 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663579 := \left(- \left((9 \times (7 - 5)) \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663582 := \left(- \left(((2 + 8) + 5 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663583 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} + \left(5 - \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9663586 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}}} + \left(5 - \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9663587 := \left(- \left(((7 + 8) - 5 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663588 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{8+8} + 5 \right) - \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9663589 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} + \left(5 - \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9663591 := \left(- \left(((1^9) + 5 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663592 := \left(\left((-2 + \sqrt{9}) \times (-5) \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663593 := \left(\left((3/\sqrt{9}) - 5 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663594 := - \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}} \right) - 5 \right) - \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9663597 := \left(((7 \times 9) + (5 \times (36 - 6)) \right)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9663598 := \left(\left(- \left((8 - 9) \right)^5 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663599 := \left(\left((-9/\sqrt{9}) + 5 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663603 := \left(\left((3 \times 0) + 6 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663627 := \left(\left((7 - 2) \times 6 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663633 := \left(\left((3 + 3) \times 6 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663661 := \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{16^6}} + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663669 := \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{6^6}) \right)^3 \right) + \sqrt{6^6/9} \right)$$

$$9663687 := \left(\left((7 + 8) \times 6 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663853 := \left(\left(- \left((3 - 5) \right)^8 \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9663937 := \left(\left((7^3) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((-3 + \sqrt{6^6})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9672471 := \left(-1 - \left((74^{\sqrt{2+7}}) - 6^9 \right) \right)$$

$$9672474 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left((74^{\sqrt{2+7}}) - 6^9 \right) \right)$$

$$9684464 := \left(-4 - \left((6 \times (\sqrt{4} + (4^8))) - 6^9 \right) \right)$$

$$9684492 := \left(\left((2 \times \sqrt{9}) \times (\sqrt{4} - (4^8)) \right) + 6^9 \right)$$

$$9684696 := \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) - \left((6 \times (4^8)) - 6^9 \right) \right)$$

$$9688734 := - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times ((3 \times 7)^{\sqrt{8+8}})) - 6^9 \right) \right)$$

$$9694692 := \left((2 \times ((9^6) - (4^9)) \times 6) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9694845 := \left(\left(-5 - \left((\sqrt{4} + 8)^4 \right) \right) \times (-969) \right)$$

$$9734696 := \left(6^9 - \left((6 + 4)^3 \times (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$9735776 := \left(\left((6^7) - (7^5) \right) \times 37 + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9737848 := \left(\left(-8 + \left((\sqrt{4} + 8)^7 \right) \right) - \left(-((3 - 7)^9) \right) \right)$$

$$9745145 := \left(-5 \times \left((4^{1+5}) - \left(-((\sqrt{4} - 7)^9) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9745599 := - \left(\left((\sqrt{9^9} - \left((5^5)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) + (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$9745936 := \left(- \left((6 + (3^9)) \right) + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}^{7+\sqrt{9}}} \right) \right)$$

$$9745939 := \left(- \left((\sqrt{9} + (3^9)) \right) + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}^{7+\sqrt{9}}} \right) \right)$$

$$9753961 := \left(- \left((16 \times (9^3)) \right) + (5^{7+\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$9756364 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{(4 \times 6 - 3)^6} - (5^{7+\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$9756955 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((5^9) - 6 \right) + ((5+7)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$9757856 := - \left(\left(\left(6\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) - (7 + (5^{7+\sqrt{9}})) \right) \right)$$

$$9758983 := - \left(\left((\sqrt{3^8} + \sqrt{9^8}) - (5^{7+\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$9759217 := \left(- ((712 \times 9)) + (5^{7+\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$9759362 := \left(2 \times \left(((6/3) + (9 \times 5))^{\sqrt{7+9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9759793 := - \left(\left(\left((- (3) - (\sqrt{9} \times (-7)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (5^{7+\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$9763955 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(((5^9) + 3) + 6 \right) + (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$9765247 := \left(\left((7 - \sqrt{4})^{2 \times 5} \right) - (((6 \times 7) \times 9)) \right)$$

$$9765375 := \left((5^{7+3}) - (\sqrt{5^6} \times (- (7 - 9))) \right)$$

$$9765439 := \left((- (93) \times \sqrt{4}) + (5^{-6+7+9}) \right)$$

$$9765499 := \left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{9}) - \sqrt{4} \right)^5 - ((6 \times 7) \times \sqrt{9}) \right)$$

$$9765529 := \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + 2)^{5+5} \right) - ((6 \times (7 + 9))) \right)$$

$$9765545 := \left((\sqrt{5^{4 \times 5}}) + (((5 - 6) - 79)) \right)$$

$$9765552 := \left((\sqrt{25}^{5+5}) + (6 - 79) \right)$$

$$9765554 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(((5 \times 5)^5) + 6 \right) - 79 \right)$$

$$9765555 := \left((((5^5) \times (5^5)) - 67) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9765561 := \left((((1 - 6))^{5+5} - 67) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9765574 := \left(\left(((\sqrt{4} - 7) \times (-5))^5 \right) - ((6 \times 7) + 9) \right)$$

$$9765589 := \left(\left(((\sqrt{9} - 8) \times (-5))^5 \right) - (6^{-7+9}) \right)$$

$$9765592 := \left(\left((2 + \sqrt{9})^{5+5} \right) - ((6 \times 7) - 9) \right)$$

$$9765595 := \left(\left((5^9) \times 5 \right) - \sqrt{(5 \times 6)^{-7+9}} \right)$$

$$9765598 := \left(\left((8 - \sqrt{9})^{5+5} \right) - 6 \right) + (- (7) \times \sqrt{9}) \right)$$

$$9765619 := \left(\left(- (\sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{16}} \right) + (5^{-6+7+9}) \right)$$

$$9765626 := \left((\sqrt{6^2}/6) + (5^{-6+7+9}) \right)$$

$$9765634 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 3)^{6+5+6-7} \right) + 9 \right)$$

$$9765641 := \left(\left((1 + (4 \times 6))^5 \right) + (6 + 7) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9765649 := \left(\left((9 \times \sqrt{4}) + 6 \right) + (5^{-6+7+9}) \right)$$

$$9765652 := \left(\sqrt{(2 - 5)6} + (5^{-6+7+9}) \right)$$

$$9765655 := \left((\sqrt{5 \times 5} \times 6) + (5^{-6+7+9}) \right)$$

$$9765667 := \left((7 \times \sqrt{6 \times 6}) + (5^{-6+7+9}) \right)$$

$$9765685 := \left((5^{(8-6) \times 5}) + (- (6) \times (- (7) - \sqrt{9})) \right)$$

$$9765694 := \left(\left((- (\sqrt{4}) + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}})^5 \right) + (6 + (7 \times 9)) \right)$$

$$9765695 := \left(((5^{9+6-5}) + 67) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9765889 := \left((\sqrt{9} \times 88) + (5^{-6+7+9}) \right)$$

$$9765945 := \left((5 \times (4^{\sqrt{9}})) + (5^{-6+7+9}) \right)$$

$$9765952 := \left(- \left(((2 - (5^9)) \times 5) + 6 \right) + (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$9765954 := \left(- \left(((4 - (5^9)) \times 5) - 6 \right) + (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$9765955 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(((5^9) + 56) + 7 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9765956 := \left(- \left((6 - ((5^9) \times 5) - 6) \right) + (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$9765959 := \left(- \left((9 - (5^{9-5+6})) \right) + (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$9765974 := \left(\left(((4 \times 7) - \sqrt{9})^5 \right) + 6 \right) + (7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right)$$

$$9765975 := \left((5^{7+\sqrt{9}}) + (- (5) \times (- (67) - \sqrt{9})) \right)$$

$$9766285 := \left((5^{8+2}) + (66 \times (7 + \sqrt{9})) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9766915 &:= \left(\left(\left(5^{1+9} \right) - 6 \right) + \left(6^{\sqrt{7+9}} \right) \right) \\
 9767955 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\left(5^9 \right) + (7 \times 67) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9779345 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 3 \right)^9 \right) + \left((7+7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9784355 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(5^5 \right) + 3 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - \left(87 / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 9786681 &:= \left(- \left(\left(1 + \left((8+6) \times \left(6 - \left(8^7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9786682 &:= \left(\left(2 - \left((8+6) \times \left(6 - \left(8^7 \right) \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9786709 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((0-7) \times 6 \right) \times \left(8^7 \right) \right) \right) / (-9) \right) \\
 9792916 &:= \left(\left(\left(61^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(2 \times \left(9^7 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9794432 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(23^4 \right) \times \left((4-9) \times 7 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9795394 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{(4+9)^{3+5}} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9796423 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^2 \right) + 4 \right) \times \left(- \left((6-97)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9796449 &:= \left((9+4) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(- \left((6-97)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9797615 &:= 5 \times \left(1 + \left(6^7 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 7 + 9 \right) \\
 9797651 &:= -1 + 5 \times \left(6^7 - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 7 - \sqrt{9} \\
 9797652 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{25} \times \left(\left(- \left(6^7 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-7) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \\
 9797653 &:= \left(\left(35 \times \left(\left(6^7 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left((7-9) \right) \right) \\
 9797654 &:= -4 + 5 \times \left(6^7 - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 7 + \sqrt{9} \\
 9797655 &:= \left(\left(5 + \left(- \left(\left(5 \times \left(6^7 \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(- (7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 9797675 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\left(7 \times \left(\left(6^7 \right) - 9 \right) + 7 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9797694 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(\left((4-9) \times \left(6^7 \right) \right) + 9 \right) \times 7 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9797696 &:= 6^9 - 6^7 - \sqrt{(9+7)^{\sqrt{9}}} \\
 9797697 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(9 + \left(- \left(\left(6^7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9+7+9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9797745 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^7} \times (-7) \right) \times \sqrt{9^7} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 9812887 &:= \left(\sqrt{7^8} \times \left(\left(\left(8^{2+1} \right) \times 8 \right) - 9 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9819887 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{7^8} \times (-8) \right) - 9 \right) \times \left(1 - \left(8^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9821959 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(9 + \sqrt{5^{9+1}} \right)^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 9824768 &:= \left(\sqrt{8^6} \times \left(\left(\left(7^4 \right) - 2 \right) \times 8 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9824892 &:= \left(\sqrt{(2-9)^8} \times \left(-4 + \left((2 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9833165 &:= \left(\left(56^{1+3} \right) - \left((3+8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9834406 &:= \left(\left(\left((60-4)^4 \right) - \sqrt{3^8} \right) - 9 \right) \\
 9834445 &:= \left(\left(\left((54 + \sqrt{4})^4 \right) - (3 \times (8+9)) \right) \right) \\
 9834465 &:= \left(\left(\left(56^4 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) - \left((3 \times 8) + 9 \right) \right) \\
 9834467 &:= \left(\left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{64} \right)^4 \right) - (38-9) \right) \\
 9834469 &:= \left(\left(\left((9 \times 6) + \sqrt{4} \right)^4 \right) - \sqrt{3^8/9} \right) \\
 9834482 &:= \left(\left(\left(28 \times \sqrt{4} \right)^4 \right) + \left((3-8) - 9 \right) \right) \\
 9834488 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(- (8) + \sqrt{8^4} \right)^4 \right) - (3+8) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9834495 &:= \left(\left(\left((5+9) \times 4 \right)^4 \right) - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8/9}} \right) \right) \\
 9834498 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 \times (9 - \sqrt{4}) \right)^4 \right) + \left((3+8) - 9 \right) \right) \\
 9834537 &:= \left(\left(\left(7 \times (3+5) \right)^4 \right) + 38 \right) + \sqrt{9} \\
 9834543 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left((3+4) - \left(5^4 \right) \right) \right)^3 \right) / 8 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 9838752 &:= \left(\left(\left(2^5 \right) \times 7 \right) \times \sqrt{(8+3)^8 \times 9} \right) \\
 9843595 &:= \left(\left(5^9 \right) + \left(\left(53^4 \right) - 8 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \\
 9843759 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(5^7 \right) \times (34+8) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 9844758 &:= \left(8 + \left(5^7 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (4+8) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 9847556 &:= \left(\left(\left(6 + \left(\left(5^5 \right) + 7 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \left(8^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 9848384 &:= \left(- \left(\left(48^3 \right) \right) - \sqrt{8^4} \right) \times (-89)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$9849188 := \left((\sqrt{8^8} + 1) \times \left(\sqrt{(9 - \sqrt{4})^8} + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9859968 := \left((8 \times (6^{\sqrt{9}})) \times ((9 + \sqrt{5^8}) \times 9) \right)$$

$$9861696 := \left(6^9 - \left(\left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{16} + 8} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9882477 := \left(\left(\left((7^7) - 4 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{2 \times 8} + 8 \right) \right) + 9 \right)$$

$$9882516 := \left(\left((6 + 1)^{5+2} \right) \times \sqrt{(8 + 8) \times 9} \right)$$

$$9882774 := \left(\left((4 \times (7^7)) - (2 - 88) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9897696 := \left(6^9 - \left(6 \times \sqrt{(7 + \sqrt{9})^8 \times 9} \right) \right)$$

$$9900549 := \left((9^4) \times \left((500 + \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9919728 := \left((\sqrt{8^2} \times (7 \times 9)) \times (-1 + \sqrt{9^9}) \right)$$

$$9923847 := \left(\left((7 + ((48 \times 3) - 2))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9936179 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^7} - \left(\left(- \left((1 - (6^3)) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9938366 := \left(\left(- \left((6 - \left(\left((6^3) + 8 \right) - 3 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9938369 := \left(\left(\left(- \left((9 - \left(\left((6^3) + 8 \right) \right) \right)^3 - 9 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$9938375 := \left((5 + (7 \times (((3 \times 8) - 3) + 9)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$9938384 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^8} - (38 + 3) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} + 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9938987 := \left(\left((7 \times (8 + 9)^{8-3}) - 9 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$9939915 := \left(- \left((5 \times ((1 - 9) - 93)) \times \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right)$$

$$9939924 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left((2^9) - 9 \right) \right) \right) \times (3^9) \right) + 9 \right)$$

$$9952696 := \left(6^9 - \left(\left(\left((6^2) + 5 \right) + 9 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9959598 := \left(- \left((89 - 595) \right) \times \sqrt{9^9} \right)$$

$$9961463 := \left(\left((36 + \sqrt{4}) \times \left(\sqrt{16^9} \right) \right) - 9 \right)$$

$$9964797 := - \left(\left(\left(\left(\left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) - 7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 6^9 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9975296 := \left(6^9 - \left(25 \times (7 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9977856 := \left(\left((6 \times 58) \times 7 \right) \times \left((7 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9979596 := \left(6^9 + \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((9 \times 7) + \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9994386 := \left(- (6) + \left(- \left(\left((8^3) - 4 \right) \right) \times \left(9 - \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9994389 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(- \left(\left((8^3) - 4 \right) \right) \times \left(9 - \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9994392 := \left(\left(\left((2^{\sqrt{9}})^3 - 4 \right) \times \left(- (9) + \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9995746 := \left(- \left(\left((6 + (4^7)) \times 5 \right) \right) + \left((9 - \sqrt{9})^9 \right) \right)$$

$$9996696 := \left(6^9 + \left(\left((6 \times (6 + 9))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / (-9) \right) \right)$$

$$9997813 := \left(\left((3 - 1) + 8 \right)^7 - \left(\sqrt{9^9} / 9 \right) \right)$$

$$9998957 := \left(- (7) + \left(\left((5 - 9) + (8^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right)$$

$$9998964 := \left(4 \times \left(\left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) - (89) \right) \times \sqrt{9^9} \right) \right)$$

$$9999575 := \left(- \left(\left((5^7) + 5 \right) \right) + \left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9})^9 + 9 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9999748 := \left(\left(\left((8 + \sqrt{4})^7 \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + ((9 \times 9)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9999754 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 5)^7 \right) - \left(\left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) + 9 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9999784 := \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{4} + 8)^7 \right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times ((9 \times 9) - 9) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9999997 := \left(\left((7 + \sqrt{9})^{9-(9+9)/9} - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

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